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The Politics of Mine Action

Normative, game and decision theoretic approaches
to post-conflict problems caused by landmines
and explosive remnants of war

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**Faculty
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**Faculty
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De Politiek van Mijnactie

Normatieve, spel- en beslissingstheoretische benaderingen
voor post-conflict problemen veroorzaakt door landmijnen
en explosieve oorlogsresten

Dissertation for the degree of
doctor in political and social sciences
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**BROKEN CHAIR
BY DANIEL BERS - HANDICAP
INTERNATIONAL**

"A single land mine — or even the fear that there might be one — can hold a whole community hostage. It can prevent the cultivation of an entire field, prevent children from walking to school and rob a whole village of its livelihood."

UN Secretary-General Kofi Annan

SAMENVATTING

Mijnactie is een begrip waarmee de media minder vertrouwd is in vergelijking met de meer gebruikelijke terminologie zoals landmijnbestrijding en ontmijningsprogramma's. Nochtans is mijnactie een geïjkt concept binnen het politieke domein van ontwapening en wapencontrole.

Mijnactie, indien de implementatie en ontruiming efficiënt verloopt, is van levensbelang om het menselijk lijden terug te dringen veroorzaakt door landmijnen en andere niet-ontplofte oorlogsresten, zoals artilleriehulzen, granaten, submunitie van clusterbommen en mortieren. Mijnactie is echter meer dan dat, ook preventieve acties zijn noodzakelijk. Om deze reden omvat mijnactie bewustmakingsprogramma's voor de lokale bevolking betreffende de gevaren van mijnen en niet-ontplofte munitie. Ook staat mijnactie in voor het vernietigen van landmijnvoorraden en de medische verzorging en begeleiding van slachtoffers van landmijnen en niet-ontplofte oorlogsresten. Samengevat, mijnactie omvat een omvangrijk pakket aan taken en is een concept dat beduidend meer omvat dan het in eerste instantie doet vermoeden.

De politieke dimensie van mijnactie, het hoofdthema van dit doctoraat, wordt vaak gekoppeld aan het Verdrag inzake het verbod op anti-persoonsmijnen (Verdrag van Ottawa) en diverse protocollen van de Conventie voor Conventionele Wapens. Deze zijn de voornaamste internationaalrechtelijke instrumenten ter bestrijding van het probleem van landmijnen en explosieve oorlogsresten. Er bestaat echter geen snelle oplossing voor het probleem van de mijnen en niet-ontplofte munitie. De universalisering van het totaalverbod op landmijnen is nog niet binnen bereik. Mijnactie dient daarom eveneens een pragmatisch concept te zijn dat ernaar streeft de impact en het gevaar van landmijnen en oorlogsresten zo snel mogelijk terug te dringen met de beschikbare middelen. Dit heeft tevens tot gevolg dat de politieke dimensie van mijnactie ruimer dient bekeken te worden, met inzonderheid de besluitvormingsprocessen betreffende de prioritisering van mijnactie activiteiten en de toewijzing van beperkte middelen.

De ondertitel van het doctoraat verduidelijkt binnen welk domein het onderzoek in het bijzonder wenst bij te dragen: "Normatieve, Spel- en Beslissingstheoretische benaderingen voor post-conflict problemen veroorzaakt door landmijnen en explosieve oorlogsresten." Concreet wenst dit doctoraat een model voor te dragen welke de besluitvormingsprocessen kan informeren met multi-criteria beslissingsanalyse. Gebaseerd op een dynamisch en holistisch concept stelt het model de best mogelijke prioritisering van mijnactie voor, rekening houdende met de unieke karakteristieken van een voorafbepaalde regio. Deze korte termijn prioriteringsbehoefte wordt eveneens in verband gebracht met de behoefte voor een geïntegreerde strategische planning op langere termijn voor mijnactie.

Dit model werd eerst in een vereenvoudigde vorm ontwikkeld om nadien in een gedetailleerde gevalstudie te worden toegepast voor Afghanistan. Door de opeenvolgende conflicten is dit land, net zoals Irak, Libanon en Cambodja, enorm vervuild met landmijnen. De problemen in deze landen werden nog verergerd door afgevuurde munitie die niet explodeerde bij impact en door achtergelaten wapenstocks. Dit fenomeen verhoogt aanzienlijk de risico's voor een hergebruik van deze explosieven in aanslagen door niet-Staatse actoren. Het in dit doctoraat ontwikkelde multi-criteria model biedt de mogelijkheid om dergelijke risico's en vele andere gegevens te verwerken. Dit resulteert in een mogelijke prioritisering van mijnactie in Afghanistan voor de bij benadering 2000 gemeenschappen die een bedreiging ondervinden van meer dan 4000 geïdentificeerde gebieden met landmijnen en explosieve oorlogsresten.

ABSTRACT

Mine action as a concept aims at alleviating the impact of landmines and similar explosive remnants of war and, contrary to its narrow interpretation, entails much more than a singular action against mines. If performed well, significant humanitarian, socio-economic and peacekeeping and/or peacebuilding benefits can be obtained via the five mine action “pillars”: *mine clearance, victim assistance, stockpile destruction, mine risk education and advocacy*. This dissertation examines the *Politics of Mine Action* and more specifically how multilateral and institutional politics steer its related decision-making processes and actions. It explores extensively the trade-off politics and game theoretical principles related to mine action as a whole, especially at a global level. This requires demonstrating via metrics how mine action contributes to a more secure environment, reduces human suffering and allows for the promotion of a variety of vital post-conflict reconstruction and development activities.

Initially, a normative and game theoretic analysis helps to study the most important political dynamics related to *assistance* in mine action. The United Nations resolution *Assistance in mine action*, an important United Nations agenda item since 1993, offers a unique source of information to analyse and clarify how UN Member States and the UN Secretariat perceive and formulate mine action. Examining this inclusive process at a global level, at which all UN Member States can exercise their political influence, provides ample insight on how the international community through consensus tries to find remedies and resolutions to a multifaceted problem. The *normative and game theoretic* analysis allows for the deduction of goals, indicators and criteria which should be indicative for the effectiveness of the current *Politics of Mine Action*. It is also a suitable lead-in for readers without extensive mine action knowledge and through which they can acquire sufficient understanding on the humanitarian, socio-economic and security problems caused by landmines.

In the following phase, several modelling aspects of mine action are examined more closely. How *game and decision* theoretic principles can be combined with quantitative and qualitative criteria will be evaluated and integrated in a normative multiple criteria model. Via statistical analysis of mine action data, the potential of strategic multiple criteria decision analysis is comprehensively illustrated. A brief analysis follows on how the *Politics of Mine Action* can correspond to overarching Poverty Reduction Strategy Papers and the United Nations Millennium Development Goals.

In order to support the empirical credibility of this dissertation, expertise acquired through participation in field studies, workshops and political processes has been applied throughout the analysis and research. In this regard, the Mine Action Program in Afghanistan serves as the case-study. The application of the normative model provides a better understanding of the beneficial influence of mine action on humanitarian emergencies, restoration of Afghan socio-economic conditions and its peacekeeping and peacebuilding effects. The importance of statistical analysis and strategic planning is illustrated at a national level. Innovative multiple criteria decision analysis and normative modelling are first evaluated and developed for the most heavily mined province and capital in the world: Kabul. For basic cross-validation purposes, the modelling methodology developed for Kabul is applied on other mine-affected provinces in Afghanistan.

Finally, the findings of the Afghan case-study are studied within a global context. The study results in the formulation of “*Grand Strategy*” findings and recommendations for the *Politics of Mine Action*.

AUTOBIOGRAPHICAL NOTE

A native of Antwerp, Belgium, Filip Van Der Linden (1966) enrolled in his Doctoral Study Program at the University of Antwerp (UA) in September 2000, simultaneously with taking up the function of deputy military adviser at the Belgian Permanent Mission to the United Nations in New York (Oct 2000 – Dec 2003).

He holds academic degrees in Military and Aeronautical Sciences from the Royal Military Academy of Belgium (1989) and International Relations (1997) from the University of Antwerp, combined with a broad experience in the political-military environment. He participated in peacekeeping, humanitarian assistance and nation building missions in three continents: Europe, Africa and Asia. Becoming a doctoral student at the University of Antwerp and the Royal Military Academy allowed him to build further upon his Belgian academic foundations.

He additionally obtained the Certificate of Peacekeeping Training at the Pearson Peacekeeping Training Centre - The New Interdisciplinary Partnership (Nova Scotia, Canada - 2000) and followed up this effort with several Peacekeeping Seminars at Columbia University, New York (2001). He finalized this two-year program in 2003 with his research thesis on strategic planning for mine action in Afghanistan and obtained the Certificate-of-training in United Nations Peace Support Operations, under the auspices of the United Nations Institute for Training and Research (UNITAR).

He has participated for several years in conferences and activities in the field of disarmament, in both UN disarmament forum at New York and Geneva, and the Organisation for Security and Cooperation in Europe (OSCE) in Vienna. Redrafting resolutions and chairing debates related to the annual UN General Assembly (GA) Resolution “Assistance in Mine Action” were part of his duties from 2001 to 2003. This further determined the scope of his doctoral research, being the “Politics of Mine Action”. He challenges the effectiveness of the global post-conflict response to humanitarian, socio-economic and security problems posed by landmines and similar explosive remnants of war.

His interest and engagement in the politics of mine action led to his appointment as Secretary of the New York based Mine Action Support Group in 2002. In this position, he coordinated and participated in several UN field visits to Eritrea, Ethiopia, Angola, DRC, South-Africa and Afghanistan, gaining considerable insight in national mine action activities.

He was twice consultant to the United Nations Mine Action Service (UNMAS) as part of the Mine Action Program in Afghanistan (MAPA). This position enabled him to contribute to the improvement of mine action strategic planning in Afghanistan. In this regard he developed a preliminary strategic plan in September 2002 for the MAPA in cooperation with the MAPA programme manager and Cranfield University, United Kingdom. In March 2003, he assisted in the Cranfield University strategic planning workshop in Afghanistan, contributing to the further development of the preliminary strategic plan of September 2002.

After his position as deputy military adviser, he became the national representative for the Belgian Armed Forces at the Coalition Coordination Centre - United States Central Command (USCENTCOM), Florida. This function allowed him to gain at a strategic level more in-depth knowledge regarding the patterns of global or trans-national terrorism and the possible military response as part of the “Coalition against terrorism”. Concurrently, he acquired a better

understanding of non-State actors' armament dynamics and the use of improvised explosive devices (IED), increasingly their terror weapon of choice. End 2004, he rejoined the UN community in New York.

Currently, his duties as a planning officer within the Military Planning Service of the United Nations Department of Peacekeeping Operations (DPKO), New York are mainly related to strategic planning of UN peacekeeping operations, in particular for the complex African Union/United Nations "Hybrid" peace operations in Sudan, Darfur. This significantly contributed to his knowledge of strategic planning and decision-making processes for UN operations in most challenging environments.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

SAMENVATTING	i
ABSTRACT	iii
AUTOBIOGRAPHICAL NOTE	v
TABLE OF CONTENTS	vii
GLOSSARY OF USED ACRONYMS	xiii
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	xvii
PRELUDE	xix
CHAPTER I: RESEARCH AIM AND METHODOLOGY	1
I.1. General Introduction	1
I.1.1. Why study the “Politics of Mine Action”?	1
I.1.2. High Politics versus Low Politics of Mine Action	2
I.1.3. Politics versus Policy of Mine Action	2
I.1.4. Important terms and definitions	3
A. Definition of mine action	3
B. Defining the “global landmine problem”	4
C. Definition of a landmine	5
D. Definition of unexploded ordnance and explosive remnants of war	6
E. Definition of a minefield	6
F. Definition of a Suspected Hazardous Area	6
G. Definition of a mine affected area or community	6
I.2. Research aim and objectives	7
I.3. Research methodology	9
I.3.1. Why normative, game and decision theory?	9
I.3.2. An empirical and ethical research approach	10
I.3.3. Research phases	11
A. Analytical process	11
B. First Phase: Normative and Game Theoretic Analysis	12
C. Second Phase: Normative Modelling	13
D. Third Phase: Case-study Afghanistan	14
E. Fourth Phase: The Global Dimension	15
F. Schematic overview of the research methodology and phases	15
CHAPTER II - PHASE-I : A NORMATIVE AND GAME THEORIC ANALYSIS	21
II.1. Introduction	21
II.1.1. Normative building blocks of a UN resolution	21
II.1.2. Expanding on the game theoretic analysis	22
II.1.3. Applicable game theoretic assumptions	23
A. Common knowledge of rationality	23
B. Consistent alignment of beliefs	23

C. Complete knowledge of rules and possible outcomes	24
II.1.4. Overview of game theoretic principles	24
II.1.5. Game theoretic equilibriums	25
A. Nash equilibrium	25
B. Bayesian equilibrium	26
II.1.6. Criteria formulation	26
A. Converging principles of expected utility and criteria selection	26
B. Pragmatic applications for the politics of mine action	27
II.2. Analysis of the UN Resolution: “Assistance in Mine Action” – 58th General Assembly	29
II.2.1. Historic background	29
A. Overview of UN Resolutions related to mine action	29
B. Introduction of the Resolution by the European Community under Belgian Presidency	29
C. Envisaged strategic objectives of the Resolution	29
II.2.2. United Nations rules, procedures and timeframes	30
A. Impact of UN rules on the political process	30
B. The importance of the UN Report on assistance in mine action	31
C. Alliance formations: from Sponsors to co-Sponsors, to non-sponsoring UN Member States	31
II.2.3. Normative and Game Theoretic Analysis of the Preamble Paragraphs (PP)	32
A. PP 1: Adoption without a vote or politics by consensus	32
B. PP 2: Role of States versus role of the United Nations	47
C. PP 3: The humanitarian and development impact of landmines	57
D. PP 4: Threat/risk postulation in mine action	63
E. PP 5: Mine victims – targeted efforts to accelerate human cost reduction	71
F. PP 6: Mine clearance: the main pillar	80
G. PP 7: The Convention on Certain Conventional Weapons	90
H. PP 8: The CCW and its dynamic review processes	94
I. PP 9: The CCW and Explosive Remnants of War	96
J. PP 10: The Anti-Personnel Mine Ban Treaty	101
K. PP 11: The MBT review and consultative processes	111
L. PP 12: Halting new mine deployments by mine-affected States	117
M. PP 13: Halting the use of landmines/explosive devices by non-State actors	121
N. PP 14: Assistance and information sharing in support of mine clearance	132
O. PP 15: Mine action resource mobilisation	136
P. PP 16: Progress in mine action related research and development	141
Q. PP 17: Cooperation and coordination of mine action	144
R. PP 18: Response to emergency mine action requirements	155
S. PP 19: Mine action coordination centres and trust funds	157
T. PP 20: The integration of mine action in peacekeeping operations	159
U. PP 21: Mine victim assistance	162
V. PP 22: Public awareness of the landmine problem	163
II.3. Phase-I response to the research aim and research objectives	171
II.3.1. Main findings	171
II.3.2. Hierarchic structuring of deducted criteria	177
II.3.3. Overview of possible criteria for normative modelling	178
II.3.4. Hierarchic overview of game theoretic characteristics	179

CHAPTER III – PHASE-II : NORMATIVE MODELLING	181
III.1. Introduction	181
III.1.1. Further exploring the main research objective of Phase-II	181
III.1.2. Basic questions before starting the normative modelling	181
III.1.3. Sub-phase A: Intrinsic modelling	183
III.1.4. Sub-phase B: Extrinsic modelling	184
III.2.Sub-phase A: Optimize short term prioritization of mine action activities	185
III.2.1 The “crisp” optimization problem	185
III.2.2. Simulation for modelling purposes	186
A. Visualisation of the prioritization problem	186
B. Suggested criteria and indicators for short-term mine action prioritisation	187
III.2.3. Available data for prioritization	188
A. Data sources	188
B. Landmine Impact Survey data	188
C. Landmine Impact Survey process	189
III.2.4. Fuzzy logic	192
A. From “crisp” to “fuzzy” optimization	192
B. Robust solutions to fuzzy optimization problems	193
C. Prioritization requires (out)ranking: from utility functions to fuzzy outranking	194
III.2.5. Preliminary considerations for the risk modelling of human cost	196
A. Humanitarian relief: the most important mine action output?	196
B. The quest for reliable statistical analysis of mine victim data	197
C. Potential explanatory variables or predictors of mine/ERW accidents	199
D. Important statistical parameters and techniques	204
III.2.6. Preliminary considerations for modelling the socio-economic impact	205
A. Cross-cutting characteristics	205
B. Discounting and the time-value of socio-economic benefits	205
C. LIS-data and clearance of socio-economic blockages	207
III.2.7. Preliminary considerations for the modelling of peacekeeping and peacebuilding effects	208
A. Mine action for peace	208
B. The challenge of modelling tangible peacekeeping/building effects	208
III.2.8. Pulling it together: Multiple Criteria Decision Analysis for mine action prioritization	209
A. Multiple criteria decision theoretic principles	209
B. Responding to the MCDA requirement	210
C. Multistage MCDA applied on a small-scale simulation	215
III.3. Sub-phase B: Optimize integrated strategic planning for mine action	225
III.3.1. From “Politics to Strategy” and from “Strategy to developing a Strategic Plan”	225
A. Strategic planning jargon	225
B. Linkage between strategic planning and the politics of mine action	225
C. No reliable strategic planning without reliable mine clearance rates	227
III.3.2. From “tunnel vision” to an integrated approach	227
A. Macro-optimization principle	227
B. Why and how link-up mine action with the Millennium Development Goals?	227
C. Linking up PROMETHEE with multiple scenario planning	231
D. Robust optimization towards multiple scenarios: third stage outranking	232
III.4. Phase-II response to the research aim and research objectives	233
III.4.1. Sub-phase A response	233
III.4.2. Sub-phase B response	234

CHAPTER IV – PHASE-III : CASE-STUDY AFGHANISTAN	235
IV.1. Introduction	235
IV.1.1. Afghanistan: a preferred test case for the model	235
IV.1.2. Prioritization and strategic planning framework	235
IV.1.3. The Afghan landmine problem	235
A. Background and brief history	235
B. The establishment of the Mine Action Programme in Afghanistan (MAPA)	237
C. Consecutive strategic assessments and planning milestones	237
IV.2. Framing of the Afghan landmine problem	238
IV.2.1. Boasting the human cost	238
IV.2.2. Boasting socio-economic benefits	239
IV.2.3. Boasting MAPA’s effectiveness and mine clearance rates	241
IV.2.4. Sub-optimal prioritization of mine action	245
A. Evolution of the classification of affected land	245
B. The Landmine Impact Survey: time for change!	245
IV.3. Applying the model on Afghanistan	249
IV.3.1. Prioritization of mine action for Kabul	249
A. Impact characteristics	249
B. Processing of LIS data	250
IV.3.2. Human cost	250
A. LIS mine victim information	250
B. Statistical analysis of KABUL survey data	252
C. Development of “human cost” preference or outranking functions	262
IV.3.3. Socio-economic impact	262
A. Socio-economic criteria and weights used for the Afghan LIS	262
B. Enriching the weak socio-economic metrics – ordinal scale development	263
C. Development of “socio-economic” outranking functions	265
IV.3.4. Peacekeeping/building effects	266
A. The Bonn-agreement: a cumbersome start of the peacebuilding process	266
B. Mine action as part of a Disarmament, Demobilization and Reintegration process	265
C. Mine action: an effective counter-IED activity in Afghanistan?	267
D. Suggested ordinal scoring mechanism	268
E. Development of “peacekeeping/building” outranking functions	271
IV.3.5. MCDA for the prioritization of mine action in Kabul	272
A. Multistage decision analysis	272
B. MCDA Kabul: first stage outranking	272
C. MCDA Kabul: second stage outranking	274
D. Geometrical Analysis for Interactive Assistance (GAIA) for Kabul	278
E. Utilization of the (out)ranking result	279
F. MCD Kabul: third-stage outranking	280
IV.3.6. Applying MCDA to other regions in Afghanistan	281
A. From provincial to national level: some validation considerations	281
B. Sample size considerations	281
C. The landmine problem at a local scale or clustering of data	282
D. Choice of clustering method	282
E. Statistical analysis and clustering at province-level	285
F. Statistical analysis of the “Northern Cluster”	291
G. Development and overview of preference functions for the “Northern Cluster”	294
IV.3.7. Integrated strategic mine action planning for Afghanistan	295
A. Mainstreaming with other humanitarian, development and reconstruction sectors	295
B. Adjusting the prioritization of mine action to changing external conditions	295

C. Linking-up short-term prioritization with multiple strategic scenarios	296
D. Considerations regarding long-term strategic planning for mine action in Afghanistan	297
IV.4. MAPA prioritization and strategic planning process	304
IV.5. Phase-III response to the research aim and research objectives	305
IV.5.1. Main findings on short-term mine action prioritisation for Afghanistan	305
IV.5.2. Main findings on integrated strategic planning for the MAPA	308
CHAPTER V – PHASE-IV: THE GLOBAL DIMENSION AND CONCLUSIONS	309
V.1. Introduction	309
V.1.1. From national to global	309
V.1.2. Global prioritization: is it a critical requirement?	309
V.1.3. Criteria relevant to the “high politics” and global dimension	310
V.2. Exploring the global dimension of mine action	311
V.2.1. The relevancy of global goal setting and costing	312
V.2.2. Mine action funding	312
A. Global resource mobilisation	312
B. Donor countries	313
C. Recipient countries	314
D. Global funding versus global human cost of landmines	315
V.2.3. Landmine impact assessment at a global scale	315
A. Past efforts	315
B. The Global Landmine Survey	316
V.2.4. Cross-country comparison	318
A. Enhancing the LIS: the most suitable platform for cross-country comparison?	320
B. No charity, but facts!	320
V.3. Conclusions and Grand Strategy recommendations	322
V.4. Future research and other applications	327
APPENDIX	329
Annex A. 58 th UN General Assembly Resolution: Assistance in mine action	331
Annex B. 59 th UN General Assembly Decision: Assistance in mine action	335
Annex C. MBT – CCW adherence, voting record of the MBT-UN resolution and co-sponsorship to the UN resolution “Assistance in mine action” from 1993 until 2005	338
Annex D. MBT versus CCW based on percentage of global population and military expenditures	339
Annex E. Non-State Actors that have signed the Deed of Commitment for Adherence to a Total Ban on Anti-personnel Mines and for Cooperation in Mine Action	342
Annex F. Examples of different kinds of SHA and terrain characteristics	343
Annex G. Correlation Poverty-Mine/UXO problems	344
Annex H. Kabul data used for statistical analysis; based on the Afghan Landmine Impact Survey	345
Annex I. Simple Linear Regression analysis of the recency factor in Kabul	348
Annex J. Simple Linear Regression analysis of the recency factor in the Northern Cluster	351
Annex K. Calculation and averaging of mine action clearance rates for strategic planning	354
FIELD VISITS AND RESEARCH	356
CONFERENCES / INTERNATIONAL MEETINGS	357
SELECT BIBLIOGRAPHY	358

GLOSSARY OF USED ACRONYMS

Most of below acronyms are frequently used in the dissertation. Due to the high number of acronyms, they are regularly written in full in order to enhance the reader-friendliness of the technical topics.

AP MBC	Anti-Personnel Mine Ban Convention or Mine Ban Treaty
ABM	Anti-Ballistic Missiles
ANOVA	ANalysis Of VArience
ANSA	Armed Non-State Actors
APM	Anti-Personnel Mines
AREA	Agency for Rehabilitation and Energy Conservation in Afghanistan
ATC	Afghan Technical Consultants
ATM	Anti-Tank Mines
AU	African Union
BAC	Battle Area Clearance
CAB	Consistent Alignment of Beliefs
CAP	Consolidated Appeal
CB	Cluster Bombs
CBA	Cluster Bombs Ammunition
CBU	Cluster Bombs Unit
CCW	Convention on Certain Conventional Weapons
CEO	Chief Executive Officer
CIS	Commonwealth of Independent States
CKR	Common Knowledge of Rationality
CMAC	Cambodian Mine Action Centre
COA	Coarse Of Action
CODUN	EU working group on UN Disarmament
COREU	Correspondence European Union
CSN	Country Strategy Note
CT	Coordination Team
CTA	Chief Technical Advisor
DAFA	Demining Agency for Afghanistan
DDA	Department of Disarmament Affairs
DFID	Department For International Development (UK)
DPKO	Department of Peacekeeping Operations
DSS	Decision Support Systems
EC	European Commission
ELECTRE	ELimination Et Choix Traduisant la REalite
EOD	Explosive Ordnance Disposal
ERC	Emergency Relief Coordinator
ERW	Explosive Remnants of War
ERW	Explosive Remnants of War
ESS	Evolutionary Stable Strategy
EU	European Union
FAO	Food and Agricultural Organisation
FV	Future Value
GA	General Assembly
GAIA	Geometrical Analysis for Interactive Assistance
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GICHD	Geneva International Centre for Humanitarian Demining
GIS	Geographic Information System

GTI	Goals, Targets and Indicators
GWOT	Global War On Terror
HALO	Hazardous Areas Life-Support Organization
HC	Humanitarian Coordinator
HDI	Human Development Index
HMA	Humanitarian Mine Action
HR	Humanitarian Relief
IACG	Inter Agency Coordination Group on Mine Action
IASC	Inter-Agency Steering Committee
IAU	Information Analysis Unit
ICBL	International Campaign to Ban Landmines
ICRC	International Committee of the Red Cross
IDP	Internally Displaced Person
IED	Improvised Explosive Devices
IMAS	International Mine Action Standards
IMSMA	Information Management System for Mine Action
IRIN	Integrated Regional Information Networks
IRR	Internal Rate of Return
ISAF	International Security Assistance Force
LDC	Least-Developed Countries
LIS	Landmine Impact Survey
LM	Landmine Monitor
MA	Mine Action
MAC	Mine Action Centre
MAC	Mine Action Centre
(UN) MACA	(United Nations) Mine Action Center for Afghanistan
MACC	Mine Action Coordination Centre
MAD	Mutual Assured Destruction
MAE	Mean Absolute Error
MAFP	Mine Action For Peace
MAIWG	Mine Action Information Working Group
MANPADS	Man Portable Air Defence Systems
MAPA	Mine Action Programme in Afghanistan
MASG	Mine Action Support Group
MAWG	Mine Action Working Group
MBT	Mine Ban Treaty or Anti-Personnel Mine Ban Convention
MBT	Mine Ban Treaty
MCDA	Multiple Criteria Decision Analysis
MDD	Mine Detection Dogs
MDG	Millennium Development Goals
MIS	Mine Impact Survey
MONUC	United Nations Organization Mission in the Democratic Republic
MOTAPM	Mines Other Than Anti-Personnel Mines
MRE	Mine Risk Education
MSE	Mean Squared Error
NAM	Non-Aligned Movement
NATO	North Atlantic Treaty Organisation
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
NMAA	National Mine Action Authority
NPV	Net Present Value
NSA	Non-State Actors
NSAG	Non-State Actors Groups

NSAWG	Non-State Actors Working Group
OAS	Organisation of American States
OCHA	Office of the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs
OMAR	Organization for Mine Clearance and Afghan Rehabilitation
OSCE	Organisation for Security and Cooperation in Europe
PD	Prisoners Dilemma
PK	Peacekeeping
PM	Programme Manager
PROMETHEE	Preference Ranking Organization Method for Enrichment Evaluations
PV	Present Value
R&D	Research and Development
R²	R-squared; coefficient of determination
Ref Pt	Reference Point
RRP	Rapid Response Plan
SAC	Survey Action Centre
SALW	Small Arms and Light Weapons
SCMA	Steering Committee on Mine Action
SEB	Socio-Economic Benefits
SHA	Suspected Hazardous Areas
SRS	Special Representative of the Secretary-General
SSR	Security Sector Reform
TSG	Technical Standards and Guidelines
TSZ	Temporary Security Zone
U	(Expected) Utility
UA	University of Antwerp
UN	United Nations
UN	United Nations
UNAMA	United Nations Assistance Mission in Afghanistan
UNA-USA	United Nations Association of United States of America
UNDAF	United Nations Development Assistance Framework
UNDP	United Nations Development Programme
UNF	United Nations Foundation
UNFIP	United Nations Fund for International Partnerships
UNFPA	United Nations Population Fund
UNHCR	United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees
UNICEF	United Nations Children's Fund
UNIFIL	United Nations
UNITAR	United Nations Institute for Training And Research
UNMAS	United Nations Mine Action Service
UNOPS	United Nations Office for Project Services
UNSECOORD	United Nations Security Coordinator
USAID	United States Agency for International Development
USCENTCOM	United States Central Command
USG	Under Secretary-General
UXO	Unexploded Ordnance
UXO LAO	Unexploded Ordnance programme in Laos
VTF	Voluntary Trust Fund
WFP	World Food Programme
WHO	World Health Organisation

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This dissertation was prepared within the framework of a collaborative project between the University of Antwerp and the Royal Military Academy. The bi-promotorship of those two Belgian Academic Institutions offered a unique opportunity to combine both the expertise and supervision on the research subject.

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Start of a long journey: 1994

“1994... a year I will always remember for being a European Community Monitor (ECM Mission) in the Balkan conflict, with many heart felt gripping encounters and wartime experiences. The meetings with a very successful and remarkable Croatian businessman “Pasa” were among them. Before the war, he was a rich tradesman in Austria. He left for helping his Bosnian home village Drijenca by providing regular and generous gifts, the reason why he was nicknamed Pasa [pacha]. When the Balkan conflict escalated further, he gathered Bosnians living in Austria and formed a combat platoon. This platoon was involved in the legendary fighting around Dubrovnik. Pasa was one of the only two wounded men of the platoon who survived. Afterwards he gathered local Croats and Muslims in the same battalion. Short in ammo and manpower, they held with bravery the treacherous Bosnian-Serbian frontlines. Pasa could tell long and colourful stories of heroism on how they fought against an outnumbering and far better equipped enemy. The European monitors, including myself, looked forward to meeting with him, not only for his charisma and hospitality but also for the respect he earned by giving up his comfortable life to defend his former village. Being more than six foot tall, typically with a big grin on his face, Pasa was a man one would not easily forget. One day however, the charismatic leader was found in total desperation, facing a sure death if he would not have been saved by one of his comrades, ... after all his deeds of heroism, Pasa had stepped on a mine, heavily wounded and paralyzed by this silent menace...”

After that profound experience, my views on the tragic impact of landmines were not confined anymore to theoretic courses at the Belgian Royal Military Academy or classroom peacekeeping seminars. Through this first confrontation, the maiming effects of landmines suddenly had a face, the face of now a broken and mutilated man in a Bosnian hospital. It was a chilling realisation of how landmines and explosive remnants of war can profoundly scar a population and nation as a whole. Moreover, this first experience was only a prelude to the beginning of a long journey, with tragically many more mine victim encounters in Afghanistan, Angola, Eritrea and Ethiopia; meetings which would later prove to be in sharp contrast with the sterile politics at the United Nations Headquarters in New York. The twofold benefits of constantly visiting the field and working within the UN system in New York also continuously reminded me to seek pragmatic and result-oriented approaches to the inevitable complexities of post-conflict problems. When pursuing a better understanding of the politics, effectiveness of mine action and the depth of its impact, it almost logically follows that mine action is not that much about landmines, it is more about individuals within their crumbling societies and slowly recovering nations.

A dissertation is without doubt a daunting undertaking. In the years dedicated to this work, the highs were sometimes altered by lows to a point that made me wonder if the rewards were worth the efforts. However, this question became irrelevant over time since I realized it should not be about rewards, but how one gradually learns and appreciates how to contribute to the peace-building community. Field missions in war ridden countries made me realize this increasingly, not out of idealism but out of sheer humanitarian interest and necessity. The encounters with mine victims were the best motivation to continue this study and set aside or postpone other projects. Finally, when put in perspective, the sacrifices made to write this work became a humbling experience since a doctoral study is a continuous invitation to think creatively, to raise new questions, investigate new possibilities and to consider old problems from a new angle. Therefore, I admit graciously that this thesis taught me that great opportunities for scientific innovations or impressive new ways to help others might seldom come; but luckily, small opportunities surround us every day.

CHAPTER I: RESEARCH AIM AND METHODOLOGY

I.1. General Introduction

I.1.1. Why study the “Politics of Mine Action”?

In the field of international affairs, the political dynamics related to arms proliferation and disarmament activities have fascinated political scientists for centuries. Studies and research in this field intensified after World War II and even more after the Cold War era. The United Nations in particular has worked for disarmament ever since its very first General Assembly resolution on "The Establishment of a Commission to Deal with the Problems Raised by the Discovery of Atomic Energy"¹.

In the context of this study, disarmament means a nation's regulated reduction or elimination of some of its weapons systems. Hence, which particular political dynamics are related to liberate the world of the scourge of landmines and other similar explosive remnants of war? Are the politics of mine action driven by an ideal based on the view that weapons cause conflicts or wars, and that the elimination of these weapons will in itself remove one of the main causes of armed conflict? Consequently, could mine action reduce significantly the potential for inter- and intrastate conflict or is it merely a confined post-conflict issue, overshadowed by other more important peace building processes? Or should one associate the politics of mine action more with disarming activities itself, whereby individual nations will no longer perceive this type of weaponry as a strategic requirement for their national security or military doctrine?

The answers on some of these questions could be rather short and simple... if there would be a universally accepted and respected ban against the usage and production of mines and explosives with similar traumatic effects... if the funding and resources for mine action would meet the requirements... if a centralized and global authority would steer an optimal prioritization process... if mine clearance technology would be fail-safe and universally accessible... and, often overlooked, if health care systems would be optimal and capable of providing adequate mine victim assistance. Unfortunately, we clearly do not live in such a utopian world. In a world where people would be so caring and considerate, explosives that could indiscriminately kill and maim innocent civilians would not have ended up in the ground in the first place. As such, the study of the “Politics of Mine Action” is much more complex than the questions above indicate and requires an appreciation of realism as well as utopianism, power or influence as well as morality and legality.

In terms of “*realpolitik*”, the issues related to the topic are multifaceted and often complex. This leads to a high degree of diversity in opinion amongst government officials, activists, practitioners, military experts and diplomats; uniquely shaping the activities of the politics of mine action and mine action activities. In terms of “*power or influence*”, the strategic impact of the usage of landmines and especially Improvised Explosive Devices (IEDs) comes to mind. Nowadays, the latter is the most feared weapon of modern insurgencies; it can inflict damage on military superpowers with tremendous political fallout. In terms of “*utopianism*”, there is the dream of a mine free world where all populations are freed from the traumatic effects of mines. This, however, would require resources beyond what is obtainable and reasonable. And last but not the least, there are the “*morality and legality*” concerns, born out of the indiscriminate and horrendous harm caused by landmines. This has been the drive behind numerous moral or ethical debates and legal initiatives, and resulted in the fastest-ever ratified disarmament treaty, ambitiously aspiring a universal and total ban on anti-personnel landmines: the “*Mine Ban Treaty*”.

¹ First General Assembly Session, UN resolution adopted on 24 January 1946, Internet. UN document available at <http://www.un.org/documents/ga/res/1/ares1.htm>, accessed on 10 January 2005.

Current trends make it conspicuous how mine action stakeholders² somewhat overwhelm the international community with policies, opinions, norms and standards on how the international community should have dealt and must deal with the significant impact landmines have on individuals and societies as a whole. In response to broad, post-conflict recovery or reconstruction requirements, mine action became a *five-pillar concept* covering: *humanitarian mine clearance, stockpile destruction, mine risk education, victim assistance and advocacy against the use of mines*, each with its own importance with *global, regional, national and local* actors and factors coming into play. Hence, the consequences of the global landmine problem are not confined to a limited number of war torn countries or regional post conflict situations but affect the international community as a whole. In its interdependence with other diverse humanitarian activities, the global politics, policy, coordination and management of mine action is a domain that has to take into account other overarching challenges. A thorough understanding of the politics of mine action requires therefore a multidisciplinary (five components of mine action) and multidimensional analysis (global, regional, national and local).

These phenomenons make the politics of mine action an exceptionally interesting and also a relatively uncharted field to research. It contains a variety of interwoven – sometimes conflicting – disarmament dynamics, game theoretic and multiple criteria characteristics which, although complex, can still be studied separately. Also, a disarmament or arms control sector which is relatively small in numbers of actors and activities and young in terms of historic development, provides unique research opportunities. The following introductory pages address these opportunities and offer further familiarization with the research topic and different political levels of mine action.

I.1.2. High politics versus low politics of Mine Action

For introductory purposes, it should be briefly addressed how according to their level the politics of mine action could be differentiated. The political interactions between States, especially national security or other strategic issues, are referred to by the realists as *high politics*, whereas national economic and social issues are viewed as subordinate *low politics*:

“In the fields of Political Science and International Relations the terms *High* and *Low Politics* often refer to different forms of policy. *Low politics* happen *near to the people* and concern areas like *health, crime and the economy*. *High politics* happen in the *international arena* and concern things like *defense and foreign policy*.”³

It is obvious that both should be addressed when studying the politics of mine action and more interestingly how they combine, interconnect and influence the decision making. Hence, this also suggests it would be interesting to explore the existence of any kind of “*medium*” politics of mine action, thereby intuitively assuming they should bridge the country-level socio-economic driven politics with the high politics between States.

I.1.3. Politics versus Policy of Mine Action

The different political levels of mine action and the related socio-economic elements call for a broader interpretation than the traditional definition of politics as the art and science of governance. It is indeed essential not to focus on governance alone but to include policy-making and economic aspects, in particular the study of rational behaviour directed towards the maximization of anticipated or expected utility. The latter can only be achieved through the optimal allocation of scarce mine action resources, which further underscores that the borders between the politics, policy and economics of mine action are particularly open.

² Affected countries, donors, diplomats, mine action practitioners, military advisers, technical consultants, etc.

³ Internet. Available at http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/High_and_Low_Politics, accessed on 12 January 2004

Addressing more in detail the politics versus policy of mine action underscores the recurrent research difficulties to distinguish policy from politics. In effect, elements of politics and policy of mine action can not be strictly separated, simply because mine action policy cannot exist without politics, and mine action politics needs policy to regulate its implementation. This can be extended towards a broader conceptual approach. The simplified flowchart shown below displays the logical order from mine action politics to concrete implementation of mine action activities. The relation and interaction between these different activities will be addressed more in depth during the consecutive research phases. Naturally the focus will be on the mine action politics, but this will include studying the effects on the consultative processes and the development of strategies and policy.

Fig. I.1: Conceptual flowchart – from mine action politics to implementation of its activities

I.1.4. Important terms and definitions

The explanation of a limited number of important terms and definitions below will facilitate a good understanding of their usage throughout the study. It should be underscored it is not within the scope of this study to address detailed technical analysis of tactical mine action issues, standards or definitions. Mine action activities themselves are only a platform to explain the related politics and decision making within primarily a *multilateral* and *institutional* context, with a specific interest in the institutional dynamics of the United Nations System.⁴ Neither will the research focus on the legal aspects of related conventions. Hence, this study avoids any duplication of previous research efforts from other mine action publications.

A. Definition of mine action

The origin of mine action can be traced back to 1988, and cannot be considered separately from the ending of the Cold War, which provided opportunities and a major shift in the security environment:

“Landmines, which had seemed a necessary weapon to use in the event of an invasion of Western Europe by Warsaw Pact forces, took on a different appearance in the changing security landscape of the early 1990s. Many international relief organizations began to draw attention to the fact that landmines were not simply waiting in arsenals to be used in the event of war, but that millions of mines had been emplaced in over one hundred countries.”⁵

At the end of the Cold War, the United Nations Organisation largely inherited this problem and therefore seized the opportunities to appeal for the first time for specific funding. These initial efforts would enable a *humanitarian* response to the problems caused by landmines during massive refugee returns in Afghanistan. Prior to this period, activities intended to reduce the impact of mines, especially through mine clearance, were largely the domain of national militaries. Politics as one can observe today were not strictly involved.

The first mainstream use of the term “*mine action*” occurred when the Cambodian Mine Action Centre (CMAC) was established as a national institution in 1993. With its responsibilities already extending far beyond clearance of mines and unexploded ordnance, it paved the way for

⁴ The term United Nations System includes the United Nations Organization and the representation/delegations of UN Member States.

⁵ McDONALD, B. (2004). *The Global Landmine Crisis in the 1990s – Landmines and Human Security*, State University of New York Press, p.31

activities which would evolve toward the current concept of mine action. The world had begun to understand that resolving the global landmine problem would be a huge undertaking and require an incalculable amount of time, money and multidisciplinary action to alleviate human suffering and restore a secure environment.⁶ Although mine action has evolved ever since, one can distinguish two phases since the genesis of mine action; the *standardization phase*, and what is perceived as the current phase, the *professionalisation of mine action*.⁷ Together with this evolution of mine action and its related activities, the political dynamics originating from the different stakeholders steadily developed. Hence, mine action has been defined differently throughout its development stages. In the 1998 UN Policy the important socio-economic dimension is addressed comprehensively:

“Mine action refers to all those activities which address the problems faced by people as a result of landmine contamination. Mine action is not so much about mines, as about people and their interactions with a mine-contaminated environment: it aims to recreate an environment in which people can live safely, in which economic and social development can occur free from constraints, and in which mine survivors are fully integrated into their societies.”⁸

The conceptual definition of mine action as stated in the United Nations Mine Action Strategy for 2001-2005 reflects the evolution from a mainly military undertaking to a component of humanitarian relief, national recovery and reconstruction in mine-affected countries:

“The purpose of mine action is to recreate a safe environment conducive to normal life and development. Accordingly, mine action refers to all those activities geared towards addressing the problems faced by populations as a result of landmine or UXO contamination. (...)”⁹

Clearly both definitions have in common that the centre of gravity lies with the people living in mine-affected regions, together with ways and means to alleviate the negative impact of mines. References to the ideal of a mine free world or environment are tellingly absent. Inevitably, the different course of actions “*mine free*” versus “*impact free*” will be an important and recurrent discussion topic throughout the study.

B. Defining the “*global landmine problem*”

The global landmine problem has been an ever-evolving problem even to the extent it is often called the global landmine *crisis*. For this reason, the global landmine problem is often defined through a sum-up of dynamic and dramatic facts which characterizes the devastating impact in terms of numbers of landmine victims, affected countries and other key quantifiers. Hence, in 2006 the Landmine Monitor identified at least 79 countries and eight areas contaminated with landmines and unexploded ordnance or explosive remnants of war.¹⁰

Figure I.2 illustrates the vastness of the contamination. As of 2005, more than 200,000 square kilometers are suspected to be contaminated by landmines and UXO. At least three governments currently use antipersonnel mines-Myanmar (Burma), Nepal and Russia. Of particular interest, Non-State Armed Groups (NSAG) are using antipersonnel mines in more countries than government forces.

⁶ BOWNESS, C. (2006). The Missing Link in Strategic Planning: ALARA and the End-State Strategy Concept for National Mine Action Planning, Mine Action Information Centre, *Journal of Mine Action 9.1*, James Madison University, Virginia

⁷ GICHD Publication. (2003) *A Guide to Mine Action*. Geneva International Centre for Humanitarian Demining, Geneva, p.25

⁸ UN Document A/53/496, annex II. Mine Action and Effective Coordination: The UN Policy (1998), New York

⁹ UN Document A/58/260 Add.1 Report of the Secretary-General on United Nations Mine Action: Strategy for 2001-2005, New York

¹⁰ ICBL(2006). *Landmine Monitor Report 2006: Toward a Mine-Free World: International Campaign to Ban Landmines*, New York

Fig. I.2: Global overview of the 79 countries and 8 areas of the world having a problem with landmines and unexploded ordnance

C. Definition of a landmine

Existing definitions of a landmine vary among the different kinds of weapons envisaged. This thesis will go beyond the technical or design oriented definition of mines and regard them as any device, even improvised ones, which may be exploded through contact by, or presence or proximity of, a person or persons, and which is capable of killing, injuring or incapacitating one or more persons in an *indiscriminate* manner.¹¹ The broadening of this definition is in line with the UN mine action resolution norm building efforts related to the impact of landmines or associated explosive devices. This is less stringent than the design oriented definition of “anti-personnel” mines used in the International Mine Action Standards (IMAS) or according to the Mine Ban Treaty (MBT), also called Anti-Personnel Mine Ban Convention¹² (AP MBC), as well as in the Convention on Certain Conventional Weapons – Amended Protocol II¹³ (CCW).

D. Definition of unexploded ordnance and explosive remnants of war

When the term landmine is used in this study, *unexploded ordnance (UXO)* and/or *explosive remnants of war (ERW)* are included, unless stated otherwise. For unexploded ordnance the

¹¹ Largely derived from the definition of a landmine according to the International Mine Action Standards (IMAS), Internet. Available at <http://www.mineactionstandards.org>, accessed on 7 July 2004

¹² AP MBC Article 2 (§1 and 3)- Definitions: “Anti-personnel mine” means a mine designed to be exploded by the presence, proximity or contact of a person that will incapacitate, injure or kill one or more persons. Mines designed to be detonated by the presence, proximity or contact of a vehicle as opposed to a person that are equipped with anti-handling devices, are not considered anti-personnel mines as a result of being so equipped. “Anti-handling device” means a device intended to protect a mine and which is part of, linked to, attached to or placed under the mine and which activates when an attempt is made to tamper with or otherwise intentionally disturb the mine.

¹³CCW – Amended Protocol II defines an anti-personnel mine as “a mine primarily designed to be exploded by the presence, proximity or contact of a person and that will incapacitate, injure or kill a person”. Anti-vehicle mines are referred to in the protocol as “mines other than anti-personnel mines” and are regulated under its general rules.

definition used as per the International Mine Action Standards, is explosive ordnance that has been primed, fused, armed or otherwise prepared for use or used. It may have been fired, dropped, launched or projected, yet remains unexploded either through malfunction or design or for any other reason.¹⁴ The definition for *explosive remnants of war* includes *unexploded ordnance* and *abandoned explosive remnants*. The latter defined as: explosive ordnance that has not been used during an armed conflict, that has been left behind or dumped by a party to an armed conflict, and which is no longer under control of the party that left it behind or dumped it. Abandoned explosive ordnance may or may not have been primed, fused, armed or otherwise prepared for use.¹⁵

E. Definition of a minefield

The International Mine Action Standards give a relatively short definition of a *minefield*: an area of ground containing mines deployed with or without a pattern.¹⁶ It is evident that minefields with unpredictable patterns - referred to as nuisance mine laying - are often more dangerous and much harder to clear than systematically laid minefields, especially in absence of minefield maps.

F. Definition of Suspected Hazardous Areas

This study will use more frequently the concept of hazardous areas or *suspected hazardous areas (SHA)*, than the term or concept of a minefield. As a more generic term it considers different kinds of contamination leading to inaccessible areas not in productive use due to the *perceived* or *actual* presence of mines, UXO or other explosive devices. This is in line with the focus of this study on the impact rather than the technicalities of these weapons.

G. Definition of a mine affected area or community

A community is being referred to as mine affected if it contains one or several areas within the community border which are believed or verified to contain mines. Similarly, an area which is believed or verified to contain mines will be termed "*a mine affected area*".¹⁷

¹⁴ International Mine Action Standards (IMAS), Internet. Available at <http://www.mineactionstandards.org>, accessed on 7 July 2004

¹⁵ Convention on certain Conventional Weapons – Amended Protocol V

¹⁶ IMAS 04.10 Second Edition, 1 January 2003, Internet. Available at <http://www.mineactionstandards.org>, accessed on 15 March 2005

¹⁷ VISTISEN, J. (2006). *Risk Assessments of Minefields in Humanitarian Mine Action – A Bayesian Approach*, Ph.D. thesis, Informatics and Mathematical Modelling, Technical University of Denmark, p.17

I.2. Research aim and objectives

“*The Politics of Mine Action*” is about the multilateral and institutional politics and policy-making in a particular disarmament domain. Through the application of game theoretic principles, it envisages bringing clarity to a myriad of political actors and courses of action in response to a complex global problem. The mixture of politics and its underpinning technicalities are further specified in the subtitle “*Normative, game and decision theoretic approaches to post-conflict problems caused by landmines and similar explosive remnants of war*”. It stipulates in which discipline this dissertation in particular wants to contribute, namely through the presentation of *innovative decision analysis approaches*. This envisaged contribution is born out of the observations

made during field visits of divers mine action programmes, in particular the mine action programme in Afghanistan.¹⁸ As illustrated in figure I.3¹⁹, the decision making problems related to the effective and efficient prioritization of mine action are extremely challenging, considering the impact of more than four thousand minefields on more than two thousand affected Afghan communities. The current efforts to define the impact of the landmine problem, largely in terms of high-medium and low impact, are commendable but criticized for not providing sufficient differentiation at national and local level to aid decision making and prioritization of mine action activities.

Fig. I.3: The Landmine Impact Survey in Afghanistan determined in 2005 that 2368 Afghan communities are impacted by 4500 minefields

This search for innovative decision analysis, however, in particular the usage of multiple criteria analysis, regression statistics, strategic planning and comprehensive cost-benefit analysis of mine action programs has been a divisive issue at the different levels of decision making in mine action. Moreover, the innovative part needs to lie in its capability to deal with currently available data. Different schools of thought present nearly opposing points of view. Several internationally respected experts in this field hesitate strongly to replace sound judgment and expertise by what they perceive as an incomprehensible and unworkable bundle of calculations. Ultimately, the mathematization of the decision analysis or prioritization process would not merit the additional time required by often overburdened decision makers or managers of post-conflict restoration programmes. They perceive it as a modern world’s instinct to reach for automation, spreadsheets and easy formulas, with a potentially questionable end result.²⁰ Their scepticism stems from the assumption that those new techniques are counterproductive, since they are likely to reduce holistic and heuristic²¹ assessments, hindering thoughtfulness rather than spur new approaches.

¹⁸ Field and study visits of Afghanistan in 2002 and 2003.

¹⁹ Survey Action Centre. (2005). Afghanistan Landmine Impact Survey, Washington, p.22

²⁰ GRAYSON, J. (2003). Mine action and development: merging strategies, *Disarmament Forum*, New York - September 2003

²¹ An heuristic approach involves intuition, rules of thumb, past experience, or common sense to make decisions. It is typically used when a formal model does not exist but with a successful outcome which highly depends on the skills and expertise of the decision maker. There are several practical steps to understand the complex problems related to mine action, like: trying to visualize it through schematic sketches, assuming there is a solution in order to see what can be derived from it, also called “reverse engineering” or “working backwards”. Another approach is trying to solve a more general problem first, also called the “inventor’s paradox”; initially aiming for a more ambitious plan may have better chances of success.

On the other hand, several countries have been requesting at a global level clear *criteria* and *indicators* to assist them in their mine action policy and decision making, more specifically regarding allocation of resources to mine-affected countries. Unambiguous *benchmarks* or *targets* to assess the effectiveness of mine action programmes are equally a recurrent request of the donor community.

In support of the envisaged innovative approach, this dissertation seeks to demonstrate that current irregular decision making approaches do not offer a comprehensive or de-conflicting prioritization process of mine action activities. Therefore, it aspires to develop a method in support of political decision making processes which better incorporate varied types of information. This includes the views of multiple stakeholders and public policies that must typically be brought to bear when humanitarian relief, disarmament and post-conflict restoration are under consideration. Additionally, the conflicting political dynamics related to the norms of the Mine Ban Treaty - whereby State Parties are obliged to respect stringent deadlines for clearance and stockpile destruction - will be brought into the equation.

By challenging the contemporary conservative views this study aims to prove that the politics of mine action and its related complex decision making processes can and should rely on advanced *multiple criteria decision analysis* (MCDA), based on normative, game and decision theoretic approaches. The central problem is how to evaluate a numerous and complex set of alternatives, based on carefully selected criteria, in order to determine a most optimal solution. Although this problem is relevant in practice, there are currently few methods available in the field of mine action. Thus, the question “*Which is the optimal method to find the best strategic response for a given landmine problem?*” will be one of the most important and challenging ones. It requires questioning the current process of prioritization of mine action activities versus other post-conflict humanitarian and development needs.

In summary, given a normative, game and decision theoretic perspective, this dissertation aims to adhere to the following four research objectives:

1. to explain comprehensively the political dynamics related to mine action;
2. to prove that the politics of mine action can benefit from a scientifically sound model based on systematic, objective and advanced multiple criteria decision analysis;
3. to prove the functionality of this model for heavily affected countries such as Afghanistan;
4. to formulate *grand strategy*²² recommendations for the politics of mine action.

²² This is the broadest conception of how an objective is to be attained. *Grand strategy* is an overarching concept that guides how nations employ all of the instruments of national power to shape world events and achieve specific national security objectives. *Paper: Saving the World for Democracy, An Historical Analysis of America’s Grand Strategy in the 21st Century* by Colonel Joe Bassani, United States Army. Available at http://www.jfsc.ndu.edu/college_resources/JOR/Grand_Strategy/American_Grand_Strategy.pdf, accessed on 17 July 2006

I.3. Research methodology

I.3.1. Why normative, game and decision theory?

For decennia the field of normative, game and decision theory has grown at a significant pace and well beyond its initial applications.²³ The introduction of game and decision theory in political science is however relatively new and its normative and descriptive applications are still evolving considerably.²⁴ As indicated above in addressing the conflicting or opposite stakeholder positions and their bargaining tactics during negotiations, one can expect the exploration of game theoretic principles to be particularly useful to explain, rather than predict, the multilateral politics of mine action at the different levels.

In the area of political science, game theory became also a helpful and widely accepted modelling method, which will be of use for the envisaged development of a normative model. Moreover, decision making theory combined with game theory will be required to provide the foundation for the theoretic modelling and understanding of competing interests, with pragmatic applications in the Afghanistan case-study.

Hence, although similar to decision theory²⁵, the exact purpose of studying the politics of mine action through game theory is because it studies decisions that are made in an environment where States interact. In other words, this approach studies choice of *preferred* State behaviour²⁶ whereby the benefits of each option or course of action are not set, but depend upon the choices of other States or key actors. *Interdependent* decision theory would perhaps be a more descriptive name for game theoretic approaches in this study since the interactive or interdependent behaviour of decision makers will be studied. Game theory in this study could be used to explain game theoretic equilibriums, which involves the different levels of incentives or expected utilities related to political decisions or possible courses of action. These equilibriums could have limited predictive value as they indicate a form of political stability, especially if this stability is desired by the numerous stakeholders involved.

The decision theoretic angle becomes more dominant when the complexity of decision making in mine action is addressed, or the complexity of the organization that has to make them. In this regard, the issue is not the deviation between *real* and *optimal* decision making, but the difficulty of determining the optimal decision in the first place. Several factors complicate this process; risk management is one of them. The combined research effort of a normative factor analysis whilst exploring game and decision theoretic applications will therefore be required to seek the *optimal response*. It will then be interesting to highlight the differences between what States regard as their *best response* and the projected *optimal or normative response* based on a system of neutral and objective criteria. The higher reliance on mathematical decision theoretic techniques, and the usage of decision support systems are therefore suggested:

²³ Primarily economists have been extensively using game theory to analyze a wide array of economic phenomena. The most famous of these is the Nash equilibrium, whereby a set of strategies is as such considered when within this set each strategic choice represents a best response to the other strategies. Consequently, there is no incentive to alter between strategic options, hence the usage of the term equilibrium.

²⁴ Game theory entered into political science since the 1950s. Lloyd S. Shapley and Martin Shubik's "A Method of Evaluating the Distribution of Power in a Committee System" published in the *American Political Science Review* in 1954 was the first paper to discuss game theory in connection with politics, Internet. Available at http://carbon.cudenver.edu/~ldeleon/pad8020/student_papers/letters1.txt.html, accessed on 10 March 2005

²⁵ The term "decision theory" itself was first used in 1950 by Prof. Emirius, he has made fundamental contributions to the theory of statistics; his principal interests these days are in the history and philosophy of statistics. He is the author of *Basic Concepts of Probability and Statistics*.

²⁶ Preferred State behaviour here means what has been perceived as the most optimal decision by the State or actor itself, which does not necessarily coincide with normative, optimal behaviour.

“Classical decision theory, so called to distinguish it from a number of non-classical theories which have grown up in the last few years, is a set of mathematical techniques for making decisions about what action to take when the outcomes of the various actions are not known”²⁷

Some alterations of the traditional game theory, which is largely based on interaction between hostile parties with different options to achieve their goals, must be expected. Indeed, long before game theory fully developed and became illustrative to think about trade-off and payoff problems systematically, military decision makers used it to influence their planning and strategies. Choices made by adversary military leaders, albeit often simultaneously, have led to the most remarkable strategic but also disastrous “games” in history whereby strategic interests tragically involved the lives of thousands or the spending of billions of dollars as during the Cold War’s arms race. The term “game” is to that extent a bit misleading, as it has nothing to do with the classic interpretation of the word. With regard to the Cold War era, during the development and build-up of the most destructive high-tech weapons, oddly, landmines were most often used in a non-sophisticated political or military setting. Stigmatized as “*weapons of the poor*”, hundreds of thousands of mines contaminated many nations during long stretched static inter- or intrastate conflicts or proxy wars. Many of these nations are stigmatized today as the most *fragile States*.

In summary, normative and game theoretic topics will be explored to explain the multilateral mine action politics of States, the complexity of the problem, and the different stakeholder positions at a global level. Decision theory is further normative since it tries to identify the *optimal* decision to take. Hence, through normative and decision theory, pragmatic applications of a *prescriptive* decision making approach can bring interesting results.

I.3.2. An empirical and ethical research approach

The study will adhere to a *pragmatic* and *ethical* approach,²⁸ where possible supported by empirical testing, real world data and evidence. The pervasiveness and impact of technology on society and on every day human life has led indeed to a growing awareness that science and technology cannot be considered above or beyond the realm of value judgments and hence of ethics. This is especially true for game and/or decision theoretic applications in political and social sciences, where methodologies for deciding how to respond are bound to many constraints and political agendas, usually under conditions requiring the allocation of scarce resources.

Mine action involves decisions that seriously impact on the lives of other people; in extremis it can make the difference between life and death. With landmines considered by a number of States as a justifiable pillar of their national security system or as an essential part of their military doctrine, the politics of mine action is characterized by ethical-political controversy or opposing visions. The remarkable dualism of States with immense landmine stocks belonging to the most ardent mine action supporters²⁹, already illustrates the contradictory dynamics and complexity of the high level politics. This will become even more apparent when studying the relevant treaties which range in their objectives from regulating the use of landmines to a total ban. Especially the study of these conflicting political positions of States promises valuable insights and game theoretic applications, not only on landmines and mine action, but also on other armament or disarmament issues such as efforts to curb the illicit traffic in small arms and light weapons (SALW).

²⁷PARSONS, S., WOOLRIDGE, M. (2000). *Game Theory and Decision Theory in Multi-Agent Systems*, University of Liverpool, p.1

²⁸The “ethical” approach will be illustrated when addressing the human cost of the landmine problem and its related aspects of quantification and qualification in number of mine victims and the socio-economic impact in terms of healthcare costs and loss of economic productivity.

²⁹Example as part of the military doctrine of United States and Finland.

In summary, ethical considerations will be of particular challenge when expanding on the normative and game theoretic modelling. This can be rightly part of a game theoretic approach:

“Game theory is the systematic study of interdependent rational choice. It may be used to explain, to predict, and to evaluate human behavior in contexts where the outcome of action depends on what several agents choose to do and where their choices depend on what others choose to do. Game theory consequently is relevant to *ethics*, and it is used in moral and political philosophy in a variety of ways.”³⁰

This will also be demonstrated during the case-study, where normative modelling will be used as a tool for improving expert assessment and decision making related to the *human cost* of the landmine problem in Afghanistan.

I.3.3. Research phases

A. Analytical process

Figure I.4: Phased research process – generic layout

The decision to adopt a phased analytical approach allows for a more manageable subdivision of the study of the politics of mine action and facilitates the identification of a distinct focus for each of the research phases. The examination, in consecutive phases of the dynamics involved, together with statistical and other mine action data, aspires to lead to a clearer perception of the global landmine problem and also a better apprehension of the effectiveness of the politics of mine action.

As illustrated in the generic figure, the research process will be based on a process of transforming *data*³¹ to *information*³² via either descriptive statistics or normative analysis and *information* to *knowledge*³³ via modelling through inferential statistics³⁴ and multiple criteria decision analysis. In the context of this study, the information part should be understood as facilitating the understanding of the current situation, whilst knowledge is further processed

³⁰Game theory and ethics, Internet. Available at <http://plato.stanford.edu/entries/game-ethics>, accessed on 10 Aug 2006

³¹*Data*: specific observations or measured numbers

³²*Information*: processed and summarized data yielding facts and ideas

³³*Knowledge*: selected and organized information that provides understanding, recommendations, and the basis for decisions

³⁴*Descriptive* statistics include graphical and numerical procedures that summarize and process data. *Inferential* statistics provide the basis for predictions, forecasts, and estimates that are used to transform information to knowledge.

information in order to move toward enhanced decision making in anticipation of predicted developments in the field of mine action.³⁵ The following pages explain briefly the research effort in each phase. This is followed by a schematic overview of the methodology and research effort throughout the different phases. As this process will be used as a general guide, it is not overly rigid and still allows for iterations as the results of the research unfold. The interrelation between the consecutive phases is characterized through the usage of distinctively patterned arrows () in the methodology flowchart.

Highlighting the research approaches to the politics of mine action, raises also the question if the subject should be studied either from the start in a holistic manner or if one should opt for reductionism. In a first response to this question, both approaches likely produce complementary viewpoints and would be needed to get a proper account of the political dynamics related to mine action. Initially, the study will likely benefit more from a holistic approach.³⁶ As per the second research phase and case-study, opting for reductionism envisages providing the desired results. This will be further discussed when addressing the methodology of this dissertation, especially when detailing the first research phase and related analysis of the politics of mine action in its different disciplines, dimensions and levels.

As a last element to the general description of the phased research process, it must be noted that specific consideration has been given to obtain a *closed-loop research concept*. The first phase normative and game theoretic analysis of the politics of mine action and the corresponding mine action goals become in the last phase the subject of possible recommendations.

B. First Phase: Normative and Game Theoretic Analysis³⁷

The first phase entails the normative and game theoretic analysis of the politics of mine action, especially at a global level, and is quite similar in methodology to a comprehensive factor analysis of complex and multifaceted political problems. In order to delineate and structure this first phase, the United Nations Resolution “Assistance in mine action” will serve as the central reference. This was a logical choice since the main objective of this resolution is to promote assistance in mine action at a global level. This results in a political process which brings together the diverging and sometimes competing or conflicting political agendas of United Nations Member States and will, therefore, often revert to game theoretic principles to explain the bargaining politics of mine action.

In order to keep this phase focused and current, the politics of mine action will be primarily envisioned since the new millennium, years characterized by the further professionalisation of mine action. More specifically, the 2003 - 58th General Assembly Resolution on Assistance in mine action will serve as the anchor of the normative analysis. It is a lengthy resolution but each preamble paragraph has its specific rationale and will be analyzed with the primary purpose to study game theoretic approaches together with the deduction of relevant goals and indicators. This resolution coincided with the first drafting and research efforts related to this dissertation. It was envisaged to derive at an early stage credible criterion from the normative modelling. It was afterwards observed that more recent UN resolutions on assistance in mine action do not offer such a solid framework as increasingly conflicting positions between UN Member States complicated the consensus process,

³⁵In other domains, especially military, this particular progression is described as the process of collecting raw data, then collation towards information, followed by analysis which gives as final product: (military) intelligence.

³⁶This approach is supported by contemporary defenders of holism about society, who believe that there are irreducible laws about social phenomena. Prominent philosophers of social science believe that theories in social science must mention unobservable theoretic entities, such as social structures, and in the scientific context of this study, those entities exist in some way that is not reducible to the individuals and their isolated behaviour.

³⁷A normative, primarily descriptive analysis provides information but does not necessarily focus on obtaining solutions and/or recommendations, although certain norm setting will pave the way for consecutive knowledge building.

therefore causing the text to revert to a minimalist version. This phase addresses primarily the first supporting research objective, namely the analysis of the political dynamics related to mine action.

It is furthermore a given that one can only define sound solutions and policies for clearly and correctly defined problems. Since one of the goals of the politics of mine action is to reduce the *human cost* and *socio-economic impact* of the global landmine problem, both will be thoroughly studied. Complex problems demand clear metrics, benchmarks and/or performance indicators. This will allow for oversight on possible progress - or lack of it - towards reaching the objectives or targets. Formulating endstates or exit strategies is then equally facilitated. Post-conflict theory and practice have advanced significantly over the past few years, yet the opinion prevails within the field of mine action that the international community lacks pragmatic, reliable and forward-leaning models for measuring true progress in certain post-conflict settings.³⁸ The following old adage referred to by the Special Representative for Mine Action of the United States could not reflect this better:

“We achieve what we measure, so we had better measure what we want to achieve.”³⁹

This is particularly applicable in mine action where progress in areas that have the most meaning must be based, as much as possible, on reliable indicators and sound data. Therefore, the politics of the UN Millennium Development Goals and its related “Goals, Targets and Indicators (GTI) model” inform this study on post-conflict recovery, with mine action as part thereof. Nowadays, it is an embedded part of UN institutional politics, although the foundation was provided through the *high politics* of UN Member States, reflecting the need for global goal and target setting.

“The Millennium Development Goals were never articulated as explicit Goals nor formally adopted in the September 2000 Special Millennium Session of the General Assembly. Rather, Heads of States affirmed objectives in seven areas for action in the *Millennium Declaration*.”

The information sources usually relied upon do not easily provide or generate accurate mine action data, which significantly complicates the measurement of the effectiveness of the politics of mine action as much as mine action activities itself. However, current efforts to assess progress are noteworthy, especially through the annual Landmine Monitor and Landmine Impact Surveys, but not to the extent that the understanding of the “global” landmine problem is satisfactory. Underlying reasons include the inconsistencies in donor reporting and especially the inconsistencies in assessing the value of mine action outputs. It brings into question how the setting of goals and targets influences the politics, and vice versa? Are we setting the right goals and targets? Are we looking for the right information and do we use the most suitable indicators?

The analysis of the politics of mine action and its related goals and indicators will not be limited to clarifying many of the political dynamics. It will also allow for the deduction of multiple criteria and lay the foundation for normative modelling which could provide decision making guidance.

C. Second Phase: Normative Modelling

This phase will further analyze how criteria and indicators related to the politics of mine action can be used in normative modelling. The research will, therefore, focus on those political factors and criteria which are closely related to the effectiveness or optimal implementation of mine action programmes. Genuinely interested or rational States would not want to spend scarce resources

³⁸ Rumsfeld’s “leaked” memo of 16 October 2003 offers an interesting example on how complex modern conflicts, such as the US led “Global War on Terror (GWoT)”, reinvigorates the quest for metrics in a fragile multidimensional and multidisciplinary peace and nation building process. Available at www.usatoday.com/news/washington/executive/rumsfeld-memo.htm, accessed on 15 March 2005

³⁹ BLOOMFIELD, L. (2003). Detritus of Conflict: The U.S. Approach to the Humanitarian Problem posed by Landmines and other Hazardous Remnants of War, *Seton Hall Journal of Diplomacy and International Relations*, Number 1

on mine action programmes which seem to be largely or consistently ineffective. This also implies that specific criteria need to be applied for the allocation of resources to have optimal effects.

The generated resources or funding, primarily through donor governments, should relate to requests from recipient governments in order to deliver adequate emergency responses, create the envisaged socio-economic benefits, and provide for peace and confidence building. This is symbolized in the schematic overview of the methodology through the intersection of the possible overlapping mine action objectives, being simultaneously the nucleus of the envisaged mine action output. It might be obvious in this simplistic scheme that the politics of mine action should aim toward an optimal combination of its resources in order to obtain “*intersection optimization*”. However, competing and conflicting demands of national political and other agendas, ever-changing environmental conditions and other constraining factors easily complicate this quest for effectiveness and efficiency. Rational decision makers seek the highest expected utilities coming from mine action. Notably, the first important use of *expected utility theory* was that of John von Neumann and Oskar Morgenstern, who used the assumption of expected utility maximization in their formulation of game theory. To apply the basic principles of utility theory in support of game theoretic applications is, therefore, an essential research theme in this phase, in particular when analyzing best strategic responses to the landmine problem.

This phase is primarily inward looking. Almost with a “*tunnel vision*” on mine action, it pursues to determine those criteria which characterizes - or should be the norm - of mine action within mine affected States. However, the modelling will be extended outside the scope of traditional mine action activities: “*from tunnel to macro vision*”. This process of modelling beyond the effectiveness and efficiency of mine action, seeks to line and link up mine action with broader, overarching development and post-conflict reconstruction strategies of mine-affected countries. Hence, this second part of the modelling phase addresses how mine action can respond to a needs analysis, security threats analysis and socio-economic benefit analysis. More specifically, it will study how mine action is or can be integrated in emergency response plans, Security Sector Reform strategies, Poverty Reduction Strategy Papers and/or national development planning.

The modelling effort will likely be a complex normative, nonlinear⁴⁰ and stochastic⁴¹ process. Resolution through theory will be difficult due to unattainable data, inputs or variables to the model. If certain variables cannot be estimated with any accuracy, then decision theory based on fuzzy data and/or advanced sensitivity analysis could bring resolution. Theoretically, the model should provide in different scenarios the optimal combination of (1) humanitarian relief, (2) socio-economic benefits and (3) peacekeeping/building efforts. The criteria and indicators deduced from the first phase will provide the desired building blocks for a multiple criteria decision analysis model for mine action, which will be tested with real world mine action data from Afghanistan in the next phase.

In summary, this dissertation aspires to illustrate through normative modelling how holistic research could take into account both statistical theory and real world political demands. It, therefore, aims to present a working philosophy of statistical regression theory that goes well beyond the abstract, which justifies the third research phase.

D. Third Phase: Case-study Afghanistan

The results of previous phases will be applied in the case-study of Afghanistan. The choice of this mine affected country is based on the fascinating dynamics of its mine action politics, as well as the size, maturity of the programme and the level of sophistication and professionalisation of Afghan mine action. Its mine action program has the potential to serve as a role model or lead program and

⁴⁰Non-linear models have one or more mathematical relationships that are not first-degree relationships.

⁴¹Stochastic models involve elements of uncertainty.

provide a basis to formulate recommendations and indications. This will facilitate the study of the global dimension of mine action politics in the last phase.

Statistical regression analysis of Afghan data and strategic planning tools will be used to explore further the potential of normative modelling. The goal of this phase is to obtain an optimal prioritization for future mine action in Afghanistan. Therefore, the recent data of the Landmine Impact Survey in Afghanistan will be of essential value. This detailed and valuable survey process will contribute significantly to the practical development and illustration of an effective methodology for multiple criteria decision analysis. This should demonstrate that the model can provide credible guidance to decision making processes in terms of an optimal prioritization or ranking of mine action activities. Apart from the high level aspects of the politics of mine action, the case-study needs therefore to broadly address the benefits of having a *short* and *long term* strategic management for the prioritization and execution of mine action activities. Such strategic management is in general the highest level of managerial activity, in the business world usually performed by the company's Chief Executive Officer (CEO) and executive team. It provides overall direction to the whole enterprise, in this context the national mine action community. This dissertation should not seek absolute incorporation of business models; however, in order to explore principles of effectiveness and efficiency in the field of mine action, guidance can be drawn from inspiring statements delivered in most competitive environments, such as the vision of Mr. Louis Gerstner, CEO IBM.

“Good strategies start with massive amounts of quantitative analysis, hard, difficult analysis that is blended with wisdom, insight, and risk taking. Truly great companies lay out strategies that are believable and executable. Good strategies are long on detail and short on vision.”⁴²

An organization's strategy must be tailored to its resources, circumstances, and objectives; successful implementation of high or strategic political goals should not require anything different. Hence, in a political context, a sound mine action strategy for Afghanistan is largely an overarching longer term plan of action designed to achieve a particular political goal or its subordinate objectives, as differentiated from tactics or immediate actions with sufficient resources at hand. This view is clearly represented in James Morrow's work on “*Game Theory for Political Scientists*”.

“Strategy is the essence of politics; a non-strategic politician cannot achieve his or her aims. The political scientist who has neither the time, the training, nor the inclination for strategic thought will be poorly equipped to understand the strategic twists and turns of politics.”⁴³

E. Fourth Phase: The Global Dimension

This final phase envisages transferring the research results, findings and recommendations of the case-study of Afghanistan from the national level to the global level. This will be based on data from the most recent publications of the Landmine Monitor and Landmine Impact Surveys (LIS).

As it is the final phase, research results are compiled from the previous phases. This will summarize the answers in response to the research aim and the four more specific research objectives. Current multilevel politics of mine action are confronted with the conclusive findings and “*Grand Strategy*” recommendations will be formulated for the *Politics of Mine Action*.

F. Schematic overview of the research phases and methodology

Although the response to the research aim and supporting research objectives cannot be exactly delineated, the main effort of each phase is according to the scheme below. Every phase focuses on one to two objectives with the case-study having a more inclusive approach.

⁴² GERSTNER, L. (2002). *Who Says Elephants Can't Dance? Inside IBM's Historic Turnaround*, Australia, by Griffin Press, cover

⁴³ MORROW, J. (1994). *Game Theory for Political Scientists*, Princeton University Press, New Jersey, p.1

First Phase: Normative & Game Theoretic Analysis

Second Phase: Normative Modelling

Multiple Criteria and Indicators

Intrinsic Utility Functions

Humanitarian Relief
Socio-Economic Benefits
Peace Building

Normative Modelling Guidance

Strategic Planning Framework

Third Phase: Case-study Afghanistan

Normative Modelling Guidance

National Resource Allocation Guidance

Fourth Phase: Global dimension

CHAPTER II – PHASE-I: A NORMATIVE AND GAME THEORETIC ANALYSIS

“Looking back at the history of the landmine problem, it is very easy to understand why efforts to develop a new set of norms banning these weapons were initially dismissed as a utopian vision of a few NGO activists. The mass production of landmines in over 50 States and their indiscriminate use in terms of millions in dozens of countries during the 1960’s, 1970’s and 1980’s had made landmines a significant factor behind seemingly intractable human suffering in civil wars that raged in places such as Cambodia, Afghanistan, Mozambique and Angola.”⁴⁴

II.1. Introduction

II.1.1. Normative building blocks of a UN resolution

The normative analysis will use the UN resolution on “*Assistance in mine action*” as a baseline reference. This UN resolution provides a solid framework for analyzing the politics, actions, problems and policymaking related to the global-strategic level of mine action and incorporates the views of all UN Member States. The uniqueness of this political process lies in its inclusiveness and consensus-driven approach, which is also essential for representative and credible normative modelling.

The term *normative* analysis indicates the interest for the normative value of the resolution, because the objective is not only to gather facts but to analyse how the politics of mine action could become more effective. Effective politics of mine action are in this context understood as both multilateral and unilateral efforts, which support or facilitate an optimal response to this global scourge. This includes evaluation of the present state of assistance in mine action as well as the direction of future development.

A typical UN resolution comprises basically two parts: (1) a primarily descriptive *preamble*; (2) a corresponding *operative part*, requesting UN Member States for requisite action. In response to the first research objective, each preamble paragraph of the 2003-58th General Assembly (GA) mine action resolution⁴⁵ will be comprehensively analysed and studied (see Annex A for the full text). The primary reason to choose this version of the resolution is due to the high informative and normative value of its preamble paragraphs. References will be made to the respective operative paragraphs as required. Other reasons to base the analysis on the 2003 resolution are the unsuccessful attempt to obtain a consensus resolution in 2004 and, as addressed during Chapter I, the minimalist version of the resolution in 2005. In the latter it was decided to bi-annualize the resolution which implies that the 2007-62nd GA will present the next opportunity to table a renewed resolution on assistance in mine action.⁴⁶ The analysis envisages valuable game theoretic and normative insights for the next phase, which entails normative modelling. The deduction of indicators and goals to characterize the politics of mine action will further structure this analytical process.

⁴⁴ LAWSON, R. (2002). *Ban Landmines! The social construction of the international ban on anti-personnel landmines 1991-2001*, Ph.D., Ottawa, Ontario: Carlton University, p.3

⁴⁵ UN Document A/RES/58/127, *Assistance in mine action*, Internet. Available from <http://www.un.org/Depts/dhl/resguide/r58.htm>, accessed on 10 Oct 2005

⁴⁶ In the 60th GA UN resolution on assistance in mine action it was decided not to include the item entitled “*Assistance in mine action*” in the provisional agenda of the 61st GA but in the agenda of the 62nd GA session, UN Document A/RES/60/97, Internet. Available at <http://www.un.org/Depts/dhl/resguide/r58.htm>, accessed on 20 Dec 2006

Notably, the resolution is the result of a *consensus* process; therefore, it includes compromising language, which is less normative than drafting originators or sponsors would like it to be. The impact of less sympathetic States on the goals of assistance in mine action is noticeable even after years of political and diplomatic manoeuvring. Consequently, the resolution does not reflect the non-compromising universal norm of a world free of anti-personnel landmines, which is the foundation of the Mine Ban Treaty.

II.1.2. Expanding on the game theoretic analysis

As highlighted in Chapter I, game theory in combination with normative analysis has been chosen because it addresses one of the central elements of this study, namely the analysis of alternative courses of action according to the different bargaining positions, tradeoffs and payoffs of the actors involved. One of the key elements when analysing the UN resolution is to study why States at the high political level *choose or reject to cooperate* and coordinate their actions.

“The landmine issue was born when NGO experts in the landmine issue and/or in mine-infested States decided to *cooperate to ban their use*. NGO experts in the field identified landmines as a major obstacle to their work. These groups viewed landmines as exacerbating regional conflicts, hindering post-conflict reconstruction, seriously undermining infrastructure, and denying land to civilian use, thereby leading to extreme pressures on existing land.”⁴⁷

The repetitive choice of the same course of action contributes to norm building, repeated games and crystallization of collective State behaviour. This is a prominent part of the repetitive effort of UN consensus building regarding the mine action resolution. The game theoretic approach in this dissertation will be further characterized by its five traditional core elements⁴⁸:

- (1) A *number of players or actors* who make decisions. In most of the high politics games the actors are obviously States or *alliances* of States⁴⁹. In addition, the conceptual term “*nature*” could be occasionally introduced as an environmental non-player element which can influence the game at some stage. In the context of this dissertation, players could also be international and/or (non)governmental organisations, local authorities and individual decision-makers.
- (2) A *set of possible strategies* which need to be considered for each actor. A strategy is an overarching plan which prescribes an action for a number of situations in which the relevant actor can make a strategic choice. In some contexts strategy will be simply synonymous with a course of action.
- (3) A *set of possible outcomes*. A particular outcome is a possible end-state of the game or political debate, and is usually described in terms of the actions which must be taken to reach the end-state, or the expected payoffs it provides to the players. The favouring of one particular outcome can be explained through game theoretic equilibrium(s). In this case the term *solution concept* can be used.
- (4) For each player there is a *characterization of the payoffs* received at each of the various possible outcomes. The concept of mine action *payoffs* will be studied when addressing aspects of decision and utility theory, and related topics such as *ordinal* and *cardinal* scale ranking.

⁴⁷ McDONALD, B., MATTHEW R. and RUTHERFORD, K. (2004). *Landmines and Human Security, International Politics and War's Hidden Legacy*, State University of New York Press, p.52

⁴⁸ Based on the methodology presented in: HOVI, J. (1998). *Games, Threats & Treaties, understanding commitments in international relations*, United Kingdom: Biddles Ltd, p.3

⁴⁹ For the purpose of this study the term *alliance* means a close association of nations or other groups, formed to advance common interests or causes - According to the American Heritage® Dictionary of the English Language, Internet. Available at <http://www.bartleby.com/61>, accessed on October 2005

- (5) Other specific aspects or *rules of the game*. The sequence of strategic moves and information available is bound by many (UN) rules and regulations which could have a significant impact on the final outcome.

Although there are many inevitable overlaps, the analysis intends to avoid any blurring of normative and game theoretic characteristics. The normative analysis will primarily support the deduction of *goals and indicators* from the UN mine action resolution. This will be often a straightforward process only requiring limited analysis of the norms and language used in the UN resolution. Conversely, game theory will assist the deduction of relevant *decision-making criteria* in an interdependent environment. This should adequately reflect the possible strategies or courses of action at different political levels.

II.1.3. Applicable game theoretic assumptions

In order to apply primarily *descriptive game theory* to the politics of mine action, certain assumptions, abstract features, characteristics and definitions need to be addressed before the analysis can take place. A few traditional game theoretic assumptions need to be discussed to clarify game theoretic reasoning, particularly game theoretic elements related to rationality and beliefs.

A. Common knowledge of rationality (CKR)

The high politics actors are considered in this dissertation to be instrumentally rational with a well-ordered set of preferences regarding their possible strategic choices or responses. Rational actors in a game want to maximize their payoffs based on this key game theoretic assumption. This implies in a context of multilateralism that game theory is considered to be largely a type of normative theory, which specifies how States should act if they are to achieve their goals.⁵⁰ The term *normative game theory* is, therefore, often used in relation with *prescriptive game theory* as both theories can advise decision makers on the best strategic choices.

Hence, the assumption on rationality is limited to a common knowledge of all actors on the maximization of expected utilities and payoffs. There are different interpretations⁵¹ possible on how the concept of rationality manifests itself. Whereas utility theory studies *individual* rational behaviour, in a game theoretic context the nuance of *interdependent* behaviour is brought into the equation. Interacting actors are determined to maximize the utilities of their own interests, whether normative or not, selfish or unselfish, as specified by their own utility function. This underscores one important aspect of this assumption, namely that *national interest* is the motivating rationale behind State action. Whichever angle is taken on this assumption, the key issue for this dissertation is that the concept of rationality is materialized through actors striving for the maximization of their payoffs or political incentives.

B. Consistent alignment of beliefs (CAB)

The term *belief* has various meanings, in game theory it summarizes an actor's - subjective - judgment about what has probably happened up to that point in a game. If actors then share the same degree of rationality, it could be assumed that actors cannot come to a different set of conclusions. Game theorists typically assume CKR. Certain experts who apply game theory in economics take it further: in order to come up with precise predictions on rational behaviour, they assume not only CKR but also make the assumption of consistently aligned beliefs (CAB).⁵² However, in this particular field of high politics the jump from CKR to CAB is regarded as too

⁵⁰ ZAGARA, F. (1984). *Game Theory, Concepts and Applications*, California: Sage University Paper, Sage Publications, p.7

⁵¹ HOVI, J. (1998). *Games, threats & treaties: Understanding Commitments in International Relations*, United Kingdom, p.4

⁵² HARGREAVES, H., and VAROUFAKIS, Y. (2001). *Game Theory: A critical introduction*, New York, p.24

controversial. Indeed, CAB would give greater analytical power but to assume that everybody's beliefs are consistent with everybody else's with regard to complex and controversial disarmament issues is not credible in the context of this dissertation. It is even considered opposite to the large diversity of beliefs of the different key players on mine action.

“Put informally, the notion of consistent alignment of beliefs (CAB) means that no instrumentally rational person can expect another similarly rational person, who has the same information, to develop different thought processes. Or, alternatively, that no rational person expects to be surprised by another rational person.”⁵³

Counter-assuming CAB automatically implies that this study invariably takes a probabilistic approach towards beliefs and the *state of the world*. This requires touching upon the combination of probability theory with game theory. For this dissertation the assumption is that limited or imperfect information is available in the world of the politics of mine action, in contrast, it is together with the non-consistent and non-alignment of beliefs largely responsible for the political dynamics. Actors will therefore vary in their beliefs and strategic choices and rely on their subjective or prior beliefs on the state of the world, which encompasses all the relevant factors a rational decision maker faces but which are beyond his control.⁵⁴

C. Complete knowledge of rules and possible outcomes

This issue will be further addressed when discussing UN rules and regulations. As part of this set of key assumptions it is understood that key actors in the UN high politics sphere have a common and complete knowledge of the UN rules and possible outcomes. However, in other political forums or at lower political levels, this assumption could be debated. Once leaving the rigid UN bureaucracy, it is assumed that generally, less knowledge, compliance or acceptance of rules exists.

II.1.4. Overview of game theoretic principles

In table II.1 a brief overview is provided of the extant *game theoretic principles*, which are hypothetically and potentially relevant when modelling multilateral political dynamics. According to relevancy, they will be further explained in subsequent paragraphs.

Basic Game Theoretic Principles		Comments
Zero-sum ↔ Non-zero sum		Zero-sum= “exactly what one actor wins, the other will lose”. Non-zero sum = payoffs do not zero out – there might be better payoffs for a “loser” than in a zero-sum game.
Non-cooperative ↔ Cooperative		Cooperative means that actors adapt their strategic choices to achieve a common objective or make “binding agreements”. Non-cooperative relates to the competitive interdependency.
Dominant equilibrium ↔ Nash equilibrium		Games with a dominant equilibrium can have Nash equilibriums. A payoff dominant equilibrium is a Nash equilibrium that is <i>pareto</i> superior.
Pure strategy ↔ Mixed strategy		Pure= move <i>a</i> is best (thus chosen), otherwise <i>b</i> . Mixed = there's a probability <i>p</i> that the player chooses <i>a</i> , and probability 1- <i>p</i> that <i>b</i> is chosen.
Finite ↔ Infinite (evolutionary)		A single game can be repeated (in)finitely (with sub-games making a “super-game”). Actors can learn during the “repetition” (infinite or evolutionary games).
Extensive form ↔ Normal form		Extensive = with full game trees. Normal (or strategic form) = a “simplified” extensive form game depicted in a table with payoffs.
(In)complete information ↔ (Im)perfect information		Complete = every player <i>knows the payoffs&strategies available</i> to other players. Perfect = to describe a state of full <i>knowledge about the actions</i> of other players that is instantaneously updated as new information arises.

Table II.1: Basic game theoretic characteristics

⁵³ Id. at 25

⁵⁴ MORROW, J. (1994). *Game Theory for Political Scientists*, New Jersey: Princeton, p. 352

As for most disarmament research, it will be of particular interest to study the politics of mine action in light of the fundamental distinction between *cooperative* games and *non-cooperative* games. In *non-cooperative* games, only credible threats and promises can make a difference to the outcome. In a *cooperative* game, the question of credible threats simply does not arise. Other game theoretic variations which merit a comprehensive analysis are related to *coordination*, *contribution* in terms of required resources for mine action and to *compliance* with existing treaties, conventions and/or resolutions. However, all these variations can be reduced in essence to *cooperative* games and *non-cooperative* games.

In conclusion, the analysis of the respective preamble paragraphs will likely demonstrate many of the above game theoretic principles in an applied fashion and do not warrant an in depth discussion at this stage. Most, if not all, politics of mine action will portray aspects of *repeated* games, or *iterated* games. Contrary to *one-shot* games, they are an *extensive form* game which consists in some number of repetitions of what is called a base game or stage game. In classic game theoretic literature, the stage game is usually one of the traditional *two-person* games. As mentioned earlier, the multilateral character of the politics of mine action will, however, necessitate reverting quite often to *n-player* games.

II.1.5. Game theoretic equilibriums

Studying game theoretic equilibriums of the politics of mine action offers valuable insights on the multilateral phenomenon such as alliance formation and compliance with legally binding instruments or treaties. In simple terms, a game presents an equilibrium if it is based on strategic choices that actors have good reasons to follow and will continue to follow. Noticeably, the study of game theoretic equilibriums has never been underexposed, as equilibriums are regarded as the organizing concepts of game theory. Although game theoretic prediction is not a priority of the analysis, the identification of equilibriums, also referred to as a solution concept, has a predictive element since it suggests what the outcome of a particular game or choice of strategies could be. In case of repeated games or multiple equilibriums it also explains, or could predict, why a State changes its strategy from non-compliance, non-contribution or non-cooperation to a more constructive position and vice versa. It allows to study why UN Member States achieve consensus for over a decade on assistance in mine action and are suddenly paralyzed upon reaching an agreement. The important understanding of different types of equilibriums will be addressed next.

A. Nash equilibrium

The most well known is the *Nash equilibrium*, named after its inventor and Nobel Peace Prize Laureate John Forbes Nash. In sum, it is a *solution concept* of a game involving two or more actors, *where no player has anything to gain by changing only his own strategy unilaterally*. If each player has chosen a strategy and no player can benefit by changing his strategy while the other players keep theirs unchanged, then the current set of strategy choices and the corresponding payoffs constitute a Nash equilibrium. Hence, *to facilitate a desired Nash equilibrium in the politics of mine action, one has to create the conditions that no unilateral deviation of the chosen politics is profitable*.

In the context of UN multilateralism, it is expected that this will offer several interesting applications. Nash equilibriums indicate, bring or maintain stability and predictability in the politics of mine action. Hence, those who have the ability to shape or influence the mine action politics or policy should aim as much as possible to create a political climate in respect with this straightforward equilibrium principle in order to avoid unwelcome political volatility or stalemate positions.

B. Bayesian equilibrium

Typical for the politics of mine action are the elements of *incomplete* and *imperfect* information on the *state of the world and the other actors*. Both aspects will be addressed in a recurrent manner and how the different actors will not have complete and perfect knowledge on all possible strategic choices and payoffs of the other actors. Relating back to the previous rejection of a *Consistent Alignment of Beliefs* requires some early expansion on how *incomplete* and *imperfect* information impacts equilibriums or solution concepts. This necessitates the introduction of *Bayes' Theorem*. Bayes successfully incorporated conditional probabilities on the state of the world, hence, a welcome game theoretic addition whenever probability theory is considered.⁵⁵

In a *non-Bayesian* game, a strategy profile is a Nash equilibrium if there is no strategy that a player could play that would yield a higher payoff, given all the strategies played by the other players. In a Bayesian game, the additional element refers to information about the payoffs of the other players being incomplete. At least one player is unsure of the type - and so the payoffs function - of another player. Hence, such games are called *Bayesian* because of the probabilistic analysis inherent to the game. The lack of information held by players and modelling of beliefs implies additional *risk* when strategic choices need to be made. Given their beliefs about the other players and the state of the world, rational players are, however, still seeking to maximize their expected payoff, whether players are modelled as risk-neutral, risk averse or risk acceptant.⁵⁶

This could become an important element for the game theoretic analysis of the politics of mine action since mine action takes place in a very complex environment with several largely unpredictable elements: limited information on landmine threats, unpredictable interactions of the local population with their affected environment, volatile security environment and uncertain resource mobilisation, to name a few. For example, State authorities interacting with a mine-affected environment can be described as a State actor interacting with what it believes to be the “*state of the world*” of this mine-affected environment. Game theoretic characteristics can be allocated to describe the interdependency between both. More and better information will influence the *beliefs of State actors* and favourably constrain and stabilize the subjective perception or beliefs regarding the landmine impact by a State actor. Additional observations and deductions will follow when analysing, amongst others, the threat and risk aspects of the landmine impact.

I.1.6. Criteria formulation

A. Converging principles of expected utility and criteria selection

Utility theory is extensively applied in economics but also provides the mathematical backbone of game theory. The first important use of expected utility theory was that of founding fathers John von Neumann and Oskar Morgenstern, who used the assumption of anticipated or expected utility maximization in their formulation of game theory. The purpose of naming it *expected* utility stems from it being considered the best prescriptive theory for decisions under risk.

“Game theory is based on utility theory, a simple mathematical theory for representing decisions. In utility theory, we assume that actors are faced with choices from a set of available actions. Each action provides a probability of producing each possible outcome. Utility is a measure of an actor’s preferences over the outcomes that reflect his or her willingness to take risks to achieve desired outcomes and avoid undesirable outcomes.”⁵⁷

⁵⁵ FINK, E. C., GATES, S., and HUMES, B. D. (1998). *Game Theory Topics: Incomplete Information, Repeated Games, and n-player Games*, California: Sage University Papers Series on Quantitative Applications in the Social Sciences, 07-122., p. 9

⁵⁶ This will be extensively discussed when addressing threats and risks related to landmines, allocation of resources and decision-making.

⁵⁷ MORROW, J. (1994). *Game Theory for Political Scientists*, New Jersey: Princeton, p.17

A selected set of goals and indicators will assist the formulation of a comprehensive set of criteria related to the politics and policy of mine action. Hence, before addressing the specifics of the UN resolution on assistance in mine action, it is important to have a clear understanding of the hierarchic concept of goals, targets and indicators and some thoughts on how representative criteria or attributes could be best derived. Quite often confusion is created through an unclear distinction or even mixing up of criteria, targets or benchmarks with goals. Relying on familiar situations, such as traffic regulations, facilitates the clarification of the important distinctions. For example, the goal of traffic regulations is to enhance safety and effective usage of the road network. Possible targets are set through numerically limiting the amount of traffic violations and traffic accidents. Indicators such as traffic speed, number of traffic violations, number of accidents, etc. are needed to keep track of traffic safety. With a problem of unsafe driving on the road network, possible actions could entail higher fines as a remedy to change risk behaviour and reduce the number of traffic violations. Other possible ways and means is to lower legal speed limits and/or improve the condition of road networks.

What could be an acceptable methodology to deduct criteria from such a simplified example? The answer on this question highly depends on future modelling purposes and the specifics of the decision-making process it should support or inform. Hence, to continue the previous example, a model which informs the prioritization of necessary improvements of the road network will require different criteria than a decision-making process related to improving compliance with traffic regulations. Criteria in the first case could involve the absence or presence of speed bumps, number of traffic lanes, roundabouts, etc. In the second case the number of police patrols, the level of fines, frequency of drinking and driving, could prioritize or guide decision-making to enhance the functioning of the traffic police corps. Both models could have specific criteria in common, like the number of recent traffic accidents. It is however obvious that the choice of criteria will be driven by the general orientation and objective of the decision-making process, which in a rational context should focus on the highest utility it can obtain through making an optimal decision. In sum, this utility maximization or optimization principle will inevitably become a central theme throughout the remainder of the study.

B. Pragmatic applications for the politics of mine action: cardinal versus ordinal utility functions

Utility functions can be either *cardinal* or *ordinal*. Depending on the quality and type of data available, this dissertation will use both. This will be illustrated throughout the analysis and especially during the case-study of Afghanistan. Since modelling is envisaged, a set of cardinal utility functions will require a set of criteria or indicators based on sufficiently accurate data. Consecutively, utility functions can be developed with directly comparable numerical scores which can be used for *preference ranking*. The numerical score for each mine action attribute represents the utility of this attribute. For instance, a utility of 10 units towards clearing 1 sq km of fertile farmland is twice as desirable as clearing 1 sq km of grazing area with a utility level of 5 units. In order to achieve credible normative modelling as envisaged in this dissertation, the concept of criteria and (performance) indicators must be directly related to the politics of mine action and the utility of mine action activities. If criteria are deducted that do not relate in the first order to the impact of the problem, then the relevancy to include them in normative modelling needs to be carefully assessed. This is for example the case when considering quantifiable mine action benefits related to the number of landmines or square kilometres cleared. As the factor analysis has a normative aspect, so does the modelling. The search for suitable criteria must, therefore, support a modelling effort, which can provide an objective normative preference for decision-making, which, as highlighted before, may be quite different from what n-players perceive as a best response to the landmine problem.

In the *ordinal* case, the magnitude of the utilities or scores is not important. Only the ordering of the choices as implied by their utilities matters. For example, a utility of 10 units allocated to clearing 1 sq km of farmland and a utility level of 5 units for clearing 1 sq km of grazing land simply state that clearing farmland is preferred to clearing grazing land, but it cannot be argued that clearing farmland is twice as desirable as clearing grazing land. Within this setting, it is important to note that an ordinal utility function is not unique, since any monotonic increase of an ordinal utility function will still provide the same ordering for the choices.

In sum, the selection of criteria is submitted to individual assessments and perception of a certain mine-affected region. It is further complicated by the different importance one attaches to the criteria or the different set of weights allocated to criteria. For the initial process of developing a list of applicable mine action criteria and suitable indicators, the “*Performance Monitoring and Evaluation Tips*” of US AID provide sufficient guidance:⁵⁸

- (1) *Direct* – avoid secondary indicators like the “numbers of mines cleared” as they do not directly relate to landmine impact reduction.
- (2) *Objective* – exclude ambiguity or subjective appreciations of real world landmine problems.
- (3) *Adequate* – avoiding using too many indicators in order to manage data effectively.
- (4) *Quantitative* – where possible, numerical precision on the landmine problem will lead to a better common understanding.
- (5) *Aggregated/disaggregated* – by mine-affected geographic area, environmental conditions, gender, age, activity.
- (6) *Practical* – if data can be obtained at a reasonable effort and/or cost.
- (7) *Reliable* – suitable for statistical analysis and prediction, in particular with human cost data.

⁵⁸ Selecting Performance Indicators, Performance Monitoring and Evaluation Tips, 1996, Number 6, US AID Centre for Development Information and Evaluation, Internet. Available at http://pdf.usaid.gov/pdf_docs/PNABY214.pdf, accessed on 3 January 2005

II.2. Analysis of the Resolution “Assistance in mine action”- 58th General Assembly

II.2.1 Historic background

A. Overview of United Nations Resolutions related to mine action

Apart from conventions, there are provisions in humanitarian law and several other UN resolutions addressing the problem of landmines. Those UN resolutions can be subdivided in country-specific resolutions and thematic or generic ones. There are numerous country-related UN resolutions⁵⁹ referring to landmine problems but only three *thematic* ones. The majority of the country related resolutions are decided or adopted by the UN Security Council within the context of international peace and security, whilst the thematic resolutions are passed through the General Assembly.

The oldest thematic resolution is related to the Convention on Certain Conventional Weapons (CCW). This resolution was initially aimed at convening a review conference on the 1980 Convention. Hence, this originated Protocol II of the CCW on mines, booby traps and other devices. The resolution addressing “*Assistance in mine action*” was the second generic resolution to be introduced to the annual UN agenda. The third and most recent one is the UN resolution in support of the Mine Ban Treaty, which replaced a preceding UN resolution aimed at establishing a moratorium on the export of anti-personnel mines.

B. Introduction of the Resolution by the European Community under Belgian Presidency

In 1993, the then twelve Member States of the European Community (EC) requested through the EC Presidency the introduction of a new item on the agenda of the forty-eighth session of the General Assembly entitled “*Assistance in mine clearance*”, which would later change to “*Assistance in mine action*”. Since this introduction, the resolution has been a recurrent UN agenda item.⁶⁰ Belgium held the EC Presidency in the second semester of 1993. Earlier that year, the Belgian government⁶¹ established a moratorium on the export of anti-personnel mines, the first nation to take the decisive step in establishing a national mine ban policy. Belgium, being proactive in this domain⁶², called for a specific UN resolution on assistance in mine clearance and provided a first draft proposal. Hence, the pioneer drafters of the text were aided by multiple actors of the UN Secretariat, in particular members of the so-called mine-clearing unit, several United Nations Agencies and the International Committee of the Red Cross. In 1993, a UN focal point for mine action had not yet established.

C. Envisaged strategic objectives of the Resolution

The resolution has evolved significantly since the 1993 version: even the title changed. However, after more than a decade of amendments, the initial objectives are still standing, namely:

- (1) increasing public awareness;

⁵⁹ In particular for heavily affected countries such as Afghanistan, Sudan, Cambodia, etc.

⁶⁰ Each year the UN Member States agree upon the agenda before the General Assembly session, traditionally starting the third week of September. In 2005, the resolution proposed to bi-annualize its incorporation in the UN Agenda, in support of the revitalization of the work of the United Nations.

⁶¹ Belgium had already played a decisive role in the global movement to ban antipersonnel landmines since the early 1990's. In 1993, the Belgian Network of the International Campaign to Ban Landmines (ICBL) was created and started to rally public opinion in support of a ban. The 1993 export moratorium was superseded by national legislation in 1995 which modifies the law of 3 January 1933 relating to the manufacturing, trade and carrying of firearms and the trade of ammunition. Internet. Landmine Monitor Report 1999, available at <http://www.icbl.org/lm>, accessed on 10 February 2004

⁶² Belgium chaired three times the negotiations on the resolution (most frequent of all EU Members): in 1993, 2001 and 2002. In 2002, Belgium chaired the process on request of the Danish EU Presidency.

- (2) asking the United Nations for coordination of the assistance;⁶³
- (3) making reference to legal instruments;
- (4) underlining the inclusion of mine clearance in several peace-keeping operations;⁶⁴
- (5) addressing the socio-economic impact of landmines; and,
- (6) requesting the assistance of UN Member States in providing the necessary information to the UN Secretary-General.⁶⁵

II.2.2. United Nations rules, procedures and timeframes

A. Impact of UN rules on the political process

The basic criterion is to have a draft resolution ready to table at the UN Secretariat by mid-November. This allows sufficient time for the translation and adoption of the resolution before closure of the regular session of the General Assembly. To respect this timeline the debate generally starts in September, which initially takes place as a closed EU meeting.⁶⁶ Via COREU⁶⁷ exchange and CODUN⁶⁸ meetings, a first agreement on a draft proposal is reached amongst EU Member States. The next step is the presentation of the draft text to the broader co-sponsors community of last year's resolution. In varying degrees, the delegations in New York can contribute to this drafting exercise, pending on their expertise. A high degree of EU-coordination and participation through their respective national Permanent Missions in New York can intensify the informal debate significantly because of the higher degree of engagement and knowledge of the New York based diplomats and military advisers.

In October, the General Debate and Thematic Discussions of the UN First Committee on Disarmament and International Security take place. This includes negotiations on the other two thematic resolutions: the UN resolution on the Mine Ban Treaty and the Convention on certain Conventional Weapons. Amongst many other First Committee resolutions, taking action⁶⁹ on those two resolutions takes place at the beginning of November, at the end of the session of the First Committee. Hence, after these discussions the *open-ended*⁷⁰ negotiations on the resolution assistance in mine action generally start.⁷¹ This implies that November is generally the timeframe during which the open-ended negotiations or informal meetings take place. From then on the meetings are open to all UN Member States and UN Agencies involved with mine action. The Agencies participate in an *advisory capacity*, a considerably weaker bargaining position, as they theoretically cannot intervene, except on request of a UN Member State.

The intricate set of UN rules and procedures is typical for the renowned heavy bureaucracy of the UN system and can complicate the consensus process; also, there is a pressing time factor involved. The analysis of the preamble paragraphs will illustrate how this influences the politics. The lack of preparation time or experience of UN Member States' delegates for such highly technical disarmament issues as mine action, both in their participatory role or chairing capacity,

⁶³ This was stipulated in preamble paragraph 6 of UNGA Res/48/7 (27 October 1993): "Considering that, in addition to the responsibilities incumbent upon States, there is scope for the United Nations to strengthen its contribution to the solution of problems relating to mine clearance." And in operative paragraph 2: "Stresses the importance of coordination by the United Nations of activities, including those by regional organizations, related to mine clearance, in particular those activities relating to information and training with a view to improving the effectiveness of operations in the field.

⁶⁴ Belgium lost UN peacekeeping soldiers due to mine accidents in 1993.

⁶⁵ The UN Secretary-General is institutionally responsible for the comprehensive UN report on the problems caused by the presence of mines and other unexploded devices.

⁶⁶ "Closed meeting" implies only EU members can take part in the debate, discuss the first draft and formulate amendment proposals.

⁶⁷ COREU stands for European Correspondence, a telex network linking the foreign ministries of the Member States.

⁶⁸ CODUN stands for "Cooperation on Disarmament in the UN System"; these meetings take place in Brussels.

⁶⁹ Taking action is the jargon used to indicate that either a *voting* is taking place on a resolution or an *adoption by consensus*.

⁷⁰ Contrary to the exclusiveness of the "closed" session, the "open-ended" session is inclusive towards all UN Member States and UN Agencies dealing with mine action or one of its related activities.

⁷¹ This is due to the workload of national delegates related to the session of the First Committee.

could further hinder effective politics and policy making. This makes the process also more vulnerable to criticism, especially from NGOs. When addressing the relevant preamble paragraphs on coordination and cooperation, the increasing influence NGOs try to exert on the United Nations and Member States will be further analysed.

B. The importance of the UN Report on assistance in mine action

There are a number of recurrent activities on landmine issues at UN Headquarters: the UN report, General Assembly Debate, UN resolutions and the activities in the First Committee on Disarmament and International Security. Around September, the UN Secretary-General's bi-annual report⁷² on assistance in mine action is published. The latter is an important document since it is indicative for the policy, strategy and activities of the UN within this domain. Certain delegations⁷³ attach sufficient significance to the report to preclude the provision of comments or amendment proposals on the draft resolution until their respective capitals consult the report and instruct diplomats accordingly. The Secretary-General's report is also the cornerstone for the Annual General Assembly plenary session on assistance in mine action. Traditionally, this two day General Assembly (plenary) session takes place well ahead of the adoption of the mine action resolution.

C. Alliance formations: from Sponsors to co-Sponsors, to non-sponsoring UN Member States

After the EU internally agrees the initial draft, the proposal is presented to the broader group of co-sponsoring UN Member States of last year's version of the resolution. Although the text is still negotiated amongst mine action supporting UN Member States, more significant concessions on the draft become possible.⁷⁴ For all clarity, *sponsors* are those countries, in this case the EU Member States, which introduced the resolution as an agenda item whilst *co-sponsors* are those UN Member States which formalize their support through subscribing and signing a co-sponsors list in the final stage of the negotiations. This act expresses their political support through an explicit approval of the objectives of the draft resolution before it is submitted for adoption (without a vote) to the General Assembly. Those States that do not sign the list are either indifferent to the resolution or do not explicitly support the resolution's language. States who are critical towards the resolution generally participate in the open-ended negotiations through either the formulation of objections to the draft proposal and/or the introduction of compromise language. Even during the adoption of the resolution in the General Assembly, UN Member States have the right to explain "their vote", which is virtual in case of consensus, thereby offering another opportunity of expressing either support or opposition towards the UN resolution.

In summary, this political debate is characterized by an expansion through three stages: first amongst sponsors, then including co-sponsors, and finally other non-sponsor UN Member States, including those having a conflict of interest or opposing the objectives of the resolution. Each of these stages brings with it some specific alliance formations and dynamics. This requires to be studied within the context of *repetitive game theory with n-players*, including issues of varying levels of cooperation and even competition or polarization between political alliances of UN Member States.

⁷² It used to be an annual report until 2004. See for the last version the A/59/284 Report of the Secretary-General to the General Assembly on Assistance in Mine Action of 20 August 2004.

⁷³ In particular those nations (e.g. Egypt, India, Pakistan, Cuba, etc.) which are of the opinion that the current UN policy on mine action does not address properly their mine action needs or concerns.

⁷⁴ Certain countries belonging to the Non-Aligned Movement (NAM) are regular co-sponsors of this resolution and sometimes fulfil a bridging or mediating function with other NAM countries which are non-supportive towards mine action. Examples are South-Africa, Jordan and Mexico; three UN Member States which adhere also strongly to the Anti-Personnel Mine Ban Convention.

II.2.3. Normative and Game Theoretic Analysis of the Preamble Paragraphs

What follows is the breakdown of the 22 *preamble paragraphs* of the UN resolution on assistance in mine action; each of the paragraphs is explained and analyzed for its direct relevance to the research aim and objectives. Most of the paragraphs key issues are indicated in red.

Owing to the anticipated differences in normative value of each preamble paragraph and game theoretic complexity, the depth and length of the analysis of the different paragraphs will vary significantly. Extensive analysis will be provided for the paragraphs dealing with the game theoretic and political aspects of consensus building, cooperation, coordination, compliance and contribution in the field of mine action. The analysis of the politics of mine action will be often a variation of similar game theoretic aspects of cooperation and compliance. Especially the first applicable preamble paragraphs need, therefore, to be comprehensively addressed with a gradual refinement of the game theoretic aspects throughout the analysis.

A. Preamble Paragraph 1: Adoption without a vote or politics by consensus

Recalling its resolution 57/159 of 16 December 2002 and all its previous resolutions on assistance in mine clearance and mine action, all adopted without a vote,

a. Analysis

1. Previous UN resolutions; from assistance in *mine clearance* to *mine action*

According to UN standards and formats, the first preamble paragraph recalls all preceding or directly related resolutions. In previous versions, the references to former resolutions⁷⁵ were listed in a detailed manner in this first paragraph but are now captured into one general reference to the resolutions: “*Assistance in mine clearance*” (1993-97) and since 1998 “*Assistance in mine action*”. The title of the resolution was subject to change as a logic result of the more holistic approach towards the global landmine problem. Conversely, the name change of the resolution from mine clearance towards mine action has since 1998 significantly complicated its adoptions without a vote. Owing to the inclusion of *advocacy for a total ban* on anti-personnel landmines, the political incentives or game theoretic payoff structures have inevitably undergone some changes. Especially non-signatories of the Mine Ban Treaty and/or the CCW try to slow down or even reverse terminology which is too progressive towards a total ban or contradicting their national security requirements and/or military doctrines. This is obviously a strategic and high politics issue and has considerably changed the dynamics of the consensus process.

More concretely, those nations who are against a total ban have interpreted the extension from mine clearance to mine action as an almost covert manner to reinforce the norm building in line with the Mine Ban Treaty. Some mine-affected countries⁷⁶ are increasingly concerned about the diverging influence this holistic policy may have on the funding of mine action projects compared to the former single funding requirements for mine clearance. This is all the more complicated for those countries where landmines are still used for national security and other military purposes.

⁷⁵ UN Resolutions; according to the respective GA session: 48/7 of 19 October 1993, 49/215 of 23 December 1994, 50/82 of 14 December 1995, 51/149 of 13 December 1996 and 52/173 of 18 December 1997, on assistance in mine clearance, and UN resolutions on assistance in mine clearance: 53/26 of 17 November 1998, 54/191 of 17 December 1999, 55/120 of 6 December 2000, 56/219 of 21 December 2001, 57/28, Internet. Available from <http://www.un.org/documents/resga.htm>, accessed on Oct 2004

⁷⁶ Especially Egypt has been a front runner to keep the focus on mine clearance, reinforced by the absence of funding or support from the International Community, especially by the World War II aggressors such as Germany and Italy, which contaminated Egypt with large amount of mines.

In addition, since 2002, significant pressure has been exerted by NGOs, in particular through the “International Campaign to Ban Landmines” (ICBL), to either significantly amend the UN resolution or re-title it to reflect its current state.

“Generally speaking, as currently written, the draft resolution is focused on support for UN Mine Action Service activities, not “*Assistance in mine action*” generally, as it is titled. The resolution should ideally be amended to be a true resolution on global assistance in mine action, particularly since the majority of operational mine clearance is done by national players, along with international Humanitarian Mine Action (HMA), NGOs and commercial operators. The UNMAS Mine Action Coordination Centres engage primarily, if not exclusively, in coordination activities, which is also important, if well done. If significant changes are not made to the existing draft, the resolution should be re-titled to “*UN System Assistance in Mine Action Coordination*”.”⁷⁷

In 2003, even more widespread ICBL lobbying took place, however, this time seeking support through States Parties of the Mine Ban Treaty.⁷⁸ More explicit arguments were used to motivate the EU presidency to give ample consideration to their proposed amendments and/or name change of the resolution. This lobbying process is very much interwoven with allusions that the global landmine problem, norm building and dynamics of a global ban are not well understood by representatives or government officials in New York, thereby indicating a *disconnect between the high and low politics*. ICBL also exploits somewhat this opportunity to criticize the strategic – and in their view too heavy-handed role of the UN in mine action. This is an interesting game theoretic aspect of *incomplete information*, whereby actors are perceived to have a significant lack of understanding what the most desired strategy of the other player(s) would or should be. The assumed disconnect and lack of information is further aggravated through what certain non-State actors perceive as insufficient broad-based consultations. It illustrates at this early stage the differing views on mine action between State actors and NGOs under the umbrella of ICBL.

“Frankly speaking, we are most disappointed that very few of our recommendations put forth last year [2002] have been incorporated into this year’s draft of the Resolution, nor were we consulted to be able to offer our input at an earlier date.”⁷⁹

2. The “art” or “tyranny” of consensus building?

Since its first introduction, this resolution has been invariably aspired as the outcome of a consensus process, called an *adoption without a vote*. Conversely, the other two thematic resolutions⁸⁰ related to mine action or landmines have been consistently adopted by a vote in the United Nations Disarmament Committee (First Committee), and consecutively adopted by a vote in the General Assembly. The resolution on assistance in mine action also differs in the sense that it has been a plenary resolution for over a decade, not subject to prior discussions in one of the UN Committees. Containing both humanitarian and disarmament issues, it cannot be categorized as a First Committee or as a Third Committee (Social, Humanitarian and Cultural issues) agenda item, but rather a mixture of both. Nowadays, as part of the UN revitalization efforts, the resolution is negotiated in the Fourth Committee.⁸¹

⁷⁷ Fax and E-mail of the Chair of the Mine Action Working Group of the International Campaign to ban Landmines (ICBL) regarding the draft UNGA Resolution on Assistance in Mine Action to the Deputy Permanent Representative of the Permanent Mission of Denmark, 22 November 2002.

⁷⁸ The following Permanent Missions to the United Nations were addressed: the Members of the European Union, Afghanistan, Angola, Cambodia, Canada, Mexico, Mozambique, Nicaragua, Norway, Peru, Thailand and South Africa, and the United Nations Mine Action Service.

⁷⁹ Fax and E-mail of the Chair of the Mine Action Working Group of the International Campaign to ban Landmines (ICBL) regarding the draft UNGA Resolution on Assistance in Mine Action to the Deputy Permanent Representative of the Permanent Mission of Denmark, 22 November 2002.

⁸⁰ The UN resolution in support of the Mine Ban Treaty and the Convention on certain Conventional Weapons.

⁸¹ UN - the Fourth Committee looks into special political matters and decolonization, has incorporated disarmament agenda items in light of the revitalization of the work of the General Assembly

Gaining consensus or adoption without a vote significantly adds to the “*moral weight*” of UN resolutions. This is as much applicable for UN resolutions processed and adopted without a vote through the UN General Assembly as resolutions voted through the UN Security Council, the latter legally binding. It is more apparent when higher political nuclear non proliferation issues are at stake such as with North Korea.

“This action by the United Nations, which was swift and tough, says that we are united in our determination to see to it that the Korea Peninsula is nuclear weapons free, Bush told reporters. The UN Security Council voted 15-0 to impose financial and arms sanctions on North Korea to punish the reclusive Communist nation for its reported nuclear weapon test.”⁸²

While the decisions or resolutions of the Assembly have no legal binding force for Governments, they carry the weight of world opinion on major international issues, as well as the moral authority of the world community. Consequently, the sponsors and co-sponsors’ strategic objective is to avoid a vote in the General Assembly as it symbolizes global unity and bears the moral strength of a Security Council resolution which has been adopted unanimously. Taking into account the views of non-supportive States therefore implies the acceptance of compromise language and multiple rounds of negotiations. Losing the consensus could also imply a weaker position of the UN Mine Action Service within the UN system. In any case, it would considerably lower the common payoff of a globally negotiated consensus outcome. This principle tends to influence significantly the bargaining dynamics of supporting UN Member States versus those opposing the current policies, with increasing polarization on the most controversial mine action issues.

During the 2004 General Assembly session, no consensus was reached, due primarily to the diplomatic actions of one State actor, Egypt. In-depth analysis of this remarkable fact is required as it will likely provide significant explanatory value regarding the high politics of mine action. It illustrates how one nation can stall the whole consensus process, regardless how strong the views are of all the other UN Member States. This is particularly noteworthy in a game theoretic context whereby a single nation can oppose a strong alliance and force them to compromise in order to save the consensus. This phenomenon has been described in a broader context by Jody Williams, who received the Nobel Peace Prize with the International Campaign to Ban Landmines, as the “*tyranny of consensus*”. It depicts the legacy of obsolete UN group structures that constrain cooperation by allowing defectors to bully would-be co-operators behind closed doors.⁸³

This phenomenon is also an interesting variant of “*power politics*”⁸⁴, whereby individual States can go against broad-based norm building and protect their own interests by threatening the consensus. The military threats or sanctions derived from the traditional power politics are well-known. This type of political pressure however, borders on political blackmailing and adds a more subtle dimension. One tactic in the game is for one State to signal convincingly their intentions before any consensus negotiations would even begin. This tactic corresponds to the previous discussed aspects regarding the *beliefs* of the actors involved.⁸⁵ For example, if one State were to ostentatiously and publicly disagree with the draft proposal of the resolution, the chair and co-sponsors would be compelled to have a less aggressive or progressive approach. This is a tactic which can be observed with most strategic disarmament issues, from Cold War main events, e.g. the Cuba missile crisis, to recent stand-off positions of North Korea and Iran.

“The statements from the negotiators and the Iranian president continue a pattern of past months, in which Ahmadinejad publicly states a hard-line position of no compromise, often in front of large crowds, even as

⁸² No author mentioned. (2006,14 October). *Bush: UN action on N. Korea "swift and tough"*, Internet. Available from <http://today.reuters.com>, accessed on 14 October 2006

⁸³ BORRIE, J. (2006). Cooperation and Defection in the Conference on Disarmament. *Disarmament Diplomacy*, Issue No. 82

⁸⁴ Derived from the German term: *Machtpolitik*.

⁸⁵ See page 23-25 for the assessment on Consistent Alignment of Beliefs and Bayesian Equilibriums.

Iran's negotiators try to reach deals behind the scenes. The Iranians appear to be *gambling* that even the hint of progress will blunt any push for UN sanctions.”⁸⁶

Fortunately there are many occasions where effective alliance formations between States and non-State actors have achieved remarkable progress in mine action. Through an overwhelming support of a high number of UN Member States, nations have been singled out before. Amendments or proposals have been blocked that were regarded as unacceptable by the EU Member States and other co-sponsors of the resolution. Different from Cold War thinking, the following contextual game theoretic view tends to be applicable.

“Life is not simply a question of the strong doing what they have the means to do and the weak accepting what they have to. Over time, the weak can, through their concerted and self-interested action, affect the behaviour even of the most powerful by modifying the pay-off structures in which cooperation and defection occur. This is something that because of the peculiar conditions of the Cold War, its theoreticians failed to recognise.”⁸⁷

Though this may not have changed the military doctrines of the larger armed forces in the world, it is through persistent mine action advocacy and norm building processes that alliances of those perceived as “weaker” States have achieved remarkable results. Hence, consensus building can be both an art and tyrannical process, depending on the political manoeuvring of its actors.

3. Obtaining consensus: a “game”?

As addressed, UN Member States will form alliances during the negotiations, especially due to the phasing (first negotiations amongst (1) sponsors, then with (2) co-sponsors and finally with (3) non-sponsors) of the debate. For explanatory purposes, the real world multilateral n-player dimension will be initially reduced to two main players or in this case two alliances: Alliance 1, the (co)sponsors; and Alliance 2, the non-sponsors. Alliance 1 is supportive and progressive, Alliance 2 is not or selective in its support. Alliance 1 is in support of the Mine Ban Treaty or a total ban, Alliance 2 is not. That is why both alliances have conflicts of interest or strongly diverging views on assistance in mine action. Alliance 1 can to a large extent be associated with the EU and the EU Presidency chairing the negotiations. Hence, the analysis will frequently associate Alliance 1 with the EU Chair.

Having addressed the main negotiation characteristics on assistance in mine action, the analysis below will seek first a traditional game theoretic fit to simplify and explain the politics involved in obtaining a consensus resolution. The three classics: (1) *Zero-Sum*, (2) *Prisoners Dilemma* and (3) *Chicken* game are selected for this initial assessment. This is not an intuitive choice but a logic one, based on the broad game theoretic coverage they offer.

“There are three particular games [chicken, zero-sum and the prisoners’ dilemma games] that have been extensively discussed in game theory and which have fascinated social scientists. The reason is simple: they appear to capture some of the elemental features of all social interactions. They can be found both within existing familiar “structures” and plausibly in “states of nature”. Thus the analysis of these games promises to test the claims of individualists. In other words, how much can be said about the outcome of these games will tell us much about how much of the social world can be explained in instrumentally rational, individualist terms.”⁸⁸

⁸⁶ ALI AKBAR DAREINI.(2006, 28 September). *Iran head unwavering on nuclear position*, Associated Press Writer, Internet. Available from www.iranmania.com, accessed on 28 September 2006

⁸⁷ BORRIE, J. (2006). Cooperation and Defection in the Conference on Disarmament. *Disarmament Diplomacy*, Issue No. 82, Cooperation and Defection in the Conference on Disarmament

⁸⁸ HEAP S., and VAROUFAKIS, Y., (1995), *Game Theory: A critical introduction*, London, p.35

4. Seeking a game theoretic fit

(1) *Zero-sum game*. Obviously the consensus debate on mine action does not exhibit the characteristics of a *zero-sum game* as there is no pure competition, or everything won by one alliance is not lost by the other alliance. The common payoffs will be greater when both alliances work together and achieve consensus on the resolution or serve each other's interests. The assumption of diametrically opposed interests in zero-sum games oversimplifies the real world situation, in which conflict of interests and interdependency take on many different formats. The effort of game theoretic modelling should first and foremost explain in an understandable way the different dynamics of consensus building, without trivializing the effort:

“Two-person, zero-sum games are poor models of most social phenomena. Almost all interesting social phenomena create mixed motives for the parties involved. There are very few situations in which two actors have directly opposed interests – perhaps only candidate competition and the military manoeuvres of warfare.”⁸⁹

(2) *Non-zero-sum game*. Neither does the political process exhibit the characteristics of a non-zero-sum game; or more particular a *Prisoner's Dilemma* (PD).⁹⁰ In this game, as omnipresent in game theory, the main or only concern of each individual player is trying to maximize his own (political) advantage, without any particular concern for the well-being of the other players. In a *one-shot* prisoner's dilemma⁹¹, cooperating is therefore strictly dominated by defecting. Hence, the only possible equilibrium for a one-shot PD game is for alliances to defect. In simpler terms, no matter what the other alliance does, one alliance will always gain a greater payoff by playing defect. Since in any situation playing defect is more beneficial than cooperating, all rational players will play defect as there is no unilateral benefit to cooperate. Again, this is obviously not a suitable game theoretic fit taking into account the upfront intention of UN Member States to achieve consensus and to profusely convince “rebellious” states not to bluntly defect in their efforts through systematically seeking the highest payoffs. This further suggests a subtle interpretation of the game theoretic assumption on common knowledge of rationality or decision-making according to the maximization of expected utilities or payoffs.

(3) *Chicken game*. A formal version of the *game of chicken* has been the subject of serious research in game theory with many different political applications whenever there is a mixture of conflict and cooperation. It is another type of non-zero-sum game, but in this particular setting of converging and conflicting interests better suited to explain the interaction between States. With the other game theoretic non-fits eliminated, the advanced analysis below will focus on the behaviour of States in a *two-alliance game of chicken*. The classic form of a chicken game is well known from the famous movie “*Rebel without a Cause*” where two men have agreed to settle their difference by staging a race with their cars toward a cliff. The one who jumps first will have to carry the stigmatizing title of “*chickie*”, waiting too long results in driving off the cliff to a certain death. Because the “loss” of swerving is so trivial compared to the crash that occurs if nobody swerves, the reasonable strategy for both alliances would seem to be to swerve before a crash is likely. Yet, knowing

⁸⁹ MORROW, J. (1994). *Game Theory for Political Scientists*, New Jersey: Princeton, p.75

⁹⁰ The Prisoners Dilemma has been traditionally illustrated through two suspects, A and B, arrested by the police. The police have insufficient evidence for a conviction and, having separated both prisoners, visit each of them to offer the same deal: if one testifies for the prosecution against the other and the other remains silent, the betrayer goes free and the silent accomplice receives the full 10-year sentence. If both stay silent, the police can sentence both prisoners to only six months in jail for a minor charge. If each betrays the other, each will receive a two-year sentence. Each prisoner must make the choice of whether to betray the other or to remain silent. However, neither prisoner knows for sure what choice the other prisoner will make. So the question this dilemma poses is: What will happen? How will the prisoners act?

⁹¹ One shot implies a game capturing only one event without an evolutionary or learning process, contrary to repeated or infinite games.

this, if one alliance believes the other alliance to be reasonable, then this alliance may well decide not to swerve at all, in the belief that the other alliance will be rational and decide to swerve, leaving the other player or alliance to obtain the highest payoffs.

5. Available strategic choices

In this simplified case, the previous generically addressed assumptions are further materialized. Hence, it is assumed that each alliance acts in a rational manner to achieve the adoption of the resolution without a vote. As such, each alliance has the choice between two strategic choices regarding the negotiations on the controversial elements or progressive language of a new draft version of the UN resolution: (1) *to compromise*⁹² with the other alliance or (2) *not to compromise*. These two strategic choices are known to both alliances, with a set of expected payoffs broadly understood by the actors. Thus, both alliances possess common knowledge regarding the rational structure of the game, which is inherent to effective functioning of UN Member States within the United Nations System.⁹³ Obviously, there will be new elements in a draft resolution which do not require a debate as they are immediately accepted by both alliances. Those common interest issues which are swiftly or automatically agreed are not considered since they do not really constitute a debate or present any of the game theoretic characteristics discussed.

6. Ordinal utility approach

If an ordinal utility approach is taken regarding the payoff structure of possible *compromising* versus *non-compromising* choices, then the payoffs can be reflected - for clarity in distinct colours - according to the following game theoretic modelling:

		Alliance 2	
		Compromise	Not Compromise
Alliance 1 (EU+ co-Sponsors)	Compromise	2,2 (win, win)	1,3 (lose, win most)
	Not compromise	3,1 (win most, lose)	0,0 (lose most, lose most)

Matrix II.1: Strategic form of the consensus game with ordinal payoffs

The strategic form in matrix II.1 explains how the most preferred choice of each alliance is for apparent reasons not to compromise in defence of its own political position or views it has on mine action issues, for example, the UN mine action policy or strategy. This can be illustrated through allocating the highest ordinal payoff (3) to the most preferred strategic choice. On the other hand, if both alliances are persistent in their non-compromising stance, then this might result in the stalling of the consensus process, or worse, no UN resolution at all. Alliance 2 risks to be stigmatized through “*name & shame*” for being non-supportive to the humanitarian cause of assistance in mine action. In game theory the term *audience cost* is often used instead and will be further discussed at a later stage. Both alliances lose most through lack of compromise, the least preferred outcome, which is reflected through allocating to this choice the lowest payoff (0,0) for both alliances. A timely anticipation of losing the consensus can avoid this situation or stalemate. Both alliances can either improve their payoffs if one alliance accepts to compromise as a last resort choice, given a payoff of 1, or, based on the threat of losing the consensus, convincing the other alliance to compromise as well and accept a payoff of 2 for both alliances. A closer study of the

⁹² Compromising actors occupy a sort of midpoint between the assertive and cooperative actors, they are willing to give up something and find a middle ground for the sake of “keeping the peace” compromising actors like negotiation, trade-offs, deals and comfortable solutions, ELLIS, D. (1994). *Small Group Decision-making; Communication and the Group Process*, New York, p.238

⁹³ The term ‘United Nations System’ encompasses the United Nations Organization, Agencies and UN Member States.

equilibriums will further add to the explanatory value of this game and its solution concepts; this is shown below.

7. Pure strategy equilibriums

Equilibriums are pure when they do not incorporate any probability factors. As explained, Nash equilibrium is a pair of strategies for which neither alliance gains by changing their own strategy while the other stays the same. If the above principle of a Nash equilibrium is applied in this game of chicken, then two pairs of *pure* Nash strategies of the chicken or *consensus game* can be deduced where neither alliance is willing to unilaterally change to another strategy:

(compromise ₁ ; not compromise ₂) (not compromise ₁ ; compromise ₂)
--

Those pure equilibriums are logical as the highest payoff (3) occurs when one alliance can obtain a compromise from the other alliance without having to compromise its own political position. Otherwise, after an alliance has compromised, changing its strategy to not compromise, with the other alliance maintaining its strategy of not compromising, reduces its payoff from 1 to 0. In other words, none of the alliances has an incentive to change its strategy if Alliance 1's current strategy is a best response to Alliance 2's strategy, and Alliance 2's strategy is a best response to Alliance 1's strategy. The reasoning for the two pure Nash equilibriums is however only applicable for a *one-shot chicken game* since it does not incorporate any dynamic or evolutionary element.

8. Mixed strategy equilibrium

The negotiations to obtain consensus on all the new draft elements in the resolution is, however, a repeated and sequential game. It would, therefore, ignore real world politics if only pure strategies are taken into consideration. This would only reflect a snapshot of the reality rather than a sequential political process. What happens if one alliance refuses each time to compromise in order to maximize its payoffs? This would lean closer towards a Prisoner's Dilemma, which was regarded as non-representative for the political dynamics in this case. Other, more sensible, enrichments of this game are, therefore, required to incorporate the evolutionary characteristics and elements such as the amount of information each alliance has concerning the strategy of the other alliance. Obviously, if Alliance 1 obtained information that Alliance 2 would easily compromise, Alliance 1 itself will hold back on compromising its position. Enriching the game with all these elements will naturally benefit the explanatory value of the game theoretic fit and equilibriums. It is, however, an exercise of balance between complication and simplification, whereby the following guidance will be applied.

“[Game theoretic] Modelling imposes discipline upon one's arguments; one must model to gain the benefits of this discipline. Many arguments in political science would profit from even the great simplification of basic models. Great technical proficiency is not needed to solve such models. However, some mathematics is necessary to solve game theory models.”⁹⁴

While it may be obvious how the above pure strategy equilibriums were developed, it may not be as obvious how to deduct the characteristics of a mixed strategy equilibrium, assuming they exist in this setting. The determination of an optimal mixed strategy continues to rest upon the assumption that rational States maximize their average *expected payoffs or utilities*, and thereby acknowledge the existence of a probability factor related to the choice of strategy. It logically

⁹⁴ MORROW, J. (1994). *Game Theory for Political Scientists*, New Jersey: Princeton, p.8

follows that the *expected* payoff is determined by summing the product of the payoff associated with each outcome and the probability that the respective outcome will occur.⁹⁵

The essence of determining a Nash mixed strategy equilibrium is to first find the probability factor where Alliance 1 is indifferent between the strategic choice “compromise” and “not compromise” in light of obtaining the consensus outcome. This is done by setting the *expected payoff or utility* of Alliance 1 (U_1) playing compromise equal to the expected payoff of Alliance 1 playing not compromise:

$$U_1 (\text{compromise}_1) = U_1 (\text{not compromise}_1)$$

Based on the (2,1) ordinal payoff or utility for Alliance 1 choosing to compromise when Alliance 2 either chooses to (compromise₂, not compromise₂), the probability factor can be defined as follows:

$$p \text{ is the probability that Alliance 2 chooses to } \textit{compromise}$$

$$(1-p) \text{ the probability that Alliance 2 chooses to } \textit{not compromise}$$

Then the expected payoff of Alliance 1 when choosing to compromise:

$$U_1 (\text{compromise}_1) = 2p+1(1-p)$$

$$U_1 (\text{compromise}_1) = 2p+1-p$$

$$U_1 (\text{compromise}_1) = p+1$$

And with (3,0) the payoff of Alliance 1 choosing to not compromise when Alliance 2 either chooses to (compromise₂, not compromise₂), the probability factor can be defined as follows:

$$U_1 (\text{not compromise}_1) = 3p+0(1-p)$$

$$U_1 (\text{not compromise}_1) = 3p$$

According to the methodology cited above, the probability parameters of a mixed strategy equilibrium can be determined as follows:

$$U_1 (\text{compromise}_1) = U_1 (\text{not compromise}_1)$$

$$p+1=3p$$

$$1=2p$$

$$p= \frac{1}{2}$$

This result in $p= \frac{1}{2}$ or a mixed strategy equilibrium where each alliance will choose to play “compromise” with a probability of $\frac{1}{2}$:

$$((\frac{1}{2} \text{ compromise}_1, \frac{1}{2} \text{ not compromise}_1); (\frac{1}{2} \text{ compromise}_2, \frac{1}{2} \text{ not compromise}_2))$$

To asses if this is a Nash equilibrium, the expected payoff of Alliance 1 needs to be examined given Alliance 2’s mixed strategy. Also the expected payoff for Alliance 1’s mixed strategy needs to be examined and then both of Alliance 1’s pure strategies:

$$U_1 (\frac{1}{2} \text{ compromise}_1, \frac{1}{2} \text{ not compromise}_1) = \frac{1}{2} [\frac{1}{2} (2)+ \frac{1}{2} (1)]+ \frac{1}{2} [\frac{1}{2} (3)+ \frac{1}{2} (0)]$$

$$U_1 (\frac{1}{2} \text{ compromise}_1, \frac{1}{2} \text{ not compromise}_1) = 2/4 + 1/4 + 3/4 = 6/4 = 3/2$$

$$\text{Compare this to: } U_1 (\text{compromise}_1) = \frac{1}{2} (2) + \frac{1}{2} (1) = 2/2 + 1/2 = 3/2$$

⁹⁵ Methodology derived from ZAGARE, F. (1984), *Game Theory – Concepts and Applications*, California: Sage University Papers Series, p.32

$$U_1(\text{not compromise}_1) = \frac{1}{2}(3) + \frac{1}{2}(0) = 3/2$$

This gives:

$$U_1\left(\frac{1}{2}\text{compromise}_1, \frac{1}{2}\text{not compromise}_1\right) = U_1(\text{not compromise}_1) = U_1(\text{compromise}_1)$$

This illustrates game theoretically Alliance 1 has no incentive or possible increase in payoff to move away from this mixed strategy, one whereby Alliance 1 will choose in a probabilistic sense 50% of the time to compromise and 50 % of the time to not compromise. If Alliance 1 prefers this mixed strategy above any other mixed strategy, then this mixed strategy combination can be regarded as a *mixed Nash equilibrium*.

For the calculation of the pure and mixed strategy equilibriums, *ordinal* values have been exercised for the payoffs. Enrichment of the game in a first phase requires moving towards *cardinal* payoffs or, even better, generalized values. If the ordinal payoff matrix in this illustrative analysis is regarded as a cardinal one, then the probability on a consensus outcome is quite good. It requires the actors to compromise half of the time. In the next paragraphs the effects of *asymmetric changes* in the payoff structure will be addressed, together with some basic analysis of the effects of imperfect and incomplete information.

9. Enrichment: changing the payoff structure from ordinal to cardinal

With a set of *cardinal payoffs*, nuances can be brought into the game and allow for more refined political preferences of State actors and alliances. If the payoff for not having to compromise is significantly increased, with an assumed political incentive three times higher than the choice to compromise, then the cardinal payoff matrix for the consensus game can be portrayed as shown below.

		Alliance 2	
		Compromise	Not Compromise
Alliance 1 (EU + co-Sponsors)	Compromise	2,2	1,6
	Not compromise	6,1	0,0

Matrix II.2: Strategic form of the consensus game with cardinal payoffs

Analogue to the methodology used above, the *expected payoff or utility of Alliance 1* when choosing to *compromise*:

$$U_1(\text{compromise}_1) = 2p + 1(1-p)$$

$$U_1(\text{compromise}_1) = 2p + 1 - p$$

$$U_1(\text{compromise}_1) = p + 1$$

And with (6,0) the cardinal payoff, the *expected payoff of Alliance 1* choosing to *not compromise*:

$$U_1(\text{not compromise}_1) = 6p + 0(1-p)$$

$$U_1(\text{not compromise}_1) = 6p$$

In order to determine a Nash mixed strategy equilibrium:

$$U_1(\text{compromise}_1) = U_1(\text{not compromise}_1)$$

$$p+1=6p$$

$$1=5p$$

This result in $p=1/5$ and signifies a mixed strategy equilibrium where each alliance will choose to play “compromise” with a probability of $1/5$:

$$((1/5 \text{ compromise}_1, 4/5 \text{ not compromise}_1); (1/5 \text{ compromise}_2, 4/5 \text{ not compromise}_2))$$

To assess if this is a Nash equilibrium, the expected payoff of Alliance 1 needs to be examined given Alliance 2's mixed strategy. Also the expected payoff for Alliance 1's mixed strategy needs to be examined and then both of Alliance 1's pure strategies:

$$U_1(1/5 \text{ compromise}_1, 4/5 \text{ not compromise}_1) = 1/5 [1/5(2) + 4/5(1)] + 4/5 [1/5(6) + 4/5(0)]$$

$$U_1(1/5 \text{ compromise}_1, 4/5 \text{ not compromise}_1) = 2/25 + 4/25 + 24/25 = 30/25 = 6/5$$

$$\text{Compare this to: } U_1(\text{compromise}_1) = 1/5(2) + 4/5(1) = 2/5 + 4/5 = 6/5$$

$$U_1(\text{not compromise}_1) = 1/5(6) + 4/5(0) = 6/5$$

Since:

$$U_1(1/5 \text{ compromise}_1, 4/5 \text{ not compromise}_1) = U_1(\text{not compromise}_1) = U_1(\text{compromise}_1)$$

In a probabilistic and repeated game theoretic sense, Alliance 1 has no incentive to move away from this mixed strategy. Hence, this mixed strategy combination is a Nash equilibrium. Since it is a symmetric game, the same equilibrium applies for Alliance 2. If the payoff of not compromising significantly increases versus the compromising one, then the Nash equilibrium presents logically a worrisome development to conduct a constructive debate. A payoff (= 1 or 2) at least three times lower than the political incentive to not compromise (= 6), results in a probability of 20% of the time choosing to compromise and 80% not to compromise. If premeditated alliances enter the negotiations with this political agenda, then obviously the prospects on achieving consensus are grim. Entering the negotiations with too progressive a resolution proposal could impact the payoff structure in a similar manner. It indicates that significantly changing the payoff structure could dramatically change the characteristics of the game and hence, its applicability and/or intended explanatory value.

10. Asymmetric change in payoffs

Before considering how this basic game may change with information available, the effects of asymmetric changes in payoffs will be assessed below, with Alliance 1 obtaining considerable higher payoffs (=10) than Alliance 2 (= 6) for not compromising.

		Alliance 2	
		Compromise	Not Compromise
Alliance 1 (EU+ co-Sponsors)	Compromise	2,2	1,6
	Not compromise	10,1	0,0

Matrix II.3: Strategic form of the consensus game with asymmetric payoffs

With the same methodology, an asymmetric mixed strategy equilibrium can be calculated:

$$U_1 \left(\frac{1}{9} \text{ compromise}_1, \frac{8}{9} \text{ not compromise}_1 \right), U_2 \left(\frac{1}{5} \text{ compromise}_2, \frac{4}{5} \text{ not compromise}_2 \right)$$

In this particular case one can, however, conclude that a distorted or asymmetric payoff structure will make a consensus outcome quite unlikely. As in the previous case, the game rather reflects the dynamics of a Prisoner's Dilemma with a mixed strategy Nash equilibrium of not compromising or defecting. Both enrichments of the game confirm an interesting side of this *consensus game*, namely that significantly changing its payoff structure changes the game to a point at which it does not answer to the classic characteristics of a *chicken game*.

Does failing to reach consensus mean that the politics in the high politics mine action debate have failed? Not necessarily, not reaching consensus could have various reasons. The draft text of the resolution could be so unbalanced, conservative or overly ambitious that either alliance has higher incentives not to compromise on its political agenda, in particular with regard to a total ban on landmines. In the real world there are different levels of expertise of the EU Chair. Some are more influential or able to diplomatically manoeuvre alliances or delegates out of deadlock situations than others. Other factors are different levels of constructiveness or obstruction from political opponents and their ability to come up with acceptable compromise language for the progressive alliance. Hence, besides a poorly led debate there are no true failures of politics. Moreover, not achieving consensus is not necessarily a bad thing. In contrast, it could invigorate significantly the debate on contentious issues with as a result the reinforcement of certain norms.

As an endnote, the consensus game is largely defined by the payoffs assigned to both alliances. If a political solution or setting requires changing these payoffs, then this new "solution concept" could be a hidden way of basically changing the game. The hideous character and complexities of defection are also present in recent real world examples. One of the more remarkable cases is how the Iraq War has been largely justified by the US Administration based on fabricated information provided by Iraqi defectors on suspected Iraqi weapons of mass destruction. It introduces a last but important Bayesian element to be considered in analysing the consensus game: the impact of available information, or in other terms: what to believe?

11. Effects of (im)perfect and (in)complete information

Perfect and imperfect information refer to the information each alliance has concerning the actions of the other alliance. A game of imperfect information is one in which neither alliance knows the actions of the other alliance before playing their own strategy. All they know is how their opponent played in previous rounds. Neither alliance knows well in advance if the other alliance is going to compromise on their position or risk to lose the consensus on assistance in mine action. With the UN rules and procedures, there is also the previously mentioned time pressure involved, with only a limited number of negotiation rounds. At an early stage, and especially in between the open-ended negotiations, there is, however, a process of what is known as "*UN corridor diplomacy*", which often results in bilateral sessions between the EU Chair and UN Member States. Over the years, numerous bilateral meetings convened on controversial mine action issues, with as most prominent State actors the United States, Pakistan, India, Cuba, Iran, China, Mexico, South Africa, Denmark and Norway. The main objective of these meetings is either to adjust the EU draft proposal beforehand or negotiate a mutual compromise position. During bilateral meetings, specific information can be obtained without the alliance peer-pressures. It increases the knowledge on how strong the views are and more specifically the likelihood that consensus might be sacrificed. An alliance benefits significantly from knowing the other alliance's strategy. Alliances must, therefore, obscure their intentions in order to maintain their strategic advantage of having their next move

hidden from the other alliance. Hence, one can expect a significant influence on the consensus game pending on how alliances are capable to influence the beliefs of the other alliance on how they will respond to their strategic choice.

Besides analysing whether an alliance has either perfect or imperfect information on the other alliance's actions, there is another qualifying element which needs to be taken into account. If each player or each alliance does not know the *payoffs* of the other alliance, one should consider as well the game theoretic notion of *incomplete information*. For example, what if the supportive alliance does not have any idea of the choices of preference of the obstructive alliance? Maybe the supportive alliance secures via corridor diplomacy that certain obstructive countries are changing their strategy to obtain more support from donor countries of the supportive alliance? Or one alliance might try to change the UN policy in mine action whilst the other alliance tries to reinforce it. In either case, the supportive alliance might become quite unclear which type of players it is facing in the obstructive alliance. A poor understanding of the political agenda of its political opponents can result in *blurred beliefs* and an unclear mixed strategy of the EU Chair which could weaken its influence on the debate.

In conclusion, the effects of imperfect and incomplete information on solution concepts of a consensus game could be significant and are inevitably complex. It probably provides a deeper understanding on the UN institutional politics of mine action, but requires significant additional game theoretic analysis beyond that what is required for this research phase. The analysis of incomplete and imperfect information remains, for this reason, limited to the description of the main effects above. It is, however, anticipated that other preamble paragraphs may offer opportunities to revisit some of these issues.

12. After achieving consensus: co-sponsoring or not?

Achieving consensus requires to be studied together with the number of UN Member States co-sponsoring the resolution. It can further quantify and qualify how States judge, support or (dis)approve the resolution and consensus process. Nations do not tend to provide or withdraw their co-sponsorship without particular reasons, thereby making it interesting to study significant variations in the number of co-sponsors as a possible indicator for the effectiveness of the high politics on assistance in mine action. Studying this indicator in a decade of consensus-oriented negotiations regarding this resolution, it can be observed that the number of sponsors and co-sponsor is known for several up and downtrends. Some of these trends have been prolonged and significant.

Fig. II.1: Number of UN Member States sponsoring the resolution

From 1999 on, consecutive strong and proactive chairing efforts resulted in a year over year increase until its peak in 2002. Either over or under-ambitious draft proposals have caused a problematic downtrend ever since with no consensus in 2004. However, secondary analysis remains required in order to gain a better understanding of the causes of significant, abrupt or specifically motivated withdrawals of co-sponsor support. Annex B, therefore, provides a detailed overview of UN Member States co-sponsoring the resolution, which can be studied together with the voting-record regarding the UN resolution in support of the Mine Ban Treaty.

13. Decision-making regarding possible Courses of Action (COA)

After the open-ended session, based on having obtained or failed to achieve consensus on the draft resolution, both the EU Chair and UN Member States have several courses of action to choose from. It is therefore interesting to combine the consensus game with the variety of possible actions. Below table describes the most important ones. In green the COA of the EU Chair, in blue the COA of the UN Member States. COA 1 and COA 2 are actions following a successful consensus game, COA 3 and COA 4 are possible actions after failing to achieve consensus.

The co-sponsoring aspects related to COA 1 and 2 have already been explained (see §12 of the analysis). COA 3 implies the acceptance of a vote on the resolution. This will probably result in a swift redrafting of the resolution since compromise language can be replaced by a most progressive version of the resolution, including strong language on a total ban on anti-personnel landmines. This occurs regularly with other ambitious disarmament resolutions but so far never with this UN resolution on assistance in mine action. In case a vote would take place, variations are possible according to UN voting regulations. It can either be a vote on one or more particular paragraphs of the resolution or on the resolution as a whole. Another possibility for the EU chair is to table a mere *technical decision*, thereby reintroducing the resolution on the next General Assembly agenda. Postponing the consensus debate might not be the best solution and could sharpen the differences between UN Member States. It also blocks obstructive States from taking any action themselves since tabling a decision equals a *fait accompli*. These particularities will be discussed whilst analyzing other preamble paragraphs. The table below gives in strategic form the interdependency of the different courses of action.

		COA UN Member States			
		COA 1: Co-sponsor	COA 2: No sponsoring	COA 3 : Vote in favour/against/abstain	No action possible
COA EU Chair	COA 1: Include in co-sponsor alliance for the next GA session	COA 2: Lobby to obtain co-sponsor support	COA 3: Table a non-compromise resolution	COA 4: Table a decision	

Matrix II.4: Possible courses of action after the open-ended debate

The earlier game theoretic modelling indicated that draft proposals of the resolution, which leads to a “distortion” of the payoff structure, either through causing asymmetries or extremities, significantly reduces the chances of a consensus outcome. This will equally complicate the bilateral contacts. To avoid a technical decision or a voted resolution, the drafters or the EU chair need, therefore, to carefully consider a balanced proposal between normative progression and acceptability for the conservative opponents. If the draft is too ambitious or at the opposite reversing progress, then the increased incentive not to compromise, either symmetrically or not, makes a fruitful consensus debate rather doubtful. It will require numerous concessions for at least one alliance. This indicates once again that, while developing a draft proposal, intimate knowledge on possible obstructive State behaviour is crucial for the outcome. The make-up of the draft resolution is a factor which is largely controllable and predictable in its impact on the payoff structure, the negotiating

skills of the Chair and type of political opponents are much less so. Since the payoff structure is subject to all these unknowns, it provides only limited explanatory value.

Finally, negotiating compromises is part of both the informal negotiations (closed meetings) - even amongst EU Member States - and the successive debate (open-ended meetings). The presentation in the flowchart illustrates the (repeated) sequence on how the courses of action could be decided. It is a condensed representation of the real process and thus a simplification. If consensus will be achieved and which COAs will prevail finally depends on the payoff structure, which will be highly influenced by the three previously addressed key factors: (1) the make-up of the draft resolution; (2) the Chair's level of ambition and negotiating skills; and, (3) the level of constructiveness or obstruction from political opponents.

Fig. II.2: Sequencing and possible courses of action

b. Deductions

The first preamble paragraph provided numerous game theoretic insights on consensus decision-making. Several aspects were comprehensively addressed to evaluate both the limitations and possibilities of game theory to analyse the politics of mine action. It became quickly apparent that the explanatory value of game theory lies in particular with its metaphoric qualities to describe political interactions, and not necessarily through advance game theoretic mathematics or game tree presentations.

1. Key points

☞ The high politics related to the consensus negotiations on assistance in mine action exhibit remarkably well the characteristics of a “*game of Chicken*” or “*Consensus game*” as a mixture of conflict or competition and cooperation. It could be applied relatively easily outside the domain of the politics of mine action since it reflects the essential dynamics of most UN resolution negotiation processes.⁹⁶ Building consensus portrays both the art and tyrannical characteristics of multilateral negotiations whereby agreements can only be reached by unanimity.

⁹⁶ The aspiration of consensus could be easily replaced by the minimum amount of votes for a UN resolution on the Security Council or General Assembly. The analysis has illustrated how the progressive alliance will negotiate with the conservative or obstructive alliance to maintain as much as possible the integrity of the original draft resolution.

- ☞ Three key factors influence the payoff structure and consequently the solution concept of the game: (1) the type and quality of draft UN resolution; (2) the EU Chair’s level of ambition and negotiating skills; and, (3) the level of constructiveness or obstruction from political opponents.
- ☞ Ultimate compromises are made primarily by UN Member States to protect the consensus outcome in order to maintain the “*moral weight*” of an adoption without a vote or to avoid “*name & shame*” or “*audience costs*” they could incur if regarded as obstructive States.
- ☞ Maintaining the consensus can become a crucial bargaining factor during the negotiations. Endangering the consensus might *in extremis* force the supportive alliance, and thereby the EU chair, to withdraw the draft resolution and only table a UN decision. This action prohibits both the supportive and obstructive alliance to exert their influence on the politics of mine action and more specifically on UN strategy and policy making.
- ☞ The number of co-sponsors subscribing to the UN resolution could serve as an indicator for the effectiveness of the high politics since it represents explicit political support for the UN mine action strategy, policy and mandated activities. It is a valuable *quantitative* indicator but requires further *qualitative* assessment.
- ☞ Owing to the dynamic pay-off structures and bargaining positions, the consensus process presents its unique challenges. It is notable how changing the payoff structure changes the basic dynamics of the game. Absence of solid techniques to determine equilibriums - other than intuitive searches - complicate the assessment of strategy pairs where neither alliance can benefit by changing its strategy unilaterally. The highlighted problem of multiple equilibriums - pure and mixed - is not a fault of game theory but a realistic reflection of real world politics. Gradual enrichment of the game provides additional explanatory value but also illustrates certain limitations of game theoretic analysis.
- ☞ Hence, if a *chicken or consensus game* has realistic payoff structures, then it is observed that neither alliance can benefit by changing its strategy *unilaterally*. However, this game was an overdrawn simplification. Different levels of cooperation or willingness to compromise require that the high politics of assistance in mine action need to be further studied in an expanded *n-player* context rather than a *two-player* game.

2. Possible indicators and criteria

As mentioned in the introduction, the deduction of the goals and indicators will be relatively easy in most of the analysis due to the normative character of the UN resolution. Together with the game theoretic analysis, however, a deeper understanding is achieved of the relevancy for the mine action politics, thereby providing the necessary elements for the next research phase.

Goal	Indicator
Political consensus on a progressive resolution on assistance in mine action	Number of co-sponsors to this UN resolution

This paragraph is directly related to interstate high politics. Criteria need, therefore, to allow the evaluation of the level of State support for assistance in mine action. In this regard, States can either express *support*, *opposition* or *indifference* towards the goals of the UN resolution. The (co)sponsoring of the resolution or significant obstruction of the consensus process can be part of the later categorization of States. It is, however, clear that this is not a stand-alone appreciation but should be valued as part of a broader set of evaluation criteria. In summary, based on their political opposition or support, the criteria below will be of value to differentiate between States.

Criterion 1	Being supportive to the consensus process on “assistance in mine action”
Criterion 2	Sponsoring the UN resolution on “assistance in mine action”

B. Preamble Paragraph 2: Role of States versus role of the United Nations

Recognizing that, in addition to the primary role of States, the United Nations has a significant role to play in the field of assistance in mine action, and considering mine action to be an important and integrated component of United Nations humanitarian and development activities,

a. Analysis

1. Which actors have the primary role?

This paragraph offers the opportunity to address the *n-player dimension* of the high politics of mine action instead of a simplified two-player or two-alliance chicken game. It will allow to acquire a better understanding of the key actors, their respective authoritative power or mandates, their area of expertise and the process they follow when deciding on how and what they can influence in terms of mine action assistance and even broader disarmament. Owing to effective lobbying of the United Nations Mine Action Service (UNMAS), the primary role in preceding versions of the resolution was attributed to the United Nations and a significant role to States. It is one of the important opening paragraphs as it sets the tone in which context the resolution should be further interpreted. However, in 2002 this element was reversed in order to allocate the primary role to States and a significant role to the United Nations. This was easily accepted by UN Member States as it better reflects how States currently take up their key role and responsibilities versus the significant, but secondary role of the United Nations in assistance in mine action.

“At the global level, the role of the UN in mine action is primarily one of coordination through the development of guidelines and standards, the collection and dissemination of appropriate information, the coordination of operational activities on the ground and the mobilisation of financial and technical resources. These functions are carried out with the support of, and in partnership with, various governments and non-governmental and international organizations.”⁹⁷

The above acknowledges the important coordinating role of the UN, especially after the creation of UNMAS, but recognizes that without the support and assistance of UN Member States, UNMAS would not even exist. Therefore, the resolution calls in its operative part for the continuation of the efforts of States, with the assistance of the United Nations and relevant organizations involved in mine action, to foster the establishment and development of national mine-action capacities in countries in which mines and other unexploded ordnance constitute a serious threat to the safety, health and lives of the local population or an impediment to social and economic development efforts at the national and local levels.⁹⁸

2. UN goal-setting: the UN Inter-Agency Mine Action Strategy

In order to frame with greater detail the multilateral mine action politics, it merits looking at the institutional mine action politics of the UN and how this translates into strategic goals. The most applicable document in this regard is the *UN Mine Action Strategy 2006-2010*.⁹⁹ The qualifying element “*inter-agency*” indicates the broad-based consultations, which precede the adoption by the Inter-Agency Coordination Group on Mine Action. Through its 14 members a multitude of UN departments, agencies, funds and programmes are involved with a rational and cost-effective prioritization of UN mine action activities as main objective, over the next five years.

⁹⁷ UNMAS Publication. (2004). A handbook for: Mine Action Programming, New York, p.2

⁹⁸ UN Document A/RES/58/127, operational paragraph 2 from UN resolution on ‘Assistance in mine action’, Internet. Available at <http://www.un.org/Depts/dhl/resguide/r58.htm>, accessed on 20 July 2004

⁹⁹ This strategy was preceded by a UN strategy for 2001-2005, Internet. Available from www.mineaction.org, accessed on October 2006

Compared to preceding efforts of UN strategy formulation, it is most apparent that the goal-setting and policy direction has been strongly influenced by the Millennium Development Goals. It is, however, not clear which methodology has been used and how the strategy will contribute precisely to the prioritization process of mine action. Similar to the *Nairobi Action Plan*, which will be discussed when addressing the Mine Ban Treaty, the UN strategy is in many regards rather an “*institutional declaration of good intentions*” than a strategic roadmap. Even with the addition of envisaged major activities and indicators of achievement, it stops short from formulating a clear understanding on how a better prioritization of mine action can be achieved neither within mine action programmes, nor among different humanitarian and development programmes, let alone any cross-country comparison mechanisms. Hence the document is helpful in providing a general “*compass heading*” but allows the actors to determine how to achieve the ambitious goals. This is not exceptional for UN policies which are the product of broad-based consultations.

The above leads to another important norm building aspect: the formulated *endstate* or UN *vision* for mine action. It states that the United Nations envisions a world free of the *threat* of landmines and ERW, where individuals and communities live in a safe environment conducive to development and where the needs of mine and ERW victims are met and they are fully integrated into their societies.¹⁰⁰ Although the UN has always strongly supported the Mine Ban Treaty, the strategy is a clear departure from the *utopian* state of a mine free world.

In conclusion, the UN strategy is an important document for this dissertation, as will be other strategic products, such as Nairobi Action Plan. These documents provide ample insight on both the high and institutional politics and will therefore be used as a recurrent reference throughout the analysis. At this stage, the following four UN strategic objectives provide some familiarisation with institutional goal-setting and how the UN sees its institutional role until from 2006 until 2010.¹⁰¹

- (1) *Strategic Objective 1*: Reduction of death and injury by at least 50%¹⁰²
- (2) *Strategic Objective 2*: Mitigate the risk to community livelihoods and expand freedom of movement for at least 80 percent of the most seriously affected communities.
- (3) *Strategic Objective 3*: Integration of mine action needs into national development and reconstruction plans and budgets in at least 15 countries by 2010.
- (4) *Strategic Objective 4*: Assist the development of national institutions to manage the landmine/ERW threat, and at the same time prepare for residual response capacity in at least 15 countries by 2010.

3. Primary role of donor countries versus mine-affected States

Resources for mine action are generated mainly through UN Member States, with mine-affected States carrying the primary responsibility for their mine-affected land and impacted population. This highlights how the primary role and accountabilities of mine action should be fulfilled. Even in emergency situations, with a failed or fragile State not capable of taking ownership of landmine problems, strategic guidance of UN Member States and their funding will enable the United Nations and/or NGOs to assist and build national capacities as required. The head of the Geneva-based Mine Ban Treaty Implementation Support Unit carefully balances the current concept of responsibility and ownership of the landmine problems.

“On one hand, individual state responsibility – in the sense that no supranational authority exists to oversee implementation and enforce compliance – means that individual mine-affected States must take full ownership over identifying their landmine problems, developing plans to address these problems and

¹⁰⁰ UNMAS Document. UN Mine Action Strategy 2006-2010, p.5, Internet. Available from www.mineaction.org, accessed on 10 April 2006

¹⁰¹ UNMAS Document. UN Mine Action Strategy 2006-2010, p.9-12, Internet. Available from www.mineaction.org, accessed on 10 April 2006

¹⁰² Based on 2006 Landmine Monitor estimates of 15000 mine victims/year, the strategic objective is to achieve at least a reduction of 7500 mine victims/year. ICBL (2006). *Landmine Monitor Report 2005: Toward a Mine-Free World*, New York

reaching out for assistance if necessary. On the other hand, partnership – as articulated in Article 6 of the [Mine Ban Treaty] convention – makes it clear that a variety of actors stand ready to help.”¹⁰³

The variety of actors is further clarified in Article 6¹⁰⁴ of the MBT, stipulating that assistance may be provided, inter alia, through the United Nations system, international, regional or national organizations or institutions, the International Committee of the Red Cross, national Red Cross and Red Crescent societies and their International Federation, non-governmental organizations or, on a bilateral basis. According to the MBT, States Parties may request the United Nations, regional organizations, other States Parties or other competent intergovernmental or NGOs to assist its authorities in the establishment of a national mine action program.

4. Categorization of mine-affected countries

Having highlighted the primary role and variety of assisting actors, it would be helpful to introduce a more refined game theoretic categorisation system of donor and recipient States in further explanation of inter-State behaviour. In a first effort to categorize recipient or mine-affected countries, their national capacity and political will to deal with their mine contamination should first and foremost be assessed. Hence, deduced from the development sector, most recipient countries fall into the following four broad types¹⁰⁵:

- (1) “*good performers*” with the national capacity and political will to sustain a mine action partnership with the international community; e.g. Afghanistan, Cambodia;
- (2) “*weak but willing*” States with limited capacity to sustain a mine action programme but favourable to cooperate with the mine action community; e.g. Chad, Sudan;
- (3) “*strong but unresponsive*” States which could be resisting a specific partnership with the mine action community because of a landmine requirement for national security purposes; e.g. Iran, Cuba, Egypt, Morocco;
- (4) “*weak-weak*” States where both political will and institutional capacity present serious challenges to a mine action programme; e.g. Sri Lanka, Myanmar.

5. Categorization of donor countries

Similarly, a classification of donor countries could be introduced according to the following broad categories:

- (1) “*first-class donors*” being highly supportive of mine action and aiming for a leading position or high visibility within the donor community by putting mine action within their national priorities; e.g. Norway, Japan, US, most EU countries, in particular Denmark;
- (2) “*average or unpredictable*” donors whereby no clear trend in support can be expected; e.g. Greece, Slovenia;
- (3) “*marginal but improving*” donor countries with a small funding budget but with yearly increase in support and engagement; e.g. Republic of Korea;
- (4) “*weak/no donors*” with no significant engagement, providing more symbolic than any kind of substantial support; e.g. Turkey, Czech Republic.

6. Alliance or coalition formations: the *n*-player Game of Chicken

As in most disarmament issues, a more subtle formation of alliances exist than the subdivision between the alliance with explicit support for more progressive language versus the

¹⁰³ BRINKERT, K. (2003). Paving the bridge between disarmament and development: resources generated by the Anti-Personnel Mine Ban convention, *Disarmament Forum*, Sep 2003, Kerry Brinkert

¹⁰⁴ This article regulates the “International cooperation and assistance” amongst donor and mine-affected States, therefore giving each State Party to the Mine Ban Treaty the right to seek and receive assistance, where feasible, from other States Parties to the extent possible.

¹⁰⁵ Based on how developing countries are categorized in general. “Why we need to work more effectively in fragile States” DFID, published by the Department for International Development on January 2005

alliance unsupportive of advancing the noble cause of assistance in mine action and/or a total landmine ban. The alliance of the co-sponsoring States contains largely similarly supportive States as many of the above cited “first-class donors” of the EU alliance. Some States have an ambiguous position towards assistance in mine action, influenced by other alliances they are part of in the UN System. According to the categories above, both a variety of recipient and donor countries are amongst the (co)sponsoring States. The considerable number of States belonging to the Non-Aligned Movement is institutionally important,¹⁰⁶ with some States instrumental in alleviating conflicts of interest between progressive and non-supportive States.¹⁰⁷

An *n-player game* is generally well suited to address any number of players. This type of game could, therefore, be used in contrast to standard two-player games that may be trivial to explain the interdependent selection of strategies in institutional and multilateral environments. In defining *n-player games*, game theorists usually provide a definition that allows for any (finite) number of players. In this context, it may be theoretically stated that the maximum number of players is limited to the 192 UN Member States. Since this analysis will, however, study the behaviour and strategies of alliances, it is envisaged to pragmatically limit the number of players to like-minded States as categorized above.

The analysis of alliance formations might benefit most from a two-prong approach. On the one hand, game theoretic modelling could describe the behaviour of multiple or *n-alliances*; on the other hand, changes in the composition of alliances or related dynamics probably require a different type of modelling. According to the above identification and categorization of the eight different groups of States, alliances can be logically set out as delineated below:

- (1) *Alliance 1* groups all the *donor countries*, although their national policies might differ on the resources they are willing to allocate to assistance in mine action. They will not differ significantly on the core issues related to assistance in mine action, but could differ on a total landmine ban.
- (2) *Alliance 2* integrates the *recipient countries*. Some national security requirements might cause nations to be considerably less in favour of a total landmine ban or other progressive mine action policies.
- (3) *Alliance 3* exhibits the hard core of *non-progressive or non-supportive States* with regard to the assistance in mine action resolution and UN policy. This is a rather dynamic alliance and one which exists largely out of States which use landmines as an active part of their military doctrine, in particular for border protection or similar national security requirements. Countries like Egypt, Cuba, China, Russia, Pakistan, India, Libya, and to a lesser extent Lebanon and Israel, have been the most active ones.

In analogy with a “*Hawk-Dove*” version¹⁰⁸ of a Game of Chicken, Alliance 1 is expected to display *Dovish* behaviour and Alliance 3 taking *Hawkish* positions. How then to label Alliance 2? Although they have the ownership of the problem, generally their main interest is to receive support from donor countries as much as possible. To proceed along the lines of this game theoretic description of interest groups of States, Alliance 2 could be labelled as the “*Cuckoo*” alliance. This metaphoric term symbolizes the interest of mine-affected countries in donor countries funding their mine action programme, similar to a cuckoo looking for another bird’s nest to put in its egg. In

¹⁰⁶ The Non Aligned Movement has its own political dynamics in the UN as an international organization of over 100 States which consider themselves not formally aligned with or against any major power bloc.

¹⁰⁷ States exemplary in their bridging efforts have been South-Africa, Jordan and to a lesser extent Mexico; observed during many negotiation rounds and direct contacts with national representatives from Jordan, South Africa and Mexico.

¹⁰⁸ As a variant of a Game of Chicken a Hawk-Dove game has a similar pay-off structure but allocates distinct characteristics at both players. In this interpretation two players contesting an indivisible resource choose between two strategies, one more escalated than the other. Their respective tactics are usually sub-divided amongst displaying threats (play Dove), or attack each other (play Hawk). To make it more applicable, this analysis chooses the association with the actors rather than the possible strategic choices.

consecutively developing a three-alliance version of a Chicken game, several characteristics of a two-player game need to be preserved. These characteristics include the following:

- (1) All State actors prefer ultimately that everyone compromises rather than everyone not compromising.
- (2) Each State actor's most preferred outcome is to be the only actor not compromising.
- (3) All State actors play the game with imperfect and incomplete information implying no knowledge upfront of the strategic choices or payoff structure.
- (4) For this variation of the three-player Chicken game, each actor prefers not to compromise if the other two actors compromise, and to compromise if any of the two other players do not compromise in order to save the consensus.

Figure II.3 portrays the different alliances described above. A considerable number of States is either indifferent or too weak in their national capacities to partake in any alliance as such, explaining why they are considered below as a weak or non-allied group of States. Arrows symbolize the flux of funding and resources between donor and mine-affected nations whereby the dotted arrow within Alliance 2 reflects the particularity of a limited number of mine-affected nations supporting others:

Fig.II.3: *n*-player dimension – Alliance formations

Hence, a three-alliance game is now considered where each alliance prefers not to compromise if at least one alliance has chosen to compromise, and to compromise only if at least one alliance does not compromise. This implies the following utilities for the Hawkish Alliance (Hawks=H, Doves=D, Cuckoos=C):

$$[u_H = (\text{compromise}_D; \text{not compromise}_H; \text{not compromise}_C)] > [u_H = (\text{compromise}_D; \text{compromise}_H; \text{compromise}_C)]$$

and: $[u_H = (\text{not compromise}_D; \text{compromise}_H; \text{not compromise}_C)] > [u_H = (\text{not compromise}_D; \text{not compromise}_H; \text{not compromise}_C)]$

		Cuckoos (C)		Compromise		Not Compromise	
		Hawks (H)		Compromise	Not Compromise	Compromise	Not Compromise
Doves (D)	Compromise	2,2,2	1,3,1	1,1,3	1,3,3		
	Not compromise	3,1,1	3,3,1	3,1,3	0,0,0		

Matrix II.5: Strategic form of the *n*-player consensus game

Matrix II.5 presents the normal form game of this particular version of a three-player Chicken game with ordinal values for the payoffs. The major difference in payoffs to the actors

engaged in this game is evident when two players choose not to compromise while one player selects compromise: the corresponding ordinal payoffs are (1,3,3), (3,1,3), and (3,3,1). If all three actors choose not to compromise, the payoff to each respective actor is (0,0,0); likewise, if three alliances need to compromise, the payoff is (2,2,2).

Intuitively the three pure Nash equilibriums are as shown below.

(compromise_D; not compromise_H; not compromise_C)
(not compromise_D; compromise_H; not compromise_C)
(not compromise_D; not compromise_H; compromise_C)

And a fourth mixed strategy Nash equilibrium can be formulated with respective probabilities p , q and r , analogue to a two-alliance chicken game:¹⁰⁹

((p compromise_D, $(1-p)$ not compromise_D); (q compromise_H, $(1-q)$ not compromise_H);
(r compromise_C, $(1-r)$ not compromise_C))

However, changing from 2-player to n -player games entails some additional considerations. A more detailed assessment of the game theoretic principles above requires again the introduction of sequential or dynamic game structures and the impact of incomplete/imperfect information. In this political context, it implies that either recipient or donor States gradually acquire more knowledge about earlier actions which might influence their payoff structure and consequently their decision-making to accept the conditions, which will likely lead to more support from donor countries for their landmine problems.

On the other hand, *evolutionary* learning through more and better information about mine-affected nations will influence the strategic *beliefs* and views of donors. This does not automatically imply that perfect information needs to be obtained by recipient and donor States; it might be sufficient a pattern is recognized within an n -player context to change State behaviour over time. Although very different in nature, misleading information on the level of mine contamination of an affected country can have a similar effect. Landmine impact surveys have indicated systematic exaggerations of heavily affected countries.¹¹⁰ More accurate and reliable assessments resulted in significant decreases in funding, e.g. the mine action programme in Afghanistan. The effect of *biased beliefs on the type of players* is, therefore, recognized as an important issue at all levels in the politics of mine action and will be readdressed with more detail when discussing public awareness issues surrounding mine action and obviously during the case-study.

7. Changing alliances: when to defect from the alliance of defectors or non co-operators?

Not only the behaviour and interaction of the alliances are of interest, but also a State's motives to change Alliances. Hawkish countries, heavily mine-affected or those still using landmines extensively, may learn and evolve towards increasingly common interests with the cuckoo alliance. Besides the consensus process of the UN resolution other interesting examples illustrate the impact of influential donor countries to provide only funding to recipient countries on a conditional basis; e.g. requesting they have to accede to the MBT. This pressure element has without doubt accelerated the growing number of States adhering to the MBT. On the other hand, depriving certain countries from any significant mine action funding became increasingly ineffective as the MBT members' pressure instrument, indicating a discount on the effects of this tactic over time. All these aspects are common to many disarmament issues outside the field of mine action and can therefore be studied below within a broader game theoretic context.

¹⁰⁹ In this particular case with symmetric ordinal utilities, the probabilities are symmetric as well.

¹¹⁰ MASLEN, S. (2004). *Mine action after Diana: Progress in the struggle against landmines*, London: Pluto Press

The “*defecting from defectors*”, or non co-operators becoming co-operators, invites further study of a Prisoner’s Dilemma (PD), in particular how it could fit this iterated cooperative game. Ironically, when a Prisoner’s Dilemma is played as a cooperative game, the dilemma is no longer present.¹¹¹ So, why still call it a PD and not again a chicken game? In this case it may be argued that the phenomenon of “defecting” or not cooperating is initially the dominating strategy or equilibrium, whilst in a chicken game “compromising” is the overarching objective. In the metaphoric context of a chicken race, neither driver enters the race with the insane intention not to swerve the car and to drive off the cliff. Equally, neither driver has the intention to swerve first; otherwise he would not have entered the race in the first place. In case of the chicken game described, *defecting* is not a dominant strategy. This is in a PD exactly the case. In order to join the cooperative Alliance, the initially non-supportive State still needs to defect from the non-cooperative alliance or defectors. This is more obvious when put in straightforward win-lose terms in the strategic form below. Hence, the optimal utility maximization strategy for both alliances is simply defection. The game dynamics of this one-shot 2-player PD are different from a chicken game due to its payoff structure. As highlighted in yellow, the highest loss is no longer incurred when both actors defect simultaneously. The alliance cooperating, whilst the other one is defecting, ends up in the most unfavourable position.

		Hawks	
		Cooperate	Defect
Doves	Cooperate	win - win	lose much – win much
	Defect	win much – lose much	lose - lose

Matrix II.6: Strategic form of a PD game with generic payoffs

However, if one considers a *sequential or n-player iterated-PD game*¹¹² the optimal strategy depends upon the strategies of likely opponents, and how they will react to repeated defections and possible co-operations. In this situation, alliances have to choose their mutual strategy time and again, and are affected by building up a memory of their previous outcomes and payoffs. The strategic form below and the explanation will further clarify how countries as part of the Hawkish Alliance can be persuaded to become co-operators.

		Cuckoos		Hawks	
		Cooperate	Defect	Cooperate	Defect
Doves	Cooperate	win, win, win	lose much, win much, lose much	lose much, lose much, win much	lose much, win much, win much
	Defect	win much, lose much, lose much	win much, win much, lose much	win much, lose much, win much	lose, lose, lose

Matrix II.7: Strategic form of the 3-alliance iterated - cooperative - PD game

When the above PD is studied in an iterated or evolutionary context, its application to reflect cooperation may not appear as problematic. If one follows what happens over time, rather than defining defection or cooperation in mine action as a single snapshot, it becomes apparent how alliances can shift. An historic example of a repeated PD is the trench warfare of the Great War.¹¹³ Initially it was best to cause as much damage to the other party as possible. After the opposing parties got to “know” each other, they realised that causing as much damage as possible to the other will only prompt a similar response. Bombarding the other’s food stock would only leave both battalions hungry. Hence, the opposing battalions learned that it is sufficient to *show* what they are capable of, instead of actually carrying out the act. This is a watered down version of the

¹¹¹ MORROW, J. (1994). *Game Theory for Political Scientist*, New Jersey: Princeton, p.111

¹¹² AXELROD, R. (1981). *The Evolution of Cooperation*. Science, 211(4489):1390-6

¹¹³ Wikipedia Encyclopaedia, Internet. Available at http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Repeated_game, accessed at July 2006

overwhelming deterrence principles of *Mutually Assured Destruction*, whereby the element of credible threat is key.¹¹⁴

In an evolutionary context, the Hawkish Alliance can gradually opt to cooperate by joining the Cuckoo Alliance whenever the (expected) gain in payoff through cooperating outweighs the immediate loss of giving up defecting. In most cases the latter implies no further usage of landmines as part of their national security strategy, landmine clearance and stockpile destruction. On the other hand, the gain is to be liberated of the stigmatization as a landmine-user, receiving international support for mine clearance and possibly obtain significant socio-economic benefits. How does this iterated PD fit with the “*politics of the great military powers*”, as keepers of millions of landmines? Obviously the United States, China and Russia have no credible or keen interest to join the Cuckoo Alliance. None of these powerful nations requires assistance to solve their landmine “*problem*”, which they currently perceive as part of their set of “*solutions*” to their security requirements or problems. Indeed, all three have declared to use landmines if there is a military requirement and distance themselves from anything close to a ban on landmines. Through the United States, the Demilitarized Zone (DMZ) between South and North Korea is as the “last frontier of the Cold War” the most heavily mined border in the world.¹¹⁵ So, is this triumvirate the most hawkish amongst the hawks? How to explain the considerable support of the United States, and recently China, to mine action? *Imitation of alliance behaviour* is one of the game theoretic particularities which could provide the best explanation.

Self-interest requires the United States to maintain its loyalty to the Hawkish Alliance of landmine users. Clearly, simultaneously *imitating the behaviour of the Doves* through providing significant support and cooperation to mine action further increases its payoffs and lowers the national and international *audience cost* for still possessing millions of technologically advanced landmines. It can finally be reduced in terms of a number of *benefits outweighing the costs*. Hence, seeking the subtle balance between costs and benefits of joining or staying out of the MBT is an important political consideration for both the US and most other countries:

“One important reason for its still-growing success [of the Mine Ban Treaty] is that many countries that initially defected for narrow national reasons have come to see the benefits of belonging to a global ban on anti-personnel mines and so joined the ranks of the co-operators. [...] What this shows is that a cluster of co-operators has been able to stigmatise a weapon system to such a great extent that they have clearly affected the behaviour of defectors, even powerful ones. An added benefit is that while these so-called “key countries” stand outside the treaty, they have less opportunity to suppress the enthusiasm of the co-operators driving the Mine Ban Treaty - or to undermine their work!”¹¹⁶

The United States is, therefore, seeking prominent positions in divers mine action forums, most recently through advocating assistance to mine action in its position as chair of the Mine Action Support Group.¹¹⁷ Ultimately, assistance in mine action became an integral part of the *US National Strategy for Combating Terrorism*,¹¹⁸ whereby landmines and ERW are regarded as one of the destabilizing root causes of fragile states and are most feared for the opportunity stock in explosives they offer to insurgencies. This will be further discussed when addressing the preamble paragraph on non-State actors using landmines or associated explosive devices.

¹¹⁴ A credible threat is immediately derived from possessing an actual assured-destruction capability with an unwavering will to use it in retaliation to an attack. From the "Mutual Deterrence" Speech by Secretary of Defense Robert McNamara, 1967. Internet. Available from <http://www.atomicarchive.com/Docs/Deterrence/Deterrence.shtml>, accessed on 27 December 2006.

¹¹⁵ THATCHER, J. (2006, 15 September). *North Korea spits defiance across final frontier of the Cold War, South Korea*, Scotsman National Newspaper online, Internet. Available at <http://thescotsman.scotsman.com/international.cfm?id=1509522006>, accessed on 27 December 2006

¹¹⁶ BORRIE, J. (2006). Cooperation/Defection in the Conference on Disarmament, *Disarmament Diplomacy*, Issue Nr 82, 2006

¹¹⁷ See current USA website of the Mine Action Support Group Chair, Internet. Available at www.state.gov/tpm/wra/c17719.htm, accessed on 10 October 2006

¹¹⁸ US DoS publication. (2006). *National Strategy for Combating Terrorism*, 2006, Internet. Available at <http://www.whitehouse.gov/nsc/nsct/2006/nsct2006.pdf>, accessed on 20 December 2006

8. Sustained cooperation, discounting effects and *minimax* principles

Although the PD has theoretically only one Nash equilibrium whereby everyone defects, cooperation can be sustained in a repeated PD if the *discount factor* stays low enough. This implies players should remain interested enough in future outcomes of the game, which in this case is determined by the expected support from donor countries. If donor support wanes, then defecting might again become the preferred strategic choice. This touches the principle whereby the actor at all times will try to minimise its maximum loss, either in terms of losing (potential) donor support and/or the loss of payoffs if an actor has to stop using landmines for national security requirements, in particular border protection. This minimizing of maximum possible loss, also called *minimax*, is a game theoretic refinement on utility maximization. It is intuitively suitable to describe the specifics of the politics of mine action whereby impact reduction is a central theme. Often socio-economic “*mine action benefits*” signify no real surpluses but are of the “*saved costs or reduced losses*” type.

9. Integration of mine action in broader UN activities and development strategies

The normative aspects of this paragraph, namely that mine action needs to be considered as an integrated component of United Nations humanitarian and development activities, is of equal importance. The integration issue requires the development of a national mine action strategy which should be part of an overarching national strategy and/or policy. Consequently, it is a national responsibility. This is well incorporated in the third strategic objective of the UN mine action strategy, which states that mine action needs to be integrated into national development and reconstruction plans and budgets in at least 15 countries. No explanation is provided why that particular number is chosen, most likely – in reference to the *feasibility theorem* above – because the drafters of the UN strategy regarded this number as realistic and achievable before 2010.

In more pragmatic terms, the UN should continue to assist concretely the national authorities by aiding or facilitating the development of these strategies, in close consultation with all relevant partners. Mine-affected countries should include activities related to mine action in their humanitarian, rehabilitation, reconstruction and development assistance activities, where appropriate, bearing in mind the need to ensure national and local ownership, sustainability and capacity-building.¹¹⁹ Therefore, mine action activities should be an integral component of strategies designed to rehabilitate health care, education, infrastructure, agriculture and marketing systems, to name but a few of the requirements of societies recovering from violent conflicts.

b. Deductions

1. Key points

- ☞ States have undoubtedly the primary role in the politics of mine action with institutional politics distinctly subordinate. In this regard, the UN mine action strategy is the main institutional tool with a particular focus on prioritization of mine action activities; it lacks a clear roadmap but reflects how the UN evolved from envisioning a world free of landmines towards a world free from the *threats* of landmines.
- ☞ Finite categorization of State behaviour between donor and recipient countries is most helpful to explain alliance formations and alterations. It allows to explain the phenomenon *how alliances achieve consensus* through the game theoretic characteristics of an *n-player Game of Chicken*. Associating strategic choices (play hawk, dove or cuckoo) with the characterisation of alliances (Hawkish, Dovish and Cuckoo Alliance) was a game theoretic alteration benefiting the clarity of the argument, together with the categorization of donor and recipient countries. According to

¹¹⁹ UN Document A/RES/58/127, operational paragraph 9 from UN resolution on ‘Assistance in mine action’, Internet. Available at <http://www.un.org/Depts/dhl/resguide/r58.htm>, accessed on 20 July 2005

the game dynamics of *iterated Prisoner's Dilemmas*, countries may decide to shift from the alliance of defectors (Hawks) to opportunistic co-operators (Cuckoos). Imitation of cooperative alliance behaviour (Doves), simultaneous with hawkish State behaviour, can lower *audience costs* or minimize *name & shame effects*.

- ☞ *Minimax* principles were touched upon to explain how actors will try to minimize their maximum loss. In the context of mine action socio-economic benefits, the next paragraph needs to address *minimax* games against *nature*. The *minimax* principle is largely based on socio-economic benefits, which are mostly of the type of *reduced costs or losses*.
- ☞ *Discount effects* are essential to explain *sustained* cooperation and require further study to understand the impact on expected benefits from mine action and how it could instigate donor fatigue or erode political will.
- ☞ States interact in most disarmament domains *without much central control*; the level of voluntary cooperation is, therefore, an important parameter for qualifying the level of effectiveness of the politics of mine action. The requirements for the emergence of cooperation have empirical relevance for the further study of compliance issues with the Mine Ban Treaty.

2. Possible indicators and criteria

The goals and indicators can be summarized below according to the primary role of States in mine action and the secondary, institutional role of the UN. Additional normative elements were deduced from the UN revised mine action strategy.

Invariably, any goal setting will benefit from a maximization of the three following indicators: (1) the level of funding; (2) national ownership; and, (3) integration of mine action into other sectors. The evaluation criteria 3, 4 and 5 reflect this accordingly. Interestingly, however, maximization of the level of integration and funding of mine action might be conflicting. Indeed, advanced integration of mine action into other sectors can result in donor countries' reprioritizing according to the most urgent needs with less funding or resources going to mine action. Criterion 6 and 7 reflects the measurement of progress in reference with the UN mine action strategy.

Goal	Indicator
Donor and Recipient States take up their primary responsibilities and role to respond adequately to landmine problems	Level of national ownership leading to a categorization of recipient States: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Good performers 2. Weak but willing 3. Strong but unresponsive 4. Weak/Weak
	Level of donor support leading to a categorization of donor countries: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. First class donors 2. Average/unpredictable 3. Marginal but improving 4. Weak donors
UN fulfils its significant role according to the UN Vision: A world free of the threat of landmines	Multiple Indicators to measure progress in achieving the 4 UN strategic objectives/targets <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Reduction of death and injury by at least 50 %. 2. Mitigate the risk to community livelihoods and expand freedom of movement for at least 80 %. 3. Integration of mine action into national development & reconstruction in at least 15 countries. 4. Assist the development of national institutions to manage the landmine/ERW threat, and at the same time prepare for residual response capacity in at least 15 countries.

Criterion 3	Level of support of donor countries for mine action programmes
Criterion 4	Level of governance/managerial capabilities and commitment to effectively implement mine action
Criterion 5	Level of integration/mainstreaming of mine action into broader humanitarian and development strategies
Criterion 6	Level of human cost
Criterion 7	Establishment of a national mine action capacity

C. Preamble Paragraph 3: The humanitarian and development impact of landmines

Reaffirming its deep concern at the tremendous humanitarian and development problems caused by the presence of mines and other unexploded ordnance that constitute an obstacle to the return of refugees and other displaced persons, to humanitarian aid operations and to reconstruction and economic development, as well as to the restoration of normal social conditions, and that have serious and lasting social and economic consequences for the populations of mine-affected countries,

a. Analysis

1. The many faces of the socio-economic impact

This paragraph highlights the significant socio-economic impact of landmines and explosive remnants of war, thereby focusing on humanitarian and development problems. It was a humanitarian crisis which prompted the creation of a mine action program in Afghanistan and significantly motivated UN Member States to draw attention to these problems via the introduction of the resolution in 1993. Currently, landmines continue to block access in many different ways; and this justifies the pertinent and normative nature of this paragraph. Each region or country has its unique set of *socio-economic blockages* and *post-conflict restoration* issues, often creating tremendous obstacles for the return of refugees and internally displaced persons, both for past and recent conflicts.

“The Halo Trust, which is partly funded by the UK Government, began operations after Russian planes showered mines on Chechnya and planted the weapons during the 1994-96 war. Halo said it had recorded 296 mined areas in Chechnya after the war and claimed this was frightening refugees from returning home.”¹²⁰

Sudan primarily experiences socio-economic blockages which significantly hinder humanitarian aid operations. In the recent past, the impact of mined roads frequently necessitated the provision of food aid via air drops, under the well-known name “*Operation Lifeline Sudan*”. The presence of landmines obliged the international community to spend massive amounts of money on air transport instead of other post-conflict restoration activities with greater marginal utility. Mine action in Sudan is, therefore, an important part of the restoration of the road network in order to reinstate the required minimum level of security. This allows the World Food Programme to deliver food assistance to the population affected by war and drought at a fraction of the cost of air transport or airdrops.

“Even where mines do not simply prevent food and medical aid from reaching people in need, they make already difficult relief operations even more hazardous. Security measures have to be stepped up, and such precautions can result in a 25-fold increase in the cost of humanitarian and development aid. This widens the ever increasing gap between growing humanitarian needs and shrinking world resources to meet those needs.”¹²¹

Put in brief, in most post-conflict situations the presence of landmines is a significant aggravating factor to an already problematic situation which often has to be dealt with as a matter of urgency. One has only to witness the grave socio-economic impact of landmines in significantly contaminated countries such as Afghanistan, Cambodia, Iraq, Angola and others to understand the tremendous challenges and obstacles landmines pose to post-conflict reconstruction, economic development and restoration of normal social conditions. In general, varying sorts and degrees of impact can be witnessed: contaminated farmland, blocked irrigation channels, blocked water access, dangerously mined roads, residential and recreational areas, inaccessible grazing routes and land.

¹²⁰ BBC News, Mine charity rejects spy charges, 11 August 2000, Internet. Available at <http://news.bbc.co.uk/1/hi/world/europe/875094.stm>, accessed on 20 October 2005

¹²¹ Anti-personnel mines: An overview.1997, Internet. Available at <http://www.quasar.org/21698/mil/minefact.htm#7>, accessed on 10 April 2005

2. Socio-economic benefits versus impact: gateway to priority setting?

In several mine action publications, the term “*impact*” has been used both for the negative effects of *landmines* and the positive effects of *mine action*. In order to enhance delineation, this study will use the term impact only in conjunction with the negative effects of the presence of landmines and unexploded ordnance, whilst the term “*benefits*” will be used with the positive effects of mine action. Obviously, it is crucial for a mine-affected country to reduce as effectively and efficiently as possible the negative impact of landmines. Conversely, underscoring and portraying the benefits triggers support from donor countries. This suggests the further development of quantifiable and qualifiable socio-economic cost-benefit calculations for national mine action programs. The majority of experts regard the mine-affected or recipient country as key towards finding solutions for its mine-affected state. Donor countries might have a significant impact on how prioritization is taking place but ultimately it should be up to the recipient country to provide the decision-making elements for national prioritization, which should result in a sound planning process and adequate use of available techniques and resources.

3. Does socio-economic impact include mine victims or casualties?

This is an important ethical question since this study will decisively avoid the practice of mixing up the tragic human cost of landmines in terms of casualties with factors categorized under socio-economic impact. Several socio-economic impact studies on landmines include the number of killed or maimed mine victims as an integral part of the socio-economic impact, including *Landmine Impact Surveys* and other comprehensive studies such as the Socio-Economic Impact of Mine Action in Afghanistan, A Cost-Benefit Analysis.¹²² Both important studies will be assessed in the case study in order to prove that through separating the human cost from the socio-economics, strong from weak socio-economic metrics, more clarity can be obtained on the impact of landmines on societies as well as a clear distinction between the possible payoffs. This will furthermore enhance the deduction of game and decision theoretic considerations, as well as strategic or operational criteria to be answered by the mine action community when prioritizing mine action efforts.

The refraining from calculating the “*utility or economic value*” of a human life in a particular country has been explained for ethical reasons. It is equally in avoidance of what could be called “*exuberant pragmatism*”. Hence, exploring avenues whereby the value of a human life is integrated into a set of strategic criteria to decide that more resources should go to country A than to country B, is an ignorance of ethic and social values. Indeed, if less resources are going to be allocated to a mine-affected State because of a lower GDP per capita - thus theoretically a lower economic output per capita and less an economic loss if that person is killed or maimed beyond being economic viable - is regarded as unacceptable. Moreover, this practice clearly diverges from the true humanitarian dimension of mine action.

Numbers of mine victims will, therefore, be assessed separately from the more traditional understanding of socio-economic impact, and categorized under “*human cost*”. Nevertheless, this inopportune exploitation of mine victim data remains part of the politics and continues to influence the allocation of resources, as per the World Bank funded socio-economic impact study (see below) of the landmine problem in Afghanistan.

“The socio-economic loss related to a fatal casualty from a mine accident in Afghanistan is conservatively estimated at less than US\$ 12,000. The loss from a typical mine victim is estimated at about US\$ 9,000,

¹²² BYRD and GILDESTAD. (2001). *Socio-Economic Impact of Mine Action in Afghanistan, A Cost-Benefit Analysis*, World Bank funded study, Internet. Available at [http://lnweb18.worldbank.org/SAR/sa.nsf/Attachments/9/\\$File/mines.pdf](http://lnweb18.worldbank.org/SAR/sa.nsf/Attachments/9/$File/mines.pdf), accessed on 25 April 2005, p.v

when the proportion of different types of casualties have been taken into account along with their respective degrees of disability.”¹²³

This dissertation regards, however, the comparison of the human cost reduction capability in numbers of mine victims as an acceptable decision-making element, even more, programmes which prove to have effective “*Zero-Victim*” strategies or targets should be favoured. However, this does not allow to bring discounting effects into the equation; this will be further addressed at the end of the discussion of this preamble paragraph.

4. Socio-economics are key utility inputs for interdependent decision-making

The socio-economic impact of the global landmine problem and socio-economic benefits of the global response belong to the key parameters influencing the politics of mine action. Targets and indicators proposed for examining the *best response* should, therefore, be practical, achievable and globally applicable to measure progress towards maximizing socio-economic benefits and payoffs through mine action. The concept of best response is a game theoretic cornerstone. In addition, the costs and benefits of mine action are not fixed, but interdependent upon the choices of other players or decision makers.

The humanitarian and developmental benefits of mine contamination need indeed to be assessed in light of the level of cooperation which can be expected from other essential actors to reap the payoffs of mine action. If potential farmland, roads or villages are cleared of landmines, local authorities or aid agencies need to approach holistically the mine action projects to have immediate productive use of the land after clearance, or have the local communities benefit from restored villages or roads. In essence, maximizing the payoffs of mine action requires a high level of cooperation and coordination.

5. Transforming socio-economic benefits into utility functions

In order to study utility maximization of socio-economic benefits of mine action, they need to be translated into qualitative and quantitative payoffs. From a utility theoretic point of view this is a key utility indicator and will be very important in establishing for the recipient and donor countries the resource allocation criteria and prioritization of mine action activities. This requires the development of socio-economic utility functions for the normative modelling chapter. The normative modelling needs also to address the requirement to develop these utility functions in harmony with national economic and development plans of action.¹²⁴ Figure II.4 illustrates the basic benefit-cost relationship. A workable concept needs to be based on net-values or real utilities.

6. Qualitative versus quantitative utility functions

A qualitative assessment of socio-economic benefits has the advantage of being rather simple to administer. It also allows the incorporation of the many intangible, direct and indirect socio-economic benefits of mine action. Mine action prioritization can take place even when credible numeric data is not available or applicable. This type of benefits could even include traumatic or psychological costs of a population living in constant fear. As explained before, there is no monetary value, which could quantify the human cost and suffering of mine victims, at least not in an ethically responsible manner.

¹²³ BYRD and GILDESTAD. (2001). *Socio-Economic Impact of Mine Action in Afghanistan*, A Cost-Benefit Analysis, 2001, World Bank funded study, Internet. Available at [http://lnweb18.worldbank.org/SAR/sa.nsf/Attachments/9/\\$File/mines.pdf](http://lnweb18.worldbank.org/SAR/sa.nsf/Attachments/9/$File/mines.pdf), accessed on 25 April 2005, p.73

¹²⁴ UN Document A/RES/58/127, operational paragraph 17 from UN resolution on ‘Assistance in mine action’, Internet. Available at <http://www.un.org/Depts/dhl/resguide/r58.htm>, accessed on 20 July 2005

Also there are no tangible parameters or unambiguous quantifiers for internal stability and security (refugee/IDP return, regional unification, DDR...). Conversely, the quantitative approach can promote a better understanding of the mine action costs versus benefits but is inevitably mathematically complex, depending on which methodology is used. It has, however, the advantage to provide at macro level (e.g. donors) tangible insights in mine action prioritization. However, numeric data needs to be credible and preferably standardized in order to allow in-country and cross-country comparison. The “jump-starting” of an economy once paralyzed by landmines is an often heard argument during donor conferences. This becomes even more convincing if this can be staffed by numerical data or used as part of a prioritization and decision-making process.

7. Minimax game against “nature”

Fig. II.4: Socio-economic benefits: benefit-cost ratio

In game theoretic terms it is minimizing the maximum expected loss, or in this context the socio-economic impact, which recalls the *minimax* description provided earlier. Minimax theory has been extended to decisions where there is no other player, but where the consequences of decisions depend on unknown facts. As touched upon earlier, a suitable approach is to interpret this as a game against *nature*,¹²⁵ whereby the impact of the environment on the local population needs to be studied in probabilistic terms.

However, this is significantly different from Von Neumann’s original *minimax theorem*,¹²⁶ only working under the following conditions: there are two players, both players are rational and desire to win to avoid a loss, it is a zero-sum game and, thus, theoretically no cooperation is possible. Contrary to the minimax theorem, this game against *nature* has in effect only one player who has more than the only two choices or strategies, without having perfect knowledge of all the possible moves of the game, which can be played multiple times. Indeed, maximizing utilities and minimizing loss or costs will be a continuous objective or challenge throughout the lifecycle of a mine action programme.

Fig. II.5: A theoretic example of the costs versus benefits during the lifecycle of a mine action programme

Figure II.5 presents a baseline case of the build-up of costs and benefits of a mine action programme.¹²⁷ Initially the investments and upfront payments of mine clearance equipment and other mine action activities outweigh the socio-economic benefits (in red), resulting in high clearance costs. As soon as emergency or high priority clearance can take place, considerable socio-economic benefits are generated. This causes the cumulative effect of

¹²⁵ Minimax, Internet. Available at <http://www.bigpedia.com/encyclopedia/Minimax>, accessed on 17 January 2007

¹²⁶ Minimax Strategy, Internet. Available at <http://www.charleswarner.us/MinimaxStrategy.htm>, accessed on 25 January 2007

¹²⁷ Baseline case illustration from ‘A Study of Socio-Economic Approaches to Mine Action’. (2001). UNDP/GICHD Publication, Geneva, p.56

these benefits to rise quickly. After several years a break-even of the costs is reached on an annual basis versus the benefits, so many more years later a break-even of the cumulated benefits could be reached versus the total program cost. In summary, a good ratio of benefits versus costs makes a mine action programme attractive for all stakeholders and should be continuously reviewed according to the changing “*nature*” of a mine-infested environment.

8. Utility; discount factor δ

A discount factor for expected utility or socio-economic benefits informs or indicates how much a decision maker prefers payoffs or rewards now over payoffs later. In most game theoretic literature the discount factor is typically written δ , with $0 < \delta < 1$. The discounted value of a socio-economic payoff can be determined by reducing its value by the appropriate discount factor per unit of time between the time when the payoff is to be valued to the time of the cash flow. The higher the δ , the higher the payoffs in the future need to be for the decision maker in order that they are preferred above current payoffs. This is analogue to possible discounting effects which could result in the loss of cooperation (minimax theorem).

Most often the discount factor is expressed as an annual rate. To calculate the net present value of a socio-economic payoff, it is divided by one plus the discount rate for each period of time that will pass. When payoffs are projected in the future, they need to be reduced mathematically to obtain the net present payoffs or values for the socio-economic benefits of mine action. This will be an essential element of consideration during the normative modelling and case-study. As part of the *ethical approach*, no discounting effects will be considered in reference with the human cost or lives potentially saved from mine accidents. It would also complicate matters endlessly if decision-making would be based on prioritising mine clearance in country A in case statistics would prove an equal number of mine accidents could be avoided one year sooner in country B.

b. Deductions

1. Key points

- ☞ Significant possibilities and opportunities exist to deduct quantitative and qualitative indicators related to the *cumulative impact* caused by landmines/ERW and the lasting social and economic consequences. This measurement of the impact of landmines will be essential for the *ranking or prioritization* of mine action projects or programmes.
- ☞ Socio-economic benefits of mine action should be a key element in decision-making at each political level. At national or field level it could allow for direct and local prioritization of mine action projects, at higher levels it could provide cross-country resource allocation guidance.
- ☞ Mine action socio-economic benefits can be recurrent, cumulative or non-cumulative and are mostly of the “*cost reduction*” type; e.g. *maximizing* mine action socio-economic *benefits* equals *minimizing* the socio-economic *impact* of landmines. In this context, a quantitative approach is generally preferred but often mathematically complex or not possible due to weak metrics or poor availability of credible data. Hence, workable utility functions need to be determined in the normative modelling phase.
- ☞ “*Human cost*” needs to be disaggregated from “socio-economic impact/benefits” and considered separately in terms of criteria selection for normative modelling. This avoids “*exuberant pragmatism*” whenever ethical issues need to be considered, e.g. no calculation of the “utility or economic value” of a human life.
- ☞ A game theoretic *best response*, minimizing the maximum loss - *minimax*, is both subject to probabilistic risk and discounting factors. Risk factors are crucial for effective decision-making in mine action; therefore, they need to be studied more in detail when analysing the next

preamble paragraph. High discount effects require higher future payoffs to be preferred above current payoffs. No discount factor will be considered regarding the reduction of “*human cost*”.

2. Possible indicators and criteria

The assessment of relevant socio-economic aspects indicates that the related payoffs and set of goals and indicators will substantially contribute to conclusive findings regarding the politics of mine action. Socio-economics will also be instrumental to formulate recommendations to increase the effectiveness of the global response and how the impact of the landmine problem can be alleviated. The goals and indicators addressed below cover the socio-economics to a large extent, although it is not an exhaustive list. As will be illustrated in the Afghanistan case-study, *country specific characteristics can require unique socio-economic impact indicators*. It will serve as a concrete example on how it influences the politics, policy and implementation of mine action activities. The importance of undertaking multi-sector assessments and surveys to better define the nature, scope and impact of the landmine problem in affected countries will then become more evident.

Based on the goal and set of indicators below, criteria are deduced which can evaluate concretely the economic recovery of cleared land and cost reduction in terms of reduced refugee/IDP support since returns can be accelerated to their cleared areas of origin, cleared km of road network avoiding extra transportation costs. Often the economic recovery of cleared areas (in km²) of agricultural and grazing land, irrigation channels, housing area will deliver the highest tangible and cumulative effects.

Although “*human cost*” has been separated from the “*socio-economic*” impact, there are important medical costs involved which may have a significant impact on the often fragile healthcare system. This socio-economic aspect is, therefore, integrated in the criteria below. The deduction, however, of other “*human cost*” related criteria is deferred to more applicable preamble paragraphs hereafter.

Goal	Indicator
Obtain socio-economic benefits through mine action and/or alleviate the socio-economic impact of landmines	Number of resettled refugees or IDP's
	Restoration of km road network and reduction in travel costs
	Restored access to productive land, drinking water and other water sources, residential area, to public administrative and community buildings
	Restoration of sq km productive farming land and grazing land
	Number of farming jobs created/reinstated through mine action
	Reduced travel times/travels costs
	Disturbance of social interactions at community level
	Restoration of irrigation systems in km or sq km
	Restoration of sq km residential area and social infrastructure
	Number of livestock killed by landmines
	Number of removed blockages to humanitarian aid

Criterion 8	Level of landmine impact on freedom of movement – returns of IDPs & refugees
Criterion 9	Level of landmine impact on the road network
Criterion 10	Level of landmine impact on productive land, water and irrigation sources
Criterion 11	Level of landmine impact on residential area and/or public buildings
Criterion 12	Level of landmine impact on mine-affected grazing land and livestock
Criterion 13	Number of mine victims requiring medical assistance
Criterion 14	Socio-economic impact of mine victims on the health care system

D. Preamble Paragraph 4: Threat/risk postulation in mine action

Bearing in mind the serious threat that mines and other unexploded ordnance pose to the safety, health and lives of local civilian populations, as well as of personnel participating in humanitarian, peacekeeping and rehabilitation programmes and operations,

a. Analysis

1. The long-lasting and variable effects of a multifaceted threat

The hideous and indiscriminate characteristics of landmines can exert higher or greater threat levels long after the ending of armed conflict. A spike in post-conflict economic activities or demographic shifts due to refugee/IDP returns can be endangered or hindered due to the multifaceted landmine threat. Hence, this preamble paragraph initiates the complexity of landmine threats, which implies multiple criteria decision-making under risk.

A national mine action policy or prioritization of mine action tasks may be viable in one year, but require an extensive revision the next year. It triggers again a particular game theoretic aspect: the unavoidable interdependency of decision makers with the element *nature*, which incorporates environmental factors or the rather unpredictable behaviour of an affected population adapting to a mine-infested environment.

2. Landmine threat versus risk

At first, the preamble paragraph mentions only the landmine threat which should not be confused with mine risks. The latter is to be linked with behaviour, which determines the probability that the threat will cause harm. In the same threat environment, uninformed or dangerous behaviour can significantly increase the risk and number of landmine accidents compared to low or zero risk behaviour. The reduction of these risks is obviously a key objective of *Mine Risk Education* (MRE). The analysis presented below focuses on the behavioural characteristics of the affected population and how the perception of the threat influences the risks of target groups assumed more vulnerable to mine accidents.

3. Perceived threat versus actual or objective threat

Threat postulation of landmines and unexploded ordnance is subject to the specifics of the affected environment and different types of landmines and unexploded ordnance. The socio-economic conditions within the mine-affected State itself are more important. It is essential to make a clear distinction between the actual or objective threat and the perceived or subjective threat.

In the next few paragraphs, a detailed categorization is provided. The outgoing threats of one specific contaminated area can be perceived in a significantly different way by the different groups summed up in this preamble paragraph. Local civilian populations will likely experience and perceive the threats differently from personnel participating in humanitarian, peacekeeping and rehabilitation programs and operations. The latter will more likely experience mandate-specific threats to their safety, health and lives. Complex mandates in high threat/risk environments can lead to extreme consequences if treat is incorrectly perceived. In the past there are notorious cases where threat perception went awfully wrong with devastating consequences. The 1968 Vietnam *My Lai massacre* committed by US soldiers on hundreds of unarmed Vietnamese civilians, mostly women and children, was a mistaken attack on what was perceived as a Viet Cong stronghold.¹²⁸ Also the

¹²⁸ Crime Library – The My Lai massacre, Internet. Available on http://www.crimelibrary.com/notorious_murders/mass/lai/index_1.html, accessed on 29 December 2006.

Iraqi quagmire has gravely affected world conscience how modern warfare continues to produce war crimes due to a wrong perception or understanding of the threat. US Marines killed 24 Iraqi civilians in 2005 during a bloody, door-to-door sweep in the town of Haditha that came after one of their comrades was killed.

“At a news conference to announce the charges, military officials would not say what they believe prompted the killings. But investigators have raised the possibility that the men went on a rampage in a fury over the roadside bombing that killed Lance Cpl. Miguel Terrazas of El Paso, Texas, and wounded two other Marines. Defence attorneys have disputed that, saying their clients were doing what they had been trained to do: responding to a perceived threat with legitimate force.”¹²⁹

4. Categorization of threat perception by a mine-affected population

The grid in figure II.6 illustrates how one could distinguish four categories. It pictures how the perceived threat relates to the objective threat with varying levels of socio-economic impact on the affected population. In this grid it is important to highlight the evolutionary dynamics between the objective and the perceived threat. This generates the question whether one can one assume that the perceived threat will converge towards the objective threat due to increased knowledge. For the purpose of this analysis, this convergence is called: evolving towards “*threat equality*”, whereby the perceived threat is correct or equal to the objective threat. This requires to revisit *Bayesian decision theory* whereby:

Fig. II.6: Objective threat versus Perceived threat

“Deciders are often uncertain about the consequences of their actions, we represent their uncertainty by subjective probabilities over the possible states of the world. These probabilities represent a deciders’ degree of belief about the likelihood of each different state. The higher the subjective probability of a state, the more likely is the decider to believe that state is the true state of the world. These beliefs should change as a decider gains new information about the state of the world”¹³⁰

Threat equality could be accelerated through a variety of factors in an effort to align the perceived threat with the objective one, or in game theoretic terms align subjective beliefs with the *true state of the world*. The table below ranks the relationship between perceived and objective threats from inducing low to high risk exposure to the threats. For example, a good mine action programme will seek to speed up the natural learning process of the affected population on living in a heavily affected environment. Landmine threat assessments or surveys could in particular

¹²⁹ WATKINS, T. (2006, 21 December). Marines charged in Iraqi civilian deaths, Associated Press Writer, Internet. Available at http://news.yahoo.com/s/ap/20061222/ap_on_re_us/marines_haditha, accessed on 21 December 2006

¹³⁰ MORROW, J. (1994). *Game Theory for Political Scientists*, New Jersey: Princeton, p.163

contribute to the resolution of category 2 or 4, shown below, of threat perception problems, whereby the perceived threat opposes the actual or objective threat.

Category	Objective Threat	Perceived Threat	Description	Risks	Impact
1	Low	Low	Correct perception of a low threat, resulting in a limited but correct adaptation of behaviour with limited socio-economic impact.	Low	Low
2	Low	High	Although the risk of mine related accidents is very low, overreaction of the local population has the consequence that too prudent behaviour hinders the normal socio-economic activities of the affected communities. The following saying is applicable: <i>"the only thing we have to fear is fear itself"</i> .	Low	Medium
3	High	High	This is the case of a significant mine and/or UXO threat whereby a correct perception exists of the safety risks. It is the case where the local community correctly deals with their affected environment and tries to reduce as much as possible the socio-economic impact.	Medium	High
4	High	Low	Most dangerous situation with potentially the highest risks for the safety of the local population. Due to insufficient awareness of the present mine threats, behaviour of the local population is not adapted causing high exposure to the threats.	High	Medium

Table II.2: Objective versus perceived threat and socio-economic impact

A wrongly perceived threat can be restored through a targeted information campaign and Mine Risk Education (MRE). In this regard, it is important to understand the root causes of why the perceived threat diverges from *threat equality*. Often it will be a complex mix of factors but two of them are undeniable, the objective threat will inevitably decrease following effective mine clearance efforts, the risks will decrease with effective MRE. These factors will be further addressed with the analysis of the next preamble paragraph, in particular how targeted efforts can accelerate the reduction of human cost.

5. Game theoretic aspects of Bayesian decision-making

The above analysis of threats and risks, together with the discussion of the previous preamble paragraph, are a variation of a theme already discussed: how to formulate a *best response* to the quite unpredictable effects of the game theoretic element *nature*? Although there are many interactions of numerous stakeholders with a mine infested environment, in its simplified form it can again be viewed as a theory of *one person games*, or a *game of a single player against nature*. Here too, aspects of both decision theory and game theory need to be assessed together. The focus is on optimal prioritization of mine action and the unifying formation of perceptions or beliefs. Moreover, it needs to recognize the complex evolutionary character of the learning process of a mine-affected population. When the belief aspects related to the subjective appraisal of the involved risks strongly deviate from the objective situation, a negative impact can be observed either way. The absence of *"threat equality"*, specifically defined for this purpose, confirms what Mark Twain once said: *"What gets us into trouble is not what we don't know; it's what we know for sure that just ain't so"*.

The most widely used form of decision theory also argues that preferences among risky strategies can be described by the traditional maximization of the expected value of a numerical utility function, where utility may depend on a number of things, but in situations of interest to economists often depends on money income.¹³¹ Probability theory is heavily used in order to

¹³¹ LEVINE, D., Department of Economics, UCLA, What is Game Theory?, Internet. Available at <http://levine.sscnet.ucla.edu/general/whatis.htm>, accessed on 12 November 2006

represent the uncertainty of outcomes, and Bayes' theorem or Law is frequently used to model the way in which new information is used to revise beliefs. This study's particular interest is to evolve in the advanced modelling phase and case-study from game or decision theoretic principles to effective and reliable multiple criteria decision analysis. This needs to point out how best to acquire new information to make complex decisions in an ever-changing environment. Bayes' theorem works well in this regard since it balances methodologically between subjective and objective information, and similarly, *prior and posterior beliefs*.

Prior beliefs or probabilities are the subjective probabilities of each *state of the world* before considering new information. Updated beliefs through new information are called *posterior beliefs or probabilities*.¹³² Hence, let A be a *state of the world* and B an *event*. The probability of B given A, written below as $P_{(B|A)}$, specifies the likelihood that B will occur given that A is the state of the world. For this reason, Bayes' theorem uses the conditional probabilities of events given $P_{(B|A)}$ to deduce the conditional probabilities of states given events $P_{(A|B)}$.¹³³ The conditional probability form of Bayes' theorem, states, therefore, in a simple mathematical formula that the posterior beliefs are a logic function of the likelihood of the prior beliefs.

It can be anticipated that Bayes' theorem could be helpful to study evolving beliefs regarding the state of a mine-affected nation. In the context of this study, beliefs are indeed based on conditional probabilities, e.g. mine action authorities decide to intervene in certain affected areas because accidents or incidents prove for them where the probability of mine accidents is higher. Earlier it was explained how Bayes' Theorem describes the relationships that exist within an array of simple and conditional probabilities. At the beginning of the analysis of this preamble paragraph, the complexities were addressed of evolving perceptions as more information becomes available. The landmine survey process is one of the primary tools to obtain a better understanding of a mine-affected environment and related threats/risks. There are different types of survey operations, but for the purpose of this example a process of general mapping of the mine contamination is considered.¹³⁴

The Bayesian aspects of more complex prior and posterior beliefs on mine accidents are illustrated in the example below and coupled to a decision-making timeframe. Hence, let A be a perceived *state of the world* and B a number of mine accidents with *nature* the array of unpredictable elements which could cause a mine accident and, therefore, change afterwards our belief on the *state of the world*. The probability of B given A, written below as $P_{(B|A)}$, specifies the likelihood that B, a number of mine accidents, will occur given that A is the *state of the world*. For this reason, Bayes' theorem uses the conditional probabilities of events given states $P_{(B|A)}$ to deduce the conditional probabilities of states given events $P_{(A|B)}$. $P_{(A)}$ is the *prior belief* or probability of the *state of the world*. It is "*prior*" in the sense that it does not take into account any information about B. $P_{(A|B)}$ is the conditional probability of A, given B, also called the posterior probability because it is derived

¹³² MORROW, J. (1994). *Game Theory for Political Scientists*, New Jersey: Princeton , p.163

¹³³ Vasserstats, Faculty of Vasser, Internet. Available at <http://faculty.vassar.edu/lowry/bayes.html>, accessed on 30 November 2006

¹³⁴ There is a distinction to be made between a *general survey* (=broad identification of landmine contamination), *technical survey* (=detailed survey assessing the best mine action response), *landmine impact survey* (=survey focusing on human cost and socio-economic impact) and ultimately the possibility of a *post-clearance survey* (=verification on how cleared land is put back to use). From GICHD Publication. (2003). *A Guide to Mine Action*, Geneva, p.20-40

from or depends upon B, the observed number of mine accidents. This reasoning can be pictorially substantiated as follows:

Fig. II.7: Bayesian approach on *prior* and *posterior beliefs* or probabilities of mine accidents

Based on the information collected on mine accidents over period $[t = -4, t = 0]$ a *prior belief* or probability of future mine accidents was determined: $P_{(A)}$. This probability was used to inform decision-making and allocate mine action resources. For explanatory purposes, this example assumes that through assessment and statistical regression analysis of predictors of mine accidents, it was believed that effective mine action could lower the number of mine accidents from the observed 10 accidents during $[t = -4, t = 0]$ to zero during $[t = 0, t = 4]$. However, events B indicate otherwise: not zero but 5 mine accidents were observed during that timeframe. This new information results through Bayes' theorem in a *posterior belief* which is very different from the *prior beliefs*. This should affect decision-making at $[t = 4]$ or earlier and logically result in allocating additional mine action resources or increase the effectiveness of the current efforts. This process can be repeated at regular intervals, whenever stocktaking of the beliefs on the *state of the world* is deemed necessary. The following expression of Bayes' theorem, with for A two possible states of the world – either it is state A or it is not – given prior events B, can be formulated as shown.¹³⁵

$$P_{(A|B)} = \frac{P_{(A)}P_{(B|A)}}{P_{(A)}P_{(B|A)} + P_{(\text{not } A)}P_{(B|\text{not } A)}}$$

Further study of the possible contribution of statistical (regression) analysis and parameters is required to support this approach in order to build up *prior beliefs* or probabilities on the likelihood of mine accidents. The second research phase of this study is, however, the right place to discuss the statistical aspects of *nature* as part of the modelling effort. At this stage, properly understood, Bayes' theorem is the fundamental mathematical law governing the process of logical inference, thereby determining what degree of confidence one can have, in various possible conclusions, based on new events or evidence available. This is exactly the process of predictive reasoning in game theory; therefore, to arrive at a logically defensible prediction one could use Bayes' theorem in modelling to support multiple criteria decision-making.

In conclusion, Bayesian decision theory provides a way to explore how information affects or alters beliefs and perceptions, and ultimately, strategic choices. It is especially valuable to study how new information or events could affect the strategy or decision-making of the actors in this study. Hence the following most relevant question: which source of information is most likely to affect a decision given a choice among possible sources? The best sources of information will steer one's belief and decision from what would be chosen in the absence of this information. It is clear now how Bayes' theorem allows updating the actor's subjective perception of the state of a mine-affected nation. If new events or information considerably changes the existing beliefs, then an important impact on the decision-making process needs to be expected. To end on a light note, when asked what would affect his decision-making in the future, the British Prime Minister Harold Macmillan once famously said: "*events, dear boy, events*".

¹³⁵ Deducted from Bayes Theorem description in MORROW, J. (1994). *Game Theory for Political Scientists*, New Jersey: Princeton, p.164

6. Utility functions and decision-making under risk

Any decision-making process includes some risk, where the most obvious one is failing to take the most optimal decision. When considering mine action decisions human life is at stake, hence, the risks cannot be higher. Wrong strategic choices or policy making could have irreparable consequences. The previous paragraphs discussed applicable game theoretic dilemmas to reflect the high politics, to a certain extent in the abstract. Mine action programme managers in the field, however, face the very concrete decision-making dilemmas, whereby risk taking can hold them directly accountable.

Safe mine clearance operations are inevitably slow, since they must ensure that every single mine is located and destroyed. Often the local population does not have the luxury and patience to wait for the mine action community to clear their land. Mine clearance perceived as too slow often results in the local population themselves undertaking mine clearance efforts, further aggravating safety and security concerns. Programme managers could, therefore, face the dilemma to accelerate demining operations, implying increased risks for their deminers or aim for maximum safety, implying slower mine clearance operations, and possibly increase the risk of mine accidents for the local population. Hence, the *mine action dilemmas* in the field can be quite more confrontational than any high level decision-making under risk.¹³⁶ The basic principle remains however, the same: the higher the risks involved, the more utility is expected to justify the decision. This is as much a standard in economics as in politics, irrespective the decision-making level under consideration.

Fig. II.8: Expected utility and effects of risk

A necessary additional nuance is the real world subdivision of decision makers that are risk averse, risk neutral or risk acceptant. According to figure II.8¹³⁷, three mine action programme managers face the above cited *mine action dilemma* of weighing the risks for mine accidents of his deminers versus risks for the local populations. One assumes they have coinciding expected utilities and outcomes for the worst and best decision. It is the decision-making in between which characterizes them. The three different types of theoretic utility functions are *concave downward* for *risk-averse* decision-making ($U_{(RAV)}$ = risk averse expected utility), *linear* for being *risk-neutral* ($=U_{(RN)}$) and *concave upward* for *risk-acceptant* ($=U_{(RAC)}$) decision-making. The nuances of decision-making in between worst and best outcome clearly indicate the much higher expected utility the risk averse programme manager will require versus the same decision to be taken by a risk acceptant programme manager. In concrete terms of the above example, the risk averse decision maker will need to have much better expectations on reducing the number of mine victims amongst the local population before he will undertake riskier demining operations with his deminers speeding up clearance. Mine clearance rates and mine accidents are often referred to as key parameters for the effectiveness of a mine action programme. Although primarily operational factors, they tend to have considerable strategic impact.

¹³⁶ WENKOFF, Joe; Technical Advisor/Program Manager, Mine Action Program, Asmara, Eritrea. Based on a personal discussion at the occasion of the Meeting of States Parties at Geneva in 2003.

¹³⁷ MORROW, J. (1994). *Game Theory for Political Scientists*, New Jersey: Princeton, p.37

In addition to earlier Bayesian thinking, here too the game theoretic approach can be further refined by treating this type of decision-making as a game against *nature* whereby the decision maker tries to minimize the maximum loss. *Minimax theorem* has been applied in an n-player context. Similar to the socio-economic impact of landmines discussed in the previous preamble paragraph, the *minimax* theorem is once again extended to decisions where there is no other player, but where the consequences of decisions depend on unknown facts. The additional element brought into the equation is how much risk a decision maker is ready to accept to minimize his loss. For example, deciding to prospect for mine clearance entails a cost which will be wasted if there are no landmines present, however, if there are, a significant reduction of human cost could follow.

This principle of decision-making under risk will remain important throughout this dissertation as the normative model will seek to reduce the socio-economic impact, human cost and threats to peacebuilding. This principle recalls the aspect of *intersection optimization* as portrayed in the Venn-diagram of the methodology plan of this dissertation. Hence, the best response/risk mitigation should result in the best combination of *human cost reduction*, *socio-economic benefits* and *peacekeeping/building effects*. In this regard, the envisaged normative model should have a build-in flexibility to allow for the varying levels of risk decision makers are ready to take.

b. Deductions

1. Key points

- ☞ The analysis of this preamble paragraph was instrumental to highlight the socio-economic impact and human cost of landmines in light of decision-making under risk. It underscored that landmines/ERW can cause post-conflict threat levels to be higher than threats during the conflict itself.
- ☞ Threat levels are inherent to an environment affected by landmines/ERW whilst risk levels depend on the interaction and behaviour of the population with their infested surroundings. Studying these threats and risks should result in risk management through optimal prioritization of mine action activities.
- ☞ Perceived versus actual or objective threats are fundamental parameters to describe and predict the behaviour of the affected population. In this regard, *threat equality* has been defined as a complete convergence of the perceived understanding of the dangers of landmines with the objective state of the world or landmine contamination. This *threat equality* can be accelerated through a variety of efforts to narrow the gap between the perceived and actual threats, or in game theoretic terms align subjective beliefs with the *true state of the world*.
- ☞ Concepts like “*nature*” and “*state of the world*” can game theoretically transform a one-player game to a two-player game taking into account probabilistic factors and decision-making under risk.
- ☞ Through *prior and posterior beliefs* Bayesian decision theory provides a way to explore how information affects or alters beliefs and perceptions, and ultimately, strategic choices. Bayes’ theorem allows for coupling beliefs to a set of strategies and hence, provide a refinement of Nash equilibriums.
- ☞ Similar to the preceding preamble paragraph, the game theoretic aspects can be largely summarized in terms of best responses aiming to minimize the maximum loss. The new element is the application of Bayesian decision theory to explain how a set of beliefs, based on the current understanding of the mine-affected environment, is attached to the possible strategic choices of the decision maker. The equilibrium in a post-conflict environment has both the decision maker as well as “*nature*” benefiting most of a *minimax* approach. Consequently, there are in this context no forces which could make the decision maker change his position unilaterally.

- ☞ The categorization of being *risk averse*, *neutral* and *acceptant* is particularly helpful to explain the *minimax* theorem in the context of integrating the element of risk in multiple criteria decision analysis. Moreover, envisaged normative modelling should have a built-in flexibility or sensitivity analysis to reflect or incorporate the varying risks decision makers are ready to take. Probabilistic factors and other statistical aspects of risk and threat factors need, therefore, to be studied in Phase-II.
- ☞ Mine *clearance rates* and mine *accidents* are regarded as key parameters for the effectiveness of a mine action programme and need to be incorporated in normative modelling.

2. Possible indicators and criteria

Although the ultimate goal is to remove all landmine threats, the deducted goal and indicators envisage in a first priority the speedy reduction of the risks for the affected population. A clear understanding of the actual threats is, therefore, a prerequisite to have effective mine action programmes, and this is further reflected in the deduction of the three criteria.

Goal	Indicator
Remove all landmine threats	Number of affected people receiving risk education (MRE)
	Community participation in landmine impact assessments
	Effective Threat Assessments which lead to targeted responses through mine clearance, marking/fencing
	Targeting change in behaviour of most vulnerable groups through gender/age-disaggregated procedures

Risk reduction and reducing the number of mine victims through targeted efforts will be studied more in depth during the analysis of the key elements in the following preamble paragraph. Deducing relevant evaluation criteria is directly related to the indicators in terms of threat reduction and targeting of risk reduction efforts, albeit with some caution that certain indicators such as the number of people receiving MRE does not warrant the effectiveness of the risk reduction effort.

Criterion 15	Level of prioritization and targeting of mine action efforts
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E. Preamble Paragraph 5: Mine victims – targeted efforts to accelerate human cost reduction

Encouraged by the reduction in the number of new mine victims, but reiterating its dismay at the existing high number of victims of mines and other unexploded ordnance, especially among civilian populations, including women and children, and recalling in this context its resolution 57/190 of 18 December 2002 and Commission on Human Rights resolutions 2003/49 of 23 April 2003, on the human rights of persons with disabilities, and 2003/86 of 25 April 2003, on the rights of the child,¹³⁸

a. Analysis

1. On a positive note: the plunging numbers of mine victims

This preamble paragraph starts surprisingly by highlighting the reduction in the number of victims of mines, whilst one should expect more alarming language. Reducing the number of mine victims is undoubtedly the main incentive to increase or at least consolidate political will in support of a total ban. Numbers of victims and casualties are also the most effective part of the well constructed campaign to influence public opinion and key players. A multitude of sources cites that tens of millions of landmines in nearly 60 countries cause well over 10,000 casualties each year, down from significantly higher casualty numbers the years before.¹³⁹ This has led to the popular dubbing of landmines as slow weapons of mass destruction and use of other catchy statements that in the last 55 years, anti-personnel mines have caused more deaths and injuries than nuclear, biological and chemical weapons combined.¹⁴⁰ These framing methods and quantifications often have a strong immediate effect but tend to erode over time.¹⁴¹ Quite often they are not based on solid data or responsible statistical analysis as shown below.

“A second important plank of the campaign’s rallying cry was “one landmine victim every 20 minutes” or, variously, 24,000 or 26,000 new mine victims every year. But the estimate was based on an extrapolation of one hospital in Afghanistan at a critical period in the repatriation of refugees. Only if the victims of all explosive remnants of war are included does it become a more credible estimate (though natural reduction and the impact of mine action has probably since reduced the true number, whatever it is).”¹⁴²

The Landmine Monitor Report indicated in 2002 one of the most significant reductions in the annual estimate of new mine victims, down from 26,000 to 15,000 per year.¹⁴³ The real figure might be higher. Again, accurate data is relatively scarce and there is possibly a considerable underreporting of accidents, particularly those during conflict, in the immediate post-conflict chaos, in remote areas, and involving children and women. However, it is also important to point out there is global progress in the reduction of new mine victims. It is exactly the purpose of the main donor countries to stress that assistance in mine action causes the number of mine victims to drop significantly. The correct framing of the human cost of the landmine tragedy is, however, a controversial issue which will be addressed from another angle when expanding on public awareness in preamble paragraph 22.

2. Are woman and children high risk groups?

Simply being a child, with a child’s natural curiosity and desire to play, touch, seek and explore, causes additional risks in a mined environment. Ordinary daily activities such as herding livestock, fetching water, or foraging for food or firewood can be deadly. Often unaware of all the

¹³⁸ See Official Records of the Economic and Social Council, 2003, Supplement No. 3 (E/2003/23), chap. II, sect. A.

¹³⁹ Based on the numbers mentioned in consecutive Landmine Monitors.

¹⁴⁰ Anti-personnel landmines - Friend or Foe? A study of the military use and effectiveness of anti-personnel mines, ICRC, March 1996.

¹⁴¹ Other more recent examples of similar political use are the number of casualties in Operation Enduring Freedom and Iraqi Freedom.

¹⁴² MASLEN, S. (2004). *Mine Action after Diana – Myths and Realities*, United Kingdom, p.27

¹⁴³ ICBL (2002). *Landmine Monitor Report 2002 - Toward a Mine-Free World: International Campaign to Ban Landmines*. New York

dangers, especially children seek landmines and other explosive remnants of war to use or sell their explosive or metal content.¹⁴⁴

In a similar post-conflict environment, a child is far more likely to die as a result of a mine blast than an adult;¹⁴⁵ and a child who survives is less likely to have access to rehabilitation, unlikely to have access to school, and almost certain to be vulnerable into adulthood. As a tragic spin-off, children and women are also to become more vulnerable if other family members are killed or injured. Therefore, States are requested by the UN resolution to develop and support national programs, where appropriate, in cooperation with the relevant bodies of the United Nations system and relevant regional, governmental and non-governmental organizations, to reduce the risks posed by landmines and other unexploded ordnance, including among women and children.¹⁴⁶ Other legal instruments related to Human Rights and especially on the rights of the child are focusing equally on the particular vulnerabilities of women and children.

Member States, the United Nations system, international and regional organizations and relevant non-governmental organizations are requested to take further action along the same lines to mainstream a gender perspective and integrate gender and age-appropriate considerations¹⁴⁷ in all aspects of mine-action programming, particularly including programmes to reduce the number of child victims and relieve their plight.¹⁴⁸

So, in direct answer to the question of this section, women and children tend to be high risk groups due to their exploring activities of the environment, but it is not a general rule for each mine-affected country. High risk groups are generally portraying high risk behaviour, and it is in this context that the effort should be targeted, either in terms of mine clearance, Mine Risk Education and/or victim assistance.

3. UXO and ERW: more lethal than landmines?!

In case of repeated offensive military operations, the usage of cluster bombs or high quantities of other types of ammunition can dramatically change the situation in a mine-affected country and hence, necessitate a reprioritization of mine action activities. This was for example very much the case in Afghanistan at the start of Operation Enduring Freedom. In 2002, it required a temporary but significant shift in focus from mine clearance to UXO or ERW clearance. Unconfirmed sources stated that after the intense coalition attacks, there were more UXO than landmine victims.¹⁴⁹ Hence, the above question cannot be answered due to the absence of disaggregated data.

Recent conflicts, in particular the usage of cluster munitions by Israel against the Hamas forces in Lebanon will further enhance the knowledge of the mine action community on the devastating effects and post-conflict impact of ERW. The current media attention, in combination with certain countries becoming increasingly proactive in their efforts to install a ban on the usage of

¹⁴⁴ This risk behaviour increases when children live in extreme poverty with cases in Afghanistan, Sudan and Cambodia; reported in consecutive versions of the Landmine Monitor.

¹⁴⁵ Since the majority of anti-personnel landmines is designed to maim rather than kill, the blast of an antipersonnel landmine does not aim to harm the vulnerable organs of an adult. A child, however, has its vulnerable body parts much closer to the ground; therefore, the effects of landmines on children are generally more lethal.

¹⁴⁶ UN Document A/RES/58/127, operational paragraph 3 from UN resolution on 'Assistance in mine action', Internet. Available at <http://www.un.org/Depts/dhl/resguide/r58.htm>, accessed on 20 July 2005

¹⁴⁷ UN Publication on Gender mainstreaming in mine action, Internet. Available at <http://www.mineaction.org>, accessed on 10 July 2006

¹⁴⁸ UN Document A/RES/58/127, operational paragraph 10 from UN resolution on 'Assistance in mine action', Internet. Available at <http://www.un.org/Depts/dhl/resguide/r58.htm>, accessed on 20 July 2005

¹⁴⁹ This could never be confirmed due to poor victim data management, partly due to the dire security situation.

cluster bombs - with Belgium again the frontrunner¹⁵⁰ - regularly shifts the attention of the global landmine problem away to a global ERW problem. When addressing the Afghan case-study, other aspects will be explained more in depth regarding the usage of sub-munitions.

“But the same problems were found in Afghanistan as in other instances of cluster bomb use: lack of accuracy in targeting during attacks, large numbers of explosive duds remaining after attacks, and difficulties in clearance. These problems suggest that this weapon has fundamental flaws and should be specifically regulated under international law. We are not arguing for a ban on cluster bombs, [...] what we want is better targeting and technology in order to reduce the humanitarian side effects.”¹⁵¹

4. The more devastating cumulative numbers of mine casualties or survivors

Figures are also scarce for survivors, but high estimates have been circulated by different sources of cumulative numbers of 35,000 amputees in Cambodia, 70,000 in Angola, and by the UNDP Comprehensive Disabled Afghans Program of 200,000 in Afghanistan.¹⁵² This broad range indicates they might be far from correct and are probably systematically overestimated. Nevertheless, they give at least an indication of the suggested scale of the problem. In areas where employment opportunities are minimal, where people with disabilities are stigmatized or a shortage of training and rehabilitation facilities is prevalent, amputees face enormous challenges. In most agrarian societies, the loss of a limb makes it almost impossible for people to work, and women, in particular, are stigmatized, impeding their chances of marriage or having children.

Assistance to mine victims is equally important as assistance in mine action. This requires ample international support for emergency assistance to victims of mines and other unexploded ordnance and for the care, rehabilitation and social and economic reintegration of the victims, and also stresses that such assistance should be integrated into broader public health and socio-economic strategies.¹⁵³ This too is an essential humanitarian goal of the Mine Ban Treaty.

“Article 6 (3) of the Convention calls for States Parties to provide assistance for the care rehabilitation and reintegration of mine victims. This constitutes a vital promise for hundreds of thousands of mine victims around the world, as well as for their families and communities. Keeping this promise is a crucial responsibility of all States Parties, though first and foremost of those whose citizens suffer the tragedy of mine incidents. This is especially the case for those 23 States Parties where there are vast numbers of victims. These States Parties have the greatest responsibility to act, but also the greatest needs and expectations for assistance.”¹⁵⁴

5. Mine victim rate reduction through mine clearance prioritization

The prioritization of a mine action program aims at reducing the number of mine victims as quickly as possible. This requires a balanced approach between mine clearance and the previously discussed MRE. In most programs, mine clearance will absorb the biggest part of the resources, often by a 10 to 1 ratio versus MRE. Notably, even without prioritization of mine action activities, the number of mine victims will experience a non-linear decrease. This is the result of the natural

¹⁵⁰ Belgium has become the first country in the world to ban the manufacture and use of cluster bombs following passage of legislation by a sound majority of its lower house of parliament. The legislation had already passed in the upper house of parliament last July. Human rights organizations such as Handicap International (HI) and Human Rights Watch (HRW) have campaigned against the lethal weapons, which kill and maim thousands of civilians each year in places like Kosovo and Iraq.

¹⁵¹ From: U.S. Cluster Bombs Killed Civilians in Afghanistan -New Report Illustrates Dangers for Iraq, Internet. Available from <http://www.hrw.org/press/2002/12/arms1218.htm>, accessed on 4 July 2006

¹⁵² ICBL 1999, 2000, + U.S. Agency for International Development Bureau for Democracy, Conflict, and Humanitarian Assistance (DCHA) Office of US Foreign Disaster Assistance (OFDA), Angola - Complex Emergency Situation Report #2, Fiscal Year (FY) 2002 - American Red Cross, Internet. Available at <http://www.cambodia.org/clubs/arc>, accessed on 23 March 2006.

¹⁵³ UN Document A/RES/58/127, operational paragraph 8 from UN resolution on ‘Assistance in mine action’, Internet. Available at <http://www.un.org/Depts/dhl/resguide/r58.htm>, accessed on 20 July 2005

¹⁵⁴ Nairobi Action Plan 2005-2009, Internet. Available at www.gichd.ch/fileadmin/pdf/mbc/MSP/6MSP/Nairobi_Action_Plan.pdf, accessed on 11 April 2006, p.5

learning process and actions of the local population dealing with the threats of a mine-affected environment.

Figure II.9 illustrates three theoretic scenarios on how the number of mine victims can digress over time. Scenario ① and ② depict the digression of the number of mine victims when mine clearance is randomly taking place without any prioritization or mine victim related tasking of mine clearance. Although no credible quantifiable research was ever done, it is widely accepted that MRE can significantly accelerate mine-affected population’s learning process to ensure that perceived threats are almost equate to objective threats. Scenario ③ represents a “best-case” scenario with the fastest decline of mine victims due to optimal “high-medium-low” impact prioritization of mine clearance and targeting of MRE. The possible characteristics of the categorization of high, medium and low impact of landmines will be comprehensively addressed later.

Fig. II.9: Digression over time of the number of mine victims

The initial high rate of mine victims during, for example, the massive return of refugees and internally displaced persons to villages abandoned during armed conflict, is followed by a rapid decline in accidents through targeted mine clearance and MRE. This sharp hyperbolic decline is obviously theoretical and will be distorted in the real world due to factors which can reverse temporarily a decline in mine victims, such as post conflict spikes in the number of mine victims through successive and often unanticipated waves of returning refugees or isolated conflicts. Also surges in economic activity or farming can lie at the basis of a sudden increase in mine victims. All of the above justifies a closer study of the best documented case of one of the heaviest mine-affected country in the world, Cambodia.

6. Linkage between conflict and mine/ERW victims

The history of conflict in Cambodia is closely related to the history of the whole region, which has suffered many years from political unrest, tension, colonial and civil wars, and from time to time international border conflicts. The excellent victim data and complex mix of conflicts and warfare, invite studying how mine/ERW victims could be linked to conflict history.

Cambodia's unrest started in particular with World War II, when Cambodia became a victim of international conflicts. However, the most damaging war took place between 1970 and 1975 when

Fig. II.10: History of conflict reflected in the fluctuating numbers of mine/UXO victims in Cambodia

more than a half million tons of air-to-ground bombs were dropped on Cambodia, causing extraordinary high levels of UXO/ERW.¹⁵⁵

The ERW legacy of this activity still traumatizes this nation today as it is assessed there are thousands of unexploded bombs still lying hidden underground. The assessment is not any better regarding landmine contamination. Throughout the three decades of mine laying in Cambodia, it was standard practice to lay much denser minefields than necessary, and to lay them not only in battlegrounds but among civilian communities. Minefield location maps were generally not drawn, and as a result, mine laying frequently took place in areas already-mined. Wet seasons caused mines to move or become buried, which further complicated the task of locating and clearing them.¹⁵⁶

This condensed historic study illustrates the complexity and effects of the usage of landmines, the involvement of myriad mine-users, both State actors and non-State actors. Cambodia is no exception, other significantly affected countries such as Afghanistan, Angola, Laos share a similar fate, although they are poorly recorded compared to Cambodia. The sharp decrease in numbers of victims once the conflict has ceased, as theoretically assumed at the beginning of the analysis, is largely reflected in the graph above, albeit subject to many other variables and depending on the specific circumstances and locations in which mines were used. Cambodia has a zero-mine/ERW victim strategy but nevertheless currently struggles to reduce the numbers to the low hundreds. On 24 February 2006, Cambodia's Mine Awareness Day, their Prime Minister told the nation:

"...we must make a serious effort to decrease the number of mine accidents as much as possible every year, to the extent that the accident rate declines to zero during the next 10 years. ... However... even though our efforts have been greater than ever before, the number of mine accidents has still remained constant, meaning that over the last four years, from 2002 to 2005, the average rate was 842 per year."¹⁵⁷

In conclusion, mine clearance of former battlegrounds might be advancing at a feverish pace in Cambodia, Afghanistan and many other nations, however, if a fast reduction of mine victims is to be achieved, a most refined prioritization of mine action is again a prerequisite. This implies that several volatile parameters need to be taken into account. For Cambodia's population, expected to double within 10 years, demographic expansion and economic growth will be prominent reasons for the increased chance of mine accidents. The second research phase will need to study the best combination of criteria and related sub-criteria to enhance prioritization and to reduce mine/ERW victims as effective as possible.

¹⁵⁵ From the Cambodian Mine Action Center Database, Internet. Available at http://www.camnet.com.kh/cmac/Landmine_UXO.htm, accessed on 8 November 2005

¹⁵⁶ Cambodian Mine Action Centre – Landmine/UXO data, Internet. Available at http://www.camnet.com.kh/cmac/Landmine_UXO.htm, accessed on 2 August 2005

¹⁵⁷ Prime Minister Samdech Hun Sen, address to the nation, Mine Awareness Day, 24 February 2006. 2006 Landmine Monitor, Internet. Available at www.icbl.org/lm, accessed on 10 July 2006

7. The effects of Mine Risk Education

Mine Risk Education has significantly grown in importance over the past years, although it remains very hard to quantify the objective risk reduction in terms or percentages of reduced casualties. MRE and risk reduction requires more study in the field of inferential statistics in combination with multiple criteria decision and sensitivity analysis. The studies, which evaluate the benefits of MRE campaigns, are few and rather hypothetical. There are no comprehensive evaluations which illustrate in quantifiable terms the assumed beneficial impact of MRE. Assumptions of a reduction of 5% in mine victims per year could be considered as rather conservative. This number was used in the World Bank funded study of the socio-economic impact of landmines in Afghanistan.¹⁵⁸

Although the absence of any clear benchmarks or credible assumptions on how MRE could proportionally reduce the number of mine victims, it is a component of mine action which enjoys growing support of the donor community.¹⁵⁹ It is relatively easy to set up, gives high visibility and fits well into an emergency response, e.g. a massive return of refugees receiving MRE before they return to their villages of origin. The important dynamics to understand in this risk education domain is how MRE has a lasting and positive influence on the behaviour of local populations at risk. Too often, high numbers are cited of MRE courses given as a surrogate indicator for its effectiveness. This is similar to attempts to influence or impress donor countries with the number of mines or square kilometres cleared, without addressing the socio-economic benefits.

“Thus, it is not the number of mine awareness “briefings” that are given that determines the success of the program, but the effective and sustained changes in behaviour of the target audience. Similarly, it is not the number of prostheses produced and fitted, but the number still being worn by amputees in the community six to twelve months later that counts.”¹⁶⁰

Even in the most advanced mine action programmes, non-relevant quantifiers are still a way of interaction between mine-affected nations and donors. This is sometimes reinforced in absence of more relevant or representative data, through customary reporting formats and the Landmine Monitor. In this regard it is illustrative how the Landmine Monitor 2006 reports the key developments in Afghanistan since May 2005.

“In May 2006, Afghanistan reported that since signing the Mine Ban Treaty, 65,973 stockpiled mines had been destroyed, including 44,819 since the beginning of 2005. [...] The pace of demining accelerated in 2005; the amount of land demined increased by over one-third to almost 140 square kilometres, despite deteriorating security. [...] Mine Risk Education reached over 1.8 million Afghans and 2,365 communities in 2005. There were 848 new casualties recorded in 2005, maintaining the relatively constant casualty rate of recent years; however, child casualties continued to increase.”¹⁶¹

8. Targeting of mine clearance and MRE

For later prioritization of mine action activities as well as multiple criteria decision analysis, threat and risk data is most valuable to guide decision-making. It leads to the identification of possible ways and means to reduce the human cost and socio-economic impact of landmines. The identified factors which explain risky behaviour could stimulate better targeting of MRE and as required, mine clearance. Indeed, sometimes a well managed MRE-campaign will not modify behaviour if there are strong incentives for the local population to continue risky behaviour, with

¹⁵⁸ BYRD and GILDESTAD. (2001). *Socio-Economic Impact of Mine Action in Afghanistan, A Cost-Benefit Analysis*, World Bank funded study, Internet. Available at [http://lnweb18.worldbank.org/SAR/sa.nsf/Attachments/9/\\$File/mines.pdf](http://lnweb18.worldbank.org/SAR/sa.nsf/Attachments/9/$File/mines.pdf), accessed on 25 April 2005

¹⁵⁹ According to the Landmine Monitor Report (2003), MRE services were provided in an estimated 47 countries in 2002 and 2003—a dramatic increase since the early 1990s, Internet. Available at <http://www.icbl.org/lm>, accessed on 22 July 2005

¹⁶⁰ GICHD Publication. (2004). *A guide to socio-economic approaches to Mine Action*. P.44

¹⁶¹ ICBL Publication. *Landmine Monitor 2006*, Internet. Available at <http://www.icbl.org/lm>, accessed on 10 December 2006.

spikes in numbers of casualties as a consequence. One of the recurrent causes is recovering explosive remnants of war to sell them as metal parts, especially in times of rising scrap metal prices in societies facing extreme poverty such as Cambodia or Laos. Both increasing mine clearance and mine risk education efforts are incapable of addressing these extreme circumstances adequately:

“The rise in scrap metal prices has prompted many people to scavenge for metal parts of discarded weaponry, including unexploded shells and bombs, said Chhiv Lim, the project manager at Mine Victim Information System, which compiles data on such incidents. The explosions were caused by tampering with the devices ... with the purpose to break them apart for sale to scrap metal buyers, he said.”¹⁶²

Behaviour or activities which are related to mine accidents evolve over time, subject to ever-changing socio-economic dynamics. The quite accurate victim data of Bosnia and Cambodia allows for some interesting observations. The well disaggregated Cambodian mine victim data¹⁶³ from 1998 and 1999 shows below that the three most dangerous activities are: (1) tampering, (2) military activities, and simply (3) travelling.¹⁶⁴ In 2002, a significant percentage increase took place of accidents related to post-conflict economic activities. However, comparing percentages alone can be misleading. Owing to the accidents related to military activities dropping to zero, there is indeed a percentage increase for accidents due to tampering but not in absolute annual numbers, which have been quite constant for these activities since 2000. This put the above alarming statement in perspective, one of the many indications of exploitation and exaggeration of mine victim data.

Activity	Casualties 1998-1999	% of Total 1998-1999	Casualties 2002	% of Total 2002
Tampering	762 (381 annually)	27%	326	39%
Military activities	514	19%	0	0%
Travelling	498	19%	150	18%
Farming	364 (182 annually)	14%	167	20%
Collecting wood	264	10%	66	8%
Collecting food	134	5%	25	3%
Herding	55	2%	17	2%
Fishing	49	2%	25	3%
Unknown	32	1%	0	0%
Other	17	1%	58	7%
Trading	1	0%	0	0%
Total	2,690	100%	834	100%

Table II.3: Casualties per activities in percentages and absolute annual numbers

Even in more favourable circumstances than extreme poverty, most affected people are heavily challenged in their interaction with a mine infested environment. The graph below shows the percentage of Bosnian people injured in areas they knew to be dangerous. Over the years, an increase of the percentage of people injured in known dangerous areas is noticeable. Again these accidents can be largely explained for economic reasons. When confronted in their communities with a subsistence economy, the population does not have any other alternative than to cultivate their land, cut the wood, etc.¹⁶⁵ With populations adapting to a dangerous environment, diminishing fear for landmine threats is an important factor. Hence, an affected population which is at first risk-averse can be forced or enticed by economic incentives to become too risk-acceptant. It is a variation on the *mine clearance dilemma*, or how to minimize maximum loss, which was explained under

¹⁶² Cambodia online, Internet. Available at <http://www.cambodianonline.net/articles200435.htm>, accessed on 10 November 2006

¹⁶³ An external evaluation of the Cambodia Mine/UXO Victim Information System (CMVIS) reported that the system is “unique in the world in terms of coverage and detail.” To December 2002, the database contained records on 56,793 mine/UXO casualties since 1979: 17,918 people were killed and 38,875 injured; 31,720 were civilians. 2003 Landmine Monitor, Internet. Available at <http://www.icbl.org/lm>, accessed on 10 April 2006.

¹⁶⁴ Combined data from the *Journal of Mine Action*, last accessed on October 2006 on <http://maic.jmu.edu/journal/5.1/Focus/Reuben%20McCarthy/mccarthy.html>

¹⁶⁵ ICRC data, Internet. Available at <http://www.icrc.org>, accessed on 8 November 2005

preamble paragraph 3 and 4. It further underscores how unpredictable the element “*nature*” is due to its constantly evolving characteristics, requiring the decision maker to continually adapt the strategic choices in order to obtain a best response. It reaffirms the requirement for a very flexible system in support of multiple criteria decision analysis.

Fig. II.11: Percentage of mine victims in Bosnia having a mine accident whilst aware of the dangers and risks

b. Deductions

1. Key points

- ☞ The number of annual landmine victims is used extensively as a critical *framing element* to measure progress or state the effectiveness of the response to the global landmine problem. The generally overwhelming *cumulative* numbers of landmine victims/survivors vary within a broad range but even the lowest estimates accentuate the tremendous *cumulative* human cost this global tragedy is causing.
- ☞ Reducing human cost is a dominant factor; the ultimate effectiveness of the outcome of the politics of mine action should be directly linked to the reduction of mine victims or the human cost. Extensive gathering of all available data on the number of mine victims/survivors should, therefore, be subject to exhaustive statistical analysis. Hence, mine victim data is of essential importance for the proportionate allocation of mine action resources and has therefore a high relevancy in cross-country and/or cross-sector comparisons.
- ☞ There are a multitude of operational and tactical elements, some of them interrelated, which influence risk behaviour, in particular the coinciding impact of ERW/landmine presence and extreme poverty. Women and children are generally high risk groups due to their behaviour and activities. The effect of diminishing fear of landmines can cause people to display high(er) risk behaviour.
- ☞ There is a strong notion that ERW/UXO contamination can be more lethal than landmines if successive conflicts aggravate the different kinds of contamination. Notably, Conflict history is reflected in the lagging numbers of mine/ERW/UXO victims; therefore, it needs to be integrated in the modelling efforts.
- ☞ The game theoretic aspects are similar to the previous preamble paragraph but focused on the human cost instead of the socio-economic benefits. The “human cost” accentuates the risks involved in case prioritization of mine clearance and targeting of MRE are not optimal. A best response is therefore again a *minimax* concept. This results in a Bayesian equilibrium, since best strategic choices are based on what a decision maker and other stakeholders *believe* is the “state of the mine-affected nation” with nature as the unpredictable element.
- ☞ Mine Risk Education fits well in a mine action emergency response but its effects are hard to quantify; often indicators are used with low relevancy. Nevertheless, *targeted or prioritized*

MRE and mine clearance are two key conditions to accelerate the reduction in human cost. Targeting of mine clearance and mine risk education efforts need to be facilitated by a most flexible multiple criteria Decision Support System (DSS) due to the volatility and unpredictability of the element “*nature*”.

2. Possible indicators and criteria

The deduction of goals and indicators is again quite straightforward for this paragraph and directly linked to the criteria and indicators deduced from the previous preamble paragraph. efforts to reduce the number of new mine victims as quickly as possible. The prioritization of mine clearance and targeting of Mine Risk Education are once more assessed as key evaluation criteria for an effective mine action programme, focused on reducing the landmine threat for the most vulnerable population groups.

Goal	Indicator
Reduction of new mine victims	Number of (new) mine victims or mine survivors
	Having an effective integration of mine victim assistance into broader public health and socio-economic strategies
Protect the most vulnerable ones; gender awareness and sensitivity	Number of specific efforts to reduce the number of new mine victims among civilian populations, especially vulnerable groups including women and children

Criterion	Idem criterion 15 – level of prioritization and targeting of mine action efforts
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F. Preamble Paragraph 6: Mine clearance: the main pillar

Deeply alarmed by the number of mines that continue to be laid each year, as well as the presence of a decreasing but still very large number of mines and other unexploded ordnance as a result of armed conflicts, and therefore remaining convinced of the necessity and urgency of a significant increase in mine-clearance efforts by the international community with a view to eliminating the threat of landmines to civilians as soon as possible,

a. Analysis

1. Mine clearance: the central mine action pillar

This has been one of the recurrent paragraphs since the initiation of the resolution, which stipulated in its first paragraph that the General Assembly is gravely alarmed by the increasing presence of mines and other unexploded devices resulting from armed conflict. An important second element, added in later versions of the resolution, is the request to the international community to significantly increase their mine *clearance* efforts. Preferably it should be an increase of efforts in mine *action*. However, mine clearance is obviously the only way to eliminate completely the threat of landmine threat to civilians and continues, therefore, to symbolize and capture the essence of mine action.

“There is an exciting untold story behind every mine cleared and destroyed: the story of a child playing freely and securely; the story of a woman reaping her crops and returning home safely to feed her family; the story of confidence built between former warring parties. For every mine survivor cared for and reintegrated into society, there is the story of a life carried on with mobility and restored dignity.”¹⁶⁶

Owing to its interventionist and direct result-oriented characteristics, mine clearance has always attracted the bulk of the funding and political attention, with significantly less effort or justification than the other mine action pillars. Mine clearance needs, however, to be broadly interpreted. The important process of landmine and ERW surveys, mapping and minefield marking should also be included. This dissertation focuses on humanitarian mine clearance, which implies clearance to humanitarian standards. It is more stringent than military mine clearance, which is primarily undertaken by soldiers to clear a safe path so they can advance unhindered during military operations. Such a breaching process is arguably a post-conflict activity as it even accepts that limited military casualties may occur. Since the preamble paragraph expresses the view to eliminating the threat of landmines to civilians as soon as possible, it is clear that this type of mine clearance focuses on the restoration of peace and security with a return to normalcy of affected population groups at community level. This can take place through three clearance methods: manual, mine detection dogs or other biosensors and mechanical clearance. Of those three methods, manual clearance - which relies on trained deminers using metal detectors and long thin prodders to locate the mines - is widely regarded as the most reliable and therefore remains the preferred method, for reasons both of cost and reliability.

It needs to be highlighted that the *UN itself does not carry out mine clearance*. In most countries they advise and assist the national authorities, and recently, an increasing number of UN peacekeeping missions to carry out mine clearance. The UN typically establishes a Mine Action Authority or Coordination Centre responsible for overseeing clearance activities. If national capacity building is adequate, then the actual clearance operations may be carried out by national NGOs or civilian agencies. Otherwise, which is often the case, military units agree to take part in peacekeeping and humanitarian operations or international NGOs. Commercial organisations are another specific branch, inevitably with a strong commercial interest.¹⁶⁷

¹⁶⁶ ICRC – How to ensure progress for the Nairobi Action Plan, Internet. Available at <http://www.icrc.org/Web/eng/siteeng0.nsf/iwpList108>, accessed on 29 May 2006

¹⁶⁷ E-MINE, Internet. Available at <http://www.mineaction.org/overview.asp?o=16>, accessed on 1 August 2006

2. Stockpile destruction: the less visible pillar

Apart from landmine destruction through mine clearance activities, close to 40 million mines in stockpiles have been destroyed.¹⁶⁸ It supports the formulation of a *decreasing* but still very large number of mines and unexploded ordnance on a global scale. In order to reflect in particular the ongoing mine clearance activities, the paragraph was modified accordingly.¹⁶⁹ This qualifying element is somewhat supported by the annual Article VII reports on mine clearance activities, as stipulated by the Mine Ban Treaty. It might be partially applicable regarding landmines, but with the recent and ongoing conflicts in Iraq, Afghanistan, Sudan and most recently Lebanon, it may be argued whether the cited decrease of ERW is still reflecting the reality. It was suggested for the sake of positivism to commend the efforts of the international community. However, the recent surge in armed violence requires a message of an alarming increase to better reflect the realities on the ground. It highlights how important it is to correctly frame a continuously evolving problem.

The destruction of large stockpiles is of course most relevant as it renders future use of these weapons impossible. However, with China, Russia and the United States possessing enormous stockpiles¹⁷⁰, it is not realistic to assume they would be ready to subscribe or offer their political support for the inclusion of direct references to stockpile destruction in any resolution and/or convention.

Fig. II.12: Landmine Monitor estimates that non-States Parties stockpile over 160 million antipersonnel mines, with the vast majority held by a just five states: China (est. 110 million), Russia (26.5 million), US (10.4 million), Pakistan (est. 6 million) and India (est. 4-5 million).

¹⁶⁸ ICBL (2006) Landmine Monitor, also available on Internet. Available at <http://www.icbl.org/lm>, accessed on 11 July 2006

¹⁶⁹ On request of the Representative of Norway, this came out of bilateral meetings where it was suggested that the resolution should better indicate the effectiveness of mine action and its effects on a global scale, September 2002, New York

¹⁷⁰ ICBL (2006) Landmine Monitor, also available on Internet. Available at <http://www.icbl.org/lm>, accessed on 11 July 2006, major findings

3. Egypt: a rebel with a cause?

Landmine or ERW impact of *recent* conflicts are not championed by all UN Member States. Egypt has been throughout the years a most active interlocutor and has held the high politics debate captive at many occasions. One of the main battlegrounds of World War II, Egypt considers itself as one of the most affected nations at a global scale. It sheds an interesting light on the consensus debate and how one or a selected group of UN Member States can resist the transformation of mine clearance to mine action in the resolution. In this regard, Egypt has challenged any progressive language and effectively stalled for the first time the consensus debate on assistance in mine action in 2004. Hence, after the study of the broader dynamics of alliance formations and interactions, this analysis will focus why and how one particular State manipulates or blocks the political debate.

In order to understand Egypt's almost obsessive interest in scrutinizing the mine action strategy proposed by the UN Secretary-General, in the Western Desert of Egypt must be addressed. As part of its own campaign, Egypt has been stating for many years the crushing numbers of having more than 20 million landmines or ERW in its territory. More recent statements cite with a remarkable but intriguing accuracy the presence of 19,7 million landmines and ERW covering an area of 287 sq km.¹⁷¹ Critics state that Egypt's problem is primarily one of a developmental nature. Egypt tries, however, to link up its landmine problem with the primarily humanitarian dimension of the UN mine action strategy. For this reason Egypt frames its landmine problem accordingly, stating that over the past six decades more than 8000 recorded casualties provide a humanitarian testimony with approximately 200 new accidents every year and many others that go unrecorded. None of these probably exaggerated numbers can be confirmed.¹⁷² Furthermore, it is the desire of the Government of Egypt to ensure full economic utilization of the available land which is currently affected. Egypt also states its efforts to reduce the number of casualties, caused by demographic pressures in development areas bordering contaminated land.¹⁷³

In broad terms, with a primary need for mine clearance, Egypt is not supportive of mine action as a five-pillar concept, especially since it implies advocacy for a total ban on landmines. The fact that Egypt neither subscribes to the Mine Ban Treaty nor the Convention on prohibitions or restrictions on the use of certain Conventional Weapons, further characterizes its non-compromising stance on several mine action issues. Egypt tries nevertheless through the consensus process to achieve more impact on the UN Mine Action Strategy and Policy, in order to influence it and obtain more support for their largely developmental mine clearance projects. It was, therefore, a prerequisite for Egypt that UN Member States would be intensively solicited during the redaction of this strategy. This was not the case, and led to significant difficulties during the consensus process in 2001. The Egyptian delegation insisted on an immediate formal review of the 2001-2005 Strategy, although this was not foreseen before 2003. After long mediation by the Belgian Chair, ambiguous language unlocked the debate, stating that the UN would seek the views of UN Member States in order to *optimize* the UN 2001-2005 Strategy.¹⁷⁴ Possible dubious interpretations of this language never led to the requested revision by Egypt.

¹⁷¹ The Views of the Government of Egypt on the Mine Action Strategy for 2001-2005 & Ways to Optimize it. Note Verbal of the PM of the Arab Republic of Egypt to the United Nations to UNMAS, 8 July 2002, New York

¹⁷² These numbers are unconfirmed and likely systematic exaggeration in order to frame the problem. The total number of landmine casualties in Egypt is not known. In February 1999, it was reported that landmines had claimed 8,313 casualties (696 killed and 7,617 injured); 5,017 were civilians. In 2006, UNDP reported that since the end of World War II, approximately 8,000 people have died as a result of landmines in Egypt's north coast and Western Desert alone. Landmine Monitor recorded at least 103 mine/UXO casualties in Egypt between 1999 and April 2006. Landmine Monitor 2006, Internet. Available at <http://www.icbl.org/lm>, accessed on 11 July 2006

¹⁷³ This is a recurrent element Egypt mentions during the consensus debates on the UN mine action resolution.

¹⁷⁴ UN Document A/RES/56/219, UN resolution on 'Assistance in mine action', Internet. Available at <http://www.un.org/Depts/dhl/resguide/r56.htm>, accessed on 20 July 2005

All the facts related to Egypt's protracted efforts to obtain more support for its national landmine problem are important, resulting ultimately in its blocking of the consensus process in 2004. Egypt finds itself, however, isolated, hardly securing any support from the donor community. Therefore, it strongly disagrees with the current resource allocation policy and in particular the lack of support from the UN, a political position which translates itself in their hardliner request to modify the UN strategy accordingly. This has been a highly discussed topic as changing the UN strategy implies a change in UN policy. However, with mine clearance in other mine-affected countries given higher priority than Egypt, it is not realistic to assume that the UN would engage in any significant resource mobilisation efforts.¹⁷⁵ The Egyptian mine clearance needs are mainly economically motivated, which also explains the Egyptian political manoeuvring to have stronger references regarding mine action for development.¹⁷⁶

Developmental mine action: what does it exactly entail in concrete economic terms for Egypt? In the past 60 years, mines and UXO in both Sinai and the Western Desert are thought to have impeded development projects that could have addressed Egypt's growing population problem, as well as provide land for tourism, agriculture, and for processing gas and oil. Government researchers estimate that approximately 12,600 square kilometres of the north-western coast and inland desert area are suitable for cultivation and pastures. One billion cubic meters of underground water reserves are made inaccessible by the presence of mines and ERW, and similar inaccessibility exists for roughly 4.8 million barrels of petroleum and 13.4 trillion cubic feet of natural gas.¹⁷⁷

4. Unsuccessful establishment of a *win-win* situation

Based on the above elements and analysis, Egypt has no attractive payoffs to join the MBT or CCW and has for obvious reasons "*a cause to be a rebel*". Mine clearance of the vast areas mentioned above would come at a tremendous cost. As long as those countries largely responsible for the landmine problem in Egypt do not contribute significantly, Egypt judges it has no incentive to accede to the treaties. Moreover, if it moves from its hawkish position to a cuckoo one, it faces several disincentives which currently still outweigh the positive payoffs.

"In June 2004, a government representative restated the country's long-held position that it needs anti-personnel mines to defend its borders and that the treaty fails to require those who laid mines in Egypt in the past to be responsible for clearing them."¹⁷⁸

Firstly, with the current prioritization of mine action activities, Egypt will only continue to get meagre or symbolic support from the mine action community. In a game theoretic sense, there is *no receptive Dove's nest for their Cuckoo's egg*. In the high politics debate, Egyptian diplomats made a mockery of limited contributions regularly, instead of the required multi-million dollar contributions¹⁷⁹:

"In 2002, the US Agency for International Development and the demining company RONCO conducted an assessment mission. From 1999 to 2003 Egypt was included in the US humanitarian demining funding program. However, it is not known what funding was disbursed or how it was used. In 2004, the German Federal Ministry of Defence provided an in-kind donation of metal detectors (estimated value €300,000)."¹⁸⁰

¹⁷⁵ As most contributions within the UN system Voluntary Trust Fund are earmarked towards a specific country, it is also clear for Egypt that it is useless to continue their efforts to obtain more funding this way.

¹⁷⁶ It has always been the position of the General Assembly to encourage the Secretary General since 1998 to "develop further a comprehensive mine action strategy that takes into consideration the impact of the landmine problem on rehabilitation, reconstruction and development with a view to ensure the effectiveness of assistance in mine action by the United Nations".

¹⁷⁷ ICBL (2006) Landmine Monitor, Internet. Available at <http://www.icbl.org/lm>, accessed on 11 July 2006

¹⁷⁸ ICBL (2005) Landmine Monitor, Internet. Available at <http://www.icbl.org/lm>, accessed on 14 July 2006

¹⁷⁹ Interventions by Egyptian representatives during the negotiations on the UN resolution assistance in mine action in 2001 and 2002.

¹⁸⁰ ICBL (2006) Landmine Monitor, Internet. Available at <http://www.icbl.org/lm>, accessed on 15 July 2006

Secondly, once Egypt joins the MBT, it has to remove the landmines at the Peninsula border with Israel, which Egypt perceives as aggravating a national security problem. Finally and thirdly, Egypt itself has the national resources to undertake mine clearance and, therefore, has to take both ownership of the problem and largely bear the cost. Almost ironically, it currently (2006) contributes a military mine clearance unit active in South Sudan as part of the United Nations Mission in Sudan (UNMIS).

So far the international community has failed to establish a positive non-zero sum game or attractive win-win situation for Egypt. Hence, Egypt increasingly takes a hard-line position, with grave consequences for the mine action consensus debate. In 2004, the Netherlands could not secure a compromise with Egypt. In their EU presidency and chairing capacity, they decided to withdraw the draft resolution and instead introduced a draft decision to maintain assistance in mine action on the UN General Assembly agenda, i.e. purely procedural (see Annex C for the 2004 Decision). A compromise could not be reached on one particular element of the draft which related to Egypt's request that a revised UN Strategy on mine action would need to be approved by the General Assembly. Since UN mine action takes place largely through voluntary and not assessed contributions,¹⁸¹ this request was unacceptable for the co-sponsors as it would create a risky precedent and deviation of standard UN rules and procedures.

As mine action progresses in numerous mine-affected States, Egypt increases the pressure on the international community to obtain support for their mine problem. This includes the strengthening of the development imperative as one of the key strategic principles of mine action. Although the development imperative is still subordinate to the humanitarian one, the revised 2006-2009 UN Strategy is now largely acknowledging in a more balanced manner than the 2001-2005 UN Strategy.¹⁸²

Finally, how now to turn this situation into a real *win-win*? As implied, both parties need to gain from the resolution of the problem. *Win-win approaches* rely basically on two techniques.¹⁸³ The first of these is to have both parties committing themselves to finding and benefiting from a solution. In this case the international community needs to become more accommodating towards Egypt, with the responsibility for solving its landmine problem shared between Egypt and at least those countries which Egypt claims to be responsible for laying the mines. Egypt, on the other hand, needs to be more accommodating through sharing directly or indirectly possible socio-economic benefits from mine action with the international community. The second technique is to emphasize stable, long-term commitments rather than quick fix solutions for one of the more critical global landmine contaminations.

5. Not achieving consensus: pre-meditated or a *trembling hand*?

In their efforts to achieve consensus, the analysis of the first preamble paragraph clarified that States interact according to the characteristics exhibited in a *Game of Chicken*, trying to hold their political position as long as they can until the other player gives in. If this does not happen, then both players will try to find a compromise solution through new compromise language which is satisfactory to both. Hence, how can it be game theoretically explained that both alliances have chosen the strategy not to compromise, resulting in the lowest payoffs? This implies utility minimization and equals a Game of Chicken with both car drivers staying the course and driving off the cliff. It brings into question the solidity of the solution concept earlier formulated whereby a mixed Nash Equilibrium would result in achieving consensus contingent to the following: (1) the

¹⁸¹ Only mine action as part of peacekeeping operations is funded through assessed contributions of UN Member States, approved and mandated through the UN Security Council.

¹⁸² UNMAS (2005). UN 2006-2009 Mine Action Strategy, Internet. Available at <http://www.mineaction.org>, accessed on 10 November 2006

¹⁸³ ELLIS, D. (1994). *Small Group Decision-making; Communication and the Group Process*, New York, p.238

draft resolution was reasonably balanced; (2) the EU Chair adequately experienced or diplomatically skilled; and, (3) both alliances sufficiently constructive in wanting to obtain a compromise.

If not achieving consensus results in the tabling of a decision, then neither alliance can influence UN policy making and strategy formulation, virtually bringing the pursuit of any national agenda to a standstill. It is therefore doubtful this must have been the political end goal of Egypt. Its precise reason to be obstructive was to influence UN strategy formulation, and therefore the UN resolution, in order to obtain more support through the UN system. It is therefore rather unsound to argue that Egypt would not ultimately accept compromise language as it did the preceding years instead of losing any impact it could have had. The EU Chair was definitely having a solid understanding of mine action, logically underscoring the importance the Netherlands attaches to the subject.¹⁸⁴ Judging diplomatic skills is then again largely a subjective matter. The EU Chair, however, tabled a draft decision rather early in the GA session, hereby placing the EU sponsors for a *fait accompli*. It indicates that not all avenues were extensively explored to achieve consensus; also, it gave the EU Member States no time to consider the alternative of a voted resolution. The late argument invoked by the Netherlands was that a possible vote was risky since Egypt could mobilise a significant number of NAM nations and thereby harm the progressive alliance in mine action. There is evidence that this lack of consultation was not well received by EU Member States.¹⁸⁵ So, what could be a game theoretic explanation why alliances or players ended up minimizing their political incentives without a dramatic change in payoff structure? Game theorist Selten,¹⁸⁶ previously involved in disarmament theory, has formulated a possible way around this paradox through invoking the so-called “*trembling hand*” phenomenon in game theory.

“The idea here is that a decision and its consequent act may “come apart” with some non-zero probability, however small. That is, a player might intend to take an action but then slip up in the execution and send the game down some other path instead. If there is even a remote possibility that a player may make a mistake - that her “hand may tremble” - then no contradiction is introduced by a player’s using a backward induction argument that requires the hypothetical assumption that another player has taken a path that a rational player could not choose.”¹⁸⁷

If the above game theoretic reasoning is applied to the stalled consensus process, then a valid explanation can be sought in the Egypt’s position. Repeatedly, Egypt has pressured the EU Chair every year to accept some of its compromise language. In order to save the consensus, and to act in a rational manner, the EU Chair and progressive States have also come up with compromise language in order not to end up with the lowest payoffs. In 2004, Egypt’s effort to control the new UN Mine Action Strategy resulted in opting for a hard-line position but with the expectation that ultimately a compromise would be reached. According to the “*trembling hand*” thinking, Egypt’s decision to pressure the Chair and other supporting States into formulating a compromise failed and hence, the act got separated from the earlier decision and send the game unexpectedly down on the path of giving up on a consensus resolution, tabling a technical decision instead.

Based on its *prior beliefs*, Egypt expected that a rational player would not give up on achieving consensus so early “in the game”.¹⁸⁸ The EU Chair, however, thought it wise to stop the bargaining and heavy trade-offs at an early stage, making clear that consensus could not to be

¹⁸⁴ The Netherlands have always been one of the most engaged and experienced partners in mine action, both in terms of political leadership – holding for two years the Chair of the Main Action Support Group – and funding.

¹⁸⁵ Exchange between Permanent Mission of Belgium to the UN with Ministry of Foreign Affairs Brussels, Mr. Marc Pecsteen, November 2004

¹⁸⁶ SELTEN, R. (1994) Nobel Prize winner in Economics, Expert in Multistage Game Models and Delay Super-games, provided ground-breaking work on redefining perfectness of equilibriums and sub-game perfectness, now often referred to as trembling hand perfectness.

¹⁸⁷ Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy – Trembling hands, Internet. Available at <http://www.science.uva.nl/~seop/archives/fall2005/entries/game-theory>, accessed on 10 March 2006

¹⁸⁸ Based on experiences with Egyptian Representatives during successive rounds of negotiations in 2001 and 2002.

reached through a recurrent pressuring process or at the cost of creating unwanted precedents.¹⁸⁹ The backward induction argument indicates that an obstructive State has to be cautious in its *beliefs* regarding the rationality or *reputation* of the other player¹⁹⁰ and needs to base its strategic choices on the assumption that there is always a small probability that another player will act differently from what it believes is rational behaviour or which behaviour to expect according to the *reputation* attributed to each *type of player*.

“In real life, it may make an enormous difference *how* you play, even if you are backing a lost cause. Against an ideal player you may be defeated [or succeed], but against a real person it is well known that certain strategies induce errors.”¹⁹¹

This different belief of rationality does not imply the possibility of irrational actors. The rationality of the different actors has been an upfront basic assumption of the game theoretic analysis in this chapter. Misconceptions are, however, possible in this regard. Rational decision-making does not imply it is ethical responsible, Adolf Hitler is a classic example. Renowned game theorists argue that although regarded as insane to the common idea of rationality, his behaviour can be explained rationally from the perspective of utility theory. He pursued abhorrent goals and took immense political risks but simultaneously pursued German nationalist expansion. He opted in his view for his *best response* possible to the *state of the world* and the opportunities it presented to him. In many ways, Hitler understood the rational dimension of the international climate of the 1930s better than any other leader did.¹⁹²

In conclusion, opinions could be divided on either the strategic choices of the EU Chair or Egypt. All of them were most rational, but rational actors can make errors, that is, achieve less desirable or unwanted outcomes. This is often due to different levels of risk the actors are ready to take, e.g. the above cited apprehension of the Dutch EU Chair that Egypt would be able to unfavourably tip the balance in case of a voted resolution.¹⁹³ On the other hand, not reaching consensus had its particular norm building and *name & shame* effects, of which more in the next section. The game theoretic “*trembling hand*” aspect might not provide a complete answer but offers at least a valuable insight how a relatively predictable *chicken* or *consensus* game can have a surprising - albeit less positive - outcome. It underlines that a solution concept or Nash equilibrium can have many different types of refinement beyond those already addressed. Also Bayesian aspects come into play again, as *beliefs* on *rationality* and *type* of the other player can vary. Ultimately, the interactions between States to achieve consensus remain complex.

6. “Free-riders” to avoid “name & shame”

In an economic context, free-riders are actors who consume more than their fair share of a resource, or shoulder less than a fair share of the costs of its production. Concurrently, in a political and game theoretic context, actor(s) are considered *free-riders* when they deliberately exploit political advantage at the complete cost or disadvantage of others. It can also be interpreted in a strictly security or mine action context in which landmines deployed by other actors provide security to a free-riding third actor without having to bear the consequences of transgressing international conventions. This has been a recurrent criticism of NATO, where in essence the military capability of using landmines is maintained through the military doctrine of one alliance member: the United

¹⁸⁹ Interview with the EU Chair in December 2004 at the Permanent Mission of the Netherlands to the UN, New York, November 2004.

¹⁹⁰ The game theoretic conceptual term has a particular use in repeated games whereby players build up a certain *reputation* which increase the predictability of their behaviour by the other player. This concept is extensively used throughout the work of FINK, E. C., GATES, S. and HUMES, B. D. (1998) *Game Theory Topics: Incomplete Information, Repeated Games, and n-player Games*. California: Sage University Papers Series on Quantitative Applications in the Social Sciences, 07-122, p.9

¹⁹¹ MORTON, D. (1997). *Game Theory: A Non-technical Introduction*, Dover Publications, p.8

¹⁹² MORROW, J. (1994). *Game Theory for Political Scientists*, New Jersey: Princeton, p.21

¹⁹³ Assessment through E-mail by the Belgian Diplomat Marc Pecsteen in his message to the Belgian Ministry of Foreign Affairs, 12 November 2004.

States. The majority of NATO-members however, would prohibit the transit of landmines over their territory, let alone contribute to its deployment.

The effective norm building over the past decade regarding assistance in mine action increasingly stigmatizes those nations opposing the noble efforts to rid the world of these indiscriminate weapons. Hence, the loose alliance which maintains landmines in their weapon arsenals has regularly portrayed a paradox mix of *front-runners* and *free-riders*. States wary of the harm of negative reporting prefer indeed to be rather low-key in supporting Egypt in its non-compromising stance. Countries like China, India, Iran and Pakistan play the game in a very subtle way, defending through Egypt's diplomatic efforts their requirements for landmines in respect with their national security issues. It demonstrates how fragile alliances are and how much the political agendas are driven by self-interest.

The free-rider *problem* is the question of how to prevent free riding from taking place, or at least limit its negative effects. Non-compromising States will try to avoid the negative payoffs derived from "*name & shame*" effects which could in this context be regarded as their *trigger strategy*¹⁹⁴ causing the free-rider problem. The term *audience cost* has been briefly used to qualify the negative fall-out of the *name & shame* during the *consensus game*.¹⁹⁵ This term was first introduced in 1994 by political game theorist James Fearon, who described a situation on the international political stage where a leader of one country backs down in an international crisis with another country. Costs increase the longer the duration of the crisis, but it depends on behaviour and decisions if the actor actually induces the costs. Clearly these costs should not be interpreted in monetary terms, but a measurable extension of loss of *reputation* or negative image as the most serious incurred cost.¹⁹⁶ There are extreme examples where *name & shame* has had the desired results, but equally where they failed to generate the necessary *audience costs*.

"*Shake Hands with the Devil*" relates the Canadian Lieutenant-General Dallaire's experiences in Rwanda. When Dallaire was ordered by the UN to rally his troops to enforce a difficult peace, the country descended into turmoil. More than 800,000 were killed in the Rwandan genocide despite Dallaire's efforts to shame the international community into action to prevent the massacre. Dallaire is credited with saving 30,000 people but blames himself most for not having been able to create effective *audience costs* for those nations which could have made a difference at the time. During the 100 days of the Rwandan genocide, the world media was more preoccupied with the proceedings of the trial of O.J. Simpsons. However, General Dallaire did in a futile later effort try to shape somewhat world conscience.

"It's up to Rwanda not to let others forget they are criminally responsible for the genocide," he said, singling out France, Britain and the United States.¹⁹⁷

For the *audience cost* related to mine action, one should consider both an international and domestic cost. The latter has been exploited as much as the first by *name & shame campaigns*, in particular those very effectively led by the International Campaign to Ban Landmines (ICBL). International change results often from the work of savvy political actors who are able to propel norm building to new heights. Consequently, the role of *transnational activist networks*, such as Human Rights Watch or the International Campaign to Ban Landmines, has been remarkable in promoting change.

¹⁹⁴ The game theoretic concept of a trigger strategy will be addressed further below the game theoretic analysis but is here the event which causes States to opt for a specific strategy in order to avoid name & shame.

¹⁹⁵ As explained in preamble paragraph 1

¹⁹⁶ FINK, E. C., GATES, S. and HUMES, B. D. (1998) *Game Theory Topics: Incomplete Information, Repeated Games, and n-player Games*, California, Sage University Papers Series on Quantitative Applications in the Social Sciences, 07-122.

¹⁹⁷ AMANPOUR, C. (2004). *West 'guilty' over Rwanda genocide*. Interview of LtGen Dallaire, Internet. Available at <http://www.cnn.com/2004/WORLD/africa/04/06/rwanda.dallaire/index.html>. Accessed on 31 December 2006

“Such groups typically uncover and publicize information about violations of legal or moral standards at least rhetorically supported by powerful democracies, including "disappearances" during the Argentine military's rule in the late 1970s, concentration camps in Bosnia, and the huge number of civilian deaths from land mines. This publicity is then used to press governments to adopt specific remedies, such as the establishment of a war crimes tribunal or the adoption of a landmine treaty. These movements often make pragmatic arguments as well as idealistic ones, but their distinctive power comes from the *ability to highlight deviations from deeply held norms of appropriate behaviour*.¹⁹⁸

In conclusion, actors whose behaviour deviates from broadly accepted norms and standards can through *name & shame* become indirectly helpful in reinforcing the norm. An effective *name & shame* campaign can initially aggravate some free-rider problems but will ultimately, through the generation of *audience costs*, become one of the most effective political tools to enforce compliance or compromises regarding assistance in mine action and/or a total ban.

7. “Blame game” to avoid “name & shame”

One more tactic needs to be addressed which is used to lower the audience cost or to respond adequately to name & shame campaigns: the *blame game*. With the otherwise formulated concept of “*bargaining before an audience*”,¹⁹⁹ the essence is not how bargaining or opposing actors interact, but how this triggers a desired response from a third actor, party or alliance. This is a well-known tactic during election campaigns, especially of two US presidential candidates trying to manipulate the voters audience.

“The reason is simple: to discredit the opposition. “Both parties do it” [...] . [Blame game politics] is an important but relatively unexplored class of game-theory bargaining problems that involve negotiators who send signals to a third party. Almost all other bargaining theories ignore the possibility that the two main negotiators want to impress a third party.”²⁰⁰

Mine-affected or mine using countries apply similar tactics to discredit other nations. Landmine-users Pakistan and India will blame each other profusely for their landmine use due to the military aggression in the Kashmir region. As mentioned above, Egypt will blame in particular Germany for its landmine problems of the Second World War: Egypt will in addition blame Israel for national security reasons at its border; Cuba will blame the United States. Hence, the main purpose of the *blame game* is to shift the focus away from who is accountable or responsible for the use or clearance of landmines or mine contamination and thereby de-stigmatize ones own image.

b. Deductions

1. Key points

- ☞ Of the five mine action pillars, mine clearance is to be considered as the centre of gravity of mine action and its related politics; therefore, this must be reflected in the modelling effort accordingly. Clearing or destroying mines is the only possible way to reach a complete solution; it, therefore, systematically attracts the most political attention and resources.
- ☞ There are mainly three mine clearance methods: manual, mechanical and mine detection dogs, rats or other biosensors. It needs to be emphasized that the UN itself does not undertake mine *clearance* activities, which underscores its important role of assistance and coordination.
- ☞ Egypt’s politics related to its landmine problems underline how each affected country is unique in experiencing the impact of landmines. Egypt belongs to a number of States which prefers a

¹⁹⁸ SNYDER, J., One World, Rival Theories, *Foreign Policy*, Internet. Available at <http://www.geocities.com/thadoc78/intltheories.htm>, accessed on 12 April 2005

¹⁹⁹ Norm concept created by Timothy Groseclose and Nolan McCarty, GSB Research Paper #1617, May 1999, Internet. Available at http://www.gsb.stanford.edu/news/research/polecon_blame.shtml, accessed on 10 January 2007

²⁰⁰ BUELL, Barbara, Blame Game Politics Manipulates Voters, Stanford University, Internet. Available at http://www.gsb.stanford.edu/news/research/polecon_blame.shtml, accessed on 10 January 2007

UN resolution on assistance in mine *clearance* in stead of mine *action*, since the latter implies a total landmine ban. *Free-riders* take a back seat on Egypt in order to avoid the *name & shame* or *audience costs* they would incur if they would openly oppose assistance in mine action. Generating *audience costs*, possibly in combination with a *name & shame* campaign, is one of the most effective political and normative reinforcing tools.

☞ Although Egypt is largely ignored by the donor community, it has been successful in reinforcing norm building on *developmental* aspects of mine action. The international community has failed so far to establish a *win-win* situation with Egypt, primarily by pressuring Egypt to take ownership of a problem largely created by other States. This led in 2004 to a blocking of the consensus process regarding the UN mine action resolution. Voting is generally feared as an alternative for consensus as it would significantly increase the competitiveness in lieu of cooperation between UN Member States.

☞ The game theoretic analysis focused primarily on the particular position of Egypt. It offered an interesting expansion on the earlier described *egalitarian* principles of the consensus process, thereby illustrating the possibility of off-the-equilibrium play. This game theoretic explanation clarified that the actors, through a “*slip of the hand*” or tremble, may choose unintended strategies, albeit with a very low, unspecified probability. This is a refinement of a Nash equilibrium, explaining how a player could change its strategy unilaterally against the rational principles of utility maximization. Decision-making under increased risks have a tendency to portray more frequently *trembling hand equilibriums*.

☞ *Win-win* situations or a more robust consensus can only be achieved through fair burden-sharing and acknowledging the important developmental purposes of mine action besides its primarily humanitarian imperative.

☞ The revised UN Mine Action Strategy reflects a better balance between the humanitarian and developmental aspects of mine action; both need to be incorporated in the normative model.

2. Overview of Normative/Game Theoretic Elements and Criteria

The main objective of the preamble paragraph is the total elimination of landmine threats, thereby achieving the ideal of a “*mine free*” world. The goal and indicators are, therefore, strictly related to mine clearance and any other activity which leads to the destruction of landmines, in particular stockpile destruction.

Goal	Indicator
Mine free world with no more new mine laying and destruction of existing stockpiles	New deployment of landmines or use of weapons with similar effects
	Number of mines left for training purposes
	Number of mines destroyed in stockpiles outside training stocks
	Area in km ² or number of mines cleared

A significant increase of mine clearance efforts or stockpile destruction is merely a qualifier on how to realize this goal. This is further acknowledged in suggested criteria 17, 18 and 19 below.

Criterion 16	Level of effectiveness and progress of mine clearance
Criterion 17	Progress or level of stockpile destruction

G. Preamble Paragraph 7: The Convention on Certain Conventional Weapons

Noting the inclusion in Amended Protocol II²⁰¹ to the Convention on Prohibitions or Restrictions on the Use of Certain Conventional Weapons Which May Be Deemed to Be Excessively Injurious or to Have Indiscriminate Effects²⁰² of a number of provisions of importance for mine-clearance operations, notably the requirement of detectability, and provision of information and technical and material assistance necessary to remove or otherwise render ineffective minefields, mines and booby traps, and noting also that Amended Protocol II to the Convention entered into force on 3 December 1998,

a. Analysis

1. The CCW& MBT: the odd or happy couple?

Several international legal instruments serve the noble cause of halting or restricting usage of indiscriminate and excessively injurious weapons. It provides a positive stimulus to countries in a commensurate position to mobilize the necessary resources to eradicate mine contamination in many mine-affected countries. In this regard, the Convention on the use of Certain Conventional Weapons (CCW) and the Anti-Personnel Mine Ban Treaty (MBT) are renowned legal instruments. The MBT is also referred to as the “*Ottawa Convention*” or as the “*Convention on the Prohibition of the Use, Stockpiling and Transfer of Anti-Personnel Mines (APM) and on Their Destruction*”. This Convention was ratified much later (1997) than the CCW. Three consecutive preamble paragraphs, PP 7 to PP9, address a variety of normative issues related to the CCW. The MBT will be addressed comprehensively in PP 10 and 11, again focusing on norm building aspects. Some of the game theoretic aspects will be discussed after having addressed the normative aspects of both conventions. How the CCW relates to the MBT and vice versa will be discussed throughout the relevant preamble paragraphs.

2. The pioneering CCW legal framework

The CCW merits acknowledgement for its first attempts to restrain significantly the widespread use of landmines at a global level. Part of its relentless efforts has been the revision of military doctrine on the usage of landmines has been part of its relentless efforts. The Convention is part of a broader political and legal regime which deals with the conduct of armed conflict, including the four 1949 Geneva Conventions on the Protection of the Victims of War and the 1899 and 1907 Hague Conventions Respecting the Laws and Customs of War on Land. Together, these treaties attempt to reduce the suffering caused by armed conflicts and provide protection to the victims of war in a manner consistent with legitimate military requirements. The full name of the convention is, therefore: “*Convention on Prohibitions or Restrictions on the Use of Certain Conventional Weapons Which May be Deemed to be Excessively Injurious or to Have Indiscriminate Effects.*”

The relevant CCW Protocol for the high politics of mine action, *Protocol II*, was adopted in 1980 together with the CCW framework convention. Protocol I on Non-detectable Fragments and Protocol III on Prohibitions or Restrictions on the Use of Incendiary Weapons were adopted simultaneously. While the MBT bans only the use of Anti-Personnel Landmines, the CCW Protocol II or the Mine Protocol deals with the subject of (1) landmines, (2) booby-traps and (3) other devices. Notably, Protocol II only restricts the indiscriminate use of landmines. While it allows the use of remotely delivered mines, it says that they must have a self-destructing and self-deactivating mechanism.²⁰³ Protocol II was amended on May 1996 and came into effect on December 1998, known today as the Amended Protocol II.²⁰⁴ The technical and other requirements to the design

²⁰¹ UN Document. CCW/CONF.I/16 (Part I), Annex B, New York

²⁰² United Nations Disarmament Yearbook, vol. 5: 1980 (United Nations publication, Sales No. E.81.IX.4), appendix VII, New York

²⁰³ GICHD Publication (2004). *A guide to mine action*, Geneva, p.164

²⁰⁴ Full text of the Convention and Protocols is available at the UN Disarmament Web page on: <http://disarmament.un.org/ccw/index.html>, accessed on 10 December 2004

and the use of mines, booby-traps and other devices, aimed at minimizing their humanitarian impact.²⁰⁵ Today the CCW has been expanded with two more Protocols. In 1995, a Protocol IV was added to outlaw the use of laser weapons specifically designed to blind and, most recently (2005) the important Protocol V regarding Explosive Remnants of War. The latter will be addressed when discussing preamble paragraph 9.

3. CCW revival

The CCW recently regained significant political interest, support and relevance. Since the CCW did not call for a total ban of anti-personnel mines, it was overshadowed by the MBT for several years and still has a considerably lower number of UN Member States' consent to be bound to its Amended Protocol II. However, due to its evolutionary character and proactive approach regarding the quite specific provisions mentioned above, the CCW became increasingly important in pursuing a legal framework for explosive remnants of war and mines other than anti-personnel mines. Many countries which belong to the States Parties to the Mine Ban Treaty are also States Parties²⁰⁶ to the CCW, although both have a substantially different philosophy.

The MBT takes an *absolute position*, aiming for a world free of anti-personnel landmines, whilst the CCW envisages a rigorously *controlled usage of the full spectrum of landmines*, including anti-vehicle mines. This implies that for countries which are States Parties to both Conventions, the total ban provisions on anti-personnel landmines of the MBT overrules the applicable provisions of the Protocol II part of the CCW. For States Parties to the MBT, the direct political utility of the CCW is to regulate in particular the usage of mines other than anti-personnel mines. Even with the substantial differences between both political and legal instruments, a detailed analysis is required of the number of UN Member States consent to be bound with the CCW compared to the number adhering to the MBT. This will further characterise the high politics and efforts involved in universalizing both treaties.

4 The CCW as a “self-enforcing” legal instrument: the *compliance game*

Through Amended Protocol II and its other protocols, the CCW has shown remarkable adaptation towards what is politically achievable and the changing impact of modern warfare. The complementary effects of the norm building processes of the CCW and the MBT need to be further highlighted when studying the consecutive preamble paragraphs. It is not the purpose of this section to extensively cover the strengths and weaknesses of the CCW, but to address a few points of direct interest for the game theoretic aspects. In absence of an international enforcement mechanism, specific interest goes to the level of compliance and which factors in the future might influence it. Analysing compliance to a multilateral treaty has its unique complexities but it can be basically reduced to studying utility aspects of compliance versus violation or defection. As long as the utility to comply, taking into account the discounting of future payoffs, outweighs the utility to defect, then a stable solution concept prevails. This is again in accordance with the assumption of rationality, whereby national interest and utility maximization is the motivating power behind State action.

²⁰⁵ Amendments to Protocol II

(1) Expansion of the scope of the Protocol to include internal armed conflicts.

(2) Party laying mines is responsible for their removal, destruction, and/or maintenance.

(3) Prohibition on the use and transfer of non-detectable anti-personnel landmines (APL).

(4) The principle that non-self-destructing APL may be used only within perimeter marked areas, protected and monitored to ensure the effective exclusion of civilians.

(5) Remotely-delivered mines must self-destruct within 30 days at 90% reliability and self-deactivate within 120 days with overall reliability of 99.9%.

(6) Prohibition on the transfer of any mine the use of which is prohibited by the Protocol.

²⁰⁶ In case of the CCW the terminology of ‘High Contracting Parties’ is used in lieu of ‘States Parties’.

As mentioned earlier, the CCW lacks verification and enforcement mechanisms and spells out no formal process for resolving compliance concerns. This puts the “entering into *force*” of the CCW and related protocols in a more modest perspective. A State Party can refute its commitment to the CCW or any of the protocols, but it will remain “legally bound” until one year after notifying the treaty depositary, the UN Secretary-General, of its intent to be free of its obligations.²⁰⁷ A compliance mechanism will only be credible if violations can be deterred through credible sanctions. The mechanism of the CCW is however limited to the (1) prevention and suppression of violations, (2) penal sanctions, (3) appropriate training of military personnel, and (4) consultations.²⁰⁸ Much depends on the States Parties to take the appropriate legislative steps at a national level. These national legislative measures should prevent and suppress violations of the Protocol by persons or on territory under its jurisdiction or control.²⁰⁹ However, in absence of a credible international sanction mechanism, international actions are limited to the earlier discussed *name & shame* campaigns and generation of *domestic and international audience costs*. Strictly taken, the CCW qualifies as a “*self-enforcing*” agreement, since it satisfies two elementary conditions: (1) each State Party complies as long as everyone else does, and (2) there is no external mechanism needed to ensure compliance.²¹⁰ It further underscores Waltz’s descriptions on how international treaties are part of a “*self-help*” system;²¹¹ whereby those international commitments are only viable as long as it is sufficiently in the State’s interest to continue to voluntarily comply with their obligations. This is obviously a vulnerable concept in disarmament matters and virtually reduces the value of the CCW and MBT to *promissory notes*. In game theoretic terms, this aspect of the politics involved could be labelled as a *voluntary compliance game*.²¹²

Proponents of voluntary compliance argue that it is in a nation’s own interest to behave responsibly and that in pursuit of a credible international image, the nations will withdraw from taking actions, which could damage its image perception domestically and/or internationally. Thus there is no need for robust compliance enforcement mechanisms. With violations or non-compliance being rare, compliance of States Parties to the CCW portrays the basic characteristics of a Nash equilibrium. Specific military requirements or threats to national security are often the only triggers which can disrupt existing equilibriums. In normal circumstances, States Parties to the CCW will unlikely change their position unilaterally. Rather in a *retaliatory* manner, States Parties would violate the provisions of Amended Protocol II, in particular when threats to its national security cause the self-interest of a State to dramatically change the payoff structure. This in turn portrays the characteristics of a *tit-for-tat* game which will be discussed in detail within the context of new deployments of landmines (preamble paragraph 12).

²⁰⁷CCW at a glance, Internet. Available at www.armscontrol.org/pdf/CCW.pdf, accessed on 10 August 2005

²⁰⁸ Convention on Certain Conventional Weapons - Article 14 stipulates this in more detail.

²⁰⁹ Sixth Annual Conference of States Parties to CCW Amended Protocol II, States Parties Appeal for Wider Adherence to Amended Protocol II on Prohibition of Mines, Booby-Traps and Other Devices, 17 November 2004, <http://www2.unog.ch/news2/documents/newsen/dc04041e.htm>

²¹⁰ HOVI, J. (1998). *Games, Threats and Treaties*, Virginia, p.121

²¹¹ WALTZ, K. (1979). *Theory of International Politics*, McGraw-Hill Humanities/Social Sciences, p.105-107

²¹² The concept of “voluntary compliance” enjoys a more frequent use to explain corporate behaviour whereby companies voluntarily adhere to self-imposed regulations but in practice often follow profit maximising behaviour which can result in violating stakeholder’s interests. Internet. Available at http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Voluntary_compliance, accessed on 29 January 2007

b. Deductions

1. Key points

- ☞ The CCW and MBT offer largely a complementary approach in terms of landmines and ERW: the CCW Amended Protocol II is broad-based and regulatory; the MBT is narrow and absolute in its total ban on landmines.
- ☞ The CCW reflects the first efforts of the international community to restrain the widespread use of landmines at a global level. CCW-Amended Protocol II was temporarily overshadowed by the MBT but has regained political significance due to its dynamic posture towards quickly evolving norms and practices in modern warfare.
- ☞ The CCW-AP II is largely a *self-enforcing* agreement due to the absence of a credible deterrence, thereby portraying the characteristics of a *voluntary compliance game*. *Name & shame* or the generation of *audience costs* are the only credible but limited sanctions available to the international community in case of non-compliance. The CCW's legally binding character is rather to be interpreted as a "*promissory note*", part of an international "*self-help*" mechanism.
- ☞ The self-regulatory game theoretic characteristics of a "*voluntary compliance game*" have been comprehensively addressed above. They largely explain the envisaged compliance of States parties to the CCW, even in absence of substantial sanctions in case of violations.
- ☞ States Parties comply because there is no benefit of changing unilaterally their strategy to non-compliance, hence, a Nash equilibrium. Name & shame and the possible creation of audience costs are the inadequate tools available to actors with a watchdog function such as the ICBL. In absence of a Nash equilibrium, the "*self-help*" system would fail because it is largely based on *political goodwill*. However, without a credible compliance mechanism, adherence to a treaty is by definition a most vulnerable concept. More game theoretic analysis provided in the discussion of consecutive preamble paragraphs will further explain both possible strategic choices of compliance or non-compliance with its possible consequences.
- ☞ Through its Protocols the CCW has shown a remarkable adaptation to the excessively injurious and in particular *indiscriminate* effects of conventional weapons of modern warfare. Owing to its more flexible regulatory provisions compared to a total ban, the related CCW thematic UN resolution has been systematically *adopted without a vote*.
- ☞ A comparative analysis between the CCW and MBT on the number of UN Member States *consent to be bound* to the respective treaties could provide interesting insights.

2. Possible indicators and criteria

Although not explicitly reflected in this preamble paragraph, the goal of the international (mine action) community is to achieve universal adherence to the CCW, Amended Protocol II and attain durable and full compliance with all provisions on the use of landmines. The criteria and indicators are, therefore, strictly subordinate to the adherence, compliance or support for the CCW, Amended Protocol II. This will at least qualify and possibly quantify the adherence of UN Member States to the CCW objectives.

Goal	Indicator
Universal adherence to the CCW – Amended Protocol II	Number of States consent to be bound by the CCW – Amended Protocol II
	Support for the CCW resolution
	Level of compliance – number of violations

Criterion 18	Adherence to the CCW - Amended Protocol II and progress on its universalization
Criterion 19	Compliance with the Amended Protocol II and its technical provisions
Criterion 20	Being supportive to the CCW resolution

H. Preamble Paragraph 8: The CCW and its dynamic review process

Noting also the conclusions and recommendations adopted at the Fourth and Fifth Annual Conferences of the States Parties to Amended Protocol II to the Convention on Prohibitions or Restrictions on the Use of Certain Conventional Weapons Which May Be Deemed to Be Excessively Injurious or to Have Indiscriminate Effects, held in Geneva on 11 December 2002 and on 26 November 2003, respectively,

a. Analysis

1. A dynamic consultative and review process: broadening of the CCW scope of application

Besides more elaborate CCW Review Conferences, States Parties to the CCW meet to deliberate on the functioning of the Protocol in “Annual Conferences of the States Parties to Amended Protocol II”.²¹³ This consultative process has been generally less comprehensive than the more systematic “*intersessionals*” and review process related to the MBT. It promotes primarily a higher degree of universality of the Amended Protocol II by reiterating the request for all States that have not yet done so to accede to the Protocol. Similar to the MBT reporting,²¹⁴ which will be discussed in the respective MBT paragraphs, national annual reports from the States Parties to the CCW are collected during the Annual Conferences. These reports contain information on mine clearance and rehabilitation programmes and steps taken to meet the technical requirements of the Protocol, including legislation related to the Protocol and international cooperation and assistance.

The *Review Conferences* are substantially different from the *Annual Conferences* of States Parties to the CCW. The amendment process during Review Conferences strengthens Protocol II²¹⁵ by extending the scope of its application to intrastate armed conflicts and through prohibiting the use of non-detectable anti-personnel mines, and restricting the use of non-self-destructing or self-deactivating mines to monitored, marked areas.²¹⁶ This extension of the CCW’s scope of application is a substantial development of international humanitarian law and helps ensure that its fundamental rules apply in all situations of armed conflict. As most conflicts today are of an intra-State nature, it is vital that the various forms of protection afforded to civilians and combatants in international conflict apply equally in non-international armed conflicts.

2. Adjusting to modern armament and warfare

The evolutionary character of the CCW resulted in the review of Protocol II. This review reflects interesting levels of cooperation as a direct consequence of the technological advancement of landmines. With the modifications, self-destructing mines may be used without any specific restrictions on their placement. Critics, in particular ICRC, rightly point out the risks involved. As new types of mines can be remotely delivered over long distances and in huge quantities by artillery or aircraft, their use could lead to an increase in civilian mine casualties. When mines are remotely delivered, their accurate marking and mapping becomes virtually impossible. The revised Protocol places no new restrictions on the use of anti-tank or vehicle mines, which, although used on a smaller scale than anti-personnel mines, are just as indiscriminate. These mines may continue to be used even if they are not detectable: neither their placement nor maximum lifetime is subject to specific control. In addition, the Second CCW Review Conference set up a *Group of Government*

²¹³ In accordance with Article 13 of CCW-Amended Protocol II.

²¹⁴ In accordance with Article 7 of the Mine Ban Treaty.

²¹⁵ For only the second time since it was adopted in 1980, States gathered to review the status and operation of the Convention on Certain Conventional Weapons (CCW). The Review Conference of States Parties, which was held in Geneva from 11 to 21 December 2001, provided an important opportunity to strengthen international humanitarian law and consider new regulations on weapons which may cause superfluous injury or have indiscriminate effects.

²¹⁶ On the basis of a proposal by the United States, States Parties agreed to amend the CCW framework Convention (Art. 1). Unlike the first Review Conference, which took place in 1995 and 1996, there was no opposition to this extension.

*Experts*²¹⁷ which addressed the increasingly important issue of “explosive remnants of war”. This will be discussed during the assessment of the next Preamble Paragraph. In general, the Review Conference encouraged States Parties to continue efforts to limit the wounding potential of small weapon systems²¹⁸ and to establish a more effective mechanism to monitor compliance with the CCW.

b. Deductions

1. Key points

- ☞ The Review Conferences further highlight the progressive norm building process of the CCW in terms of installing specific limits on the use of land mines, e.g. non-detectable, remotely delivered and persistent landmines.
- ☞ The Review Conference resulted in the establishment of a Group of Government Experts which provides the momentum for the political process related to Protocol V – ERW and mines other than anti-personnel landmines (MOTAPM).

2. Possible indicators and criteria

There are few new elements in this paragraph which can further validate the outcome of the analysis. This paragraph merely connects preamble paragraph 7 and 9, addressing Amended Protocol II and Protocol V on ERW respectively. The goals are inextricably linked to universalizing adherence to the CCW and efforts to optimize its implementation. Hence, the criteria are the same as of the previous preamble paragraph.

Goal	Indicator
Effective and universal adherence to the CCW process.	Number of States Parties consent to be bound to the CCW
Criteria	Idem criteria 18 and 19

²¹⁷ Reference to document CCW/CONF.II/2 the Expert Group was established with two separate coordinators, one for explosive remnants of war and the other for mines other than anti-personnel mines. This Group of Government Experts meets about three times per year, Internet. Available at www.mineaction.org, accessed on 10 July 2005

²¹⁸ The Conference also adopted a Final Declaration which makes reference to multipurpose explosive bullets, legal reviews for new weapons, means or methods of warfare and blinding laser weapons.

I. Preamble Paragraph 9: The CCW and Explosive Remnants of War

Noting further the **new additional Protocol** to address the **post-conflict impact of explosive remnants of war** adopted by the Meeting of States Parties to the Convention on Prohibitions or Restrictions on the Use of Certain Conventional Weapons Which May Be Deemed to Be Excessively Injurious or to Have Indiscriminate Effects, held in Geneva on 27 and 28 November 2003, and noting the agreement reached on mandates for further work by the same Meeting,

a. Analysis

1. ERW, the main indiscriminate threat of the new millennium?

While the international community has taken significant steps to end the injury, suffering and fatalities caused by anti-personnel landmines, large numbers of civilians are killed or injured each year by other explosive munitions. Such weapons include anti-vehicle mines, sub-munitions from airborne cluster bombs (CB) or land-based systems, artillery shells, hand-grenades, rockets and other similar ordnance. Like anti-personnel mines, these Explosive Remnants of War (ERW) are increasingly cited as having a similar or bigger impact than anti-personnel mines. Modern warfare created vast ERW problems which tend regularly to overshadow the global landmine problem. It is an example how new conditions on the ground affect norm building processes and perceptions of the problems.

“Another area that has received too little attention is ERW—particularly CMs²¹⁹—which are also affecting the lives of millions of people around the world. In some heavily contaminated countries, trends have shifted, and more civilian accidents are caused by ERW than by landmines. Indeed, such was the case in Cambodia last year. Addressing the ERW problem, including CMs, requires urgent attention. ERW/CMs have similar impact (if not more) on communities as landmines. Current thinking with respect to ERW/CMs is at a nascent stage, as it was in 1988 regarding landmines. Should we learn from the landmine experience and take immediate action in this area, or wait 16 years to learn it all over again the hard way? This choice must be made—and quickly.”²²⁰

Fig. II.13: Post-conflict impact of mines and ERW in Lebanon, following the cluster bombs attacks (2006)

²¹⁹ CM stands for the abbreviation of cluster munitions

²²⁰ AQA, S. (2005). Mine Action: Success and Challenges. *Journal of Mine Action*, Issue 9.1, MAIC - James Madison University, Washington DC

By design, sub-munitions are *area weapons*. Once delivered by cluster bomb, rocket or other means, they are dispersed over a large area called a “*cluster bomb footprint*” and sometimes in excess of one hundred thousand square metres. Figure II.14²²¹ illustrates the impact of the most recent conflict between Israel and Lebanon whereby the majority of cluster bombs were fired by artillery. In this case a buffer-footprint of 250 meters radius is used. When targeting is imprecise or a mistake is made, the effects of missing the target in a civilian area can be far greater than with traditional ordnance. Cluster bombs scatter scores of tiny explosives and many of the small bombs fail to explode, in effect littering the conflict area with thousands of small land mines. Large numbers of civilians may be caught in sub-munitions attacks and suffer collateral damage when such weapons are used on nearby military objectives. It obviously becomes a violation of international law when civilians are deliberately targeted.

Fig. II.14: The simultaneous use of similarly looking food packages air dropped over Afghanistan was one of the shocking moments in the history of the use of cluster bombs munitions.

“The rights group Amnesty International and UN human rights experts have accused Israel of deliberately targeting civilian areas and indiscriminate use of cluster bombs during the July-August war. The groups allege Israel laid mines and dropped as many as 4 million cluster bombs on Lebanon. [...] UN ordnance clearing experts have said that up to 1 million cluster bombs failed to explode and continue to threaten civilians. Israel says use of cluster bombs is permitted under international law.”²²²

2. Protocol V of the CCW, a crucial step forward in addressing ERW

The political will of States Parties to address new issues, such as explosive remnants of war, anti-vehicle mines and other weapons, highlights the key role that the Convention can play in ensuring that the law remains current and responsive to developments in the nature and conduct of modern warfare. A Group of Government Experts was, therefore, established to examine the different types of munitions that become explosive remnants of war, and the features which could prevent munitions from becoming explosive remnants of war in the first place. Notably this Group also assesses the adequacy of existing international humanitarian law in minimizing the post-conflict risks of ERW and issues related to assistance and cooperation.²²³

Importantly, none of the polarization which has hindered discussions in other multilateral negotiations, such as the Review Conference of the Biological Weapons Convention, was present in the CCW context. The Second Review Conference of the CCW has shown that the treaty can maintain a dynamic regime. New political and other issues related to conventional weapons can be examined and regulations developed if necessary. The speedy ratification of Protocol V by States Parties is indicative for its initial success.²²⁴ It also indicates a shift in focus from anti-personnel landmines and a better understanding of the actors of the specific strengths of the CCW-process.

“Clarifying terms of reference became pertinent in the course of discussions on ‘explosive remnants of war’ leading up to the Second Review Conference of the Convention on Certain Conventional Weapons (CCW), which was held in Geneva in December 2001. The general view of delegates was that anti-personnel mines

²²¹ Composition of maps available at IRIN, Internet. Available at www.irinnews.org, accessed on 8 January 2007

²²² Cluster bombs injure five in Lebanon, Associated Press, Internet. Available at

http://news.yahoo.com/s/ap/20061225/ap_on_re_mi_ea/lebanon_cluster_bomb, accessed on 25 December 2006

²²³ Convention on Certain Conventional Weapons, recent developments, Internet. Available at <http://www.us-mission.ch/ccw/ccwabout.html>, accessed on 17 January 2007

²²⁴ Protocol V was adopted on November 28, 2003 in Geneva and enjoyed its entry into force on 12 November 2006.

were dealt with adequately elsewhere, and thus did not need to be part of the CCW Group of Governmental Experts' work."²²⁵

However, similar to high politics perceptions of complex landmine clearance issues, also regarding ERW, it could be questioned how well the high politics connect with the low politics or address the real challenges on the ground.

"The CCW's working term for ERW is not particularly helpful for researchers because it is a diplomatic term that does not necessarily resemble the way information is collected in the field. The reality is that for an area to be made safe, deminers have to clear all munitions present."²²⁶

Recent efforts of the ICRC included proposals to restrict the use of cluster bombs and other sub-munitions, calling for a prohibition on the use of sub-munitions against any military objective situated within a concentration of civilians. The reason for this rule is that not only do large numbers of sub-munitions fail to explode as intended after they are dropped or launched (an estimated average of 10%-20%), but because of their devastating area-wide impact these weapons have. Even when they function properly, their indiscriminate effects on civilians are significant. As addressed before, *name & shame* tactics are also applied with varying levels of success. The outspoken example below is again of the most recent and extensive usage of cluster bombs against Lebanon.

"While the statement refers to the devastating 34-day war that killed 1301 Lebanese and 157 Israelis, why does it dare not name those on both sides who committed these war crimes? Why is the statement so damning of the bombs but never names the bombers? Is it assumed that all readers already know or is it deemed irrelevant in the context of apolitical humanitarian aid? Perhaps any finger pointing of Israel is a political landmine that our Foreign Minister needs to tiptoe around.[...] Also, we should support the 25 nations who recently committed to a new international agreement to regulate cluster bombs and back international efforts to circumvent the supply chain of cluster bombs by pressuring the US to stop supplying Israel with these weapons.[...]. Lastly, we should call a spade a spade on the international public record by naming Israel and indeed Hezbollah."²²⁷

The repetition of the broad-based lobbying effort of NGOs in obtaining support of State actors is remarkable, even establishing a "*Cluster Munitions Coalition*". Analogue to the banning of landmines, Belgium was again the frontrunner in ratifying national law banning the use of cluster munitions in February 2006. This took place together with Norway's adoption of a moratorium and call for an international treaty banning this weapon.

3. Protocol V; another paradox in disarmament politics?

With the tremendous ERW problems in Lebanon, Iraq and Afghanistan, the US urges all states to adhere to Protocol V to the Convention on Explosive Remnants of War, enjoying an impetus after entering into force on November 12, 2006. President Bush transmitted this Protocol to the US Senate for advice and consent to ratification on June 20, 2006.²²⁸ The US had a huge impact on the political process leading to Protocol V, for obvious reasons of national self-interest. They proclaim that States should now focus on fully implementing Protocol V and applicable law of war rules, and not on negotiating new rules on cluster munitions or other explosive remnants of war.²²⁹ This is just one of the many examples where the US is, in many cases, the main cause of the problem, whilst pressuring States into accepting their preferred policies or strategic choices.

²²⁵ Explosive remnants of war – A global survey – The United Kingdom Department for International Development (DFID) funded the research and production of this report., Published in June 2003 by Landmine Action, 89 Albert Embankment, London Landmine Action 2003 – p.4

²²⁶ Landmine Action (2003). *Explosive remnants of war – A global survey*, Landmine Action, London, p.5

²²⁷ WAKIM, J. (2007). *Bombers should be named*, Internet. Available at <http://www.news.com.au>, accessed 13 February 2007

²²⁸ Internet. Available at <http://www.us-mission.ch/Press2006/0621Protocols.html>, accessed on 29 April 2005

²²⁹ The United States is of the opinion that the strict rules of Protocol V, in combination with the existing law of war, and the Geneva and Hague Conventions, will mitigate the effect of explosive remnants of war, including cluster munitions, on civilians. Review Conference on the Convention on Certain Conventional Weapons, Media Note, Office of the Spokesman, Washington, DC. November 3, 2006. Available at <http://www.us-mission.ch/ccw/110706MediaNote.html>, accessed on 5 January 2007

To a certain extent it is a paradox, one could call it the “*pot calling the kettle black*” paradox. In most cases, the majority of States in conflict neither have the capabilities nor the weapon systems to comply with the strict US rules of engagement. Most war-fighting nations are at odds with the sophisticated US targeting methods to decrease post-conflict threats or impact. They are not capable or willing to share munitions strike data with humanitarian organizations, partly because of fear they will be held accountable for clearance and victim assistance. The following ongoing investigations support this:

“Israel has insisted that all the weaponry it used during the 33-day summer war was in compliance with international law. However, Lt Gen Dan Halutz, Chief Of Staff of the Israeli Defense Forces (IDF), in November ordered an investigation into the military's use of cluster bombs during the war, specifically the IDF's Northern Command unit. A month earlier, the US State Department launched an inquiry into whether Israel misused US-made cluster bombs in Lebanon. The investigation is looking into what munitions were used and whether they were used against non-military targets. Washington has supplied Israel with cluster bombs since the 1970s on the understanding that they would only be used against defined *military* targets.”²³⁰

4. New CCW protocols in the making: self-enforcement through tailored “*package deals*”?

Owing to the dynamic nature of the CCW-Protocol structure, more latitude exists to obtain better cooperation of State actors than with the rather rigid Mine Ban Treaty. The Third Review Conference²³¹ of the States Parties to the CCW reviewed again the operation of the Convention's protocols, thereby welcoming the entry into force of a fifth protocol addressing ERW, and considering new restrictions on anti-vehicle landmines. Anti-vehicle landmines can pose as great a threat to civilians as anti-personnel landmines although no strict provisions are foreseen in the CCW, let alone the MBT. The current negotiation process to adopt a new protocol to strictly regulate the use of anti-vehicle mines called upon the remaining delegations to seize the opportunity to adopt the protocol at the Review Conference, or to admit that it is not possible to achieve consensus at this time.

A proposal for a protocol on anti-vehicle mines has now been formally cosponsored by a dozen States and enjoys growing support. It is known as the *coalition* of the “*12 Nation Proposal*”. The US has been particularly proactive in this group of like-minded States. This small alliance, however, is still opposed by several countries. Those who support the proposal for a new protocol are hopeful that objections can be overcome and progress made in addressing the serious problems that can be posed by the use of anti-vehicle mines.²³² Much remains to be done to develop a legal framework for Mines Other Than Anti Personnel Mines, often abbreviated as MOTAPM. However, thus far all the political efforts have had at least a strong norm building effect.

The combination of the growing number of CCW Protocols portrays increasingly the game theoretic benefits of a modular concept of *package deals*. In its entirety, the modular concept of the CCW seeks to provide new rules for the protection of military personnel and, particularly, civilians and civilian objects from injury or attack under various conditions by means of fragments that cannot readily be detected in the human body by X-rays.²³³ In absence of an enforcement and verification mechanism, States Parties can with relative impunity refute their commitment to the CCW or any of the protocols. Moreover, States can adhere to the CCW as long as they have only adopted two of the five protocols²³⁴, the minimum required to be considered a signatory. Hence, the

²³⁰ BBC News, US probes Israel cluster bomb use, 25 August 2006, http://news.bbc.co.uk/2/low/middle_east/5286352.stm

²³¹ Third CCW Conference took place in Geneva, Switzerland, November 7– 17, 2006

²³² Rationale for a New Protocol on Anti-vehicle Mines (2002, November 26). Available at <http://www.ccw-treaty.com/260902avmines.htm>, accessed on 5 January 2007

²³³ This includes attacks by landmines, booby traps, incendiary weapons and blinding laser weapons.

²³⁴ The US for example has only adopted CCW protocol II and V.

prospects of adherence or compliance to the CCW as a whole are more positive because not adhering or defecting to comply with one of its protocols generates a smaller *audience cost* than not adhering or defecting to comply with the CCW in its totality. This modular concept of protocols to the CCW enhances the self-enforcement of the agreement as a whole. The benefits of a modular “*package deal*” concept can be summarized as follows:

“[...] the prospects for designing a self-enforcing agreement could improve considerably if several issues are linked together in one agreement. In particular, linkage may be an advantage if external enforcement is difficult or even impossible. The reason is that in a *package deal* it suffices that the entire agreement is self-enforcing. The same need not to be true for its individual components.”²³⁵

b. Deductions

1. Key points

- ☞ ERW can have at least a similar impact on affected population groups as landmines, especially in terms of protracted collateral damage of cluster bomb munitions. Inevitably current ERW problems substantially affect norm building in the politics of mine action.
- ☞ The CCW portrays a dynamic and evolutionary normative process; new protocols are considered for anti-vehicle mines and cluster bomb munitions. Protocol V has been fundamental for ERW to frame the problem and receive considerable attention and political momentum; its speedy ratification is indicative for its further success. The modular concept of protocols, with various tailored combinations of “*package deals*”, enhances adherence and compliance with the CCW in a regime of self-enforcement. However, much remains to be done by like-minded States to develop a legal framework for Mines Other Than Anti Personnel Mines (MOTAPM).
- ☞ Nevertheless, Protocol V, together with other ongoing initiatives regarding a ban on cluster bombs or a protocol installing additional restrictions on the use of MOTAPM, convincingly illustrate that the principles of the “*Ottawa model*” can be successfully repeated, albeit on a smaller scale. The analysis of the following MBT related preamble paragraphs will address extensively the modalities and political implications of this model.
- ☞ The “*pot calling the kettle black*” paradox has been initiated for this study to characterize the double standards phenomenon portrayed by powerful nations, in particular the US, regarding armament and disarmament.
- ☞ There were no distinct games identified, although certain game theoretic characteristics addressed can be related to the level of compliance with the CCW. Both effects of possible *package deals* and *double standards* are indicative for the complexities to install a legal regime when facing an ever-changing regulatory environment in which landmines and cluster munitions are used, together with the tremendous post-conflict fall out of ERW.

2. Possible indicators and criteria

The normative deductions can be summarized in terms of consent of States Parties to be bound by Protocol V, which also guides the criterion formulation.

Goal	Indicator
Universal adherence to ERW protocol V	Number of States adopting protocol V
Criterion 21	Adherence to Protocol V of the CCW and progress on its universalization

²³⁵HOVI, J. (1998). *Games, Threats and Treaties: understanding commitments in international relations*, Virginia, Chapter 5 – Explaining Compliance

J. Preamble Paragraph 10: The Anti-Personnel Mine Ban Treaty

Noting that additional States have ratified or acceded to the Convention on the Prohibition of the Use, Stockpiling, Production and Transfer of Anti-personnel Mines and on Their Destruction, which entered into force on 1 March 1999, bringing the total number of States that have formally accepted the obligations therein to one hundred and forty-one,

a. Analysis

1. The Mine Ban Treaty (MBT): an ending or never-ending success story?

The MBT's limited role in only banning of *anti-personnel* mines is key to understand the politics. It has no provisions regarding other important areas such as ERW, which are covered by the CCW. Previous analysis highlighted how the CCW-Amended II Protocol has been overshadowed by the MBT perceived success story. The assessment below will put this in perspective. Not necessarily to spell out some polarisation as in the following statement but to factually compare the influence both legal instruments have on the norm building process.

"The Anti-Personnel Mine Ban Convention of 1997, commonly called the "Mine Ban Treaty," or more often the "Ottawa Treaty," is loved by some - loathed by others. To some it is the lynchpin of mine action activities, to others it is a distracter from pragmatic mine action challenges. Some will not take action against mines without "it" being invoked, others will not take action if "it" is invoked."²³⁶

Both cited positions capture well some of the opposing political dynamics of the fastest ratified treaty in history; maybe too fast. Many States Parties to the MBT realize now they underestimated the task at hand. A significant number do not live up to the required commitments enshrined in key paragraphs of the MBT. The statement below reveals in a subtle though lucid manner the differing aspirations between the politics or policy of mine action and those behind a "mine free" world:

"Mine action is a dynamic, active enterprise. By its very nature, it is a process of discovery, of uncovering the unknown. A great deal has been learned in the field during the past seven years and some of this knowledge diverges from the tenets of the Ottawa Convention. Mine action has the potential, if allowed, to eliminate the most pressing effects of landmines in fairly short order. The future of mine action and the future of the Ottawa Convention, while sharing common goals and aspirations, are not the same -- and this is not necessarily a bad thing."²³⁷

2. More on "double standards" or "pot calling the kettle black" paradox

The above polarization captures again some delicate aspects of the paradoxical nature of disarmament politics. The MBT has accentuated how State actors can play opposing roles simultaneously: be active mine action partners, yet contradict the MBT. States having immense stockpiles of weapons belong simultaneously to the most vocal disarmament advocates. Some of these actors dictate other States to abandon their possession or accession of those "prohibited" weapons or strictly regulate its use. Treaties like the MBT, CCW or the Non-Proliferation Treaty are therefore regarded as unjust or discriminating by many under-developed countries. For example, high-technology landmines with self-deactivating mechanism are allowed by the CCW. Inevitably this technology comes at an additional cost, making landmines no longer a weapon for the poor to protect themselves against adversary elements. Whilst the US, as the most outspoken advocate of these technologically advanced mines, can easily comply with the new CCW regulations and restrictions, this is much more difficult or virtually impossible for other countries. The creation of new terms such as "*non-persistent mines*" are interesting normative aspects in order to generate a

²³⁶ BARLOW, D. (2004). The Ottawa Convention in Perspective. *Journal of Mine Action*, Issue 8.1, MAIC - James Madison University, Washington DC

²³⁷ Post Nairobi Summit: Perspectives on Global Policies to End the Landmine Crisis Panel Discussion, United Nations Association of the United States of America (UNA-USA), New York, March 5, 2005

new, more permissive, public perception on the possible use of landmines in either defensive or offensive operations. It also further underscores the “*pot calling the kettle black*” paradox.

“The United States stands alone in seeking a technological solution to the anti-personnel mine problem. Many nations have also argued that it would be unacceptable to permit wealthy nations to use sophisticated and expensive mines, but expect poorer nations to give up the cheap dumb mines available to them.”²³⁸

3. It’s all about the economics?!

This brings to mind a similar catchphrase of the 1992 Clinton-Gore campaign.²³⁹ Is the aspiration of a *mine free* world prospectless if the focus is predominantly on the bare economic facts? A possible angle on this question could be as follows:

“Yet the most significant factor limiting the future impact of the Ottawa Convention is not one of policy but one of economics. By requiring the removal of each and every last APL, without regard to cost or benefit, in order to achieve the stated aim of a ‘mine free’ world, the Ottawa Convention creates huge economic inefficiencies, inefficiencies that will in the end curtail its implementation and applicability. Through the impact survey process and fifteen years of experience, mine action practitioners know and recognize that a major proportion of the world’s mines exist in marginal land where no one lives or works. In a world of scarce resources and competing humanitarian demands -- HIV/AIDS, malaria, poverty, food security, etc. -- we can not afford the opportunity costs of spending \$3 million to clear 8 landmines as one NGO did in Chad.”²⁴⁰

This statement once again questions the absoluteness of the MBT concept of a “*mine free world*”, but the argument misses refinement. It reflects the typical pragmatic and hands-on policy of the United States but opposes strictly the opening statement of this study. For UN Secretary-General Kofi Annan rightly stated the essence of the landmine problem: “*A single land mine - or even the fear that there might be one - can hold a whole community hostage.*” It adds to the importance of having a correct perception of the problem, as previously addressed when discussing the landmine threats. Nevertheless, it is of specific interest to study these statements, both the sophisticated and more simplistic ones. These diverging norm building processes partly shape the politics and economics of mine action.

4. The economics and the politics

With the brief assessment above, it may be concluded that judging the MBT according to strict economic criteria is creating a political anachronism. These criteria were definitely not an upfront issue during the early nineties. The confrontation at that time with outright alarmingly high levels of mine victims, following the conflicts in Cambodia, Afghanistan and Mozambique, was shaping the politics more than anything else. Nevertheless there is a lot of middle ground whereby both diverging opinions can in a concessive manner, acknowledge simultaneously the politics and economics involved.

“Whereas when the Convention entered into force, little in precise terms was known about the global landmine problem or the problem faced by most affected States. Since the Convention was established, significant methodological, organization and operational advances have been made in identifying areas in which anti-personnel mines are known or suspected to be emplaced.”²⁴¹

²³⁸ USCBL 2004 Briefing on U.S. Landmine Policy. Delivered by Steve Goose, Director of Human Rights Watch Arms Division and Head of ICBL Delegation at Nairobi Summit on a Mine-Free World: First Five-Year Review Conference for the Mine Ban Treaty, Internet. Available at http://www.banminesusa.org/news/887_brief.htm, accessed on 12 November 2004

²³⁹ There was a mild recession because of the transition from a Cold War influenced economy to a peacetime economy. Clinton-Gore enjoyed six or so years of the “peace dividend”. They claimed credit for a strong economy whereby their republican counterparts argued they had no hand in creating. Their popular catchphrase: It’s all about the economics, stupid!

²⁴⁰ KIDD, R. (2005, March 5), Office of Weapons Removal and Abatement, Internet. Available at <http://www.state.gov/t/pm/rls/rm/43183.htm>, accessed on 12 April 2005

²⁴¹ Review of the operation and status of the Convention on the prohibition of the use, stockpiling, production and transfer of antipersonnel mines and on their destruction: 1999-2004, First Review Conference, Nairobi

Moreover, a treaty of this kind is not two-dimensional according to political and economic issues; its enduring strength is captured particularly in its core-humanitarian objectives. This also reflects a coordinated response of crisis and expectation management towards a suffering population.

“We are not dealing with an academic exercise or ‘business as usual’, but endeavouring to effectively address a humanitarian crisis. We are dealing with real people: children, women and men. We must translate the expectations and hopes we raised with the Convention into reality. If we succeed, the landmines campaign would truly inspire and support the humanitarian cause in other respects. That would be a real accomplishment.”²⁴²

5. Again: no universal adherence, no glory!

Similar to the preamble paragraphs of the resolution referring to the CCW, the MBT related preamble paragraphs cannot specifically advocate the Mine Ban Treaty. A fragile balance must be respected at a global level between the references to political support for the MBT and CCW in the different paragraphs of the resolution. Strong advocates of the MBT have tried almost every year to reinforce the paragraphs in order to draw out the value of the MBT to the politics of mine action more upfront. Without exception those efforts have been in vain, illustrating the true consensus character of the whole undertaking. Many of the remaining non-member States of the MBT will explicitly not allow any kind of “glorification” of the perceived successes of the Treaty, especially since the First Committee already provides for a voted resolution which strongly advocates the MBT.

With the gradual annual increase of the number of formally adhering States, the MBT continues to prove to be an increasingly supported legal instrument to halt largely the proliferation of anti-personnel landmines. However, it should not be regarded as the solution to the specific problems faced by mine-affected communities. Rather, reference to the Treaty in the context of the mine action resolution should spur the international community to a greater support for mine action programs. Even more as for the CCW, the success of the MBT has been primarily explained by the remarkably high momentum and levels of cooperation.

“Common to virtually all successes in multilateral disarmament and arms control have been 'like-minded' groups of negotiators and the countries they represent generating momentum through pro-active mutual cooperation. Examples include: the core-group in the negotiations on anti-personnel landmines that resulted in the 1997 Mine Ban Treaty; and the emergence of the seven-country New Agenda Coalition that helped to broker a success at the 2000 Review Conference of the Nuclear Non-Proliferation Treaty.”²⁴³

It is true that several powerful nations stay outside the MBT. In one sense, it is a weakness that the MBT has not been "universalised". But in another sense, there is a virtual halt to international trade, and the number of countries, in which landmines are currently being used, is down to the single digit numbers. It implies that having nations outside the MBT should neither be over- nor underestimated, instead it requires a balanced appreciation of the effects of the MBT in concrete terms:

“Of course, a treaty doesn’t make everything perfect overnight. Until the ban on use of anti-personnel mines is universally accepted, there will continue to be new mines placed in the ground. As Dianna correctly noted, the treaty will make life safer in the future, it won’t solve the existing problems or even prevent new ones.”²⁴⁴

²⁴² MASLEN, S. (2004). *Mine action after Diana: Progress in the struggle against landmines*, London, Pluto Press, p.174

²⁴³ BORRIE, J. (2006). Cooperation and Defection in the Conference on Disarmament, *Disarmament Diplomacy*, Issue No. 82

²⁴⁴ MASLEN, S. (2004). *Mine action after Diana: Progress in the struggle against landmines*, London, Pluto Press, p.170

In its catalyst function, the MBT is without any doubt successful. This is substantiated by the number of States, such as China and the United States, which attend the MBT related meetings in their observer status at regular intervals, not to express their direct interest to join the MBT, but for their interest in the related humanitarian mine action objectives. This is neither in conflict with their adherence to the CCW nor in conflict with their military doctrine.

6. Enforcement of compliance; another treaty relying on “Good-Samaritan” politics

Compliance with the MBT by States Parties has been impressive, but not absolute or uniform. Since the Mine Ban Treaty entered into force, the ICBL has consistently raised questions about how States Parties interpret and implement certain core aspects of the MBT.²⁴⁵ In particular, the ICBL has expressed concerns regarding the issues of joint military operations with non-States Parties, the prohibition on assisting banned acts, foreign stockpiling and transit of anti-personnel mines, mines with sensitive fuses and anti-handling devices, and the permissible number of anti-personnel mines retained for training and development purposes. The ICBL has pointed out that some States Parties have diverged from the predominant legal interpretation and predominant State practice on these matters.²⁴⁶ These possible mixed interpretations indicate certain normative weaknesses of the MBT, typical of a treaty drafted during challenging negotiations between the NGO community and State actors.

Under the MBT, similar to the CCW, the UN Secretary-General is responsible for organizing fact-finding missions, upon request, to investigate allegations of non-compliance. Also, the Secretary-General receives annual reports from States Parties on the measures they have taken to implement the treaty, including the locations and quantities of any and all mines.²⁴⁷ Instead of creating a new and costly organization to administer the treaty and perform inspections, the NGO community was entrusted with the task of monitoring implementation of the ban. Hence, medium politics actors almost formally verify the compliance of high politics actors. This is another, more outspoken, demonstration of how NGO community can create *audience costs* through making accusations of non-compliance. A similar partnership is developing around the small arms issue.

7. The MBT ratification: replicas in the making or cloning on demand?

The MBT is the most rapidly ratified treaty of its kind in history, reaching the required 40 State ratifications in only nine months. Efforts to replicate this so-called “model” in other disarmament domains have been a recurrent phenomenon. Sectors with many similarities such as Small Arms and Light Weapons (SALW), try to establish a similar synergy between the NGO community and State actors. An International Action Network has matching objectives with the ICBL.

“To varying degrees, each of these States²⁴⁸ has embraced the “Ottawa model” of *government-NGO collaboration*, particularly in the areas of brainstorming for policy initiatives, holding consciousness-raising seminars, and funding programs to assist reintegration of former combatants and to collect and destroy weapons. And *NGOs from the north and south recently came together* to launch a coordinating structure - the International Action Network on Small Arms - to rationalize and facilitate their research, advocacy and practical work.”²⁴⁹

²⁴⁵ Especially regarding the interpretation of Articles 1, 2, and 3 of the MBT.

²⁴⁶ Millions of Landmines Destroyed, Human Rights News, Internet. Available at <http://hrw.org/english/docs/2004/11/17/9690.htm>, accessed on 6 April 2006

²⁴⁷ The reporting provisions are stipulated in article 7 of the MBT, consequently naming it “*Article 7 reporting*”.

²⁴⁸ Countries like Belgium, Canada, Japan, the Netherlands, Norway, South Africa, and Switzerland showed a particular engagement.

²⁴⁹ LUMPE, L. (1998, November) Controlling Small Arms: Progress & Priorities. *Disarmament Diplomacy*, Issue No. 32, Internet. Available at <http://www.acronym.org.uk/textonly/dd/dd32/32lora.htm>, accessed 3 April 2005

Subsequently, the *norm* “*Ottawa process*” became short-hand for denoting a negotiating process that has two salient features: an initiative led and characterized by partnership between governmental and nongovernmental experts, practitioners, and negotiators; and, multilateral negotiations outside the established forum of the Disarmament Committee in Geneva.

Owing to this initial success, several State actors became increasingly wary of the intrusive political effects of the powerful activism of NGO alliances. To counter, *power politics* have been thrown in at an early stage by the most influential UN Member States. Former US Ambassador to the UN, Bolton, has been traditionally outspoken on these issues, even to the point of calling them undemocratic:

“We do not support the promotion of international advocacy activity by international or non-governmental organizations, particularly when those political or policy views advocated are not consistent with the views of all member States. What individual governments do in this regard is for them to decide, but we do not regard the international governmental support of particular political viewpoints to be consistent with democratic principles.”²⁵⁰

When the strongholds of NGOs intensify or even aggravate similar disputes, the counter-productive effects of a reprimanding pose of NGOs versus State actors becomes visible. Both argument and counter-argument indicate how much is at stake and how forces at the medium politics level pressure State actors through negative image building and the creation of international and/or domestic *audience costs*:

“Apparently, the Bush administration recognizes that our model could prove of decisive importance and wants to stop it now. I hope many if not all of you share my outrage at this attempt to take away our voices - - and that you will let your governments know that you are outraged that the 'world's greatest democracy' is behaving in such an undemocratic fashion.”²⁵¹

The above statements are related to replication efforts of the Ottawa model in the domain of small arms and light weapons. However, it indicates how important it is to have a comprehensive understanding of the different circumstances in which a similar model is applied. The strong and unconstructive argumentation demonstrates involvement different of payoff structures compared to the exceptional political momentum which existed at the time the MBT was crafted. It supports the general thinking that international treaties do not have much viability if one does not anticipate high levels of compliance from the outset. Even after the successful ratification of a treaty, it is likely to remain vulnerable to strong lobby groups throughout its lifetime. The position of the US military is exemplary in this regard. For decades they consolidated the strong belief that landmines should be maintained in the US weapons arsenal for its perceived military utility in even modern warfare. There again, the ICBL or other NGO tactics to highly stigmatize the US for its policy did not always attain the desired effects but could, in contrary, result in the lack of credibility.

“It should have been possible to examine the issues by: establishing the scope of the problem; determining our level of responsibility, if any; and finally, presenting solutions that are consistent with the growing tendency to send American troops in harm's way throughout the world. Unfortunately, it was not that simple. Emerging were such phenomena as: exaggerations and lies; an empty treaty; non-governmental organizations (NGOs) and others who used the former to promote the latter; and a less than fully engaged Pentagon.”²⁵²

In conclusion, both advocates and adversaries of the MBT try to generate *audience costs*, to discredit each others international image and norm building credibility. The Ottawa model has not

²⁵⁰ US DoS, Internet. Available at <http://www.state.gov/t/us/rm/2001/index.cfm?docid=4038>, accessed on 19 April 2006

²⁵¹ Jody Williams reaction on Bolton's intervention, July 2001, Small Arms and Light Weapons (SALW) negotiations at the United Nations

²⁵² Landmines, Lies, and Other Phenomena by Major General Jarvis D. Lynch, Jr., U.S. Marine Corps (Retired), Internet. <http://www.jinsa.org/articles/articles.html/function/view/categoryid/140/documentid/415/history/3,645,140,415>

proven to be a “one size fits all” concept and was primarily successful because it corresponded exceptionally well to the actual political circumstances. The politics related to small arms and light weapons (SALW) benefit from the evolutionary learning experience of medium politics actors. However, the timing and framing of the problems are quite different and, therefore, require further exploration of a multi-track approach. In conclusion, the Ottawa model and its related politics are a far cry from being a repeated sub-game equilibrium in an infinite super-game on banning all types of weapons with indiscriminate effects on innocent civilians.

8. Norm building through the annual Landmine Monitor

The Landmine Monitor, created by the ICBL, has been exemplary in recording the essential facts of the problem on a global scale and provides the Campaign backbone of *framing* the landmine problem. Indeed, although ICBL states to be objective, it remains part of a conscious effort in full support of a total ban on anti-personnel landmines. This will be further addressed when discussing aspects of public awareness in preamble paragraph 22. Annually, progress and setbacks are reported in the domains of eradication of landmine contamination, resource mobilisation, violations of treaties and other possible setbacks. Therefore, it uses a comprehensive set of indicators to portray MBT related achievements over the past years. For example, the 2004 Landmine Monitor Report lays out the major findings over a time period of five years²⁵³:

- (1) 152 countries have agreed to ban anti-personnel mines.
- (2) 62 million stockpiled anti-personnel mines have been destroyed.
- (3) More than 1100 square kilometres of land have been cleared since 1999, destroying more than 4 million AP mines, nearly 1 million anti-vehicle mines, and many more millions of pieces of unexploded ordnance.
- (4) About 22.9 million people attended MRE sessions between 1999 and 2003.
- (5) There has been no publicly acknowledged, legal trade in AP mines.

The above facts and figures respond directly to the ambitious goals and deadlines set forward in the MBT. However, apart from the decrease in the number of mine victims or casualties, all of the above indicators are rather *secondary* mine action indicators, as none of them directly reflects generated socio-economic benefits, security and peacebuilding effects. Certain socio-economic experts could refer in this case to the term “*proxy indicators*”. This reflects they are linked to the socio-economic benefits of mine action by one or more assumptions.

As mentioned in previous paragraphs, the focus of this study is not on how many square kilometres have been cleared, landmines destroyed or how many people have attended mine risk education sessions. This dissertation focuses on how politics can facilitate a best response combination of mine action activities, which should lead to an optimal reduction in human cost and security threats with a maximum generation of socio-economic benefits. Simply put, it would be a moral injustice to spend scarce resources on the clearance of existing large and dangerous minefields in deserts, mountain hills or any other minefields that have no impact in very low or non-populated areas, at the cost of more obvious urgent needs in the same or neighbouring countries. On those justifiable grounds, the MBT provides possible extensions of the 10-year deadline to clear all mines after ratification of the Convention.

“As anyone who has observed mine clearance knows, it is a slow, dangerous and tedious task. It requires absolute concentration, the right tools and courage under adverse conditions. Likewise, the full and effective implementation of this unique Convention demands of each of us absolute concentration, mobilising the necessary tools, and courage under challenging circumstances.”²⁵⁴

²⁵³ ICBL Publication. Landmine Monitor report 2004: Executive summary, page 3

²⁵⁴ ICRC statement: How to ensure progress for the Nairobi Action Plan, Statement by Dr. Jacques Forster, Vice-President of the ICRC. Sixth Meeting of the States Parties to the Convention on the Prohibition of the Use, Stockpiling, Production and Transfer of Anti-Personnel Mines and on their Destruction, Zagreb, 28 November 2005

9. The norm “mine free” versus “impact free”

According to the International Mine Action Standards, the term *mine free* is applied to an area that has been certified as clear of mines to a specified depth. This term is obviously applicable to a country or an area that has not had a mine contamination problem.²⁵⁵ The term *impact free* is a term applied to countries that may still have mines but where the mined areas do not have a negative socio-economic impact on communities, e.g. the mines may be in remote, marked and unpopulated areas. However, if one verifies how these terms are interpreted at field level then the distinction is more straightforward and indicates normative blurring of the concept of *mine free* versus *impact free*. This can be partly attributed to the efforts to come up with an unambiguous standard or norm. For example, in the eyes of the managers of the Afghan mine action programme²⁵⁶ *impact free* is described as shown below:

- (1) All high priority mined areas and battle areas will have been cleared and other lower priority areas will have been surveyed and permanently marked.
- (2) The number of mine/UXO victims will have been reduced significantly, and adequate reporting, accident surveillance, medical care, and rehabilitation will be available to mine survivors through public and community health services.
- (3) Mine awareness/risk reduction education will be available to all through schools, health and other community education programs, and community leaders.
- (4) The Government of Afghanistan will have enacted legislation banning the production, sale or use of mines. All existing stockpiles of mines will have been destroyed.
- (5) Mine action will be integrated into overall national development plans. A national Mine Action Program will be in place, with the necessary legislative framework and inter-ministerial oversight.

These five conditions indicate that at field level a less restrictive understanding exists of a mine *impact free* status, even accepting the continuation of mine accidents, albeit significantly reduced. According to these conditions, Belgium is a good example of being *impact free* but not *mine free* with an annual tonnage averaging around two hundred of ERW from World War I and II. In conclusion, *impact free* is an ambiguous concept. Although it would be sensible to prefer a treaty without utopian goal-setting of a *mine free* world, changing to *impact free* may create normative problems rather than solutions. This largely explains why the MBT remained unchanged during the First Review conference in Nairobi, 2005.

10. MBT versus CCW: global observations on consent to be bound

The preceding analysis underscored how the MBT differs in essence from the CCW, standing for a total ban and total clearance of landmines instead of seeking to regulate the use of landmines. The voting patterns of both generic resolutions, the one in support of the CCW and the other in support of the MBT bring starkly to light how different the high politics are spelled out. Figure II.15 shows the voting pattern for the UN resolution which calls upon UN Member States for the universal implementation of the MBT. Longstanding efforts of both legal instruments to obtain

Fig. II.15: Number of States consent to be bound to the MBT and CCW

²⁵⁵ IMAS definition of Mine Free and Impact Free, IMAS 04.10, Second Edition, 01 January 2003

²⁵⁶ Based on the preliminary needs assessment for recovery and reconstruction in Afghanistan.

universalization has been regarded as one of the major challenges but also as an important indicator of norm building progress. Activists for a total ban have frequently emphasized how expeditiously the MBT came into effect. The growing number of States adhering to the Treaty would continue to be one of the key indicators of progress and success; this has now been quantified in different ways, lately as a percentage, as long as it serves the purpose to strengthen the image and momentum of the Mine Ban movement.

“Committed by the Convention “to work strenuously towards the promotion of its universalization in all relevant fora,” the States Parties have made this a core task of their collective endeavours these past five years. In that short time, almost 75 per cent of the world’s States have joined, proving their commitment and capacity to fulfil national security responsibilities without anti-personnel mines, establishing a global framework for effective mine action assistance and cooperation, and demonstrating the significant benefits of joining this common effort.”²⁵⁷

Annually visualizing the adherence illustrates the justified concern that one of the most important goals, universal adherence, is neither achievable nor attainable in a realistic sense. It is obvious that the last three years approach stagnation, that is, far from the explosive start and growth of the three first years. In effect, the CCW might have been outdone by the MBT but it is quite successful in maintaining a relative constant growth rate of States joining this convention.

11. Level of adherence: CCW versus MBT based on percentage of Global Military Expenditures and Population

The below MBT-CCW comparison provided below invites considering other factors than just the number of States consenting to be bound by one or both conventions. A quite different outcome can be expected when going beyond simply comparing the number of States Parties to the CCW versus the MBT. Qualifying parameters such as (1) military expenditures and (2) population size need to be brought into the equation in an effort to enrich the comparative analysis when evaluating global support for the CCW versus the MBT. Researching how both conventions quantitatively relate to each other if States are weighted according to their percentage of Global Military Expenditures or percentage of Global Population provides another angle on the “universalization” objective.

Fig. II.16: CCW versus MBT based on percentage of Global Military Expenditures

Fig. II.17: CCW versus MBT based on percentage of Global Population

²⁵⁷ E-mine. Nairobi Action Plan 2005, Internet. Available at [www.mineaction.org/CTA2/Nairobi Action Plan.pdf](http://www.mineaction.org/CTA2/Nairobi%20Action%20Plan.pdf), accessed on 12 May 2006

Annex D provides a detailed breakdown. In both cases it sheds quite a different light on the level of adherence, whereby the CCW convincingly outweighs the MBT. Admittedly, the percentages based on population have lower relevance than those based on military expenditures. However, when studying the level of adherence, the key argument is to look beyond the number of States or Contracting Parties to a treaty to quantify its perceived success. As much as possible other elements should be brought in the equation in an aggregated manner.

Consequently, the results paint a more modest picture of the perceived lead in universalization of the MBT versus the once overshadowed CCW- Protocol II. Not only does the CCW incorporate the major military powers in the world, it also includes all five Permanent Members of the UN Security Council.

12. Voting patterns for the UN resolutions in support of the MBT and CCW

A few other interesting comparative observations can be made. There has only been a small increase of *votes in favour*. An equally interesting observation is the nearly unchanged hard core of abstaining countries²⁵⁸. Approximately twenty UN Member States have been systematically giving this signal of “*soft political resistance*” since the inception of this resolution in 1999. With subsequent minor changes, the recent list of abstaining countries is as follows²⁵⁹: Azerbaijan, China, Cuba, Egypt, India, Iran, Israel, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Lebanon, Libya, Marshall Islands, Micronesia, Myanmar, Pakistan, Palau, Republic of Korea, Russian Federation, Syrian Arab Republic, United States of America, Uzbekistan and Vietnam.

Fig. II.18: Voting Pattern for the annual UN resolution to advocate and support

The contrast to the voting pattern of the UN resolution in support of the CCW is obvious, simply because there was never a vote. Since its inception, the CCW UN resolution has been adopted by consensus, which results in a higher moral weight of this resolution relative to the one in support of the MBT.

b. Deductions

1. Key points

- ☞ The MBT has polarizing, unifying and dividing effects following the ambitious goal and target setting which took place at a time when the problem was poorly defined, resulting nowadays in a “*political anachronism*”. The “*mine free*” status is becoming increasingly controversial with the economics being the most limiting factor. Hence, norm building of “*mine free*” versus “*impact free*” has been complex, blurred and unstable, however, with gradually more focus on “controlling the problem” through impact reduction compared to “perfect solutions”.
- ☞ Universalization of adherence to the MBT seems to be unrealistic, further underscored by the relatively stable core group abstaining from the annual UN resolution in support of the implementation and universalization of the MBT. It would be sensible to prefer a treaty

²⁵⁸ Only during the launch in 1999 of this resolution there was one vote against, unintentionally, coming from Lebanon. Later was clarified that Lebanon intended to abstain, reason why for the purpose of this study the vote has been incorporated in the abstaining votes.

²⁵⁹ UN Document. A/RES 59/84, Internet. Available at www.un.org, accessed on 17 May 2006

without utopian goal-setting of a “*mine free*” world, however, changing the current *black-and-white politics* towards the more nuanced concept of an landmine “*impact free*” world may create more normative problems than solutions.

- ☞ Similar to the CCW, the MBT depends largely on the self-regulatory game theoretic characteristics of a “*voluntary compliance game*” and has no international enforcement of compliance mechanism. States Parties to the MBT comply because there is no benefit of changing unilaterally their strategy to non-compliance, hence, a Nash equilibrium. *Name & shame* and the possible creation of domestic and international *audience costs* are the only mechanisms to restore compliance in case of violations.
- ☞ The absence of “against” votes regarding the UN thematic resolution in support of the MBT, confirms the successful norm building and *name & shame* effect. The principle of generating *audience costs* has been applied by both the advocates and adversaries of the MBT.
- ☞ The CCW was quickly overtaken by the MBT in absolute numbers of States adhering to the MBT but this gap has been fading over the past years, in particular now with all the permanent members of the UN SC consent to be bound to the CCW. Adherence to the MBT compared to the CCW Protocol II is put in perspective when other parameters are used than the number of States Parties to the Treaty, e.g. military expenditure.
- ☞ Similar to double standard issues related to ERW, technological advancement of landmines results in yet another “*pot calling the kettle black paradox*”. The current sophisticated “non-persistent landmines” have less indiscriminate effects as their active time can be regulated precisely, depending on warfare requirements.
- ☞ The normative effect of the “*Ottawa model*” has invited replicate behaviour with success in other disarmament domains (e.g. small arms and light weapons, cluster bombs).

2. Possible indicators and criteria

The number of signatories to the MBT and the voting records regarding the UN resolution in support of the MBT are the most obvious and straightforward quantifiable parameters to measure progress regarding the universalization of the MBT. This is logically reflected in the indicators and criteria below.

Goal	Indicator
Universal Adherence to the MBT and especially to its core-humanitarian objectives	UN Member States consent to be bound to the MBT
	Number of UN Member States voting in favour of the UN resolution in support of the implementation of the MBT
	Number of UN Member States abstaining during the vote for the UN resolution in support of the implementation of the MBT

Criterion 22	Adherence to the Mine Ban Treaty and progress on its universalization
Criterion 23	Voting in favour/abstaining of the MBT resolution

K. Preamble Paragraph 11: The MBT review and consultative processes

Noting also the conclusions of the Fifth Meeting of the States Parties to the Convention, held in Bangkok from 15 to 19 September 2003, taking note of the reaffirmed commitments that were made by the States parties in the Bangkok Declaration, among other things, to pursue efforts related to the core humanitarian objectives of the Convention, urging all States parties and relevant organizations to participate actively in the work of the intersessional programme established by States parties to the Convention, and noting that the First Review Conference, to which the Secretary-General will be invited, will be held in Nairobi, from 29 November to 3 December 2004,

a. Analysis

1. A consultative process par excellence

Intersessional programmes of the Mine Ban Treaty address all the preparatory work for the annual *Meeting of States Parties* through 5-day sessions of consultations on the Treaty objectives and standing committees on mine action activities. This yearly, comprehensive and consultative process relates to the core humanitarian objectives and is decidedly better than other, often stagnated, processes within the field of disarmament politics. That cachet is reflected in the ever-increasing participation in these consultations and meetings by the States Parties to the MBT, together with other governmental and non-governmental participation and observers. During these sessions the political implementation process of the MBT is kept alive, its annual Article 7 reporting is studied, its commitments are refreshed, resource mobilisation encouraged and norm building enhanced. In the familiar conceptual flowchart shown below illustrates how mine action politics precedes the mine action consultative process. It indicates that such a consultative process is essential for the effective development of a strategy, policy and implementation of mine action activities.

Fig. II.19: Conceptual flowchart – Mine Action Consultative Process

As stipulated by the MBT, a first Review Conference took place five years after ratification of the Treaty. The Conference outcome was presented through an action plan and, in deference to the host city, called the *Nairobi Action Plan*. This action plan contains the most significant and concrete proposals since the ratification of the MBT; it will be assessed in the paragraphs below to contribute to the deductions of relevant goals, targets and indicators.

2. The Nairobi Action Plan; a plan for more action ... and more resources!

The Nairobi Action Plan's main objective is to achieve the full and effective promotion and implementation of the Convention and to mobilize resources to face the challenges ahead. These include, in particular, more substantial political, financial and material efforts to meet mine clearance deadlines beginning in 2009 and to improve assistance to mine victims.²⁶⁰ The plan is, therefore, trying to counter a gradual loss of commitment.²⁶¹ Discounting effects on future payoffs will be addressed later in the discussion of

Fig. II.19: One of the logo's used during the Nairobi review Conference – capturing the essence and vision of the MBT.

²⁶⁰ ICBL, Internet. Available at www.icbl.org/campaign/actionplan, accessed on 12 March 2007

²⁶¹ ICRC perceives the current situation as one of a creeping disengagement at national and international levels.

this preamble paragraph. New elements are the specific recommendations towards States Parties together with setting SMART objectives, the acronym for Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant and Time-Based. *Intersectoral* groups are designated to oversee the process of achieving these objectives accordingly, based on a *national* plan of action.²⁶²

Donor States Parties in full support of the MBT goals fear that certain mine-affected States Parties, which are in the last stages of fulfilling their mine clearance obligations,²⁶³ will not be able to do so due to a lack of resources. Faced with both the magnitude of the task of clearing mines and with donor fatigue, some mine-affected States Parties are tempted to set goals that fall far short of clearing all mined areas as required by Article 5 of the Convention. If States Parties sway, they would put the Convention at great risk.

The *Nairobi Review Conference* concluded that funding is either stagnating or largely insufficient to provide support to all five pillars of mine action programmes. In particular victim assistance is under-funded taking into account the ever-growing number of mine victims. The Conference was further sobering in underscoring that, while the annual number of new mine victims has fallen in most mine-affected States Parties, it is not yet possible to record an overall improvement in the situation of landmine survivors.²⁶⁴ Resources and opportunities for mine survivors remain largely inadequate, both on a global level and in most of the countries where the medical infrastructure struggles to respond to the most basic requirements. Likewise, until mined areas are cleared, mine risk reduction and education programmes will need to be enhanced to prevent new casualties.

As emphasised in the Nairobi Action Plan, while mine-affected States Parties bear the greatest responsibility to clear mined areas and to ensure that their health and social services systems are able to care for victims, they also have the greatest needs and expectations for assistance. Two prerequisites to fulfil these needs can be drawn from the Nairobi Action Plan. First and foremost, governments of mine-affected countries must assume greater responsibility for the planning and implementation of mine clearance and victim assistance programmes. While the support of international agencies is very important, it is bound to fail in the long-run if governments do not take ownership of their problem. Secondly, donors must support mine-affected countries that take ownership of their problems and articulate their plans and needs clearly.

In conclusion, the Nairobi Action Plan provides a more business-like approach towards achieving the ambitious goals of the MBT. The clear delineation of accountabilities confronts both affected and donor countries with their respective responsibilities. This raises the element of proportionate burden-sharing which will be assessed in the next sections.

3. Diner's Dilemma or *free-riders*?

Burden-sharing poses in general interesting challenges for an alliance, at this point the States Parties to the MBT in their efforts to generate the necessary resources required to *free* the world of landmines and ERW. Assessing how burden-sharing can evolve in a broader world of would-be co-operators or defectors is a required theoretic insight to understand the underlying dynamics of the politics of mine action. It should reflect both rational and evolutionary experience, as observed in a wide range of disarmament or security related phenomena. Game theory is likely to offer again interesting insights on how this type of international relations can be best explained.

²⁶² Standing Committee on Victim Assistance and Socio-Economic Reintegration (2006, May 9). Presented by Sheree Bailey Victim Assistance Specialist. GICHD, Internet. Available at <http://www.gichd.ch>, accessed on 15 June 2006

²⁶³ In compliance with Article 5 of the Mine Ban Treaty

²⁶⁴ While many mine-affected States Parties have witnessed a significant decline in the annual number of new mine victims since the entry into force of the Convention, the ICRC observed and mentions several affected States Parties that have experienced increases in mine and unexploded ordnance casualties, by up to 19% between 2003 and 2004.

The *Diner's Dilemma* (DD) is a less well known variation of the *n-player Prisoner's Dilemma* (PD). The situation imagined is several individuals go out to eat. Prior to ordering, they agree to split the check equally between all of them. Each individual must now choose whether to order the expensive or inexpensive dish. It is supposed that the costlier dish is better than the cheaper one, but not better enough to warrant paying the difference if you were eating alone. Each individual reasons that the added expense he adds to his bill by ordering the more expensive item is very small, and thus the more gustatory experience is worth the cost. However, if every diner reasons this way then they each pay for the cost of the more expensive meal, which, by hypothesis, is worse for everyone than ordering and paying for the cheaper meal.

In the context of States Parties to the MBT, the DD requires some modifications. The actors joining the dinner have different objectives, challenges and political incentives. They share, however, a common aspiration: a *mine-free* world. Achieving such an ambitious objective bears an enormous cost. Gradually, this has been better comprehended by those nations who acceded to the MBT almost a decade ago and those who currently consider. The ideal of a *mine-free* world could be compared to the *most expensive meal*, whereby nations who are able to assist mine-affected countries, and mine-affected countries themselves, are faced with a similar dilemma. If a mine-affected country was to rely on its own resources, then in the majority of cases it would not order the expensive meal. If donor countries were not to rely on burden-sharing to assist the many mine-affected countries, then the majority would likely be hesitant to join the MBT. Although there are no reliable estimates, the cost to assist affected countries meeting the ambitious MBT deadlines to become mine-free will be enormous.

There is, however, an essential difference between the burden-sharing under the MBT and the DD. The States Parties do not agree upfront to split the check. There is not even an arrangement to determine minimum contributions to the MBT alliance. This is, therefore, quite different from other burden-sharing methods such as in NATO. Each NATO-member needs to maintain a number of military capabilities committed to NATO in case a collective response under Article V of NATO's Charter is invoked to the extent that there is even an annual burden-sharing report.²⁶⁵

In case of the MBT, each party "joins the meal" under the common understanding that contributions are made according to what is regarded as possible and affordable, without any specific obligations or compliance mechanisms. This complicates the game theoretic DD modelling as it invites actors to seek the highest payoff through joining the MBT without incurring costs. In extremis, actors might choose to join the meal and let others pay for them, whereby indeed a mixture of a DD with *free-riders* could be the most representative for the real world situation.

4. Applied Diner's Dilemma and equilibrium analysis

The DD will be further analysed according to the following parameters²⁶⁶, with n the number of players/States Parties let:

- g represent the joy of eating the expensive meal or, in its applied form, the payoff achieving a *mine-free world*,
- b represent the joy of eating the cheap meal or the payoff related to the less ambitious objective of a *world free of the significant impact of mines* or an *impact-free world*.

Respectively:

²⁶⁵ There are several versions of this report, some for internal, others for external use. Burden-sharing within NATO has always been problematic due to the absence of a mechanism or scale of assessed contributions. Discussion with Col Bullivant Garry, former drafter of the NATO internal burden-sharing report, 15 December 2006

²⁶⁶ Methodology based on the approach of Gneezy, U., E. Haruvy, and H. Yafe (2004). The inefficiency of splitting the bill: A lesson in institution design, *The Economic Journal* 114, 265-280

- h is the enormous cost of a *mine-free* world;
- l is the more reasonable cost of an *impact-free* world.

As described, the following generic payoff ordering needs to be respected in absolute values to reflect the game theoretic characteristics of a Diner's Dilemma:

$$h > g > b > l$$

Also, in order to make the game sufficiently similar to the Prisoner's Dilemma, the initial assumption prevails that a particular *State actor Q* prefers to order the expensive meal given others will help defray the cost:

$$g - \frac{1}{n}h > b - \frac{1}{n}l$$

Consider an arbitrary set of strategies by the other *State actors*. Let the total cost of those *State actors* meals be x , then:

- the cost of ordering the cheap meal is $\frac{1}{n}x + \frac{1}{n}l$
- the cost of ordering the expensive meal is $\frac{1}{n}x + \frac{1}{n}h$

So the utilities for each meal are:

- $g - \frac{1}{n}x - \frac{1}{n}h$ for the *expensive* meal
- $b - \frac{1}{n}x - \frac{1}{n}l$ for the *cheaper* meal

By hypothesis, the payoff or expected utility of ordering the expensive meal is higher. Note that besides the strategic choice of *State actor Q* the choice of strategies by the *other State actors* was arbitrary and that the situation is symmetric. This proves that in a one-shot game the expensive meal is strictly dominant and thus the unique Nash equilibrium. If all *State actors* order the expensive meal all of the “diners” pay h and their total utility is negative: $g - h < 0$. On the other hand, suppose that all the *State actors* had ordered the cheap meal, then their utility would have been positive: $b - l > 0$. This demonstrates an interesting similarity between a DD and a PD. Like the PD, everyone is worse off by collectively opting for the expensive meal in a unique equilibrium than they would have been if they pursued another strategy.

However, if one studies the DD in a real world - mine action context, then the evolution of the game portrays different dynamics. Adhering to the above game theoretic or metaphoric language, the group of n -players or MBT States Parties – with n gradually increasing over time – decides to have repeated diner sessions infinitely. The group of n -players also decides on the establishment of voluntary fund(s) whereby all States Parties are invited to contribute upfront to cover future costs. The size of contributions is not predetermined but is “according to the possibilities of States Parties”. Hence, States Parties bear costs now to reap benefits/joy of an expensive meal later. This recalls the previously discussed *discount factor*. What the n -players could observe over time, needs to be studied now. First and foremost, the one-shot DD game hypothesis above is no longer applicable. Logically, the highest expected utility was attributed to the strategic choice for the most expensive meal. In absence of an *equal or proportionate burden-sharing* and *compliance mechanism*, players/States Parties will likely observe varying, probably increasing, degrees of the *free-rider problem*. Having to pay significant, high but also unpredictable payoffs in

advance, *discounts* the distant payoffs of a *mine-free* world considerably. Last but not least, the repeated game confronts players with the expensive meal becoming even more expensive over time. More mine/ERW-affected States Parties joining the MBT, many of them without the means to resource their own mine action programmes, further increases the collective cost of a *mine-free* world.

The above phenomenon causes a multiple eroding effect on the expected utilities of the most expensive meal or *mine-free* status. The *discounting* of future payoffs (decrease g), together with a significantly higher cost (increase h) and more *free-riders* causing less players to defray the costs (decrease n) with an increasing total cost of the meals (increase x), illustrates how the expected utility (E) of the expensive meal can decrease drastically in a repeated DD:

$$U_{\text{expensive meal (=mine-free)}} = g \downarrow - \frac{1}{n} \uparrow x \uparrow - \frac{1}{n} \uparrow h \uparrow$$

Consequently, based on the reasoning above four immediate conditions need to be fulfilled to maintain high levels of support and compliance to achieve a *mine-free* world:

- (1) Increase payoffs of a *mine-free* world;
- (2) Limit discounting effects of distant payoffs through optimal prioritization;
- (3) Reverse donor fatigue or limit *free-rider* problem;
- (4) Cost control of achieving a mine-free world, or increasing effectiveness and efficiency.

Clearly the Nairobi Action Plan drafters did not undertake a DD game theoretic analysis of the situation, however, their plan reflects significant awareness regarding the four challenges mentioned above. It does however not attempt to address adequately each one of them; therefore it approaches again a “*promissory note*”, full of good intentions vice a true *roadmap*. It is all about ensuring better compliance, requesting more resources, meeting mine clearance deadlines but not with confrontational elements in light of better burden-sharing. One of the best ways will be to increase the funding for mine action through UN *assessed budgets* instead of *voluntary contributions*. This will be further addressed in the discussions of more applicable preamble paragraphs.

Economic game theorists Gneezy, Haruvy and Yafe recently (2004) tested the above game theoretic reasoning in a “field” experiment.²⁶⁷ Groups of six diners faced different billing arrangements. As predicted, actors consume more when the bill is split equally than when they have to pay individually. It could be that laboratory experiments are misleading in predicting behaviour in real-world settings but they do offer some explanatory value and expectation management towards more just burden-sharing regarding the boundless resource mobilization required to free the world of landmines and ERW.

b. Deductions

1. Key points

☞ The MBT benefits from a repeated norm-reinforcing consultative process, which enhances and facilitates its implementation. The *Nairobi Action Plan* provides in this regard an impetus to counter the eroding effects on resource mobilisation caused by competing demands and overly ambitious target setting.

²⁶⁷ GNEEZY, U., HARUVY, E. and YAFE, H. (2004). The inefficiency of splitting the bill: A lesson in institution design, *The Economic Journal* 114, 265-280.

- ☞ The Diner’s Dilemma captures well the political and burden-sharing implications of the most important norm building aspect of the MBT: creating a mine-free world. In an academic interpretation of the Diner’s Dilemma, the utility of ordering the expensive meal or mine free world is higher and this leads to a situation whereby the strategic choice for the expensive meal is strictly dominant, resulting in a unique Nash equilibrium. The ‘*Diner’s Dilemma*’ explains the multiple eroding effects on resource mobilisation, in particular due to the absence of a proportional burden-sharing, and further underscores the logic to aim for “impact free” rather than the utopian “mine free”.
- ☞ Factors crucial for maintaining or increasing current levels of donor support are identified as increasing payoffs of achieving a mine-free world, enhancing cost-effectiveness of mine action, limiting discounting effects of future payoffs, reversing *donor fatigue* through limiting free-rider problems. *Donor fatigue* could be further aggravated through the *free-rider problem*.

2. Possible indicators and criteria

The goal and indicators are directly linked to the MBT. The recent Nairobi Action Plan is a most concrete reminder of the MBT deadlines and core humanitarian objectives. This is reflected in the choice of indicators and formulation of criteria.

Goal	Indicator
Fulfil the core humanitarian objectives of the Mine Ban Treaty	Progress towards making the MBT deadlines
	Conclusions and recommendations formulated during Annual Conferences which further an effective global response to landmines
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Universalization of the MBT 2. Mine clearance deadlines (2009) – efforts to make these deadlines 3. Destroy stockpiled anti-personnel mines 4. Increase in effectiveness and efficiency of mine action 5. Fulfilment of Art 6 obligations (substantial political, financial and material assistance to mine-affected States) 6. Increase in victim assistance efforts

Criterion 24	Progress on achieving the core humanitarian objectives of the Mine Ban Treaty – Nairobi Action Plan
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L. Preamble Paragraph 12: Halting new mine deployments by mine-affected States

Stressing the need to convince mine-affected States to halt new deployments of anti-personnel mines in order to ensure the effectiveness and efficiency of mine-clearance operations,

a. Analysis

1. The stigma of being a mine-affected State

This paragraph is remarkable because it singles out mine-affected States with regard halting new deployments of anti-personnel mines. Hence, the language used is somehow ambiguous as the actors responsible for new deployments are not specified, however mine-affected States are held accountable. New anti-personnel mine deployments endanger significantly the efficiency and effectiveness of ongoing mine action programmes in mine-affected States; this explains the main purpose of this paragraph.

Previous efforts to generalize this paragraph in regard all UN Member States were unsuccessful. During the 2002 debate, the US blocked the proposed amendment to extend this preamble paragraph towards all Member States. Contrary to US military doctrine, the envisaged inclusiveness could not be accepted since it would obviously prohibit their further usage of landmines. For the US and other States using anti-personnel landmines, this paragraph should first and foremost stigmatize the highly irresponsible act of continuing deployments of mines whilst expensive and painstakingly slow mine clearance takes place elsewhere in the mine-affected State. Then again, it is another example of the “*pot calling the kettle black paradox*”. Even nations which have been traumatized for decades by landmines, booby-traps and suicide bombers will not hesitate to use cluster ammunitions and landmines in abundance if “modern” warfare so requires.

“The Israeli army sowed landmines in south Lebanon during its summer conflict with Hezbollah in Lebanon, the United Nations said on 25 November. The claims came after British and Bosnian bomb disposal experts each had a foot amputated after a newly laid Israeli-made anti-personnel landmine exploded on Friday, according to a statement by the UN’s Mine Action Coordination Centre in South Lebanon.”²⁶⁸

2. New or renewed landmine use: don’t be the first to defect or “tit-for-tat” ?

One simple and famous -but *not* necessarily optimal - strategy for preserving cooperation in repeated PD’s is the game theoretic strategy called *tit-for-tat*.²⁶⁹ Based on the English saying, “*tit-for-tat*” means “equivalent retaliation”. It recalls again the notorious game theoretic dynamics related to Mutually Assured Destruction (MAD), first strike and second strike principles of the Cold War. Another dreaded variant is the *tit-for-tat arms race*, which was feared by McNamara following the push of the US administration to establish an “Anti-Ballistic Missile (ABM)-system.”²⁷⁰

Donor countries using this strategy in the “small world” of mine action context will initially cooperate with the international community to achieve their mine action goals, through responding in kind to recipient nation's previous actions. If the recipient country was previously cooperative, the donor country is cooperative; if not, the donor actor is not. Hence, once a nation joins the States Parties to the MBT, it enjoys through the “moral commitment or obligations” of Article 6 of the MBT the support of the donor community. In most cases, new mine laying after acceding to the MBT has had a disastrous effect on the funding of the mine action programme. This has been

²⁶⁸ ISRAEL-LEBANON: Accident reveals newly laid Israeli mines, UN says. Internet. Available at <http://www.irinnews.org>, accessed on 26 November 2006

²⁶⁹ It was first introduced by Anatol Rapoport in Robert Axelrod's two tournaments, held around 1980. Rapoport combined his mathematical expertise with psychological insights to the study of Game theory and semantics. He extended these understandings into studies of psychological conflict, dealing with nuclear disarmament and international politics.

²⁷⁰ VANDENBERGHE, Y. (2002). *The Cold War; 1917-1991*, Leuven, p.231

equally true for mine action programmes paralyzed by corruption, misleading information or ineffective management. Cases such as Angola, Bosnia and Cambodia have demonstrated in the past that this not only discredits most significantly the ongoing clearance efforts but also jeopardizes the mine action funding levels at a global level. Competing demands from other humanitarian or development sectors will quickly gain ground if the mine action sector lacks credibility.

Since the *tit-for-tat* strategy tells each player to always cooperate in the first round and to take thereafter whatever action the opponent took in the previous round, it is an evolutionarily stable strategy (ESS). Other PD strategies, such as “always defect”, are also evolutionarily stable. In principle, this type of strategy cannot be invaded by any competing alternative strategy.²⁷¹ Hence, this concept is another equilibrium refinement to Nash equilibriums. The difference between an unqualified Nash equilibrium and ESS Nash equilibriums is that the former may sometimes exist due to the assumption that rational foresight prevents actors from playing an alternative strategy with no short-term cost, but which could eventually be beaten by new strategy. An ESS concept is defined to exclude such equilibriums, and assumes that biologic phenomena like “*natural selection*” is the only force which selects against using strategies with lower payoffs.²⁷²

In a perfect world, a group of players *all* playing tit-for-tat will never see any defections because tit-for-tat is the rational response for each player in a population where others play tit-for-tat. Everyone playing tit-for-tat is obviously a Nash Equilibrium. In the imperfect world of the politics of mine action, let alone broader disarmament issues, there are two possible complications which require further study in this regard.²⁷³

First, the State actors must be uncertain as to when their interaction ends. Suppose it is known when the last round comes, then it could be rational for State actors to defect, as no punishment will be possible. Now consider the second-last round. In this round, players also face no punishment for defection, as they know they will defect in the last round anyway. Therefore they defect in the second-last round. However, this means they face no threat of punishment in the third-last round, and defect there too. This could simply be iterated backwards through a game tree until one reaches the first round. Since cooperation is not rational in that round, tit-for-tat is no longer a rational strategy, and we get the same outcome—mutual defection—as in the one-shot PD which has been extensively discussed. Therefore, cooperation is only possible in repeated PDs where the expected number of repetitions is indeterminate. Of course, this does apply to many real-life games.

A second, more relevant complication stems from difficulties to distinguish defection from cooperation. If this distinction is imperfect, then logically, so will be the “best” response. The lines get particularly blurred when there is not only a clear distinction missing between the actions but in particular between the actors. If in a theoretic setting tit-for-tat State actors mistake mine laying by non-State-actors as abhorrent behaviour of States itself, they could opt to retaliate for their disloyalty to the MBT through withdrawing all support to their respective mine action programmes.

“Rebel groups are planting landmines in Columbia, even though the government is a state party. In Myanmar, not a state party, we believe the problem to be quite significant. In Chechnya there's a serious problem. In the Maoist insurgency in Nepal, there is some evidence that landmines are still being used. We're talking four or five countries that are still using them. Also, in the build up of tension in 2002 between Pakistan and India, there were reports of new mines being laid along the border, but only briefly.”²⁷⁴

²⁷¹ Internet. Available at <http://www.gametheory.net/Dictionary/TitforTat.html>, accessed on 16 June 2006

²⁷² Internet. Available at http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Evolutionarily_stable_strategy, accessed on 8 July 2006

²⁷³ These complications are a recurrent theme in Robert Axelrod's book ‘*The Evolution of Cooperation*’ which also elaborates comprehensively on the different characteristics of tit-for-tat games and qualifies them accordingly in different types.

²⁷⁴ UN Integrated Regional Information Networks. Interview with Martin Barber, Director of the UN Mine Action Service, Internet. Available at <http://www.irinnews.org/webspecials/hma/intBarber.asp>, accessed on 1 March 2006

This new mine laying of non-State actors, in particular in States consent to be bound by the MBT, could potentially set off a chain-reaction of mutual defections from which an affected State can *never* recover if donor countries reply to the first encountered defection with defection, thereby begetting further defections, and so on. This will be addressed further in the analysis of the next preamble paragraph.

3. “(Grim) Trigger” strategies versus “Carrots not Sticks”

As explained above, a *trigger strategy* is a class of strategies employed in a repeated Prisoner's Dilemma. The game theoretic principle is for a particular donor country or the donor community handling a *trigger strategy* to initially cooperate and to “punish” the other actor or opponent whenever a certain threshold level (=trigger) of defection is observed. The level of punishment and the sensitivity of the trigger or threshold vary with different trigger strategies. It is, therefore, interesting to go one step further in qualifying possible responses to non-compliance with existing landmine treaties. There are mainly two possibilities: a forgiving and unforgiving strategic response.

If the punishment or retaliation for non-compliance continues indefinitely, then such a trigger strategy evolves towards an ongoing defection of the donor country towards the recipient state. Hence, such a strategy is strictly unforgiving. This also explains why this game theoretic concept is further qualified as a *Grim* trigger strategy. In a mine action context this is normally characterized by an explicit abandonment of support for any type of ongoing mine action activities; a situation which is most exceptional. Donor support withdrawal has taken place but more frequently due to lack of confidence in a mine action programme or sheer corruption, such as the previously cited cases in Cambodia and Bosnia. At a high political level, the mechanisms as foreseen in the MBT have never been really triggered.

“Under the Ottawa Convention, a system of verification exists, whereby countries believed to be using APMs, could be subjected to international inspection. So far, said the ICRC, the verification system has never been *triggered*. The ICRC also stated that sanctions could be imposed on countries where major concerns of non-compliance exist. While significant progress has been made, UN landmine experts also noted caution.”²⁷⁵

Hence, it is relevant to wonder why compliance is generally satisfactory. Does it work well because of possible Grim trigger responses or effective deterrence? Is primarily name & shame keeping the States Parties in check? Or is it because certain States have made explicit statements before that, even in absence of a forceful international compliance mechanism, the obligations under the MBT should be taken most seriously.

“In its statement New Zealand outlined its efforts to promote universalization of the treaty in the Pacific and its contributions to mine clearance activities. It expressed support for the development of universally understood and agreed compliance measures and warned: ‘It would not be in the Convention’s interests for it to be perceived as a lame duck when allegations and evidence of non-compliance arise.’”²⁷⁶

Taking into account that all States consent to the treaties on a voluntary basis, it is arguably the element of deterrence that is the main driving force behind the exceptionally high levels of compliance. The international mine action community generally judges that a better strategy is the “*tit-for-tat with forgiveness*”. Unlike the *Grim trigger strategy*, this game only “remembers” one previous move when determining whether to cooperate or defect. When the mine-affected State does not comply or defect, on the next move, the donor countries sometimes cooperate anyway, although

²⁷⁵ UN Integrated Regional Information Networks. Africa: Well-Known And Invisible Killer Littered Throughout Africa, Internet. Available at <http://www.irinnews.org>, accessed on 3 April 2006

²⁷⁶ Statement by Paul Tipping, New Zealand’s Ambassador to Mexico, to the Third Meeting of States Parties, Managua, 19 September 2001, p.2

with a small probability. This allows the actors occasional recovery instead of getting trapped in a cycle of defections.²⁷⁷ The exact probability depends on the line-up of opponents. *Tit-for-tat with forgiveness* is best when miscommunication is introduced to the game — when one's move is incorrectly reported to the other actor. This recalls the above complication regarding the difficulties of distinguishing defection from cooperation in a tit-for-tat game, or otherwise, wrong or blurred beliefs regarding the *reputation* of the actors.

In summary, disarmament politics make use of triggers to respond to non-compliance. Some of them result in *grim responses*, especially when the stakes are high and each of the opponents perceives their position as one of strength. The US response to perceived Iraqi nuclear, biological and chemical warfare projects is an outspoken example. Other responses are quite forgiving and give preference to “*carrots above sticks*”. The strategic impact of non-compliance to the MBT is obviously of a different dimension when compared to the possible apocalyptic outcome of totally unrestrained proliferation of nuclear weapons. Hence, grim trigger strategies in response to non-compliance to the MBT could instead harm the affected population than deter those really responsible for deploying new landmines. Nevertheless, disarmament politics require recognizing the uniqueness of every situation, both at the low or high end of the disarmament spectrum.

“Every regime is unique and no one formula can solve it. Different situations call for different approaches. In this case, offering the proverbial “carrot” is more conducive than “sticks”. North Korea is an ultra Stalinist State where the late Kim Il Sung and his son Kim Jong Il are seen as God, and North Koreans will do anything for him including pressing the nuclear button.”²⁷⁸

b. Deductions

1. Key points

- ☞ Certain military doctrines promote clear directives and technological requirements for the “responsible” use of anti-personnel mines.
- ☞ A *tit-for-tat game* largely reflects the political dynamics involved when compliance violations of international treaties (re)occur. Most direct *tit-for-tat* effects are significant drops in funding, *name & shame* and the generation of *audience costs*, possibly globally affecting mine action funding levels.
- ☞ Significant compliance breaches of existing treaties approach *grim trigger* “punishments”.

2. Possible indicators and criteria

Goal	Indicator
Halt new mine deployments to safeguard effective mine clearance	Deployment of mines in mine-affected States with ongoing mine clearance

Criteria 25	No new deployments of landmines
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²⁷⁷ Internet. Available at http://www.bookrags.com/Prisoner's_dilemma, accessed on 31 January 2005

²⁷⁸ BIN TALIB, H. (2006, December 18). Carrots - not Sticks - for Kim, New York, *Newsweek*, p.18

M. Preamble Paragraph 13: Halting the use of landmines/explosive devices by non-State actors

Stressing also the pressing need to urge non-State actors to halt immediately and unconditionally new deployments of mines and other associated explosive devices,

a. Analysis

1. A successful first-timer

This preamble paragraph was for the first time proposed during the 57th General Assembly session. Somehow it was visionary in being introduced right before non-State actors would use landmines and similar explosive devices at an unprecedented scale in Iraq and Afghanistan:

“The number of mines being used in Iraq, and the share of casualties for which they are responsible, dwarf anything ever before seen by the American military. During World War II three percent of U.S. combat deaths were caused by mines or booby traps. In Korea that figure was four percent. By 1967, during the Vietnam War, it was nine percent, and the Pentagon began experimenting with armored boots. From June to November of 2005, IED’s were responsible for 65 percent of American combat deaths and roughly half of all nonfatal injuries.”²⁷⁹

Initially, Pakistan supported by Cuba, China and Egypt resolutely rejected this new addition in the UN resolution, especially since it was first proposed as an extension of the preceding preamble paragraph which aims at halting new mine deployments by State actors. As a number of non-State actors (NSA) are active in the disputed Kashmir region, Pakistan regarded this amendment proposal the opening of a “*Pandora’s Box*”, and objected strongly to possible associations of State policy with landmine deployments by NSAs.²⁸⁰ Hence, consensus was achieved by creating a stand-alone preamble paragraph which strongly requests State actors to urge NSA to halt new landmine deployments.²⁸¹ The distinction with the previous paragraph was further reinforced by adding the words *immediate* and *unconditional* in regard the halt of new deployments.

From another perspective, China was one of the delegations struggling with the absence of an international legal definition²⁸² of non-State actors (NSA). The search for alternatives such as non-State armed groups or rebel groups brought no definite resolution. Recent documents make use of the term Armed Non-State Actors, abbreviated ANSA.²⁸³ In ongoing efforts to define these actors, the 2006 report on the usage of landmines highlights the broad array of possible non-State actors.

“Some of these groups may have clearly defined political objectives, while this may be less clear-cut in other cases. Some NSAs may control territory and have established administrative structures parallel to those of the state, while others have loose command structures and weak control over their members. Some concentrate their forces on attacking military targets, while others attack civilians.”²⁸⁴

²⁷⁹ BRYCE, R. (2006, February). *Man versus Mine*. The Atlantic Monthly, Internet. Available at <http://www.theatlantic.com/doc/prem/200601/explosives>, accessed on 7 April 2007

²⁸⁰ The Pakistani Representatives strongly intervened during the 2002 open-ended meetings to exclude any reference to non-State actors in the UN resolution on assistance in mine action.

²⁸¹ Cuba’s suggestion to separate the PP in the PP 12 and the above PP 13 was ultimately welcomed by all delegations during the last open-ended meeting with UN Member States, November 2003, UN, New York.

²⁸² Non-State actors include rebel groups, irregular armed groups, dissident armed forces, guerrillas, liberation movements, freedom fighters, etc. estimates go up to almost two hundred “recognized” NSAs, not including drug cartels and many of the smaller, loosely organized NSAs. Certain NSAs were, are or might be active in States which are member of the Mine Ban Treaty. The Non-State Actors Working Group (NSAWG) of ICBL: “every region in armed conflict today, AP mines are found in armouries of non-state groups. AP mines are reported to be frequently used more often by NSA than States; their AP mines are usually more dangerous and volatile than commercial landmines.

²⁸³ Armed Non-State Actors and landmines; a global report of NSA mine action, Internet. Available at <http://www.genevacall.org>, accessed on 12 January 2007, p.2

²⁸⁴ *Ibid*, at 8

2. The “Geneva Call”: a cry in the dark?

The Non-State Actors Working Group (NSAWG)²⁸⁵, established by the ICBL, developed a complementary process to engage NSAs in an unconditional ban on landmines and obtain their cooperation on integrated mine action. They further promote and disseminate research and information related to NSAs and landmines. Since 1997, NSAWG members have been approaching NSAs to discuss the landmine problem and seek their commitment to a ban. Actions against the use of *anti-personnel* landmines by NSAs are further known under the concept of the “Geneva call”. To engage armed non-State actors in committing themselves to a mine ban, every few years the NSAWG organizes landmark conferences in Geneva. The main purpose is to build more momentum to effectively deal with NSA. The first conference, “Engaging Non-State Actors in a Landmine Ban, A Pioneering Conference”, was held in Geneva at the beginning of the Millennium.²⁸⁶

3. The “Deed of Commitment”

The political mechanism is to get armed NSAs sign a so-called “*Deed of Commitment for Adherence to a Total Ban on Anti-Personnel Mines and for Cooperation in Mine Action*”, or to deposit their unilateral declarations. The custodians for these deeds are the authorities of the Republic and Canton of Geneva. Under the standard “*Deed of Commitment*” signatory groups not only commit themselves to the MBT but also pledge to cooperate in the monitoring and verification of their commitment, notably by providing information and allowing fact-finding missions. In all, through the Deed of Commitment the NSAWG has established durable contacts with multiple NSAs.²⁸⁷ Progress is further illustrated by the approximately thirty armed non-State actors signing the Deed of Commitment. Annex E provides a detailed overview.

A clearer perspective on the elements influencing these specific NSA armament dynamics is gained through analysis of the global distribution of armed NSA using APM. Figure II.20 and II.21 show the distribution deduced from data²⁸⁸ compiled by Non-violence International, a member of the Thailand Campaign to Ban Landmines and the NSAWG.

Fig. II.20: States with active NSAs who either use, produce, stockpile, or are affected by AP mines

Fig. II.21: Numbers of Active NSAs within Regions who use, produce, stockpile, or are affected by AP mines

²⁸⁵ Non-State Actors Working Group, Internet. Available at <http://www.icbl.org/lm>, accessed on 20 July 2004

²⁸⁶ The event was organized and hosted by the Swiss Campaign in cooperation with members of the Colombian Campaign, Mines Action Canada, the Philippine Campaign, the UK Working Group on Landmines, and the Zimbabwe Campaign. Representatives of about 30 countries attended. Landmine Monitor 2000, NSA Working Group Report, p.944, also available at www.icbl.org/lm.

²⁸⁷ In Burma/Myanmar, the Philippines, Sri Lanka, India, Pakistan Colombia, Angola, Sudan, Turkey, Iraqi Kurdistan, Kosovo/Yugoslavia, and the Polisario in Western Sahara/Morocco. In places such as the Philippines and Colombia where political negotiations are taking place, NSAWG and Geneva Call campaigners lobby for specific agreements relating to landmine use.

²⁸⁸ Fact Sheet 2002 – NSAs and the Ban on Anti-personnel Landmines, Compiled by Non-violence International, a member of the Thailand Campaign to Ban Landmines and the ICBL Working Group on Non-State Actors.

It can be easily concluded that the majority of the countries with NSAs using landmines belong to the most mine-affected continents: Africa and Asia. This data does not cover all non-State armed groups in the world today, as there are no reliable reports on several prominent ones, e.g. the many groups currently active in Afghanistan and Iraq. Recent Landmine Monitor Reports confirm that only a few governments currently use anti-personnel mines, while NSAs use them in many more countries.²⁸⁹ This gives a more concrete perception of the relative latitude of the problem with NSAs. The Nairobi Action Plan presently demands these paper commitments to be met by more actions, more specifically in areas controlled by NSAs:

“Now it is time to move a step further. The AP mine ban, as accepted by armed groups through the Deed of Commitment, needs to be implemented. Mine action programs based on the five traditional pillars are necessary also in areas controlled by ANSAs. Action 46 of the Nairobi Action Plan 2005 – 2009 provides a welcome basis for States, but also for all other actors concerned, to promote and carry out mine action in such areas.”²⁹⁰

In summary, the critical indicator of progress is indeed not the number of signed “Deeds of Commitment” but an effective halt of armed NSAs using anti-personnel landmines and other associated explosive devices. Hence, the scope of the current commitment is limited as it only implies a ban similar to the MBT. In absence of credible compliance mechanisms, it is again no more than a promissory note or goodwill declaration. However, possible complementary effects of NSA mine action such as peace-building, security and disarmament, are important. These can be sometimes even more significant than the primary benefits. Given these benefits, it is important to prioritize mine action in these areas to further hinder or disrupt the usage of landmines. The main conclusion of the above analysis is that engaging NSAs in mine action has significant benefits, since their involvement supports efforts to reduce the humanitarian impact of anti-personnel mines and unexploded ordnance. The NSA activities regarding their use of anti-personnel landmines is, however, the smaller part of the NSA problem compared to the issues addressed in the following sections.

4. “Associated” or “Improvised” Explosive Devices?

The term *associated* explosive devices requires clarification. Why did UN Member States refrain from using the well-known term *Improvised Explosive Devices (IED)*? This was the result of specific norm conservative considerations.²⁹¹ UN Member States did not want to expand assistance in mine action beyond the indiscriminate characteristics of landmines. IEDs, better known under the popular term “roadside bombs”, quickly evolved to significantly lethal configurations and are indeed used in a targeted fashion. In order to assess the usage of IEDs, and the changing tactics, techniques and procedures of non-State actors in making them, it is important to better understand the root causes, cultural and psychological factors related to the usage of their current weapon of choice. Figure II.22 provides some insight of the

Fig. II.23: This graphic shows one of the possible tactics how anti-tank mines could be employed as roadside bombs

²⁸⁹ Landmine Monitor 2005 reported for example only 3 governments using landmines, whilst NSAs used landmines in thirteen countries, Internet. Available at www.icbl.org/lm, accessed on 30 March 2006

²⁹⁰ Armed Non-State Actors and landmines; a global report of NSA mine action, Internet. Available at <http://www.genevacall.org>, accessed on 12 January 2007

²⁹¹ As observed during the 2003 open-ended consultations regarding the UN Resolution on assistance in mine action

sophisticated tactics used in insurgency warfare.²⁹²

Every violent conflict has its own dynamics, therefore, it is essential to address the consecutive steps from acquiring the necessary materials, constructing the device and putting it to use with its variety of desired political outcomes and devastating “side-effects” or collateral damage. In irregular armed conflict’s recent past, interesting examples can be found on how the Irish Republican Army (IRA) started with the usage of crude anti-personnel bombs or mines, consisting of a handful of roofing nails wrapped around a lump of plastic explosives. These improvised weapons were detonated simply by lighting a fuse. They evolved towards remotely controlled bombs, capable of eluding the sophisticated countermeasures of the British Ministry of Defence’s scientific research.²⁹³

The ongoing military activities in Iraq and Afghanistan provide concrete examples. It underscores how the current technological improvements and tactical adaptations of both coalition forces and armed NSAs shed an interesting light on the IED problem. However, also decade-old conflicts in the Middle East could be of interest. Unsurprisingly, Israel²⁹⁴ - normally a passive partner in the mine action debate – requested to replace “*Associated*” by “*Improvised*” Explosive Devices.²⁹⁵ This was resolutely objected in 2003 by other UN Member States for the above mentioned concerns of overstressing the current scope and normative understanding of mine action. In the present most challenging circumstances, the distinction between *associated* and *improvised* became largely an artificial one. For this reason, the analysis below will holistically approach the tremendous problems IEDs cause in modern conflict and nation building processes. This obviously includes how landmines and ERW are providing the basic building materials for insurgency attacks in Iraq and Afghanistan.

5. IEDs and Intra/Inter State Armament/Disarmament Dynamics

Both, largely self-explanatory graphs in figure II.23 and II.24 on the next page, highlight some differences in the evolution of conflict intensity and military effort between regular/interstate warfare and intrastate/insurgency warfare. Post-conflict peace-building processes, disarmament, demobilization and reintegration issues (DDR) as those faced in Afghanistan and Iraq portray blurred and poorly delineated “post-conflict” situations.

In peacekeeping operations the distinction between interstate and intrastate conflict depicted in figure II.23 and II.24 is habitually categorized as *traditional* peacekeeping for interstate conflict, often through a buffer force, and *complex* peacekeeping for intrastate operations. The latter is often characterized by a more cumbersome nation building phase and hindered by protracted outbursts of violence, such as insurgency activities in worst case scenarios. It becomes particularly complex when post-major combat fighting escalates, and even more so if it culminates into combating an invisible insurgency opponent. The US calculated that by militarily winning the war in Iraq and Afghanistan, using overwhelming power,²⁹⁶ they would also swiftly win the peace. Therefore, the question: is there a “best” military response to counter hideous and hit-and-run IED attacks? Are game theoretic considerations helpful to confirm the statement below?

“Fear and uncertainty, of course, ultimately breed mistrust. That may be the most damaging aspect of the IEDs: they prey on American minds, making soldiers suspicious of the local population and ultimately

²⁹² Pulse of War, Internet. Available from www.pulseofwar.com, accessed on 2 December 2006

²⁹³ Countering the new terrorism/ Ian O. Lesser... [et al], 1999, published by RAND, prepared for the United States Air Force by RAND’s Project AIR FORCE

²⁹⁴ As a result of the conflict between Israel and the Palestinians, Israel is also contaminated by ERW. A further hazard has arisen from Palestinian IEDs, including homemade mortars, rockets, mines and roadside bombs. In addition, Israeli military training fields are at times inadequately fenced or not fenced at all, and some UXO remain uncollected. Landmine Monitor 2006

²⁹⁵ This was a request formulated during the open-ended 2003 consultations at UN Headquarters, New York

²⁹⁶ According to the Powell-doctrine.

isolating them. For military theorists, the *IED problem in Iraq is insoluble* no matter how much time or money is spent. "If we can't engage the enemy," he says, "what do we do? *The answer is, we lose.*"²⁹⁷

Fig. II.23: Interstate armament to disarmament dynamics

Fig. II.24: Complex spectrum of intrastate conflict- IED armament dynamics

²⁹⁷ BRYCE, R. (2006, February). *Man versus Mine*, The Atlantic Monthly, Internet. Available at <http://www.theatlantic.com/doc/prem/200601/explosives>, accessed on 7 April 2007

6. Game theoretic considerations regarding the tactics used in today's insurgencies

Studying insurgencies from a game theoretic point of view is enthralling, and several research initiatives are currently analysing the game theoretic aspects of insurgencies taking place in Iraq and Afghanistan. Professor John Nash himself experienced how the US undertook considerable effort to apply game theory during the Cold War period. He recognizes the need for more game theoretic analysis regarding the situation in Iraq, especially with the quickly changing dynamics on the ground. In a reaction on the US loss of five helicopters and its crew in a short period of time he responded with tacit criticism:

“The American side said the *shock-and-awe tactics* would do the work. But then the US army began using helicopters like buses to transport soldiers from one point to another.”²⁹⁸

The Pentagon outsourced a game theoretic study to two private firms using different gaming techniques, then compared and contrasted the results.²⁹⁹ However, in their overestimates regarding the outcome of a full-scale invasion they proved to be appallingly wrong, thereby indicating again the dangers of game theory if too much quantification or simplification is sought. Additional efforts based on more inclusive scenarios are ongoing. Some experts regard it as too little, too late; others offer most chilling perspectives or afterthoughts:

“We did not anticipate the Iraqi strategy of scattering and striking back with small arms and roadside bombs. *So we didn't game for it,*” [...]“But we now know that the initial invasion killed far fewer Iraqis than we had anticipated. Strategically this is not a good thing because all of our data indicates that killing at least 500,000 Iraqis would have prevented remaining forces reaching the threshold necessary to form an effective insurgency. If we had killed a million, perhaps two million right off? Well, in hindsight that may have been the most desirable result from a game theorist perspective.”³⁰⁰

Indeed, game theoretic “mistakes” risk to be further amplified whenever possible strategic scenarios are ignored and possible options are adjusted to the available means rather than what should be the anticipated *true state of the world*:

“There's no point in publishing what the administration and the military don't want to hear,” says Mike Gelertner with an edge of bitterness. “I've been with Systems Research for 15 years and we've done some garbage in garbage out projects for Uncle Sam. But we really missed the boat on this one. We thought they'd stand up against us and we'd bomb them and mow them down. But they ran away to fight another day.”³⁰¹

The insurgencies in Afghanistan and Iraq have demonstrated their capability to withstand US military pressure, particularly through the dynamic and sophisticated nature of their insurgency tactics' relentless efforts:

“The attacks offer a sweeping narrative on evolving tactics by Sunni insurgents who have proved remarkably adaptable.[...] It was unclear whether the confluence of new insurgent tactics — attacking isolated combat posts, targeting helicopters more intensely and using chlorine bombs — was coincidental or in response to the US troop increase. [...] insurgents are always “seeking to achieve higher levels of effectiveness” and these new tactics are part of the normal “evolution of sophistication.”³⁰²

²⁹⁸ NASH, J. (2007) India Military News, Internet. Available at <http://www.einnews.com/india/newsfeed-india-military>, accessed on 2 January 2007

²⁹⁹ Systems Research Inc. and GenCo Elements and from the article written by McCARTHY J. and NEWELL S. (2005) *Iraqi Insurgency Proves A Life Saver. Pentagon Study Reveals Many Thousands More Would Have Died If Iraq Forces Had Resisted*, Internet. Available at <http://www.theassassinatedpress.com/mc.htm>, accessed on 29 April 2007

³⁰⁰ The initial military's game theoretic estimates of dead Iraqis in the event were around 600,000. *Systems Research Inc.*, a private company based in Herndon, Virginia came up with a figure nearly 40% higher than that of the US Army By JOHN McCARTHY & SIMON NEWELL 2005 *Iraqi Insurgency Proves A Life Saver Pentagon Study Reveals Many Thousands More Would Have Died If Iraq Forces Had Resisted*, Internet. <http://www.theassassinatedpress.com/mc.htm>

³⁰¹ McCARTHY, J. and NEWELL, S. (2005) *Iraqi Insurgency Proves A Life Saver Pentagon Study Reveals Many Thousands More Would Have Died If Iraq Forces Had Resisted*, Internet. <http://www.theassassinatedpress.com/mc.htm>, accessed on 12 January 2006

³⁰² Iraqi insurgents use 2nd 'dirty' bomb, Internet. Available at <http://www.military.com/NewsContent/0,13319,126118,00.html?ESRC=topstories.RSS>, accessed on 3 March 2007

Game theoretically, how did IEDs become such a feared weapon in modern intrastate conflict? First and foremost, IEDs have significant tactical, operational and strategic advantages. The majority can be used in standoff attacks which allow insurgents to evade counter-attacks, in particular from regular military forces.

“For the most part, the enemy is reverting more and more to mines, IEDs and mortars. They know that we will make them pay heavily if they open up in a direct fire fight with us. Just the other day some guy tried to lob a 60mm mortar round at us with his hands. He somehow lit the thing on fire and tossed it at us thinking it would explode.”³⁰³

As direct military confrontation can be largely avoided, insurgents aim to maintain the limited tactical capabilities and resources together with the strategic initiative required to protract an effective insurgency campaign in a type of warfare which is primarily about ideas. A mature insurgency campaign continuously changes its tactics, techniques and procedures thereby erecting extremely challenging circumstances, forcing a military superpower to adapt their best strategic response at the initiative of the insurgents.

“As long as the insurgents can use IEDs to inflict damage on US soldiers without ever engaging them directly, they will have a tactical advantage. “Our whole military is based on the idea of overwhelming firepower put on targets,” says William S. Lind, a noted military theorist who has written extensively on asymmetric warfare. “But that doesn't work in this type of conflict. We are fighting an enemy that has made himself *untargetable*.”³⁰⁴

The phenomenon of war or conflict fatigue versus a downwards spiral of violence is an essential game theoretic element to consider, for both the regular forces and the insurgents. It has proven to be a dangerous assumption that the usage of IEDs or modified anti-tank mines should be interpreted as a phase of final desperation or last resort of non-State actors. This was poorly assessed by several US commanders involved in the Iraq conflict, only to be followed by increasingly deadly months for US troops due to casualties of roadside bombs or suicide attacks. Similarly, an element of denial was noticeable regarding the increasing insurgency threats for US air assets.

“Despite the losses [4 US helicopters], Caldwell said it was premature to conclude that the threat to US aircraft posed by Sunni insurgents and Shiite militiamen had increased dramatically. There's been an ongoing effort since we've been here to target our helicopters, Caldwell said. Based on what we have seen, we're already making adjustments in our tactics and techniques and procedures as to how we employ our helicopters.”³⁰⁵

In fact, this explained that IEDs are the perfect weapon for long-term asymmetric conflict.³⁰⁶ They are cheap, effective, and anonymous. The interaction often involves strategies or tactics outside the bounds of conventional warfare and portrays many, if not all, characteristics of a *tit-for-tat* game, which will be addressed next.

³⁰³ Soldier's Letter from Iraq (2003, 15 September), Internet. Available at http://d-n-i.net/fcs/soldiers_letter.htm, accessed on 12 January 2006

³⁰⁴ BRYCE, R. (2006, February). *Man versus Mine*, The Atlantic Monthly, Internet. Available at <http://www.theatlantic.com/doc/prem/200601/explosives>, accessed on 7 April 2007

³⁰⁵ U.S. pilots alter tactics after downings, ROBERT H. REID, Associated Press Writer, Internet. Available at http://news.yahoo.com/s/ap/20070204/ap_on_re_mi_ea/iraq, accessed on 27 Augustus 2007

³⁰⁶ Asymmetric warfare is a term that describes a military situation in which two opponents of unequal power or capacity of action, interact and take advantage of the strengths and weaknesses of themselves and their enemies. This interaction often involves strategies and tactics outside the bounds of conventional warfare.

7. A tit-for-tat game causing a spiral of violence?

When studying a tit-for-tat game in the context of insurgency warfare and use of IEDs, it is crucial to ask what the triggers are.

“The key difference is the trigger: whether it is in opposition to an established, status quo authority (insurgency) or to a new authority installed by foreign invaders (resistance). The opposition in Iraq was clearly triggered by the US-led invasion and occupation -- not by dissatisfaction with an established, status quo authority.”³⁰⁷

For example, Afghanistan’s and Iraq's complex network of tribes and family relations means some families have members on both sides of the conflict. Further adding to the complexity are the “foreign” fighters' attacks on US, NATO forces, police and government officials. This triggers a secondary response from local insurgents who are more loyal to tribe and family than to ideology.³⁰⁸ One should indeed be cautious not to simplify and ignore the proxy wars which are fought through insurgencies. The US is increasingly vocal on the involvement of Pakistan in the insurgency activities in Afghanistan and of Iran in Iraq, citing how their sophisticated IEDs harm, in particular, US troops.

“Challenged on the accuracy of U.S. intelligence, President Bush said Wednesday there is no doubt the Iranian government is providing armor-piercing weapons to kill American soldiers in Iraq. But he backed away from claims the top echelon of Iran's government was responsible.[...] There have been mixed signals in the administration about Iran's involvement in supplying Shiite groups in Iraq with a particularly lethal type of roadside bombs known as explosively formed penetrators [e.g. hollow charges which are able to harm troops in armoured vehicles].”³⁰⁹

With no end to the insurgency and a political solution to break the tit-for-tat retaliations on the ground, the targeted use of IEDs is going to remain one of the principle obstacles to peace. It will continue to blur the lines between main combat and post-conflict recovery both in Iraq and Afghanistan.

“Samarra started a downward spiral of *tit-for-tat* sectarian violence that has proven difficult to arrest, and which is at the centre of the battle of Baghdad today. So Samarra was a big event that a lot of us knew was significant, and sadly, its aftershocks have played out each day with the discovery of more dead bodies.”³¹⁰

“Insurgent activity in Afghanistan has risen fourfold this year, and militants now launch more than 600 attacks a month, a rising wave of violence that has resulted in 3,700 deaths in 2006, a bleak new report released Sunday found.[...] Insurgents have launched a record number of roadside bombs and suicide attacks this year, and there have been clashes all year between insurgents and Afghan and NATO security forces, particularly in the southern and eastern provinces near the border with Pakistan.”³¹¹

8. IED use by non-State armed groups: a “wicked problem”?

In general, seeking sophisticated strategies or best responses for complex problems invites new problems. They are more difficult for other players to infer, their use increases the probability of misperceptions and sub-optimal responses. Wicked problems have incomplete, contradictory, and changing requirements; and their resolutions are often difficult to recognize as such because of complex interdependencies. In the landmark article “*Dilemmas in a General Theory of Planning*”,

³⁰⁷ Internet. Available at <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Talk:Insurgency>, accessed on 20 March 2007

³⁰⁸ JERVIS, R. (2006, 25 January). General sees rift in Iraq enemy, *USA TODAY*, 25 Jan 2006

³⁰⁹ HUNT, T., Bush: Iran is source of deadly weapons, AP White House Correspondent, Internet. Available at http://news.yahoo.com/s/ap/20070215/ap_on_go_pr_wh/bush, accessed on 14 February 2007, Three senior U.S. military officials, at a weekend briefing in Baghdad, said the highest levels of the Iranian government had ordered the weapons smuggled into Iraq. They based their claim on the belief the weapons are moving into Iraq through the Iran's Revolutionary Guards elite Quds Force

³¹⁰ KITFIELD, J. (2006) U.S. options to control violence in Iraq narrowing, *National Journal*, Internet. Available at <http://www.govexec.com/dailyfed/1006/102006nj2.htm>

³¹¹ STRAZIUSO, J. (2006, November 11) *Insurgent activities spike in Afghanistan*, Associated Press Writer

Horst Rittel and Melvin Webber observed that there are a set of problems that cannot be resolved with traditional analytical approaches.³¹² They state that while attempting to solve a wicked problem, the solution of one of its aspects may reveal or create another, even more complex problem. The current IED phenomenon portrays most, if not all, ten characteristics as identified by Rittel and Webber as a wicked problem. In essence, wicked problems have no definitive formulation and have no stopping rule. As it is hard to define the current use of IEDs and insurgency problems in any single way, it is difficult to tell when it is or will be resolved. Rather the problem-solving process ends when resources are depleted, stakeholders lose interest or political realities change. Rittel and Webber make further the link to particular multiple criteria decision analysis challenges. In absence of unambiguous criteria for deciding if the problem is resolved, ensuring all stakeholders agree that a response may not be the best but “*good enough*” can be a challenge. This needs to be addressed in the context of *robust solutions* for *fuzzy problems*.

Other game theoretic complexities are added through considering wicked problems that do not have a well-described set of potential solutions. Each wicked problem can be considered a symptom of another problem. The use of IEDs in insurgencies portrays indeed a complex set of interlocking issues, tactics and constraints that change over time, embedded in a most volatile social context. It has been illustrated above that the triggers of the wicked IED problem can be explained in numerous ways.

“The local sheiks know who is conducting the [IED] attacks. Of course, they want *tit-for-tat* and won't tell us unless they get what they want. If we give them what they want, we lose face and become incompetent while the sheiks become more powerful. [...] the local sheiks assist the terrorists in one way or another to get what they want. Of course, these are the same guys who will be in charge of the local governments once they are established.”³¹³

There are many stakeholders who will have various and changing ideas about what might be the true nature of the problem, what might be causing it and how to resolve it. However, game theoretic or Cartesian thinking further stagnates with the absence of possible sets of responses to wicked problems in terms of “*retaliate/reconcile*”, “*defect/not defect*” or “*carrots/sticks*”.

“U.S. forces, too, continue to tally losses at the hands of extremists despite signs of more successful raids against bases and weapon stockpiles. The military said nine soldiers were killed Monday in two separate roadside bombings north of Baghdad, making it the deadliest day for U.S. troops in Iraq in nearly a month. [...]The U.S. forces are seeking a “*reconciliatory approach*” to avoid sparking a backlash on the streets, said Col. Richard Kim. One small gesture seemed to show appreciation: a child offered soldiers ice cream bars.”

The moral is that tit-for-tat games are very difficult to escape from. The international community should, therefore, avoid such situations, rather than relying on cunning strategic choices for trying to get out of them.

“We will not succeed in transforming the Middle East by threatening to change regimes by military action. A better model is offered by the joint approach Europe and America took after the Cold War to transform Eastern Europe and the former Soviet Union. Together, we successfully promoted stability, security, economic reform and democratic progress throughout that region. We offered these states the opportunity to work with and participate in Atlantic and European institutions. They were encouraged to settle historic disputes, integrate their economies and adopt open political systems. Our emphasis was upon *carrots not sticks*, inclusion not exclusion, assistance and encouragement not sanctions and coercion.”

The requirement for alternative, non-military strategies, to break the tit-for-tat loop has been echoed by former UN Ambassador Holbrooke.

³¹² RITTEL, H. and WEBBER, M. (1973). “Dilemmas in a General Theory of Planning,” *Policy Sciences*, 4, 155-169.

³¹³ Soldier's Letter from Iraq. (2003, 15 September). Internet. Available at http://d-n-i.net/fcs/soldiers_letter.htm

“Engaging in a broad-based diplomatic offensive, and beginning a redeployment of US forces in Iraq, represents the best way to secure America's interests in the region and combat the serious threat of terrorist networks.”³¹⁴

In summary, IEDs most often have a *disastrous effect on peacekeeping/building operations*. They amplify extensively the negative impact of landmines, ERW or any type of associated explosive devices and might largely uphold a “military victory”. Both Iraq and Afghanistan have enormous stockpiles of landmines and other explosive remnants of war, which currently serve as abundant logistic stocks to produce IEDs. In combination with local and cultural habits they became extremely difficult to detect. There is little doubt that the successes of the insurgency attacks in Iraq have triggered rather than dampened insurgency or terrorist attacks on a global scale.³¹⁵ The answer to the question if the military component of a peace support operation can solely achieve victory, let alone successfully counter insurgency operations in absence of a viable peace process, becomes increasingly irrelevant.

The following sobering views of former Statesman Kissinger recognizes the decreasing effects of the military to accelerate the peacebuilding process in Iraq. In his capacity as adviser to the Bush administration on Iraq, in August 2005, he stated in memorable fashion that “victory over the insurgency is the only meaningful exit strategy”.³¹⁶ Currently, IEDs contribute dramatically to the vicious cycle of sectarian violence by non-State actors or armed groups. The complex spectrum of intrastate conflict depicted above is even optimistic as insurgencies can become solely responsible for the majority of military and civilian casualties, or worse, evolve towards an all-out civil war. If the back of the insurgence, and thereby its most lethal IEDs, cannot be broken, then there may be indeed no substitute for the absence of military victory.

“If you mean by '*military victory*' an Iraqi government that can be established and whose writ runs across the whole country, that gets the civil war under control and sectarian violence under control in a time period that the political processes of the democracies will support, *I don't believe that is possible.*”³¹⁷

b. Deductions

1. Key points

- ☞ In absence of an international legal definition of non-State actors (NSA) other alternatives, such as non-State armed groups, have been explored. Landmines are a most suitable weapon to protect or facilitate other illegal activities, e.g. protection of poppy fields and arms smuggling. “Illegal” use of landmines by NSA has in many regards overtaken the “regulated (CCW)” use by State actors.
- ☞ Involving NSA in mine action can generate benefits in terms of peacekeeping, security and disarmament. It is equally important to prioritize mine action in areas with armed NSAs to further hinder or disrupt the usage of landmines and other associated explosive devices.
- ☞ Protocol V is the first meaningful but limited political initiative to urgently address the issue of both stockpiled landmines and munitions. It has been a welcome addition to the MBT related “*Deeds of Commitment*”, which are nothing more than a goodwill intention and only target the use of anti-personnel mines by NSA.

³¹⁴ SANNER, A. (2007, February 24). *Former UN envoy supports Iraq pullout*. Associated Press Writer, Internet. Available at abcnews.go.com/Politics/wireStory?id=2901347, accessed on 24 February 2007

³¹⁵ There were numerous problems with the 2003 report on ‘Patterns of Global Terrorism’ which was discredited for its faulty use of data and statistics. The first version of the report underwent some editing which reversed the outcome of the report and rather an increase of terrorism needed to be reported.

³¹⁶ KISSINGER, H. (2006, November 19) Internet. Available at <http://edition.cnn.com/2006/WORLD/meast/11/19/iraq.kissinger/index.html>, accessed on 20 November 2006

³¹⁷ KISSINGER, H., as interviewed by the BBC on 19 November 2006, as reported by TARIQ P., Associated Press Writer, Internet. Available at http://news.yahoo.com/s/ap/20061120/ap_on_re_mi_ea/britain_iraq_kissinger, accessed on 19 November 2006

- ☞ Effective political or other actions against armed NSA require a comprehensive understanding of the complexities of intra-state conflict and armament dynamics. Critical indicator of progress, however, is again not the number of “Deeds of Commitment” signed but an effective ban and the practice of effective mine action prioritization to disrupt the armament dynamics.
- ☞ A conservative interpretation of mine action does not include *Improvised Explosive Devices* or “*roadside bombs*”, due to the targeted use versus the post-conflict indiscriminate effects of landmines. The rarely used term “*Associated explosive devices*” has led to subjective and conflicting interpretations on the scope of assistance to mine action.
- ☞ IEDs become increasingly effective and are extremely difficult to detect, which is amplified by the usage of ordinary daily use items such as pressure cookers or remotely controlled starting of motorbikes filled with former landmine explosives.
- ☞ Stockpiles or weapon caches of landmines/ERW become gigantic logistic stocks to build IEDs. It follows that IED usage of landmines/ERW is an extremely cost-effective way of insurgency warfare with high politics and national security implications.
- ☞ Most advanced technology has so far been incapable to timely detect and deter this type of NSA activities. In the context of insurgencies, understanding the underlying *triggers* in a *tit-for-tat game* is more important than symptomatically seeking best retaliatory or reconciliatory responses.
- ☞ IED use by non-State armed groups has a *disastrous effect on peacekeeping/building operations* and presents most, if not all, characteristics of a “*wicked problem*”.

2. Possible indicators and criteria

Evaluation criteria related to this preamble paragraph can be summarized in terms of assessing the activities of State actors to stop NSA from using landmines/ERW. This can include both pro-active and preventive mine/ERW clearance as reactive measures. Both the presence or availability of landmine/ERW “IED building materials” and the intent to use them will determine the risks involved.

Goal	Indicator
Stop usage of mines/ERW by NSA	Intent of NSA to use landmines/ERW
	Activities of State actors inhibiting NSA using landmines/ERW
	Signing of the “Deeds of Commitment”
	Presence of types of mines/ERW which can easily lead to the construction of IEDs by NSA

Criterion 26	Level of pressure of State actors to inhibit non-State actors from using landmines/ERW
Criterion 27	Combined presence and intent to use landmine/ERW explosives to construct IEDs

N. Preamble Paragraph 14: Assistance and information sharing in support of mine action

Recognizing the importance of assisting mine clearance in mine-affected countries by ensuring that the necessary maps and information and appropriate technical and material assistance are provided to help to remove existing minefields, mines, booby traps and other unexploded ordnance,

a. Analysis

1. Information sharing and standardization of mine action

Preamble paragraph 14, 15 and 16 focus primarily on the delivery of (cost)effective assistance and resource mobilisation. This includes direct calls to UN Member States to provide all kinds of assistance, be it financial, technical or material. This is also reflected in the operative part of the resolution, whereby UN Member States, especially those that have the capacity to do so, are specifically requested to provide the necessary information and technical, financial and material assistance, as appropriate, and to locate, remove, destroy or otherwise render ineffective minefields, mines, booby traps and other devices, in accordance with international law, as soon as possible.³¹⁸ However, this paragraph makes an important reference to information sharing, which is critical for the successful implementation of mine action:

“In many ways, mine action management is almost as much about information as it is about mines.”³¹⁹

Owing to its importance, mine action information management and sharing will be the main topic further below. How information is provided and used has inevitably a significant impact on coordination and prioritization of mine action at all levels. Obviously, depending on the high-medium-low politics level, the requirements for information and standardisation differ. In this regard, the assistance in mine action resolution aspires to set the norm and therefore encourages efforts to carry out surveys, effectively manage information through an information management policy and Information Management System for Mine Action (IMSMA). Standardisation can be achieved through conducting mine action in accordance with accepted national and international standards, including International Mine Action Standards (IMAS).³²⁰

2. Main information management challenges

One of the major challenges most mine-affected countries face today is the lack of reliable and workable information regarding the *impact* of the landmine/ERW problem. Yemen was the first country to complete a UN-certified *Landmine Impact Survey (LIS)*.³²¹ At the time of the completion of this survey, Yemen had at its disposal the most comprehensive set of mine-related socio-economic impact data in the world. This data allowed Yemen to develop effective national mine action strategies and work plans. Consequently, the LIS process quickly gained recognition as a benchmark against which mine action successes could be measured. Subsequently, this triggered surveys in more than a dozen nations. However, *standardization* and *data exploitation* of these surveys, and any other mine action *information sharing*, continues to present specific challenges.

Another important information management challenge is the cross-country comparison of mine action programmes in order to better inform donors in accordance with clear and reliable

³¹⁸ UN Document A/RES/58/127, operational paragraph 22 from UN resolution on ‘Assistance in mine action’, Internet. Available at <http://www.un.org/Depts/dhl/resguide/r58.htm>, accessed on 20 July 2005

³¹⁹ GICHD (2004), *A guide to Socio-Economic Approaches to Mine Action Planning and Management*, Geneva, p.3

³²⁰ UN Document A/RES/58/127, operational paragraph 6 and 17 from UN resolution on ‘Assistance in mine action’, Internet. Available at <http://www.un.org/Depts/dhl/resguide/r58.htm>, accessed on 20 July 2005

³²¹ This survey took place in 2000 and covered at least 95 percent of the suspected impacted areas in Yemen with a high degree of confidence.

numeric evaluation systems. This has been a repeated request from UN Member States, in particular important donor countries such as Japan.

“[...] the United Nations Mine Action Service should make a table on the present status of mine action in each mine-affected country, providing information on such matters as the rate at which mines are being cleared, diffusion of mine awareness, and the development level of mine victim assistance, and introducing a numeric evaluation system, so that donors can easily understand in which area of mine action progress has been insufficient and which target countries need more international support.”³²²

IMSMA has this potential; however, so far expectations have not been met. It requires more than a sophisticated software system; it requires again extensive coordination from the actors who are responsible for providing the inputs. If no quality baseline data is provided, combined with poor information management, then nothing credible or useful should be expected with regard to comparable data. The requisite extensive inter-programme coordination has its own complications, and one of the reasons is the protective handling of information, which goes beyond the re-engineering problems cited below:

“I think we all hoped that IMSMA would allow us to extract basic comparable data about contaminated areas, clearance and victims from the databases of major mine action programs. For a number of reasons this has not yet happened. I believe it should soon be possible, but it will require the GICHD to successfully “re-engineer” the system and many national programs to clean up their databases.”³²³

Fortunately, there continues to be significant progress. The UN Mine Action Service (UNMAS) plays a crucial role in expanding an electronic mine information network.³²⁴ This network should facilitate the interaction and information-sharing between key actors at the high-medium-low politics. Nowadays, it is a platform for mine-action programmes to circulate standard reports on the scope and impact of the mine problem, available mine-action resources and the progress achieved in the field. It is intended to be a web-based information gateway³²⁵ developed to support both the planning and coordination of global mine action problems, programs, best practices and technologies. This electronic mine information network involves a number of UN and non-UN partners and is coordinated by UNMAS. It builds on a large number of mine action databases, information systems and websites.³²⁶ There is even a new database specifically designed to compile ERW-related information and a large electronic portfolio of mine action programmes and projects. However, the major constraints are related to its data management, including the compiling and updating of information into the database.

3. Minefield maps and information: is the problem per definition hidden?

In order to enhance targeting and prioritization of mine action, minefield maps can make a tremendous difference in terms of effectiveness and efficiency of mine action. Disregarding nuisance mine laying by non-State actors, there is often a relatively good mapping of minefields. This does not imply that minefield maps are made easily available. There are a number of complex

³²² Note Verbal from the PM of Japan to UNMAS dated 3rd June 2002, regarding the Mine Action Strategy for 2001-2005, later forwarded to the PM of Belgium to the UN with the request to reflect this suggestion in the draft proposal of the Resolution Assistance in mine action.

³²³ BARBER, M. (2004, November) MASG Newsletter, Internet. Available at <http://www.mineaction.org/overview.asp?o=144>, accessed on 12 July 2005

³²⁴ The Electronic Mine Information Network was launched by the United Nations Mine Action Service (UNMAS) on 18 September 2001, on the occasion of the Third Meeting of States Parties to the MBT.

³²⁵ It is also useful as a general research and reference tool for landmine matters. The information contained in the database would be available to Member States, United Nations agencies, regional and non-governmental organizations, and others. It is hoped that the database will help support the mine clearance efforts of various Member States and organizations. A/49/357-61

³²⁶ The Information Management System for Mine Action (IMSMA) developed by the Geneva International Centre for Humanitarian Demining (GICHD) in cooperation with UNMAS to support the coordination and management of mine action programs in the field. More interesting and up to date is the website managed by James Madison University and the GICHD to provide up-to-date information on the International Mine Action Standards. The database developed by the UN Department for Disarmament Affairs (DDA) manages the reports submitted by States Parties to the AP MBT under its Article 7.

issues which result in minefield maps not being provided for many years after the conflict. One important reason is accountability and more specifically ownership of the problem.

If States consent to be bound by the MBT and CCW, then they have certain obligations to provide maps, information and annual reports. The MBT has extensive annual, national reporting procedures, best known under “*Article 7 reporting*”. The CCW has less stringent annual reporting procedures but stipulates that parties to the conflict are obliged to make available without delay all available information concerning minefields, mined areas, mines, booby-traps and other devices laid by them in areas no longer under their control. However, subject to reciprocity, where the forces of a party to a conflict are in the territory of an adverse party, either party may withhold such information from the Secretary-General and the other party, to the extent that security interests require such withholding, until neither party is in the territory of the other. In the latter case, the information withheld shall be disclosed as soon as those security interests permit. Wherever possible, the parties to the conflict shall seek, by mutual agreement, to provide for the release of such information at the earliest possible time in a manner consistent with the security interests of each party.³²⁷ If one or both parties to a conflict are not bound by the CCW, reference to international or human rights law offers legitimate alternatives.

Even through UN resolutions, UN Member States can be held accountable. The UN resolution on assistance in mine action emphasizes in its operative part the importance of recording the location of mines, of retaining all such records and making them available to concerned parties upon cessation of hostilities, and welcomes the strengthening of the relevant provisions in international law.³²⁸ Both past and present UN peacekeeping indicates how important the issue of assistance in mine action is for the UN Security Council with regard to post-conflict restoration and return to normalcy. One of the most recent examples is the UN resolution 1701 whereby the provision is requested to the United Nations of all remaining maps of landmines in Lebanon in Israel’s possession.³²⁹ Since this issue has been dragging on for many years, with Israel withholding many maps of its minefields laid during the invasion and occupation of Lebanon, a coherent approach is sought in line with the spirit of the CCW, whereby the parties shall endeavour to reach agreement on the provision of technical and material assistance, including the undertaking of joint operations necessary to fulfil such responsibilities.³³⁰

4. Standardisation challenges

The UN has played a vital role in developing International Mine Action Standards (IMAS) but would not have achieved the desired results without the assistance of the Geneva International Centre for Humanitarian Demining (GICHD) and other partners in mine action. Based on these IMAS, *national* mine-action standards need to be developed.³³¹ This has proven to be far more challenging than initially anticipated, and has exposed some downsides of the IMAS norm building concept:

“National adaptation of IMAS remains to be achieved in the overwhelming majority of mine action programmes. The language of the IMAS is difficult, sometimes even for native speakers (although an easy to read guide is under development). So as is done for other ISO standards, there is a need to support the written documentation with appropriate training. And it is as important to be realistic: the search for perfection takes time and may lead to unnecessary loss of life.”³³²

³²⁷ CCW Convention - Article 14

³²⁸ UN Document A/RES/58/127, operational paragraph 21 from UN resolution on ‘Assistance in mine action’, Internet. Available at <http://www.un.org/Depts/dhl/resguide/r58.htm>, accessed on 20 July 2005

³²⁹ Internet. Available at www.un.org, UNSCR 1701

³³⁰ CCW Convention – Article 10, paragraph 4

³³¹ UN Document A/RES/58/127, operational paragraph 18 from UN resolution on ‘Assistance in mine action’, Internet. Available at <http://www.un.org/Depts/dhl/resguide/r58.htm>, accessed on 20 July 2005

³³² MASLEN, S. (2004). *Mine action after Diana*, United Kingdom: Pluto Press, p.43

Whichever challenges remain, the impact of IMAS on norm building could be considered most significant and second in line compared to norm building efforts through the International Campaign to ban landmines, the Mine Ban Treaty and the concept of a mine free world.

5. Standardized sources of information

The *Landmine Monitor* contains detailed and somewhat standardized information on every country in the world with regard to landmine use, production, stockpiling, trade, humanitarian mine clearance, mine awareness education, and mine survivor assistance. It is the best and most updated source of information on the landmines issue and is used by the ICBL, other NGOs, teachers, students, governments, and others worldwide. Other important sources of information are listed below.

- (1) UN general website;
- (2) Documents, resolutions and reports related to mine action;
- (3) E-mine; information gateway to mine action information;
- (4) UNMAS annual report
- (5) UN Mine Action Portfolio
- (6) IMAS
- (7) Website of the UN Department of Disarmament Affairs - MBT Article 7 Reporting;
- (8) Survey Mine Action Centre: Landmine Impact Surveys;
- (9) ICBL and GICHD website;
- (10) ICRC reports.

b. Deductions

1. Key points

- ☞ The landmine problem is per definition hidden; although available, minefield maps are sometimes withheld in order to avoid ownership of problem caused by that particularly country. Essential information and maps are sometimes not shared amongst the different key players, hampering effective planning and execution of mine clearance.
- ☞ One of the most important information management challenges is the cross-country comparison of data.
- ☞ As highlighted in the analysis, primarily the CCW provides ample legal clauses on maps, information and appropriate technical assistance. Once again the norm building by the CCW and the MBT is supported by the positive cumulative effects of both legal instruments.

2. Possible indicators and criteria

Goal	Indicator
Optimal support for mine clearance efforts in mine-affected countries	Level of material assistance and funding
Optimal information sharing and standardisation	Mine action based on international mine action standards
	Mine action benefiting from an effective information management system with IMSMA effectively implemented

Criterion 28	Level of funding, technical and material support for mine clearance efforts in mine-affected countries
Criterion 29	Level of information sharing
Criterion 30	Level of standardisation of mine action

O. Preamble Paragraph 15: Mine action resource mobilisation

Noting that the resources allocated to mine-action activities have increased in recent years, but stressing the need to mobilize additional resources and to secure the best possible utilization of such resources, particularly for victim assistance, in order to meet increasing requirements, and encouraging all States, the United Nations and other international, regional and non-governmental and private organizations to continue their efforts in this regard,

a. Analysis

1. Ever-increasing demands for funding

This paragraph addresses in a general and normative way three issues through which vague qualifiers pursue an increase of donor efforts.

- (1) Acknowledgement of overall increased donor support over a time span of several years;
- (2) Continuation of efforts in this regard by all partners in mine action. These partners are Governments, regional organizations and other donors providing financial and in-kind contributions to mine action, including contributions for emergency operations, peacekeeping operations and for national and local capacity-building programs.³³³
- (3) Need to mobilize additional resources.

The countries shown in Table II.4³³⁴ were selected based on extensive and comparable data as part of Article 7 reporting as required by the Mine Ban Treaty. Reports from seven significantly mine-affected countries indicate that, at current rates of clearance and expenditure, it will take 135 years and \$20 billion to do the job in those countries alone. With this table the author made the statement: the math is simple, the policy and operational implications are not so simple.

Hazard area (sq km)	In 2002			Needed for completion	
	Area cleared (sq km)	Funding Cost (millions USD)	Cost/ Sq km	Cost (millions USD)	Time (years)
11,840	86	140	1.62	20,000	135

Table II.4: Mine clearance projection for Afghanistan, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Cambodia, Chad, Mozambique, Thailand and Yemen

In fact, even the math is not simple. The effort above purposely frames the problem as a desperate situation based on mathematical worst-case scenarios and data too general to sustain a detailed analysis. The Landmine Impact Survey's estimates of Suspected Hazardous Area are reflected in the overestimate of 11,840 sq km contaminated land, such as the 10 to 1 assumed over-estimation of hazardous areas for Cambodia.³³⁵ Nevertheless, a clear trend line emerges from the data and it stretches far into the future. It definitely puts the projected MBT deadlines and norms for mine clearance in a humbling perspective.

2. The high level interaction with representatives from donor countries

Resource mobilisation is a basic activity of each mine action programme, which when successful tends to have some if not all of the following six points that make a national mine action

³³³ As stipulated in paragraph four of the operative part of the Resolution, see Annex A.

³³⁴ EATON, B., Area Reduction: A Solution Whose Time has Come. *Journal of Mine Action*, Issue 7.3, MAIC - James Madison University, Washington DC, MAIC - James Madison University, 2003

³³⁵ 4000 sq km versus 400 sq km

programme attractive from a donor's point of view³³⁶ and that is an expansion on the earlier categorization of donor countries:³³⁷

- (1) dedicated and capable leadership by the recipient government;
- (2) commitment, accountability and transparency to the stakeholders in terms of financial and performance of duties;
- (3) a national strategic planning process, containing a realistic and achievable vision; prioritized goals and measurable objectives;
- (4) investment strategy with national contributions to support the plan;
- (5) ability to learn and adjust the national mine action program as the plan is carried out.

Since the establishment of the Monterrey Consensus,³³⁸ where all developed countries were urged to make concrete efforts toward the goal of 0,7 percent of gross domestic product as official development assistance, the above points have become gradually more recurrent on the donor's list of desiderata. World leaders step forward with more support but more conditionally.

"President Bush himself came to Monterrey to announce a surprising and welcome increase of United States foreign assistance in a new project known as the Millennium Challenge Account, or MCA. He pledged that the United States would increase its foreign assistance to countries that demonstrated the *will* and the *capacity* to use the funding effectively."³³⁹

The United States focuses on a measurable output that enables them to gauge progress – or lack thereof – to rationally prioritize how the US State Department can allocate resources for mine action, increase their management oversight of mine action programs around the world as well as making them more transparent to all stakeholders. Thus definitely looks for the integration into broader strategies and is not hesitant to mention that it clearly has to fit into their national agenda.

"Our Humanitarian Mine Action Program does not operate in isolation. It complements and serves as a tool to accomplish the Department of State's mission of creating a more secure, democratic and prosperous world for the benefit of the American people and the international community. The mission of the Bureau of Political-Military Affairs, in which my office is located, is to integrate diplomacy and military power to foster a stable and secure international environment hospitable to American values and interests."³⁴⁰

Four criteria can further help to determine which countries will receive their humanitarian mine action assistance and the degree of funding for that assistance. In relation with the conditional approach above, the following could be considered: (1)the mine-affected country's humanitarian need, (2)how rendering aid would coincide with their foreign policy interests, (3)the efficiency and transparency of the mine-affected country's national mine action program, and (4)the affected nation's own genuine commitment to rid itself of its landmines and UXO.³⁴¹

The collection of criteria above rightly exposes the requested conditions to keep the international community sufficiently engaged.³⁴² If the national authorities show more leadership and the mine action community good institutional developments, then the studied *Diner's Dilemma*

³³⁶ As deduced from Richard Kidd, USA rep – Nov MASG meeting, Internet. Available at <http://www.mineaction.org/overview.asp?o=144>, accessed on 12 July 2005

³³⁷ See analysis of preamble paragraph 2 of the UN resolution on assistance in mine action.

³³⁸ The Monterrey Consensus was the outcome of the 2002 Monterrey Conference, the United Nations International Conference on Financing for Development. It was adopted by Heads of State and Government on 22 March 2002. Since its adoption, the Monterrey Consensus has become the major reference point for international development cooperation. Internet, available at <http://www.un.org/esa/ffd>, accessed on 10 June 2006

³³⁹ SACHS, J. (2005). *The End of Poverty. Economic possibilities for our time*, New York, p.218

³⁴⁰ Statement by Richard Kidd at the Humanitarian Mine/UXO clearance Technology and Cooperation Workshop - Kunming, China, 26-28 April 2004

³⁴¹ Colonel John Jordan, Chief of Humanitarian Mine Action in the U.S. Department of Defense

³⁴² Bob Eaton during the RMASG - Newsletter Nov 2004, Internet. Available at <http://www.mineaction.org/overview.asp?o=144>, accessed on 12 July 2005

phenomenon of *donor fatigue* can be put in perspective. It nevertheless remains crucially important that the global landmine problem is better defined:

“[...] the spending is still over 250 million USD per year. The EC and the US have published transparency strategies. We are getting more information, there are a lot of sources, but we still can't define the problem we are trying to solve. Donors should begin to have a coherent and broad strategy. Can the donor community agree on a consistent reporting by recipient countries? The donors could come together to define categories and requirements for consistent reporting.”³⁴³

3. Resource mobilisation forum, support and contact groups

International financial support to mine action is unlikely to increase dramatically in the near future. The mine action community is growingly aware of this reality and will, therefore, increasingly seek its justification within a broader conflict-recovery and development oriented context. A critical eye for the cost effectiveness and practical humanitarian and socio-economic benefits of mine action is, therefore, once again an important factor in determining the exact position of mine action within broader assistance strategies.

Fig. II.25: Efforts to improve donor coordination

The Mine Action Support Group (MASG)³⁴⁴ and Resource Mobilisation Contact Group³⁴⁵ have been frequent and strong advocates of better donor coordination, one of the core objectives of these groups. Resource mobilization is an area where a renewed approach³⁴⁶ is needed in order to realize the interlinked objectives to increase transparency, predictability and coordination of resource mobilization.³⁴⁷

The UN Mine Action Service interacts intensively with the MASG to obtain more clarity and funding predictability but has had limited success. Several other parallel initiatives rarely brought the desired results and illustrates once again how challenging it is to coordinate State behaviour in a multilateral context whenever there are no direct incentives to do so.

³⁴³ Bob Eaton during the RMASG - Newsletter Nov 2004, Internet. Available at <http://www.mineaction.org/overview.asp?o=144>, accessed on 12 July 2005

³⁴⁴ The MASG is a donor forum chaired and convened by Member States, which meets on a monthly basis, generally in New York, to discuss thematic and operational matters of concern to donors.

³⁴⁵ The Resource Mobilisation Contact Group has been created in 2002 and functioned for almost three years in the margin of the Intersessional meetings of the Mine Ban Treaty. It has focused on two objectives that are critical to the successful implementation of the MBT: (1) continued and adequate funding for mine action; and (2) the best possible utilisation of resources available for mine action.

³⁴⁶ Under the Belgian MASG Chair (2002), efforts were undertaken to come to a “complete picture”. Consequently, a ‘country profile’ was developed with the intent to provide an overview of the total amount of funding a mine action program was getting, since donors requested a clear overview per *donor-country* and *recipient-country*.

³⁴⁷ MASG presentation at the occasion of the 5th International Meeting of Mine Action Program Directors and Advisors at Geneva, May 2002

“I ask you all for your ongoing cooperation [...] in providing the information that is being requested. On the basis of this research, we hope to draw a detailed map of funding flows over the past few years ahead of the Sixth Meeting of States Parties. This information will contribute significantly to ongoing discussions on efficiency and effectiveness and provide meaningful input into our discussions on cooperation and assistance.”³⁴⁸

4. Mine action funding: based on *tit-for-tat* politics, *reciprocal altruism* and *credit games*?

A common thread has been presented throughout the analysis of this paragraph: the requirement of a best response based on measurable objectives, a sufficient absorptive capacity of the recipient country and skilful management capabilities to lead multi-million dollar programs. Regarding the latter, big variations in management skills and political leadership in an expert field as mine action are predictable. This argues for an inclusion of these elements as essential decision-making criterion for the resource allocation by donor countries, aptly assisted by the UN or other international institutions. Donors growing quest for well-run programmes has been well anticipated by the management of the more advanced mine action programme, e.g. Afghanistan. They expeditiously experimented with the usage of professional software planning tools and strategy development which will be further addressed in Phase-III, the Afghan case-study.

The above explains in a different context the game theoretic *tit-for-tat* concept. Funding for mine action is linked to the exigency to have a solid management and planning capability either already established or with the commitment to put it in place. If there is *reciprocal altruism*, then it should be stressed that the altruistic part is increasingly conditional to provoke the reciprocity, which is equally part of the kinder spirit and interpretation of a *tit-for-tat* game.

“According to Axelrod, *tit-for-tat* is successful because it is 'nice', 'provokable' and 'forgiving'. A nice strategy is one which is never first to defect. In a match between two nice strategies, both do well. A provokable strategy responds by defecting at once in response to defection. A forgiving strategy is one which readily returns to co-operation if its opponent does so; unforgiving strategies are likely to produce isolation and end co-operative encounters.”³⁴⁹

Another *tit-for-tat* element omnipresent in resource mobilisation for mine action is the request of donor countries to obtain international visibility and credit for their contributions to mine action. Very few references can be found in game theory but this *tit-for-tat* game could qualify as a “*credit game*”. It simply implies that donors will not engage themselves into funding of mine action programmes unless they get credit or recognition for it. The *credit game* also explains why donor countries prefer to provide support in a direct bilateral move in lieu of contributing in a multilateral context or through UN Trust Funds, even if the latter, through economies of scale, uses mine action funding more effectively. Often bilateral support is in light of strategic partnerships between two nations with specific foreign policy issues involved – e.g. former colonial ties - and economic reasons. Obvious examples in this regard are the US support to mine action programmes in Vietnam and Cambodia, Belgian support to the programmes in Lebanon, the Democratic Republic of Congo and Cambodia.

³⁴⁸ Contact Group on Resource Mobilisation, 13 June 2005, Internet. Available at http://www.gichd.ch/fileadmin/pdf/mbc/IWP/SC_june05/speeches_gs/Norway_13June05.pdf, accessed on 2 October 2006

³⁴⁹ Internet. Available at <http://www2.owen.vanderbilt.edu/mike.shor/Courses/GTheory/docs/Axelrod.html>, accessed on 10 November 2006

b. Deductions

1. Key points

- ☞ Trying to quantify the global cost or projected timelines to clear all mines is an overwhelming research activity with limited value.
- ☞ Three key elements for more effective mine action resource mobilisation and allocation are *increased transparency, higher predictability* and *global coordination*.
- ☞ The repeated quest for more resources is rarely substantiated or based on a solid cross-cutting analysis. Mainstreaming of mine action into development and peacebuilding has been driven by efforts to broaden the funding base.
- ☞ Donor countries are increasingly conditional and allocate their resources on a *tit-for-tat* basis to a particular mine-affected country, applying, amongst others, primarily measurable objectives, a sufficient absorptive capacity of the recipient country and skilful management capabilities. The United States is particularly business-like and pragmatic; support to mine action is an element of US foreign policy, serving US interest, in particular as part of their “global war on terror” strategy.

2. Possible indicators and criteria

In line with this preamble paragraph, all indicators and criteria are related to the resources required for mine action and the managerial capabilities to warrant an effective and efficient execution of the mine action programme, which can be once again summarized in terms of *optimal prioritization* and *strategic planning*.

Goal	Indicator
Having resource mobilization mechanism which are transparent, predictable and globally coordinated	Consultative processes in support of increased transparency, higher predictability and global coordination
Optimize the mobilization and allocation of additional resources	Amount of resources
Effective and efficient management of mine action programmes	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Dedicated and capable leadership by the government 2. Commitment to the stakeholders. 3. Planning process leading to a national plan. 4. National Strategic Plans contain: a realistic and achievable vision; prioritized goals; measurable objectives. 5. Investment strategy with national contributions to support the plan. Commitment to transparency and accountability in terms of financial and performance of duties. 6. The national mine action program learns and adjusts whilst the plan is carried out.

Criteria 31	Resource mobilization per capita
Criteria 32	Level of effectiveness and efficiency of a mine action programme
Criteria 33	Coordination, transparency and predictability of mine action funding

P. Preamble Paragraph 16: Progress in mine action related research and development

Concerned at the limited availability of safe and cost-effective mine-detection and mine-clearance equipment, as well as the need for effective global coordination in research and development to improve relevant technologies, and conscious of the need to promote further and more rapid progress in this field and to foster international, national and local technical cooperation to that end,

a. Analysis

1. Global coordination and cooperation in mine action

In addition to preamble paragraph 14 and 15, the preamble paragraphs 16 to 21 address comprehensively issues related to mine action coordination and cooperation in all its aspects and dimensions. In the following analysis, coordination is to be interpreted as those interactions which clarify or delineate the tasks amongst the different actors in order to obtain synergy, and to avoid duplication or competition. Cooperation implies the joint execution of shared tasks in fulfilment of common objectives. Hence, coordination of mine action can take place without having to cooperate, but effective cooperation requires effective coordination.

This paragraph focuses on the global coordination of research and development (R&D) in order to enhance the effectiveness and efficiency of mine action. R&D will only be addressed in this context; otherwise it would fall outside the scope of this study. The comprehensive analysis of aspects of coordination and cooperation will be primarily addressed in preamble paragraph 17, which is the key paragraph on this issue.

2. Research and development; what should be the norm?

Over the past years it became increasingly apparent that a lot of research and development effort has gone to mine detection equipment that is unlikely to be of practical use in the near future. Too much R&D money went to badly user-oriented projects. The term *disconnect* was frequently used to describe the relationship between the R&D sector and the people in the field. In general two distinct high political or strategic views can be observed regarding the support of the development of mine action technology.³⁵⁰

- (1) The *negative* view. Nothing has substantially changed since the Second World War and much R&D money is being spent with no result; military security prohibits some technology; commercial market is too small to drive development of new products; impractical equipment is often being developed in isolation; promised new technology has not delivered the solution for all the problems; R&D community is not aligned to the field; R&D is only focused on clearance technology and not on victim assistance and Mine Risk Education, etc.
- (2) The *positive* view. Progress is evolutionary, not revolutionary; existing clearance equipment has improved (metal detectors more sensitive, mechanical equipment adapted); significant advances in IT-equipment (IMSMA); user needs better defined; some new equipment fielded; better understanding of use of scent detection; standard test procedures established and evaluations conducted; R&D money is not taking funding from other mine action activities.

In reinforcement of the positive view, real progress in the following three areas is currently pursued with a sense of pressing necessity: (1) hand-held dual sensor mine detectors that will dramatically reduce the incidence of false alarms encountered by existing metal detectors; (2)

³⁵⁰ MANSFIELD, I. (2005, July) MASG Newsletter, Internet. Available at <http://www.mineaction.org/downloads/1/July%202005.pdf>, accessed on 3 December 2005

systems for quickly reducing suspected areas to the area that is genuinely contaminated³⁵¹; and, although some considerable progress has already been made, (3) systems for route-proving and route clearance. This can be transformed into more detailed criteria:

“Criteria are: reliable, cost effective, appropriate, robust. Conditions are: need by the user (technology has to be appropriate to the situation and expertise has to be around for reparations); development of the technology must be complete (users can’t make modifications); a competent manufacturer must be involved; sufficient quantities and sustained funding must be provided.”³⁵²

In its operative part, the UN resolution further stipulates that UN Member States and regional, intergovernmental and non-governmental organizations and foundations that have the ability to do so, provide technological assistance to mine-affected countries to promote (1), user-oriented scientific research on and development of mine-action techniques and technology, within (2), reasonable time frames, so that mine-action activities may be carried out more safely and cost-effectively, and also urges them (3), to promote collaboration at all levels in this regard.³⁵³ The different levels of cooperation highlight again the importance of having a well-connected high-medium-low and strategic-operational-tactical approach.

3. Key strategic planning parameters: mine and battlefield clearance rates

The above sections summarize the key normative issues for this study. Technological and scientific challenges in finding landmines are a specific research domain. Also here the challenges to determine the best response pose a unique multiple criteria problem. Not only are mines buried at different depths, in different soils, in different terrains affected by every known weather pattern, but there are over five hundred types, models and varieties of landmines that are composed of different materials, contain different explosives, differing components, and sometimes unique anti-tampering or triggering devices.³⁵⁴ In Annex F, a collection of different operational environments illustrates additional challenges to perform mine clearance.

Therefore, taking either a positive or negative view, to achieve substantial increases in mine clearance rates or decreases in mine detection time,³⁵⁵ requires a paradigm shift in mine detection R&D. Rather than focusing on individual technologies operating in isolation, mine detection R&D should emphasize the design from first principles and subsequent development of an integrated, multi-sensor system that would overcome the limitations of any single-sensor technology.³⁵⁶ This toolbox approach does not make cooperation and coordination in this field any easier but seems to be the best answer in absence of a technological breakthrough. After many R&D attempts to create and develop state-of-the-art, multi-efficient mine clearance technology, the first results can now be observed in the field, but almost without exception these are new variations of old technology.

In sum, the silver bullet has not yet been found and it is unlikely that any one technology will provide the breakthrough necessary to substantially improve mine clearance rates. If there is any significant improvement to be expected than it will be likely through the more effective usage of biosensors in combination with improved vapour detection technology. For example, based on their extreme olfactory sense, giant African pouched rats could be trained as cheap, reliable and fast

³⁵¹ To date, dogs have been used extensively in this role; however their capabilities are limited by a variety of different factors. In particular rats, but also bees and colour-changing plants have been touted as having significant potential in this area.

³⁵² Mine Action Support Group Newsletter, Internet. Available at [www.mineaction.org/downloads/1/July 2005.pdf](http://www.mineaction.org/downloads/1/July%2005.pdf), accessed on 23 April 2005

³⁵³ UN Document A/RES/58/127, operational paragraph 23 from UN resolution on ‘Assistance in mine action’, Internet. Available at <http://www.un.org/Depts/dhl/resguide/r58.htm>, accessed on 20 July 2005

³⁵⁴ Humanitarian Demining, Internet. Available at <http://www.humanitarian-demining.org/demining/threat.asp>, accessed on 10 May 2006

³⁵⁵ While maintaining high probabilities of detection without any compromise on the safety of the mine clearance activities.

³⁵⁶ RAND study, Internet. Available at http://www.rand.org/pubs/monograph_reports/MR1608/MR1608.ch3.pdf, accessed on 10 November 2006

biosensors for detection of landmines. They offer a promising and sustainable alternative to more expensive mine detection dogs or technologies that require extensive expertise from abroad.³⁵⁷

b. Deductions

1. Key points

- ☞ A better understanding of the challenges of providing technological assistance to mine-affected countries inevitably requires knowledge of the different mine types and models. ERW - cluster bombs - encountered during mine and battlefield clearance activities, pose similar challenges in terms of risks, but clearance rates can be considerably faster.
- ☞ No single implementation parameter of mine action is as important for strategic planning and so much affected by R&D as the rate at which clearance operations could take place. Clearance rates for different clearance activities are often merged, purposely leading to superior output formulation of mine action programmes.
- ☞ Many misperceptions on clearance rates remain, especially at the high political level, partly instigated by the overambitious clearance timelines of the MBT.
- ☞ R&D to increase the effectiveness and efficiency of mine action - in particular mine clearance - has been widely evolutionary, but without any significant breakthrough. Main R&D criteria have been defined as: (1) reliable, (2) cost effective, and (3) robust. Coordination and collaboration is important at and in between all levels in order to have mine action technology which is user-friendly, timely and affordable.

2. Possible indicators and criteria

R&D in the context of this study has primarily implications for key strategic planning parameters in terms of mine clearance rates and possible improvements thereof. It is obvious that long-term mine action programmes (> 5 years) significantly benefit from faster clearance rates, even if it is only an acceleration of mine clearance rates with a few %.

Goal	Indicator
More progress in the development of safe and cost effective mine detection and clearance equipment/sensors	Improvements in the rate of mine clearance
	Level of cooperation and coordination in R&D
	Reliability, cost-effectiveness, and durability of mine clearance equipment
	User-oriented, reasonable timeframes for R&D of mine detection and clearance equipment
	Faster mine clearance rates in respect with International Mine Action Standards (IMAS)

Criterion 34	Progress in the field of mine detection and clearance equipment
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³⁵⁷ APOPO trains sniffer rats to detect explosives and diagnose disease. This unusual idea has been developed into a competitive technology by a group of Belgian and Tanzanian researchers and animal trainers, Internet. Available at <http://www.apopo.org/newsite/content/index.htm>, accessed on 12 May 2007

Q. Preamble Paragraph 17: Cooperation and coordination of mine action

Reaffirming the need to reinforce cooperation and coordination in the area of mine action at all levels and to devote the necessary resources to that end, including resources to support national and regional capacity-building initiatives, where applicable, and the work of the United Nations in this regard,

a. Analysis

1. International mine action cooperation and coordination: a “Catch-22” ?

This preamble paragraph underscores the importance of cooperation and coordination in mine action at all levels. The comprehensive analysis of cooperation and coordination is, therefore, the core of the analysis in this paragraph. It intends to highlight the key coordination challenges, delineating and defining the implications at different political levels of mine action. As anticipated, more game theoretic principles will be applied to explain the different bargaining positions of the key stakeholders.

Long and ongoing debates amongst the United Nations, UN Member States, Regional Organisations and implementing NGOs have contributed to norm building on how coordination and cooperation could be best “*institutionalised*”, if by all means the latter is an appropriate term to use. The saying “*everybody wants to coordinate, but nobody wants to be coordinated*” tellingly captures the sub-optimal coordination which regularly exists. Coordination challenges are present at all levels; at field level, especially when the United Nations steps in too heavy handed,³⁵⁸ and between donor countries or UN institutional actors.

“On the global role of UN mine action centres HALO does not believe that they should co-ordinate, control and try to implement - as this will always lead to conflict with the implementing agencies who will see UNMAC [UN Mine Action Centre] behaving like a football referee who half way through the game decides to pick up the ball and score a touch down. It cannot work.”³⁵⁹

Mine action coordination and cooperation needs to be studied in relation with the involved actions and actors. Besides the negativism cited above, the UN has a vital role to play in the coordination of mine action activities, primarily at the highest policy level and in many different ways at an implementation/executive level. Clearly this preamble paragraph³⁶⁰ envisages emphasizing this important UN role. The reference below provides a refined summary, which further highlights the key coordination issues.

“In addition to increased resources, the key to addressing most of these challenges is effective coordination. Donor countries can play a valuable supportive role at the *national* - but more importantly at the *global* - level. It may not be an exaggeration to say that little coordination can take place if the donors do not make it a key priority and even a pre-condition for funding. While the establishment of the Mine Action Support Group and the Resource Mobilization Contact Group are welcome initiatives, each and every donor organization should ensure that its global, geographic, and thematic plans and priorities are well-coordinated and that decisions are made with adequate information concerning national priorities and other donor plans and programmes.”³⁶¹

This dissertation defends the concept where the institutional politics ought to materialize the *medium* politics of mine action and function as the bridging and coordination mechanism between the high and low politics. The strategic guidance on the prioritization of efforts is hereby a most

³⁵⁸ This was observed and stated by INGOs during field visits of mine action programmes in Eritrea and Afghanistan in 2002 with UNMAS and the members of the Mine Action Support Group.

³⁵⁹ Mail HALO Trust of 6 September 2002, Guy Willoughby, forwarded to the relevant permanent missions at the UN

³⁶⁰ In addition to the preamble paragraph 2 and the specifically dedicated operative paragraph 11 on the reinforcement of cooperation and coordination

³⁶¹ AQA, S. (2005). Mine action. Success and Challenges. *Journal of Mine Action*, Issue 9.1, MAIC - James Madison University, Washington DC

essential element. Consequently, the United Nations Policy on Mine Action and Effective Coordination recognized this important issue in the following section of the policy document³⁶²:

“The requirement for prioritization and accountability: all programs should have well-established mechanisms to set priorities for mine action activities on the basis of need and the most effective use of available resources. [...] Programs should also incorporate clearly defined accountability mechanisms to ensure that priority needs are met and that there is cost-effective use of available resources. They should involve periodic review exercises in order to determine overall effectiveness in approach, orientation and implementation, and to advise on what changes, if any, need to be introduced.”³⁶³

Fig. II.26: Cooperation and coordination in mine action

Coordination and cooperation in mine action is complex which justifies a visualisation of the interactions rather than a lengthy explanation. Hence, before addressing the UN role specifically, the schematic overview below depicts the coordination (symbolically, \leftrightarrow) between the key actors, with their corresponding activities to the high, medium and low politics.

³⁶² UNMAS Document (1998) UN Policy on Coordination, Internet. Available at <http://www.mineaction.org>, accessed on 3 January 2006

³⁶³ A/53/496, Annex II on www.ods.un.org - 1998, United Nations policy on Mine Action and Effective Coordination

The follow-on sections will further address the most relevant cooperation and coordination issues.

2. UNMAS as a United Nations focal point for mine action

The coordination, centralisation and oversight of mine action activities have been occasionally a “minefield” of their own. The United Nations Mine Action Service (UNMAS) was, therefore, established in October 1997 to serve as a focal point for mine action in the United Nations and to support the UN’s recently updated vision of “*a world free of the threat of landmines and UXO, where individuals and communities live in a safe environment conducive to development, and where mine survivors are fully integrated into their societies.*”³⁶⁴ Therefore, UNMAS undertakes an ongoing collaboration with and coordination of all mine-related activities of the United Nations agencies, funds and programmes, in accordance with United Nations mine-action policy.³⁶⁵ UNMAS is a key medium politics actor and the most important interface between the UN and the UN Member States. Its functions are: policy development and coordination, assessment of the landmine threat, programme initiation and support, information management, quality management and technology, advocacy and treaty implementation, and – last but not least - resource mobilization.³⁶⁶ UNMAS also manages or supports mine action operations in humanitarian emergencies and peacekeeping operations.

Fig. II.27: UNMAS as the focal point of mine action in the United Nations

3. Competing actors in medium politics

The principles of collaboration and coordination within the UN system are significantly influenced by the three key actors, UNMAS, UNICEF and UNDP. They have to obtain funding largely through voluntary contributions; sometimes this leads inevitably to turf protection and competition, which can come at the cost of good cooperation and coordination.

“[...] Although each institution claims that it would have never engaged in turf battles if only the others hadn’t started first, in this war there are no innocent parties. Scarce resources inspire competition. Competition leads to misunderstandings and these lead to compartmentalization of information and protection of ‘territory’. The end result is an erosion of the collaborative processes and cross-fertilization of ideas that should generate progress.”³⁶⁷

The above phenomenon does not go unnoticed. When UNMAS consulted UN Member States to obtain their views on the first UN Strategy for mine action,³⁶⁸ major donor countries such

³⁶⁴ UNMAS, UN Document 2006 Strategy, Internet. Available at <http://www.mineaction.org>, accessed on 12 July 2005.

³⁶⁵ UN Document A/RES/58/127, operational paragraph 12 from UN resolution on ‘Assistance in mine action’, Internet. Available at <http://www.un.org/Depts/dhl/resguide/r58.htm>, accessed on 20 July 2005

³⁶⁶ Internet. Available at <http://www.mineaction.org>, accessed on 3 July 2005

³⁶⁷ GRAYSON, J. (2003) Mine action and development: merging strategies. *Disarmament Forum*, p.15 - 24

³⁶⁸ The UN Member States requested in the UN assistance in mine action resolution of 2001 that their views were solicited on the UN Strategy for 2001-2005

as Japan expressed their concern over the observed competition between UN Agencies or how UNMAS adopts up its role as the UN focal point for mine action.

“With regard to Strategic Goal Five [= UN cooperation and coordination of mine action], the United Nations Mine Action Service should exercise stronger leadership with regard to the other United Nations mine action related agencies so as to *effectively coordinate their operations*, collect updated information on the situation of activities and resource mobilization, and promptly share such information with donors and mine action related NGOs.”³⁶⁹

Although the separation of mine action tasks appears to be adequately delineated in figure II.28 below, in reality some duplication and institutional competition has proven to be sporadically problematic. The already cited possible competition for funding and other resources, and the fragmentation of mine action functions over so many UN agencies and other regional, national and local actors are most daunting tasks. To this end, UNMAS coordinates “on paper” the work of 14 UN offices, departments, programmes and funds involved in mine action, in accordance with their mandates, areas of expertise and comparative advantages.³⁷⁰ Figure II.28 depicts only the main UN actors.

Fig. II.28: Core activities of UNMAS/UN agencies and possible competing resource mobilisation

Fortunately there are several existing coordination mechanisms to alleviate coordination problems. These mechanisms include: the Humanitarian Liaison Working Group, the Inter-Agency Standing Committee and the Executive Committee on Humanitarian Affairs at the headquarters level; the UN Resident/Humanitarian Coordinator and UN country team meetings at the field level. The latter is particularly important to coordinate with the international and national NGOs. UNMAS is also bound to ensure that all like-minded partners outside the UN system, including NGOs, the

³⁶⁹ Note Verbal from the Permanent Mission (PM) of Japan to UNMAS dated 3rd June 2002, regarding the Mine Action Strategy for 2001-2005, later forwarded to the PM of Belgium to the UN with the request to reflect this suggestion in the draft proposal of the Resolution Assistance in mine action.

³⁷⁰ These are: the Department of Peacekeeping Operations (DPKO), the United Nations Mine Action Service (UNMAS), the Department of Disarmament Affairs (DDA), the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), the United Nations Children’s Fund (UNICEF), the United Nations Office of Project Services (UNOPS), the Food and Agriculture Organisation (FAO), the Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA), the Office of the Special Advisor on Gender Issues (OSAGI), the Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights (OHCHR), the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR), the World Food Programme (WFP), the World Health Organization (WHO) and the World Bank.

GICHD, the International Committee of the Red Cross and other components of the International Red Cross and Red Crescent Movement, are sufficiently engaged.³⁷¹

In summary, the high number of medium politics actors, the institutional element of competition, the possibility of duplication and the ever-changing coordination requirements of a dynamic mine action programme necessitate the management of expectations regarding the UN's coordinating and bridging capabilities between the high and low politics. The evolutionary character of mine action programmes requiring different types of coordination will be addressed in the next section.

4. UN assistance during the lifecycle of a mine action programme

The life cycle of a mine action program and the related UN institutional responsibilities are depicted below. During emergency or peacekeeping situations, UNMAS frequently has the primary responsibility for the inception and support of mine action activities, often in part with other relevant

Fig. II.29: Costing and Stages of a mine action programme

agencies. This corresponds with phase one. UNDP is largely engaged in mine action aligned to phase three which largely entails development-oriented mine action. Hence, phase two is more a transition phase whereby the majority of mine action programs evolve towards national capacity-building. This will ultimately result in a transition to a national program under the auspices of a national mine action authority. UNICEF, focused on MRE, can - and often should - be involved as early as phase one and remain active throughout phase three.

From this schematic lifecycle it may be deduced that an ever-evolving requirement to coordinate different types of mine action and therefore actors. The dynamic nature of mine action coordination is also reflected in the outcome of Landmine Impact Surveys. As previously mentioned, the survey data focuses on the landmine impact on communities and handles a straightforward classification system according to a landmine impact score: *high*, *medium* or *low*. This mine impact score is based on the sum of human cost and socio-economic factors.

5. Further refining and defining the different political levels of mine action

To facilitate a better understanding of the politics of mine action, several references have been made to the different political levels. The distinction high-medium-low politics could, however, benefit from a more comprehensive assessment as it is one of the cornerstones of the analysis. Research only delivered few previous references regarding the suggested norm or concept of *medium politics* in this study. As part of the ongoing efforts to install a small arms ban, the following has been stated in respect with the high politics of mine action:

“Small arms control became *medium politics* on the international agenda in 1998. It was called medium relative to the high politics of landmines, the issue's progenitor in many minds, but it was the subject of a feverish pace of activity compared to just one year ago. Most notable, in late October sixteen States in West Africa signed a binding agreement to ban the production, import and export of small

³⁷¹ UN Document. A/53/496, Mine Action and Effective Coordination: the United Nations Policy, New York

arms for a three year trial period. In addition, western hemisphere governments signed (and several ratified) a convention on illicit manufacture and transfer of firearms. Preparations for negotiation of a global protocol against firearms trafficking were begun. And, during the summer, the Canadian government proposed a treaty barring transfers of military-style small arms to insurgent forces and other non-State actors.”³⁷²

The above citation refers to medium politics as a general concept. One can deduce that the usage of medium versus high politics somewhat relates to the number of States involved and level of success attained. The politics involved are rather described as a qualified effort compared to the successful outcome of the high politics towards a total ban on landmines. This deduction is neither in harmony with the more standing definitions of high and low politics, nor helpful in providing a useful concept for this study. It is not because a high level political phenomenon is taking place on a smaller scale - but with similar characteristics - that it should automatically be “downgraded” to medium politics. The qualification of “middle” power fails also to provide a straightforward linkage with the medium politics:

“The end of the Cold War also provided opportunities for *middle powers* such as Canada to embrace an issue of international concern despite a lack of interest in a landmine ban from the United States. The interest of middle powers and NGOs was essential to the development of the 1997 Mine Ban Treaty.”³⁷³

Therefore, defining precisely a concept such as *medium politics* requires more assessment than initially expected. Delineating better the high and low politics of mine action may best facilitate the definition of the political medium in between. When recapitulating the general definitions of high and low politics³⁷⁴ in a specific mine action context, then the high politics of mine action are those political dynamics where the State is one of the key actors for reasons related to national security, defence policy, military doctrine or other strategic issues such as the impact of high numbers of mine victims during emergencies or a refugee crisis. It encompasses what matters most to and between States: maintain national sovereignty and remain secure from external attacks. Consequently, the high politics of mine action entail the political interactions between sovereign States themselves, between the United Nations and sovereign States or between NGOs, regional organizations and States. This recalls the renowned “*Ottawa-model*”.

The low politics can be more precisely defined as those *socio-economic* or *development* factors influencing the implementation and prioritization of mine action, more specifically the impact element of mine contamination (e.g. the process of Landmine Impact Surveys) on nation building processes, its pursuit of economic well-being and national development programs. They are said to be of considerably lesser importance than the high politics, nevertheless important enough to state that the politics at this level require sufficient national and local ownership for mine action programmes to be really effective. Ultimately, national and local decision-making at this level should even have the ability to reprioritize originally intended funding for mine action whenever other more urgent socio-economic or development needs arise.

The concrete and precise definition of the high and low politics of mine action facilitates the further description of a *medium level*, which can address the politics where States are not the key actors. But first, is the above delineation between high and low politics really sufficient to state there is a gap in between? Some security studies argue that an artificial distinction could be considerably overdrawn, even if one uses a narrow definition of high and low politics, for several reasons. First, it ignores the *economic* underpinnings of military power and national security that many *realists* themselves acknowledge as essential components of national power. Second, it takes for granted the

³⁷²LUMPE, L. (1998, November), Controlling Small Arms: Progress & Priorities. *Disarmament Diplomacy*, Issue No. 32, Internet. Available at <http://www.acronym.org.uk/textonly/dd/dd32/32lora.htm>, accessed on 12 August 2006

³⁷³McDONALD, B. (2004). *The Global Landmine Crisis in the 1990s – Landmines and Human Security*, New York: State University of New York Press, p.31-32

³⁷⁴See also paragraph I.1.2 regarding the introductory remarks of high politics versus low politics.

independence States have both from the international economy and from domestic political opposition when mobilizing economic resources in support of security objectives. Finally, it glosses over the potential for States to achieve national security objectives in an interdependent world economy by using economic instruments, such as economic sanctions decided by the UN Security Council and otherwise economic incentives.³⁷⁵

Additional analysis could provide welcome refinements of terminology, however, it will not necessarily deliver more useful inputs for the next research phase. Given the complexity and variety of social phenomena in the disarmament sector, any particular set of distinction will be somewhat arbitrary. The methodology used in this study is indeed a departure from the widely employed six levels recognizable to social analysts, namely: *world system*, *society*, *organizational field*, *organizational population*, *organization*, and *organizational subsystem*. Clearly the *high politics* are to be associated with the *world system* and *society* with the allocation of the other levels to the medium and low politics as less evident. It depends which angle one takes on those organizational and societal elements. *Medium politics* can largely be associated with an *organizational field*, and a *population*, if one defines both as representing a collection or aggregate of organizations that share a strategic vision and common goals.³⁷⁶ This leaves the *low politics* to be associated with the *organization* and *organizational subsystems*. Based on these supplementary arguments, caution dictates not to oversimplify a complex reality through a too stringent categorization of multi-level political interactions. A similar observation can be made if too much eagerness is applied to draw sharp lines between the strategic, operational and tactical level of any type of operation. Modern warfare in Iraq and Afghanistan clearly illustrates the strategic impact and repercussions at the highest political and military level of tactical insurgency weapons, as was extensively addressed under preamble paragraph 13. Therefore, without losing sight on the interdependence of the high and low politics or strategic, operational and tactical, an acceptable and distinct focus needs to be applied when trying to define the medium politics of mine action without trying to separate what is blurred in the real world.

In summary, when limited to the political interactions *within* the institutional and organizational entities, amongst NGOs, the United Nations, ICRC and to a certain extent regional organizations such as the EU, African Union (AU), Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS) and Organisation of American States (OAS), it is possible to indicate a specific political medium and process amongst a distinct group of key actors. Moreover, precisely non-State actors contribute significantly to the *implementation* of mine action. This further justifies explicit recognition through defining the political interactions amongst these actors as the *medium politics* of mine action. Also the *public-private partnership*³⁷⁷ for mine action can be included in the *medium politics*, which is primarily situated in the United States and largely based on the initiatives and enthusiasm of private donors.

“As needs exceed projected available resources, however, the United Nations will have to develop new strategies to expand the base of contributors and introduce non-traditional donors to mine action. *Alliances with the private sector*, partnerships between public and private entities, and academia have significant potential for raising consciousness and resources.”³⁷⁸

7. Medium or “middling” politics of mine action?

Critical voices might call the medium politics sometimes the middling politics of mine action. The phenomena described earlier such as turf protection, competition for funding, and

³⁷⁵ Internet. Available at <http://www.jmss.org/2000/article1.html>, accessed on 7 may 2005

³⁷⁶ SCOTT, R. (2001), *Institutions and organizations*, California, p.82

³⁷⁷ U.S. Department of State is working with non-governmental organizations, civic associations, philanthropic foundations, educational institutions, and private corporations to protect innocent civilians from the threat of landmines.

³⁷⁸ Canada’s guide to the global ban on landmines, Internet. Available at <http://www.mines.gc.ca>, accessed on 7 may 2005

“clubbiness” mentality, with in- and out-groups, can form obstacles between the high and low politics of mine action and hinder its overall effectiveness. With a relatively small group of key actors at the level of medium politics, clubbiness effects reduce the constructive involvement or influence of others. This further indicates that of the three political levels of mine action, the effectiveness of medium politics is essential if cooperation amongst the UN, national and local authorities, international and national NGOs are to deliver the desired results in terms of synergy between all these actors. The above only outlines the necessary conceptual delineation of the politics to answer some of the questions below with more clarity during the case-study.

“Mine action almost always occurs in a *sensitive political environment*. Landmine and UXO contamination is a product of armed conflict which is a manifestation of political crisis. Despite this seemingly obvious statement, research on mine action has tended to focus on technical elements of mine and UXO clearance, the movement leading to the anti-personnel mine ban, or the socio-economic impact of landmines. There has been surprisingly little study of the politics of the clearance process itself. Key questions have often remained unanswered: Who carries out demining and what was their record during the conflict? Who benefits politically from the aid given to support mine action? Who act as ‘middlemen’ between international donors and the local deminers and to what uses do they put their profit?”³⁷⁹

8. A game theoretic perspective on mine action coordination and cooperation

Having addressed numerous normative aspects, the next paragraphs will take a game theoretic angle on the specific challenges of mine action coordination and cooperation addressed in this and preceding preamble paragraphs. Coordination games are a class of games in which pure strategy Nash equilibriums exist when players choose the same or corresponding strategies. This naturally represents the most desired setting for the key actors in mine action. Consequently, the traditional games to explain this type of favourable coordination are those in which the actors obtain the highest payoffs when they choose the same strategy, such as the “*Stag Hunt*” game.

Although most political scientists focus on the PD as the game that best represents the problem of social cooperation, game theorists generally believe that the *Stag Hunt* represents an equally, or more interesting context in which to study cooperation and its problems. As for other games, the *Stag Hunt* was originally also a tale³⁸⁰ before it became one of the most studied games. The story is of hunters with two choices: hunting a hare or hunting a deer. Hunting a hare does not require any cooperation or coordination with other hunters. There is, however, no chance of hunting for a deer, but the chances of a successful deer hunt increase sharply with the number of hunters. A deer is much more valuable than a hare. Given these facts, interaction and cooperation is required and this is generally known as the “*stag hunt*”. In this regard, game theorist Brian Skyrms' studies the ideas of cooperation and collective action by analyzing the substantial relationship between the *stag hunt* and the *prisoner's dilemma*.

“If two people cooperate in prisoner’s dilemma, each is choosing less rather than more. In prisoner’s dilemma, there is a conflict between individual rationality and mutual benefit. In the stag hunt, what is rationale for one player to choose depends on his beliefs about what the other will choose. Both stag hunting and hare hunting are Nash equilibria. That is just to say that it is best to hunt stag if the other player hunts stag, and it is best to hunt hare if the other player hunts hare”³⁸¹

To remind, the symmetric PD in matrix II.8 below does not provide the highest possible payoffs when both players decide to cooperate. Hence, cooperation will only be achieved when there is a long-term perspective on increased gains if cooperation is chosen by either actors or

³⁷⁹ Bosnia’s Political Landmines, Published in September 2006 by Landmine Action, 89 Albert Embankment, London SE1 7TP, www.landmineaction.org

³⁸⁰ Based on a prototypical story found in the work of Jean-Jacques Rousseau in a “Discourse on Inequality”. Rousseau contrasts the pay-off of hunting hare (where the risk of non-cooperation is small and the reward equally small) against the pay-off of hunting the stag (where maximum cooperation is required but the reward is much greater.) Penguin Classics; (February 5, 1985)

³⁸¹ SKYRMS, B. (2003). *The Stag Hunt and the Evolution of Social Structure*, United Kingdom: Cambridge University Press. p.2-4

increased costs if defection is maintained. This needs to take into account possible discounts and evolutionary aspects which make one actor trust the other to cooperate.

		Actor 2	
		Cooperate	Defect
Actor 1	Cooperate	win - win	lose much – win much
	Defect	win much – lose much	lose - lose

Matrix II.8: Strategic form of a PD game with generic payoffs

If a similar game theoretic approach is applied, then the strategic form of a *Stag Hunt* game clearly indicates the payoff differences. Hunting a stag gives obviously the highest payoff but requires hunters to cooperate (win much), hunting a hare can be done alone but with smaller payoff (win). Hunting a stag alone is very challenging and will most likely result in an unsuccessful hunt (lose). A player is, however, confronted with his biggest loss whenever he chooses to cooperate with the other hunter, believing he will cooperate in a reciprocal manner, but with the other hunter letting him down. Hence, the *Stag Hunt* is a game which describes a conflict between safety, trust and social cooperation. This explains why in various game theoretic publications other names are used for this game or its variants such as “*assurance game*” and “*trust dilemma*”.³⁸²

		(I)NGOs		
		Hunting stag together	Hunting hare	Hunting stag alone
UN	Hunting stag together	win much, win much	lose much, win	lose much, lose
	Hunting hare	win, lose much	win, win	win, lose
	Hunting stag alone	lose, lose much	lose, win	lose, lose

Matrix II.9: Strategic form of the *Stag Hunt* game with generic payoffs

Although generic, the normative and game theoretic elements in matrix II.9 provide a suitable explanation for the many political aspects related to cooperation and coordination in mine action. The key actors are all aware that they would benefit from cooperating together in order to obtain synergy of their combined efforts. But there is again that crucial element of risk in the decision-making which alters strategic choices away from what seems logic utility maximization. Cooperation and coordination are hindered by a lack of trust and shared vision between the implementing and institutional (UN) actors. More importantly, there is a fear to lose any funding opportunities if they cannot solicit donor countries directly to fund their specific mine action projects. Thus, rational actors at the low politics level, in particular national and international NGOs, are drawn in one direction by considerations of risk and in another by considerations of mutual benefit. In order to protect their independence and individuality, NGOs opt often to settle for lower expected utilities compared to what could be achieved through UN coordinated mine action. Some of the mine action NGOs - like HALO Trust - are renowned to remain as independent as possible, or in *stag hunt* terminology:

“[...] the payoff of hunting hare is absolutely independent of how others act. We could vary this slightly without affecting the underlying theme. Perhaps if you hunt hare, it is even better for you if the other hunts stag, for you avoid competition for the hare. If the effect is small, we still have an interaction that is much like the Stag Hunt. It displays the same tension between risk and mutual benefit.”³⁸³

These risks versus mutual benefits depend highly on what the low politics actors expect the medium politics actors to do in the field of mine action. David Hume (1740) was perhaps the first to

³⁸² BRYANT, J. (2003). *The Six Dilemmas of Collaboration: Inter-organisational Relationships as Drama*, Publisher: John Wiley & Sons. P 156-158.

³⁸³ SKYRMS, B. (2003). *The Stag Hunt and the Evolution of Social Structure*, United Kingdom: Cambridge University Press. p.2-4

make explicit reference to the role of this mutual knowledge in coordination. In *A Treatise of Human Nature*, Hume argued that a necessary condition for coordinated activity was that agents all know what behaviour to expect from one another.³⁸⁴ This is perhaps one of the most confrontational elements in the ongoing debate of effective mine action coordination and cooperation. There is no inclusive agreement on which coordination functions the UN should fulfil and more critical voices tend to see a significantly smaller UN role.

“One main issue is whether the UN should implement programmes (aside from situations where the UN is the de facto government, as occurred in Kosovo). As has been suggested more generally with respect to international aid, there are strong arguments in favour of the statement that, ‘instead of competing with NGOs and bilateral agencies at the project level, UN agencies should concentrate on their traditional domains, that is, their normative roles in their fields of specialisations.’”³⁸⁵

Others see a conflict between too much “*institutional overhead*” limiting the national independency of their mine action NGOs at field level, visibility and other interests, further amplified by the earlier cited *trust dilemmas* and *credit games*.

“On the global role of UN mine action centers HALO does not believe that they should co-ordinate, control and try to implement - as this will always lead to conflict with the implementing agencies who will see UNMAC behaving like a football referee who half way through the game decides to pick up the ball and score a touch down. *It cannot work.*”³⁸⁶

Norway withdrew its co-sponsorship in 2001 primarily due to its concern regarding the above-mentioned coordinating role of the UN Mine Action Service. The Norwegian opposition of the UN coordinating role has been primarily related to protect the relative autonomy of the activities of the Norwegian mine action NGOs, e.g. Norwegian People’s Aid.

“The UN Mine Action Service has an important role in securing the integration of mine action issues in the work of the UN system wherever it may be relevant; it is important, however, to make a distinction between the [UN] Secretariat’s coordinating and mainstreaming task within the UN system, and the operative, field based mine action carried out by UN and non-governmental organizations.”³⁸⁷

The more critical or protective voices see the increasing developments and efforts to coordinate mine action as a big distracter, taking away large amounts of funding from the core activities, in particular mine clearance. The statement below reveals even higher levels of distrust at field level. Some NGOs perceive many of the coordinating activities by the UN merely as forms of job creation and “occupational therapy”. They look for every opportunity to make a mockery of it. They are in particular frustrated by the fact that all these high overhead costs further deplete mine clearance funds and diminish their resources. It is a biased and cynical statement but nevertheless makes a valid point, leading therefore to quoting in its entirety this NGO perspective on coordination activities.

“The answer is simple. It often boils down to a lack of determination to get the job done – and that means a lack of determination by some of the people who run “Mine Action”. Instead managers, whether they be UN, government and even non-government, seem content to encourage millions of dollars being spent NOT on mine clearance, but yet more endless working groups, workshops, information management systems, symposia, strategies, studies, standards, plans, policies, portfolios, principled programming, processes, procedures, quality management, mainstreaming, methodologies, measurables, monitoring, quality control, consultations, consultants, courses, conferences, capacity building – and the full range of outreaches, outputs, inputs, indicators, impacts, intervention logic, linkages, gendering, thematics, logical frameworks, normative frameworks, blockages, goals and super-goals. Oh, of course, we accept that some of these are important, but Europe was cleared with

³⁸⁴ Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy, First published Tue Aug 28, 2001; substantive revision Tue Dec 6, 2005, Internet. Available at <http://plato.stanford.edu/entries/common-knowledge/>, accessed on 18 January 2007

³⁸⁵ MASLEN, S. (2004). *Mine action after Diana: Progress in the struggle against landmines*, p.173

³⁸⁶ Mail HALO Trust of 6 September 2002, Guy Willoughby, forwarded to the relevant permanent missions at the UN

³⁸⁷ Agenda Item 28: Assistance in Mine Action, Norwegian explanation of vote 16 December 2002

simple planning by experienced practitioners, followed by action. It was “the product, not the process” that was important. Mine clearance is not difficult – it has been described as a mix of gardening and archaeology – in fact not really much more difficult than digging up potatoes or cassava – just more dangerous and requiring strict procedures.”³⁸⁸

b. Deductions

1. Key points

- ☞ The lack of coordination of mine action efforts is a problem at all political levels.
- ☞ The medium politics of mine action can be largely associated with institutional and/or organizational politics.
- ☞ Competition for resources and turf battles amongst *medium* politics actors, can hinder effective mine action coordination and cooperation. In addition, the requirements for mine action coordination evolve continuously during the theoretic lifecycle of a mine action programme
- ☞ Mine action coordination, either by a designated body or by existing planning and coordination structures, is necessary to ensure that resources are spent according to needs and priorities, as well to ensure quality assurance, and to avoid duplication of efforts.
- ☞ UNMAS as a focal point for UN mine action has been criticized for lack of institutional leadership and coordination of other UN actors. Discussing coordination issues can be simplified when subdivided along *high/medium* politics (international + UN/NGOs) and medium/low politics (UN/NGOs + national).
- ☞ Strong mine action coordination mechanism are of particular value in situations where donors and operators converge in large numbers in order to safeguard solid mine action prioritization.
- ☞ Global and thematic plans and priorities need to be well-coordinated in order that decisions are made with adequate information concerning national priorities and other donor plans and programmes. Optimal prioritization of efforts is the recurrent theme throughout effective coordination of mine action in order to have the most effective use of available resources.
- ☞ The further refining of the definitions of the different political levels of mine action has brought out the particular usefulness of describing the characteristics and dynamics of the medium politics; and this is associated with institutional and NGO politics.
- ☞ Stag Hunt game provides considerable explanatory value of coordination problems within the mine action community. Coordination between the different actors are hindered by *trust dilemmas* and competition for funding, in particular between the UN and (I)NGOs.
- ☞ Depending on the pay-off structure, certain actors will consistently look for better coordination and cooperation, others will seek to *dis-coordinate* since they attach higher utilities at maintaining their full independence, control, ownership, identity and many other possible reasons which could outweigh the expected benefits from cooperation.

2. Possible indicators and criteria

The goal, indicators and evaluation criterion reflect the basic requirement for States that mine action needs to take place in a coordinated fashion in order to have the best effects and avoid duplication of efforts.

Goal	Indicator
Optimal mine action cooperation and coordination	Institutional, intersessional or ad hoc mechanism in place to facilitate coordination and cooperation between the different political levels of mine action
	Having a well functioning focal point in the UN dealing with mine action
	Adequate development and integration of mine-action standards in all programmes
National and regional capacity-building	Level of effectiveness of national/regional capacity building efforts

Criterion 35	Level of cooperation and coordination of mine action activities
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³⁸⁸ Landmines and Sex, Statement given by Guy Willoughby, HALO Trust, on behalf of the NGO Perspective, Internet. Available at http://www.icbl.org/layout/set/print/news/summit_update_2/landmines_and_sex

R. Preamble Paragraph 18: Response to emergency mine action requirements

Noting with appreciation the finalization of an emergency response plan by the United Nations to respond to emergency mine-action requirements,

a. Analysis

1. Emergency response: humanitarian disaster relief versus peacekeeping operations

If there is a functional government, then a UN emergency response may be requested by the respective authorities of the mine-affected country. According to relevancy, this could be undertaken by the Special Representative of the Secretary-General or the UN Resident Coordinator or Humanitarian Coordinator. In case of the establishment of a new UN peacekeeping mission, it could as well be by the Head of the Planning Team. UNMAS is responsible for UN emergency mine action and coordinates the development and implementation of an *Emergency or Rapid Response Plan*. This takes place in cooperation with other agencies, often as part of a broader emergency response plan or needs analysis. The UN normally has the initial resources and staff on standby to respond at relative short notice. However, there are substantial differences between peacekeeping and humanitarian emergencies.³⁸⁹

The previously mentioned “Inter Agency Consultancy Group” (IACG) will normally approve the UN coordinated response. In case of Iraq, a system of *UN Flash Appeals* included a request for more than \$13 million for mine-action activities for a six-month period.³⁹⁰ This system of flash appeals has its particular challenges, in particular in case of humanitarian emergencies, since it is still based on voluntary contributions. Conversely, in case of peacekeeping operations, mine action could be funded through the assessed peacekeeping budget as part of the peacekeeping mandate and take place through either a military or civilian capability. Hence, the burden-sharing mechanisms are substantially different between humanitarian emergencies and peacekeeping operations.

2. Crisis management challenges

The Rapid Response Planning (RRP) process relies on cooperation and joint planning with mine action and other partners. It builds on the capabilities of organizations already in-country and agrees to a response accordingly, ensuring the integration of individual plans in order to achieve an overall strategy. Coordination with NGOs working in mine action occurs at this level. On the one hand, the emergency response and flash appeals often benefit from intervening in affected countries or regions which temporarily enjoy international media focus. On the other hand, time frames could be too short to set up or expand a mine action programme capable to deal with a significant or complex emergency. There are multiple challenges, but it is likely that obtaining or sharing critical information together with cooperation and coordination will be at the forefront.

“Information has been poorly coordinated, and although you can access, for instance, statistics on a given town or village via the municipality, there is no central mechanism to provide a global view of the different projects going on in Lebanon at any given time, said Rabih Bashour, coordinator for the relief and reconstruction committee [...].”³⁹¹

³⁸⁹ UN Publication. (2004) Mine Action Programming Handbook. Internet. Available at www.mineaction.org, accessed on 2 May 2005

³⁹⁰ Flash appeal was launched on 28 March 2003. A particularly high level of land mine contamination is reported in northern Iraq and along the borders with Iran, Kuwait, Jordan, Syria and Turkey. There is also a range of Unexploded Ordnance (UXO) - including cluster munitions - throughout Iraq. In the event of large-scale air and ground attacks by coalition forces, there may be further mine contamination and an additional threat from UXO and cluster munitions. In areas where there is landmine and UXO contamination the work of the humanitarian agencies will be constrained, if not impossible. http://www.mineaction.org/docs/1130_.asp

³⁹¹ LEBANON: Poor data limits aid work; IRIN-OCHA, Internet. Available at http://www.irinnews.org/report.asp?ReportID=56833&SelectRegion=Middle_East

All these challenges have already been extensively addressed elsewhere in the analysis. Coordinating the allocation of resources at a global level amongst different mine-affected countries has been repeatedly flagged to be a particularly challenging area. Determining and allocating resources within a mine-affected country appears to be less complicated once a programme is fully up and running. However, during emergency situations, valuable time can be lost to establish “well-established prioritization mechanisms” and to generate the necessary emergency funding. In this regard, the mine action community is increasingly aware that the global landmine problem has to compete more than ever before with other sectors and that emergency aspects of the global landmine “crisis” benefit less from the media spotlight they used to have.

“These disturbing trends may be the result of attention and resources being diverted to other more visible crises, following the tendency of the international community to react to humanitarian needs only when they reach extraordinary proportions. In a sense, this is the way the Convention came about – in response to a global humanitarian crisis gaining the attention of the world media. Although the landmine crisis is not as visible today as it was ten years ago, it has lost *none* of its urgency.”³⁹²

b. Deductions

1. Key points

- ☞ UNMAS is responsible for leadership in emergency mine action. Their Rapid Response Planning process relies on highly effective cooperation and joint planning; and, requires the three political levels of mine action to operate in a concerted manner. In this regard, the system of “*flash appeals*” is regularly used to mobilize resources at short-notice. UN emergency mine action is most important in case of failed or fragile States.
- ☞ Emergency mine action can benefit from being in the media spotlight, enjoy sufficient funding, but suffer from a lack of cooperation and coordination, information shortage and absence of a well-established prioritization mechanism. Once beyond emergency relief, consultative processes, cooperation and coordination may be improved but prioritization of mine action will remain challenging throughout.
- ☞ In terms of emergency response capabilities the link to the game theoretic concept of *best response* is obvious as it is the chosen strategy which minimizes in this case most speedily the maximum loss caused by the emergency. Similar to previous analysis of risk and threat related aspects of mine action, the element of nature can be adopted as the virtual other player.

2. Possible indicators and criteria

Goal	Indicator
Optimal emergency response capability	Level of effectiveness of the emergency response; capability to minimize the maximum loss

Criterion 36	Establishment of adequate emergency response capacities for mine action
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³⁹² Same ICRC statement of 28 November 2005: How to ensure progress for the Nairobi Action Plan, Statement by Dr. Jacques Forster, Vice-President of the ICRC. Sixth Meeting of the States Parties to the Convention on the Prohibition of the Use, Stockpiling, Production and Transfer of Anti-Personnel Mines and on their Destruction, Zagreb, 28 November 2005

S. Preamble Paragraph 19: Mine action coordination centres and trust funds

Welcoming the various established mine-action coordination centres, as well as the creation and existence of international trust funds for mine-action activities,

a. Analysis

1. Mine action coordination at a national level

This paragraph only adds the *national* dimension to the *international* coordination and cooperation issues comprehensively covered in preamble paragraph 17. *Mine action coordination centres* are largely situated at the low politics level but are strongly interfaced with the medium politics. They can operate either under UN auspices or with full *national* ownership. The latter is most desirable as it is a possible indication of a functional government taking responsibility of their national landmine problem. In that case, a national mine action authority, largely an inter-ministerial body, will conduct all oversight of mine action. This authority gives the strategic guidance to the mine action centre regarding the day-to-day coordination of the programme.

2. The key capacity-building role of UNDP and UNICEF, coordinated by UNMAS

The establishment of national mine action coordination centres is a critical national capacity building effort. Capacity building is essential to achieve long-term sustainability, national management and coordination of mine action. A broad range of governments and organizations are therefore involved in mine action capacity development, including the UN, the UN Office for Project Services (UNOPS), Cranfield University Mine Action and the Geneva International Centre for Humanitarian Demining (GICHD). Over the past few years, UNDP's programmes in mine action have increased due to widespread awareness of the value and importance of capacity building strategies for dealing with the long-term consequences of landmines and ERW. UNOPS acts as a general service provider for many of these programmes, and the work is coordinated by UNMAS to ensure an integrated UN response. UN Member States are regularly requested to support the activities of those centres and the trust funds established for the coordination of assistance in mine action and the promotion of national ownership.³⁹³

Although capacity development is not considered a core component of mine action, the International Mine Action Standards deal with capacity building.³⁹⁴ It recognizes that a National Mine Action Authority has to be in place to ensure political oversight and responsibility. Another very important element is national legislation. The GICHD published in 2003 is a guide for developing national mine action legislation.³⁹⁵ The advantages of regulating mine action through national legislation are:

- (1) Wide involvement of the national parliament and government agencies in the development of the law.
- (2) Strong mandates, roles and responsibilities for the mine action coordination centres.
- (3) Large degree of transparency in the planning and tasking of mine action.
- (4) Better and direct accountability to donors.

³⁹³ UN Document A/RES/58/127, operational paragraph 19 from UN resolution on 'Assistance in mine action', Internet. Available at <http://www.un.org/Depts/dhl/resguide/r58.htm>, accessed on 20 July 2005

³⁹⁴ IMAS 7.10, Internet. Available at www.mineactionstandards.org/imas.htm, accessed on 22 March 2006

³⁹⁵ Internet. Available at www.gichd.org, accessed on 17 July 2005

3. Trust funds

The UN Voluntary Trust Fund (VTF) for Assistance in Mine Action was initially established to assist affected countries in the assessment of their landmines/ERW problem.³⁹⁶ However quickly evolved towards providing resources for all types of mine action activities and programmes, especially in situations where other funding is not immediately available. Therefore, it is of utmost importance to finance emergency mine action in case flash appeals do not immediately provide the necessary resources. Since its inception, the VTF has received contributions amounting to more than 300 million US dollar. This is considerable, taking into account the *credit game* requirements of many countries before they engage in funding. To accommodate this, donor countries maintain a high level of control and visibility after they contributed to the VTF. Many contributions come together with a specific earmarking on how, where and when financial contributions can be used. This leads inevitably to a quite rigid use of the UN VTF with limited leeway to use funding in a flexible manner if the requirements and/or priorities suddenly change.

As mentioned in the analysis of preamble paragraph 17, UNDP and UNICEF mobilize their own resources for mine action.³⁹⁷ They have separate trust funds and mechanisms to mobilize resources but that does not detract from the competition for funding.

b. Deductions

1. Key points

- ☞ National mine action coordination centres are critical for a functional government to take up its full responsibility and exercise its national authority over a mine action programme.
- ☞ Independent mobilization of resources by UN agencies can lead to competition.
- ☞ The UN VTF and UNDP Trust Fund are solid funding mechanisms, their good use solely depends on voluntary funding by UN Member States which prefer multilateral above bilateral funding of mine action.

2. Possible indicators and criteria

The below criteria and indicators are largely a repetition of what has been deduced from preceding preamble paragraphs but with a focus on coordination and funding mechanism at a national level.

Goal	Indicator
Having well established mine action coordination centres	Having effective cooperation and coordination in mine action
	Level of national capacity building
Having well established international trust funds for mine action	Financial contributions to trust funds

Criterion 37	Management and planning capabilities of national mine action coordination centres
Criterion 38	Having established adequate fund raising mechanisms

³⁹⁶ The UN VTF was established by the UN Secretary-General on 30 November 1994

³⁹⁷ Between August 2003 and August 2004, UNDP raised more than \$70 million. About \$30 million of that amount was raised through the organization's Thematic Trust Fund for Crisis Prevention and Recovery. Internet. Available at www.mineaction.org, accessed on 10 July 2006

T. Preamble Paragraph 20: The integration of mine action in peacekeeping operations

Noting with satisfaction the inclusion in the mandates of several peacekeeping operations of provisions relating to mine-action work carried out under the direction of the Department of Peacekeeping Operations of the Secretariat, in the context of such operations,

a. Analysis

1. Inclusion in UN peacekeeping mandates

It is of critical importance that ceasefire agreements and peace accords properly address mine action concerns and provide an appropriate framework for the effective initiation and implementation of mine action activities. Too often in the past, essential mine/ERW-related issues have either not been addressed at all in cease-fire agreements and peace accords or addressed too late and inadequately. In the worst cases, they have been addressed in a way that did not take account of technical realities and raised unrealistic expectations, delaying the establishment of proper and effective mechanisms for the implementation of mine action programs.³⁹⁸ Fortunately, in situations where landmines are a significant obstacle to the resumption of normal life and reconstruction, UN resolutions, cease-fire agreements and peace accords increasingly consider a multidisciplinary mine action approach and facilitate effective international cooperation and coordination.

The mine action programmes in Eritrea and Ethiopia benefit from being part of the first UN peacekeeping mission which formally included in its mandate provisions related to mine action. It specifically asked for the UN Mission to: “*coordinate and provide technical assistance for humanitarian mine action activities in the Temporary Security Zone (TSZ) and areas adjacent to it.*”³⁹⁹ More recent examples are the UN resolutions related to UN peacekeeping operations in the Democratic Republic of the Congo (MONUC) and the previously referred to UN resolution 1701 (UNIFIL) to request the transfer of the maps of minefields in the previously Israel held occupied territory in Lebanon.

Recent conflicts and peace processes generally require an even more significant presence of mine action tasks in peacekeeping mandates, especially with reference to ERW. Therefore, specific guidelines have been developed which have been made widely available to United Nations mediators, moderators and Special Representatives of the Secretary-General. These guidelines request all parties to the conflict to incorporate provisions on mine action, where relevant, in ceasefire and peace agreements or other relevant arrangements.⁴⁰⁰

2. Normative peacekeeping/building aspects and implications for UN mandates

The integration of mine action in peacekeeping operations needs to be measured in light of its *conflict restoration* and *confidence building* effects.⁴⁰¹ The related normative aspects gained significant political impetus following the increasing interest of the UN Security Council Members to incorporate mine action in the mandated tasks of a UN peacekeeping/building operation. A number of elements need to be in place to make this part of a successful post-conflict restoration process. It requires the exchange of all relevant information on minefields and the parties to the conflict should commit themselves to actively supporting the identification, marking and eventual clearance of all minefields. The population at risk needs to be actively identified in order to benefit

³⁹⁸ The Paris Peace Agreement for Cambodia of 23 October, 1991 had for example only limited provisions regarding the gigantic landmine and ERW problem, lacking an holistic mine action approach.

³⁹⁹ UN Document, S/RES/1320 of 15 September 2000

⁴⁰⁰ UN Document, A/RES/58/127, operational paragraph 14 from UN resolution on ‘Assistance in mine action’, Internet. Available at <http://www.un.org/Depts/dhl/resguide/r58.htm>, accessed on 20 July 2005

⁴⁰¹ Which is also highlighted in operative paragraph 15 of the UN resolution – see Annex A

from the prompt development of MRE programmes. The peace accord should imply a total ban on mines, especially anti-personnel mines. For governments, this commitment should involve accession to the MBT. For non-State Actors, this could involve signing the “Deed of Commitment”. Based on realistic timeframes, the parties to the conflict should commit themselves to the total destruction of all their stockpiles of landmines. When necessary, the parties should agree to international assistance through the UN or other organizations, to facilitate mine action activities, in particular during the initial implementation phase of the peace agreement.

3. The political vulnerabilities of mine action for peacekeeping/building

One of the main challenges lies in the dramatic change of former *combatants* into *humanitarian actors*. Although examples in the field show the potential, this transition process needs to offer the right incentives in order to positively influence their choice for a new existence.

“Moreover, by encouraging potentially undesirable people to profit from reconstruction work, mine action funding can provide an incentive to engage with the peace process. [...]. Moreover, while acknowledging that mine action can hardly “change dreadful people who carry guns into peace loving humanitarians,” it is “not a bad transition” for demobilized soldiers, who have “been associated with weaponry and explosives ... and [are] used to rough work in the field.”⁴⁰²

It also raises the question whether a conflict is possible in a mine clearance operation between the political objective of peacebuilding and the humanitarian objective of mine action:

“[...] according to the context, *mine action can be more oriented towards saving lives or towards peacebuilding or towards development*. [...] There were isolated cases where ex-combatants working as deminers went back to war. On the other hand mine action has a *confidence-building* aspect: *it sends a clear message to the community that the signs of war are being removed*.”⁴⁰³

If the mine action prioritization process itself gets politicized, then a particularly complex situation exists. In a post-conflict environment the priorities of the government should be acknowledged; however in ongoing or simmering conflicts, there have been situations where the UN has not responded to requests by governments simply because there was no access to the warring factions. Sometimes it is even outside UN control if NGOs who have other views decide to work only in rebel controlled areas. This highlights again the importance to engage non-state actors through the Geneva Call and Deeds of Commitment to respect and to adhere to humanitarian norms. The unfortunate few examples (Sudan) still provide concrete evidence where mine action and peacebuilding come together. Without the political goodwill of the parties involved, there should be no illusions if any of the desired peacebuilding results will be achieved.

“The [mine action] program is unique and very advanced compared to the other dimensions of the peace process. [...] (SPLM) called the program an excellent confidence building measure: the population is being prepared through concrete steps for the moment when the peace-agreement will be signed. [...] (UNMAS) explained that MA has three facets in Sudan: (1) peacebuilding; (2) promotion of the goodwill between the parties; (3) promotion of the peace process.”⁴⁰⁴

Preamble paragraph 13, which refers to the immediate halt of new landmine deployments by non-State actors, has interesting implications for mine action for peace. Involving non-State actors, previously engaged in mine laying, in clearing the landmines can be part of a DDR-process whilst aiming at confidence and peacebuilding. Communication between all parties and leadership by an independent actor or NGO may facilitate the process. However, caution has been expressed in relation to conditioning mine action advances on advances in the peace process: if confidence-

⁴⁰² Bosnia’s Political Landmines, Published in September 2006 by Landmine Action, 89 Albert Embankment, London SE1 7TP, www.landmineaction.org, page 13

⁴⁰³ MASG newsletter, 2004, Internet. Available at <http://www.mineaction.org/overview.asp?o=144>, accessed on 12 July 2005

⁴⁰⁴ Ibid

building measures fail, they may *undermine confidence rather than build it*. Hence, caution is advised when stating what constitutes “success” so as not to raise expectations excessively when dealing with mine action in a sensitive conflict situation. One key practice to facilitate mine action activities in difficult situations is transparency on behalf of all actors. Humanitarian actors need to be transparent towards both NSAs and the concerned state(s) in order to avoid security risks and accusations of “spying”. By being open and clear about their activities, humanitarian actors can convince the parties of their neutrality. NSAs and the concerned state(s) also need to be transparent towards humanitarian actors in order to maximize the benefits from mine action, as restrictions on information sharing may cause delays or lead to the cancellation of operations.

4. Funding of “mine action for peace”

Some sceptical voices in the mine action community had initially understated the growing role of *mine action for peace*. Nowadays, with mine action embedded in several UN peacekeeping operations, it has proven to be more than just another effort to reinvigorate the support from donors. Whenever mine action becomes an active part of a UN peacekeeping/building mandate, a much more reliable funding of mine action is warranted. Contrary to voluntary contributions a relatively fair and just system is installed when mine action is financed through the UN peacekeeping budget whereby burden-sharing takes place according to the agreed UN peacekeeping scale of assessments. Therefore, the game theoretic particularity of this paragraph leads to the previously discussed *Diner’s Dilemma* but whereby UN Member States agree, through the UN Security Council, to contribute through a burden-sharing mechanism according to the UN scale of assessed contributions.⁴⁰⁵ This implies that again the United States, Japan, Germany, France and the United Kingdom are paying approximately 80% of the mine action costs.

b. Deductions

1. Key points

- ☞ Mine action for peace or for peacekeeping or peacebuilding purposes can become politicised, especially when the conflict is not fully terminated or in absence of a comprehensive peace agreement.
- ☞ After mine action for humanitarian purposes, and to create socio-economic benefits, mine action for peacekeeping and peacebuilding purposes is increasingly recognized.
- ☞ Peacekeeping/building effects of mine action are *largely intangible*.
- ☞ Funding for “mine action for peace” as part of a UN peacekeeping mandate and/or DDR programme is significantly more transparent, predictable and long-term.
- ☞ Mine action for peace is very vulnerable to the (political) goodwill of the conflicting parties.

2. Possible indicators and criteria

Below criteria and indicators focus on the confidence building effects and DDR in post-conflict settings, either as part of peacekeeping or peacebuilding efforts.

Goal	Indicator
Have an effective inclusion of mine action in (UN) peacekeeping/building operations	Solid mine action guidelines for ceasefire and peace agreements
	Confidence-building measures through incorporating mine action in DDR programmes

Criterion 40	Mine action integrated in DDR programmes
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⁴⁰⁵ The UN scale of assessed contributions is based on a variety of factors but is largely correlated with the Gross Domestic Products of UN Member States.

U. Preamble Paragraph 21: Mine victim assistance

Commending the action taken by donor and recipient Governments, the United Nations system, regional organizations, the International Committee of the Red Cross and non-governmental organizations to coordinate their efforts and seek solutions to the problems related to the presence of mines and other unexploded ordnance, as well as their assistance to victims of mines,

a. Analysis

1. Mine victim assistance

Victim assistance has been addressed earlier in regard the socio-economic impact and high accompanying medical costs. Victim assistance activities cover the full spectrum from emergency medical care to physical rehabilitation, psychological support, and social and economic reintegration. *Within* the UN system, UNMAS works closely with the World Health Organisation and other UN entities, in particular UNICEF. *Outside* the UN system, ICRC is the most important partner.⁴⁰⁶ Victim assistance is also a MBT obligation.⁴⁰⁷

2. UN policy on the scope of mine action in victim assistance

The United Nations has issued an expanded policy on the scope of mine action in victim assistance. This policy calls for effective and coordinated response of mine action centres and organizations in victim assistance, especially in the areas of data collection, advocacy, planning and coordination, community relations and support to service delivery. For further normative modelling, a best mine action response highly depends on the health infrastructure in place. It is, therefore, important that this is taken into account in light of prioritization of mine action.

b. Deductions

1. Key points

- ☞ The UN mine victim assistance policy provides solid strategic guidance for victim assistance.
- ☞ The available medical support can influence prioritization of mine action and give, for example, higher priority to areas where medical support is largely insufficient to threat mine accidents.

2. Possible indicators and criteria

Rational players will seek a best response in terms of minimizing the possible mine victim losses. The ability of local or national health care systems to treat mine victims is, therefore, a crucial element, reflected in the strategic choices, criteria, goals and targets below.

Goal	Indicator
Optimal assistance to mine victims	Level of medical support to mine victims
	Socio-economic impact and cost of medical care

Criteria 41	Ability of health care systems to provide assistance to mine victims
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⁴⁰⁶ E-mine, Internet. Available at www.mineaction.org, accessed on 1 August 2006.

⁴⁰⁷ Article 6 of the MBT states that “Each State Party in a position to do so shall provide assistance for the care and rehabilitation, and social and economic reintegration, of mine victims and for mine awareness programs.”

V. Preamble Paragraph 22: Public awareness of the landmine problem

Welcoming the **role of the Secretary-General in increasing public awareness** of the problem of landmines,

a. Analysis

1. Framing of the global landmine problem

The *public awareness* envisaged in this paragraph should not be confused with any of the previously discussed mine awareness training or mine risk education. It entails every effort, and in this context the efforts of Secretary-General Ban Ki Moon, in promulgating widespread knowledge on the global landmine problems. The UN Secretary-General has been a central anchor and actor in promoting mine action throughout the regular publication of UN progress reports on mine action activities, together with the development of UN mine action strategies and policies. UN Member States have requested those reports, from the first UN mine action resolution in 1993 until the present one. The first requested versions of the UN mine action reports were rather restrictive and were primarily focused on the effects of landmines from armed conflicts, with an emphasis on how the role of the UN could be strengthened regarding mine clearance related activities. In recent UN reports, a clear shift can be observed towards more strategic issues, including public awareness. However, a distinction needs to be made between the current global response to the landmine problem and the awareness of it. As stated below, raising public awareness is just one of the many mine action aspects which requires further improvement.

“The landmine problem is still far from being adequately addressed. Despite impressive progress, key challenges lie ahead. Vast tracts of valuable land continue to be plagued by landmine and ERW contamination. Thousands of people continue to fall victim to landmines each year, while medical, rehabilitation and full re-integration services remain woefully inadequate. Many countries have yet to join the Ottawa Convention, and coordination among mine-affected States, donors, the United Nations and civil-society organizations needs further improvement. In addition, the mine action community needs to identify creative and effective ways to further raise public awareness of the issue.”⁴⁰⁸

Apart from the UN Secretary-General, other well-known personalities in the public domain contribute extensively to public awareness, e.g., the President of Switzerland, Queen Noor, and Her Highness Princess Astrid of Belgium. Through Adopt-a-Minefield and HALO Trust, Heather Mills and Sir Paul McCartney have been important advocates for mine clearance and a total ban. None of these public personalities, however, could achieve exposure generated by *Princess Diana*.⁴⁰⁹ So many years later, her death is still regarded by the mine action community as a significant blow to the global advocacy effort and fundraising efforts.⁴¹⁰

“The death of Princess Diana meant that anti-landmine activists lost their most visible advocate. Yet while the issue may seem to be on the global backburner, the problem of unexploded ordnance remains as acute as ever. Millions of mines from wars both past and present remain scattered across 83 countries, with 15,000 to 20,000 killed or maimed by them every year.”⁴¹¹

With a hugely successful advocacy campaign, she was capable of

Fig. II.30: One of the most published visits of Princess Diana of mine victims (Mine action programme in Angola)

⁴⁰⁸ AQA, S. (2005). Mine Action: Success and Challenges. *Journal of Mine Action*, Issue 9.1, MAIC - James Madison University, Washington DC

⁴⁰⁹ Internet. Available at www.martinfrost.ws/htmlfiles/diana2.html

⁴¹⁰ IRIN, Internet. Available at <http://www.irinnews.org/webspecials/HMA/intBarber.asp>, Interview of Martin Barber, 2004

⁴¹¹ POLIER, A. (2004, December 3) 'It can be done', *Newsweek*

bringing the global landmine crisis into peoples living rooms, aiding the NGO community in its compelling pressure on governments to ban landmines.

The usage of the term “*framing*” in the heading of this section is chosen purposely and the phenomenon requires more in-depth analysis. Frames form a kind of platform or system to raise public awareness. Like the International Campaign to Ban Landmines (ICBL), a solid framing system needs to be built up over time. Tellingly, in this regard the long-term effort involves strong moral and ethic frames, not just communicative frames. Although very direct, *communicative* framing involves only the lowest level of framing in terms of impact the framing effort could have. *Moral* or *ethic* frames are often the real carriers of the message. Based on ethic frames, ICBL balances *negative* campaigning (against landmine users and the disastrous effects) in the context of *positive* campaigning (advocating the ideal of a mine free world).

Correct or *unbiased* framing of the landmine problem is then again a complex issue on its own. The Landmine Monitor has been exemplary in recording the essential facts of the problem on a global scale and it is a most important publication for the ICBL to *frame* this global problem whilst targeting a multilayered audience, including strong opponents of a total ban on landmines. Figure II.31⁴¹² and II.32 are just two ICBL examples which illustrate the use of skilled framing methods. The ICBL Landmine Monitor is to extensively support their campaigning efforts. This inevitably influences the objectivity of its factual reporting as it is generally written by researchers who belong to the strongest advocates of the MBT. This is, however, limited bias compared to possible manipulation by funding-hungry players. This phenomenon has direct links to certain game theoretic principles and is well captured in the following one sentence:

Fig. II.31: Example of catch phrases in support of framing methods by ICBL

“While decision makers are trying to manipulate the environment, their environment is trying to manipulate them.”⁴¹³

Catch phrases have been cited together with effective awareness raising efforts. Also recurrent exaggerations of landmine contamination and overstated numbers of mine victims have been briefly addressed. For example, although most tragic, the picture below was accompanied with incoherent and significantly inflated numbers of mine accidents and landmines deployed. This type of *biased framing* has only one purpose: overstate the problem to obtain competitive advantage over other sectors and get more mine action funding. Often the UN is brought into the equation to increase the credibility of the message.

According to the UN, Afghanistan is one of the top three most-mined countries on the planet. About 200,000 civilians have died and 400,000 have been disabled in mine incidents in Afghanistan. Approximately 6,000 more will lose their lives or limbs every year in the war battered country due to mine incidents, says a report issued by the United Nations Office for Coordination of Humanitarian Assistance to Afghanistan-mine clearance programme (UNOCHA). Afghanistan is infested with 10 Million anti-personnel mines ready to explode the moment anyone stepped on them. In Afghanistan alone, about 20 innocent civilians including children and women, daily fall victim to mines, half of whom lose their lives due to lack of medical facilities. Due to the presence of mines, access has been denied to more than 488 square kilometres of land, including agricultural fields, irrigation canals roads and residential areas. Over 30% mine victims in Afghanistan are children. The legacy of that long war also included 750,000 amputees.⁴¹⁴

Fig. II.33: Framing bias in representing landmine facts by national NGOs

⁴¹² Internet. Available at <http://www.menstuff.org/logos/landmines3.JPG> accessed on 18 January 2007

⁴¹³ MORTON, D. (1997). *Game Theory: A Non-technical Introduction*, Dover Publications, p.6

⁴¹⁴ Internet. Available at <http://www.rawa.org/image4.htm> accessed on 19 January 2007, RAWA is the oldest political/social organization of Afghan women struggling for peace, freedom, democracy and women's rights in Afghanistan since 1977.

Framing theory and the concept of *framing bias* suggests that how something is presented, the “*frame*”, largely influences the strategic choices people or actors make. The relationship between framing theory and game theory inevitably relates to a larger belief system. Hence, effects of framing are to be understood within the larger *belief* system, linked to strategic choices and solution concepts or equilibriums. To limit the effects of *framing bias*, significant aspects are the amount of information or data and the type of response options available. Indeed, similar scenarios in mine-affected nations may lead to different assessments, which may affect how a framed landmine problem is interpreted and how a best response is formulated.

Figure II.32 and II.33 illustrate how young children injured by mine accidents are systematically used in advocacy websites or on the cover of the Landmine Monitor Report, despite the majority of mine victims in many countries being male adults.⁴¹⁵ For example, 90% of the 2245 mine victims in Afghanistan during 2002-2004 were male with only 17% younger than 14.⁴¹⁶ Conversely, the example below illustrates how norm building has been influenced through skilful *reframing* the military doctrine on the usage of landmines. In order to “*de-stigmatize*” it, new norms are created such as: “*smart or non-persistent*” landmines:

“The new policy characterizes landmines according to their active lifespan (or “*persistence*” to use the government's term), and re-frames the focus from anti-personnel mines, which are comprehensively prohibited by the Mine Ban Treaty, to all types of landmines, both anti-personnel and anti-vehicle. Under the new policy, US forces will be able to use self-destructing and self-deactivating anti-personnel and anti-vehicle mines indefinitely, without any geographic restrictions. These are the types of mines designed to blow themselves up after a set period of time; they are often called “*smart*” mines, and the US now calls them “*non-persistent*” mines.”⁴¹⁷

Fig. II.32: Attention-grabbing Landmine Monitor Covers, from its inception consistently putting children mine victims at the forefront

Recent spikes in the use of IEDs against US troops in Iraq and Afghanistan have also been subject of sophisticated framing methods; it could be labelled *framing through statistics*. Both

⁴¹⁵ ICBL, Internet. Available at www.icbl.org, accessed on 10 November 2006

⁴¹⁶ Survey Action Centre. (2005). Afghanistan Landmine Impact Survey – Executive Summary, Washington

⁴¹⁷ USCBL 2004 Briefing on U.S. Landmine Policy. Delivered by Steve Goose, Director of Human Rights Watch Arms Division and Head of ICBL Delegation at Nairobi Summit on a Mine-Free World: First Five-Year Review Conference for the Mine Ban Treaty. Internet. Available at http://www.banminesusa.org/news/887_brief.htm, accessed on 12 December 2006

graphs shown below portray the devastating impact of roadside bombs. Figure II.34, which was used to dramatically frame the problem, is the *percentage* of US soldiers killed by IED; the right graph covers exactly the same period and facts.⁴¹⁸ However, the right graph provides both the number of US deaths and IED deaths. This provides better comparison and reference and is, therefore, less susceptible to biased interpretation.

Fig. II.34: Percentage of IED deaths

Fig. II.35: IED deaths versus total US deaths

Or better, IED casualties could be based on the unbiased or factual figures in the graph below.⁴¹⁹

Fig. II.36: Unbiased presentation of the dramatic increase of IED fatalities of US Forces operating in Iraq

Biased or even corrupt statistics have also been used to exaggerate the landmine problem in order to trigger more resource mobilization. However, its positive effects were short lived and the framing bias induced significant loss of confidence of the donor governments.⁴²⁰

“In their enthusiasm for the story, journalists have often sought out the most *sensational statistics* and, when these *no longer have the desired effect, have sometimes invented their own*. The first guesstimate for the

⁴¹⁸ BRYCE, R. (2006, February). *Man versus Mine*, The Atlantic Monthly, Internet. Available at <http://www.theatlantic.com/doc/prem/200601/explosives>, accessed on 7 April 2007

⁴¹⁹ Iraq coalition casualty count, Internet. Available at <http://icasualties.org/oif/IED.aspx>, accessed on 19 August 2007

⁴²⁰ In 1999, CMAC faced a stream of allegations of financial impropriety, nepotism, corruption and mismanagement, and as a result in 2000 donor contributions were withheld, forcing the downsizing of field operations. A strategy for reform and restructuring was developed and by the middle of 2001 CMAC’s situation stabilized, allowing the rebuilding of a consistent capacity. Landmine Monitor, 2004, Cambodia, available at <http://www.icbl.org/lm/2004/cambodia.html>, accessed on 20 July 2005

number of mines threatening communities began at 110 million and rose steadily with successive press articles. Multiplied by equally *ill-founded estimates of the cost and time required to clear each mine*, this yielded spectacular numbers for public consumption; apparently, thousands of years and billions of dollars would be needed. While the impressive statistics certainly grabbed headlines, the prospect of such an expensive and protracted campaign led many to *conclude that global demining was totally unachievable*, further reports stating that more mines were being laid than cleared just added to the *sense of hopelessness*.⁴²¹

One does not have to look far to find other examples on how deviation of customary UN practice and statistical analysis can have quite devastating effects and cause significant concern regarding the integrity of a community of experts. The past crisis and loss of confidence related to the well known United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) Human Development Index⁴²² serves as an excellent example. Using information “creatively”, as a way to influence national development strategies and thinking, should not go beyond what could be regarded as a healthy, innovative and thought provoking process. Indeed, the margin for mistakes or manipulation of data becomes particularly small if one tries enthusiastically to invade the political comfort zone of governments and their generally orthodox statisticians.

Apart from the hard facts on the ground, the aspect of the political effects of statistics is furthermore well captured in the following description of the mine-ban movement.

“[...] we note that the mine-ban movement did not seek to take control of traditional sources of state power [...] or the United Nations (as many environmental and human rights organizations do). Rather, it generated power by flooding global media with unsettling statistics and images and by using the internet and other technologies to build an extensive, trans-national coalition that could not be discounted, co-opted, or, ultimately, denied political space.”⁴²³

Further extrapolating the above to a highly technical domain as mine action, illustrates that ample possibilities exist to exploit the fact that either at government level or amongst mine action practitioners, the leadership is not, by and large, composed of technical data experts on mine action. Essentially, many of the information the mine action community presents, has to be taken on *trust*. There is hardly any scrutiny or distinction possible between information or statistics which are quite accurate and those which a professional statistical community would consider to be inappropriate, selective, and biased treatment of data to support certain positions. This phenomenon needs further study, especially in light of the advocacy role which the distribution of mine action related information fulfils.

In essence, a mix of game and frame theoretic characteristics is present in the *public awareness* domain of the politics of mine action: a message, an audience, a messenger, a medium, (choking) images, a context, and as highlighted, higher-level moral and ethic frames.⁴²⁴ The conditions that generally affect or constrain framing efforts are: the robustness, completeness, and thoroughness of the framing effort.⁴²⁵ The experts cited earlier in framing theory, Snow and

⁴²¹COLIN, K. (2004). *Demining: Enhancing the Process, Landmines and Human Security - International Politics and War's Hidden Legacy*. Albany: State University of New York Press

⁴²²In 1990, the UN system, through the UNDP, made an important foray into the global statistical arena with the publication of the first Human Development Report, a document that has since been published on an annual basis. The Human Development Index (HDI) is since then one of the more accepted indexes to quantify progress and deprivation and to give scale to crucial socio-economic phenomena that were not directly identifiable and measurable themselves. The inquiry by a group of experts which called for an unfit use of data and statistical inaccuracy, led to a “downgrading” of the HDI to merely a simplistic indicator which is not meant to be a statistically precise instrument but a tool for advocacy and for illustrating the desperate plight of the populations of particularly poor countries. WARD, M. 2004. Quantifying the World – UN Ideas and Statistics, United Nations Intellectual History Project, p.200-203

⁴²³MATTHEW, R. (2003). *The evolutionary dynamics of the movement to ban landmines*. Alternatives: Global, Local, Political

⁴²⁴George Lakoff, a Professor at UC Berkeley, who is most famous for his ideas about the centrality of metaphor to human thinking, political behaviour and society. He is particularly famous for his concept of the “embodied mind” which he has written about in relation to mathematics. In recent years he has applied his work to the realm of politics, exploring this in his books. His latest political work: *Don't Think of an Elephant! Know Your Values and Frame the Debate!* <http://linguistics.berkeley.edu/people/fac/lakoff.html>

⁴²⁵SNOW, D. and BENFORD, R. (1988). *Ideology, frame resonance, and participant mobilization*. *International Social Movement Research*, 1, 197-217.

Benford, identify three core framing tasks which influence decision-making and are essential to mobilize the different actors or advocates. The three tasks are: (1) *diagnostic framing* for the identification of a problem and assignment of blame; (2) *prognostic framing* to suggest solutions, strategies, and tactics to a problem, and (3) *motivational framing* that serves as a rationale for action. This framing concept is remarkably well understood and omnipresent in the mine action politics, exercised by both the advocates and opponents of a total ban on landmines. In its ultimate form framing efforts become part of an advocacy network. The mine action community, in particular ICBL, has been exemplary in this regard, and this will be further addressed in the following sections.

2. Framing and advocacy networks

The framing efforts of ICBL and national mine action programmes are also an essential part of connecting the high-medium-low politics of mine action. *Frame alignment* between different layers of actors is regarded as an important element in social mobilization or movement.⁴²⁶ When individual frames become linked in congruency, *frame alignment* occurs, producing “*frame resonance*”. This is key to the process of a group transitioning from one frame to another and has been particularly successful in the global movement to ban landmines. In framing theory they are analysed as “*transnational advocacy networks*”. The strength of the NGO community, and in particular ICBL, is its ability to encourage non-traditional international actors to mobilize information strategically and to persuade, pressure, and gain leverage over much more powerful organisations and State actors. These advocacy networks benefit considerably from the media as framing and pressure instruments, even in terms of increasing compliance with the MBT, which recalls the frequently cited *name & shame* tactics.

“The media seems to be playing an increasingly important part as a verification device, since violations of international agreements are considered to be news.”⁴²⁷

Interestingly, the MBT not only benefits but it is also an important part of the framing effort.

“Perhaps the [Mine Ban] treaty's greatest impact has been on public perception. Reports of mines now evoke images of legless veterans, of maimed children, of Diana in protective gear walking near a minefield in Angola.”⁴²⁸

In summary, the *mine action advocacy networks* not only try to influence policy outcomes, but they transform through framing the norms, terms and nature of the landmine debate.⁴²⁹ This process has many positive *frame resonance* and *alignment effects* between the different advocacy groups, including the impetus it provides to the mobilisation of resources for mine action.

“Advocacy networks are significant transnationally and domestically. By building new links among actors in Civil Societies, States, and international organisations, they multiply the channels of access to the international system. In such issue areas as the environment and human rights, they also make international resources available to new actors in domestic political and social struggles.”⁴³⁰

⁴²⁶ SNOW, D. and BENFORD, R. (1988). *Ideology, frame resonance, and participant mobilization. International Social Movement Research*, 1, 197-217.

⁴²⁷ HOVI, J. (1994), *Games, Threats and Treaties: understanding commitments in international relations*, Virginia, p.121

⁴²⁸ LEE MYERS, Steven (1999) *Diana's Dubious Legacy: Land-Mine Ban Has Trouble Getting Off the Ground*, Internet. Available at <http://www.nytimes.com/library/review/090599land-mines-review.html>, accessed on 10 November 2006

⁴²⁹ KECK, M. and SIKKINK, K. (1998). *Advocacy Networks in International Politics*, Cornell University Press, p.2

⁴³⁰ *Ibid* at 1

3. From framing theory to prospect theory

Prospect theory was developed by Tversky and Kahneman⁴³¹ to better understand the impact of framing effects on *decision-making under risk*.⁴³² Based on prospect theory, framing of the landmine problem can be further studied in terms of gains and losses. According to this theory, actors value a *certain* gain more than a *probable* gain with an equal or greater expected value; the opposite is true for losses. As illustrated in the figure II.37, gains and losses are evaluated from a subjective reference point. It is noticeably *S-shaped* and, as its *asymmetry* implies, given the same variation in absolute value, there is a bigger impact of losses than of gains, reflecting loss aversion. Or otherwise expressed, the displeasure associated with the loss is greater than the pleasure associated with the same amount of gains.

Fig. II.37: Impact of framing effects on decision-making under risk

According to this theory, the framing of the global landmine problem will more easily achieve the desired effects of increased resource mobilisation or global awareness if it focuses on the direct impact of the problem, rather than the future benefits of the solution. As highlighted above, actors respond differently, depending on whether their strategic choices and *set of beliefs* are framed in terms of gains or in terms of losses. More concretely, politics confronting decision makers with the hard facts of the human cost will have more effect (loss aversion) than potential socio-economic benefits. It makes the decision makers accountable for their strategic choice of “*doing nothing*”, implying a continuation of mine accidents. After all, it is a question of perception.

“[...] Framing effects are perceptual. They are analogous to optical illusions in terms of whether the glass is half full or whether the glass is half-empty. The framing effects occur when a subject makes a different choice depending on whether the same outcomes are phrased as though they were gains versus as though they were losses. Sometimes framing effects are confused with reflection effects.”⁴³³

Similar to the number of mine victims, numbers of war victims have important political or military strategic effects which are currently omnipresent in the media. They can even become a key benchmark for success or failure and erode most significantly public support.

“Hundreds of Iraqis are killed every week in sectarian violence which is threatening to pitch Iraq into full-scale civil war. A toll of 3,000 U.S. dead is likely to be an emotive one for Americans but it is less than the number of Iraqi civilians killed in a typical single month in the latter part of 2006, according to the most recent statistics from the United Nations.”⁴³⁴

Furthermore, the linkage between game, frame and prospect theory is closely related to previous references to discount effects whereby future payoffs are generally less valued than current payoffs. This also explains that campaigns can gradually erode with a decrease in *framing effects*. Campaigns, therefore, regularly need an impetus, which is also applicable for the effectiveness of

⁴³¹ Daniel Kahneman is currently a faculty member at Princeton University and a fellow at Hebrew University. Amos Tversky was a pioneer of cognitive science and a key figure in the discovery of systematic human cognitive bias and handling of risk.

⁴³² KAHNEMAN, D. and TVERSKY, A. (1979). *Prospect Theory: An Analysis of Decision under Risk*, *Econometrica*, p.263-291.

⁴³³ Framing and Framing Theory, Internet. Available at <http://www.csun.edu>, accessed on 1 November 2006

⁴³⁴ Bomb kills 2,999th U.S. soldier in Iraq, Reuters, 31 December 2006, Internet. Available at http://news.yahoo.com/s/nm/20061231/ts_nm/iraq_soldier_dc, accessed on 1 November 2006

the extensively discussed *name & shame campaigns* or creation of audience costs. The better framing efforts single out the actor(s) to be stigmatized, the less diluted the *framing effects* are, resulting in an increased audience engagement.

“We may have slowed the pace of destruction caused by anti-personnel mines, but we are still far from ending it. The true test of our commitment to this goal is whether we - governments, international agencies and civil society - *can remain sufficiently engaged outside of the public spotlight and in the absence of the sense of drama that characterised the early years of the mine ban campaign.*”⁴³⁵

b. Deductions

1. Key points

- ☞ Public awareness envisaged in this paragraph is very different from the mine awareness training or mine risk education discussed in preamble paragraph 5.
- ☞ The global landmine problem is still far from being adequately addressed; public personalities, in particular royal or presidential representatives, can play an essential role in raising public awareness.
- ☞ *Framing* is an unavoidable part of human communication in politics and *framing effects* are omnipresent in the media, in particular regarding the framing of global problems, in order to trigger a desired response.
- ☞ *Frame alignment* and *frame resonance* further characterizes the significant norm building effects whenever the high-medium-low politics act in harmony, ultimately resulting in a transnational advocacy network. Consecutively, framing can enhance compliance with treaties, as the media plays a vital role in the name & shame tactics in case of non-compliance. Hence, it reverts to the formerly identified “self-regulating” equilibriums regarding “voluntary” compliance with the CCW and MBT.
- ☞ *Framing bias*, by deliberately distorting the facts, is a frequent phenomenon in mine action to strengthen its position when competing for funding.
- ☞ According to *prospect theory*, confronting the international community with the impact of landmines compared to the benefits of mine action improves chances to mobilize more support.

2. Possible indicators and criteria

The objective of the paragraph - increasing public awareness - is straightforward, the deduction of concrete targets and indicators less so. There are numerous efforts, publications and reports which contribute to the public awareness of the landmine problem but it is a near impossible task trying to structure this in a manner it could be measured against a specific target. For completeness, however, the table below captures the essence of how effective public awareness could be qualified in a normative manner.

Goal	Indicator
Have optimal public awareness and correct framing of the global landmine problem	All types of reports such as the Landmine Monitor, Article 7 MBT reporting, CCW related reporting, UN reports on progress achieved regarding the implementation of the UN resolution on assistance in mine action and the implementation of the UN mine action strategy.
	Efforts related to the correct framing of the global landmine problem and adequate mine action response.

Criterion 42	Balanced and effective public awareness campaigns and objective framing of the landmine problem
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⁴³⁵ FORSTER, J. (2005). How to ensure progress for the Nairobi Action Plan, Sixth Meeting of the States Parties to the Convention on the Prohibition of the Use, Stockpiling, Production and Transfer of Anti-Personnel Mines and on their Destruction, Zagreb, 28 November 2005

II.3. Phase-I response to the research aim and research objectives

II.3.1. Main findings

The systematic deductions from each preamble paragraph provided a comprehensive summary of the relevant normative issues and game theoretic characteristics related to the politics of mine action. In this context, the conclusions shown below are limited to the main and overarching findings of Phase-I.

Finding 1: The politics of mine action portray a dynamic set of norms to reduce the *human cost, the socio-economic and peacekeeping impact of landmines and explosive remnants of war.*

The normative analysis of the politics of mine action illustrated how perceptions and norms related to the global landmine problem have significantly evolved over the last decade. Anti-personnel landmines belong now to one of the most stigmatized weapons compared to one of the most frequently used weapons between the beginning of the Second World War and the end of the Cold War. Nowadays, the politics have triggered - and are subject of - increasingly efficient and effective mine action efforts. Some of the most tangible outcomes are the assistance to humanitarian emergencies, the reduction of security risks and the enhancement of post-conflict reconstruction and development. In the international arena, several nations are taking steps to eliminate the threat posed by all types of landmines, including anti-vehicle mines and mines with sensitive fuses. The analysis of the preamble paragraphs of the UN resolution on assistance in mine action indicates its normative and prescriptive value on how to reduce the impact of this global scourge. In a variety of ways the resolution emphasizes how mine action should reduce human suffering and aid post-conflict restoration processes and development.

Although not inclusive, an equally productive dialogue and progress exist in venues related to the Mine Ban Treaty and the Convention of Certain Conventional Weapons. Within the CCW, the ratified protocol on explosive remnants of war and the ongoing discussions on mines other than anti-personnel mines are clear examples that dynamic normative processes in the field of disarmament can and do work. However, new norms such as *non-persistent* versus *persistent* mines, including efforts by the US to consider a ban on the transfer or trade of all persistent mines, indicate norm building may take unexpected turns the coming years. This is also noticeable regarding the utopian goal-setting of the MBT. Normative aspects related to terminology of a “*mine impact free*” world versus “*mine free*” were translated in substantially different effects on the politics and implementation measures involved, and this will be further addressed in the second finding. It highlighted in particular the unique complexities and competitive aspects of different groups of actors involved in developing a set of mine action norms as universal as possible.

Finding 2: A world “*free of the impact of mines*” gradually replaces the norm and utopian goal-setting of a “*mine free*” world.

Over the last years, there has been a gradual change in measuring the effects of mine action from *output maximization* (number of mines lifted, km² cleared, etc.) towards a focus on *impact minimization* of mines on populations. Measurement of effects increasingly takes a socio-economic angle; this is noticeable through the gradually improving Landmine Impact Surveys. The different and concrete ways of looking at impact include: direct effects of mines in killing and maiming, effects on local economies, livelihoods and poverty. An important function of measurement of socio-economic impact is to supply data for the improvement of prioritization and strategic planning of mine action operations. The usefulness hereof for mine action effectiveness and efficiency and overall resource allocation will be addressed in the following phases and in particular illustrated during the case-study.

The shift from the quasi unlimited resources required to materialize the one decade old “mine-free” norm towards mine “impact-free” is most significantly influencing the current political climate. The “mine free” status is becoming increasingly controversial with the economics being the most limiting factor. Norm building of “mine free” versus “impact free” has, therefore, been complex and blurred. Consecutively, the international community shifted its focus on impact reduction compared to “perfect” solutions. It would be sensible to prefer a treaty without utopian goal-setting of a “mine free” world, however, changing the current “*black-and-white politics*” towards the more nuanced concept of a landmine “impact free” world, may create more normative problems than solutions.

Whichever “*state of the world*” envisaged or aspired, it will highly depend on the medium to long-term efforts of affected governments to use affordable *indigenous* capacities, which is increasingly demonstrated by national mine action for development and mine action for peace and confidence building purposes. In most cases, those affected nations - even fragile governance structures - will seek to accelerate national capacity building and even use their own funds. Again, it can be observed that once the shift takes place from internationally to nationally led programmes, the norm generally moves simultaneously from “mine-free” to “impact-free”.

Finding 3: The “Ottawa model” became the norm building “guru” in disarmament politics.

The “Ottawa model” has been exemplary in terms of norm building, which has invited replicate behaviour with success in other disarmament domains based on (1) a strong partnership between governmental and non-governmental actors, and (2) process-wise independent from the largely paralyzed Disarmament Conference in Geneva.

For example, there has been NGO activism directed at the use of cluster munitions for more than thirty years, especially regarding their use in Lebanon, Afghanistan and during *Operation Desert Storm*. Through the example set by the Ottawa model, the current strengths of the existing advocacy networks and skilled framing efforts, unprecedented norm building progress has been achieved over the past three years. Cluster bombs are now as much stigmatized in their use as landmines, with similar name & shame campaigns.

This culminated in Belgium's decision to replicate its pioneering ban of landmines. Hence, Belgium became the first country in the world to outlaw the manufacture, trade, storage and use of cluster bombs in February 2006. The Israel-Lebanon conflict from July until August 2006 demonstrated another devastating use of cluster munitions which became the straw that broke the camel's back. Austria's decision to work for an international instrument on the weapon and the international controversy over the use and impact of cluster munitions was met by 48 governments in Oslo in February 2007 in order to reaffirm their commitment to a new international prohibition on the weapon.

Expert meetings on cluster munitions will be held in 2007 to clarify technical, legal, military and humanitarian aspects of the weapon with a view to developing an adequate international response against a weapon which is largely a redundant legacy of the Cold War. They were initially designed for use against mass Warsaw Pact army formations charging across the central European plain. But clearly, modern intrastate warfare takes place more than ever before in close vicinity of innocent people. Too many examples in history demonstrate tragically how difficult, if not impossible, it becomes to achieve military or strategic aims if large numbers of innocent civilians are killed in the process.

Finding 4: Achieving compliance with treaties: the unique strengths of a “self-help system”.

Repeatedly it was stated that the ultimate high politics of States are focusing on security and preservation. For decades landmines have played a crucial role in this regard for a large number of States. Today that number of States is only a fraction of what it used to be. However, States are as much “*security-seekers*” as ever before and will likely continue or restart their use of landmines if they are essential for their survival or to resist hegemony. For this reason, one of the important studied political elements in Phase-I was the absence of a credible international enforcement or compliance mechanism regarding the CCW and the MBT.

The successful norm building has a reinforcing *name & shame* effect which can generate considerable domestic and international audience costs. The MBT benefits from a repeated norm-reinforcing consultative process which undoubtedly enhances compliance and facilitates its implementation. The Nairobi Action Plan provides an impetus to counter the eroding effects on resource mobilisation caused by many competing demands and very ambitious MBT target setting.

Strictly taken, both the MBT and CCW qualify as “*self-enforcing*” agreement, since it satisfies two elementary conditions: namely each State Party complies as long as everyone else does, and there is no external mechanism needed to ensure compliance. It further underscores how international treaties are part of a “*self-help*” system as described by the renowned political scientists Kenneth Waltz. Tellingly, those international commitments are only viable as long as it is sufficiently in the State’s interest to continue to voluntarily comply with their obligations. This will obviously remain a vulnerable disarmament concept which, in essence, reduces the value of the CCW and MBT to *promissory notes*.

Finding 5: Defining the different levels at which mine action is exercised, allows for a distinct charting of the political dynamics.

It was initially assessed how mine action, as a multidisciplinary and multidimensional activity, is manifestly present at two distinct levels: the high and low politics. The high politics of mine action were explained based on the strategic and political interactions related to legal or political instruments between UN Member States themselves and to a certain extent between States and the United Nations Organisation, the latter fulfilling an institutional role as facilitator and moderator. The low politics were specified as the socio-economic or development factors influencing the prioritization and implementation of mine action.

Further refinement and explanatory value was sought through the identification of a third level: the medium politics. Through defining medium politics, an additional political layer was introduced in order to better characterize the institutional politics within international organizations, regional organizations, the interactions among non-governmental organizations, the United Nations, the International Committee for the Red Cross and regional political bodies such as the European Union and the Organization of American States. This type of institutional politics has its own unique characteristic and portrays elements of (dis)coordination and competition. Combined and interrelated, the politics at these three levels influence how mine action resources are mobilized and allocated, and ultimately how mine action takes place at field level. This will be reflected further below in the chart on hierarchic and game theoretic characteristics of the politics of mine action and related decision-making.

Finding 6: The game theoretic analysis provided an essential contribution in structuring, understanding and explaining the politics of mine action.

In the fragmented and systematic way it was applied, the combined normative/game theoretic analysis is not amongst the most traditional research methodologies. It is, therefore, sensible to question if game theory is indeed a suitable research tool at a doctoral level to study complex disarmament politics? Is the largely *math-free* approach in explaining game theoretic complexities a credible one? Is the outcome sufficiently counter-intuitive? If so, what in general has the most innovative thinking been?

The introductory sections of Phase-I provided preliminary justification to apply game theoretic principles. To remind, the combined analysis was chosen to acquire sufficient knowledge regarding the global landmine problem, the politics, key actors and their *interdependent* decision-making and actions. In this regard, an important spin-off was the deduction of relevant criteria in anticipation of normative modelling. It can now be confirmed that the game theoretic analysis provided considerable explanatory value. It allowed for a systematic breakdown and game theoretic modelling of the different actors at the different political levels, each with their actions or interdependent strategies. Routinely the game theoretic analysis embraced political philosophy, which created room for some scepticism regarding the less than noble intentions of some of the political actors involved. Several paradox elements were addressed between providing a coherent international response to the fall-out of armed conflict and many State actors pursuing their own political or national security agenda. At times, this research approach and effort may have overindulged in too much Cartesian thinking, basic dualisms and systematic categorization, but it was a deliberate choice to bring structure in myriad complexities related to the politics of mine action.

Another observation is that the game theoretic analysis did not have to rely significantly on advanced technical assessments to prove its usefulness in this first research phase. This was further supported by the thesis formulation which emphasises that this dissertation is most about (disarmament) politics and again much less about the technical specifics of mine action itself. Game theory has only been involved as much as it was regarded useful to serve the research objectives and staffed as required with real world examples. In the dynamic field of mine action, it would be incorrect to pursue a conclusive political analysis, simply because there are too many moving parts and parameters. The game theoretic broad-brushing was, therefore, far-preferred above any type of detailed mathematical explorations. A virtually math-free approach maintained the focus where it should be: largely non-predictive and slightly normative or prescriptive. Although, indirectly, some forward looking assessment was provided. In addition, the recurrent use of conceptual metaphors, which are omnipresent in game theory, has further demonstrated to be instrumental. Not only does it keep a comprehensive political analysis digestible, it also permits to introduce game theoretic principles which are open for further individual assessments and interpretations. The other advantage of a game theoretic analysis is its timelessness. Even though circumstances may change, human nature remains largely the same; and certain human elements - especially moral, ethical and psychological factors - are at the root of all politics.

In sum, in addition to the normative aspects, game theory was assessed as helpful in explaining the politics in this field. The productive outcome of Phase-I in terms of key points for the next phases, together with the list of deducted criteria, allows a positive perspective of the advantages of this combined methodology.

Finding 7: Game theory is flexible to alterations, which facilitated the analysis.

The principles of utility maximization were demonstrated convincingly in a broader context than game theory originating from strict military strategic principles. The analysis illustrated how the politics of mine action will continue to adapt through a dynamic system of (amended) protocols and/or adjustments to other political or legal frameworks. Even beyond the classic game theoretic applications, the analysis was reluctant to keep the essence of game theory untouched, even when some new elements were added or game theoretic variations were suggested. That is why the analysis of strategic choices, best responses, minimizing maximum loss and the evolution of coordination and cooperation in the field of mine action was a rewarding game theoretic study subject, thereby taking into account the adaptation of game theoretic principles and modelling according to the challenges cited below:

“Recently, the Operations Other Than War – peacemaking, peacekeeping, humanitarian relief operations – are of special interest. The asymmetric environment they represent can be modelled in a natural manner using game theory. However, they pose many challenges to the applied game theory in terms of analysis and prediction.”⁴³⁶

These limited game theoretic alterations facilitated its use in combination with the normative approach. Arguably game theory is entitled to stand alone as a solid analysis and research tool. It provides *complementary* explanatory value on the politics of mine action and how the political actors behave in a situation of complex interdependence in decision-making. Perhaps it is game theory being closely tied with other scientific principles of utility theory, probability theory, normative theory, decision theory and framing theory, which is leading to best results. Somehow this confirmed earlier research observations in equally complex domains, namely that game theory is best presented as an appendage when applied in political science. Game theory as a stand-alone methodology is too vulnerable to rely solely upon to improve anyone’s understanding of complex political or even economic phenomena. Therefore, in this study it is to be regarded as a research tool in light of a broader systematic assessment.

Finding 8: Large-scale use of landmines and ERW in insurgency activities presents *wicked problems* which require a multi-disciplinary response.

The biggest current and future threat of landmines and ERW will potentially come from its transformed and targeted use as Improvised Explosive Devices. Mines and explosives remnants, either from stockpiles or recycled from the field, will most likely continue to fuel insurgency or terrorist activities taking place in Iraq and Afghanistan, or elsewhere. It is currently the main threat and will likely continue to significantly endanger crucial peacebuilding processes with regional and even global consequences for peace and security. No adequate strategic response has so far been provided by regular military forces and it is most doubtful there is one.

The current combined political, military and humanitarian efforts seem to have no decisive effects on non-State armed or insurgency groups using ERW in IED. On the contrary, the use of mines and ERW in IED becomes more sophisticated and effective by the day; the calls for a non-military response louder. Gradually, the impact on the normative aspects becomes more apparent. A few years ago the term IED was mentioned with a certain reluctance as part of a mine action programme. Nowadays, the terrible nature of the current IED problems make increasingly clear that the normative concept of mine action needs to embrace its efforts and campaign activities against the dangers of IEDs.

⁴³⁶ KARAKANEVA, J. (2003). *Game theoretic modelling for planning and decision-making*, Information & Security: An International Journal, Volume 12, Number 1

Finding 9: Two key challenges or opportunities are: optimized *short-term prioritization and integrated long-term strategic planning of mine action.*

To optimize the global effects of the politics of mine action, the three political levels of mine action should act in harmony. Achieving the desired synergy becomes more challenging beyond the emergency response phase of mine action. When there are high numbers of mine victims, the three political levels of mine action tend to remain well synchronized. Once beyond emergency relief, an element of competition causes consultative processes, cooperation and coordination to be more challenging. The views of donor countries, the United Nations, NGOs, the World Bank and mine-affected States regarding the utility of certain mine action projects - especially when the international community faces many competing demands - quickly diverge once beyond the most pressing humanitarian emergencies. Hence, decision-making is less straightforward, unless *credible prioritization mechanisms are put in place.*

The analysis has demonstrated that the inclusion of mine action in development and post-conflict restoration activities poses unique resource mobilization challenges. It requires from the actors an optimal integration or mainstreaming of mine action into the overall strategic aims of development and/or post-conflict restoration plans. At the international level, significant blockages to mainstreaming of mine action remain. The current decision-making tools do not fully integrate mine action with international development. Due to political agendas, budgetary and other constraints, in particular absence of specific expertise and knowledge, donor countries are often poorly coordinating mine action with other development interventions.

The Nairobi plan of action also identified mainstreaming of mine action as a priority. At the medium political level, major multilateral and bilateral development actors should work in partnership to enhance this integration process. This new trend of mainstreaming cannot achieve the desired results through UN institutional politics alone; it requires first and foremost an optimal prioritization of mine action, based on a close partnership and joint action by all mine-action actors and the development community. Again, if the high-medium-low politics are not well connected on the issues, then efforts in this regard could be futile. Key stakeholders involved in this process are the governments of mine-affected States, donor governments, UN agencies, and international financial institutions as well as national and international nongovernmental organizations and institutions. In sum, the problems and challenges repeatedly highlighted the requirement for refined short-term prioritization of mine action activities and advanced long-term strategic planning.

While the mainstreaming of mine action into development and post-conflict reconstruction has been broadly recognized, there has been little focused policy development on the subject. Efforts to engage key stakeholders in discussions about mainstreaming mine action within national development strategies are either ongoing or poorly documented. This is partly because mine action has traditionally not been addressed within a formal development framework. Rather, mine action has typically been treated as a humanitarian problem that attracts significant funding in the immediate aftermath of hostilities, but considerably less over the long-term. It further supports the conviction that short-term goals are more easily part of an effective norm building campaign than long-term ones. Therefore, while humanitarian funding should continue, a parallel strategy of incorporating mine action into development planning and budgets should be embraced.

II.3.2. Hierarchic structuring of deducted criteria

At the introduction of the normative and game theoretic analysis, the conceptual guidelines for deducing evaluation criteria, goals and indicators have been briefly addressed. As the analysis further illustrated, the political process related to mine action is rife with complex and competing factors. In order to have a transparent and workable set of weighted criteria, it could be best considered to reduce the extensive number of criteria into subsets of approximate 15 criteria.⁴³⁷ More evaluation criteria may cause confusion, duplication and especially a loss of oversight which will negatively influence uniformity in its application by decision makers in a technically complex domain such as mine action. Conversely, as emphasized during the introduction, far fewer criterions tend to cause a loss of sensitivity and lead to an undesired simplification of the model.

Different decisions at the low-medium-high political level require different criteria. Some of the criteria are very concrete; others are quite generic and rather portray the characteristics of a recommendation. For this reason, the characteristics of the criteria have been further assessed according to their relevancy for the High(H), Medium(M) and Low(L) politics. For the *high* politics, marked yellow, the evaluation criteria need to allow differentiation *in between* mine action programmes of different mine-affected States but also include all matters related to national and international security concerns. For the *low* politics, marked green, the criteria extensively reflect the socio-economic issues which could guide the prioritization of mine action activities accordingly *within* a particular mine action programme. Regarding the *medium* politics, marked blue, the criteria are primarily portraying institutional characteristics and reflect the major coordination, cooperation, standardisation or other mine action policy issues.

This hierarchic *delineation of criteria is somewhat artificial*, as was also emphasized during the delineation of high-medium-low politics of mine action. It is, however, a welcome and necessary categorization for modelling purposes. Nevertheless, the most important criteria are omnipresent at the three levels, indicated in the hierarchic overview on the next page. Owing to the many overlaps, it is preferable not to strictly categorize the criteria in subsets yet and to leave the further processing of criteria and indicators to the next phases. Moreover, this effort will be largely driven by the type and quality of data available. Hence, its further exploitation in the modelling phase and case-study will largely depend on how the identified indicators can be best combined with the criteria.

⁴³⁷ YOON,K.P. and HWANG,C. (1995). *Multiple attribute decision-making: an introduction*, Sage University Paper series on Quantitative Applications in the Social Sciences, 07-104. Thousand Oaks, California

II.3.3. Overview of possible criteria for normative modelling

As a spin-off from the normative and game theoretic analysis, forty-two criteria were deducted. In addition to the many identified potential indicators, they could guide decision-making at one or more of the identified political levels of mine action. A preliminary assessment according to the relevancy of each criterion at the three political levels has been provided below.

	Level		
	H	M	L
C 1: Being supportive to the consensus process on “assistance in mine action”	■		
C 2: Sponsoring the UN resolution on “assistance in mine action”	■		
C 3: Level of support of donor countries for mine action programmes	■		
C 4: Level of governance/managerial capabilities and commitment to effectively implement mine action	■	■	
C 5: Level of integration/mainstreaming of mine action into broader humanitarian/development strategies	■	■	
C 6: Level of human cost	■	■	■
C 7: Establishment of a national mine action capacity	■	■	
C 8: Level of landmine impact on freedom of movement – returns of IDPs & refugees			■
C 9: Level of landmine impact on the road network			■
C 10: Level of landmine impact on productive land, water and irrigation sources			■
C 11: Level of landmine impact on residential area and/or public buildings			■
C 12: Level of landmine impact on mine-affected grazing land and livestock			■
C 13: Number of mine victims requiring medical assistance			■
C 14: Socio-economic impact of mine victims on the health care system			■
C 15: Prioritization and targeting of mine action efforts	■	■	
C 16: Effectiveness and progress of mine clearance	■	■	■
C 17: Progress or level of stockpile destruction	■	■	
C 18: Adherence to the CCW - Amended Protocol II and progress on its universalization	■		
C 19: Compliance with the Amended Protocol II and its technical provisions	■		
C 20: Being supportive to the CCW resolution	■		
C 21: Adherence to Protocol V of the CCW and progress on its universalization	■		
C 22: Adherence to the Mine Ban Treaty and progress on its universalization	■		
C 23: Voting in favour/abstaining of the MBT resolution	■		
C 24: Progress on achieving the core humanitarian objectives of the Mine Ban Treaty – Nairobi Action Plan	■	■	
C 25: No new deployments of landmines	■	■	■
C 26: Level of pressure of State actors to inhibit non-State actors from using landmines/ERW	■	■	
C 27: Combined presence and intent to use landmine/ERW explosives to construct IEDs	■	■	■
C 28: Level of funding, technical and material support for mine clearance efforts in mine-affected countries	■	■	
C 29: Level of information sharing	■	■	
C 30: Level of standardisation of mine action	■	■	
C 31: Resource mobilization per capita	■	■	
C 32: Level of effectiveness and efficiency of a mine action programme	■	■	
C 33: Coordination, transparency and predictability of mine action funding	■	■	
C 34: Progress in the field of mine detection and clearance equipment	■	■	
C 35: Level of cooperation and coordination of mine action activities	■	■	
C 36: Establishment of adequate emergency response capacities for mine action	■	■	
C 37: Management and planning capabilities of national mine action coordination centres	■	■	
C 38: Having established adequate fund raising mechanisms	■	■	
C 39: Level of integration of mine action in peacekeeping/building operations	■	■	
C 40: Mine action integrated in DDR programmes			■
C 41: Ability of health care systems to provide assistance to mine victims			■
C 42: Balanced and effective public awareness campaigns and objective framing of the landmine problem	■	■	

Table II.4: Identified criteria which could be used for modelling purposes

II.3.4. Hierarchic overview of the game theoretic characteristics

The overview on the next page of the hierarchical and game theoretic characterization of the politics of mine action summarizes and visualizes the main dynamics. It highlights in a symbolic sense the interdependency of the decision-making processes between the three defined levels of the politics of mine action: *high politics* (shaded yellow) primarily related to the *interactions between States*, *medium politics* (shaded blue) to reflect the *institutional and organisational politics*, and *low politics* (shaded green) to reflect *national politics primarily related to socio-economic issues*. It further depicts how the various actors at each level, based on their set of interrelated criteria (indicated by the red arrows), will determine their possible options or alternatives according to their interpretation of the possible scenarios. Finally, it reflects the interdependent selection of the response, which – in a game theoretic and rational context – should be the one perceived as the best response taking into account the responses of the other actors.

In Nash equilibrium situations, it was explained that rational States or other actors will not change their best response(s) unilaterally as it will result in lower payoffs or political incentives. In absence of this type of equilibriums, actors will alter their decision-making in order to maximize their payoffs. Besides being a cornerstone in game theory, this interdependent choosing of strategies based on payoff or utility maximization, is a principle which is embedded in the classic interpretation of incentive-driven politics, or simply, self-interest.

To remind, the analysis started with a simple two-person *chicken game* to explain consensus negotiations, with both pure and mixed equilibrium points. It evolved quickly towards explaining the most relevant (UN) multilateral politics of mine action in terms of *alliance formations*, *compliance games*, and *name and shame* tactics. Its envisaged *audience costs* were applied to explain the main political dynamics of States vis-à-vis mine action related conventions and its compliance issues. State mine action funding of a “*mine free*” versus an “*impact free*” world was explained through the *Diner’s Dilemma*, and *Tit-for-Tat* games were applied regarding the dreaded use of landmines/ERW by NSA. *Free-rider* problems, *blame* and *credit games* were additional refinements to the main game theoretic dynamics and characteristics identified.

The international-strategic responses of States to the global landmine problem have, obviously, its repercussions on the institutional and national scenarios (indicated through the blue arrows). Conversely, what finally can be delivered in the field or implemented has also a decisive influence on the scenarios at medium and high level. If for example mine clearance is much slower than initially estimated or significantly hindered due to security problems, then this *national* scenario will or should be reflected in the assessment of the *international* or *institutional* scenarios. This permits that the national, field-operational constraints are reflected in the high or medium politics decisions (dotted blue arrows).

In sum, many of the game theoretic characteristics and identified equilibriums can be associated at the three levels, albeit in a different context. Similar to the criteria, trying to dissect clinically the political interactions would oversimplify the charting of complex, interwoven politics. Preferably, strategic choices or best responses at all levels should seek to respect or facilitate the establishment of desired equilibriums. If, for example, a landmine “*impact free*” world is desired above a “*mine free*” world, then equilibriums can shift with significant repercussions. The politics, strategies and policies need to be adjusted accordingly. In this regard, the UN is critical in providing stakeholders both at the high and low level the guidance and resources required. The revised UN mine action strategy and ongoing coordination efforts are commendable in this regard but would benefit from more authoritative and concrete guidance. At this stage it only emphasizes how the international community should strive to reduce, through MDG-alike goal setting, as fast as possible the impact of the global landmine problem (*minimax*) without clinging to utopian goal setting.

Fig. II.38: Identified game theoretic characteristics of the politics of mine action and related decision-making

CHAPTER III – PHASE-II: NORMATIVE MODELLING

III.1. Introduction

III.1.1. Further exploring the main research objective of Phase-II

Political and social scientists run high risks to oversimplify or unwittingly leaving out important elements during modelling efforts, owing to insufficient knowledge of the real world situation. There is a tendency to underestimate the complexities at hand. Former mine action cost-benefit analysis in Laos is just one of the many examples.

“A very simple model is useful for explaining basic cost-benefit concepts, but even the simple rice economy in Lao PDR is more complicated, and it is important to understand its features to ensure the model can usefully (and safely!) serve as a tool for decision-making.”⁴³⁸

The comprehensive normative and game theoretic analysis of Phase-I intended to significantly reduce this risk. To remind, the main research effort of this Phase implies a focus on how mine action data and statistical analysis can be integrated in a normative modelling process. Phase-I confirmed that there is a need for a sophisticated *short-term prioritization model*, including *a risk management capability*, combined with robust and *integrated strategic mine action planning*. This model should be able to better inform decision-making at the different political levels: low, medium and high. It should also better indicate *how* to direct resources to mine action and *when* to redirect those resources to other post-conflict restoration areas where they could have a higher expected utility. Phase-I comprehensively addressed how this can be expressed either in terms of reducing human suffering or any other post-conflict impact of landmines and ERW.

The analysis has demonstrated that reliable criteria and indicators related to mine action will be of utmost importance to establish a credible scoring method. This will allow evaluating possible courses of action and hence, formulating *an optimal mine action response*. The Afghan case study ought to demonstrate this in more practical detail. This phase needs, therefore, to develop the basic modelling features before studying how complex Afghan mine action data and statistical analysis can be modelled and assist in determining short-term priorities and long-term planning. The objective is to prove that through decision theoretic techniques and a suitable decision support system the current decision-makings processes can be optimized and reduce significantly trial and error. The introductory sections below will address further how this research objective can be pragmatically translated into research actions.

III.1.2. Basic questions before starting the normative modelling

A systematic research approach brought the desired outcome for Phase-I: an understanding of the politics of mine action and the deduction of relevant *criteria* and *indicators* which could be used in decision-making at different political levels. The acquired knowledge will also aid the credible formulation of realistic strategic scenarios and options. Building upon the numerous findings of Phase-I, the modelling effort of Phase-II can be structured based on the following questions:

- (1) *What* do we exactly try to model?
- (2) *How* are we going to model it?
- (3) *Which* (software) support system is required to facilitate the modelling effort?

On the first question the answer has been provided above. Both an *intrinsic* and *extrinsic* optimization needs to be sought for mine action activities to be effective and efficient compared to

⁴³⁸ GICHD (2002). *A Study of socio-economic approaches to Mine Action*, Geneva, p.42

other post-conflict requirements. Phase-II will be subdivided in a sub-phase A and B due to the relatively distinct *short-term* prioritization and *long-term* planning requirements.

The second question requires a more comprehensive answer. Similar to the normative analysis, the first requirement lies in the envisaged *prescriptive* characteristics of the outcome of the model; reason why it is qualified as a *normative* model.

“A *normative* model is developed to represent the decision problem, facilitate ongoing analysis, and produce a recommended course of action. The technique is most useful in managerial situations where risk is significant. The resulting formal model is capable of generating optimal strategies for multi-stage decision problems that involve a variety of contingencies.”⁴³⁹

The second requirement is due to the comprehensively addressed multi-layer politics of mine action. The model needs, therefore, to allow a *hierarchical* or *staged multiple criteria decision analysis*, i.e. to allow optimal sequential decision-making over time. Hence, as much as possible a systematic classification of criteria will be introduced according to the three political levels of mine action identified in Phase-I. To structure this process, in general three modelling principles can be identified:⁴⁴⁰

- (1) apply *multiple criteria utility-based decision theory*;
- (2) rank objectives and related criteria in priority order and optimize them sequentially;⁴⁴¹
- (3) turn some criteria into constraints.

With the modelling complexities at hand, likely a combination of the above three modelling principles will bring the best results, taking into account the following considerations:

- (1) optimization per criteria;
- (2) statistical analysis to assist in the process of determining weight vectors.

In answer to the third question, the construction of the normative model will be “ground-tested” for its full potential and applicability during the Afghan case-study; thereby supported by both statistical and decision support software tools. It is the aspiration to maintain as much as possible the concept of the research model developed in this phase but with the necessary refinements and adjustments to handle the complex mine action data of Afghanistan.

Before closing of this section, there is one more fundamental observation to be made or question to be asked: once developed, *what are the chances that this normative model will actually be used?* Many models are never used for a variety of reasons, including:⁴⁴²

- (1) it was not deemed relevant to model or make predictions in the setting envisioned;
- (2) potential users of the model did not trust the relationships, weights or variables;
- (3) the data necessary for the model was not routinely available.

In order to address these potential pitfalls, the research effort will pay specific attention to the availability of data, the credibility and user-friendliness of the model. The model needs therefore to facilitate both *decision quality* and *decision acceptance*. Both are often interrelated but the latter is of particular importance and can be enhanced through increased transparency of the decision-making process. Transparent decision-making models should be anyhow the objective since they permit evaluation and thereby strengthen institutional credibility and legitimacy. Such a model could result in more confidence amongst the decision-makers and those who have to implement mine action. To remind, the *trust dilemma* was cited in Phase-I as one of the main reasons for coordination and

⁴³⁹ Decision Modelling, Internet. Available at <http://groups.msn.com/DecisionModelling/decisionanalysis1.mswn>, accessed on 5 May 2007

⁴⁴⁰ VIGNAUX, G. (2005). *Multi-attribute decision problems*, Victoria University of Wellington, New Zealand

⁴⁴¹ This is also known under the technique of Goal Programming.

⁴⁴² HARRELL, F. (2001). *Regression Modelling Strategies*, New York: Vanderbilt University, p.4

cooperation problems in mine action. Hence, having answered the basic modelling questions and discussed the basic principles, modelling requirements can be summarized as follows:

- (1) transparent and comprehensible;
- (2) sufficiently refined and sensitive;
- (3) flexible to change and updates;
- (4) able to handle different types of data;
- (5) able to make numerous assessments;
- (6) able to incorporate uncertainty, risk and imprecision;
- (7) able to produce credible and clear outputs in terms of mine action prioritization;
- (8) able to incorporate a time dimension.

Effective and reliable risk management will be essential throughout the modelling effort. This is directly related to the human cost. Here too, *sensitivity analysis* needs to facilitate the identification of parameters in a model that reduces risks and can cause significant changes in the decision-making. The case-study will need to demonstrate how important it is to be able to change weight vectors or coefficients as an essential part of risk management, which implies adaptability of the model to changing circumstances and priorities.

The previous deductions support the general conclusion that the decision-making process cannot and should not be fully mapped or quantified. A multitude of decision makers is generally involved in resource mobilization and allocation. Probably the opinions will differ on how the model needs to be balanced out. This underscores that the effective implementation of mine action activities requires a close interaction with the decision-making process above a “black-box” approach which hides a variety of poorly considered assumptions. In the envisaged decision-taking the underlying assumptions at least once, and once they have been accepted or in-calculated by the decision maker, it can become more efficient to ignore some or all of them.

III.1.3. Sub-phase A: Intrinsic modelling

Fig. III.1: Sub-Phase A First Intersection Optimization

First an intrinsic modelling process will be pursued. This implies that - in anticipation of the outer-directed modelling - the intrinsic modelling will study the intersection optimization of the five core components of mine action in relation to the three possible mine action outputs: (1) humanitarian relief, (2) socio-economic benefits and (3) peace keeping/building. To remind, intrinsic modelling will in a strict sense only take into account elements and challenges inherent to a mine action programme, without looking at the broader post-conflict recovery challenges of a mine-affected State.

In order to achieve the objectives of this Phase, it is furthermore necessary to study how mine action can produce most *effectively* and *efficiently* the aforementioned desired outputs, which requires a solid understanding and distinction of both terms. Effectiveness is traditionally described as “*doing the right job*” and most important for the prioritization of mine action. Efficiency is about “*doing the job right*” and involves operational and tactical considerations

regarding the implementation of mine action. It becomes particularly interesting if both concepts are

combined, especially since they do not necessarily correlate. A mine action project can be very beneficial to the local community but executed in a very expensive or inefficient manner, whilst mine-contaminated desert land can be very efficiently cleared but of benefit to none. Where the concept of effectiveness is primarily focused on benefits, efficiency is centred around costs, or to put it more in basic mathematical terms:

- (1) Effectiveness = benefits/costs or output/input
- (2) Efficiency = measurable unit of mine action activity/cost

The task at hand is to model the deduced evaluation criteria and indicators. The optimization of the intersection needs to be measurable, based on the five core activities of mine action and optimization functions linked to criteria essential for multiple criteria decision-making

Problem A – Optimize short-term prioritization of mine action

III.1.4. Sub-phase B: Extrinsic modelling

Fig. III.2: Sub-Phase B Second Intersection Optimization

This sub-phase will focus on the requirement to line up an intrinsic prioritization process with *extrinsic* planning factors. Mine action should never take place in isolation! Phase-I highlighted how the current realm of global goal-setting for development is one of the key areas where mine action could seek better mainstreaming. Hence, mine action needs to be part of an overarching strategic planning process and pursue alignment with the post-conflict restoration objectives of a mine-affected State. It is, therefore, important to highlight some of the strategic mechanisms to harmonize mine action with the different strategic planning processes and ultimately the MDGs.

Problem B – Optimize integrated strategic planning for mine action

III.2.Sub-phase A: Optimize short-term prioritization of mine action activities

III.2.1. The “crisp” optimization problem

To remind, *optimization* in the context of this dissertation is the process through which specific decision-making techniques will determine the optimal response to a given landmine impact problem. In order to solve this problem in a practical way, the problem is first converted to a simplified *crisp* optimization problem. This implies the absence of data uncertainty and fuzzy logic.

If there would only be one evaluation criteria with function $f(x)$ to be optimized, with A the set of possible solutions, actions or alternatives, then the following basic formula would be valid:⁴⁴³

$$OPT \{ f(x) / x \in A \}$$

In case of multiple or k criteria:

$$OPT \{ f_1(x), f_2(x), \dots, f_j(x), \dots, f_k(x) / x \in A \}$$

The mine action budget can be subdivided according to its five sub-activities: mine clearance, risk education, victim assistance and stockpile destruction.

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} (1) \text{ Partial Budget Mine Clearance} = v \\ (2) \text{ Partial Budget Mine Risk Education} = w \\ (3) \text{ Partial Budget Victim Assistance} = x \\ (4) \text{ Partial Budget Stockpile Destruction} = y \\ (5) \text{ Partial Budget Advocacy} = z \end{array} \right\} \text{Total Budget} = v + w + x + y + z$$

With the envisaged related mine action output being threefold, and each of the five mine action activities possibly contributing to humanitarian relief, socio-economic benefits and peacekeeping, the total output can be expressed as follows:

- (1) Humanitarian Relief = HR
- (2) Socio-Economic Benefits = SEB
- (3) Peacekeeping/building = PK

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} v = HR_1 + SEB_1 + PB_1 \\ w = HR_2 + SEB_2 + PB_2 \\ x = HR_3 + SEB_3 + PB_3 \\ y = HR_4 + SEB_4 + PB_4 \\ z = HR_5 + SEB_5 + PB_5 \end{array} \right\} \text{Total Output} = \sum_{n=1}^5 HR_n + \sum_{n=1}^5 SEB_n + \sum_{n=1}^5 PK_n$$

In summary, an optimal combination of HR, SEB and PK needs to be achieved at the lowest combined budget or cost possible in order to achieve crisp optimization. This will be in accordance with the (weighted) preferences of the decision-maker, based on the expected maximum utilities which flow from the utility functions or in anticipation of multiple criteria decision analysis, the *preference functions*. The following simple mathematical equation captures the straightforward principles of *effectiveness* and *efficiency*. It is meant to evolve in complexity throughout this chapter.

$$OPT \text{ Mine Action} = OPT \frac{\text{Total Output}}{\text{Total Budget}} = OPT \left\{ \frac{\sum_{n=1}^5 HR_n + \sum_{n=1}^5 SEB_n + \sum_{n=1}^5 PK_n}{v + w + x + y + z} \right\}$$

⁴⁴³ BRANS J-P. and MARESCHAL, B. (2002) *PROMETHEE-GAIA*, Brussels, p.36

III.2.2. Simulation for modelling purposes

A. Visualisation of the prioritization problem

In preparation of the case-study, the small-scale simulation in figure III.3 represents a simplified, fictitious mine/ERW affected region in Afghanistan. It will confront the above theoretic crisp approach with the prioritization complexities at hand. This basic setting will, therefore, facilitate the development of a basic normative model in line with the related real-world multiple criteria decision analysis of not five but several thousand affected communities in Afghanistan. The methodological principles on how to prioritize the five communities below (A, B, C, D and E with a varying degree of contamination) will be studied in the following sections.

The human cost in this layout is only specified according to a two-fold concept of *frequency* and *recency* of mine/ERW accidents. Statistical data analysis of the Afghan survey will indicate if other parameters or statistical predictors can be included. Similarly, the socio-economic factors are visualized in terms of blockages and not specified in terms of economic capital of inaccessible km² of farm, grazing or other types of land or sources. Peacekeeping/building factors are even more reduced, merely indicating certain regional institution building activities which could benefit from mine action.

Fig. III.3: Small-scale prioritization problem

B. Suggested criteria and indicators for short-term mine action prioritization

N°	Evaluation Criteria	Impact	Possible Indicators
C 6	Level of human cost	HC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of injured/killed mine victims
C 8	Level of impact on freedom of movement – returns of IDPs & refugees	SE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of resettled refugees or IDP's Restoration of km road network and reduction in travel costs Restored access to productive land, drinking water and other water sources, residential area, to public administrative and community buildings Restoration of km² productive farming land and grazing land Number of farming jobs created/reinstated through mine action Reduced travel times/travels costs Disturbance of social interactions at community level Restoration of irrigation systems in km or sq km Restoration of km² residential area and social infrastructure Number of livestock killed by landmines Number of removed blockages to humanitarian aid Socio-economic impact and cost of medical care
C 9	Level of landmine impact on road network	SE	
C 10	Level of landmine impact on productive land, water and irrigation sources	SE	
C 11	Level of landmine impact on residential area and/or public buildings	SE	
C 12	Level of landmine impact on grazing land and livestock	SE	
C 13	Number of mine victims requiring medical assistance	SE	
C 14	Socio-economic impact of mine victims on the health care system	SE	
C 27	Combined presence and intent to use landmine/ERW explosives to construct IEDs	PK	
C 40	Mine action integrated in DDR programmes	PK	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Confidence-building measures through incorporating mine action in DDR programmes
C 41	Ability of health care systems to provide assistance to mine victims	HC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Availability of medical support to mine victims
<p>HC = Human Cost SE = Socio-Economic PK = Peacekeeping/building</p>			

Table III.1: Relevant criteria for mine action prioritization at national level

Based on the analysis and outcome of Phase-I, Table III.1 presents a selection of criteria and combines them with identified indicators. The majority of the criteria are related to the *low politics* and cover primarily socio-economic aspects. Human cost (HC) and peacekeeping/building effects have separate criteria and indicators. The indicator for the human cost criteria number 6 is straightforward. For criteria 41 the indicator of the availability of medical infrastructure will influence the risks for mine victims. A decision-maker would logically give preference to impacted communities with no medical infrastructure above those who have. The indicators for socio-economic (SE) criteria can be subdivided in weak and strong metrics in terms of blocked/restored access and km² of affected land respectively. Peacekeeping (PK) criteria 27 and 40 are also linked to weak metrics indicators or qualifiers rather than quantifiers. Ultimately the use of these criteria will be largely information-driven. Hence, the next section will study the possible sources of information for these indicators and address the aspects of strong versus weak metrics with more detail.

III.2.3. Available data for prioritization

A. Data sources

Phase-I highlighted that the cost and effort of gathering mine action information is high. This sub-phase will, therefore, focus on landmine impact surveys as they are the key source of survey data and other essential modelling information. However, as stated in the introduction of this chapter, the model or decision support system should have sufficient build-in flexibility to alter or enrich the analysis whenever additional or enhanced real-world information becomes available. Together with data analysis, this will pose its unique modelling challenges in determining utility functions, weights, combined optimization, etc.

B. Landmine Impact Survey data

Through its blend of surveyed parameters or variables, the Landmine Impact Survey (LIS) takes into consideration the risk aspect of mine contamination as well as the socio-economic impact with the relative magnitudes of the attached weights determined through extensive consultations of multiple stakeholders. Section C will look into the basic principles, strengths and flaws of this survey process. In anticipation thereof, an overview is provided below on the different types of information gathered by the LIS.

a. Survey data per impacted community

- (1) The survey records what it calls the “*distance RefPt to MA-edge*”; which is the estimated distance (in meters) of the centre of the community (e.g. church or mosque) to the border of the suspected mined area.
- (2) The number of “*Old*” victims killed and number of “*Old*” victims injured; this number totalizes the mine accidents which happened *before* the 2-year time span considered by the LIS $[t_1, t_2]$. “*New*” victims killed and injured are those who took place between $[t_1, t_2]$.

Fig. III.4: ‘Old’ versus ‘new’ mine victims in the LIS

- (3) Population; current or pre-conflict
- (4) Medical infrastructure for mine victims: if there is emergency and/or rehabilitation care, vocational training, other care, no care or unknown care.
- (5) Mine action activities: marking and survey, mine clearance, local clearance

b. Survey data on the contamination

- (1) A distinction is made between anti-personnel mines (AP), anti-tank mines and unexploded ordnance (UXO) or ERW.
- (2) Number of mined areas.
- (3) Socio-economic impact of the contamination in terms of *blocked access* to different types of land (farming and grazing land), resources (water sources) or infrastructure (residential, administrative and other public buildings).

c. Survey data per mine/ERW victim:

- (1) Gender and age of victim.
- (2) Military or civilian.
- (3) Activity during the mine accidents (e.g. farming, wood collection), detonation date and detonation coordinates, if the accident happened in a known dangerous area and sometimes the specifics if the mine accident resulted in amputation, loss of sight, other wounds or was fatal.

C. Landmine Impact Survey process

a. Current LIS categorization

Figure III.5 shows how the enumeration and consequently categorization in “high, medium and low impact” of mine-affected communities takes place. The illustrative example is a mine-affected community which reported two mine victims over the last 24 months together with a blocked access to drinking water and some blocked roads. This cumulates into a total *Mine Impact Score* (MIS) of 9. Hence, according to the MIS categorization system, the impact on the community is to be considered “medium”, two points short of being ranked as highly impacted. It makes no distinction if those 2 mine accidents took place last week or 23 months ago. Neither does it make a distinction if the socio-economic blockages result in critical access roads being blocked and/or blocked access to sole water sources.

Hence, on the one hand the LIS scoring/categorization system is attractive for its simplicity, on the other hand the system is quite insensitive to a number of factors which may result that two very different landmine impact settings may result in receiving exactly the same MIS. In addition, the LIS Mine Impact Score is not designed to be sensitive to a range of other factors, including the size and number of the SHAs affecting one or more communities, or the total number of landmine victims preceding the survey. Therefore, the LIS *weak-metrics principles* will need to be addressed in more depth before exploring improvements to the current system and/or better exploitation of the survey data.

Locality Identifier: Indicators	District:	Community: Weights	Points to add	Score
The community reported that				
• there were mines.	YES	If so, give	2 points	2
• there was UXO	NO	If so, give	1 point	—
			Subtotal for explosives realm:	2
• access to some irrigated crop land was blocked.	If so, give	1	points	—
• access to some rainfed crop land was blocked.	If so, give	1	points	—
• access to some fixed pasture was blocked.	If so, give	1	points	—
• access to some migratory pasture was blocked.	If so, give	0	points	—
• access to some drinking water points was blocked.	If so, give	2	points	2
• access to some water points for other uses was blocked.	If so, give	1	points	—
• access to some non-cultivated area was blocked.	If so, give	1	points	—
• access to some housing area was blocked.	If so, give	1	points	—
• some roads were blocked.	If so, give	1	points	1
• access to some other infrastructure was blocked.	If so, give	1	points	—
Total number of points (sum of weights) to be equal to			Σ 10 points	
			Subtotal for socio-economic realm	3
• there were 2 mine victims in the last 24 months.		Multiply with 2 points for victims	4	4
			Points for victims	4
			Total mine impact score:	9
If the impact score is 0, rank the community as having “no known mine problem” If the score is between 1 and 5, the impact is considered to be “low”. If the score is between 6 and 10, the impact is considered to be “medium”. If the score is higher than 10, the impact is considered “high”.				
MEDIUM				
Impact ranking:				

Fig. III.5: Example of the LIS scoring system

b. Why use weak-metrics in Landmine Impact Surveys?

This question brings up the dilemma of limiting the cost of data gathering together with weak-data comparability versus the requirement for detailed survey data to establish a credible prioritization of mine action. The LIS mine impact score model is easy to comprehend and calculate,

and indeed, it keeps information costs down. However, if surveys cannot be compared in absence of cross-country comparison mechanisms, the advantages to hold on to a weak-metric survey system can be questioned. Possible statistical predictors such as the *recency* of mine accidents and the *proximity* of minefields to the affected community have been studied in the Afghan LIS.⁴⁴⁴ However, the statistical analysis of LIS-data remains limited and is surely not expanded towards assisting the prioritization of mine action. Even under pressure of the mine action community, modifications to the survey methodology and survey data collection have been very limited and not substantial. There has always been a reluctance that changing the weak-metric concept would distort a delicate balance.

“The *weak-metric* approach is easy to criticise, but difficult to replace. Elements have been injected into the survey format that threatens mission creep and hybridisation while improving the commonality with some of the mine action professions. The international survey management will need to keep a good balance between stability and improvement of a standard design on the one hand, and openness and creativity on the other.”⁴⁴⁵

It follows that the weak-metric system was installed to promote a standardized global survey approach and circumvent certain expected obstacles if cross-country comparison of mine action programmes would be pursued. This choice is giving contradictory ambitions free play and has invited quite some criticism, especially when the survey takes up other tasks as quantifying the size of the problem. In 2004, the Survey Working Group (SWG) even decided that it would no longer publish area figures in its printed reports because the confidence level in area estimates based on current general survey techniques was simply too misleading. They decided that LIS-interviewers will continue to carry out visual inspection and record estimates of areas and define polygons where possible, but that this data would be recorded in the database as provisional.⁴⁴⁶

“All previous LIS’ had increased the amount of suspected area, sometimes by a factor of 10 or more. This result called into question the true worth of the survey, which was actually aimed at understanding the landmine/UXO impact upon the people involved, their livelihoods and the country, and not the measurement of the size of the problem in terms of mine-/UXO-contaminated area alone. The availability of its data represented a major step forward in our ability to strategize.”⁴⁴⁷

Noticeably, this argument seems to be applicable on a limited number of finalized impact surveys. Especially the Cambodia LIS did harm the credibility and value of the LIS concept. Its estimate of 4000 km² suspected hazardous area was one of those overestimates which falls under the factor 10 exaggerations.⁴⁴⁸ Also the accuracy of the Mozambique LIS has been contested at several occasions. However, with the LIS in Afghanistan, a much better approach led to quite satisfactory results and demonstrated the feasibility to have both a credible impact study and quite accurate estimation of the total contamination in terms of square kilometres; similar for the ongoing survey in Angola.

“Of note, please can UNMAS learn from the mistakes of certifying countries such as Cambodia and Mozambique, and never again certify a "process" just rather than the "product", particularly if the stamp of approval is being given just because the process done matched the proposed process – regardless of whether the proposed process was flawed. Today we have heard lots of sensible talk from NPA and others about the need for task cancellation and area reduction – of course none of this is new, but none of this would be necessary at all if the LIS been properly thought through early on with greater field involvement from mine trained surveyors.”⁴⁴⁹

⁴⁴⁴ Landmine Survey Action Centre. (2005). Afghanistan Landmine Impact Survey, Washington, p.177

⁴⁴⁵ GICHD (2002). A Study of Socio-Economic Approaches to Mine Action, Geneva, p.40

⁴⁴⁶ EATON, B. (2003). Area Reduction: A Solution Whose Time has Come. *Journal of Mine Action*, Issue 7.3, MAIC - James Madison University, Washington DC

⁴⁴⁷ BOWNESS, C. (2005). The Missing Link in Strategic Planning. *Journal of Mine Action*, Issue 9.1, MAIC - James Madison University, Washington DC

⁴⁴⁸ Rather 400 km² compared to 4000 km² is a frequently cited opinion of experts on the Cambodian landmine problem.

⁴⁴⁹ US Department of State, Internet. Available at <http://www.state.gov/t/pm/wra/69398.htm>, accessed on 1 April 2006

In summary, the metrics used in the LIS mine impact score model suffer from a number of shortcomings. It is therefore questionable, whether the current LIS methodology can adequately contribute to the prioritization of mine action.

c. Limitations of the Mine Impact Score for prioritization

The current impact scoring methodology has, indeed, its limitations regarding national prioritization of mine action activities, which is acknowledged by the Survey Action Centre:

“One caution, the mine impact score is a category, not a priority. The Survey Action Center and Survey Working Group have never claimed that the score is a basis for determining priorities – it is a rough category to help sort out where further [and more expensive] analysis is required. The metric is weak because the cost in time and money to improve the metric and the reliability of the data collection would overwhelm most processes. Priority setting is a very complex rational-political-subjective process in the end and the Landmine Impact Survey can provide a basis for a poly-variant discussion that goes well beyond the Landmine Impact Survey.”⁴⁵⁰

These limitations will be comprehensively addressed during this phase and the case-study in order to formulate suitable remedies which take into account the above mentioned rational, political and subjective elements. This will not necessarily discard the current MIS system which will remain useful to establish the initial qualitative low-medium-high classification. Owing to its simplicity, the MIS is, therefore useful for the first stage of priority setting and as an effective framing method of the problem in order to gain donor confidence. However, there it pretty much stops. The processing of survey data lacks refinement and credibility due to the merging of weak and strong metrics, of two distinct phenomena, in one MIS.

“[...] it is now accepted that a low impact score does not mean a low priority for clearance, nor a high impact score is necessarily a high clearance priority, and that proximity to mined areas and other development or infrastructure factors will be included in a new scoring system for Sudan and other countries. Also, that country demining tasks and plans will not have to be based on LIS. HALO welcomes this as we have been banging on for 4-5 years that the LIS scoring system had badly skewed reality, and had resulted in millions and millions of donor dollars being wasted sorting out great swathes of land that were never mined.”⁴⁵¹

Even quite recent and already improved landmine impact survey procedures are still subject to critical feedback from the numerous stakeholders in this process, including the survey manager of the LIS in Afghanistan.

“In my opinion, the present LIS scoring methodology needs a critical revision. The socioeconomic blockages and scores allocated for recent victims were sometimes found to be misleading in Afghanistan.”⁴⁵²

These rather harsh critics should, however, not be taken as a sole reference to value the LIS concept. Undoubtedly, the amount of data gathered through this survey process is impressive and has largely facilitated a more systematic approach to assessing the strategic impact of landmines. As stated in the introduction, the objective of this dissertation is to suggest improvements of prioritization which do not require dramatic changes in the survey data collection but rather its data processing, assessment and exploitation. Owing to the stochastic nature of mine accidents in combination with the usage of weak metrics, the followings section will introduce the concept of fuzzy logic and optimization.

⁴⁵⁰ E-mail communication with Survey Action Centre, Washington. Mr. Bob Eaton, 13 February 2006

⁴⁵¹ US Department of State, Internet. Available at <http://www.state.gov/t/pm/wra/69398.htm>, accessed on 3 February 2007

⁴⁵² Survey Action Centre. (2005). Afghanistan Landmine Impact Survey, Washington DC, p.203

III.2.4. Fuzzy logic

A. From “crisp” to “fuzzy” optimization

The analysis so far has indicated that determining an optimal mine action response to address affected communities is not as simple as providing a priority ranking of communities based on a crisp mathematical optimization or outranking method. This would largely ignore some of the specific challenges inherent to mine action related data, complex decision-making under risk and fuzzy considerations or constraints.

“The new challenge that we face in the information-rich environment of today is how to handle those very complicated, large size problems. The information-rich environment is usually full of noise, vagueness, uncertainty as well as conflicts and contradictions. The compounding effects of the numerous uncertainties arising in the large size problems can easily make their solutions extremely time-consuming, if not intractable.”⁴⁵³

In reality the utility of the different mine action activities is uncertain and, therefore, *expected* utility functions need to be used. Fuzzy optimization describes an optimization problem with fuzzy objective or utility functions and fuzzy constraints. The results obtained from classical methods of optimization involving deterministic variables exhibit various shortcomings. In particular for mine action data, the effects of the uncertainty attached to input information can not be ignored altogether or only taken into account to a limited degree. This fuzzy optimization principle can be installed through *indifference/preference thresholds* as part of preference functions, which will be further discussed in the next sections.

As identified in the introduction, the model should be able to incorporate data according to fuzzy logic. This could be achieved through installing thresholds; e.g. a certain affected community will only be preferred over another community if the expected utility functions indicate that the projected benefits of mine action are *sufficiently higher* than those in another affected community, taking into account the uncertainty attached to the data. This will avoid ranking of affected communities based on absolute input information differences. Hence, the earlier classical deterministic optimization problem is now considered under both aspects of uncertainty and probability. The proposed way to incorporate fuzzy logic is through *fuzzy multiple criteria decision analysis*.

Fig. III.6: Basic fuzzy logic example

“Fuzzy logic” provides a suitable way to approach, complex, “non-crisp” optimization problems.⁴⁵⁴ It is used for (out)ranking problems not easily definable by practical mathematical models and derives much of its power from its ability to draw conclusions and generate responses based on vague, ambiguous, qualitative, incomplete, or related information.⁴⁵⁵ Hence, including fuzzy logic in the modelling methodology for the imprecise mine action optimization problem envisaged, needs to balance the modelling effort between a pragmatic

⁴⁵³ FANG S. (editor), Fuzzy Optimization and Decision-making. *Journal of Modelling and Computation Under Uncertainty*. North Carolina State University, Internet. Available at <http://www.ise.ncsu.edu/fangroup/fuzzy.dir/FODM.html>, accessed on 20 June 2006

⁴⁵⁴ Fuzzy Logic was initiated in 1965, by Lotfi A. Zadeh, Professor for computer science at the University of California in Berkeley. Basically, Fuzzy Logic (FL) is a multi-valued logic that allows intermediate values to be defined between conventional evaluations like true/false, yes/no, high/low, etc. Notions like rather contaminated or very contaminated can be formulated, mathematically and processed by computers, in order to apply a more humanlike way of thinking in the programming of computers. L.A. Zadeh, “Making computers think like people”, International Conference on Engineering Education (ICEE). Spectrum, 8/1984, pp. 26 -32.

⁴⁵⁵ VIOT, G. (1993, February). Fuzzy Logic in C, Creating a fuzzy-based inference engine, *Dr. Dobb's Journal*, Internet. Available at <http://www.ddj.com/184408940?pgno=19>, accessed on 9 July 2007

response to the problem and a scientific approach. Indeed, this fuzzy approach requires a sufficient expert knowledge for the formulation of the modelling principles, especially in terms of determining indifference and preference thresholds between possible response choices. In this image, *cold*, *warm*, and *hot* are functions mapping a temperature scale. A point on that scale has three “truth values”⁴⁵⁶ — one for each of the three functions. For the particular temperature shown, the three truth values could be interpreted as describing the temperature as “fairly cold”, “slightly warm”, and “not hot”.

Fig. III.7: Fuzzy optimization of mine action output

Similarly, a fuzzy combination of the three possible mine action outputs will bring better results. It is not because community E, depicted in figure III.7, suffered twelve mine victims compared to eight mine victims of community A that one can automatically conclude that E should have a much higher priority than community A. Merging aspects of probability theory together with fuzzy logic will be required to obtain more satisfactory and credible rankings according to the (fuzzy) preferences of the decision-maker(s). For example, the probability of future mine accidents in community E can be lower than community A due to intensive mine risk education or marking and fencing of minefields surrounding community E, hence, requiring community A to receive a higher priority than community E. Other reasons could be changes in (risk) behaviour of the population of community A; maybe the regional economic circumstances obliges the population to farm mine-affected areas surrounding community A whereby community E is situated in an area with little or no productive land. All these possible reasons may justify the decision maker’s wish to outrank only a community if the delta in human relief or human cost reduction with another community is significant enough to outrank it. In order to incorporate fuzzy logic into an optimization model, a necessary transformation of “fuzzy logic” into “fuzzy optimization” needs to be installed. In this case the correct combination of probability aspects with the unique characteristics of mine action data needs to be achieved.

In sum, the employment of fuzzy logic might be helpful, for very complex processes, when there is no simple mathematical model, for highly nonlinear processes or to be able to process combined tangible and intangible expected utilities or mine action benefits. According to literature on the specifics of this method, the employment of fuzzy logic is not recommendable if the conventional approach yields a satisfying result, an easily solvable and adequate mathematical model already exists, or the problem is *simply not solvable*.⁴⁵⁷ In the latter case, one enters again the domain of the “wicked problems”, which have been studied in the first research phase when addressing the tit-for-tat insurgency dynamics with its related use of IEDs.

B. Robust solutions to fuzzy optimization problems

Mine action prioritization or optimization problems will be rarely univocally determined: several scenarios are possible. During the case-study, it may be useful to replace the game or

⁴⁵⁶ In logic and mathematics, a logical value, also called a truth value, is a value indicating to what extent a proposition is true. In classical logic, the only possible truth values are true and false. However, other values are possible in other logics: fuzzy logic and other forms of multi-valued logic use more truth values than simply true and false. Algebraically, the set {true, false} forms a two-element Boolean algebra.

⁴⁵⁷ HELLMAN, M. (2001, March) Fuzzy Logic Introduction, Internet. Available at <http://www.fpk.tu-berlin.de/~anderl/epsilon/fuzzyintro4.pdf>, accessed on April 2007

decision theoretic concept of respectively best and optimal solution (for one set of data) by a concept of robust solution, i.e. “*sufficiently good*” for all or several scenarios.

This new paradigm opens a lot of new theoretical and methodological problems which go beyond the scope of this dissertation. It is, however, important that some of the basic principles of fuzzy optimization and the formulation of robust responses are recognized and touched upon. Certainly the fuzzy optimization problem for mine action prioritization presents an excellent real world case to test various approaches and methodologies. Moreover, study of robustness in multiple criteria decision-making is currently an active research domain.

“Thirty years ago, the scientific community in decision aiding was confronted to the challenge of solving problems where several criteria were present. This led to the development of MCDA and to a lot of new concepts and tools. We are now facing to the challenge of taking into account the uncertainties, which are irremediably present in any decision aiding process. This probably justifies the development of a specific vocabulary and theoretical framework, a new typology of the decision problems and new methodologies.”⁴⁵⁸

C. Prioritization requires (out)ranking: from *utility* functions to *fuzzy outranking*

a. From *utility* functions to *preference* functions

Optimizing short-term prioritization of mine action can be supported through *preference functions* rather than fully developed *utility functions*. These preference functions will allow the prioritizing or ranking of impacted communities *based on the differences between the evaluations* of possible alternatives/actions or based on differences in scoring regarding a predetermined set of criteria. The process itself will, nevertheless, still be utility-based.

The model needs, therefore, to distinctly disaggregate “human cost” from “socio-economic benefits and peacekeeping/building effects” in order to avoid the current mixing of incompatible data or strong with weak metrics; as highlighted in Phase-I and earlier in Phase-II. Statistical analysis and game theoretic *minimax* principles will need to further guide this process. In this context, *maximizing* mine action socio-economic *benefits* equals *minimizing* the socio-economic *impact* of landmines. *Minimizing* human *cost* means *maximizing* humanitarian (emergency) *relief*.

Phase-I touched upon the basic principles of (expected) utility when addressing the converging principles of utility theory and criteria selection.⁴⁵⁹ If the utility of a mine action activity is according to the following $u(x) \geq u(y)$, then it allows the decision maker to strictly prefer community x to y or is indifferent between them.

A straightforward example, suppose a decision maker's setting of the following:

$X = \{\text{communities with } n_1 \text{ landmine blockages of roads, farmlands, water sources, and } n_2 \text{ mine victims}\}$, and its:

Socio-economic utility function U_1 with:

$$\begin{aligned} u_R (\text{clearing 1 road blockage}) &= 1 \\ u_G (\text{clearing 1 grazing land blockage}) &= 2 \\ u_W (\text{clearing 1 water blockage}) &= 3 \\ u_F (\text{clearing 1 farmland blockage}) &= 4 \end{aligned}$$

Human cost utility function U_2 with:

$$u_A (\text{saving 1 person from a mine accident}) = 5$$

⁴⁵⁸ VINCKE, P. (2003) Forum: About Robustness Analysis. SMG, MCDA Newsletter, Université Libre de Bruxelles, Internet. Available at <http://www.inescc.pt/~ewgmcda/ForVincke.html>, accessed on 3 July 2007

⁴⁵⁹ See Phase-I, p. 26

In this simple case, a rational decision maker will prefer to allocate mine action resources to communities which cumulate the highest *combination* of *u-scores* from U_1 and U_2 . Note that for U_1 and U_2 to be uniform utility functions on X, they should be defined for every community in set X. Hence, a utility function simply rationalizes a *preference relation* on X if for every x, y belonging to the set X, $u(x) \geq u(y)$ if and only if $x \geq y$. If U_n rationalizes the \geq relation, then this implies \geq is *complete* and *transitive*, and hence rational.

In order to simplify calculations during the modelling effort, assumptions need to be made when developing these preference functions. Consequently, when assessing the mathematical characteristics of the expected utilities, it needs to be determined if the preference function is for example *linear*, *logarithmic* or *Gaussian*. If it can be determined or assumed that *linear* functions give the best or satisfactory results, then this would significantly simplify the modelling.

In addition, the logic of an outranking process may be considerably facilitated by using preference functions together with a reversing the *minimax* principles. This should, however, not be confused with *maximin*, which stands for *maximizing the minimum gain*. Hence, outranking of affected communities could take place based on indications of *maximum (or higher) loss*; e.g. impacted communities will outrank other communities in case they experience a higher human cost, more socio-economic impact and a higher (potential) disruption of peacekeeping/building efforts, or a combination thereof. In straightforward terms, the highest rankings will be allocated to the most affected communities.

b. From crisp preference to fuzzy outranking

The essence remains how the combined *costs*, *benefits* and *risk elements* studied generically in Phase-I can be optimized. In this regard, the *expected utility hypothesis* reflects the utility of mine action activities facing *uncertainty*, which is of particular importance regarding the human cost of the landmine problem. The expected utility is thus an *expectation* in terms of probability theory which projects a *level of uncertainty* regarding the above crisp *u-values*. Approaching now the modelling as a *fuzzy outranking process*, allows for the incorporation of *uncertainty*, *non-transitivity* and *incomparability* in the preference or outranking relationships.

“To some extent *fuzzy relations* offer a compromise between *value functions* and *preference relations*; their power of expressiveness is far beyond the one of value functions since they are good models for such phenomena as non-transitivity and incomparability. ELECTRE III, PROMETHEE and other methods for decision aid (e.g. Roy, 1990; Fodor & Roubens, 1994) build and exploit a *fuzzy outranking relation*.”⁴⁶⁰

In sum, the envisaged modelling through evaluation criteria remains utility-based but the fuzzy aspects of the prioritization problem requires a shift from modelling based on *crisp utility values* towards a *fuzzy outranking process* of affected communities. Determining the *indifference* or *preference* thresholds, inherent to fuzzy outranking, will depend on how the decision-maker will balance the model between having sufficient sensitivity and otherwise sufficient indifference. This will avoid that a particular mine affected community is preferred over others with sufficient certainty. The methodology to construct a fuzzy outranking relation will be subject of further modelling for the three mine action outputs. This will require an outranking algorithm which provides a fuzzy outranking of affected communities based on a maximization of:

- (1) the human cost;
- (2) socio-economic impact, and;
- (3) peacekeeping/building impact.

⁴⁶⁰ LOPEZ, L. (2005, January). Multicriteria decision aid application to a student selection problem. *Pesquisa Operacional*. Jan/Apr 2005, vol.25, no.1, p.45-68. Internet. Available at http://www.scielo.br/scielo.php?script=sci_arttext&pid=S0101-74382005000100004&lng=en&nrm=iso, accessed on 10 April 2007

III.2.5 Preliminary considerations for the risk modelling of human cost

A. Humanitarian relief: the most important mine action output?

Phase-I clarified how the majority, if not all, key stakeholders value the ultimate effectiveness of the outcome of the politics of mine action in terms of direct and measurable reductions of mine victims. This explains the extensive support “*zero-victim*” strategies generally receive. Hence, for modelling purposes and the development of credible preference functions, the case-study has to pursue a detailed collection of all past and current data available on the number of mine victims/survivors and exercise extensive statistical data analysis. Targeted or prioritized mine clearance and MRE were identified as two key conditions to accelerate the reduction in human cost. Mine victim data is, therefore, of essential importance for the proportionate allocation of mine action resources and has therefore a high relevancy in cross-country and/or cross-sector comparisons.

As addressed previously, the model should be able to incorporate important risk management considerations. The weighting process may need to anticipate the different risk profiles of the possible decision maker(s), being *risk-averse*, *risk-neutral* or *risk-acceptant*. An alternative way to study this is to assess different risk levels through *sensitivity analysis*. Fortunately, through the fuzzy logic and outranking methods the model will not be restrained by crisp mathematics, which also avoid the unethical practise to place monetary values on human life.

“Reducing the deaths and injuries from UXO accidents does free medical resources for other public health tasks. However, the medical costs of treating UXO victims is minuscule compared to the risk-reduction expenditures of UXO LAO, so a *cost-benefit case cannot be made unless monetary values are placed on human life and suffering*. Cost effectiveness analysis is a useful tool in such situations. For example, one can compare the average cost of saving one life through, say, malaria control or training programmes for traditional birth attendants.”⁴⁶¹

Mine accidents are considered in this study as stochastic events. The intend is to analyze them in a specific *population of interest*, which is an affected region to be defined in terms of affected communities or sub-regions according to statistical observations or broader research requirements. In this regard, the frequency by which mine accidents happen is envisaged as a function of statistical predictors or independent variables describing the state of the mine-affected community under study in a given observation period.

Compared to other humanitarian sectors, mine action has the advantage that several activities and achievements can be more easily translated, not necessarily simplified, into quantifiable terms. Nonetheless, incomplete data in an incomplete model leads to false conclusions or as the popular saying goes: “*garbage in, garbage out*”. Poor mine action data has frequently led to statistical data analysis giving way to unreliable deductions and trivial prognoses. This can be easily extended to the most important statistical data related to the human cost or number of mine victims.

“We do not know exactly how many people are killed and maimed by mines around the world. According to one rough estimate, 800 persons, mostly civilians, are killed by mines and unexploded ordnance every month, while several thousand are wounded, often very severely. None of the mine infested countries produce reliable statistics.”⁴⁶²

At this modelling stage, it can further be assumed that skilled usage of statistics *without estranging the target public* can contribute without precedent to a better understanding of the landmine problem. As touched upon before, it is assumed that the quality of mine action data is out of a statistical perspective problematic. However, the potential for useful deductions is likely and

⁴⁶¹ GICHD (2001). A Study of socio-economic approaches to Mine Action, Geneva, p.69

⁴⁶² FALTAS, S. (2000). *Peacebuilding - A Field Guide*, Getting Rid of Mines, Edited by Luc Reyhler and Thania Paffenholz, Colorado, p.429

has been encouraged by other research centres such as the Geneva International Centre for Humanitarian Demining (GICHD):

“More analysis is needed of the inferential potential of the survey data, and this will be facilitated when the correlation among indicators become empirically known from the first country surveys. It is desirable that developers of other indicator systems do similar investigations of their information value. As a form of such exercises, *computer simulation should be used aggressively.*”⁴⁶³

B. The quest for reliable statistical analysis of mine victim data

a. Former research

After extensive literature research, only one comprehensive publication could be consulted on comprehensive analysis of mine victim data.⁴⁶⁴ The doctoral thesis “*Risk Assessments of Minefields in Humanitarian Mine Action*” takes a Bayesian, binomial approach for its risk evaluation model. Notably, only two predictors or parameters are taken into consideration: the integer m , which denotes the number of so-called functional mines in a minefield, and the parameter q , which denotes the probability of a randomly selected mine being encountered by a person, a vehicle, etc... during a predefined observation period. The Bayesian study - to maintain clear distinction with the modelling efforts of this thesis hereafter called the *binomial approach* - elucidates upfront that the true values of the binomial parameters, which can indeed jointly characterize the state of the mined area, will rarely be known in advance. The study further states that beliefs about these values, based on whatever information is available, could be expressed in terms of probability distributions $p(m)$ and $p(q)$. The research philosophy of this dissertation is contrary to the binomial approach, the *focus being clearly on impacted communities and not on minefields*.

As studied in the first research phase, the binomial approach prepares the way for the introduction of Bayesian data analysis by which updates of the probability distributions can be generated from new accident data.⁴⁶⁵ Hence, updating probability distributions $p(m)$ and $p(q)$ through incoming accident statistics according to Bayes’ rule makes the suggested risk model dynamic. Out of a statistical point of view, the binomial approach presents an impressive exploration and exploitation of Bayes’ Rule but it is narrow in its methodology compared to the holistic and inclusive angle this thesis envisages. The following sections will further explain the main obstacles and propose alternative, statistical methods of what is expected to be available data during the case-study. Indeed, the major obstacle to a real-world application of the binomial model seems simply to be the lack of actual or credible information about the two parameters q and m . A considerable part of the consulted thesis focuses therefore on ways to provide information about q through statistical modelling.⁴⁶⁶ For better information on m , sources are suggested which might provide information of a more subjective or qualitative nature about the possibility of mine contamination in a given area. It is suggested optimistically that this should include military staff and other ex-combatants with local knowledge, and local or regional authorities.

In conclusion, the analytical challenge to estimate these parameters by the collection and synthesis of the above cited various types of information seems to *underestimate the statistical potential of the information largely available through the Landmine Impact Surveys*. The binomial approach presents comprehensive statistical methods which do not extensively explore possible predictors of mine accidents based on LIS data. Consequently, this dissertation will further explore

⁴⁶³ GICHD (2004). *A Study of Socio-Economic Approaches to Mine Action* (Revised edition of the Operational Handbook published in May 2002), Geneva, p.27

⁴⁶⁴ VISTISEN, J. (2006). *Risk Assessments of Minefields in Humanitarian Mine Action – A Bayesian Approach*, Ph.D. thesis, Informatics and Mathematical Modelling, Technical University of Denmark, p.17

⁴⁶⁵ See Phase-I, p.66-67

⁴⁶⁶ VISTISEN, J. (2006). *Risk Assessments of Minefields in Humanitarian Mine Action – A Bayesian Approach*, Ph.D. thesis, Informatics and Mathematical Modelling, Technical University of Denmark, p.17

how landmine risk assessment *can become operational in real-world conditions*. The researcher of the binomial model suggests admittedly similar areas of improvement.

“There is no doubt, however, that to exploit the full potential of the mixture model concept *in a real life application*, one should aim at the more generalized versions of mixture models in which *explanatory variables* enter into the expression of both the mixture components and the mixture parameters. [...] Given that explanatory variables are decided to be included in future work, the lack of relevant statistical material *leaves us to speculate on what might candidate as explanatory variables*. [...] All variables may possibly influence what might loosely be termed the level of human activity which again determines the probability parameter.”

b. A more holistic approach

In direct response to the research suggestions above, the statistical research in this thesis will endeavour to identify as much as possible candidate explanatory variables. The publication “*A Study of Socio-Economic Approaches to Mine Action*” emphasizes that mine action is just as much about *data analysis and processing* as it is about mines, which was also repeatedly highlighted in Phase-I.⁴⁶⁷ It is at this stage fair to conclude that the binomial approach of the cited thesis represented substantial innovation concerning data processing of mine action information, but that the binomial approach to risk assessment and ranking of minefields can and should be further expanded. If further improved and extended through the statistical identification of real world predictors, then decision makers will be better informed in their prioritization efforts. The envisaged approach need to *balance holistically the relevant factors* in order not to risk any oversimplification or lack of inclusiveness inherent to a minefield centred approach.

“To simplify matters we will deal exclusively with the risk aspect of mine contamination. This limitation does not intend to downplay the importance of socio-economic considerations in relation to HMA. In other words, it is to be understood that any systematic risk assessment based on the approach outlined in the following chapters should be properly counterbalanced by some kind of socio-economic analysis before a final ranking of minefields can be made.”⁴⁶⁸

From the earlier depicted simulation in figure III.3, figure III.8 below portrays just one affected community. As an initial mental estimate of possible causal relationships, the next section will describe possible explanatory variables for mine accidents. Once the mine victim data of the Afgan case-study undergoes a detailed assesment, a comprehensive statistical analysis will be undertaken. As for now, a sum-up of potential predictors, followed by some statistical considerations, will further complement the earlier description of the survey data available through the LIS. This warants that the statistical analysis will take from the start a realistic and pragmatic approach.

Fig. III.8: Socio-economic blockages and mine accidents

⁴⁶⁷ GICHD (2001), *A Study of Socio-Economic Approaches to Mine Action*, UNDP/GICHD Publication, Geneva

⁴⁶⁸ VISTISEN, J. (2006). *Risk Assessments of Minefields in Humanitarian Mine Action – A Bayesian Approach*, Ph.D. thesis, Informatics and Mathematical Modelling, Technical University of Denmark, p.12

C. Potential explanatory variables or predictors of mine/ERW accidents

As simulated in figure III.8, possible independent variables could be split up into three broad groups: *minefield-specific* variables, *community-specific* and *region-specific* variables.

a. Minefield-specific variables

1. Types of mines (AP-mine, AT-mine) and UXO or ERW

Fig. III.9: Different types of AP mines

Each mine has its specific activation characteristics, in more technical terms called the activation or *threshold pressure* depending on the fusing mechanism and position/depth of the mine in the ground.⁴⁶⁹ A risk assessment of a mixed mine-field (= different types of AP and/or AT-mines in the same minefield) is logically more complex than when only the characteristics of a single type of mine have to be taken into consideration. The presence of ERW could also significantly contribute to incidents.

2. Ageing of mines/ERW

Fig. III.10: Aged and corroded AT-mines

Although most mines maintain their basic characteristics for many years, a gradual degrading inevitably takes place. This can vary between a few years and many decades. Ageing or corrosion can render mines and/or ERW out of use or require far larger threshold pressures to activate them compared to the intended design.⁴⁷⁰

These ageing effects should not be considered as similar to the self-destructing mechanisms discussed during Phase-I; the “*non-persistent mines*”. The latter is an *active* mechanism, while ageing is a *passive* process.

3. Proximity/Distance of a Mined Area (MA) from the community

Proximity refers to the shortest distance (D) from a community centre (usually the church or the mosque) to the “starting point” of each MA. Intuitively it is suggested that MAs close to a community represent more of a danger than those that are more distant.

In general terms, distances from community centres to MAs tend to increase in areas of the country where settlements are more dispersed. In heavily populated areas, those distances tend to be shorter, reflecting the smaller areas-of-influence controlled by each community.⁴⁷¹

Fig. III.11: The proximity-factor

⁴⁶⁹ Picture from Internet. Available at <http://www.priceclash.co.uk/zero-landmine>, accessed on 12 April 2005

⁴⁷⁰ Picture from Internet. Available at <http://www.flickr.com/photos/willposh/285531134/in/photostream>, accessed on 2 February 2007

⁴⁷¹ Survey Action Centre. (2005). *Afghanistan Landmine Impact Survey*, Washington, p.36

4. Frequency and recency of previous accidents

Frequency refers to how consistently a minefield has caused incidents over time. It can be measured by dividing the two year victim reporting period of the LIS into four, six-month periods. Within each six-month period, minefields have seen one or more incidents or are free of any incidents. Hence, in reference to Bayes theorem, it needs to be examined how activity in prior periods affects the likelihood of mine incidents in future ones.

Recency, in the context of the LIS, refers to the two year time frame the survey considers for its collection of victim data. In this regard, the victim data of the Afghan LIS can be statistically analysed per semester. According to Bayesian principles, regression statistics of mine accidents of consecutive semesters could inform on the likelihood of a mine accident, based on prior and posterior probabilities.

Fig. III.12: Observation timeline of *recency* and *frequency* of mine accidents

5. Density/ Pattern/Size of mine laying – mine spacing

This parameter is also straightforward since the correlation between the numbers of landmines or ERW in a SHA and the risk of an accident is intuitively understood. It can further be assumed that mine laying patterns aim to be as effective as possible. Figure III.13⁴⁷² illustrates a patterned minefield along the Kuwait-Iraq border. “*Nuisance minefields*” can entail significantly higher risks compared to minefields laid with logic or linear patterns.

Fig. III.13: Minefields in Kuwait

“Roads, road shoulders, bridges, obstacles, and other structures must be cleared in open areas. The *main threat comes from nuisance mines*, so regard each potential site as a nuisance minefield and use established minefield clearing procedures.”⁴⁷³

The size of the suspected area in m² can also be statistically significant. All other things being equal, a tenfold increase in the size of the contaminated area within a community could be statistically studied on how it possibly relates to higher numbers of victims.

6. Precautionary measures: fencing and marking

Fig. III.14: Fencing/marketing of minefields

Apart from installing a MRE-education campaign, marking and especially fencing of mine fields can offer about the best alternative to mine clearance.⁴⁷⁴

As a potential explanatory variable, similar difficulties exist regarding the unbiased measurement of the possible beneficial effects of marking and fencing of minefields or areas with ERW.

⁴⁷² Picture from Internet. Available at www.quick3kgt.com/kuwaitpics.html, accessed on 23 February 2007

⁴⁷³ Combat clearance, Internet. Available at <http://www.globalsecurity.org/military/library/policy/army/fm/20-32/chap13b.html>, accessed on 3 June 2007

⁴⁷⁴ Picture from Internet. Available at <http://jpatokal.iki.fi/photo/travel/Israel/Golan>, accessed on 12 February 2007

b. Community-specific variables

1. Frequency and type of activities

The activities of the affected local population in the vicinity or returning refugees will greatly influence the exposed risk levels. A good understanding of their general interaction with a mine-infested environment is essential to seek how for example data on mined or blocked access to productive land, blocked roads and access to drinking water can assist in the prioritization process.

“During the period 1992-1994 some 2.5 million Afghans returned home. Following this spontaneous repatriation, a considerable increase in the number of victims is believed to have taken place. The deficient victims’ statistics can, however, not provide any confirmation here.”⁴⁷⁵

2. Frequency and type of risk behaviour

High risk behaviour generally finds its origin in lack of information or more precisely lack of Mine Risk Education. Apart from daily activities such as harvesting firewood, getting potable water, collecting scrap metal, risk behaviour such as tampering with ERW or ignoring marked areas can significantly increase the risks of having a mine or ERW accident.

“As expected, communities which claim business and trade as one of their important economic bases run a significantly lesser risk of mine and UXO incidents. This is in line with assumptions that business and trade create employment alternatives that take workers off contaminated land.”⁴⁷⁶

3. Risk groups

Certain groups of the affected population might face higher risks than others due to a combination of group specific activities and/or risk behaviour. Often women and children between the 4-14 age range are particularly vulnerable as they are more engaged in explorative activities like firewood collection, hunting, scrap-metal, etc...

4. Frequency, timing and type of Mine Risk Education

MRE can be very effective in raising fast and at relative low costs the level of knowledge of the affected population on how to mitigate the risks as much as possible. As studied in Phase-I, intense MRE can be the best choice during the start-up phase of a mine action programme. Early human cost reduction could be achieved if MRE takes place in an effective and targeted manner. The difficulty has been however to measure the MRE effect on human cost without bias from other factors or possible explanatory variables.

5. Strength of overall community institutions: *dependency factor*

Communities with a weak institutional infrastructure could be considerably more vulnerable due to a high dependency on few and limited (economic) resources. If there are no alternatives for farming contaminated land, and no institutional capability to explore other resources, then those communities could have no other options than to engage with their mine-affected environment.

“Communities in the north, dependent on a few critical resource areas and with limited institutional assets, find it much harder to adapt to the dangers of mines. Because the parameters affecting risk calculations are

⁴⁷⁵ BYRD and GILDESTAD. (2001). *Socio-Economic Impact of Mine Action in Afghanistan*, A Cost-Benefit Analysis, 2001, World Bank funded study, p.7

⁴⁷⁶ Survey Action Centre. Lebanon Landmine Impact Survey, Washington, Internet. Available at <http://www.sac-na.org/index.html>, accessed on 12 April 2005

few and their influence is strong, it is possible to predict mine incidents in the future.”⁴⁷⁷

c. Regional-specific (or local) factors

1. Seasonal factors and climate conditions

Seasonal factors can influence the behaviour of vulnerable population groups and both significantly increase or decrease the probability of mine accidents. For example, farming activities takes place with varying intensity levels in every season. This can result in dramatic spikes of victims every time agricultural activities increase in mine or ERW infested areas and drop to zero during wintertime. Conversely, wintertime may well induce higher mine victim rates due to increased firewood collecting activities. Summertime could also result in higher numbers of mine accidents in areas where numerous blockages exist to potable water sources.

Climate conditions could play an equally significant role in planning and executing mine clearance operations. Extreme weather conditions could hamper mine clearance operations – wet climate, heat, snow or frozen ground, etc suggest a higher priority be assigned to these areas when weather conditions permit. Drought could increase the dependency of the local population on poorly accessible or blocked potable water sources.

2. Geographic region and characteristics

Every region likely portrays its unique characteristics and influences how the population interacts with its environment. Affected communities in urban areas will differ significantly in their interaction compared to communities in mountainous or other areas with few roads or poor accessibility.

Importantly, to aggregate or disaggregate data according to a specific geographic region can result in better statistical significance due to possible reductions in variance of explanatory variables. Seeking the right balance between aggregating/disaggregating data according to certain geographic regions will be a research-intensive but likely very worthwhile effort to improve the credibility of later exploitation of statistical results.

3. Conflict history

As studied for Cambodia in Phase-I, factors like *years of conflict* and *years since last mine laying* demonstrate mine victim causality. Survey teams found that those factors most associated with past conflict, *particularly the length of time since conflict ended* in a community and the size of the contaminated area, outweigh other factors that might allow the community to adjust well to landmine threats of the affected region.⁴⁷⁸

4. Regional/local economy and or activities

The return of refugees can cause the economic activity to jumpstart, causing increased risks if the population depends on mined, productive land. Certain economic activities can be based on the collection of scrap metal, which often involves children in search of ERW. Reliance on business or trade also reduces a community’s risk factor, taking people away from intense use of land.

⁴⁷⁷ Survey Action Centre. Chad Landmine Impact Survey, Washington, Internet. Available at <http://www.sac-na.org/index.html>, accessed on 12 April 2005

⁴⁷⁸ Survey Action Centre. Lebanon Landmine Impact Survey, Washington, Internet. Available at <http://www.sac-na.org/index.html>, accessed on 12 April 2005

5. Terrain and other geographic features

Terrain conditions and vegetation can cause specific risks to the population and in particular to deminers. Annex F provides numerous examples.

d. Overview of possible predictors of mine/ERW accidents

Factor	Explanation
$p(z_t)$	Probability of observing Z_t accidents in $\Delta(t)$
T	Time
$\Delta(t)$	Observation period [t;t+1]
Z_t	Number of accidents in $\Delta(t)$
$Y(n)$	Years since last mine laying
$H(n)$	Conflict history – years of mine laying
$M(n)$	Number of minefields
$SEB(n)$	Number of socio-economic blockages
MC	Safety through mine clearance
M	Safety through “marking” of minefields
F	Safety through “fencing” of minefields
MRE	Safety through Mine Risk Education
B	Risks due to dangerous behaviour
D	Risks due to density/pattern of mine laying
L	Risks due to location
A	Risks due to type of activities
T	Risks due to type of mines and/or ERW

To calculate $p(z_t)$, i.e., the probability of Z_t mine accidents during a timeframe $\Delta(t)$, it is valuable to consider the possible sequence of events, which are prerequisites for a mine accident: firstly, during $\Delta(0)$ there has to be a landmine triggered⁴⁷⁹ by a person or a vehicle, etc. Whether a mine is triggered during a random contact will in general depend on the type of activity during the contact: walking, farming, firewood collection, driving, etc.

To incorporate this variability into the model could bog down the study at this stage in rather tactical considerations, similar to variables as the type of mine, threshold pressure, fusing mechanism, condition of mine (ageing and corrosion). Therefore, it will be essential to develop a mine action risk assessment capability which can be combined with the overall *strategic set-up* of the normative model based on multiple criteria decision analysis. To remind, the risk assessment element of this model needs to offer the decision maker the possibility to balance human cost versus socio-economic benefits and peacekeeping/building effects. As minefield accidents by nature are random events, the central quantity in a risk assessment is the probability distribution $p(z)$, where z denotes the number of accidents during a future observation period of a certain length. During an observation period $\Delta(t)$, in a symbolic and non-exhaustive formula, the explanatory variables influencing the probability of mine accidents could be presented as follows:

$$p(z_t) = [Y(n) + H(n) + M(n) + SEB(n)] + [B + D + L + A] - [MC + M + F + MRE]$$

All the factors above are likely to influence the threats and risks inherent to mine-affected regions and impacted population. Through statistical analysis of landmine victim related data, the relationship should be established. Factors which prove to be statistically significant can be retained as credible predictors of mine accidents.

⁴⁷⁹ Military-tactical elements, such as threshold pressure required to detonate a landmine are due to the research aim of this doctorate not taken into consideration.

The reliability of the statistical analysis and model building will depend largely on the number of mine-affected communities and/or number of mine victims. Affected regions with low numbers of victims will probably not portray with relative strength the factors contributing to mine accidents.

D. Important statistical parameters and techniques

a. Statistical significance of mine victim predictors

A statistical result of analysing mine victim data will be called *significant* if it is unlikely to have occurred by chance. It is suggested at this stage that a standard level of significance of 5% should be maintained throughout the study. Hence, performing a test of significance, assuming the significance level is 5%, and the p-value is lower than 5% then the *null hypothesis* would be rejected. Informally, the outcome is said to be “*statistically significant*” for the mine victim predictor being considered.

b. Goodness of statistical fit – coefficient of determination: R^2

By definition, the *goodness of statistical fit* or *coefficient of determination*, R^2 [R-square] is the fraction of the total squared error that is explained by the model. It is with other words the proportion of a sample variance of a response variable that is “explained” by the predictor. Thus values approaching 1 or 100% are most desirable. Hence, this *goodness of statistical fit* is an important coefficient to consider for the risk management aspects of the model and the *allocation of weights*.

Inevitably, mine action data contains significant *irreducible* error, with likely no amount of statistical fits able to improve the low values of R^2 . However, even with a marginally low goodness of statistical fit, statistical analysis can indicate some interesting trends. Generally, statistical significance depends on sufficient confidence and logic understanding of the *causal relationship between the variables*.

Importantly, to compensate low goodness of statistical fits, the statistical analysis should not pursue very high-order polynomial models in the mistaken but widely held belief that as the number of parameters approaches the number of observations, the model can be made to pass through every point. In this regard, two important statistical techniques or principles need to be taken into account; the effects of *aggregating data* and *sample size*.

c. Aggregating data

Unprocessed mine victim information will unlikely permit too much noise and lower the significance of statistical observations. Inaccurate or inconsistent data can hinder a programme's ability to understand its current – and future – prioritization problems. This leads to poor decisions that can cause a host of negative results, including lost lives.

As part of an effective data enhancement strategy, aggregating data can help better understand a mine action environment. Aggregating data describes data combined from several measurements which could significantly enhance trend recognition. In its simplest form, aggregated data is data that has been “summarized”. This means that some form of detailed mine action data has been rolled up to less detail. Summarized can mean that the data was rolled up or averaged but there are also more complex transformation rules to summarize data.

d. Sample size of mine victim data and clustering

The *sample size* of a statistical sample of mine affected communities is the number of observations or measurements that constitute it and is typically denoted *n*. The larger the sample, the more sure the statistical findings reflect the population. This indicates that for a given confidence level, the larger the sample size, the smaller the confidence interval. This is an important consideration for this dissertation, keeping in mind that in order to detect regional-specific trends, statistical analysis needs to be performed on smaller sample sizes in order to establish causal relationships between possible statistical predictors and mine victims. There are however also important practical considerations related to the populations and/or sample size, the quality of data and possible clustering and/or aggregation of data.

“The final sample size should be scrutinized for practicality. If it is unacceptable, the only way to reduce it is to accept less precision in the sample estimate. Of course the sample size you select must make sense. This is where the trade-offs usually occur. We want to *take enough observations to obtain reasonably precise estimates of the parameters of interest* but we also want to do this within a practical resource budget. The important thing is to quantify the risks associated with the chosen sample size.”⁴⁸⁰

Arbitrary clustering of mine action data into clusters of similar characteristics presents the difficulty of deciding what constitutes a good clustering. There is probably no absolute “best” criterion which would be independent of the final aim of the clustering. Consequently, it is the data of the case-study itself which must supply this criterion, in such a way that the result of the clustering will warrant a satisfactory sample size of a mine affected region with similar characteristics together with a sample size large enough for credible statistical analysis.

III.2.6. Preliminary considerations for modelling the socio-economic impact

A. Cross-cutting characteristics

As highlighted during the first research phase, mine action is extensively cross-cutting in terms of qualitative and quantitative, tangible and intangible, socio-economic benefits. Hence, the intrinsic modelling needs to have the flexibility to incorporate in the prioritization process continuously evolving socio-economic factors which can be of a very different nature. These benefits could either be recurrent, cumulative or non-cumulative. As concluded in Phase-I, most of these benefits are of the “*cost reduction*” type. According the LIS-data available, focus should go to the skilful incorporation of weak-metrics data in terms of socio-economic blockages.

If possible, enrichment of data need to be achieved through the incorporation of *discount factors* and quantifiers regarding the *socio-economic value of land* and the *level of socio-economic dependency* an affected community faces vis-à-vis inaccessible socio-economic resources.

B. Discounting and the time-value of socio-economic benefits

a. Future values versus present values

The phenomenon of time-value of payoffs was explained at several occasions during Phase-I. To remind, no discount factors will be considered regarding the future reduction of “human cost” or for the relatively intangible peacekeeping/building effects of mine action. Discounting of future socio-economic benefits should preferably be part of the initial modelling effort. It however highly depends on the availability of credible and quantifiable data. If given a choice between receiving

⁴⁸⁰ National Institute of Standards and Technology, *Selecting Sample Sizes*, Engineering Statistics Handbook [online] (Gaithersburg, MD: National Institute of Standards and Technology), Internet. Available at www.itl.nist.gov/div898/handbook/ppc/section3/ppc333.htm, accessed on 19 June 2006

socio-economic benefits or payoffs today and the same amount sometime in the future, the model should suggest reference for affected communities where mine action will achieve the quickest benefits. Similarly, most actors will want to delay a cost or a negative payoff.⁴⁸¹ With other words, actors discount the value of future benefits. The rate of discount is calculated by assessing how much more of the future benefit or payoff a person would demand to exchange it for the benefit today. For example, a decision-maker would have to choose between a socio-economic benefit of 1000 US\$ today from 1100 US\$ a year from now. If the decision-maker discounts his future benefit with more than 10%, then the rational choice would be the 1000 US\$ today. In case the annual discount rate is 10%, the equivalent amount in two years would need to be equal or more than: $US\$1000 \times (1.10)^2 = US\1210 in order to make the decision-maker consider to give up his immediate benefit of cleared land.

With r = annual discount rate and y = number of years, the general formula is:

$$\text{Future Value (FV)} = \text{Present Value} * (1 + r)^y$$

$$\text{Present Value (PV)} = \text{Future Value} / (1 + r)^y$$

Concretely, the intended purpose of the model is to show the decision maker the best way forward and identify the mine action areas of greater and lesser opportunity, prioritise the mine action options and clarify the differences between the options. As a positive spin-off, it will offer to donor and mine-affected countries a better understanding of the essential decision-making factors, improve the communication, cooperation and coordination, and prescribe the best allocation of resources to achieve the aforementioned goals. The model is envisaged to have a high level of flexibility in order to incorporate at all times the generation of new and better options.

b. Net Present Value (NPV) and the Internal Rate of Return (IRR)

This is equivalent to the basic formula for discounting a future value to calculate the present value:

$$PV = FV / (1 + r)^y$$

The NPV is simply the present value of benefits minus the present value of costs. The basic formula for any one future year is:

$$NPV_y = (B_y - C_y) / (1 + r)_y$$

where:

$$\begin{aligned} NPV_y &= NPV \text{ for year } y \\ B_y &= \text{Value of benefits in year } y \\ C_y &= \text{Costs in year } y \end{aligned}$$

When repeating the calculation for each year and adding the results together, the full formula is:

$$NPV_y = \sum (B_y - C_y) / (1 + r)^y$$

The internal rate of return (*IRR*) is the discount rate that would have to prevail for the *NPV* to equal zero, or with other words to make the *PV* of the stream of benefits equal the *PV* of the stream

⁴⁸¹ GICHD (2004). A Study of socio-economic approaches to Mine Action, Geneva, p.42

of costs. A high *IRR* indicates a good investment. This discount aspect can be further integrated in the earlier optimization formula as per below.

$$OPT \text{ Mine Action} = OPT \left\{ \frac{\sum_{n=1}^5 HR_n + \sum_{y=1}^x \frac{\left(\sum_{n=1}^5 SEB_n \right)^y - C^y}{(1+r)^y} + \sum_{n=1}^5 PB_n}{v + w + x + y + z} \right\}$$

Although theoretically sound, the above NPV approach assumes an *unlikely amount of certainty for funding allocation in a mine action related context*. It does not take into account the weak data and highly unpredictable environment in which socio-economic benefits will be generated and/or lost. The NPV presumption that investment decisions in mine action are either reversible or now-or-never propositions is largely unrealistic. *Nature* and the uncertain or undetermined responsiveness and receptiveness of the other actors towards mine action problems and solutions is a prelude of the game theoretic dimension of the extrinsic modelling process. When solely regarded as socio-economic investment opportunities, the choices of other actors and the choice of timing can alter the outcome of mine action programmes in many critical ways. Preferably, the *NPV rule should be adjusted or simplified for modelling purposes* in order to reflect the high amount of uncertainty.

C. LIS-data and clearance of socio-economic blockages

As explained, the LIS uses weak socio-economic metrics with information limited to blockages. Although more detailed information would be helpful, focusing on these blockages fits well into the modelling philosophy of impact reduction. Indeed, often mine action programmes have no other choice than focus with the limited resources on *removing socio-economic blockages*. In this case, minefields are carefully assessed to determine the *minimum clearance activity required* to remove the blockage. In most cases this will not require clearance of the entire minefield, but rather opening an appropriate passage and marking the remaining area for clearance at a (much) later stage. While it may be less in line with the “complete clearance” objectives of the Mine Ban Treaty or less efficient in logistics terms, the program will reap *quicker and greater benefits versus costs expended*.

In assessing the blockage - and thus the positive impact of removing that blockage - it is important to confirm whether the removal of this blockage would be beneficial with immediate or short-term effects. That is, will the land be used as intended simply with the removal of the blockage, or does it require provision or investment of additional resources? If it does require further resources, and they are already guaranteed, then this is a particularly high priority; if it requires further resources and they are not assured, then this should be considered a lower priority site for clearance. Clearing these sites will actually constitute wastage since potential productive output of the cleared area will not be realized immediately after clearance has taken place and the area may lay dormant until other inputs arrive. Hence, discount effects could be incorporated in the model according to ordinal scales below.

Scoring	Exploitation of cleared land?
HIGH (or 3)	0 to 1 year
MEDIUM (or 2)	1 to 2 years
LOW (or 1)	More than 2 years

Post-conflict recovery and/or socio-economic studies often provide workable parameters which indicate the (economic) value of land in productivity terms. This could be coupled with LIS-data to enrich the outranking process with more quantifiable data.

Ranking methods could be further enhanced based on information regarding socio-economic alternatives for blocked assets. It is obvious that the impact is far greater when the access is blocked to the one and only water source of a community than for a community with many alternatives. Socio-economic value of land and the level of socio-economic dependency could be modelled in a similar manner.

Scoring	Socio-economic alternative?
HIGH (or 3)	NO
MEDIUM(or 2)	MAYBE/PARTIALLY
LOW (or 1)	YES

III.2.7. Preliminary considerations for modelling peacekeeping and peacebuilding effects

A. Mine action “for peace”

As studied in Phase-I, peacekeeping and peacebuilding effects come in many forms, including promoting human security, confidence-building measures, power-sharing arrangements, electoral support, strengthening the rule of law, and economic and social development.⁴⁸² A minimal strategic objective for peacekeeping is that past violence does not recur. A more ambitious threshold is that democratic processes are seen to take hold, post-conflict and economic recovery financed by donors gives way to self-sustained growth, divided societies start to deal collectively with memories of the past as well as visions for the future, and a state of law emerges.

It is obvious that peacekeeping effects cannot be strictly separated from humanitarian relief and socio-economic benefits. For modelling and delineation purposes, a rather narrow interpretation of peacekeeping is suggested. For that reason, the focus will be on concrete factors which could jeopardize the creation of conditions for sustainable peace.

B. The challenge of modelling *tangible* peacekeeping/building effects

a. Mandated mine action tasks versus mine action funded through voluntary contributions

Phase-I addressed how mine action can belong to a variety of mandated tasks of a peacekeeping/building operation. In a few examples, mine action has been mandated as a critical activity to the peace process. Mandated mine action activities enjoy assured funding through UN assessed peacekeeping budgets. This can imply that prioritization is less a challenge since funding is specifically approved for a predetermined set of mine action activities. It is even possible that in the same country mandated mine action is taking place next to mine action funded through voluntary contributions.⁴⁸³ Hence, the short-term prioritization process may only be required for the latter.

⁴⁸² United Nations DPKO, Internet. Available at <http://www.un.org/Depts/dpko/dpko/faq/q1.htm>, accessed on 11 February 2007

⁴⁸³ This is the case for the mine action programmes in Eritrea and Ethiopia. Mine action is funded through the peacekeeping budget of UNMEE for clearing mines in the Temporary Security Zone (TSZ) or for demarcation activities at the Eritrean-Ethiopian border.

b. Disarmament, Demobilization & Reintegration (DDR)

In order to allow prioritization, geographic differentiation is required. The LIS does not provide any information in this regard. Hence, other sources of information need to indicate if there are confined areas where the integration of former combatants is an important confidence-building measure. National or local authorities could express preference to intensify mine action in these areas where DDR programmes could successfully absorb former combatants in order to reduce the risk of relapse to conflict.

c. Insurgency activities and/or use of IED

The LIS provides sufficient information to differentiate between impacted communities according to the type of contamination: anti-personnel mines, anti-tank mines and/or explosive remnants of war. Analyzing IED attacks indicates that the majority of them are made from ERW and anti-tank mines.

The risks of IED and/or landmines insurgency attacks need to be staffed through threat assessments which indicate a clear intent of the factions to recycle landmines and ERW for insurgency activities. Preferably, an accurate geographic threat mapping should be part of this assessment. In sum, the IED threat depends on the presence and/or *availability of mines/ERW* and the *level of intent to use them or modify them into IEDs*.

III.2.8. Pulling it together: Multiple Criteria Decision Analysis for mine action prioritization

A. Multiple criteria decision theoretic principles

Multiple criteria decision analysis (MCDA) has known a very rapid development during the last twenty years and has been characterized by a lot of methods and applications in need of more consolidated theoretical concepts. There is a plethora of MCDA modelling techniques. Some techniques are better suited to some decision contexts than others. There are, however, many common elements of the various techniques, which will be addressed below.

As explained, the research in this phase envisages the development of a prescriptive or *normative* MCDA model. Seeking the most optimal allocation of limited resources is a common problem confronting most high level decision makers; however, the complex politics of mine action add an extra dimension to it. Often MCDA does not offer an optimal solution in a strict sense, since no alternative can be the best one on each criterion.

This underscores the notion of a *best or robust* response compared to an *optimal* one. For example, the human cost and socio-economic criteria can be conflicting. Compromise solutions have to be considered, which brings up the key issue: how to find the best compromise solution and, equally important, convince the decision makers it is the best response?

“Multicriteria decision aid is usually found useful as it can help decision makers to evaluate problems involving conflicting objectives, since they can take simultaneously into account several sources of judgment even if measured in different units. Under such difficult conditions MCDA methods foster rationality in decision-making and can support decision making as a process. In this sense evaluation constitutes an instrument which is able to *enhance political as well as technical debate*, helping to *build consensus* and to control the ‘quality’ of different proposals.”⁴⁸⁴

⁴⁸⁴ CARBONE, F. (2000). MCDA Methods Comparison: Environmental Policy Evaluation applied to a case study in Italy, 3rd Biennial Conference of the European Society for Ecological Economics, Vienna, May 3 – 6, Internet. Available at <http://www.wu-wien.ac.at/project/esee2000/PapersPDF/H300.pdf>, accessed on 12 July 2006

Fig. III.15: Multiple criteria decision analysis, process and envisaged outcome

This makes the task of prioritization of mine action programs even more daunting, since it clearly is not limited to a mathematical or business exercise of a single decision-maker. As in many other multilateral environments, mine action planning and resource allocation is characterized by multiple decision makers, stakeholders and other interested parties making inputs to the decision-making process. Ideally, prioritization and strategic planning for mine action requires the collaborative effort of all relevant stakeholders in order to create common ownership of the problem and proposed solutions.

This process also requires an ongoing and/or dynamic evaluation, one that can be easily replicated and used to justify the mine action resources requested. As illustrated in figure III.15, this works best on the traditional basis of (1) a set of options or alternatives, (2) a set of evaluation criteria and (3) a set of

potential strategic scenarios. The scoring of each option in each strategic scenario will result in a ranking which can further inform the decision-making process.

It needs to be carefully assessed if advanced MCDA leads to a level of complexity that is too great for any pragmatic approach. It should be the contrary and, therefore, relying on advanced decision support systems may be both desirable and inevitable. Often the impression exists at field or national level that too many elements are to be compared in too many ways, resulting in a sentiment that oranges are being compared, not even to apples, but to shoes.

B. Responding to the MCDA requirement

a. Selection of a suitable Decision Support System

A *decision support system* (DSS) can take many different forms and the term is used in many different ways. In general, a DSS is simply a computerized system which assist a decision analysis or decision-makings process. Because there are many approaches to decision-making, the concept of DSS in decision theory is very broad. Supporting a *decision* means assisting the information analysis, the generation of alternatives and making of (strategic) choices. In the context of the modelling effort, supporting the *decision-making process* involves supporting the evaluation and/or the comparison of alternatives. In practice, DSS are usually software applications that perform such a supporting role. Hence, the selection of such an application needs to respond well to the modelling requirements formulated in the introduction of this chapter. It needs, therefore, to be an interactive, flexible, and adaptable software system which is able to use different types of data, thereby providing an easy-to-use interface and allowing for the decision maker's own insights.

b. The (out)ranking requirement

1. Preference Ranking Organisation Method for Enrichment Evaluations (PROMETHEE)

It would go beyond the scope of this study to provide a comparative analysis of possible DSS for prioritization of mine action. ELECTRE III and PROMETHEE were cited earlier in the context of fuzzy optimization. In brief, both are suitable to address the prioritization or ranking requirement of a high number of affected communities or alternatives.

A preference grew for PROMETHEE, developed further under the name *Decision Lab 2000*⁴⁸⁵ by Belgian Prof. J.P. Brans and B. Mareschal at the Brussels Free Universities. Its anticipated ability, strong visuals and ease to assist decision maker(s) during complex fuzzy decision-making processes was the decisive reasons. Since PROMETHEE multiple criteria methods are based on *fuzzy* evaluations of the differences between pairs of alternatives for each criterion, it is anticipated it will respond well to the fuzzy logic requirement. PROMETHEE is further a straightforward non-parametric method,⁴⁸⁶ which ranks a number of objects on the basis of a range of variables or criteria and preference functions based on a transparent outranking algorithm. The PROMETHEE-Decision Lab 2000 software allows for a user-friendly interface, further enhanced through the *Geometrical Analysis for Interactive Assistance (GAIA)*.⁴⁸⁷ As will be illustrated throughout the modelling efforts, this graphical tool has the potential to facilitate considerably the decision-making analysis.

2. The basic concept of *generalized criteria and preference functions*

PROMETHEE treats matrixes with $a_1, a_2, \dots, a_i, \dots, a_n$, being n potential alternatives for action or affected communities and $C_1, C_2, \dots, C_j, \dots, C_k$ being k evaluation criteria. A *generalized criterion* is associated to each criterion in order to take into account the scale and deviation features of the indicator(s) related to the criteria. For this purpose the (normalized) preference function $P(a_1, a_2)$ giving the degree of preference of alternative a_1 over alternative a_2 for criterion C_i is defined as a function of the deviation $d = C_i(a_1) - C_i(a_2)$. Figure III.16 illustrates the typical non-decreasing function $H(d) = P(a_1, a_2)$, $d \geq 0$ for a criterion C_i to be maximized. For each generalized criterion $C_i(a)$ to be optimized, at most two parameters have to be identified by the decision-maker.

(1) Indifference threshold : q

High if uncertainty, low accuracy of measurement or surveyed mine action related data

(2) *Strict* preference threshold : p

As small as possible if no loss of information is advisable (accurate data)

$q < d < p$: *hesitation or uncertainty zone*

⁴⁸⁵ Visual Decision was founded in 1998 to fill the gap between the so-called traditional '*decision support systems*' (DSS) which were mostly intensive data processing applications with limited integration in the decision-making process itself. Internet. Available at www.visualdecision.com, accessed on 10 February 2007

⁴⁸⁶ Non-parametric models differ from parametric models in that the model structure is not specified *a priori* but is instead determined from data and that the number and nature of the parameters are flexible and not fixed in advance.

⁴⁸⁷ Decision Lab 2000 was developed by (U.L.B. and V.U.B.). PROMETHEE and GAIA form the methodological basis of the PromCalc software, which have been used in many applications in various countries. The computing core of Decision Lab has been developed by the U.L.B. team under an exclusive agreement with Visual Decision. Some users of Decision Lab will use only basic functions while others, looking for more strength, will benefit from advanced sensitivity analysis.

Fig. III.16 The basic concept of a fuzzy preference function

The fuzzy logic principles discussed earlier can be established through the PROMETHEE threshold structures. This can be an intermediary area, between the indifference and the strict preference, where the decision-maker would likely hesitate between both situations, based on the information presented. Deviating from Boolean logic, this observation requires the introduction of a preference model including two distinct thresholds: the *indifference* threshold, under which the decision-maker is clearly indifferent, and the (strict) *preference* threshold, above which the decision-maker has a clear strict preference. The intermediary area is considered as a region where he hesitates between indifference and preference. The properties of these structures, in connection with the conditions which are imposed on the thresholds, constitute a research subject for the case-study.

PROMETHEE requests that for each criterion a specific preference function is defined. This function is used to compute the degree of preference associated to the best alternative in case of pairwise comparisons. PROMETHEE calculates positive and negative preference flows for each alternative. The positive flow is expressing how much an alternative is *dominating* (power) the other ones, and the negative flow how much it is *dominated* (weakness) by the other ones. Based on these flows, the PROMETHEE I partial ranking is obtained. PROMETHEE II will provide a *complete ranking* based on the *net flows* in case the positive and negative preference flows result in an incomparability.

3. Choices of generalized criterion – preference functions

Six possible shapes of preference functions are available in PROMETHEE.⁴⁸⁸

Fig. III.17 The six generalized criteria of PROMETHEE

⁴⁸⁸ These are described in detail in BRANS, J-P and MARESCHAL, B. (2002) PROMETHEE-GAIA. Une méthodologie d'aide à la décision en présence de critères multiples, Brussels, Edition de l'Université de Bruxelles, p.51-57

- (1) Type I - Usual Criterion: there is “indifference” only if there is no difference between the actions scores
- (2) Type II - U-shape criterion (quasi-criterion): there is “indifference” as long as the scores difference is less than q
- (3) Type III - V-shape criterion: criterion with linear preferences; the preference varies linearly with the difference
- (4) Type IV - Multi-level criterion: between the scores between 0 and p. If the difference is more than p, the action is strictly preferred. There is “indifference” as long as the score difference is less than q, low preference if the scores difference is between q and p, and strict preference if the scores difference is higher than p.
- (5) Type V - Linear criterion (with indifference area): there is “indifference” as long as the score difference is less than q. The preference varies linearly with the difference between the scores between q and p, and becomes strict if the scores difference is higher than p.
- (6) Type VI - Gaussian criterion: the preference increases with the difference between the scores as expressed in:

$$H_j(d_j) = 1 - e^{-\frac{d_j^2}{2s_j^2}}$$

4. Prioritization or outranking procedure of affected communities

A number or a set A of *possible actions or alternatives*, representing the five affected communities (A,B,C,D,E), to be prioritized or ranked in order of preference: $[a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5]$

A number of evaluation *criteria*: $[C_1, C_2, C_3, \dots, C_m]$

The *weights* assigned to each criterion: $[w_1, w_2, w_3, \dots, w_m]$

A set of *preference functions* defines how one alternative is to be preferred relative to another or the way in which alternative “ a_1 ” is preferred over action “ a_2 ”: $[P_1, P_2, P_3, \dots, P_m]$

The stepwise outranking procedure is as follows:

Step 1: Transformation of the *scoring* matrix to a *difference* matrix: for each criterion, the entries of the raw data matrix are subtracted from each other in all possible ways to create a *difference d matrix*.

Step 2: Application of the preference function: for each criterion, the selected *preference function* $P(a_1, a_2)$ is applied to decide how much the outcome a_1 is preferred to a_2 .

Step 3: Calculation of an overall or global *preference index*, π

$$\pi(a_1, a_2) = \sum_{j=1}^m w_j P_j(a_1, a_2)$$

This relationship provides an overall index π , for comparison of preference of affected communities.

If weights are normalized so that $\sum_{j=1}^m w_j = 1$, then the following can be stated:

$\mathcal{I}(a_1, a_2) \approx 0 \Leftrightarrow$ weak global preference of a_1 over a_2

$\mathcal{I}(a_1, a_2) \approx 1 \Leftrightarrow$ strong global preference of a_1 over a_2

Step 4: Calculation of outranking flows for the set A

As visualized, the positive outranking flow, (φ^+), indicates how an affected community outranks (dominates) all others while the negative outranking flow, (φ^-), shows how all others outrank each object (is dominated). In sum, the higher the φ^+ and the lower the φ^- the higher the preference for an affected community.

Step 5: Comparison of outranking flows: application of the rules below for pair wise comparisons of all results produces a partial ranking or partial pre-order of the affected communities:

1. a_1 outranks a_2 if:

$$\begin{aligned} &\varphi^+(a_1) > \varphi^+(a_2) \text{ and } \varphi^-(a_1) < \varphi^-(a_2) \\ &\text{or} \\ &\varphi^+(a_1) > \varphi^+(a_2) \text{ and } \varphi^-(a_1) = \varphi^-(a_2) \\ &\text{or} \\ &\varphi^+(a_1) = \varphi^+(a_2) \text{ and } \varphi^-(a_1) < \varphi^-(a_2) \end{aligned}$$

2. a_1 is indifferent to a_2 if:

$$\varphi^+(a_1) = \varphi^+(a_2) \text{ and } \varphi^-(a_1) = \varphi^-(a_2)$$

3. a_1 cannot be compared with a_2 otherwise

Step 6: Calculation of net outranking flow:

$$\varphi = \varphi^+(a) - \varphi^-(a)$$

This relationship eliminates the rule where a cannot be compared to b, thus removing the partial pre-order; the expression of net outranking flow, φ , is intuitively more convenient but the information is less reliable. This will be illustrated through the generic example.

5. Geometrical Analysis for Interactive Assistance (GAIA)

As briefly touched upon earlier, the *GAIA plane*⁴⁸⁹ offers a visual representation of the data, with some clearly defined symbolic elements:

- (1) Criteria are represented by axes. The orientation of the axes shows possible similarities or conflicts between criteria.
- (2) Actions or alternatives are represented by their symbols. Their positions enable the user to identify the strong and weak features of the respective alternatives in accordance with the criteria set. Upward triangles will be used for mine-affected communities.
- (3) The “*II*-decision axis” or “*decision stick*” represents the condensed weighting of the criteria. Modifying the weights of the criteria will cause the *II*-decision axis to move dynamically in the GAIA plane. A three dimensional representation of the decision axis emphasizes the position of the axis.

Fig. III.18: Projections on the GAIA Plane

In summary, the *GAIA plane* offers an excellent overview of conflicts among criteria, characteristics of actions, and reasonableness of criteria. In *Decision Lab 2000*, this method is used collectively with the three dimensional representation to help the decision maker identify the best compromise solution. As common with any graphical representation, the interpretation of the GAIA plane is restricted to a limited number of alternatives. This is definitively not a shortcoming of *Decision Lab 2000*, but a general difficulty with large decision tables and their visualization. This will become clearer when not five but several hundreds of mine-affected communities need to be prioritized and projected.

C. Multistage MCDA applied on the small-scale simulation

For purposes of illustration, the following sections will explain how MCDA could be applied in for the five affected communities from figure III.3. It will demonstrate how even in this overly simplified setting it is already a challenge to prioritize mine action. Hence, before taking up the case-study, this example will explain the basic MCDA *mechanisms* and *consecutive stages*, thereby illustrating how the potential of PROMETHEE before engaging much more complex and sizable decision-matrixes during the case-study.

a. Socio-Economic Impact

1. Socio-economic impact scoring of affected communities

Based on LIS survey data, scoring data can be determined, justified and entered into the multi-criteria decision matrix in order to obtain a prioritization of the five options. Considering each affected community as a competing alternative, this implies 5 series of scoring on the 11 socio-economic criteria illustrated in matrix II.10.

⁴⁸⁹ BRANS and MARESCHAL (2005). op cit, Multi Objective Pinch Analysis (MOPA) using PROMETHEE to Evaluate Resource Efficiency, Hannes Schollenberger, proceedings of the International Scientific Annual Conference Operations Research 2005; Bremen

The scoring matrix either allows to use numerical values or, in this case, Boolean values. The result is exactly the same since the Boolean values are automatically converted to numeric values. The weight vectors can either be normalized or, in this case, maintain their allocated values by, for example, a broad group of stakeholders.

	Mines?	UXO?	Pasture?	RF-Crop?	Irr-Crop?	Drink-water?	Other water?	Non Cult-Area?	Housing?	Admin?	Other Infra?
Min/Max	Maximize	Maximize	Maximize	Maximize	Maximize	Maximize	Maximize	Maximize	Maximize	Maximize	Maximize
Weight	2.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	2.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
Preference Function	Usual	Usual	Usual	Usual	Usual	Usual	Usual	Usual	Usual	Usual	Usual
Threshold Unit	Absolute	Absolute	Absolute	Absolute	Absolute	Absolute	Absolute	Absolute	Absolute	Absolute	Absolute
Average Performance	0.8000	0.8000	0.6000	0.4000	0.4000	0.6000	0.6000	0.6000	0.4000	0.4000	1.0000
Standard Dev.	0.4472	0.4472	0.5477	0.5477	0.5477	0.5477	0.5477	0.5477	0.5477	0.5477	0.0000
Unit	Scale	Scale	Scale	Scale	Scale	Scale	Scale	Scale	Scale	Scale	Scale
Community A	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes
Community B	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Community C	Yes	No	No	No	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	Yes
Community D	No	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Community E	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes

Matrix II.10: Scoring matrix of the five communities on the 11 socio-economic criteria

Based on the earlier discussed modelling considerations, more criteria can be added to this matrix in order to incorporate preference functions to reflect differences between blocked access to high or low value socio-economic resources, immediate or distant socio-economic benefits and/or socio-economic dependency pending alternatives to blocked access to socio-economic resources.

As discussed earlier, the affected communities are regarded as alternatives/units evaluated within an outranking context. In order to do so the preference functions are according to a *maximization* of the socio-economic impact, human cost and peacekeeping effects. Hence, the more socio-economic blockages a community experiences or both mines and UXO are present, the more favourable the community will score on the 11 criteria illustrated above, resulting in the positive and/or negative flows per community. The total sum of ϕ^+ and ϕ^- will determine the net preference flow, allowing a complete

Fig. III.19: Weighting of criteria and ϕ flows of preference

ranking (PROMETHEE II). These net preference flows are reflected in figure III.19, together with the weight vectors (in %) per criteria. For only five communities the suggested prioritization or (out)ranking can be immediately deduced.

Matrix II.11 and figure III.20 presents the exact value of all flows. In this case there is neither incomparability nor an indifference problem to outrank the five communities. All $\sum \varphi^+$ and $\sum \varphi^-$ allow for complete outranking [$\forall \varphi^+(a) > \varphi^+(b) \wedge \varphi^-(a) < \varphi^-(b)$] without having to rely on net preference flows to avoid outranking incomparability.

	Φ^+	Φ^-	Φ
Community A	0.2115	0.1923	0.0192
Community B	0.4615	0.0577	0.4038
Community C	0.0769	0.4423	-0.3654
Community D	0.2115	0.3846	-0.1731
Community E	0.3077	0.1923	0.1154

Matrix II.11: Socio-Economic Impact Preference Flows

Fig. III.20: Complete Preference Ranking of affected communities

2. The GAIA plane and sensitivity analysis

The extensive possibilities of PROMETHEE to perform sensitivity analysis are of particular interest. This special feature, called “Walking Weights”, allows modifications of the weights allocated to the different criteria and/or scenarios. Through changing the weight of the elected criterion by using the slider bar, the values are automatically updated, thus the impact of changing the weights can be assessed immediately. It allows for quick and transparent adjustments through visualizing the effects of changing the weights in real-time.

Fig. III.21: Visualization through the GAIA plane of the criteria, ranking, options and pi-decision axis or axis of preference

Through changing the weight of the elected criterion by using the slider bar, the values are automatically updated, thus the impact of changing the weights can be assessed immediately. It allows for quick and transparent adjustments through visualizing the effects of changing the weights in real-time.

This could facilitate considerably group decision-making and facilitate the establishment of inclusive consultative processes for determining post-conflict recovery/reconstruction priorities. For example, an extended drought has caused a higher socio-economic dependence on irrigated crop fields. As a result, more communities experience mine accidents caused by the population trying to get access to blocked irrigated cropland and/or (drink) water sources. In such situations it would be justified to increase the weight factor for these criteria. It could or could not change the ranking or prioritization of mine-affected

communities. In this case, increasing the weight coefficient from 11 \rightarrow 30% for irrigated cropland does *not* affect the above ranking. Hence, the earlier proposed ranking is a robust decision versus

varying levels of socio-economic impact or dependence of Afghanistan on irrigated cropland. However, a similar increase (6 → 30%) of the weight factor for the drink-water criterion causes a change in ranking of the mine/UXO affected communities apart from community B.

Fig. III.22: Applying the walking weights function for sensitivity or robustness analysis

b. Human Cost

1. Human cost scoring of affected communities

Based on LIS mine victim data, scoring data will now be determined, justified and entered into the multi-criteria decision matrix in order to obtain a prioritization of the five options.

	Victims 0-6m?	Victims 7-12m?	Victims 13-18m?	Victims 19-24M?	Predictor 1	Predictor 2
Min/Max	Maximize	Maximize	Maximize	Maximize	Minimize	Maximize
Weight	10.0000	8.0000	6.0000	4.0000	1.0000	2.0000
Preference Function	Linear	Linear	Linear	Linear	Linear	Usual
Indifference Threshold	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	50.0000	-
Preference Threshold	2.0000	2.0000	2.0000	2.0000	100.0000	-
Gaussian Threshold	-	-	-	-	-	-
Threshold Unit	Absolute	Absolute	Absolute	Absolute	Absolute	Absolute
Average Performance	1.6000	1.0000	1.6000	3.6000	400.0000	2.8000
Standard Dev.	1.9494	0.7071	0.8944	3.2094	374.1657	0.8367
Unit	Number of Victims	Number of Victims	Number of Victims	Number of Victims	Meters	Nr of Minefields
Community A	5.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	300.0000	4.0000
Community B	1.0000	0.0000	1.0000	2.0000	500.0000	3.0000
Community C	0.0000	2.0000	3.0000	4.0000	100.0000	3.0000
Community D	1.0000	1.0000	2.0000	2.0000	1000.0000	2.0000
Community E	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	9.0000	100.0000	2.0000

Matrix II.12: PROMETHEE scoring matrix for the 5 affected communities on the six 'human cost' criteria

Considering each affected community as a competing alternative, this implies 5 series of scores on 6 illustrative “human cost” criteria in matrix II.12. Four of the 6 criteria (one per surveyed semester) are related to recency and frequency factors, addressed earlier.⁴⁹⁰

The next section will illustrate how higher weights for more recent mine accidents versus equal weights for all four semesters will influence significantly the ranking. Also for illustrative purposes, two criteria, labelled *Predictor 1* and *Predictor 2*, have been added. Statistical analysis will need to determine possible and credible mine victim predictors in the case-study.

As reflected in figure III.23, PROMETHEE 1 Partial Ranking results in the same rank for Community B and D due to incomparable positive/negative flows. The positive flows indicate that Community B is slightly preferred or dominant over D, but the negative flows indicates that Community B is less preferred, or dominated more, than D or any other affected community according to the scoring on the 6 criteria.

This outranking problem is remedied or “defuzzified” through the PROMETHEE Complete Ranking method, whereby the final ranking is determined based on the net flows. Hence, in this case Community D outranks B; the difference of negative flows is bigger for Community B (Δ negative flows = $-0.23-0.3 = -0.7$) than the difference in positive preference flows of Community B over D (Δ positive flows = $0.00-0.04 = -0.4$), or otherwise formulated, Community D is preferred over B with a net preference flow of $|0.3|$.

Fig. III.23: An example of PROMETHEE I partial human cost ranking of the five affected communities

⁴⁹⁰ See Phase II – p.200

2. Human cost sensitivity analysis

As addressed in the previous section, another example would be provided to illustrate how varying the weight coefficients of criteria can change drastically the ranking. In the left case, *recency* effects are considered through the allocation of higher weights to more recent victims. Logically, Community C with the highest total number of victims [Sem₁=0, Sem₂=2, Sem₃=3 and Sem₄=4] over the survey observation period of 24 months will outrank Community A, which had 5 victims during the last observed semester [Sem₁=5, Sem₂=1, Sem₃=1 and Sem₄=1]. The effects of modifying the weights of the criteria from incremental to equal weights will cause the *J1*-decision axis to move dynamically in the GAIA plane, away from the “*victims 0-6 months?*” criterion.

Fig. III.24: ‘Human Cost’ outranking of affected communities; with and without *recency* effects

c. Peacekeeping/building effects

1. Peacekeeping/building scoring of affected communities

	AP Mines?	AT Mines?	UXO?	IED-insurgency activities?
Min/Max	Maximize	Maximize	Maximize	Maximize
Weight	1.0000	2.0000	3.0000	5.0000
Preference Function	Usual	Usual	Usual	Usual
Indifference Threshold	-	-	-	-
Preference Threshold	-	-	-	-
Gaussian Threshold	-	-	-	-
Threshold Unit	Absolute	Absolute	Absolute	Absolute
Average Performance	0.8000	0.4000	0.8000	1.4000
Standard Dev.	0.4472	0.5477	0.4472	1.3416
Unit	Yes=1, No=0	Yes=1, No=0	Yes=1, No=0	None =0, Low=1, Medium=2, High=3
Community A	Yes	No	Yes	None
Community B	Yes	No	Yes	Medium
Community C	Yes	Yes	No	High
Community D	No	No	Yes	Medium
Community E	Yes	Yes	Yes	None

Matrix II.13: Scoring matrix for the five affected communities on the 4 ‘peacekeeping’ criteria

The same LIS data on the presence of UXO/ERW and landmines used for the socio-economic criteria can now be used for the scoring of communities regarding the possible negative impact on peacekeeping activities. However, complementary information to the LIS-data is essential in order to incorporate the possible risks and impact of IED/insurgency activities on peacekeeping operations. Geographic risk mapping or other differentiating elements are a requirement to establish a sufficiently refined outranking process with sufficient refinement.

Fig. III.25: PROMETHEE complete ranking for peacekeeping/building effects

Pending data availability, mine action in support of local or regional DDR-activities is another criterion with could be considered.

d. Modelling considerations on setting weights and thresholds p, q and s

1. Weighting of criteria

There are numerous methods to weight criteria depending on the type and number of criteria, model, etc. It is essential that objectivity is provided to an otherwise subjective process of allocating weights. This is regarded as a most critical step in the envisaged modelling process and for the credibility of the outcome of the (case)study as a whole. Once the weighting of criteria is completed for the Afghan case-study, the rating of options or alternatives can be performed against these criteria using either ordinal or cardinal scales. In order to obtain this acceptable level of objectivity, it is an essential requirement to pursue a process of allocating weights to criteria which takes into account:

- (1) a high number of key stakeholders; the higher the number and the relevancy of the stakeholders involved in the weighting process of decision-making criteria, the higher the credibility of the outcome;

- (2) a *statistical reliability factor* regarding the data used in the model; logically, more reliable should get more weight than less reliable information. As mentioned earlier, the coefficient of determination R^2 can serve as a *baseline reference* in this regard.

2. Setting of thresholds and fuzzy optimization techniques

For the credibility of the model, the setting of thresholds is of equal importance as the weighting of criteria. Thresholds p, q or s directly impact ϕ which could consecutively change the prioritization or rankings of alternatives. Where the setting of weights is intuitively understood, indifference and/or preference threshold setting is generally more complex. Logically, the impact of threshold setting on preference ϕ depends primarily on type of preference function but it requires careful analysis to determine the threshold values in order to respect the desired balance between maintaining sufficient sensitivity or differentiation capacity of the outranking algorithm while avoiding that the model is not fuzzy enough. In the latter case the model would unnecessarily outrank alternatives based on negligible numerical differences. Beyond these principles, literature research did not provide any systematic or detailed methodology to determine threshold values.

“Specially defined or generally accepted values for the parameters q , p and s , or methods to define them, are found *extremely rarely in literature* concerning multi-criteria decision theory. The reason for this is based on the understanding that there are neither “correct” values for the parameters nor is there a “correct” way to define these. The parameter values always depend on the specific decision problem as well as the preferences and assessment of the decision maker. If it is difficult for the decision maker to define such parameter values a moderator and/or an experienced analyst is of help, i.e. *homme d'etude*.”⁴⁹¹

This was assessed in a similar manner by renowned decision theorist Jyrki Kangas:

“The indifference threshold can be defined either with respect to the uncertainty of the criteria values or as a threshold at which the differences become perceptible to decision makers (Rogers and Bruen 1998b). Maystre et al. (1994) defined the indifference threshold as the minimum margin of uncertainty and the preference threshold as the maximum margin of uncertainty with respect to different criteria. Thus, the preference threshold implies that there is no doubt that a certain alternative is better than the other. However, *there are no right values for the thresholds, or even a right way to define them*.”⁴⁹²

For the case-study, experimental methodologies could include setting the *indifference threshold* to zero and the *preference threshold* set to be the difference between the best and the worst alternative for each criterion. This means that alternatives with the same criteria values will be considered indifferent, and all the other comparisons are in the *hesitation zone* except for the comparison of the *best* and the *worst* alternative with respect to each criterion. Other possibilities are for example to set the indifference threshold to one tenth of the range of variation and the preference threshold to half of it. This means that differences less than 10% of the range of variation will be considered indifferent and the differences more than 50% of the range of variation will not be considered to have a greater effect on the decision than the differences which were 50% of the range of variation.

The Gaussian preference function offers an interesting alternative method for the introduction of fuzzy logic. It only requires the determination of one preference threshold value to obtain similar fuzzy effects compared to the requirement of setting a *strict* indifference and preference threshold for Type IV and V criterion (multi-level and linear criteria). The standard deviation of the scorings can be a good reference value for setting threshold s . However, its interpretation and effects may be less transparent. Hence, if applied, its effects in the case-study need

⁴⁹¹ TREITZ, M. (2006). Production Process Design Using Multi-Criteria Analysis, Internet. Available at www.ubka.uni-karlsruhe.de/indexer-vvv/2006/wiwi/20, accessed on 13 February 2007

⁴⁹² KANGAS, J. and PYKALAINEN, J. (2001). Outranking methods as tools in strategic natural resources planning, Internet. Available at www.lamsade.dauphine.fr/mcda/biblio/Author/KANGAS-J.html, accessed on 13 February 2007

to be well examined and understood. In real world applications, the decision-maker needs to have a good understanding as well to avoid that the model suffers from the “black-box” syndrome.

“If the analyst is not familiar enough with the roles and interpretations of the choice models, the results of the analyses easily become more or less random. Furthermore, when applying any decision support method, it is crucial to understand the technical roles of each part of the evaluation model, and to take these roles into consideration in all stages of the planning process. Often, *more important than the choice of the method applied is to thoroughly understand the method and to apply it correctly.*”⁴⁹³

e. Multiple objective optimization

1. Requirement for second stage outranking

In order to respond adequately to the objective of intersection optimization of sub-phase A, a *second stage outranking process* needs to combine the three individual outranking processes, illustrated in figure III.26. It is noticeable how each outranking presents a different priority order.

Fig. III.26: Combining net ϕ 's of three mine action outputs in order to achieve multiple objective optimization

Hence, a *compromise outranking* can be achieved through reintroducing the net ϕ values of each community in a second stage outranking process. Logically, the average scoring performance should be 0 since the ϕ 's of domination and being dominated balance each other out. Pending on the situation or anticipated scenarios, the decision-maker can set or adjust the weights for the three mine action outputs. For illustrative purposes, a decision-maker is assumed which gives the highest weight to the human cost, second highest weight to the socio-economic benefits/impact and the lowest weight to peacekeeping effects.

- (1) Weight factor Human Cost = $W_{HC} = 6$
- (2) Weight factor Socio Economic Benefits/Impact = $W_{SEB} = 3$
- (3) Weight factor Peacekeeping Effects = $W_{PK} = 1$

	Human Cost	Socio Economic Benefits	Peacekeeping effects
Min/Max	Maximize	Maximize	Maximize
Weight	6.0000	3.0000	1.0000
Preference Function	Gaussian	Gaussian	Gaussian
Indifference Threshold	-	-	-
Preference Threshold	-	-	-
Gaussian Threshold	0.2500	0.2900	0.2500
Threshold Unit	Absolute	Absolute	Absolute
Average Performance	-0.00	-0.01	-0.00
Standard Dev.	0.25	0.29	0.25
Unit			
Community A	0.27	-0.02	-0.34
Community B	-0.26	0.40	0.11
Community C	0.23	-0.37	0.34
Community D	-0.23	-0.17	0.00
Community E	-0.02	0.12	-0.11

Matrix II.14: Scoring matrix with net ϕ for final ranking

A *Type VI - Gaussian* function is suggested at this stage. In order to have a uniform fuzzy optimization process for the three criteria, the three standard deviations of the net ϕ 's of the three mine action outputs are used to set *preference threshold s*.

The objective is again to establish a *PROMETHEE-Complete Ranking* of the five communities or alternatives. Hence, the uncertainty zones created through fuzzy logic preference threshold setting is in the

⁴⁹³ TREITZ, M. (2006). Production Process Design Using Multi-Criteria Analysis, Internet. Available at www.ubka.uni-karlsruhe.de/indexer-vvv/2006/wiwi/20, accessed on 13 February 2007

end again “defuzzified” through an outranking based on the five net preference ϕ ’s of the impacted communities.

“A different approach to address the uncertainty in preferential information in multi-criteria methods is carried out by fuzzy approaches [Carlsson and Fuller, 1996; Ribeiro, 1996]. Employing trapezoidal fuzzy intervals for the preference parameters, fuzzy preference flows can be used to represent the decision problem within the outranking approach PROMETHEE [Geldermann et al., 2000b]. The ranking of the alternatives is ultimately based on the defuzzified fuzzy preference flows.”⁴⁹⁴

Matrix II.14 and figure III.27 further depict what has just been explained. It portrays how the second stage outranking has the significant advantage to present a more transparent outranking process to the decision-maker(s) compared to the 21 criteria before.

2. GAIA-plane visualization of the best compromise

The GAIA-plane further illustrates the lay-out of the three criteria and the best compromise the outranking process according to the weighting of these criteria. It is clear that Community A of the Small-scale prioritization problem in figure III.27 is the most preferred alternative, followed by Community C. Compared to the current low-medium-high impact categorization of the Landmine Impact Surveys, this outranking process signifies a considerable enrichment of the decision analysis process and has a promising management potential owing to its dynamic users-concept.

Fig. III.27: Visualisation in the GAIA plane and final outranking

f. Missing data

Particularly useful for mine action data is the ability of Decision Lab to handle correctly scoring matrixes with “missing values”. It regards missing values as not known or not relevant and represents missing values by a question mark.⁴⁹⁵ As soon as data is entered for at least two alternatives or affected communities, they will contribute to the outranking process and generate positive or negative preference flows between these communities. This allows developing a standardized and comprehensive evaluation framework for mine action programmes whereby data can be gradually inserted throughout the information-gathering process and life cycle of a mine action programme.

⁴⁹⁴ TREITZ, M. (2006). Production Process Design Using Multi-Criteria Analysis, Internet. Available at www.ubka.uni-karlsruhe.de/indexer-vvv/2006/wiwi/20, accessed on 13 February 2007

⁴⁹⁵ This is explained in the help menu of Decision Lab 2000

III.3. Sub-phase B: Optimize integrated strategic planning for mine action

III.3.1. From “Politics to Strategy” and from “Strategy to developing a Strategic Plan”

A. Strategic planning jargon

The unanticipated insurgency war in Iraq resulted in an exceptional use of the term *strategy*. Currently, the whole strategic planning jargon is frequented exhaustively to explain the ongoing US “*peacebuilding*” processes in Iraq and Afghanistan. The repeated calls for an *exit-strategy*, clear *benchmarks*, achievable *strategic objectives*, *strategic options* became commonplace. These examples extensively underscore how important strategic planning is and how it can be present in the full spectrum of political decision-making. Many of the strategic planning activities are closely related to the framing dynamics discussed in Phase-I. The sequel of *diagnostic*, *prognostic* and *motivational* framing underscores how a strategic planning effort could be communicated to stakeholders, in particular donors, and even broader audiences. Inevitably, strategic planning is essential to lay a foundation for policy development and operational planning.

B. Linkage between strategic planning and the politics of mine action

In complex multilateral planning environments, such as planning for multidisciplinary UN peacekeeping operations,⁴⁹⁶ extraordinary efforts take place to streamline strategic planning into an integrated process. Mine action is, whenever relevant, a substantial part of this planning process. Developing a solid linkage between the politics of mine action and strategic planning is further an intricate process, especially because most mine action politics tend to take place in a poorly structured or non-systematic approach. To explore the full array of effects of planning at the strategic level, often various approaches have to be tried, involving several information-gathering and planning methods. Hence, strategic planning should be conceptually understood within the context of this study. Based on the preceding normative modelling phase, strategic planning is supported and facilitated according to the following formulation:

“Planning is *normative decision-making*. It is *not science*. Done well, it is *science-based* but *value-driven*. Normative pluralism is a fact of life for planners, and analytical answers simply do not exist.”⁴⁹⁷

Having defined planning, the effects of *not* planning could be described, although ironically, as follows:

“Planning is an unnatural process; it is much more fun to do something. The nicest thing about not planning is that failure comes as a complete surprise, rather than being preceded by a period of worry and depression.”⁴⁹⁸

Strategic planning is a logic extension of, or further builds upon, a strategic factor analysis, albeit normative or not. It needs to take into account the most relevant elements, including those which can measure its successful implementation.

“How the plan is put together will rest on careful analysis and policy, but the most significant point is that all clearance work can now be reported *against progress indicators that are hugely more informative than mere square meters cleared and numbers of mines or UXO destroyed*.”⁴⁹⁹

⁴⁹⁶ In UN jargon, a specific distinction is made between traditional and complex peacekeeping operations. Traditional peacekeeping is associated with Chapter VI of the Charter and inter-State conflicts, complex peacekeeping operations are often Chapter VII peacekeeping operations due to intra-State conflicts.

⁴⁹⁷ Trade-Off Analysis Planning and Procedures Guidebook (2002, April). US Army Institute for Water Resources, Decision Methodologies Division, Internet. Available at www.usace.army.mil/cw/cecw-cp/news/pa_newsletter/v5i4.pdf, accessed on 10 March 2006

⁴⁹⁸ Quote by Sir John Harvey-Jones. Chairman of Imperial Chemical Industries, United Kingdom

⁴⁹⁹ Survey Action Centre. (2005). Afghanistan Landmine Impact Survey, Washington, p.197

Based on the deductions and findings of Phase-I, the strategic planning envisaged in this study suggests a process to provide the decision maker(s) with credible long-term options or possible courses of action, often complemented with a *best response* recommendation. The following criteria from Phase-I present a non-exhaustive list of requirements for the successful incorporation of a *short-term prioritization process* for mine action in *long-term strategic planning* for a mine action programme. Some of the criteria could be grouped together, while the identified “indicators” rather serve in this context as “elements of evaluation” of a mine action programme.

Criteria	Elements of Evaluation
C4: Governance/managerial capabilities and commitment to effectively implement mine action	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Evaluate national ownership of the mine action problem in order to be categorized as a good performing programme
C5: Integration/mainstreaming of mine action into broader humanitarian/development strategies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Evaluate level of integration of mine action in overarching humanitarian, development, post-conflict restoration strategies, including victim assistance into broader public health and socio-economic strategies.
C15/16: Prioritization and targeting of mine action efforts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Evaluate efforts to reduce the number of new mine victims among civilian populations, especially vulnerable groups including women and children Evaluate Number of affected people receiving risk education (MRE) Community participation in landmine impact assessments Effective Threat Assessments which lead to targeted responses through mine clearance, marking/fencing Targeting change in behaviour of most vulnerable groups through gender/age-disaggregated procedures
C29/30: Information sharing and standardisation of mine action	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Evaluate if mine action is benefiting from an effective information management system with IMSMA effectively implemented Evaluate if mechanisms are in place to facilitate coordination and cooperation between the different political levels of mine action Verify if mine action is based on international mine action standards
C16/17/32/35: Effectiveness and efficiency of a mine action programme	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Effectiveness and progress of mine clearance and level of stockpile destruction, including number of mines left for training purposes Number of mines destroyed in stockpiles outside training stocks Progress on achieving the core humanitarian objectives of the Mine Ban Treaty – Nairobi Action Plan Level of cooperation and coordination of mine action activities
C36: Establishment of adequate emergency response capacities for mine action	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Level of effectiveness of emergency response capabilities
C37: Management and planning capabilities of national mine action coordination centres	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Level of effectiveness of national/regional capacity building efforts
C38: Adequate fund raising mechanisms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Evaluate financial contributions to the programme in terms of transparency and predictability
C39: Effective integration of mine action in peacekeeping/building operations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No new deployment of landmines or use of weapons with similar effects
C42: Balanced public awareness campaigns and objective framing of the landmine problem	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Evaluate if reporting on landmine problems is reliable and objective.

Table III.2: Strategic planning criteria and elements of evaluation

Satisfying key stakeholders’ expectations regarding these criteria and elements of evaluation will be essential to gain or maintain donor confidence. A strategic planning process for mine action requires furthermore a highly structured and rational approach in which strategic options can be evaluated against the above criteria in a transparent manner. Similar to a generic strategic planning process, the following disciplines need to be part of the process:

- (1) establish a feasible and affordable strategic objective
- (2) analyse all relevant factors (the strategic analysis)
- (3) generate strategic options/scenarios
- (4) evaluate strategic options/scenarios
- (5) select the “best” strategic option
- (6) develop and implement the strategic mine action plan

C. No reliable strategic planning without reliable mine clearance rates

The above considerations underscore that strategic planning for mine action programmes requires a clear strategic vision. This implies a solid understanding of the national landmine problem and the desired end state. Strategic planning should then focus how this long-term end state can be achieved most effectively and efficiently. This requires a committed and continuous planning effort, based on a proper data management, analysis and use of strategic planning support tools. Reliable *mine clearance rates* are most important in this regard. As stated before, cleared square meters is not a preferred progress indicator. Nevertheless, realistic mine clearance rates are critical to evaluate what is strategically *achievable* and *affordable over the long-term*. This is particularly important with regard to the mine clearance deadlines of the MBT.⁵⁰⁰

III.3.2. From “tunnel vision” to an integrated approach

A. Macro-optimization principle

Before addressing strategic planning for mine action any further, it needs to be emphasized – based on the build-up formula used throughout Phase-II – that the new element in terms of intersection optimization is the cross-sectoral maximization of the effectiveness of post-conflict restoration efforts. Theoretically, resources going to mine action need to be prioritised versus all the other post-conflict restoration requirements. This is reflected in the symbolic optimization formula below through incorporating all budget lines and HR, SEB (with discount effects) and PB outputs of the different sectors.

$$OPT \text{ Post-conflict Restoration} = \left\{ \frac{\sum_{z=1}^b HR_n + \sum_{y=1}^x \frac{\left(\sum_{z=1}^b SEB_n \right)^y - C^y}{(1+r)^y} + \sum_{z=1}^b PB_n}{\sum_{z=1}^b \text{Budget Lines}} \right\}$$

(Humanitarian)
(Reconstruction/Recovery)
(Development)

B. Why and how link-up mine action with the Millennium Development Goals (MDG)?

a. Interesting parallels

In an initial response to the *why* question, *many parallels* between the politics related to the UN MDG and the goals of the Mine Ban Treaty need to be pointed out. Both had their first five year *review process* and considered the year 2005 as a milestone regarding the assessment of previous achievements and projection of future needs. They equally use an endorsed *action plan* to better direct the efforts of the international community and similarly thrive on the synergy of more than 1000 dedicated NGO’s. Global campaign efforts for a total ban on the use of antipersonnel landmines or for a “Mine Free World” are quite identical in their characteristics to global calls for “Making Poverty History”. Shocking catchphrases like 10 million children die of the consequences of extreme poverty every year,⁵⁰¹ or *1 child every three seconds*, reminds the framing efforts studied in Phase-I: *one landmine victim every 30 minutes*. The campaign to free the world of landmines started well before the MDG campaign and with some similarities, they obviously differ in scope,

⁵⁰⁰ To remind, all areas cleared 10 years after acceding to the MBT.

⁵⁰¹ UN Press Release GA/10018 (2002, May 8) General Assembly, Twenty-seventh Special Session 2nd Meeting (PM) on: Obstacles developing countries face meeting goals for children, New York

size and dimension. Both however, offer an increasing number of valuable insights on how to mobilize an often more divided than unified donor community behind a well-known ambitious vision for a better world.

b. Success based on a shared philosophy

Phase-I covered some of the strengths and weaknesses of the MBT. In further comparison, it is interesting to briefly analyze why the practice of the MDG as a development framework has been more successful where others failed? At present, the eight MDG⁵⁰² – which range from halving extreme poverty to halting the spread of HIV/AIDS and providing universal primary education, all by the target date of 2015 – form a blueprint agreed to by all the world's countries and the entire world's leading development institutions. All eight of the MDG, and the corresponding eighteen targets, are taken directly from the *Millennium Declaration of 2000*. The development issues are made exceedingly concrete via tangible goal setting and with increasingly reliable data the majority of the indicators are quite workable. The most touching development objectives are directly related to the lives of people, and that is the exact reason why they have galvanized unprecedented efforts to meet the needs of the world's poorest, much better compared to earlier abstract or economic goal settings such as 5% income growth or other GDP related formulas or quantifications. The first successful round of the MDG goes hand in hand with the impressive support for the MBT with its comparable tangible humanitarian goals and deadlines, however the latter still far short from having universal support.

c. The importance of an integrated strategic planning framework

In relative terms, how is the progress in reaching the MDG compared to making the deadlines of the MBT? Well, even without an in-depth analysis of the MDG process, it is quite obvious that at the current rate of progress the international community is neither on track to realize the MDG in 2015, nor as the international community will provide sufficient support to make many of the 10 year deadlines of the MBT for a mine free status of mine-affected MBT member States. Unfortunately, if there is not a greater sense of urgency the achievements are not going to be even close, especially in Africa.

Which mechanism can harmonize the multi-level mine action politics towards the MDG? Will it be sufficient to enhance current external consultative processes and set aside concerns that this might reduce mine action funding due to other more competitive development activities? Should we better explore the opportunities to more substantially integrate mine action into sub-strategies relative to the MDG? Being the world's time bound and quantified targets, the MDG are what they are, eight strategic development goals, and the mine action community might not obtain the desired result by creating a specific ninth MDG solely for addressing mine action purposes. Certain significantly mine-affected countries have done this or are in the process of doing so, but if it will mobilize additional resources beyond the funding required for the internationally endorsed MDG is still to be seen, especially since the current funding is already largely insufficient.

Consequently, the *subordinate planning level to the MDG* is likely a much more suitable interface since it allows for a more substantial and tangible inclusion of national mine action goals and strategic plans into *integrated* concepts such as *Poverty Reduction Strategy Papers, National Development Plans, Security Sector Reform Plans, Emergency Response Plans and Needs Analysis*

⁵⁰² In September 2000, world leaders adopted the Millennium Declaration. The Declaration covers issues of peace, security and development, including the environment, protection of vulnerable groups, human rights and governance. The Declaration consolidates a set of inter-connected development goals into a global agenda. These goals are designated as the "Millennium Development Goals" or "MDGs": (1)Eradicate extreme poverty and hunger, (2)Achieve universal primary education, (3)Promote gender equality and empower women, (4)Reduce child mortality, (5)Improve maternal health, (6)Combat HIV/AIDS, malaria and other diseases, (7)Ensure environmental sustainability and (8)Develop a global partnership for development

Frameworks. These cornerstone documents offer a comprehensive integrated strategic planning framework and they could provide strategic guidance on deadline setting for mine clearance activities in accordance with the Mine Ban Treaty.

Nevertheless, also here are potential pitfalls and obstacles. Frequently there is a lack of above mentioned nationally driven plans, or they suffer from unrealistic expectations, fragmentation, gaps or duplication. One should expect to detect inadequate links between priorities in the political and security arena and the economic and social arena. Unfortunately, new indigenous governments overloaded with too many planning decisions are also more rule than exception, often giving way to an early loss of momentum in the process of post-conflict restoration. Last but not least, strategic deadline setting can be both helpful and obstructive; realism and sensible targets should prevail above rigorous policies trying to make the MBT or MDG timelines, causing imbalances in other equally important sectors.

d. Subordinate planning level to the MDG: a practical strategic planning framework for mine action

1. (Emergency) Needs Assessments – Emergency Response Plan

In a broad sense, needs assessments have always been accompanying humanitarian relief, post-conflict-restoration and development efforts, although often under very various formats and different informative levels to the decision-making process. Preferably a needs assessment should clearly define the problem through a systematic study of the way things are and the way they should be.⁵⁰³ This repeats the earlier formulated requirement on the establishment of a clear strategic vision. Hence, in general four steps are systematically present in a good needs assessment which, adjusted for mine action, are the following:

- (1) perform a “gap” analysis to identify the current mine action requirements;
- (2) identify priorities and importance of possible mine action activities;
- (3) identify the causes of the landmine problems and/or mine action opportunities;
- (4) identify possible mine action solutions and opportunities.

Through a needs assessment one has also the opportunity to create a strong *framing* message through highlighting the consequences if the mine action programme is or is not implemented. The latter is in planning jargon also called the “*do nothing option*”.

However, needs assessments have a number of limitations which need to be taken into account during the strategic planning process for mine action. As previous analysis has demonstrated on several occasions in this study, humanitarian assistance, reconstruction and development can not be strictly delineated. Post-conflict reconstruction activities often have a significant humanitarian and/or development dimension providing labour, a social structure, food-for-work programs which also support longer term economic development objectives.

“One of the most notable examples of a program that cannot be easily placed in either category is demining, which has a strong humanitarian element but also is an essential ingredient of reconstruction. While reconstruction might be defined as replacing what was destroyed, it is obvious that changes in development paradigms, technology and scale economies mean that this definition is too limited. Since preparing detailed investment plans for the development of every sector is impossible during a rapid needs assessment, it follows that these assessments may be of limited use in preparing investments at the level of sectors and locations.”⁵⁰⁴

⁵⁰³ One can observe that a needs assessment portrays many similarities with a SWOT-analysis (Strengths –Weaknesses-Opportunities-Threats), the latter however more holistic in its approach taking into account internal and external threats to the current situation and possible solutions.

⁵⁰⁴ McKECHNIE, A. (2002). Humanitarian Assistance, Reconstruction & Development in Afghanistan: A Practitioner’s View, International Conference on Post-Conflict Reconstruction, Hiroshima, Japan

2. Security Threats Analysis and Security Sector Reform

A security sector can be defined in a variety of ways. To revert to game theoretic terms, the basic list of “actors” includes the military, paramilitary, police, intelligence, and border and customs authorities, each with their specific utilities and strategic responses. *Security Sector Reform* (SSR) is often an important precondition for good governance, security, human rights, and the achievement of poverty-reduction goals. The aim of SSR is to strengthen civilian management and oversight of security sector institutions. It also has a special role to play in the demobilisation and reintegration of security sector personnel and other combatants, in post-conflict societies.

The disarmament, demobilisation and reintegration (DDR) of ex-combatants into peacetime economic and social life is essential for restoring security. Hence, the reintegration of demobilized soldiers in mine action programmes can contribute significantly to SSR. As studied in Phase-I, the establishment of effective DDR programmes includes political negotiations, humanitarian relief, the technical aspects of weapon disposal and socio-economic interventions to provide livelihoods, training and skills. In sum, DDR as part of “*mine action for peace*” is an important aspect of security sector reform during transitions to peace.

3. Poverty Reduction & National Development Planning

Figure III.28 combines the World Bank 2005 ranking of the income economies with the 2005 Landmine Monitor; see Annex G for a detailed overview. It is obvious that the landmine problem is significantly income or poverty correlated. More than 50% of low income and low-middle income countries are mine affected versus 20% of high-middle income countries and 10% of high income countries. Ending poverty is essentially a political process that is specific to the local economic, social, cultural, ecological and gender equality circumstances in each country.

Fig. III.28: Correlation landmine/UXO problems with poverty

Armed violence and the general absence of a secure environment cause the inhibition of economic activity and poverty which in turn creates a breeding ground for armed violence. Domestic security concerns aggravated by the presence of mines/ERW cause social, economic and developmental exclusion, erosion of community values, militia activities, tribal rivalry and general political unrest are some of the reasons for the continuous usage of landmines and worse, IED. The widespread contamination of landmines and ERW often complicates the implementation of *poverty reduction strategies and national development plans*. It has been a recurrent theme how landmines and UXO block the normal functioning of households, places a heavy burden on scarce health care resources, prevents return of refugees to unsafe villages and further seriously negatively impacts rural poverty due to unsafe farmland and grazing areas. In sum, the integration of mine action in poverty reduction strategies is of critical value to fight the poverty/violence trap and remove some of the obstacles to sustainable development.

C. Linking-up PROMETHEE with multiple scenario planning

Prioritization of mine action will normally be affected by a significant change of the situation or external conditions. As explained in the MCDA introductory paragraphs, this significant change in conditions can be defined through *multiple scenarios*. Although PROMETHEE is not a suitable long-term strategic planning tool, it offers the possibility to link up the mine action prioritization process with multiple strategic scenarios. As illustrated in figure III.29, the impact of different strategic scenarios can be incorporated by changing the weight coefficients for the three mine action outputs. This is similar to shifting the weight coefficients with the *Walking Weights* function, except that multiple settings can be simultaneously presented and easily compared.

The short-term impact of different scenarios is demonstrated by figure III.29 with the changes in decision axis reflecting the illustrative change in weight coefficients according to the anticipated mine action requirements for each scenario.

The short-term impact of different scenarios is demonstrated by figure III.29 with the changes in decision axis reflecting the illustrative change in weight coefficients according to the anticipated mine action requirements for each scenario.

Scenario 1:
Security situation very volatile – risk of insurgency activities

- (1) Human Cost: 0.4
- (2) Socio-Economic Benefits: 0.3
- (3) Peacekeeping/building: 0.3

Scenario 2:
Security situation stable but the number of mine victims remains unacceptably high or increases due to demographic shifts, caused by refugee/IDP returns:

- (1) Human Cost: 0.75
- (2) Socio-Economic Benefits: 0.2
- (3) Peacekeeping/building: 0.05

Scenario 3:
Security stable but landmines increasingly block or hinder the economic recovery process:

- (1) Human Cost: 0.4
- (2) Socio-Economic Benefits: 0.5
- (3) Peacekeeping/building: 0.1

Fig. III.29: GAIA assisted multiple scenario planning

D. Robust optimization towards multiple scenarios: third stage outranking

The previous section indicated how for each scenario the ranking changes following the changes of the 3 weight coefficients allocated to the three mine action outputs. This process can be introduced as a *third stage* of the MCDA-outranking in order to establish a robust optimization towards anticipated changes in external conditions. These anticipated changes in scenarios need to be reflected in the probability or likelihood allocated to each scenario. Hence, the third stage modelling will provide a final or *best response* outranking which takes into account these possible scenario changes.

This function can also serve as a tool for robustness analysis since comparing the impact of different scenarios on the ranking will demonstrate how robust a certain ranking is to changing scenarios. As illustrated in figure III.30, the ranking of the five communities will change according to the probability allocated to each scenario. Two examples are provided below. In situation 1, the decision-maker allocates an equal probability or likelihood to each scenario. In situation 2, the decision-maker allocates a much higher probability to the “economic rebound” scenario (S3 with likelihood of 80%), regards the likelihood of an insurgency very low (S1 only 20%) and a demographic shift as an irrelevant scenario (S2 with likelihood of 0%). The differences in allocated probabilities results in a change of net ϕ sufficiently large to change the ranking or prioritization. It can be observed that a ranking will undergo limited change if the decision axis only varies between scenario S1 and S3. If the decision-maker allocates a much higher probability to the “demographic shift” scenario, then a more drastic change in ranking would occur.

Fig III.30 Multiple scenario or robustness analysis according to 3 different scenarios

III.4. Phase-II response to research aim

III.4.1. Sub-phase A response

Sub-phase A findings: The optimization of short-term prioritization of mine action resulted into the promising development of a multiple criteria decision analysis model based on outranking algorithms.

Fig. III.31: Assessed capabilities of the Decision Support System

Table III.3 gives an overview of the 8 formulated requirements at the introduction of the modelling phase and the assessed potential of the decision support system to assist mine action prioritization. The results for the first intersection optimization are reassuring in anticipation of much more complex outranking of the case-study. Setting of weights and fuzzy logic thresholds will undoubtedly pose additional challenges.

	Modelling requirement	Characteristics of the developed model
1	Transparent and comprehensible	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No "black box syndrome" Logic processing of data
2	Sufficiently refined and sensitive	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No limits on the number of criteria Can be refined or enriched as new, credible data becomes available
3	Flexible to change and updates	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> User-friendly – model can be easily updated with new data Handles well missing data Handles well large numbers of alternatives Approaching the basic computational principles of artificial intelligence
4	Able to handle different types of data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Qualitative and quantitative data Numeric or integer data Cardinal or ordinal values Easily processes first stage net flows in second stage outranking
5	Able to make numerous assessments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sensitivity analysis Able to incorporate conflicting criteria Multiple scenarios
6	Able to incorporate uncertainty, risk and imprecision	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Principles of fuzzy logic are easy to introduce; the ability to deal with uncertain and fuzzy mine action information is an undisputable advantage of outranking methods. Risk management capabilities of the model are clear
7	Able to produce credible and clear outputs in terms of mine action prioritization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide short-term prioritization or ranking Aid long-term planning though the ability to reflect different scenarios in the prioritization process
8	Able to incorporate a time dimension	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Discount factors can be reflected in the socio-economic criteria Recency factors related to mine victims can be reflected

Table III.3. Preliminary assessment of the characteristics of the developed prioritization model

III.4.1. Sub-phase B response

Sub-phase B findings: The optimization of integrated strategic planning resulted in the exploration of an integrated strategic planning framework rather than an extension of the model.

Examining the Phase-I criteria with regard to sub-phase B resulted in quite a different approach compared to the stringent multiple criteria modelling effort in sub-phase A. The analysis of the human cost, socio-economic and peacekeeping impact provided concrete factors for the *in-country mine action prioritization effort* but related to strategic planning and management of mine action programmes, the identified sub-set of 15 criteria portrays *rather regulatory characteristics* and (planning) *constraints*. These qualifying criteria or elements are hard to fit into a clinical *cross-country prioritization process* based on measurable progress or strategic performance indicators. Otherwise, they can serve as elements of evaluation or guidelines. All in all, they should be part of a strategic planning framework. The strategic plans directly subordinate to the MDGs such as needs assessments, poverty reduction strategy papers and national development planning provide in this regard the best interface and reference for the development of strategic mine action plans.

In this respect, optimizing integrated strategic planning for mine action will benefit from a standard approach, which does not necessarily imply it should be developed according to a strict rulebook, a blueprint or a set of programmed instructions. More important is that the *unifying theme of the strategic vision* or end state of a mine action programme gives *coherence and direction* to the strategic plans and the development of various strategic options. In order to trigger a broadly accepted strategic planning process, it speaks for itself that *integration* and *national ownership* of the process should be encouraged as much as possible. The analysis has highlighted the many challenges in this regard and emphasized the pragmatic steps to be followed.

The ability of the model to *link-up short-term prioritization with longer-term strategic planning* is of particular interest. Hence, the three mine action outputs serve simultaneously as three key strategic planning parameters. How mine action can best contribute in an integrated fashion to humanitarian relief, socio-economic benefits and support to the peace process needs to be anchored in the prioritization model through the weight coefficients allocated to the three mine action outputs. They need to reflect the requirements identified in the overarching strategic planning framework. This should also contribute to the robustness of the short-term prioritization towards multiple scenarios.

CHAPTER IV – PHASE-III: CASE-STUDY AFGHANISTAN

“A fundamental characteristic of an optimally functioning mine action programme is that it seeks to respond in the most effective and efficient way possible to what people actually need – not what the mine action programme happens to be able to deliver at any given moment.”⁵⁰⁵

IV.1 Introduction

IV.1.1. Afghanistan: a preferred test case for the model

The case-study will tie up and apply the knowledge acquired via the previous two phases on the *most advanced and largest mine action programme* worldwide. The earlier political analysis, deductions, partial conclusions and modelling principles are envisaged to concretely support the outcome of this phase: an *optimal strategic prioritization* for the *Mine Action Programme in Afghanistan* (MAPA), together with recommendations to optimize *integrated long-term strategic planning*.

The operational constraints at the mine action implementation level, in concert with the formulation of credible strategic assumptions and strategic estimates, will require a pragmatic exploration of the outcome and findings of the previous phases. In addition, this case-study will concretely highlight how the politics involved can and will influence the implementation of a mine action programme in an environment of peace enforcement, peacekeeping and peacebuilding activities. Owing to the very dynamic situation, this case-study is tied down to a specific research timeframe; primarily 2003-2005(survey) data will be considered.

IV.1.2. Prioritization and strategic planning framework

Phase-II suggested decision theoretic methods and principles with decision support systems able to assist *short-term prioritization* and *integrated strategic planning*. Based on the MCDA-model developed in Phase-II, the most important result expected from this phase is a solid demonstration of its potential with real-world data.

The case-study will also thoroughly analyze the impact of the important strategic provision of Article 5 of the Mine Ban Treaty, requiring that each State Party “*undertakes to destroy or ensure the destruction of all anti-personnel mines in mined areas under its jurisdiction or control, as soon as possible but not later than ten years after the entry into force of this Convention for that State Party*”. This deadline has inevitably a significant influence on the prioritization and strategic planning processes, funding and implementation of the mine action programme. The challenges to meet such an ambitious deadline seem to have been systematically under-estimated. The envisaged “*optimal response*” of this phase will allow assessing what is feasible in this regard.

IV.1.3. The Afghan landmine problem

A. Background and brief history

Afghanistan is a landlocked, mountainous, geographically remote, sparsely populated, ethnically diverse, yet geopolitically important country. From the 1930s to the late 1970s, the country was at peace and underwent a modest degree of economic and social development.

⁵⁰⁵ Based on strategic planning principles of the GICHD (2204) Guide to Socio-Economic Approaches to Mine Action Planning and Management, Geneva.

During this period, development was concentrated in the cities and towns, whilst most rural areas retained their traditional way of life, governance structures and social practices. More than two decades of conflict since 1978, combined with successive years of drought, have resulted in widespread human suffering and massive displacement of population, both within Afghanistan and as refugees in neighbouring countries. At a given moment in time, an estimated seven million people were vulnerable to famine. Armed conflict has degraded or destroyed its infrastructure, depleted its human resource base severely, caused a brain drain and eroded its social capital. Many of the state institutions are not properly functional, and the economy and society remain fragmented according to ethnic lines.

Notwithstanding these challenges real progress is being demonstrated in many ways across the country. There is a massive investment in rebuilding the infrastructure and transportation. Schools and universities have re-opened. Local markets are thriving with locally grown products and locally manufactured goods. Kabul is full of energy and a sense of purpose.⁵⁰⁶ However, the needs and expectations of the Afghan population remain enormous, and the lack of security remains the most pressing problem.

Afghanistan is heavily contaminated both with landmines and ERW. Most of the mines were laid during the Soviet occupation and the subsequent communist regime between 1980 and 1992. During this period and the subsequent war between Afghan government troops and the “*mujahedeen*”⁵⁰⁷, landmines were used indiscriminately by all sides in the war. Mines were used for conventional military purposes, and also as part of the Soviet strategy to depopulate villages to prevent local support for the mujahedeen. Mines were therefore placed in houses, irrigation systems, agricultural land and grazing areas, as well as being used for conventional military purposes on roads and around military establishments. Conventional forces used mines to force people off the land and to reduce potential support for their enemies. Guerrilla forces used mines to block roads and to harass opponents. Modern delivery systems enabled mines to be scattered by helicopters and other aircraft. Landmines and UXO are scattered throughout the country in urban and commercial areas, towns and villages as well as on farmland.

Landmines were also used in the internal fighting among various armed groups after 1992, particularly in Kabul city and its outskirts. The problem was made worse in October 2001, with newly laid mines and booby traps reportedly used by the Northern Alliance, Taliban and Al-Qaeda fighters, and from unexploded cluster munitions and ammunition scattered from storage depots hit by air strikes. Mine and UXO contamination affects 31 out of the 34 provinces. In 2002, a total of 800 km² was estimated to be contaminated by landmines and another 500 km² of former battle area contaminated with ERW.

Fig. IV.1: Historic overview of minefields in km² by year of mining

⁵⁰⁶ During repeated missions to Kabul (between 2002 and 2004) the economic revival could be easily observed.

⁵⁰⁷ Mujahideen is a term for Muslims fighting in a war or involved in any other struggle. Mujahid, and its plural, mujahideen, come from the same Arabic root as *jihad* ("struggle").

B. The establishment of the Mine Action Programme in Afghanistan (MAPA)

After the signing of the Geneva Accord on the Soviet withdrawal from Afghanistan in 1988, it was predicted that there would be a mass repatriation of Afghan refugees from Pakistan and Iran. Bearing in mind this predicted mass repatriation and the problem of landmines in Afghanistan, MAPA was established during the same year. Initially MAPA focused on training as many Afghans as possible in order to equip them with necessary skills for mine clearance. It was predicted that the trained Afghans would, on their return, clear their villages and fields of mines.⁵⁰⁸ On July 2002, President Karzai announced that Afghanistan would become a State Party to the Mine Ban Treaty, and subsequently the Government of Afghanistan officially ratified the Treaty. At that time, the Government established an ambitious target - *to free Afghanistan from the impact of anti-personnel mines within five years*.⁵⁰⁹ Implicit in this objective was the need by the end of 2007 to clear all mined areas significantly affecting the local communities, and to remove the threat from all other areas by risk reduction measures such as fencing, marking and Mine Risk Education. Hence, in September 2002, the MAPA announced a strategy that aimed to clear all high-impacted areas by 2007, and to remove the threat imposed from all remaining mined areas by 2012.

C. Consecutive strategic assessments and planning milestones

As illustrated in figure IV.2, numerous assessments of the Afghan landmine problem took place. The development of national strategic plans and various assessments has been an incremental process, supported by increasingly sophisticated impact surveys. Sketchy socio-economic impact assessment efforts in the late nineties have been expanded towards the comprehensive and standardized Landmine Impact Survey from 2003-2005. Figure IV.2 also depicts the strategic planning tools and processes. The significance of all these assessments has been rated in terms of output utility.

Fig. IV.2: Output utility of the different strategic surveys, planning tools and processes

Some of the activities shown above were or are time-sensitive. Owing to the dynamic situation, mine action data can only be used for a relative short timeframe. The assessments and tools still relevant today are the LIS, the Information Management System for Mine Action (IMSMA) and the strategic planning tool FREEWAY⁵¹⁰. The latter succeeded HIGHWAY, a similar strategic planning tool. This will be discussed further when addressing long-term strategic planning

⁵⁰⁸ BYRD and GILDESTAD. (2001). *Socio-Economic Impact of Mine Action in Afghanistan*, A Cost-Benefit Analysis, 2001, World Bank funded study, Internet. Available at [http://lnweb18.worldbank.org/SAR/sa.nsf/Attachments/9/\\$File/mines.pdf](http://lnweb18.worldbank.org/SAR/sa.nsf/Attachments/9/$File/mines.pdf), accessed on 25 April 2005

⁵⁰⁹ President Karzai made this statement public during the ICBL conference in Kabul, Afghanistan 28-31 July 2002, A Total Ban on Anti-Personnel Mines.

⁵¹⁰ HIGHWAY and FREEWAY are strategic planning tools for mine action developed by Cranfield University, UK. They are primarily spreadsheet based and able to project mine action outputs and costs during the lifecycle of a mine action programme.

issues. As emphasized before, LIS-data will be of critical value for the case-study. The following sections will address the framing politics and rhetoric in absence of credible LIS-data.

IV.2. Framing of the Afghan landmine problem

IV.2.1. Boasting the human cost

Before the LIS, no accurate data was available beyond the estimated 300 mine victims per month. This number, which almost served as an *anchor value*, was derived of data from the International Committee of the Red Cross (ICRC) in Afghanistan. At that time, their numbers were pretty much doubled by mine action practitioners for the accidents unaccounted for due to the absence of an adequate medical infrastructure in Afghanistan. The general landmine surveys⁵¹¹ of 1993 and 1998 have led to estimates of daily accident rates, but these are based on extrapolations and not hard data. Afghan mine action NGOs collected data during their survey work while the ICRC collected information from certain clinics and hospitals. Hence, the overall effort was piecemeal and unscientific. Consecutively, having no accurate data available made it easier to frame the landmine impact in terms of human cost in order to have the desired impact on donor countries.

“Afghanistan is the most mine and unexploded ordnance (UXO) - affected country in the world, with 732 km² of known mined area, of which an estimated 100km² are mined in former frontline areas, and approximately 500km² of UXO in contaminated battle areas. There are some 200,000 survivors of mine/UXO accidents and a death and injury rate running at 150-300 per month prior to the current crisis.”⁵¹²

With the rather simplistic mathematical exercise in figure IV.3 the numbers of *potential* victims were calculated.⁵¹³ This was further based on the assumption that the number of mine victims would experience a linear decrease according to the number of square kilometres high priority land cleared.⁵¹⁴ Based on the World Bank funded socio-economic impact study,⁵¹⁵ a 5%

Fig. IV.3: Mine victims with accelerated mine clearance of Afghanistan

⁵¹¹ Performed by the Afghan Mine Clearance and Planning Agency (national mine action NGO).

⁵¹² Afghanistan - Preliminary needs assessment for recovery and reconstruction. Internet. Available at www.adb.org/Documents/Reports/Afghanistan/pnarr.pdf, accessed on 13 January 2007

⁵¹³ The Strategic Plan for Mine Action in Afghanistan and Related Socio-Economic Benefits. Internet. Available at <http://www.mineaction.org/downloads/Strategic%20Plan.doc>, accessed on 19 January 2006

⁵¹⁴ It was decided by the UN programme management to be more conservative and assume 250 mine victims per month.

⁵¹⁵ BYRD and GILDESTAD. (2001). *Socio-Economic Impact of Mine Action in Afghanistan, A Cost-Benefit Analysis*, 2001, World Bank funded study, Internet. Available at [http://lnweb18.worldbank.org/SAR/sa.nsf/Attachments/9/\\$File/mines.pdf](http://lnweb18.worldbank.org/SAR/sa.nsf/Attachments/9/$File/mines.pdf), accessed on 25 April 2005

annual reduction in number of mine accidents was introduced to reflect the natural “learning process” of the local population.⁵¹⁶ Hence, donor countries were explained which *life-saving difference* they could make through funding the MAPA. This recalls earlier aspects of *prospect theory*.⁵¹⁷ In this context, what could be more convincing than people saved from mine accidents.

As illustrated, clearing all minefields with a high impact over 5 or 7 years compared to *no clearance*, resulted in compelling numbers of people saved from mine accidents. The prognoses was based on having sufficient funding to clear all minefields with a high impact in 5 years, and remaining minefields with a low impact over the next five years. In such a favourable situation, approximately 17000 people would be *saved* from mine accidents over a period of ten years compared to *no mine clearance* in Afghanistan (e.g. the “doing nothing” option).

Given the media attention Afghanistan enjoyed right after the Taliban regime was toppled, this calculation of an estimated 17000 people saved was used by the UN in its efforts to mobilize the maximum amount of resources possible for this programme. One strong statement would follow after the other, highlighting the advantages of the strategic approach of accelerating mine clearance efforts. It confronted the donor countries with the human cost of the Afghan landmine problem and which tragedy could further develop if the international community was not ready to respond swiftly with sufficient funding.

“A comprehensive strategic plan that maximizes the outcomes accruing from mine action in Afghanistan has been developed. The first component of this strategy will clear high impact areas within a five year period with targeted mine risk education programmes and clear the remaining low impact areas within a subsequent five year period. This plan will reduce the number of mine and UXO victims by an estimated 17,000.”⁵¹⁸

The estimate in figure IV.3 was used until more accurate data increasingly indicated that the number of victims could have been overestimated. Revisions based on a lower victims/month rate still projected 11 to 12 thousand mine victims. These numbers were still impressive, if they would not be based again on quite inflated estimates. In addition, the framing suggested a loss in “economic labour potential” and “saved medical costs” which was indeed extremely costly to the Afghan society.⁵¹⁹ Both “costs” assume however that every person who became victim of a mine accident would otherwise have been fulltime employed in a thriving Afghan economy. It was also optimistically assumed that every mine victim would benefit from adequate medical support.

IV.2.2. Boasting socio-economic benefits

With the estimated number of people saved from mine accidents being the pitch line during donor meetings, other benefits have been addressed in a similar way. Framed in equally impressive amounts of saved costs, they mount up to hundreds of millions US\$, again according to the principle of “loss of economic potential” and “costs related to refugee camps”.

“In 2002, almost 1.8 million refugees returned from Pakistan, Iran and the Central Asian Republics, and mobility throughout the country increased significantly. Displaced populations sought to return to their

⁵¹⁶ See also Phase-I, preamble paragraph 4 analysis, p. 63-70

⁵¹⁷ Phase-I, p.169

⁵¹⁸ TAPA 2003 Afghanistan- project rationale, Internet. Available at www.reliefweb.int/appeals/afg/TAPA2003, accessed on 12 July 2007

⁵¹⁹ This is a central theme in the study from BYRD and GILDESTAD. (2001), *Socio-Economic Impact of Mine Action in Afghanistan, A Cost-Benefit Analysis*, 2001, World Bank funded study, Internet. Available at [http://lnweb18.worldbank.org/SAR/sa.nsf/Attachments/9/\\$File/mines.pdf](http://lnweb18.worldbank.org/SAR/sa.nsf/Attachments/9/$File/mines.pdf), accessed on 25 April 2005

homes, however, in many cases mine/UXO contamination did not allow for their safe and sustainable return.”⁵²⁰

Often the estimates are based on unsubstantiated extrapolations, which easily cite millions of affected Afghans but fail to provide any meaningful qualification.

“Landmines and unexploded ordnance (UXO) affect some 6.4 million Afghans living in, or who plan to return to, one of 2,400 contaminated communities. The names of new victims and survivors from landmines and UXO are added to the list of past victims and survivors, a number now thought to be in excess of 100,000 people according to the best estimates.”⁵²¹

Only exceptionally the presence of landmines or ERW is the sole reason why refugees or IDPs do not return to their villages of origin. In many “creative” calculations this fact seems to be ignored. Depending on the costs or benefits considered, the difference in outcome between a minimalist and maximalist approach can be considerable. Some statements give the impression that a mine action programme could be a most profitable undertaking, based on isolated case-studies and overly optimistic economic assumptions.

“Mine action in Afghanistan has been extremely cost-effective based on experienced UN and NGO mine clearance teams and large scale use of mine detection dogs. Each dollar spent yields about \$4.60 in economic returns. The annual yield for one square kilometre of clearance is as much as US \$2,000 for grazing land and from \$13,500-520,000 for farmland. Cleared roads provide some \$250,000 in economic benefits per 50km. Mine action has resulted in an estimated 50% reduction in civilian mine victims, and has facilitated the return or resettlement of approximately 1.53 million refugees and IDPs.”⁵²²

The table below reflect some of the calculations of socio-economic benefits based on total clearance of Afghanistan by 2013, in order to respect the MBT deadlines.⁵²³ Based on socio-economic survey data,⁵²⁴ cumulative returns were indeed impressive but further based on unrealistic assumptions. For example, the costs for an estimated 100000 refugees - blocked from return by landmines - was simplistically cumulated for over a decade in order to come up with economic

	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	
Cost per refugee/year	60	66	73	80	88	97	106	117	129	141	
Refugees/IDPs due to mined residential area	70000	30000									
Reintegration the Afghan society		35000	85000	100000	100000	100000	100000	100000	100000	100000	
Average per capita GDP (=200 USD)	200	206	212	219	225	232	239	246	253	261	3% growth
Future Value	420000	9190000	18035300	21854540	22510176	23185481	23881046	24597477	25335402	26095464	Total M US\$: 199
Economic benefits due to the return of Refugees & IDPs =											
Clearance of high prio agricultural land - Potential Socio-Economic Benefits of MAPA 2003-2012											
170 km² high priority	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	
Economic benefit/km²	112000	115360	118820,8	122385,424	126056,9867	129838,6963	133733,8572	137745,8729	141878,2491	146134,5966	3% growth/year
km² of agricultural land cleared	34	68	102	136	170	170	170	170	170	170	
Future Value	3808000	7844480	12119722	16644418	21429688	22072578	22734756	23416798	24119302	24842881	Total M US\$: 179
Economic benefits due to clearance of high prio agricultural land =											
Recovery of grazing areas & decreased loss of livestock - Potential Socio-Economic Benefits of MAPA 2003-2012											
	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	
Livestock savings/km²	2441	2392	2344	2297	2252	2206	2162	2119	2077	2035	2% drop per year (=3% growth - 5% drop accident rate)
Net output value/km²	1682	1732	1784	1838	1893	1950	2008	2069	2131	2195	
agricultural/grazing/roads = 580 km² gradually cleared	62	104	176	260	370	410	450	490	540	580	
Future Value	255626	428963	726664	1075208	1533504	1704112	1876832	2051994	2272007	2453288	Total M US\$: 14
Economic benefits due to recovery of grazing areas & decreased loss of livestock =											

Fig. IV.4: Long-term projections of socio-economic benefits used to impress donors of effectiveness of the Afghan Mine Action Programme

⁵²⁰ MAPA 2002 Strategy, Internet. Available at www.reliefweb.int/library/documents/2003/unmas-afg-03nov.pdf, accessed on 12 July 2007

⁵²¹ UNMAS website – Country profile Afghanistan. Internet. Available at www.mineaction.org, accessed on 3 July 2006

⁵²² Afghanistan - Preliminary needs assessment for recovery and reconstruction, Internet. Available at http://www.mineaction.org/countries/_refdocs.cfm?doc_ID=463&country_ID=910, accessed on 12 June 2006

⁵²³ The Strategic Plan for Mine Action in Afghanistan and Related Socio-Economic Benefits. Internet. Available at <http://www.mineaction.org/downloads/Strategic%20Plan.doc>, accessed on 19 January 2006

benefits of 199 million dollars! For the calculation of the economic benefits following the clearance of high value agricultural land and grazing, it is assumed that immediately after clearance the land returns to full productive use and has an economic return at maximum profitability. These overly optimistic estimates emphasize some of the challenges and methodological risks regarding the quantification of socio-economic benefits.

After the strategic planning attempts in 2002, it became increasingly obvious that all these estimates, benchmarks and goals were too ambitious, while mine clearance of Afghan land painstakingly slow. The sudden introduction of the conditionality, cited below, that operations had to be further accelerated in order to achieve these goals was nothing short from a cover up. The UN programme management got caught up in its own approach and the juggling of numbers indicates a further loss of realism. As per below annual reporting, the programme would now clear 157 km² between 2003-2008 and a completely unrealistic 630 km² during the five years thereafter, still in a desperate attempt to make the MBT clearance deadlines. Notably, the initial “former battle area” estimate of 500 km² was suddenly reduced to 51 km².

“With the acceleration of the programme, 157,748 km² of designated high impact area and 51 km² of former battle area (only contaminated by UXO) can be cleared within five years. (...) In the remaining five years 236.622 km² of medium impact area and 394,370 km² of low impact area will be cleared. The strategy also includes benchmarks and goals for overall coordination, mine risk education, monitoring, and evaluation, training and coordination with mine victim organizations.”⁵²⁵

In sum, together with the projected reduction in mine accidents, socio-economic benefits have been systematically exaggerated for fund-raising purposes, quickly leading to unrealistic expectations on what can be really achieved on the ground. The next sections will put in perspective the projected mine clearance output of the MAPA.

IV.2.3. Boasting MAPA’s effectiveness and mine clearance rates

The strategic importance of *reliable mine clearance rates* is one of the conclusions of the preceding research phases. Studying the consecutive strategic planning efforts for Afghanistan demonstrates convincingly that exaggerated clearance rates jeopardizes the value and credibility of the whole strategic planning effort and outcome. Table IV.1 shows the clearance rates which were used during the initial strategic planning efforts. The clearance rates are largely the result of empiric mine clearance data,⁵²⁶ observed during a period when less stringent mine clearance regulations were applicable.

With the introduction of the International Mine Action Standards (IMAS) much higher security standards for mine clearance operations would slow down mine clearance rates, sometimes with more than 50%! Table IV.1 illustrates also the large variance of clearance rates⁵²⁷ depending on the type of land or infrastructure: agricultural land, grazing land, residential area, roads and irrigation channels. Based on these rates, an initial average was determined for basic strategic planning purposes of approximately 1400 m² per day and per mine clearance team (between 20 to 24 deminers). This would soon prove to be a significant overestimate which would distort the whole strategic planning process.

⁵²⁴ BYRD and GILDESTAD. (2001), *Socio-Economic Impact of Mine Action in Afghanistan*, A Cost-Benefit Analysis, 2001, World Bank funded study, Internet. Available at [http://lnweb18.worldbank.org/SAR/sa.nsf/Attachments/9/\\$File/mines.pdf](http://lnweb18.worldbank.org/SAR/sa.nsf/Attachments/9/$File/mines.pdf), accessed on 25 April 2005

⁵²⁵ UNMAS Document, United Nations Mine Action programme for Afghanistan, Annual Report 2002, New York, p.10

⁵²⁶ These overly optimistic clearance rates were provided by UNMAS for the second strategic planning effort (September 2002).

⁵²⁷ Data reliability and clearance rate accuracy also suffered from up-beat statements of NGOs in trying to outrank their peers on clearance performance.

UNOCHA Mine Action Programme for Afghanistan							
Mine Clearance Rate (Applicable as at 15 October 2001)							
Agency	System/Method	Agri-land (sqm/T-hours)	Grazing (sqm/T-hours)	Residential (sqm/T-hours)	Road (sqm/T-hours)	Irrigation (sqm/T-hours)	General Average
ATC	Manual	230	199	8	0	0	146
	Mechanical support to Clearance	29	49	14	0	28	30
DAFA	Manual	192	732	33	0	145	276
	Mechanical support to Clearance	87	0	38	90	237	113
OMAR	Manual	298	311	80	0	559	312
	Mechanical support to Clearance	11	0	15	0	11	12
HALO	Manual	115	146	57	171	0	122
	Mechanical support to Clearance	81	0	107	0	0	94
	Survey	155	114	99	200	0	142
MCPA	Manual	200	344	18	0	0	187
	Survey	479	269	162	663	465	408
Area	Manual	0	60	0	0	60	60
DDG	Manual	66	30	35	26	0	39
MDC	By Dogs	542	550	375	502	642	519
	By Dogs	3144	3300	2250	3012	0	2927
General Average Per Hour		212	239	51	502	145	230
General Average Per Day		1272	1434	306	3012	870	1379

Table IV.1: Mine Clearance rates in Afghanistan

Other clearance rates for planning are related to *battle area clearance* (BAC). These areas need only to be cleared from unexploded ordnance or visible explosive remnants of war; hence, as per below, clearance rates in m²/day can be *five to twenty times higher than mine clearance rates*.

UNOCHA - Battle Area Clearance Rate						
NGOs	DAFA MCT-BAC	HALO MCT-BAC	ATC MCT - BAC	DDG MCT-BAC	MCPA SVY-BAC	HALO SURVEY - BAC
Total sqm	2969571	81484054	13359023	600000	13418939	86894099
Total Team - Hour	743	4435	2709	96	2991	4250
Average	3997	18373	4931	6250	4486	20446

Table IV.2: Battle Area Clearance (BAC) rates in Afghanistan

Even higher than average *mine clearance* and *battle area clearance* rates were used for the strategic planning assumptions in “HIGHWAY” strategic planning software, illustrated in figure IV.4.⁵²⁸ The outcome in terms of cost and land cleared depends on clearance rates (Box N°1) and assumed improvements of the clearance rates (Box N°2), multiplied by working times (Box N°3) in order to obtain the output on a yearly basis.

The costs in figure IV.4 can be subdivided into the training of mine clearance teams (Box N°4), equipping them (Box N°5) and annual running costs (Box N°7). Costing is disaggregated according to the different activities related to the *mine clearance “toolbox”*: *manual clearance*, *mechanical clearance* and *mine detection dog clearance*. In addition to the running cost per team, other annual costs related to mine risk education, victim assistance, marking of minefields, management overhead and Explosive Ordnance Disposal have to be included in order to obtain the total cost for the Mine Action Programme in Afghanistan.

⁵²⁸ The Strategic Plan for Mine Action in Afghanistan and Related Socio-Economic Benefits. Internet. Available at <http://www.mineaction.org/downloads/Strategic%20Plan.doc>, accessed on 19 January 2006

Assumptions STRATEGIC PLANNING ASSUMPTIONS

1. Clearance Rates (Team/Day)

With Mech Prep	Without Mech Prep	sqm (Manual)
1650	1440	
3250	3250	sqm (Dog)
	1240	sqm (Mech)
	1200	sqm (Tech Survey)
	36000	sqm (BAC)

2. Clearance Rate Improvements

Year #	2	5	%
Year #	5	5	%
Year #	8	3	%
Year #	0	0	%

4. Initial Team Training Costs (\$ / Team)

	Training	ReTrain Cost	ReTrainTime
Manual	\$ 3200	20 %	9
Dog	\$ 3800	20 %	10
Mechanical	\$ 2900	20 %	9
Tech Survey	\$ 1200	20 %	9
BAC	\$ 3700	20 %	8

7. Annual Running Costs (\$/Year)

	Running
Manual	\$ 173000
Dog	\$ 101000
Mechanical	\$ 161000
Tech Survey	\$ 76600
BAC	\$ 117600
Mines Awareness	\$ 2500000
Victim Assistance	\$ 500000
Community Marking	\$ 6000000
Project Management, Administration	\$ 4000000
EOD	\$ 3000000

3. Working Times

Manual	215	Days / Year
Dog	215	Days / Year
Mechanical	215	Days / Year
Tech Survey	215	Days / Year
BAC-EOD	215	Days / Year

5. Initial Team Equipping Costs (\$ / Team)

	Equipping	Re Equip Cost	ReEquipTime
Manual	\$ 117600	20 %	9
Dog	\$ 77000	20 %	10
Mechanical	\$ 157000	20 %	9
Tech Survey	\$ 46000	20 %	9
BAC	\$ 210000	20 %	8

6. Training Time

1 Months

8. Programme Duration

3 5 7 9 11

Strategic Assumptions

Template Update Test

Fig. IV.4 Strategic planning assumptions related to the Mine Action Programme in Afghanistan

As mentioned earlier, HIGHWAY/FREEWAY strategic planning tools have been used for consecutive strategic planning efforts. The main reason to address it at this stage is to highlight the *impact of unrealistic clearance rates, resulting in unrealistic outcomes and prognoses*. Only 20 to 30% of the projected clearance in figure IV.5⁵²⁹ would take place in the real world. The 10-year timeframe (2003-2012) of the Mine Ban Treaty for the clearance of all minefields (then estimated 800 km²) in Afghanistan pressured the UN programme management into a *spurious strategic planning process*.

Fig. IV.5: Unrealistic clearance rates leading to spurious strategic planning results

This also had its repercussions on the interaction with donor countries and raised the expectations far beyond what the MAPA would be able to deliver. The required output was coupled to prognoses of the required expansion of personnel and mine action assets. The number of employees required, illustrated in figure IV.6, was a significant underestimation

⁵²⁹ Mine action Programme for Afghanistan, Strategic Plan 2003-2012. Internet. Available at <http://www.reliefweb.int/library/documents/2003/govafg-afg-31jan.pdf>, accessed on 19 January 2006

due to the use of excessively high mine clearance rates.⁵³⁰ This did not even take into account other expansion constraints such as mine dog breeding programmes not being able to reach the capacity required to clear more than 30 km² per year; or competition for labour force between the different post-conflict restoration sectors.

Fig IV.6: Programme expansion to meet the strategic MBT clearance deadlines

“Salary scales have also become a serious headache for Afghan demining agencies, which complain they are losing key staff to UN and other agencies such as USAID or foreign contractors offering substantially higher pay. This may seriously impair the operating capacity of some NGOs.”⁵³¹

In a similar way the unrealistic mine clearance rates resulted into cost estimates which would quickly prove to be far below to what would be really required. Illustrated in figure IV.7⁵³², early strategic planning projected a total cost of 500 million US\$ in order to make Afghanistan mine free, or an estimated average of 625,000 US\$/km².

“According to cost estimates developed in 2002, some US\$ 300 million will be required to carry out the first five years of the mine action strategy, with another US\$ 200 million required for the remaining five years. Using current casualty rates, an estimated 12000 victims could be prevented by this plan.”⁵³³

Fig IV.7: Portrayed strategic objectives and strategic requirements to achieve the Mine Ban Treaty deadlines

⁵³⁰ Mine clearance rates were assumed the double of what was realistically possible. The Strategic Plan for Mine Action in Afghanistan and Related Socio-Economic Benefits. Internet. Available at <http://www.mineaction.org/downloads/Strategic%20Plan.doc>, accessed on 19 January 2006

⁵³¹ MASLEN, S. (2004). *Mine Action after Diana – Myths and Realities*, United Kingdom, p.40

⁵³² Mine action Programme for Afghanistan, Strategic Plan 2003-2012. Internet. Available at <http://www.reliefweb.int/library/documents/2003/govafg-afg-31jan.pdf>, accessed on 19 January 2006

Based on Landmine Monitor reports, figure IV.8⁵³⁴ reflects both the clearance of minefields and battlefields over a time span of 15 years. It clearly indicates how the output in terms of km² minefield clearance has been fluctuating around 30 km² per year. The extra capacity generated since 2002 has been largely used for battle area clearance, more specifically the clearance of unexploded cluster bombs from US air strikes against the Taliban.

The Landmine Impact Survey (LIS) in Afghanistan would later confirm that the sustainable output of clearing 30 km² per year which could result in very positive effects on the ground, if the mine clearance efforts are well prioritised and targeted!

“Overall, it is estimated that up to 100 square kilometers of minefields need to be cleared in order to get rid of all SHAs that are associated with recent fatalities. Based on *current clearance rates of 30 square kilometres per annum*, it is not inconceivable that the most dangerous 20% of SHAs could be cleared in three years.”⁵³⁵

IV.2.4. Sub-optimal prioritization of mine action

A. Evolution of the classification of affected land

a. Two categories: high and low impact

Until 2003, the MAPA classified mine-affected land mainly in two categories: *high* and *low* priority land. High priority land was defined as contaminated areas with a significant risk of mine/UXO accident or affected land with significant economic potential (farmland). Low priority

Fig. IV.8: Minefield and Battlefield clearance in Afghanistan (in km²)

land was characterized as being mainly desolate mountainous land and grazing areas with low economic value.

b. Five categories of contaminated land

The division in Afghanistan between high and low priority mine clearance tasks did not allow a refined operational response to the mine/ERW contamination, let alone establish a prioritization system based on even rudimentary forms of multiple criteria analysis. Operators in the field developed prioritization mechanisms which categorized affected land according to five categories: *High Priority 1, High Priority 2, Medium Priority 3, Low Priority 4* and *Low Priority 5*.⁵³⁶ A variant

⁵³³ Mine Action Programme for Afghanistan, Progress Report, 1 January 2003 to 20 March 2004, Government of Afghanistan

⁵³⁴ Graph based on composite information of SIMAA for the period 1990-99, Landmine Monitor 2004 for 1999-2003, Landmine Monitor 2005 for clearance data 2004.

⁵³⁵ Landmine Impact Survey of the Islamic Republic of Afghanistan, Survey Action Centre, Washington, p. 12

⁵³⁶ Refer to field visit in March 2003 - based on results from earlier surveys

of this prioritization system was applied by the international NGO *HALO Trust* for its mine clearance operations in the Kabul area and northern Afghan provinces.

This categorization definitely had potential but met obstacles for its nationwide implementation due to a degree of sophistication which could not be met by credible data and a general lack of standardisation.

c. Three categories of impacted communities: high-medium-low

In anticipation of the LIS, a landmine survey working group studied the above sub-optimal prioritization mechanisms. In accordance with the LIS methodology, a standardized high-medium and low impact categorization of *affected communities* was introduced, hereby replacing the former high-low impact categorization of *mined land*.

B. The Landmine Impact Survey: time for change!

In line with the findings and recommendations of Phase-II, the research objective of the modelling is to ensure that the limited resources of the Afghan mine action programme could have the greatest possible effect in each planning cycle on the human cost, peacekeeping/building risks and socio-economic blockages imposed on mine affected Afghan communities. As confirmed in Phase-II, the LIS is of critical value to assist prioritization of mine action.

Based on the LIS-results, 2368 communities were identified as mine affected. This represents 8% of the 33,139 communities in Afghanistan. An estimated 4.2 million people live in landmine/UXO-impacted communities, with 1.6 million of these people living in high-or medium-impact communities. It is estimated that approximately 15% of *all* Afghan citizens are living in mine-impacted communities.

Figure IV.9 indicates that 281 (12%) communities are categorized as high impact, 480 (20%) as medium impact, and 1,607 (68%) as low impact. Additionally, the LIS confirmed the existence of 4,514 Suspected Hazard Areas (SHA). Sixteen percent of the SHAs are located in high impact communities while 23% are in medium impact communities and 61% in low impact ones.⁵³⁷

Fig. IV.9: Overview of the impact scores of mine-affected communities according to the Afghan LIS

⁵³⁷ Survey Action Centre. (2005) Landmine Impact Survey of the Islamic Republic of Afghanistan, Washington DC, p.9

Below maps⁵³⁸ provide an overview of the magnitude of the landmine problem in terms of affected communities and territory. Same colour code for high impact (red dots), medium impact (orange) and low impact (yellow).

Fig. IV.10: Overview results of the Afghan Landmine Impact Survey

The level and exploitation of information provided by the LIS will be criticized in this case-study, although being much better than other sources of information the MAPA has relied upon before. For example, after many years of efforts to obtain maps of minefields laid in Afghanistan by the former Soviet Union, the MAPA received a set of maps of Kabul and other areas in northern Afghanistan. Sub-optimal coordination and perhaps an element of competition between the UN and the different international and national NGOs, caused several delays in information-sharing.⁵³⁹

Fig. IV.11: Old USSR Map of mined positions in and around Kabul City versus LIS

⁵³⁸ Survey Action Centre. (2005) Landmine Impact Survey of the Islamic Republic of Afghanistan, Washington Dc, p.20

⁵³⁹ This was witnessed during a field visit to the Mine Action Programme in Afghanistan in March 2003 at the occasion of a strategic planning workshop in Kabul.

Figure IV.11 illustrates that the level of detail is not always satisfactory or useful.⁵⁴⁰ It indicates imprecisely the location of minefields and provides no information on the level of impact on surrounding communities. Not surprisingly most Afghan mine action prioritization and strategic planning suffered initially from trial and error.

“The targets set by the strategic plan are also *prepared on the basis of outdated data*. No-one knows now the precise extent of mine /UXO contaminated land in Afghanistan. The end of the war has opened up areas of the country that were previously inaccessible and will likely reveal new minefields. A “retrofit” Landmine Impact Survey is now seeking to provide much-needed baseline data with which to review targets and priorities both for purposes of mine clearance and mine awareness programmes.”⁵⁴¹

Hence, based on the much better LIS-data, this research phase will now apply and further refine the normative model developed in Phase-II. The modelling effort will start with one of the most heavily affected areas in the world: Kabul.

⁵⁴⁰ Map obtained through USCENTCOM CENTRIX database, Operation Enduring Freedom, Florida-Tampa, 2004

⁵⁴¹ MASLEN, S., (2004). *Mine Action after Diana – Myths and Realities*, United Kingdom, p.40

IV.3. Applying the model on Afghanistan

IV.3.1 Prioritization of mine action for Kabul

A. Impact characteristics

Kabul is the most heavily impacted province in Afghanistan. It is comprised of 968 communities, of which 313—or 32% of them—are impacted by landmines. Thirteen percent of all the impacted communities in Afghanistan are in Kabul province. Of the 313 impacted communities, the LIS determined that 18% are high impact, 28% are medium impact, and 54% are low impact. The survey further states that landmines and ERW impact all of the province’s 14 districts, with the districts of Paghman and Shakardara containing 40% of the impacted communities in the province. In both of these districts, nearly one-half of all the communities are impacted, which is clearly noticeable in the below map.⁵⁴² Taken together, these two districts contain 229 suspected hazardous areas (SHAs) as well as the second and third highest number of victims for any district in Afghanistan.⁵⁴³ Only Bagram district in Parwan province has more victims.

In stark contrast with the previous map, the map in figure IV.12 allows for a much better appraisal of the Kabul landmine impact footprint, the density of the impacted communities and the relation between affected communities, the road network and terrain.

Fig IV.12: Impacted Communities in Kabul environment and Kabul Province

⁵⁴² Overview Map. Landmine Impact Survey of the Islamic Republic of Afghanistan, Survey Action Centre, Washington

⁵⁴³ Survey Action Centre (2005). Landmine Impact Survey of the Islamic Republic of Afghanistan, Washington DC, p.100

The complete survey was conducted from November 2002 to January 2005. However, the Kabul impact information portrayed is based on survey data collected between December 2002 and April 2004. Due to the enormity of the Afghan LIS, survey tasks were staggered. It lasted until end 2006 for the results to be officially published on the Survey Action Centre website. The certification process and translation took almost as much time as the survey process itself.⁵⁴⁴

B. Processing of LIS data

In Annex H detailed survey data is provided. The initial survey data needed quite some processing to facilitate regression analysis. In order to do so, the qualified military activity was quantified, data related to injured and fatal mine victims was merged, the number of total blockages per affected community was calculated.

IV.3.2. Human cost

A. LIS mine victim information

Fig. IV.13: Estimated mine victims/year reported by the LIS

The introduction of this chapter highlighted that mine accident or victim data was for a long time an inherent weakness of the information management of MAPA. Despite more than ten years of operations, with considerable archival documentation and on-going data gathering mechanisms, it did until the LIS not have a comprehensive understanding of the landmine death and injury rate country-wide.

The detailed and methodical collection of LIS-data concerning actual rates of death and injury will be of significant value for prioritization and targeting as well as providing a baseline from which future progress could be judged. The next subchapters will indicate how to use this survey information to best effect.

Figure IV.13 left, provides the estimated number of mine victims for the whole Afghanistan. It is based on the survey reports and increased by

⁵⁴⁴ A draft copy of the survey results was however available as soon as the LIS was finished.

15% for unreported victims. It indicates lower numbers than those projected during the “earlier framing” of the Afghan landmine problem (150-300 victims/month).

Figure IV.14 below, illustrates the detailed numbers of mine victims for the Kabul province. The highly unlikely fluctuation of the number of victims per month clearly indicate flaws in the survey methods as it is impossible that the number of victims will vary repetitively between 1 per month and approximately 40 victims the next month.

The data per semester is likely more reliable and much less influenced by the victim data registration methods inherent to the Afghan LIS. In order to have reliable time series for statistical analysis, figure IV.14 illustrates the importance of the collection methodology or processing of survey victim data.

Such data collection flaws are of particular concern in light of Bayesian data analysis or any other statistical analysis whereby the time dimension is critical; in particular in case of trend analysis to detect a causal relationship between *seasonal factors* causing higher numbers of mine victims.

Fig. IV.14: Number of registered 2002-2003 victims in Kabul reported by the LIS

In line with the principles and recommendations of Phase-II regarding the statistical analysis of mine victim data, the following sections will address the main observations and relevant statistical results. Both satisfactory and poor statistical results will be addressed. As depicted in the methodology of Chapter I, “StatGraphics Centurion Statistics Software” will be used for all statistical analysis.⁵⁴⁵

⁵⁴⁵ Statgraphics is a line of computer programs that perform and explain basic and advanced statistical functions. As of December 2005, the current release is the 15th version: Statgraphics Centurion XV. Internet. Available at www.statgraphics.com, accessed on 10 January 2006

B. Statistical analysis of KABUL survey data

a. Null and alternative hypothesis formulation

1. Overarching null hypothesis: Survey data on mine accidents reflects a stochastic phenomenon which is not statistically significant.

2. Alternative hypothesis: Advanced statistical analysis of mine accident data, including local data clustering and aggregation, will provide a statistical significant outcome with mine accident predictors suitable for decision analysis modelling.

b. Regression analysis of Kabul based on non-aggregated community level data

1. Screening for potential predictors: multiple variable regression analysis

With dependent variable “total recent victims” and 10 independent variables in table IV.3, this statistical method allows for a first screening in search for statistically significant mine accident predictors.

	Variables	R^2
F	Old victims killed/injured	14,9461
H	Number of Mined Areas	7,36583
I	Total Blockages (1 point per blockage)	2,78093
G	Population	1,46115
J	Total Mine and UXO contamination	0,571705
B	Years since last mine laying	0,466107
A	Total years of mine laying	0,420687
E	SHA Distance from Community	0,337838
D	Military Activity	0,337838
C	Years since last conflict	0,337838

Table IV.3: Ten independent variables

Fig IV.15: Adjusted R^2 plotting of variables

For *ten independent* variables, 313 observations, the statistical multiple variable regression analysis fits 1024 models. Only the best models are reflected in the “*adjusted*” R^2 plot in figure IV.15. Compared to R^2 , *adjusted* R^2 includes a correction factor for the number of variables. This explains why the *adjusted* R^2 value can decrease through adding more variables with low or no statistical significance.

With a R^2 of $\approx 15\%$, only the variable “*Old mine victims*”⁵⁴⁶ seems to have any potential as a statistical predictor for “*Recent mine victims*”.⁵⁴⁷ The next sections will further explore the statistical value if the regression analysis is based on *non-aggregated* community level data.

⁵⁴⁶ To remind, the reported number of victims *before* the LIS considered 24 months timeframe for observations of mine accidents.

⁵⁴⁷ The number of victims during a 24 month period before the LIS.

2. Poisson regression compared to a simple linear regression of the variable “Old Victims Killed/Injured”

Since community level data of mine victims is based on integer numbers, Poisson regressions can be considered. This is not a requirement for linear regressions.

In case of the *Poisson regression*, the result of fitting a *Poisson model* of the relationship between “*Total Recent Victims*” and “*Old Victims Killed/Injured*” can be described according to the following Poisson equation:

$$Total\ Recent\ Victims = exp(0.0458174 + 0.0123349 * Old\ Victims\ Killed/Injured)$$

The *percentage of deviance* in *Total Recent Victims* explained by the model equals 10.7657%. This statistic is similar to the usual R^2 statistic. Because the P-value is less than 0.05, the result is statistically significant at the 95.0% confidence level.

In case of the *linear regression*, the equation of the fitted *linear model* is:

$$Total\ Recent\ Victims = 0.517058 + 0.0579789 * Old\ Victims\ Killed/Injured$$

The P-value in the analysis of variance (ANOVA) is less than 0.05; hence, there is again a statistically significant relationship between *Total Recent Victims* and *Old Victims Killed/Injured* at the 95.0% confidence level.⁵⁴⁸ The R^2 statistic indicates that the model as fitted explains 14.94% of the variability in *Total Recent Victims*. The correlation coefficient equals 0.386602, indicating a relatively weak relationship between the variables.

3. Community level data largely confirms null hypothesis

Non-aggregated community data contains a lot of *noise* which significantly complicates trend analysis. It is in particular susceptible to outliers. Only the independent variable “old victims injured/killed” provides any statistical significant results, and even then. Neither the Poisson regression, nor the linear regression provides an attractive statistical goodness of fit for further modelling purposes.

⁵⁴⁸ ANOVA will be a standard procedure throughout the statistical analysis, unless stated otherwise.

c. Regression analysis of LIS mine victim data at district level

1. Aggregating data at district level

The map in figure IV.16 and table IV.4 provide a clear overview of the different levels of contamination per district and LIS impact data. More than 400 victims were reported in the 24-month period prior to the LIS. Annex H provides the detailed LIS-data per district, together with the calculations of the community data aggregated at district level.

Fig. IV. 16: Kabul province with its 14 impacted districts

District Name	Communities	Communities Impacted	High	Medium	Low	SHAs	Recent Victims
Shakardara	124	66	10	20	36	109	95
Paghman	133	60	13	16	31	120	80
Surobi	109	28	8	6	14	83	70
Khaki Jabbar	49	27	6	10	11	65	47
Kabul	191	24	1	6	17	31	9
Mir Bacha Kot	35	21	4	4	13	59	18
Dih Sabz	76	20	4	7	9	49	26
Qarabagh	47	14	3	2	9	25	25
Chahar Asyab	45	12	3	5	4	25	17
Musayi	40	12	0	5	7	15	5
Kalakan	18	11	3	4	4	31	14
Guldara	23	8	1	1	6	11	8
Bagrami	47	6	0	3	3	9	6
Istalif	31	4	0	0	4	5	0
TOTAL	968	313	56	89	168	637	420

Table IV.4: Summary of Districts and Communities, by level of impact and number of recent victims

2. Dependent variable: “Recent mine victims”

The arithmetic average of the *dependant variable* “total recent victims” per community portrays a significant variation at district level; from zero victims in Istalif to more than an average of two victims per affected community in the more remote Surobi district.

The following sections will provide the statistical regression analysis of the dependent variable “recent victims” versus the ten independent variables in table IV.6.

	District	Recent Mine Victims
1	Bagrami	1
2	Chahar Asyab	1.42
3	Dih Sabz	1.3
4	Guldara	1.00
5	Istalif	0.00
6	Kabul	0.38
7	Kalakan	1.4
8	Khaki Jabbar	1.81
9	Mir Bacha Kot	0.9
10	Musayi	0.45
11	Paghman	1.34
12	Qarabagh	1.92
13	Shakardara	1.46
14	Surobi	2.59

Table IV.6: Averages of ‘recent mine victims’

3. Ten independent variables

Independent variable		1	2	3	4	5
District		Total years of mine laying	Years since last mine laying	Years since last conflict	Mil Act Quantified	Distance RefPt to MA-edge(meters)
1	Bagrami	6.33	8.83	8.83	3.00	513.33
2	Chakar Asyab	9.17	11.67	7.83	2.50	205.50
3	Dih Sabz	11.4	9.25	9.25	2.55	145.35
4	Guldara	7.63	9.25	3.13	2.63	171.88
5	Istalif	6.25	6.25	6.25	3.00	432.50
6	Kabul	8.83	4.54	3.79	2.71	254.75
7	Kalakan	20.9	4.4	4.2	3.3	24.8
8	Khaki Jabbar	11.96	8.46	8.62	3.12	211.00
9	Mir Bacha Kot	16.7	3.8	3.15	3.15	42.7
10	Musayi	10.09	10.18	9.73	3.00	586.27
11	Paghman	12.63	7.90	6.12	3.05	287.41
12	Qarabagh	14.77	3.77	3.46	3.23	97.69
13	Shakardara	11.52	7.26	3.15	2.89	129.37
14	Surobi	7.07	15.74	7.11	2.93	100.56
Independent variable		6	7	8	9	10
District		Old Victims Killed Injured	Population	Mined Areas	Total blockages	Total AP/AT/UXO contamination
1	Bagrami	23.33	2775.00	1.50	1.17	1.83
2	Chakar Asyab	9.67	480.00	2.08	1.92	1.33
3	Dih Sabz	10.4	1701	2.45	2.35	1.5
4	Guldara	7.75	967.50	1.38	1.00	1.13
5	Istalif	12.50	1875.00	1.25	1.00	1.25
6	Kabul	15.63	3064.17	1.29	1.42	1.29
7	Kalakan	7.8	703.8	3.1	2	1.7
8	Khaki Jabbar	11.23	671.77	2.50	3.31	1.50
9	Mir Bacha Kot	10.2	988.5	2.95	2.2	1.5
10	Musayi	7.00	411.27	1.36	2.27	1.36
11	Paghman	14.71	1441.73	2.03	2.22	1.56
12	Qarabagh	20.85	990.00	1.92	1.85	1.54
13	Shakardara	15.26	1032.00	1.68	2.00	1.22
14	Surobi	26.85	523.85	3.07	1.44	1.15

Table IV.6: Aggregated data (arithmetic means) of impacted communities at district level

4. First screening for mine accident/victim predictors: multiple variable regression analysis

Dependent variable: Total Recent Victims
 Ten independent variables:

- A=Total years of mine laying
- B=Years since last mine laying
- C=Years since last conflict
- D=Mil activity Quantified
- E=Distance RefPt to MA edge in meters
- F=Old Victims killed or injured
- G=Population
- H=Mined Areas
- I=Total blockages
- J=Total AP-AT-UXO contamination

Fig IV.17: Adjusted R² plotting of variables

Figure IV.17 shows the results of fitting various multiple regression models to describe the relationship between “Total Recent Victims” and 10 predictor variables. Regression models have been fitted containing all combinations from 0 to 10 coefficients/variables.⁵⁴⁹

Analysis of Variance

Source	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F-Ratio	P-Value
Model	5.78782	7	0.826832	78.48	0.0000
Residual	0.0632146	6	0.0105358		
Total (Corr.)	5.85104	13			

Standard Error of Est. = 0.102644

Mean absolute error = 0.05164

Stepwise regression

Method: backward selection

Step 0: 10 variables in the model. 3 d.f. for error.

R-squared = 99.59% Adjusted R-squared = 98.22% MSE = 0.00801487

Step 1: Removing variable *Total years of mine laying* with F-to-remove =0.0170342

9 variables in the model. 4 d.f. for error.

R-squared = 99.59% Adjusted R-squared = 98.66% MSE = 0.00604528

Step 2: Removing variable *Years since last conflict* with F-to-remove =2.85035

8 variables in the model. 5 d.f. for error.

R-squared = 99.29% Adjusted R-squared = 98.16% MSE = 0.00828246

Step 3: Removing variable *Population* with F-to-remove =2.63235

7 variables in the model. 6 d.f. for error.

R-squared = 98.92% Adjusted R-squared = 97.66% MSE = 0.0105358

⁵⁴⁹ Statgraphics, Internet. Available at www.statgraphics.com, accessed on 22 January 2005

Final model selected: The output shows the results of fitting a multiple linear regression model to describe the relationship between *Total Recent Victims* and 6 retained independent variables.

The equation of the fitted multiple linear regression model is:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Total Recent Victims} = & -4.39589 + 0.212122 \times \text{Years since last mine laying} + 1.25261 \times \text{Mil Act} \\ & \text{Quantified} - 0.00487606 \times \text{Distance RefPt to MA edge meters} + 0.0271059 \\ & \times \text{Old Victims} - 0.738778 \times \text{Mined Areas} + 0.334226 \times \text{Total blockages} + \\ & 1.32009 \times \text{Total AP-AT-UXO contamination} \end{aligned}$$

Since the P-value in the ANOVA table is less than 0.05, there is a statistically significant relationship between the variables at the 95.0% confidence level. The R^2 statistic indicates that the model as fitted explains 98.9% of the variability in *Total Recent Victims*. The adjusted R^2 statistic, is 97.6%. The standard error of the estimate shows the standard deviation of the residuals to be 0.102644.

This only looks like an extraordinary good statistical fit. Unfortunately, almost 100% explanatory value of the model is definitely too good to be true. If this would be such an extremely reliable statistical result, then the modelling effort could stop here since mine accidents could be predicted with high certainty through solely relying on this multiple linear regression model.

As highlighted in Phase-II, statistical analysis should not pursue very high-order polynomial models with a number of parameters approaching the number of observations. This is an excellent example on how *not* to further pursue multiple linear regression modelling. Professor J. Scott Armstrong extensive publications on research in survey and forecasting methods further confirms that there are indeed many simple ways to raise R^2 ; but other than that, they are of *no value*.⁵⁵⁰

“If the number of variables is comparable to the number of data points, and if the variables are only imperfectly correlated among themselves, then a very modest search procedure will produce an equation with a relatively small number of explanatory variables, most of which come in with significant coefficients, and a highly significant R^2 . *This will be so even if Y is totally unrelated to the X's*.”⁵⁵¹

He further states that to maintain credibility in survey research the most important thing is not to be found guilty of the frequent statistical manipulations below:

- (1) Discard outliers after you examine the regression results.
- (2) Aggregate the data, especially when it reduces sample size significantly.
- (3) Experiment by trying lots of variables.
- (4) Try different functional forms.
- (5) Use stepwise regression and retain all coefficients with t statistics greater than 1.0.
- (6) Include a lot of variables in the final equation.

In conclusion, these rules indeed yield R^2 values of over 90%; however, the dangers for incorporating such unreliable statistics in the model would definitely outweigh any potential benefits. For this reason, the statistical analysis will focus entirely on the calculation of R^2 of *simple* linear regressions to avoid as much as possible untrustworthy statistical analysis and establish a uniform procedure to scan mine victim data for possible predictors. To remind, only statistical significant results will be taken into consideration (P-value < 0.05).

⁵⁵⁰ ARMSTRONG, J., (1985). *Long-Range Forecasting*, 2nd ed., Philadelphia, p. 487

⁵⁵¹ GOOD, P., HARDIN, J. (2003). *Common Errors in Statistics*, New Jersey, p.146

5. Simple linear regression analysis of aggregated variables

Simple linear regression analysis was performed on all ten independent variables. All statistical analysis was subject to analysis of variance. Only two variables provided an attractive goodness of fit, with P-values below 0.05: (1) the distance between the community centre and the minefield(s) and (2) the number of mined areas.

(1) Total Recent Victims vs. Distance RefPt to MA edge (in meters)

Coefficients

	Least Squares	Standard	T	
Parameter	Estimate	Error	Statistic	P-Value
Intercept	1.73424	0.257757	6.7282	0.0000
Slope	-0.00228199	0.000912124	-2.50184	0.0278

Analysis of Variance

Source	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F-Ratio	P-Value
Model	2.00572	1	2.00572	6.26	0.0278
Residual	3.84532	12	0.320443		
Total (Corr.)	5.85104	13			

Correlation Coefficient = -0.585489

Standard Error of Est. = 0.566077

$$\Rightarrow R^2 = 34.3 \%$$

The equation of the fitted model is:

$$\text{Total Recent Victims} = 1.73424 - 0.00228199 * \text{Distance RefPt to MA edge (meters)}$$

Since the P-value in the ANOVA table is less than 0.05, there is a statistically significant relationship between “Total Recent Victims” and “Distance RefPt to MA_edge_meters” at the 95.0% confidence level. The R^2 statistic indicates that the model as fitted explains 34.2797% of the variability in Total Recent Victims. The correlation coefficient equals -0.585489, indicating a moderately strong relationship between the variables.

(2) Total Recent Victims vs. number of Mined Areas

Coefficients

	Least Squares	Standard	T	
Parameter	Estimate	Error	Statistic	P-Value
Intercept	-0.10988	0.466362	-0.235611	0.8177
Slope	0.64805	0.217821	2.97515	0.0116

Analysis of Variance

Source	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F-Ratio	P-Value
Model	2.48378	1	2.48378	8.85	0.0116
Residual	3.36725	12	0.280604		
Total (Corr.)	5.85104	13			

Correlation Coefficient = 0.651539

Standard Error of Est. = 0.529721

$$\Rightarrow R^2 = 42.5 \%$$

The equation of the fitted model is:

$$\text{Total Recent Victims} = -0.10988 + 0.64805 * \text{Mined Areas}$$

6. Summary of the regression analysis of aggregated independent variables

Nr	Potential predictor	P-value	Correlation	R ² (in %)	MCDA criteria?
1	Total years of mine laying	0.46	0.21	4.62	Rejected
2	Years since last mine laying	0.13	0.41	17.27	Rejected
3	Years since last conflict	0.92	0	0.08	Rejected
4	Mil Act Quantified	0.63	0.13	1.93	Rejected
5	Distance RefPt to MA edge (in m)	0.02	0.56	34.3	Retained
6	Old Victims Killed Injured	0.09	0.47	22.42	Rejected
7	Population	0.07	0.49	24.6	Rejected
8	Mined Areas	0.01	0.65	42.5	Retained
9	Total blockages	0.26	0.32	10.36	Rejected
10	Total AP-AT-UXO contamination	0.88	0	0.19	Rejected

Table IV.6: Retained/rejected victim predictors for MCDA modelling

In sum, based on aggregated data at district level the statistical regression analysis indicated that the *closer* and *more numerous* the mined areas are around a community, the more mine victims are predicted. “Old victims Killed/Injured” was rejected with a P-value > 0.05. Based on more accurate “New mine victims” data of accidents which took place during a 24-month period prior the survey, the subsequent and complementary regression analysis in the following sections envisage to bring more precision regarding the *recency* effects of mine accidents.

7. Regression analysis of the *recency* factor for Kabul

Phase-I and II elaborated extensively on Bayesian principles of *prior* and *posterior* information and probabilities. In light of this, table IV.7 provides in *time series* format the mine victims per semester in order to have the ability to do time series analysis through simple linear regression analysis between the different semesters. The aggregation procedure at this juncture is just the sum-up of mine victims per semester without the requirement of calculating district averages. Similar to the preceding statistical analysis, coefficients of determination will be calculated for further exploitation in light of the requirement to determine “human cost” weight coefficients for the MCDA-model.

Nr	Province	District	Victims per Semester			
			0-182 days	183-365 days	366-548 days	549-731 days
			SEM1	SEM2	SEM3	SEM4
1	Kabul	Bagrami	1	1	0	4
2	Kabul	Chahar Asyab	1	4	6	6
3	Kabul	Dih Sabz	7	8	7	3
4	Kabul	Guldara	0	3	3	2
5	Kabul	Kabul	1	6	1	1
6	Kabul	Kalakan	2	7	4	1
7	Kabul	Khaki Jabbar	13	26	4	3
8	Kabul	Mir Bacha Kot	1	9	5	3
9	Kabul	Paghman	12	24	16	27
10	Kabul	Musayi	0	4	1	0
11	Kabul	Qarabagh	1	11	6	6
12	Kabul	Shakardara	15	27	17	33
13	Kabul	Surobi	9	30	17	11
14	Kabul	Istalif	0	0	0	0
	Kabul	Average/community	0.19	0.48	0.29	0.32
		Standard variation	0.59	1.4	0.79	1.18

(1) Simple Regression SEM1 vs. SEM2

Dependent variable: SEM1
 Independent variable: SEM2
 Linear model: $Y = a + b \cdot X$

Coefficients

	Least Squares	Standard	T	
Parameter	Estimate	Error	Statistic	P-Value
Intercept	-0.911789	1.2423	-0.733954	0.4798
Slope	0.473984	0.0753946	6.28671	0.0001

Analysis of Variance

Source	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F-Ratio	P-Value
Model	276.333	1	276.333	39.52	0.0001
Residual	69.9175	10	6.99175		
Total (Corr.)	346.25	11			

Correlation Coefficient = 0.893349

Standard Error of Est. = 2.64419

The equation of the fitted model is: $SEM1 = -0.911789 + 0.473984 \cdot SEM2$

$\Rightarrow R^2 = 79.8072 \%$

Since the P-value in the ANOVA table is less than 0.05, there is a statistically significant relationship between SEM1 and SEM2 at the 95.0% confidence level. The R^2 statistic indicates that the model as fitted explains 79.8072% of the variability in SEM1.

(2) Overview regression analysis of the recency factor

Analogue to the regression analysis between the first and second semester, Annex I provides a detailed overview of the regression analysis between all the other possible combinations for Kabul. It can be observed that when the number of semesters in between observations increases, the standard error of estimation increases whilst logically R^2 and the correlation decreases.

Kabul	R^2	Δ SEM	Correlation	Stand. Error	Statistical Fitted Model
SEM 1 vs. SEM 2	79.8%	1	0.89	2.64	$SEM1 = -0.911789 + 0.473984 \cdot SEM2$
SEM 1 vs. SEM 3	54.0%	2	0.73	3.98	$SEM1 = 0.382909 + 0.679129 \cdot SEM3$
SEM 1 vs. SEM 4	53.12%	3	0.72	4.03	$SEM1 = 2.0231 + 0.387228 \cdot SEM4$
SEM 2 vs. SEM 3	65.8%	1	0.81	6.48	$SEM2 = 2.87716 + 1.41249 \cdot SEM3$
SEM 2 vs. SEM 4	43.6%	2	0.66	8.33	$SEM2 = 7.49049 + 0.661141 \cdot SEM4$
SEM 3 vs. SEM 4	70.98%	1	0.84	3.43	$SEM3 = 3.12908 + 0.484511 \cdot SEM4$

Table IV.8: Overview regression analysis between semesters

d. Calculation and normalization of weight coefficients based on multiple R^2 calculations

The *coefficient of determination* is for the purposes of this case-study calculated in %-values according to:

$$R^2 = 100 \left(1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2} \right) \% \begin{matrix} \longrightarrow \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2 = \text{sum of squared errors (SS}_E) \\ \longrightarrow \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2 = \text{total sum of squares (SS}_T) \end{matrix}$$

Hence, in this simple linear regression case, R^2 is simply the square of the correlation coefficient or the *squared correlation*, giving the *proportion of the common variance* between the dependent and independent variable.⁵⁵² Consequently, the R^2 percentage decreases more quickly with lower correlation values. The proportion of variance not shared between the variables, obtained through subtracting the coefficient of determination from the unity, is called the *coefficient of alienation*.⁵⁵³ In addition, the coefficient of determination is always positive while correlation coefficients turn negative in case of a decreasing linear relationship. The interpretation of R^2 or (squared) correlation coefficients depends further on the context and purposes. In the context of this statistical analysis, R^2 should only be used for weighting purposes if a causal relationship between the two variables can be logically assumed.

Several possible contributing factors to mine accidents have been addressed during Phase-II in order to obtain a better understanding of the causes underlying the correlation. This is important in case of the 10 aggregated independent variables. In this regard, the Kabul regression analysis indicated that the closer a minefield is to the centre of the community and the higher the number of minefields around the community, the higher the number of mine accidents. If these relationships are accepted as causal and the result is statistically significant (P-value < 0.05), then the squared correlation or R^2 provides a logic and non-sophisticated reference for the determination of weighting coefficients. In case of the *recency* factor, the logic understanding of the causal relationship is less critical, since the effort is not to understand the underlying factors which contribute to mine accidents but simply to calculate how a certain number of mine accidents during a six-month period is correlated with the number of mine accidents in successive semesters. Based on the regression analysis of the *recency* factor, coefficients of determination can be averaged over several semesters covered by the survey data. The four semesters allow calculating the 6-months recency effect for: SEM 1vs2, SEM 1vs4 and SEM 2vs3. Two R^2 can be calculated regarding the 12-month recency effect: SEM 1vs3 and SEM 2vs4.

$$\bar{R}_{0-6months}^2 = \frac{R_{SEM\ 1vs2}^2 + R_{SEM\ 2vs3}^2 + R_{SEM\ 3vs4}^2}{3} = (79.8+65.8+70.98)/3 = \mathbf{72.2\%}$$

$$\bar{R}_{7-12months}^2 = \frac{R_{SEM\ 1vs3}^2 + R_{SEM\ 2vs4}^2}{2} = (54+43.6)/2 = \mathbf{48.8\%}$$

For the purposes of the dissertation, these two averaged R^2 are regarded as sufficient to adequately incorporate the highly statistically significant recency effects. Based on further detailed mine victim reports of subsequent semesters, averaging R^2 for first and second semester recency effects will become increasingly reliable for the determination of weight coefficients. *Normalization* in table IV.9 of the R^2 of all four criteria is a simple procedure. It is not a strict requirement for PROMETHEE but it facilitates comparison between different weight coefficients and is therefore more transparent towards decision-maker(s).

Kabul	R^2	Normalized weight coefficients
Victims 0-6 months	72.2%	0.365
Victims 7-12 months	48.8%	0.247
Distance to minefield (in m)	34.3%	0.173
Number of Mined Areas	42.5%	0.215
		$\Sigma = 1$

Table IV.9: Normalization of averaged R^2 in weight coefficients

⁵⁵² The *linear correlation coefficient*, measures the strength and the direction of a linear relationship between two variables. The linear correlation coefficient is sometimes referred to as the *Pearson product moment correlation coefficient* in honor of its developer Karl Pearson. <http://mathbits.com/MathBits/TISection/Statistics2/correlation.htm>

⁵⁵³ ABDI, H. (2007). *Coefficients of correlation, alienation and determination*. In N.J. Salkind (Ed.): *Encyclopedia of Measurement and Statistics*. Thousand Oaks (CA): Sage. pp. 158-162.

C. Development of “human cost” preference or outranking functions

Table IV.10 below provides the 4 identified “human cost” outranking functions. For illustrative purposes, an *indifference threshold* q is suggested to anticipate measurement inaccuracies regarding the “distance of the community to the minefield(s)”. Contrary to the other criteria, distance to minefield(s) is a minimization function with highest rankings allocated to communities closest to the minefields (=higher risk of a mine accident). To install an indifference threshold, a type II criterion (U-shape) is required. Since fuzzy logic will be introduced at the second stage of the MCDA modelling effort, any double incorporation of fuzzy logic should be avoided. Therefore, Type I criterion/preference functions are a suitable choice.

Nr	Criteria	Selected Preference function	Min/Max	Normalized Weights	Indifference Threshold q-value	Preference Threshold p-value
1	Victims 0-6 months	Criterion I: Usual	Max	0.365	N/A	N/A
2	Victims 7-12 months	Criterion I: Usual	Max	0.247	N/A	N/A
3	Distance to minefield (in m)	Criterion II: U-shape	Min	0.173	50 m	N/A
4	Number of Mined Areas	Criterion I: Usual	Max	0.215	N/A	N/A

Table IV.10: Human cost outranking functions

IV.4.3. Socio-economic impact

A. Socio-economic criteria and weights used for the Afghan Landmine Impact Survey

Table IV.11 is based on the criteria and weights of the Afghanistan LIS. The weights have been determined through inclusive stakeholder consultations. In this case it is not really required to normalize the weights in order to facilitate comparison. Hence, it is a straightforward process to model these weak metrics and weights as illustrated in table IV.12.

Nr	Criteria	LIS Weight
1	Presence of mines	2
2	Presence of unexploded ordnance	1
3	Access to some pasture was blocked	1
4	Access to some rain-fed cropland was blocked	1
5	Access to some irrigated cropland was blocked	2
6	Access to some drinking water points was blocked	1
7	Access to some water points for other uses was blocked	1
8	Access to some non-cultivated area was blocked	1
9	Access to some housing area was blocked	1
10	Some roads to administrative centres were blocked	1
11	Access to some other infrastructure was blocked	1

Table IV.11: Weighting of socio-economic criteria in the Afghanistan LIS

B. Enriching the weak socio-economic metrics - ordinal scale development

a. Geographic differentiation according to the socio-economic value of agricultural land

Based on the study of the *Socio-Economic Impact of Mine Action in Afghanistan*,⁵⁵⁴ a geographic differentiation is possible at provincial level. In 2001, eight small case-studies took place to determine several socio-economic parameters with regard to the value of Afghan farming and grazing land. These case-studies were put together based on common characteristics of the provinces. As can be observed in figure IV.18, the size and number of provinces varies significantly but at least they are grouped together. In case of the Kabul analysis no differentiation is possible but if outranking is pursued at national level or from a cluster of provinces from two or more case-studies, then differences in socio-economic value of land can be used for a better qualification of the socio-economic blockages.

Case Study	Provinces
I	Badakhshan, Takhar, Baghlan, Kunduz, Samanghan, Balkh, Jozjan, Faryab
II	Parwan, Kabul, Kapisa.
III	Logar, Wardak.
IV	Nangarhar, Laghman, Kunar
V	Kandahar, Zabul, Oruzgan
VI	Ghazni, Paktika, Paktia
VII	Helmand
VIII	Herat, Badghis, Farah, Nimroz

Fig IV.18: 2001 World Bank Case-Studies of the agricultural areas on the basis of cropping patterns and cropping intensity

The refinement of the *weak metrics* of socio-economic “blockages” should take place based on credible ordinal scales. Irrelevant levels of detail or quantification should be avoided. The socio-economic parameters in table IV.13 need, therefore, to be transformed from “crisp values” to “ordinal scales”.

⁵⁵⁴ BYRD and GILDESTAD. (2001). *Socio-Economic Impact of Mine Action in Afghanistan*, A Cost-Benefit Analysis, World Bank funded study. p.40 -60

b. Weighting based on the World Bank study of the economic potential of cleared land⁵⁵⁵

Case Study	Annual value of one km ² agricultural land		Annual value of one km ² grazing area		Annual value of one km ² irrigation systems	
Case Study I	14 000	Low	2076	High	34000	Low
Case Study II	79 000	Low	1556	Medium	237 000	Low
Case Study III	193 000	Medium	1500	Low	578 000	Medium
Case Study IV	135 000	Low	1500	Low	404 000	Low
Case Study V	520 000	High	1905	High	1558 000	High
Case Study VI	47 000	Low	1287	Low	141 000	Low
Case Study VII	59 000	Low	1707	Medium	174 000	Low
Case Study VIII	60 000	Low	1932	High	177 000	Low

Table IV.13: Transformation of cardinal data into ordinal scales with Low=1, Medium=2, High=3

For illustrative purposes, the crisp values of table IV.13 are transformed into an ordinal scale based on a proportional, linear approach:

(1) Range value *agricultural land*:

$$14000 - 520000 \Rightarrow \Delta = 506000/3 \text{ per ordinal segment: } 169000$$

Low segment: 14000 - 183000

Medium segment: 184000 - 352000

High segment: 353000 - 520000

(2) Range value *grazing land*:

$$1287 - 2076 \Rightarrow \Delta = 789/3 \text{ per ordinal segment: } 263$$

Low segment: 1287 - 1550

Medium segment: 1551 - 1814

High segment: 1815 - 2076

(3) Range value *irrigation systems*:

$$34000 - 1558000 \Rightarrow \Delta = 1524000/3 \text{ per ordinal segment: } 508000$$

Low segment: 34000 - 542000

Medium segment: 543000 - 1050000

High segment: 1051000 - 1558000

If required, a more sophisticated ordinal scale can be developed. Based on the wide range of the values in table IV.13, additional ordinal levels could indeed bring more refinement since the majority of the values are qualified as “low”.

⁵⁵⁵ BYRD and GILDESTAD. (2001), *Socio-Economic Impact of Mine Action in Afghanistan*, A Cost-Benefit Analysis, 2001, World Bank funded study, Internet. Available at <http://lnweb18.worldbank.org>, accessed on 25 April 2005

C. Development of “socio-economic” preference or outranking functions for Kabul

Nr	Criteria	Selected Preference function	Min/Max	LIS Weights	Indifference Threshold q-value	Preference Threshold p-value
1	Mines	Criterion I: Usual	Maximize	2	N/A	N/A
2	UXO/ERW	Criterion I: Usual	Maximize	1	N/A	N/A
3	Fixed pasture	Criterion I: Usual	Maximize	1	N/A	N/A
4	Rain-fed Crop	Criterion I: Usual	Maximize	1	N/A	N/A
5	Irr. Cropland	Criterion I: Usual	Maximize	2	N/A	N/A
6	Drinking water	Criterion I: Usual	Maximize	1	N/A	N/A
7	Other water	Criterion I: Usual	Maximize	1	N/A	N/A
8	Residential	Criterion I: Usual	Maximize	1	N/A	N/A
9	Roads Admin	Criterion I: Usual	Maximize	1	N/A	N/A
10	Other Infra	Criterion I: Usual	Maximize	1	N/A	N/A
11	Other roads	Criterion I: Usual	Maximize	1	N/A	N/A

Table IV.12: ‘Socio-economic’ outranking functions

The weak metrics qualify for Type I-Usual Criteria. As illustrated during Phase-II, LIS weight coefficients can be adjusted in case changes in socio-economic conditions and challenges so require. For example, a higher priority or higher weight coefficient could be considered to places where Afghan refugees and/or internally displaced persons (IDP) are planning to repatriate. Local Afghan authorities can cooperate with UN-Agencies by identifying areas to which refugees/IDPs will repatriate.

The first and second criterion, the presence of “mines” and “UXO/ERW” allows reflecting the *intangible* socio-economic effects on local communities in Afghanistan; e.g. the sociological and traumatizing effects of mine and UXO/ERW presence on the local population. In the Afghan programme, mine action prioritization has always been strongly influenced by different types of contamination: cluster bombs, landmines, and anti-vehicle mines. For example, clearance during spring 2002 was focused on cluster bomb units (CBU) areas in order to remove remnants of cluster bombs before growth of vegetation conceal their location. Subsequently, this policy was reversed, and a new preference for dealing with minefields prevailed.

It all illustrates how weighting coefficients can adjust adequately mine action prioritization in accordance with the desired effects on the ground. Once more, it emphasizes the importance of the opening statement of this chapter, wherein is stated that a mine action programme should not be purely driven by operations for the sake of operations but how it can adapt towards what people really need.

IV.4.4. Peacekeeping/building effects

A. The Bonn-agreement: a cumbersome start of the peace building process

The Afghan peace building process is not based on a classic peace agreement. The power-sharing agreement signed in Bonn in November 2001 was between the partners belonging to the *Afghan Northern Alliance*, a military-political umbrella organization created by the Islamic State of Afghanistan in 1996, who “*won the war*” with the extensive support from US coalition forces.⁵⁵⁶ It leaves out such difficult issues as setting up a firm plan and/or timescale for the disarmament and reintegration of former soldiers. As a non-inclusive peace agreement, it does not discuss whether and how the war’s “*losers*” should be incorporated in such a process which makes it very vulnerable to Taliban resurgence and insurgence activities. It is important to stress that Afghanistan should not be considered as a failed State but neither should it be regarded as a post-conflict country.

The security situation is most volatile in the eastern and southern parts of the country and the government continues to struggle with building up more authority outside of the capital, Kabul.⁵⁵⁷ As a result, Afghanistan has ended up with what can be termed a “*conflictual peace building*”⁵⁵⁸ process or could be categorized as a fragile State. Which are the other fragile States? On this, inevitably, quite different interpretations circulate. The United Kingdom’s Department For International Development (DFID) lists 46 countries, with an aggregate population of some 900 million or 14 per cent of the world total, as fragile.⁵⁵⁹ Among them are two giants: Indonesia, with a population of 212 million and Nigeria, with a population of 133 million. Afghanistan is, however, unique with regard to the external actors playing a significant military and political role in a mixture of *peace enforcement*, *peacekeeping* and *peacebuilding* activities.

B. Mine action as part of a Disarmament, Demobilization and Reintegration process

As part of the broader peace process, the *Afghanistan’s New Beginnings Programme* was established by the Afghan Transitional Authority and the UN to plan and lead the Disarmament, Demobilization and Reintegration process (DDR) for former combatants.

“In July 2005, a nationwide project for the destruction of anti-personnel mines and ammunition was launched when the Government of Afghanistan and the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) signed an Agreement on Anti-Personnel Mine & Ammunition Stockpile Destruction. In line with this 2-year project, ammunition deemed safe to be moved will be transported to secure storage facilities while the remainder will be destroyed. All mines will be destroyed.”

Japan is the lead nation for DDR in Afghanistan and the major financial contributor. The target set for the three-year process was up to 100,000 soldiers and officers.⁵⁶⁰ By 2005, 50000 soldiers were integrated into their communities.⁵⁶¹ For reintegration, the former combatants are offered opportunities in different sectors: agriculture, vocational training and job placement, small business opportunities, and mine clearance. A pilot phase was introduced at several locations, Gardez, Mazar-e Sharif and Kabul, starting in October 2003, with Kandahar set to follow. Within

⁵⁵⁶ Officially the *Agreement on Provisional Arrangements in Afghanistan Pending the Re-Establishment of Permanent Government Institutions*, the Bonn Agreement was the initial series of agreements intended to re-create the State of Afghanistan following the US invasion of Afghanistan in response to the September 11, 2001, terrorist attacks, an invasion which ended the twenty-plus-year-long Afghan Civil War.

⁵⁵⁷ Ironically, President Karzai has been nick-named as the “Mayor of Kabul”

⁵⁵⁸ SUHRKE, A., BERG, K. and STRAND A., (2004). *Conflictual peacebuilding: Afghanistan two years after Bonn* Bergen: Chr. Michelsen Institute (CMI Report R 2004: 4), Bergen, p.75

⁵⁵⁹ DFID (2005, January). Why we need to work more effectively in fragile States, Internet. Available at www.dfid.gov.uk, accessed on 12 November 2006

⁵⁶⁰ Under the concept of “Consolidation of Peace”, announced by Minister for Foreign Affairs, Japan provided 35 million dollars grant aid that forms the framework for the DDR, Internet. Available at <http://www.us.emb-japan.go.jp/english/html/policies/political/supportforafghanistan.htm>, accessed on 15 March 2007

⁵⁶¹ IRIN, Internet. Available at <http://www.reliefweb.int>, accessed on 10 March 2006

the DDR framework, the programme aims to provide mine clearance and vocational training, as a “*Mine Action for Peace*” (MAFP) programme.

“A pilot phase has begun in three locations – *Kunduz, Parwan, Kabul* – and approximately 138 of the 1,000 combatants planned to be reintegrated at each location are to be deminers. The main phase is to take place on a country-wide basis and to include cities such as *Mazar, Kandahar, Jalalabad* and *Herat*. Of the 100,000 that are to be demobilized under this plan, as many as 8,000 could be deminers.”⁵⁶²

Thus, the MAFP project aims to assist both in peacebuilding “from above” – by demobilizing former soldiers – and in peacebuilding “from below” – through building capacities, confidence and support for the peace process in local communities. In sum, with all other conditions the same, areas where mine action can contribute to DDR should be preferred above others.

C. Mine action: an effective counter-IED activity in Afghanistan?

a. IED building materials in Afghanistan

For Afghanistan, the more sophisticated and frequent use of IED lies in their simplicity and the availability of the requisite materials and explosives. Often IEDs are assembled from a complex mix of ERW, landmines and any other accessible material required to build these devices. Mine action breaks down the logistic platform of IED-building materials. Figure IV.19 shows how ERW is readily available in many areas of Afghanistan.⁵⁶³

Fig IV.19: Kabul - Explosive Remnants of War

b. Risk and trend analysis of IED usage in Afghanistan

As studied in Phase-I, IEDs are discriminate in their use, unlike mines. They give the element of control to NSAs, allowing them to claim hit-and-run victories. Hence, NSAs in Afghanistan are not aiming to blow up a jingle truck passing by but to effectively target coalition forces and other engaged actors in the nation building process of Afghanistan. For this reason they will modify landmines, in particular anti-tank mines, toward remotely controlled explosive devices. Radio or wire command detonation is used instead of the indiscriminate pressure-plate activation of mines. Higher precision and more lethal effects are the result.

Fig. IV.20: Two anti-tank mines are configured into an IED, while an Afghan child with automatic gun sits and watches

⁵⁶² BERGEN, A. (2004, April 29). The ‘Mine Action for Peace’ Programme, Afghanistan: Workshop Report Kabul, Internet. Available at <http://www.cmi.no/pdf/?file=/afghanistan/doc/AfghanistanArneS.pdf>, accessed on 10 January 2007

⁵⁶³ Internet. Available at <http://www.mech.uwa.edu.au/jpt/demining/countries/afghan/kabul02/Image13.html>, accessed on 10 August 2006

Fig. IV.21: Two anti-tank landmines under the motorbike seat with remote controlled detonation system

Fig. IV.22: Roadside bomb made of a propane tank with detonating cord attached to two TC-6 anti-tank landmines

The pictures in figure IV.21 and IV.22 give a few examples of the building of IEDs in Afghanistan.⁵⁶⁴ Especially the usage of remotely detonated IEDs might allow the NSA to become more effective since their chances of being injured are reduced as compared to other methods of attacking the Coalition Forces. NSAs are indeed weary of trying to engage the Coalition directly and having heavy firepower or close air support called in upon them and prefer the mine rigged bicycle to be remotely detonated when they are miles away. Analyzing the IED problem in the Afghan conflict environment requires a multifaceted approach, owing to the complex mixture of peace operations, development aid and emergency relief efforts ongoing. Success in creating a better understanding has so far been limited. The amount of highly volatile factors makes it a daunting task to indicate how mine action can achieve reliable, long-term peacekeeping/building effects.

The potential that mine action can have as a peace and confidence-building measure depends primarily on two factors: the intent of warring factions to use IEDs and the capability to build them. This needs to be further developed into a credible weak-metrics system, based on available information. In line with the modelling considerations of Phase-II, the following risk management principle can be incorporated in the model.

$$IED\ Threats = IED\ Capabilities \times Intent\ of\ Afghan\ NSAs$$

D. Suggested ordinal scoring mechanism

a. *IED Capabilities*; differentiation according to type of contamination

IEDs are most easily constructed from artillery shells, mortars and other types of heavy ammunition. In particular shaped charge explosives are having deadly armoured penetrating effects, similar to anti-tank mines. Due to the high presence of anti-tank mines in Afghanistan, the development of shaped charge IEDs, illustrated in figure IV.23, is less frequent than for example in Iraq or the Middle East.⁵⁶⁵ A sensible weighting process needs to take into account the two major factors discussed earlier: the presence of potential IED building material or IED capabilities and the intention to use it. Some information is available through the LIS and security assessments related to the ongoing peace support operations in the region.

Fig. IV.23: Shaped charges with focused explosion force

⁵⁶⁴ Pictures were obtained through US Central Command documentation, Mac Dill Air Force base, 2004, Florida

⁵⁶⁵ Internet. Available at www.defense-update.com/features/du-2-05/IED-2.htm, accessed on 3 June 2006

The Afghan Landmine Impact Survey data provides per community the information on presence of anti-personnel mines, anti-tank and unexploded ordnance or ERW. Anti-personnel landmines are arguably a significant IED threat, unless they are used in larger quantities. When converted into IEDs, anti-tank mines become very lethal. Large quantities of randomly available ERW, however, pose the biggest threat. Based on the LIS-data, a preliminary weak-metrics weighting system could therefore be established as per below. This can be more refined whenever more accurate and/or credible information becomes available.

Type	Suitability for building IEDs	Ordinal Scale
Anti-personnel mines	Low	1
Anti-tank mines	Medium	2
UXO/ERW	High	3

b. Intent to use IEDs; geographic differentiation and quantification of attacks in Afghanistan

The below graph⁵⁶⁶ provides useful trend analysis in order to assess the general *intent* to use IEDs in Afghanistan. However, it only indicates the increase in number of incidents but does not allow any geographic differentiation which can assist the MCDA prioritization process. It just indicates the increasing magnitude of the violence over a three year period.

Fig. IV.24: Rising number of security incidents in Afghanistan between 2002-2004

“An alarming trend that emerged in 2003 was the use of landmines as the basis for Improvised Explosive Devices, used to target Afghan government officials, national and international aid workers—including mine-action personnel—and international troops operating within the coalition and the United Nations-sanctioned International Security Assistance Force (ISAF). *This trend highlights the need for action to address the issue of stockpiled landmines and munitions in Afghanistan.*”⁵⁶⁷

The majority of current and detailed information related to IED attacks and other insurgency activities is highly classified information.⁵⁶⁸ Consequently, this case-study uses rather broad, declassified information to illustrate the possibility to differentiate the IED risks geographically according to the anticipated intent of factions to build and use IEDs. This is further based on the basic assumption that mines and ERW trafficking within Afghanistan is a significantly disrupted activity by NATO and Coalition Forces. Hence, the availability of IED building materials in one area does not solve the shortage or demand in another area. Without this assumption, mine action prioritization would not have any effect as warring factions would always have easy access to IED building materials throughout Afghanistan or from neighbouring countries, in particular Iran.

⁵⁶⁶ Information from United States CENTCOM, Centrix database, Operation Enduring Freedom

⁵⁶⁷ Country profile Afghanistan, Internet. Available at http://www.mineaction.org/countries/countries_overview.cfm?country_id=910
Country profile Afghanistan, accessed on 22 November 2006

⁵⁶⁸ USCENTCOM, NATO and UNAMA have different and somehow complementary intelligence gathering capabilities on insurgency activities in Afghanistan.

As illustrated in figure IV.25 and the graphs in figure IV.26 and IV.27, a geographic differentiation of IED threats is possible according to the four sectors of Afghanistan.⁵⁶⁹ It is clear that the Sector South and East face a higher number of attacks and IED insurgency activities due to presence of numerous Taliban tribes. Based on threat assessments, clearance of ERW and anti-tank mines could be preferred in these areas compared to

much lower threats in Sector North and especially Sector West. Hence, an additional geographic ranking element can be brought into the equation.

Fig. IV.26: 2002-2004 Overview of attacks per Afghan Sector West-North-South-East

The below graph illustrates that at least half of the attacks are related to the usage of mines, mortars and IEDs, which allows for a quantified appraisal of the intent to use IEDs

Fig. IV.27: 2002-2004 Overview of direct and indirect attacks in Afghanistan

⁵⁶⁹ Graphs based on information available to the Coalition Partners to Operation Enduring Freedom, United States Central Command, Florida – USA, April 2004

Sector	Intent Ordinal Scale	Threat Ordinal Scale
West	Low	1
North	Medium	2
South	High	3
East	High	3

Similar to the ordinal ranking of the capability to build IEDs, an ordinal ranking system to prioritise affected communities according to the intent-level associated with the four sectors is proposed for MCDA. As explained earlier, although the graphs allow for a quantification of IED attacks, the data is not regarded as sufficient to install cardinal scales.

E. Development of “peacekeeping/building” preference or outranking functions

Nr	Criteria	Selected Preference function	Min/Max	Weights	Indifference Threshold q-value	Preference Threshold p-value
1	Presence of anti-personnel (AP) mines	Criterion I: Usual	Max	1	N/A	N/A
2	Presence of anti-tank (AT) mines	Criterion I: Usual	Max	2	N/A	N/A
3	Presence of UXO/ERW	Criterion I: Usual	Max	3	N/A	N/A
4	IED activity	Criterion I: Usual	Max	6	N/A	N/A
5	DDR Programme	Criterion I: Usual	Max	1	N/A	N/A

Table IV.14 Peacekeeping/building outranking functions

Table IV.14 presents the five suggested criteria based on the preceding analysis. Again Type I - Usual Criteria are suggested as outranking functions since there is no requirement to install indifference/preference threshold at this stage. Illustrative weights are allocated based on a balance between *presence & intent*.

IV.3.5. MCDA for the prioritization of mine action in Kabul

A. Multistage decision analysis applied

During the model building in Phase-II, the five-community simulation with a limited number of criteria touched upon the requirement of *multistage MCDA*. It was anticipated that applying outranking algorithms on complex problems with numerous alternatives, such as the prioritization of mine action in Kabul, is preferably performed in more than one stage. This allows different levels of complexity to be dealt with by the appropriate (in-country) experts and/or decision makers. In line with the different political levels of mine action, a distinction can be made between operational and strategic MCDA. Preferably the number of evaluation criteria is drastically reduced at a second and/or third stage so the prioritization model can be easily used or demonstrated at the strategic or high politics level. It is also preferable to *introduce fuzzy logic at the second stage, which will result in less complicated modelling and threshold setting* owing to the lower number of criteria. As a direct consequence, the *fuzzy logic effects will be more transparent* and, therefore, avoid the “black box” syndrome.

B. MCDA Kabul: first stage outranking

This section will illustrate the first stage of MCDA-outranking of the 313 impacted communities of Kabul. Based on the availability of real-world data, a total of 21 criteria were developed and used in scoring matrixes: 5 “*strong metrics*” criteria for human cost prioritization, 11 “*weak metrics*” criteria for outranking related to socio-economic benefits and 5 “*weak metrics*” criteria related to peacekeeping/building effects.

For illustrative purposes, one of the 21 criteria - the absence or presence of adequate medical facilities with regard to human cost weights - was added in a “*dormant mode*”; e.g. zero weight was allocated in stand-by of more reliable information.

The colour codes per district in figure IV.28 will facilitate the landmine impact analysis and illustration of the 14 affected districts with its 313 impacted communities. In accordance with the preference functions developed, the next page illustrates the three scoring matrixes for the first ten communities.

Fig. IV.28: Kabul Province and its 14 Districts

Fig. IV.29: Weighting of the 21 criteria

Fig IV.30: First stage MCDA: scoring on the 21 criteria of the first 10 of 313 impacted communities

Fig. IV.31: Net ϕ related to the 'human cost', 'socio-economic benefits' and peacekeeping/building effects

The net preference ϕ per mine action output indicate the refined differentiation for the human cost, slightly less differentiation regarding the socio-economic benefits and a relative unrefined outranking of the impacted communities for the peacekeeping/building effects. It clearly shows the impact of strong versus weak metrics on the outranking results and the required ability of the model to handle different levels of outranking information in a second stage.

C. MCDA Kabul: second stage outranking

a. Scoring: net ϕ

In this second stage, the outranking process will combine the net ϕ of the three first-stage MCDA's and obtain, according to the weights allocated to the three mine action outputs, a combined optimal ranking of the 313 communities.

Figure IV.32 illustrates again the scoring matrix for the first 10 communities of the 313. Since for the scoring the net ϕ are used, the *average performance* of all communities should be zero, reflecting the mathematical balance between domination and being

	Socio Economic Impact	Human Cost	Peacekeeping/building Impact
Min/Max	Maximize	Maximize	Maximize
Weight	3.0000	6.0000	1.0000
Preference Function	Gaussian	Gaussian	Gaussian
Indifference Threshold	-	-	-
Preference Threshold	-	-	-
Gaussian Threshold	0.1139	0.2890	0.2630
Threshold Unit	Absolute	Absolute	Absolute
Average Performance	-0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
Standard Dev.	0.1139	0.2890	0.2630
Unit	Phi Net	Phi Net	Phi Net
C1	-0.0005 (20)	-0.5149 (306)	-0.1664 (10)
C2	-0.0005 (20)	-0.5438 (308)	-0.1664 (10)
C3	-0.0005 (21)	-0.1785 (223)	-0.3979 (13)
C4	-0.0005 (20)	-0.5573 (309)	-0.1664 (10)
C5	-0.0005 (20)	-0.5607 (310)	-0.1664 (10)
C6	-0.0005 (20)	0.2030 (62)	-0.1664 (10)
C7	0.2862 (5)	-0.0074 (144)	-0.1664 (10)
C8	-0.0721 (24)	-0.1319 (201)	-0.3979 (13)
C9	-0.0721 (24)	0.0405 (127)	-0.3979 (13)
C10	-0.0005 (20)	-0.2959 (269)	-0.1664 (10)

Fig. IV.32: Second stage MCDA: Net ϕ of the alternatives/impacted communities related to the three mine action outputs

dominated in the outranking algorithm. According to the maximization of the Gaussian (type VI) preference functions, communities with the highest human cost, socio-economic and peacekeeping impact will obtain the highest rankings. Based on the fuzzy optimization principles of Phase-II, this MCDA stage is well suited to introduce preference threshold s .

b. Fuzzy optimization; preference threshold setting

1. Gaussian Preference Function

The high number of affected communities or alternatives complicates the analysis on the one hand but facilitates the assessment of certain modelling aspects on the other hand. Contrary to the modelling simulation in Phase-II, the effects of varying preference threshold s can be skilfully assessed with regard to its impact on ϕ and hence, the prioritization process. Increasing preference threshold s [$s_j \rightarrow s_k$] results in lower $H(d)$ values [$H_1(d) \rightarrow H_2(d)$] for the same d between the scores of two affected communities. Otherwise formulated, with d remaining the same, increasing s lowers the level of preference between two communities. Consequently, it will result in lower ϕ values and a lower differentiation capacity or sensitivity of the model during the outranking.

Fig. IV.33: Varying threshold s : effect on the Gaussian Preference Function (Type VI)

2. Preference threshold (s) setting

Two *threshold* s values are of interest.

- (1) If preference threshold s equals the difference $d(a_1, a_2) \rightarrow d_j = s_j$

then:
$$H_j(d_j) = 1 - \frac{1}{e^{1/2}} = 1 - \frac{1}{2.71828^{1/2}} = 0.39$$

- (2) If threshold s is set equal to the standard deviation $\rightarrow s = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (a_i - \bar{a})^2}{n-1}}$

then for $d(a_1, a_2)$:

$$H_j(d_j) = 1 - e^{-\frac{d_j^2}{2 \left(\sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (a_i - \bar{a})^2}{n-1}} \right)^2}} = 1 - e^{-\frac{d_j^2}{2 \left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (a_i - \bar{a})^2}{2-1} \right)}} = 1 - e^{-\frac{(a_1 - a_2)^2}{2((a_1 - \bar{a})^2 + (a_2 - \bar{a})^2)}} = 1 - \frac{1}{e} = 0.63$$

This illustrates that if $d_j = C(a_1) - C(a_2)$ equals the set threshold s_j , then the Gaussian preference function will result always in a rather low preference value of $H(d) = 0.39$. If the sample *standard deviation* value is used to set threshold s , then $H(d) = 0.63$; which implies a stronger preference. The *standard deviation* as initial *preference threshold* default setting will be of particular interest for the further integration of fuzzy logic in the optimization process.

Smoothed graphs 1 and 2 connect the net preference ϕ of the 313 affected communities. The *standard deviation* of scoring values is used as a baseline value to set preference threshold s . In case of graph 1, s is set equal to the standard deviation. Graph 2 is the result of s with a value of twice the *standard deviation*. Graph 3 reflects the net preference ϕ when a *crisp prioritization algorithm* is applied (= no thresholds). The comparative overlay suggests that using the standard deviation of the scoring data is a good compromise between maintaining sufficient differentiation capacity of the model while introducing a welcome level of fuzziness to avoid crisp mathematical outranking of no threshold setting. Further increasing preference threshold s , results in a *deteriorating differentiation capacity of the model*, illustrated below through a quickly decreasing angle θ . A further increase of *threshold* s will in the end reduce the preference ϕ to negligible values or 0. Ultimately, it depends on the profile of the decision-maker how much “fuzziness” he wishes to introduce in the model, together with setting the weights for the three mine action outputs/effects. This recalls the risk averse-neutral-accepting categorization of decision-makers, studied in Phase-I.⁵⁷⁰

Fig. IV.34: Effects of different values for preference threshold s on the ϕ and sensitivity of the model

⁵⁷⁰ Phase-I, p.68

c. PROMETHEE II complete ranking and weight setting

Figure IV.35 illustrates the complete PROMETHEE II combined ranking of the 313 affected communities (figure shows only ten first and ten last). The net preference ϕ 's provide a "landmine impact footprint" of the impacted communities per district. It is obvious that D1, D2, D4, D5, D6 and D10 have primarily negative net preference flows, while D7, D9, D11, D12, D13 and D14 have primarily positive net ϕ while D3, D8 portray a mixed ϕ profile. All this is the result of a preference threshold setting s equal with the standard deviation of the scoring values and a 30-60-10% weight setting for respectively the socio-economic impact, human cost and peacekeeping/building impact.

Fig. IV.35: Combined PROMETHEE II ranking based on the net ϕ related to the 'human cost', 'socio-economic benefits' and 'peacekeeping/building effects'

D. Geometrical Analysis for Interactive Assistance (GAIA) for Kabul

Fig. IV.36: Combined human cost, socio-economic impact and peacekeeping/building effects

The GAIA plane provides a complementary way to visualize in an *interactive* way the key aspects of the prioritization process according to the three “mine action output” criteria (in green). The “*decision axis*” (in red) provides the prioritization “compass heading”. Owing to the high number of alternatives, the clarity of the GAIA plane may suffer from saturation if its size cannot be significantly enlarged. On the other hand, as long as the number of criteria remains limited, the GAIA plane will continue to provide useful information and add an additional assessment possibility to the already comprehensive ranking process of impacted communities.

E. Utilization of the (out)ranking results

Table IV.15 illustrates how the PROMETHEE II Complete Ranking provides precise ranking information compared to the unrefined LIS high-medium-low impact categorization of mine-affected communities, this all without any additional information gathering efforts and/or costs. The high correlation between the LIS categories and the PROMETHEE ranking is noticeable but also the desired *enrichment of the impact and risk assessment*. For example, Community 105 and 108 experienced 4 recent victims but differ considerably in ranking; respectively 60 and 11.

DISTRICT 8	COMMUNITY	RECENT VICTIMS	LIS CATEGORY	PROMETHEE RANKING	
Khaki Jabbar	Community 86	Jango Zay	0	MEDIUM	204
	Community 87	Zendan	4	HIGH	10
	Community 88	Malik Khel	0	LOW	179
	Community 89	Taghar	3	MEDIUM	108
	Community 90	Mirza Khan Karez	0	LOW	265
	Community 91	Baghgay	1	MEDIUM	280
	Community 92	Not in AIMS	11	HIGH	4
	Community 93	Not in AIMS	0	LOW	209
	Community 94	Dawran Khel	0	MEDIUM	281
	Community 95	Malang	7	MEDIUM	51
	Community 96	Chalaw(Woli Khel)	0	LOW	178
	Community 97	Kharoti	0	LOW	230
	Community 98	Darband	0	MEDIUM	47
	Community 99	Sherullah	0	MEDIUM	165
	Community 100	Chakari	7	HIGH	3
	Community 101	Shomam Zay	0	LOW	308
	Community 102	Khurd Kabul	0	LOW	235
	Community 103	Taghari Ulya	3	MEDIUM	207
	Community 104	Gurjay	2	MEDIUM	134
	Community 105	Not in AIMS	4	HIGH	60
Community 106	Tizini Khas	0	LOW	118	
Community 107	Jorobay	0	LOW	307	
Community 108	Not in AIMS	4	HIGH	11	
Community 109	Ghozgay	1	MEDIUM	105	
Community 110	Charwazi	0	LOW	259	
Community 111	Aynak	0	LOW	191	
Community 112	Khaki Jabbar	0	MEDIUM	72	

Table IV.15: New PROMETHEE ranking versus old LIS-categorization

Community 105 and 108 experienced 4 recent victims but differ considerably in ranking; respectively 60 and 11. These differences in ranking are not only caused by the numerous other than “human cost” related criteria but are also caused by the incorporation of the *recency* factor of mine accidents. Hence, communities with 4 victims over the last semester will outrank communities with the same number of mine victims longer ago. Even between communities with 0 victims, the *risk management element* of the model will allocate a higher priority to communities impacted by more numerous or closer minefields. Figure IV.37 illustrates for District 8 how the LIS map with its categorized communities can now be further refined with this accurate ranking/prioritization information.

Fig. IV.37: PROMETHEE I prioritization results for the affected communities of District 8, Kabul

In theory, based on the linear statistical fits from the statistical regression analysis, it is possible to calculate the increase in mine accidents once deviating from the most optimal “human cost” ranking (obtained when setting human cost weight at 100%). These extensive calculations would require, amongst others, data on the size of the minefields in order to compute the time required to clear the minefields and/or mine blockages. Consecutively, it would for example be possible to assess every six or twelve months the number of impacted communities which remain exposed to significant mine accident risks because of clearance operations elsewhere for socio-economic purposes.

To a certain extend, the model will need to be expanded in the operational domain if such assessments are deemed relevant and research-worthy. There are, indeed, many operational factors which will influence the final execution of mine clearance or broader implementation of mine action. Security constraints can require a significant adjustment of this strategic prioritization process, or factors like terrain condition, climate or vegetation. Operational factors could suggest to first clear areas without dense vegetation and or to first clear areas with a slope less than 20 degrees. Prioritization could also be based on the size of the mined area or how quick a socio-economic blockage alone could be cleared, similar to military tactics related to minefield breaching clearance. Expected clearance rates on a specific task can also influence its priority order. Operational clustering can also require deviating from the ranking as suggested in figure IV.37. Grouping clearance activities can increase the efficiency of operations by reducing time lost through commuting, setting up field camps and simplified logistics in support of the mine clearance assets.

In sum, the sound implementation of a prioritized list of mine action activities is critical to further the effective allocation of mine action resources. This needs to be part of an ongoing consultative process which takes into account the unique local characteristics of the landmine problem in Afghanistan, the “priorities or agenda” of key stakeholders and most importantly the population at risk. This process will be addressed more comprehensively at the end of Phase III.

F. MCDA Kabul: third-stage outranking

Phase-II addressed the possibility to link-up *mine action prioritization* with *integrated strategic planning* through a *third-stage MCDA process*. This would allow adjusting the ranking determined for one particular setting to be adequate for multiple scenarios. In this case, the anticipated likelihood of each scenario will be incorporated through *probability factors* allocated to multiple scenarios. This is of particular interest for the volatile situation in Afghanistan in order to determine a best response or compromise ranking which is *robust towards significant changes of external conditions*.

More details on third-stage outranking will be provided in later sections covering strategic planning considerations for mine action in Afghanistan. First, for broader assessment and validation purposes, the credibility of the methodology and results for Kabul will be tested upon other provinces in Afghanistan.

IV.3.6. Applying MCDA to other regions in Afghanistan

A. From provincial to national level: some validation considerations

To remind, the main goal of the statistical research is to explain and predict mine accidents. The objective is to account for the reasons why the dependent variable varies among the surveyed affected communities in this study, to predict future occurrences to inform decision making, and simply to describe any relationship among the variables. In this regard, the case-study successfully identified a credible MCDA-procedure for prioritization of mine action for the Kabul province.

In order to validate or adequately extrapolate this methodology to other provinces or regions of Afghanistan, some suggested statistical considerations and concerns in Phase-II need to be emphasized. Hence, in order to keep the modelling process credible, the statistical analysis needs to be based on data (sub)sets of as high a number of affected communities as possible, without ignoring the unique local characteristics of the landmine problem in Afghanistan. The following sections will, therefore, address statistical methods and clustering techniques which allow MCDA to be applied with a similar level of confidence as for Kabul.

B. Sample size considerations

Using Kabul as an initial research platform for the case-study had many advantages. The amount of data of the 313 impacted communities was on the one hand a sizable, representative population, on the other hand the *amount of data was manageable* compared to the complete LIS population of 2368 impacted communities. Based on a geographic-district framework, this principle could be repeated. As of June 2005, the Afghan Ministry of the Interior recognised 398 districts, divided between the 34 provinces.⁵⁷¹ The Kabul province is, however, the only province in Afghanistan with such a high number of affected communities.

A similar sample size of several hundreds of affected communities remains nevertheless desirable in order to validate as much as possible the preceding findings for Kabul. In line with the modelling suggestions of Phase-II, this may require the development of an *approach which clusters several mine-affected provinces*.

Fig. IV.38: Regional density of affected communities in relation with the Afghan structure of 34 provinces and 398 districts

C. Analyzing the landmine problem at a local scale or clustering of data

Data clustering is a common technique for statistical data analysis, which is used in many fields, including data mining, pattern recognition, image analysis and bio-informatics. In the context of this case-study, *clustering is the classification of affected provinces into different groups*, or more precisely, the partitioning of landmine impact data into subsets (clusters), so that the data in each subset share some common impact characteristics or trait - often called generically “*proximity*” according to some statistically defined distance measure. For the case-study, it should allow to classify the affected provinces into groups that are as much as possible *homogeneous within themselves and heterogeneous between each other*, on the basis of the defined set of variables or potential mine victim predictors used for Kabul. These *homogeneous sets of impacted provinces* should provide a data set of sufficient sample size and produce through regression analysis better coefficients of determination, which in turn can be used to guide the setting of weights (w) for the human cost segment of the MCDA model.

D. Choice of clustering method(s)

a. Basic clustering principles

Data clustering algorithms can be *hierarchical* or *partitional*. Hierarchical algorithms find successive clusters using previously established clusters, whereas partitional algorithms determine all clusters at once. Hierarchical algorithms can be *agglomerative* ("bottom-up") or *divisive* ("top-down"). *Agglomerative algorithms* begin with each element as a separate cluster and merge them into successively larger clusters. *Divisive algorithms* begin with the whole set and proceed to divide it into successively smaller clusters.⁵⁷² Again, the smaller data set of impacted communities of the Kabul province, aggregated to its 14 districts, will serve as platform to decide which clustering algorithm(s) are suitable for this type of data and variables.

There are two basic clustering methods:

- (1) *Agglomerative hierarchical methods*: Agglomerative hierarchical clustering methods begin by placing each observation into a separate cluster. Clusters are then joined, two at a time, until the number of clusters is reduced to the desired target. At each stage, the clusters joined are the pair that are closest together.
- (2) *k-Means method*: This method begins by identifying k items as initial *seeds* for each cluster. Items are matched to the closest cluster.

b. Statistical methodology for clustering of mine affected communities/areas

Next to selecting one of the above clustering methods, selecting a *distance measure* is an important step in any clustering process in order to determine the earlier mentioned *proximity*. This will determine how the similarity of two impacted districts is calculated. In order to create clusters of observations of mine affected communities, it is indeed important to have a measure of “*closeness*” or similarity so that districts with similar characteristics may be joined together. It will also influence the shape of the clusters, as some elements may be close to one another according to one distance and further away according to another. In order to do so, the following steps are suggested:

- (1) Reduction of the community data/observations (through aggregation)
- (2) Selection of a distance measure⁵⁷³

⁵⁷¹ Maps Afghanistan, Internet. Available at

http://www.aims.org.af/services/mapping/geo_codes/geocodes_anatomy/geocodes_anatomy.html, accessed on 31 March 2006

⁵⁷² EVERIT, B. (2001). *Cluster Analysis*, United Kingdom, p. 57-60

⁵⁷³ Common distance functions are the *Euclidean* distance, the *Manhattan* distance (also called taxicab norm or 1-norm), the maximum norm and the *Mahalanobis* distance, the latter corrects data for different scales and correlations in the variables.

- (3) Selection of a clustering algorithm
- (4) Determination of the number of clusters
- (5) Validation of the analysis

c. Optimizing clustering results for Kabul

1. Opting for the “Agglomerative, Squared Euclidean Furthest Neighbour” method

The *agglomerative* and *k-means* method provide quite distinct clustering results. When applied on Kabul data, the *agglomerative clustering method* was very well in line with the *anticipated outcome*. Even without a statistical clustering method, the highly affected districts are visually recognizable. Hence, the agglomerative method with the often used *Squared Euclidian* distance measurement was withheld as clustering methodology for Afghan LIS-data. This implies a distance measuring by placing each mine affected district in a separate cluster and then combining clusters based on their distance from each other based on:

$$d(x, y) = \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - y_i)^2$$

In this procedure, x and y represent the location of two districts in the n -dimensional space of the observations. Where Euclidean methods could further differ is in how they define the distance between two clusters:

- (1) *Nearest neighbour* (single linkage): defines the distance between 2 clusters as the minimum distance between any member of one cluster and a member of the other.
- (2) *Furthest neighbour* (complete linkage): defines the distance between 2 clusters as the maximum distance between any member of one cluster and a member of the other.

2. Squared Euclidean distance plotting

This distance measurement takes place until the desired number of clusters of impacted districts is formed. The *furthest neighbour method* was used to create 2 distinct clusters with similar characteristics from the 14 observations supplied at district level for the Kabul province. To form the clusters, the procedure began with each observation in a separate group. It then combined the two observations which were closest together to form a new group. After re-computing the distance between the groups, the two groups then closest together were combined. This process was repeated until only 2 groups of districts remained.

Fig. IV.39: Agglomeration distance plot for Kabul clustering

The number of final clusters can be adjusted based on the distance plot in figure IV.39. In this particular case, opting for three clusters would result in isolating District 14. However, in case of a small population of interest, the number of cluster will rarely exceeds three or four. In this particular case, it is obvious that Districts 7, 9, 11, 12 and 13 constitute an “axis of high impact” through the Kabul province, which further supports the credibility of this clustering method as it statistically confirms what can be visually identified.

Hence, the agglomerative method using furthest neighbour squared Euclidian distance measurement results in a Cluster 1 of 9 districts (64.29%) and a Cluster 2 of 5 districts (35.71%).

3. Cluster Centroids

The average values for each variable in each cluster are called cluster *centroids*. The centroids of Cluster 1 are indicated in green; of Cluster 2 in red. It provides an interesting and convenient way to compare the characterizing values of each cluster. “Higher Impact” Cluster 2 has for example a centroid of 1.404 recent victims compared to the significantly lower centroid of 1.105 recent victims of Cluster 1.

Cluster	Total years of mine laying	Years since last mine laying	Years since last conflict	Mil Act Quantified
1	8.7477	9.352	7.171	2.826
2	15.304	5.426	4.016	3.124

Cluster	Distance RefPt to MA_edge_meters	Old Victims Killed Injured	Population	Mined Areas
1	291.238	13.817	1385.51	1.875
2	116.394	13.764	1031.21	2.336

Cluster	Total blockages	Total AP_AT_UXO contamination	Total Recent Victims
1	1.764	1.371	1.105 ←
2	2.054	1.504	1.404 ←

4. Kabul district clustering dendrogram

The clusters produced by the algorithm are most easily interpretable via a dendrogram, as illustrated in figure IV.40. This is further facilitated if the 2 clusters can be geographically associated with the Kabul-14 district map.

Fig. IV.40: Clustering dendrogram for the Kabul province – 14 districts

E. Statistical analysis and clustering at province-level

a. Reduction or aggregation of province-level data: two options

In anticipation of aggregation of data from multiple provinces, two possible methods are presented below.

1. Method 1: No aggregation at district level; based on arithmetic means of community data

Considering a set or sample of affected communities: $C = [c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n]$, then this data can be aggregated or averaged at province-level (\bar{p}) through the calculation of arithmetic means:

$$\bar{p} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n c_i$$

The arithmetic mean (or simply the mean) of the impacted communities is the fastest way to aggregate survey data at province-level for further statistical analysis.

Fig. IV.41: No aggregation at district level

2. Method 2: Aggregation at district level; based on weighted means of community data

Using *weighted means*, or *weighted averages*, has some advantages and disadvantages. It would require considerable time and effort to adjust the complete LIS population in order to have weighted averages for the close to 300 affected districts. The advantage is, however, that the extra aggregation layer at district level avoids unbalances in the aggregation process since the weighted means of impacted communities will result in a more representative aggregation process at province-level. Hence, based on the illustrative example in figure IV.42, the *weighted district averages* (\bar{d}) should be calculated as follows:

$$\bar{d} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i \bar{c}_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i} \Rightarrow \bar{d} = \frac{4\bar{c}_1 + 8\bar{c}_2 + 4\bar{c}_3 + 2\bar{c}_4 + 11\bar{c}_5}{29}$$

Fig. IV.42: Aggregation at district level using weighted community averages

Theoretically, if all the weights are equal, then the weighted mean is the same as the arithmetic mean. This method would be required if an outranking of provinces was to be envisaged, based on a population of weighted district averages. The case-study, however, limits itself to validating the research results obtained for Kabul through defining a cluster of a limited number of provinces with similar characteristics in terms of sample size, statistical predictors and recency factors for mine accidents. For this reason, the case-study envisages Method 1, basing its statistical regression analysis on *averaged community data* without unnecessarily establishing an aggregation layer of weighted averages at district level. However, observations or district-averages which are based on too few communities could be removed from the population in order to avoid biased results originated by a few outliers.

b. Opting for Method 1: no aggregation at district level

Table IV.16 reflects the averaged community data for the 31 affected provinces on a total of 34 provinces in Afghanistan. One of the provinces, Nuristan, has been removed due to its outlying characteristics vis-à-vis the statistical population. This province has only 2 affected communities but with a very high mine victim rate.

Nr	Province	Sector	Province	Total years of mine laying	Years since last mine laying	Mil Act Quantified	Distance RefPt to MA-edge(meters)	Old Victims Killed/Injured	Pre-War Population	Mined Areas	Sum of economic impact	Total contamination	Total Recent Victims
1	Bamyan	Central	Bamyan	7.48	6.68	3.80	292.48	6.28	1440.00	1.84	1.24	1.24	0.68
2	Ghazni	Central	Ghazni	3.01	19.18	3.14	104.40	11.79	805.40	1.81	1.53	1.23	0.60
3	Kabul	Central	Kabul	11.23	7.81	3.78	191.89	14.24	1160.59	2.04	1.99	1.36	1.34
4	Kapisa	Central	Kapisa	12.98	4.47	3.88	455.15	13.07	797.58	1.49	1.44	1.21	2.07
5	Logar	Central	Logar	9.37	11.58	3.56	88.25	21.42	1418.11	2.03	2.66	1.51	1.44
6	Parwan	Central	Parwan	11.81	6.01	3.91	415.23	19.75	1317.11	2.07	1.83	1.28	1.32
7	Wardak	Central	Wardak	5.09	14.52	3.30	175.88	7.34	726.18	1.84	1.39	1.39	0.55
8	Khost	East	Khost	9.29	13.80	2.93	203.13	13.24	771.33	1.64	1.27	1.20	0.22
9	Kunar	East	Kunar	9.60	13.87	4.00	158.67	18.33	1673.20	1.47	1.13	1.07	0.13
10	Laghman	East	Laghman	9.00	10.60	3.73	141.53	8.07	742.00	2.47	1.13	1.27	0.80
11	Nangarhar	East	Nangarhar	7.35	13.15	3.82	93.61	12.33	2131.06	1.67	1.55	1.37	0.41
12	Nuristan	East	Nuristan	3.50	0.00	2.50	265.00	21.50	4200.00	1.00	2.00	1.00	19.50
13	Paktika	East	Paktika	6.51	15.29	3.56	92.61	13.27	694.98	1.34	1.83	1.22	0.51
14	Paktya	East	Paktya	10.19	10.66	2.70	92.72	12.50	680.53	1.97	1.93	1.32	0.86
15	Badakhshan	North	Badakhshan	9.00	10.22	3.39	432.71	15.33	660.73	1.71	1.88	1.04	0.65
16	Baghlan	North	Baghlan	8.78	16.09	3.81	227.48	8.62	861.47	2.05	1.74	1.11	0.61
17	Balkh	North	Balkh	5.34	10.10	3.44	121.03	7.90	1507.59	1.75	1.77	1.24	0.90
18	Faryab	North	Faryab	8.36	7.55	3.61	98.18	9.36	4199.09	1.73	1.91	1.24	0.48
19	Jawzjan	North	Jawzjan	1.78	11.33	3.33	50.33	3.56	2040.00	1.22	1.89	1.22	0.22
20	Kunduz	North	Kunduz	6.24	3.88	3.83	91.95	9.61	1608.36	2.53	1.80	1.38	0.68
21	Samangan	North	Samangan	8.14	5.24	3.88	316.41	15.24	1693.23	2.13	1.64	1.17	1.33
22	Sari Pul	North	Sari Pul	6.15	7.92	3.85	116.00	8.38	4375.38	2.31	2.08	1.08	1.62
23	Takhar	North	Takhar	5.48	4.06	3.90	345.92	7.01	946.45	1.99	1.88	1.08	2.47
24	Hilmand	South	Hilmand	10.26	12.52	3.53	90.76	10.58	1147.26	1.53	1.74	1.68	0.60
25	Kandahar	South	Kandahar	9.40	12.01	3.84	96.75	9.41	695.55	1.68	1.80	1.41	0.56
26	Nimroz	South	Nimroz	10.93	9.57	3.93	132.57	5.50	1009.29	1.57	2.50	1.50	0.07
27	Zabul	South	Zabul	10.31	11.78	3.41	82.13	5.53	87.19	1.75	1.56	1.28	0.00
28	Badghis	West	Badghis	4.63	7.74	4.00	173.05	9.26	1454.21	1.74	2.05	1.68	0.32
29	Farah	West	Farah	6.10	14.33	3.54	146.08	23.90	1806.92	1.92	2.28	1.87	0.79
30	Ghor	West	Ghor	7.29	11.10	3.76	103.90	10.05	1100.57	1.62	1.81	1.33	1.05
31	Hirat	West	Hirat	10.02	10.41	3.61	99.44	16.54	1687.55	1.97	1.89	1.46	0.79

Table IV.16: Arithmetic averages at provincial level of the 2368 impacted communities

“Nuristan is composed of 189 communities, only two of which—or one-tenth of 1% of the total—are impacted. Of the province’s six districts, two are impacted. In Kamdesh district, the LIS identified 35 recent victims in one impacted community with one SHA. The communities reported no mine action activities in the province.”⁵⁷⁴

At this stage it is therefore suggested that further statistical analysis should be based on an aggregation of *minimum 3 affected communities*. As suggested earlier, this will avoid that one or two communities could distort the statistical findings. Minimum sample size calculations could suggest a higher number. This would, however, result in the rejection of a significant amount of valuable data. Hence, only Nuristan will be removed from the statistical analysis.

⁵⁷⁴ Survey Action Centre (2005) Landmine Impact Survey of the Islamic Republic of Afghanistan, Washington DC, p. 122

c. Regression analysis of data aggregated at provincial level

Before commencing the clustering process of Afghan provinces, a complementary statistical observation is addressed below. Three simple linear regressions proved that regression analysis of aggregated data at provincial level provides also statistically significant mine victim predictors. This is important in case a prioritization process at provincial level would be envisaged. In that case, aggregation should be based on *weighted district averages* as described in *Method 2* above, in order to obtain more representative coefficients of determination than the ones determined for the three *provincial* mine victim predictors below. It may well be possible that the R^2 improves significantly compared to the relative low values below.

The below statistical analysis does not longer take into account certain local/regional characteristics of the Afghan landmine problem. Hence, this contributes to a lower statistical goodness of fit of possible predictors. For example, the “Number of Mined Areas” has an R^2 of 42,5% and correlation coefficient of 0.65 for the Kabul analysis compared to 14,5% and 0.38 respectively as a result of the regression analysis of aggregated data at national level. Interestingly, the *direct* linear relationship for Kabul becomes an *inverse* linear relationship at national level regarding the statistical fit of the Simple Regression - Total Recent Victims vs. Distance RefPt to MA.

1. Simple Regression - Total Recent Victims vs. Number of Mined Areas

P-Value = **0.0376**
 Correlation Coefficient = 0.381389
 Standard Error of Est. = 0.539982

Total Recent Victims = $-0.51689 + 0.72115 * \text{Mined Areas}$

⇒ $R^2 = 14.5 \%$

2. Simple Regression - Total Recent Victims vs. Distance RefPt to MA

P-Value = **0.0037**
 Correlation Coefficient = 0.513186
 Standard Error of Est. = 0.5011349

Total Recent Victims = $0.349832 + 0.00259549 * \text{Distance}$

⇒ $R^2 = 26.3 \%$

3. Simple Regression - Total Recent Victims vs. Years since last mine laying

P-Value = **0.0014**
 Correlation Coefficient = -0.55533
 Standard Error of Est. = 0.485674

Total Recent Victims = $1.68324 - 0.0842289 * \text{Years since last mine laying}$

⇒ $R^2 = 30.8 \%$

d. Agglomerative - Euclidian Cluster Analysis of Afghan Province data

1. Determination of the number of clusters

Based on the cluster procedure developed for Kabul, 4 clusters were created from the 30 observations supplied. To form the clusters, the procedure began again with each observation in a separate group. It then combined the two observations which were closest together to form a new group. After re-computing the distance between the groups, the two groups then closest together were combined. This process was repeated until only a workable number of groups remained.

Determining the value for the number of clusters was again guided through the analysis of the "Agglomeration Distance Plot". Distance jumps are noticeable starting from 6 groups or less clusters, indicating less homogeneous clusters are starting to be formed through the inclusion of provinces with less proximity. Similar to the cluster analysis for Kabul, the lowest possible number of clusters is preferred in order to maintain the number of affected communities per cluster sufficiently high for later statistical regression analysis. Opting for 4 clusters is therefore considered as a good choice for further analysis.

Five clusters would also be a sensible approach, in particular as it would further subdivide Cluster 2 (43.3%), resulting in five similar sized clusters ($\approx 20\%$). Like for the Kabul cluster analysis, the clusters in table IV.17 are coloured for ease of visualisation and reference.

Fig. IV.43: Agglomeration distance plot for Afghan provinces

Cluster	Members	Percent
1	7	23.33
2	13	43.33
3	5	16.67
4	5	16.67

Table IV.17: Four clusters quantified in numbers of districts and % of the total cluster population

2. Analysis of the centroids of the four clusters

Cluster	Total years of mine laying	Years since last mine laying	Mil Act Quantified
1	8.35429	7.83571	3.74429
2	7.22615	13.2985	3.46462
3	9.482	6.0	3.792
4	8.258	11.148	3.712

Cluster	Distance RefPt to MA_edge	Old Victims Killed/Injured	Pre_War Population	Mined Areas
1	147.353	10.3543	2173.28	2.12714
2	123.28	10.2977	1059.62	1.67769
3	393.084	14.08	1083.02	1.878
4	126.142	14.132	1367.16	1.758

Cluster	Sum of economic impact	Total contamination	Total Recent Victims
1	1.72	1.29	0.912857
2	1.63077	1.26077	0.509231
3	1.734	1.156	1.568
4	2.246	1.648	0.644

The centroids provide again a useful overview of the values characterizing the four clusters. The third cluster has a much higher number of recent victims, up to three times higher than for the other clusters and is therefore of particular interest. However, before making a final choice which cluster to further analyze, an analysis of the dendrogram in figure IV.44 together with a geographic association will avoid that a specific cluster or region is analysed in the abstract.

Fig. IV.44: Dendrogram Distance Metric: Squared Euclidean Furthest Neighbour Method

Fig. IV.45: Plotting of Squared Euclidean clusters at the provincial level

The plotting of the different clusters confirms again the presence of common characteristics of the landmine problem at a local scale. It is however important to have a basic understanding or mental estimate why the impact of landmine problem within one country can be experienced in very different ways. Often the conflict history will be a good reference point. In this regard, Phase-I briefly analysed the situation in Cambodia and highlighted the volatility of the number of mine victims with regard to its conflict history. The maps⁵⁷⁵ in figure IV.46 indicate areas held by the different warring factions. It is noticeable that *Cluster 3 largely coincides with the area held by the Northern Alliance* and Cluster 1 to a certain extent with former frontlines of the Taliban.

Fig. IV.46: Former Northern Alliance held territory and Taliban frontlines

⁵⁷⁵ Internet. Available at <http://www.senliscouncil.net>, accessed on 22 May 2006

Furthermore, a detailed *cluster scatterplot* allows visualizing the two-dimensional cluster relationship between the dependent and independent variables; in the below plot “*Years since last mine laying*”. The four clusters are projected in overlay with the centroids encircled in green. The simple linear regression between the two variables has been superimposed. With a coefficient of determination of 30%, it reflects the relatively high goodness of fit of the statistical predictor: “*Years since last mine laying*” at provincial level.

Fig. IV.47: Cluster Scatterplot for Total Recent Victims – Years since last mine laying (linear regression analysis in overlay)

Significant overlaps can be observed in the cluster scatterplot but it is obvious how Cluster 3 has a considerable higher centroid value of *Total Recent Victims* versus *Years since last mine laying*. The overlaps itself are not uncommon when dealing with real world data; fuzzy cluster analysis can further supplement the process.

“Data of the same cluster should be similar or homogenous, data of disjunct clusters should be maximally different. Assigning each data point to exactly one cluster often causes problems, because in real world problems a crisp separation of clusters is rarely possible due to overlapping of classes. Also there are usually exceptions which cannot be suitably assigned to any cluster. For this reason a fuzzy cluster analysis specifies a membership degree between 0 and 1 for each data sample to each cluster.”⁵⁷⁶

However, for basic validation purposes it is sufficient to simply identify a cluster of provinces which portray common local characteristics. Similar to Kabul, the provinces of the “*Northern Cluster*” have high numbers of mine victims. Cluster 3 is, therefore, chosen to validate the alternative hypothesis that statistical analysis of mine victim data results in statistical significant regression analysis of mine victim predictors.

⁵⁷⁶ F.KLAWONN, F. and KRUSE, R., Derivation of Fuzzy Classification Rules from Multidimensional Data, Internet. Available at <http://fuzzy.cs.uni-magdeburg.de/papers.html#fuzdat>, accessed on 22 July 2006

F. Statistical analysis of the “Northern Cluster”

a. Aggregated data at district level

The table below represents the averaged data of the 508 affected communities, for the 42 districts of the five clustered provinces. Throughout the case-study there has been a minimum rejection of data. However, only districts based on the arithmetic means of *three or more* affected communities will be considered in the population in order to avoid too much impact on the statistical results by the data of a few affected communities, in particular if they qualify as statistical outliers. In all, only 9 districts are removed from the population in table IV.18, which discards the data of 13 affected communities from the regression analysis; a mere 2% of the 508 affected communities in the Northern Cluster.

Sector	Province	Nr of affected communities	District	Years since last mine laying	Distance RefPt to MA-edge(meters)	Population	Mined Areas	Blockages	Old Victims killed/injured	Total Recent Victims
North	Badakhshan	3	Badakhshan	9.3	36	340	1.7	1.3	5.33	0.33
North	Badakhshan	2	Darwaz	8.0	15	150	2.0	2.0	8.50	3.00
North	Badakhshan	23	Fayz Abad	11.6	167	580	1.7	1.7	21.52	0.57
North	Badakhshan	1	Ishkashim	3.0	12000	60	1.0	3.0	10.00	0.00
North	Badakhshan	2	Jurm	13.0	64	420	1.0	1.5	2.00	0.00
North	Badakhshan	4	Kishim	14.0	88	645	2.5	1.8	25.00	1.50
North	Badakhshan	7	Kuran Wa Munjan	10.9	181	194	1.6	2.0	12.14	0.14
North	Badakhshan	2	Shahri-Buzurg	3.0	375	2460	1.0	2.0	1.50	0.00
North	Badakhshan	1	Shighnan	3.0	30	30	2.0	3.0	30.00	3.00
North	Badakhshan	1	Wakhan	3.0	10	534	3.0	6.0	0.00	1.00
North	Badakhshan	2	Zebak	6.0	2700	222	3.0	6.0	14.00	1.00
SUBTOTAL		48						0.0	0.00	
Central	Kapisa	3	Koh Band	5.0	268	490	2.0	1.3	11.67	1.67
Central	Kapisa	12	Kohistan	5.1	505	1395	1.3	1.3	15.08	2.42
Central	Kapisa	4	Mahmud Raqi	3.5	20	2205	4.0	4.3	17.50	3.00
Central	Kapisa	16	Nijrab	4.4	547	246	1.0	1.1	6.44	2.25
Central	Kapisa	5	Tagab	3.8	548	391	1.2	1.4	24.00	1.40
SUBTOTAL		40						0.0	0.00	
Central	Parwan	65	Bagram	4.1	72	1661	2.2	3.1	19.63	2.22
Central	Parwan	36	Chaharikar	4.4	219	2415	2.0	2.7	46.11	1.75
Central	Parwan	9	Ghorband	4.7	914	1528	3.7	1.6	6.22	0.44
Central	Parwan	8	Hisa-I-Awali Panjsher	15.0	1093	2760	2.5	1.3	39.50	0.13
Central	Parwan	1	Hisa-I-Duwumi Panjsher	16.0	51	492	1.0	1.0	20.00	1.00
Central	Parwan	25	Jabalussaraj	4.7	238	1554	1.4	1.6	13.16	1.04
Central	Parwan	15	Kohi Safi	8.3	94	470	1.9	2.5	13.80	2.20
Central	Parwan	19	Panjsher	17.9	1041	698	2.1	1.1	22.63	0.26
Central	Parwan	40	Salang	5.8	157	498	2.4	1.7	16.73	0.90
Central	Parwan	21	Shekh Ali	4.3	1100	765	1.9	1.3	3.43	0.71
Central	Parwan	8	Shinwari	4.0	1049	1358	2.4	1.0	7.25	1.13
Central	Parwan	7	Surkhi Parsa	4.0	1754	250	1.0	1.0	0.57	0.57
SUBTOTAL		254						0.0	0.00	
North	Samangan	13	Aybak	9.6	72	2365	2.4	1.7	7.38	0.31
North	Samangan	35	Dara-I- Suf	3.4	401	1500	2.1	1.5	11.54	1.94
North	Samangan	6	Hazrati Sultan	7.2	233	2450	1.7	1.3	23.67	0.33
North	Samangan	10	Khuram Wa Sarbagh	5.4	235	1839	2.6	2.1	31.90	2.30
North	Samangan	14	Ruyi Du Ab	4.8	427	1123	1.8	1.8	16.29	0.50
SUBTOTAL		78						0.0	0.00	
North	Takhar	11	Bangi	3.4	141	665	3.8	2.2	7.82	1.00
North	Takhar	11	Chal	3.0	541	1053	1.5	2.2	4.36	3.18
North	Takhar	7	Farkhar	5.3	808	1320	1.6	1.7	6.57	1.86
North	Takhar	6	Ishkamish	3.0	285	870	1.5	2.0	4.83	2.50
North	Takhar	14	Kalafgan	4.5	197	970	2.6	2.4	13.00	4.64
North	Takhar	14	Khwaja Ghar	3.3	373	795	2.1	1.5	7.21	2.64
North	Takhar	5	Rustaq	12.8	920	1776	1.0	1.4	8.80	1.60
North	Takhar	19	Talugan	3.2	174	884	1.4	1.9	4.26	1.89
North	Takhar	1	Yangi Qala	3.0	30	480	1.0	2.0	7.00	0.00
SUBTOTAL		88								

Table IV.18: Aggregated data at district level of the 508 impacted communities of the Northern Cluster (3)

The methodology applied for the analysis of the Kabul province will be replicated for the statistical analysis of the 5 clustered provinces: Badakhshan, Kapisa, Parwan, Samangan and Takhar. Consequently, the following sections reflect the statistical significant results of the regression analysis of the independent variables and the recency effects.

b. Significant statistical fits of mine victim predictors

1. Simple Regression - Total Recent Victims vs. Blockages

P-Value = **0.0039**

Correlation Coefficient = 0.488844

Standard Error of Est. = 0.936545

$$Total\ Recent\ Victims = 0.125805 + 0.76817 * Blockages$$

$$\Rightarrow R^2 = 23.9 \%$$

2. Simple Regression - Total Recent Victims vs. Years since last mine laying

P-Value = **0.0049**

Correlation Coefficient = -0.478708

Standard Error of Est. = 0.94256

$$Total\ Recent\ Victims = 2.3245 - 0.128163 * Years\ since\ last\ mine\ laying$$

$$\Rightarrow R^2 = 22.9 \%$$

c. Mine victims recency analysis of the “Northern Cluster (3)”

For the statistical recency analysis there is no need to average data since it uses the mine victim data at district level. Hence, there is no requirement to consider the elimination of certain districts.

Nr	Sector	Province	District	Number of Victims			
				SEM1	SEM2	SEM3	SEM4
1	North	Badakhshan	Baharak	0	0	0	1
	North	Badakhshan	Darwaz	0	1	5	2
	North	Badakhshan	Fayz Abad	1	1	3	7
	North	Badakhshan	Kishim	0	3	2	0
	North	Badakhshan	Kuran Wa Munjan	1	0	0	0
	North	Badakhshan	Wakhan	0	1	0	0
	North	Badakhshan	Zebak	0	1	0	0
2	North	Badakhshan	Shighnan	3	0	0	0
	Central	Kapisa	Koh Band	0	1	1	3
	Central	Kapisa	Kohistan	0	5	5	16
	Central	Kapisa	Mahmud Raqi	2	1	1	8
	Central	Kapisa	Nijrab	6	10	9	11
3	Central	Kapisa	Tagab	0	3	0	4
	Central	Parwan	Bagram	31	47	32	34
	Central	Parwan	Chaharikar	5	19	5	31
	Central	Parwan	Ghorband	0	1	0	2
	Central	Parwan	Hisa-I-Awali Panjsher	0	0	0	1
	Central	Parwan	Hisa-I-Duwumi Panjsher	0	1	0	0
	Central	Parwan	Jabalussaraj	0	2	0	21
	Central	Parwan	Kohi Safi	6	11	12	4
	Central	Parwan	Panjsher	2	0	1	2
	Central	Parwan	Salang	0	4	8	24
	Central	Parwan	Shekh Ali	0	3	6	6
4	Central	Parwan	Shinwari	1	2	2	4
	Central	Parwan	Surkhi Parsa	0	0	1	3
	North	Samangan	Aybak	1	0	0	2
	North	Samangan	Dara-I- Suf	15	20	21	11
	North	Samangan	Hazrati Sultan	0	0	1	0

	North	Samangan	Khuram Wa Sarbagh	3	13	5	0
	North	Samangan	Ruyi Du Ab	5	0	1	1
5	North	Takhar	Bangi	2	1	1	6
	North	Takhar	Chal	7	15	10	2
	North	Takhar	Farkhar	4	6	3	0
	North	Takhar	Ishkamish	2	4	8	1
	North	Takhar	Kalafgan	0	0	24	41
	North	Takhar	Khwaja Ghar	15	15	7	0
	North	Takhar	Rustaq	2	5	1	0
	North	Takhar	Taluqan	4	3	10	18

Table IV.19: Mine/ERW Victim data for the 2-year LIS surveyed period

1. Simple linear regression of the recency factor in the “Northern Cluster”

Similar to the regression analysis of the recency factors for Kabul, the below and Annex J provide the statistical significant results for the “Northern Cluster”.

2. Overview regression analysis of the recency factor for the “Northern Cluster”

Cluster	R ²	Correlation coefficient	Standard Error of Est.	Fitted Model
SEM 1 vs. SEM 2	84.5	0.92	2.35	SEM1 = -0.0844758 + 0.609096 * SEM2
SEM 1 vs. SEM 3	54.5	0.73	4.04	SEM1 = 0.153353 + 0.606338 * SEM3
SEM 1 vs. SEM 4	11.5	0.34	5.63	SEM 1 = 1.76403 + 0.191605 * SEM4
SEM 2 vs. SEM 3	56	0.74	6.00	SEM2 = 0.722688 + 0.927232*SEM3
SEM 2 vs. SEM 4	20	0.45	8.08	SEM2 = 2.57511 + 0.380247*SEM4
SEM 3 vs. SEM 4	46	0.37	5.35	SEM3 = 1.60521 + 0.466173*SEM4

Table IV.20 Overview of R² for the regression analysis of the recency factors of the ‘Northern Cluster’

d. Calculation of weight coefficients based on multiple coefficients of determination

Average R² for 0-6 months mine accidents = (84.5+56+46)/3 = **62.2%**

Average R² for 7-12 months mine accidents = (54.5+20)/2 = **37.3%**

Normalization for weighting of human cost criteria:

Northern Cluster	R ²	Normalized weight vectors
Victims 0-6 months	62.2	0.425
Victims 7-12 months	37.3	0.255
Number of blockages	23.9	0.163
Years since last mine laying	22.9	0.156
		∑ = 1

Table IV.21 Human cost criteria for the ‘Northern Cluster’

e. Geographic differentiation of socio-economic factors

Case Study	Provinces - Northern Cluster highlighted in blue
I	Badakhshan, Takhar, Baghlan, Kunduz, Samanghan, Balkh, Jozjan, Faryab
II	Parwan, Kabul, Kapisa.

Case Study	Annual value of one km ² agricultural land	Annual value of one km ² grazing area	Annual value of one km ² irrigation systems
Case Study I	14 000	Low	2076
Case Study II	79 000	Low	1556

Table IV.22. Socio-economic geographic differentiation

Only limited geographic differentiation is possible based on a High versus Medium value of grazing area between the three provinces belonging to case-study I (Badakhshan, Takhat and Samanghan) and two provinces belonging to case-study II (Parwan and Kapisa).

G. Development and overview of outranking functions for the “Northern Cluster”

Nr	Criteria	Selected Preference function	Min/Max	Normalized Weights	Indifference Threshold q-value	Preference Threshold p-value
1	Victims 0-6 months	Criterion I: Usual	Max	0.365	N/A	N/A
2	Victims 7-12 months	Criterion I: Usual	Max	0.247	N/A	N/A
3	Number of Blockages	Criterion I: Usual	Max	0.173	N/A	N/A
4	Years since last mine laying	Criterion II: U-shape	Min	0.215	2 years	N/A

Table IV.23. Human Cost outranking functions

Modifications of the 21 formerly identified outranking criteria of Kabul are largely limited to the human cost criteria. The weight coefficients of the recency criteria (Nr 1 and 2) need to be adjusted according to the normalized weights of table IV.23. The two mine victim predictors for Kabul need to be replaced by two more relevant or statistically significant criteria for the Northern Cluster, namely the number of socio-economic blockages/blocked access to economic resources, farmland and infrastructure and the number of years since last mine laying.

Notably, similar to the “distance from minefield” criterion for Kabul, the mine victim predictor “years since last mine laying” is characterized by an *inverse* linear relationship with the dependent variable. Also here an indifference threshold was installed to illustrate how the model could incorporate possible technical measurement errors/survey inaccuracies during the first MCDA stage.

With regard to the socio-economic criteria, only a minor adjustment could be suggested in order to take into account the difference in annual value of grazing area in between provinces. This does not require a change of the weight coefficient of the socio-economic criterion “blocked access to fixed pasture land”, but the instalment of an ordinal scale in stead of the current Boolean concept.

In absence of more accurate data, no modifications to the peacekeeping/building criteria could be suggested.

IV.3.7. Integrated strategic planning for mine action in Afghanistan

A. Mainstreaming with other humanitarian, development and reconstruction sectors

One of the main findings of Phase-I and II was to avoid that mine action prioritization and strategic planning would take place in isolation. Consequently, integrated and long-term strategic planning has to face the complexity to balance short and long-term mine action objectives of saving lives (=zero-victim strategy), maximizing socio-economic benefits and peacekeeping effects, in respect with other critical needs of a recovering society. This recalls also the changing requirements owing to the lifecycle characteristics of a mine action programme, studied in Phase-I.⁵⁷⁷ During the past emergency phase in Afghanistan, following the increased military activity and usage of cluster munitions, saving lives and alleviating suffering regardless of the intrinsic value of Afghan land or its substitutability has been - in respect with the humanitarian imperative of mine action – the primary driving factor for task prioritization. Meanwhile, the strategic objectives have shifted. Hence, taking a longer term perspective into account requires a continuous evaluation of the humanitarian imperative versus the potential threat of a fragile or absent security country-wide and lack of development. This needs to acknowledge the potential threat of a greater number of casualties from the possible resumption of internal conflict or insurgency-warfare and may, for example, require more emphasis on the favourable peacekeeping effects mine action could generate.

Phase-II explained the methodology to link-up the (short-term) prioritization with the integrated strategic planning process and related planning framework. The following section will present the results of applying exactly the same methodology.

B. Adjusting the prioritization of mine action to changing external conditions

Figure IV.48 illustrates how changing external conditions can require the decision-maker to adjust the weight coefficients in order to revise the mine action prioritization or “best response” accordingly. The influence on the outranking is clearly visible. Where in setting 1 some districts have largely dominating preference φ 's (e.g. D8, D14 – green arrows), setting 2 indicates significant changes.

Fig IV.48: Impact of changing the weight coefficients on the outranking process

Fig. IV.49: GAIA-presentation of the impact of changing the weight coefficients

The GAIA-presentation clearly reflects the shift from overweight “human cost” to “peacekeeping impact” in the decision axis. As explained in Phase-II, this Walking Weights function can provide direct information and sensitivity analysis whenever the changing external conditions so require. It represents, however, rather a reactive response to varying circumstances. Multiple-scenario in the next section is more pro-active in the way it allows determining robust mine action prioritization to volatile circumstances or varying scenarios.

C. Robust optimization: linking-up short-term prioritization with multiple strategic scenarios

As suggested during Phase-II, adding a *third-stage* to the outranking process allows robust optimization through linking-up of short-term prioritization with longer term strategic planning scenarios. Both Setting 1 and 2 below address multiple scenarios but with different probabilities

Fig. IV.50: Prioritizing and planning for a volatile strategic environment or multiple scenarios

577 See Phase I – p. 148

allocated. For illustrative and methodological purposes, the same scenarios, parameters and probability factors were used as in the small-scale simulation of Phase-II. Hence, in case of increasing economic activities, the decision-maker may want to opt for a robust ranking taking into account a higher likelihood of the “economic rebound” scenario (S3), whilst still taking into account a looming risk of spikes in insurgency activities (S1). As illustrated, the decision-making process may discard one of the scenarios as unlikely (S2) and allocate zero probability.

As noticeable in figure IV.50, once all the data is entered, in particular the weights and probabilities related to the different strategic scenarios, the positioning of the decision-axis clearly indicates the effects of the different scenarios on the prioritization. These probability factors can be continuously adjusted. However, the sizeable Afghan mine action programme will portray significant inertia to adjust, especially when the reprioritization includes drastic changes in the required funding and allocation of resources. It should, therefore, be acceptable that rankings are only reviewed once per semester, unless specific circumstances justify a higher review frequency. The GAIA plane has the ability to inform the decision-making process in this regard. A radical repositioning of the JI-axis may call for an earlier than planned review.

In sum, the *three key mine action outputs* are simultaneous *three key prioritization and strategic planning parameters* which need to be carefully adjusted in accordance with anticipated or developing conditions on the ground. If well monitored and exploited, PROMETHEE will support any bridging between short-term prioritization and possible strategic developments/scenarios. The GAIA plane informs “in a blink” on the robustness of a certain ranking in case a shift between scenarios takes or could take place.

D. Considerations regarding long-term strategic planning for mine action in Afghanistan

With an emphasis on integration in overarching strategies, Phase-I and II provided the foundation of a strategic planning framework for mine action. Hence, it is not within the scope of this case-study to provide comprehensive strategic plans but rather to provide some key considerations to adequately respond to flaws in the planning process highlighted in the beginning of this case-study, to remind: *unrealistic outputs due to unrealistic clearance rates, excessive framing bias, poor prioritization, deadline setting and information management.*

a. What is affordable and sustainable?

The UN mine action policy, encouraged mine action programs - in particular, those managed or supported by the United Nations – to develop or identify *five-year* strategic plans. Although no broad-based evaluation exist on how ongoing planning efforts produce the desired results, it can be generally assumed that most strategic plans with a horizon of five years or longer are not particularly very strategic in substance and tend to *focus too much on mine clearance alone*. As discussed in Phase-I, the revised UN mine action strategy has set the strategic objective *to integrate all the components of mine action* into national development & reconstruction in at least 15 countries.⁵⁷⁸

Hence, what has been inherently missing from the current approach in Afghanistan? With many uncertainties of donor and national funding and other variables affecting the mine action programme, the flaws identified in the beginning of the case-study resulted in multi-year strategic plans which in the real world could not be followed and implemented. The problem seems to be that with so many uncertainties involved as in Afghanistan, the strategies produced result in a revolving *process of constant analysis and adjustment* and are not providing the steady strategic guidance in the face of changing conditions. Unfortunately, the process of converting the politics of mine action

⁵⁷⁸ See Phase-I, p.56

into sound strategies cannot present a successful track-record, especially for big and complex mine action programmes:

“Unless the mine problem involved was very small, these plans usually wound up as shelf decorations but most often proved to be unwieldy and *very difficult to harmonize with the realities of unstable resource flows*, recruiting difficulties and the myriad other problems that beset mine action programs.”⁵⁷⁹

That is why a strategic mine action plan should be first and foremost *affordable* and *sustainable*, based on *realistic assumptions*. Before presenting strategic options to donors, political authorities and senior management, consensus should exist on these strategic assumptions and expectations on what the mine action programme should be able to deliver. In line with the assessment of Phase—II, this requires a balanced needs assessment, a clear strategic vision with feasible objectives and deadlines, and credible strategic planning parameters. All these aspects will be briefly covered in the following sections; not to repeat what has already been addressed in Phase-II but to take into account some of the particularities and challenges of the Afghan landmine problem in this regard.

b. Balanced needs assessment: mine action versus other sectors

The early (2002) *Preliminary Needs Assessment* for Afghanistan⁵⁸⁰ did *not integrate* the funding requirements for humanitarian assistance that had been and were expected to remain financed through an appeals mechanism orchestrated by the UN. As mentioned before, there is some inevitable overlap between humanitarian relief and reconstruction. Owing to this lack of integration, donors did not respond well to multiple appeals for Afghanistan. Hence, integration needs to be launched from the start. Such policy integration will not only help address the needs of affected communities but will also open the door for significant additional resources to mine action, from both national resources and official development assistance.

The basic principles of a need assessment have been addressed in Phase-II and it highlighted how this assessment should provide the initial necessary information – and logical underpinning – for a strategy to be successfully developed. With over ninety per cent of all national development resources currently provided by international cooperation partners, enhancing the effectiveness and integration of external funding is absolutely vital for the attainment of post-conflict recovery and development targets, including the MDGs.

c. Clear strategic vision and objectives for mine action in Afghanistan

As explained in Phase-II, strategic planning in mine action should start by clarifying the vision and strategic objectives of the organization. For this case-study, the vision is the desired future end state of the Afghan Mine Action Program. This implies a shared political, socio-economic and security end state.

In general, a mine action programme may have one or more strategic objectives in order to achieve its specific end state. They should define realistic and achievable objectives and especially be consistent with the overall vision of the Afghan national authorities. Therefore they should be defined in *simple and unambiguous terms*. A common error is to have too many or too ambitious strategic objectives. This creates confusion and a lack of focus and clarity. Strategic planning may be the extension of a normative process but is ultimately all about unity of effort and strategic direction. Just as for this study in responding to its overarching achieving aim, in order to realize its strategic vision it may be helpful to define a set of enabling objectives, each addressing a separate

⁵⁷⁹ BOWNESS, C. (2005). The Missing Link in Strategic Planning: ALARA and the End-state Strategy Concept for National Mine Action Planning, Journal of Mine Action -MAIC 9.1, James Madison University, Washington DC

⁵⁸⁰ IRIN, Internet. Available at www.reliefweb.int/library/documents/2002/undp-afg-15jan.pdf, accessed on 27 March 2006

activity such as quality management, the mobilization of resources or training. It is recommended that objectives be set within a reasonable period of time, rather *three years* compared to five years or longer.

This political statement would have a most significant influence on the strategic planning which now had to be designed to achieve this objective. This process will be addressed further below.

d. Nation and national capacity building to enhance ownership of the landmine problem

If Afghanistan is to consolidate its opportunity for peace, then it will require unification under a Government that is recognized in its role as *service-provider*. With already limited resources and manpower to do this in the Kabul region, it is essential for the broader stability of the country and acceptance of the Government to extend its functionality to the other 33 Afghan provinces. Thus the role of the Afghan Government in clearing roads, restoring telecommunications, power and water, needs to manifest its authority and ability to take ownership of its most pressing problems. Consequently, the Government needs to be closely involved and consulted during the development of strategic plans. This requires an inclusive planning and resource allocation process, not only with the Government but also the local population.

“As a condition for an efficient planning process, an *option should be kept open for the local community to bring its influence to bear* on priority-setting also among the main sectors of development and support, like health, education, water supply etc. *Ideally it should be possible to divert funds from mine-action to other sectors and vice-versa*, when the local community expresses well-conceived priorities on that account. In most cases to day this will not be possible, as funds are firmly tied to programmes. Within the existing context rational behaviour on the part of the local community will rather be to seek every opportunity of external funding that emerges, and leave the responsibility for overall planning to outside forces and authorities.”⁵⁸¹

e. Mine Ban Treaty and clearance deadlines

The background to this case-study mentioned how President Karzai stated his intentions to free Afghanistan from the high impact of landmines within *five years*. This required a further increase of an already very significant amount of external funding with relatively low competing demands from other countries. In 2002, the mine action programme in Iraq was still profusely funded by the oil-for-food programme, leaving the MAPA in the spotlights. The acceleration from seven to five years was the direct trigger of the revision of the first effort to calculate the efforts and costs related to an inadequately defined problem with a different understanding of high and low priority land, socio-economic impact and human cost and a “wild variety” of clearance rates. All these caveats would prove to significantly hamper strategic planning at that time. As states earlier, *accurate planning was subordinate to framing bias in order to generate more resources*. In fact, the whole strategic planning effort was initially more related to promoting the programme and to please the donors, than an application of advanced managerial and planning techniques.

The Mine Ban Treaty has a strong *humanitarian* imperative and pressing mine clearance deadlines. However, *national development* can become gradually the prime long-term objective, despite casualties in minefields outside the prioritized development area. It further underlines the importance and complexity of the MAPA task prioritization model for mine clearance deadlines and the necessary broad consensus it should have, especially amongst donor countries and the Afghan authorities. In this regard the Afghan based Mine Action Working Group (MAWG) has a vital role

⁵⁸¹BYRD and GILDESTAD. (2001). *Socio-Economic Impact of Mine Action in Afghanistan*, A Cost-Benefit Analysis, 2001, World Bank funded study, Internet. Available at [http://lnweb18.worldbank.org/SAR/sa.nsf/Attachments/9/\\$File/mines.pdf](http://lnweb18.worldbank.org/SAR/sa.nsf/Attachments/9/$File/mines.pdf), accessed on 25 April 2005, p.67

to play. The efficacy of the MAWG will be vital for *setting realistic mine clearance deadlines*, the further enhancement of MAPA and a smooth transition of the programme to the Afghan authorities.

“The question now *what is sustainable*. The Mine Action Coordination Agency for Afghanistan (MACA) has prepared a strategic plan that calls for a further increase in clearance capacity. Its targets are to eliminate the mine/UXO threat in all priority areas by 2007 and in low-priority areas by 2012. However, this looks like a wish list than a firm prospect. These targets are predicated on the basis of donor support continuing at about the same level as in 2002 for the next five years. The *slower arrival of funds* in 2003 *calls that expectation into question and with it the prospects for achieving operational targets*.”⁵⁸²

f. Determine reliable mine clearance rates: a critical planning parameter

The clearance capacity/productivity of the different components of the MAPA should be treated as a most important planning issue. Empirical data, based on the mine action activities over the past decade years did in hindsight not provide a basis for credible analysis regarding future MAPA achievements and has led to overly optimistic planning. Limited post clearance documentation about the cleared land does not allow sound extrapolations towards future MAPA achievements. The International Mine Action Standards (IMAS), more specifically the higher safety precautions for de-miners, have slowed down significantly mine clearance rates. Nowadays, Afghan deminers need to investigate each signal and excessive amounts of time are consequently invested in highly polluted grounds with small metal fragments due to extensive prodding and sapping procedures. The impact of these factors at an execution or *operational level* should be well understood in order to reflect this correctly at a *strategic planning level*.

Field visits to mine clearance organizations such as HALO Trust and Afghan Technical Consultants (ATC)⁵⁸³ revealed much lower clearance rates (50 to 70%) than the ones used during early planning sessions. During a strategic planning workshop at Kabul, the mine clearance rates in the table IV.24 below were obtained via a questionnaire to four national mine action NGOs and one international NGO; HALO trust.⁵⁸⁴ The optimistic indices of DAFA and OMAR were put in perspective when annual performances of both NGOs were further analyzed. In both cases, extracts from landmine monitor reports were toning down their high indices within an acceptable range of the ones from ATC and HALO Trust. The conclusion is that a clearance rate of approximately *600 m²/per team/per day* is a reliable estimate for strategic planning purposes (compared to the earlier estimate of *1400 m²/per team/per day*). Some detailed calculations are provided in annex K.

	Organisation				
	ATC	AREA	DAFA	OMAR	HALO
Method	Manual Clearance (without mechanical preparation)				
Anti-personnel Mines	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Anti-Tank Mines	No	Yes	Yes	No	Yes
UXO	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Number Ops	24 deminers	18 deminers	24 deminers	24 deminers	22 deminers
Agricultural Land	500	900	1980	2700	330
Irrigation Channels	250	0	1260	360	220
Grazing Land	750	600	3030	1423	440
Roads	0	0	3666	0	110
Residential	200	0	516	468	154
Average Rate	340	300	2090	990	251

Table IV.24: Mine clearance rates provided by national and international NGOs during the workshop

⁵⁸² MASLEN, S. (2004). *Mine Action after Diana – Myths and Realities*, United Kingdom, p. 39

⁵⁸³ These field visits took place during Strategic planning Workshop from 1-10 March 2003 at Kabul.

⁵⁸⁴ This strategic planning workshop took place in March 2003 and invited all national and international mine actions NGOs in order to enhance national ownership of the planning efforts.

g. Establishment of a multiple scenario, multiple option strategic planning process

1. Planning for equilibriums, not only best-case scenario!

Long-term strategic planning is an exercise of balance between providing *stability and flexibility* to adapt to the ever-changing parameters. This recalls the basic principles of a Nash equilibrium. Hence, planning for equilibrium points is in theory planning for realistic scenarios where no party would benefit from changing its strategy unilaterally. Hence, the “*offer & demand*” dynamics between donor countries and Afghanistan would be somehow on “*cruise control*”, providing multi-year funding for multi-year demands. *Real world strategic planning*, however, has *not the benefit of long-term stability*. Therefore, a considerable but reasonable amount of strategic options should be subject of study and analysis in a way changes in equilibriums amongst the key actors, hence, Afghanistan vis-à-vis the donor community, can be incorporated or, at least, sufficiently anticipated. This can allow more time for political engagement and avoid drastic management changes due to shortages of funding which may jeopardize the whole mine action programme.

“Funding for mine action peaked in 1998, allowing for continued programme growth, but decreased substantially in 1999 and 2000. The severe shortfall of \$3.5 million for the activities of the Mine Action Programme for the period from September through December 2000 forced the programme to *suspend its staff on two months’ leave without pay and to freeze staff salaries and increments*. As a further consequence, only 64 per cent of the sites targeted for clearance will be cleared in 2000.”⁵⁸⁵

The simulation of different strategic scenarios allows for a rather simple methodology of analysis and prioritization, transparent and easily updated as more reliable data becomes available through the ongoing landmine impact survey. In a very complex operating environment, one benefits from strategic planning procedures, which are easy to comprehend and translate in clear messages towards the Afghan mine action stakeholders in order to further international support and national ownership of the process.

The evaluation of options against a range of possible future scenarios is the process of *determining the best performing strategic option or strategic fit*. SWOT and PESTEL analysis⁵⁸⁶ can be helpful to determine the strengths and weaknesses of each option. In this regard, each option could be again assessed on how well it satisfies a number of key criteria, including: the socio-economic benefits (at community, local and national level), the costs, the achievability (using the human skills and technology likely to be available), stakeholders needs and expectations, international treaty obligations and national legal requirements, and the risk of the option failing to achieve the declared strategic objective as a result of political intervention, the withdrawal of donor support, or a worsening security situation. Sensitivity analysis can further inform decision-makers of the strength of a strategic option versus external threats and changes, especially related to funding.

2. Credible assessment of multiple long-term scenarios and development of options

There are a multitude of scenarios possible related to developments of the security situation in Afghanistan and/or other competing demands at a global scale. In the end, how the politics of mine action in Afghanistan are materialized will largely depend on the generation of funding and allocation of resources. Hence, to opt for funding or resource-driven strategic scenarios described in table IV.25 is quite straightforward; either the current funding levels can be maintained or they will significantly increase or decrease.

⁵⁸⁵ S/2000/1106 Report of the Secretary-General on the Situation in Afghanistan and its Implications for International Peace and Security

⁵⁸⁶ SWOT stands for Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats. PESTEL stands for Political, Economic, Social, Technical, Environment and Legislative. It is a strategic planning technique that provides a useful framework for analysing the environmental pressures on a programme or an organisation.

	Funding-Scenario	Description
1	Increase	Donor community is willing to meet increasing funding requirements over time, in order to bring back safety, security and economic viability to Afghanistan.
2	Steady	The MAPA will be able to maintain the existing donor commitment to the programme.
3	Decline	With the MAPA transitioning to full national ownership and management, international donor support significantly declines as more national funding is expected.

Table IV.25: Overview of 3 possible funding scenarios

Since the MAPA has been totally dependent upon donor funding, reductions in those contributions will substantially affect the goals of the strategy. If strategic goals are too ambitious, substantial additional funding will be required from a variety of donor sources, including the Afghan Government, to meet humanitarian, development and reconstruction needs.

At first, the Afghan programme was successful in its appeal to this type of donor sources, consecutively raising approximately 60 million US\$ for 2002 and 2003, 70 in 2004 and 99 million US\$ in 2005. Current levels of funding are decreasing and indicate *donor fatigue and much stronger competition for mine action resources*. Hence, donors have only enabled the programme to reduce significantly the social and economic impact of landmines and unexploded ordnance but in order to meet the Convention mine clearance deadline, funding is required far beyond what is reasonably to be expected. This supports again the assessment that initial goal-setting was unrealistic.

The goal of achieving a mine and ERW free Afghanistan by 2013, and assisting landmine survivors, is simply not affordable and feasible. Ongoing consultations need to indicate what is feasible and affordable and better judge equilibrium scenarios with regard to support from the international community in conjunction with integrated strategic plans which portray a realistic strategic vision. The development of five options in table IV.26, together with the visualization and assessment in the next section will demonstrate that the early projections cited below were not credible.

“A period of five years (2003-2007) will be required to address all mine- and UXO-contaminated areas that have a high impact on Afghan communities, in addition to marking medium and low impact areas. In the following five years (2008-2012), medium and low impact areas will be addressed.”

Possible quantification of strategic options:

Option	Description	Planning's horizon	Projected Cumulative Cost (million USD)
1	Clearance of 80 km ²	5 years	200
2	Clearance of 200 km ²	5 years	350
3	Clearance of 350 km ²	10 years	550
4	Clearance of 670 km ²	10 years	850
5	Complete clearance - 800 km ²	10 years	950

Table IV.26: Overview of 5 possible options

4. Quantification and visualisation of the long-term strategic requirements

The previously described scenarios can be used in an assessment of the different strategic options in search for a *strategic fit*.⁵⁸⁷ Each of these long-term strategic options can be measured and weighted in a model with similarities to the normative model developed for national prioritization of mine action. For the five options, based on realistic strategic scenarios and assumptions (e.g.

Fig. IV.52: Annual cost comparison for the five options

Fig IV.51: Human Resource requirements for the five options

realistic mine clearance rates - 600 versus 1400 m² per team per day), the results in terms of annual programme costs and human resources required are visualized in figure IV.52 and IV.53. This was calculated with Cranfield University strategic planning support software (HIGHWAY ®). Noticeable is the big influence of slower mine clearance rates on long-term options 4 and 5. Instead of the early projections of 8000 employees in human resources required to clear Afghanistan by 2013 (=Option 5), the realistic mine clearance rates almost triple this requirement.

Not only was it very unlikely that the donor community would have had the commitment to meet such high and significantly changing demands year after year, expansion limitations would simply not have allowed meeting the projected output requirements.

In sum, an early study of possible options and scenarios would have permitted from the onset (= 2002 accession to the Mine Ban Treaty) to state that the mine action programme in Afghanistan would be unable to meet the 10-year Mine Ban Treaty deadline (=2013). It further confirms that the Afghan Government will seek by 2012 an extension period of up to ten years, which is a stipulated provision in the Mine Ban Treaty.

⁵⁸⁷ Scoring and weighting methods could also be applied but due to the limited number of options individual assessments are generally preferred in the UN decision-making environment. More details of this methodology are described in VAN DER LINDEN, F. (2003). Strategic Planning for the Mine Action Programme in Afghanistan, Internet. Available at <http://www.unitarpoci.org/media/vanderlinden.pdf>, accessed on 12 April 2005

IV.4. MAPA prioritization and strategic planning process

Fig. IV.53: The process to achieve the specific goals and “products” required

Before closing off this phase, the general processes envisaged for the development of the *short-term prioritization* and *integrated strategic plans* need to be addressed. Much of it has already been explained before and the key elements are therefore visualized in the largely self-explanatory flowchart of figure IV.53. In summary, the MAPA could further expand through the existing (UN) Mine Action Centre (MACA) for Afghanistan the *regional prioritization and coordination* of the different mine action activities of the national and international mine action organizations. The MACA should facilitate an ongoing dialogue with all key stakeholders, in particular the United Nations Assistance Mission in Afghanistan, Donor Countries, the Afghan Government and all relevant (inter)national NGOs and demining organisations. This way, priorities and strategic plans are part of an *ongoing consultative process* which safeguards a broad-based ownership of the landmine problems in Afghanistan. This should also enhance mine action standardization and synergy amongst the different Mine Action implementing partners.

In order to develop a credible regional prioritization process, the statistical methodology and multiple criteria decision analysis presented in this case-study should be based as much as possible on up to date LIS and other mine action information. Consecutively, regional mine action centres should present a regional programme of work to the MACA, which will decide on how national mine action resources and funding should be allocated in accordance with an overarching annual plan, balancing the regional programmes of work, and a long-term integrated strategic plan, balancing the national post-conflict restoration priorities. It is critical that mine victims are registered accurately per semester in order to perform credible regression analysis and review weight coefficients if any significant change in the statistical results can be observed. This weight coefficient review process is equally necessary if noticeable changes take place in the socio-economic and/or peacekeeping domain.

IV.5. Phase-III response to research aim and supporting research objectives

IV.5.1. Main findings on short-term mine action prioritisation for Afghanistan

Finding 1: The model developed in Phase-II needed only few and minor adjustments for its real-world use in Phase-III, thereby maintaining its favourable characteristics developed and identified during the small-scale simulation.

Phase II/sub-phase A findings provided an overview of the essential modelling requirements and how they were met with PROMETHEE during a simplified prioritization process for a small-scale simulation. Since there are no documented PROMETHEE case-studies with several hundred alternatives, it was initially uncertain if the outranking algorithm of Decision Lab 2000 would handle well such large amounts of data. Not only dealt PROMETHEE remarkably well with the real world-data of Kabul, it met satisfactorily all the projected modelling requirements of Phase II. Owing to the high number of impacted communities, the saturation of the optional GAIA-plane presentation and other functions could be largely resolved through enlarged displays and print-out capabilities.

Finding 2: The data of the Afghan Landmine Impact Survey is of critical value for the development of a short-term prioritization model, less so for the development of an integrated strategic plan.

Without the database of the Afghans LIS, it would have been impossible to feed the model with adequate data. Although some time series irregularities were discovered in the Kabul survey data of mine victims, it allowed for credible human cost outranking. More accurate reporting of mine victim data should allow for the detection of seasonal effects and possible related fluctuations in mine victim numbers.

The weak metrics socio-economic data of the LIS allowed for sufficient differentiation in the outranking process, although clearly less than the human cost data. Some aspects could not be incorporated, such as the discounting effects of future socio-economic benefits. Adequately incorporating differences of the economic value of cleared land requires better quality data than the parameters used for the “Northern Cluster”.

The LIS socio-economic weight coefficients allow basing the socio-economic part of the model on broad-based consensus values. In sum, without the LIS data, credible modelling would be sheer impossible. This does not preclude, however, that the model should benefit as much as possible from a variety of credible sources of information.

In sum, the LIS provides survey data which already leads to satisfactory outranking results. Further enhancements or adjustments of LIS procedures and methodology will likely lead to a further optimization of the short-term prioritization model. Only for the peacekeeping/building effects some subjective weight coefficients were used.

Finding 3: Simple linear regression analysis of aggregated data provides statistical significant observations at district and provincial level, thereby rejecting the null hypothesis.

The statistical analysis of non-aggregated community data produced only poor or statistical insignificant results. Conversely, statistical significant simple regression equations between the dependent variable “recent victims” and a set of “independent variables – mine victim predictors” were identified for Kabul, the “Northern Cluster” and at national level, based on aggregated data at provincial level.

For Kabul, the distance between the hazardous areas/minefields confirmed that in a more urban setting the closer the residential areas are to the minefields the higher the risks for mine accidents. This relationship was not found statistically significant for the “Northern Cluster”. A higher number of mined areas around a community proved also to be a credible mine victim predictor for Kabul.

For the Northern Cluster, the credible mine victim predictors are the number of socio-economic blockages and the number of years since last mine laying. The higher the number of blockages, the higher the predicted number of mine victims. This could be explained by the higher dependency or lack of socio-economic alternatives in the Northern provinces compared to the Kabul area which forces the local population to take higher risks in their interactions with a mine-infested environment.

Finding 4: The uniform application of simple linear regression analysis was preferred above mixing different types of statistical fits.

Pursuing multiple linear regression models proved to be an unreliable undertaking. Hence, throughout the statistical analysis, only one particular type of regression model has been considered, namely, that of a linear equation relating the dependent variable to the independent variable. Sometimes theoretical considerations indicate that this is the only form of the model required. On the other hand, a linear model is often used because either the theoretical form or the relationship is unknown and a linear equation appears to be adequate, or the theoretical form is known, but is rather complex, and a linear equation may provide a sufficiently good approximation.⁵⁸⁸

Hence, in this case, choosing for simple linear regressions as the most appropriate regression model was the result of a combination of theoretical reasoning, practical considerations, and careful scrutiny of the available data.

Finding 5: The coefficient of determination (R^2) or the goodness of statistical fit provided a credible reference for determining the weight coefficients of those mine victim predictors which proved to be statistical significant (p-value <0.05).

The coefficient of determination provided straightforward guidance for the determination of the weight coefficients of human cost criteria. Isolating the independent variables through simple regression analysis avoided the effects of *multicollinearity*. If there would be a high degree of linear correlation amongst two or more explanatory variables in a regression model, then it would have been difficult to separate the effects of them on the dependent variable. This would have resulted in biased R^2 . The multiple regression analysis with a R^2 close to 99% indicates that significant multicollinearity effects should be suspected.

Simple linear regressions offer the additional advantage of the coefficient of determination being the square of the correlation coefficient. This provides additional safety against Type-I errors (false positives) since low correlation coefficients will result in even lower coefficients of determination and, hence, lower weight coefficients.

It was also observed that the R^2 of the statistical significant fits for Kabul presented the highest values as well for the mine victim predictors as for the recency effects. Clustering data and/or statistical analysis at a national level ignores some of the local/regional characteristics of the

⁵⁸⁸ Statistical Analysis for Decision Making, Morris Hamburg, Wharton School of Finance and Commerce, University of Pennsylvania, p. 504

landmine problem and reduces the goodness of fit. For example, contrary to Kabul some provinces portray a direct linear relationship between the number of mine accidents and the distances of the minefields from the communities.

Finding 6: Statistical clustering procedures provided the desired large sample sizes and statistical significant observations, thereby taking into account the unique local characteristics of the landmine problem in Afghanistan.

The traditional agglomerative, Squared Euclidean Furthest Neighbour method provided reliable clustering results. This method recognizes the unique local characteristics of the landmine problem in Afghanistan. Not only does it provide the possibility to build up sample sizes large enough for credible statistical analysis, it also resulted again in the determination of mine victim predictors. The somewhat different recency effects and different mine victim predictors between the Kabul and “Northern Cluster” statistical analysis confirmed that a local approach should be explored to the fullest extent possible.

Finding 7: MCDA based on PROMETHEE provided for a holistic and flexible platform to produce credible outranking results with a minimum of subjective inputs.

Identified criteria during Phase-I have been largely incorporated in the model with slight adjustments according to the data availability from the Landmine Impact Survey. The multistage approach resulted in MCDA with at the 1st stage 21 criteria, reduced at the 2nd stage to the three mine action outputs. Different levels of insight and expertise are required to exploit the model at each stage. The 1st stage is largely situated at the technical level, the 2nd stage at the decision-making level. The two PROMETHEE stages offered an excellent combination of strong and weak metrics.

Third stage MCDA offered the possibility to develop a prioritization of mine action which takes into account a possible volatile environment with two or more distinct strategic scenario. A decision-maker may indeed prefer a certain amount of robustness in the prioritization of mine action toward affected communities.

Fuzzy logic could be successfully applied and improved further the credibility of the modelling effort based on preference thresholds. First stage MCDA included some indifference thresholds to illustrate how measurement errors could be incorporated in the model. At the second stage, a general or uniform inclusion of fuzzy optimization was established.

IV.5.2. Main findings on integrated strategic planning for the MAPA

Finding 8: Earlier framing of the landmine problem in Afghanistan portrays systematic framing bias for resource mobilisation purposes.

Acceding to the Mine Ban Treaty resulted from the onset in a high pressure on the programme, which forced the management in stating unrealistic expectations and overly optimistic output predictions. Both systematic exaggerations of the Afghan landmine problem and of what the Afghan mine action programme would be able to deliver resulted in a significant distortion of the complex realities on the ground, largely resulting in strategic plans which were neither feasible to implement, nor affordable in terms of funding requirements.

Finding 9: Accurate estimates of clearance rates are critical for long-term strategic planning and have caused major errors in the costing estimates.

Mine clearance rates can be based to a great extent on past year's studies, experiences, parameters and outcomes, but it should also recognize the importance of having up to date clearance data, in order to acquire a better and credible understanding of the long-term strategic impact.

This will avoid the tendency to rely too much on past achievements of mine action programmes, not allowing for sufficient anticipation towards future dynamics and inadvertent changes of situations or scenarios. This demonstrates again the complexity to satisfy simultaneously short and long-term planning requirements. Strategic prioritization and planning for mine action should sufficiently provide the decision makers the capability and flexibility to maintain the highest possible output at any level of funding available at any moment in time. These principles will be further staffed during the case-study.

Finding 10: Integration of mine action in overarching strategies brings in the right checks and balances.

The aim should not only be to maximize donor funding by balancing overall priorities to cover both the mine action humanitarian imperative and critical security and development objectives, but also to demonstrate a balanced approach within a much broader overarching Afghan humanitarian and development plan. The country will benefit most of a holistic approach in this regard, not from tunnel-vision on isolated objectives.

CHAPTER V – PHASE-IV: THE GLOBAL DIMENSION AND CONCLUSIONS

V.1 Introduction

V.1.1. From national to global

Before concluding the dissertation, this phase will take into account the *global dimension* of the landmine problem and explore how key findings of the previous phases could be transformed into *grand strategy* recommendations. Hence the question, how can mine action benefit from a global approach? Ask most experts in mine action what is meant by the global dimension of mine action and they will intuitively refer to the global devastating impact of the landmine problem as it both affects contaminated States and donor countries. The global mapping of the landmine problem can be best assessed through the facts and figures of the annual Landmine Monitor or the Global Landmine Impact Survey. The UN and the GICHD are international organisations with selective but often more advanced consolidation of country-specific mine action information.

As discussed during Phase-I, the need for global coordination of resource allocation and required data management has known limited success over the last decade due to the reluctance and lack of transparency of donor countries, mine affected States and programme managers. The provision of detailed data has been problematic or biased, especially when it could in one or another way affect the funding of the programme. With the findings and recommendations from the previous phase, global resource allocation mechanisms could be studied according to similar methodological principles as those applied at a national level. Ideally, and in line with the logic maintained throughout this thesis, the rationale or the primary goal of mine action on a global scale should be to minimize as fast as possible the global human suffering from the effects of landmines. This should not take away resources which could be used in other sectors with greater effect. How this is best achieved requires *theoretically a global prioritization process* on when and where mine action programmes should be implemented, continued or expanded. This indicates the need for objective global mechanisms which should bring benefits to all actors involved but has known little or no progress so far.

“The idea of data sharing and consolidation on a regional or even global basis has been around since the early days of mine action. Advocates of data sharing point to *increased efficiency, improved resource allocation and donor demand for reporting* as powerful reasons for adopting various data consolidation plans. Unfortunately, sharing mine action information is not always an easy task. Whether data is to be shared at the global, regional, national or even local level is a *question that often arouses spirited debate and discussion*.”⁵⁸⁹

V.1.2. Global prioritization: is it a critical requirement?

The development and advantages of a decision-analysis model for mine action prioritization or resource allocation at a national level have been comprehensively assessed with the Afghan case-study. However, the requirement for a *global* prioritization process needs to be questioned carefully. At a global level, should there be a necessity for a more systematic and rational resource allocation process, then it needs inevitably to be placed in a larger methodological context.

To begin, it is *unlikely that international organisations will easily adopt a global modelling approach* which is *insensitive to political and diplomatic constraints* inherent to funding allocation and international aid. Even at a global level, there is a tendency to approach donor and mine affected countries on an *individual* basis, due to the uniqueness of the relationship the UN and other international or regional organisations tend to build up with each of them, and for good

⁵⁸⁹ The GICHD Regional Support Centre: An Approach to Regional Information Management, by Simon Berger, Regional Coordinator for Latin America and Alan Arnold, Programme Manager, GICHD, MAIC Issue 5.1, 2001

reasons. However, data analysis and cross-country comparisons between different mine action programmes remains desirable and is most informative when addressing the global dimension. To remind, Phase-I indicated that States are requesting this information from the UN. This implies that attention should go both to successful mine action programmes as well as to those programmes which were or are either largely inefficient or ineffective. To do this, out of a *pragmatic* point of view, *uncomplicated mechanisms* are required that *standardize comparisons* between mine-affected countries.

V.1.3. Criteria relevant to the “high politics” and global dimension

Applicable for this phase, table V.1 lists the majority of “high politics” criteria from Phase-I. Many of them are related to the political and legal instruments of mine action. It is largely a straightforward process to assess the “*country profile*” rather than the performance of a State in terms of adherence to the MBT and CCW Protocols, sponsoring of the UN resolution on “assistance in mine action”, resource mobilisation per capita, etc.

The usefulness to build up a *country profile* according to various criteria in table V.1 will be studied in the next sections. Most information to qualify countries according to the criteria below can be retrieved either from UN voting records or sponsor lists and annual publications or reporting related to the Landmine Monitor and/or Mine Ban Treaty - Article 7 reporting.

Nr	Criteria	Country Profile
1	C1: Being supportive to the consensus process on “assistance in mine action”	Yes/No
2	C2: Sponsoring the UN resolution on “assistance in mine action”	Yes/No
3	C6: Level of human cost	Landmine Monitor
4	C7: Establishment of a national mine action capacity	Yes/No
5	C17: Progress or level of stockpile destruction	Article 7 MBT reporting
6	C18: Adherence to the CCW - Amended Protocol II	Yes/No
7	C19: Compliance with the Amended Protocol II and its technical provisions	Yes/No
8	C20: Being supportive to the CCW resolution	Yes/No
9	C21: Adherence to Protocol V of the CCW	Yes/No
10	C22: Adherence to the Mine Ban Treaty	Yes/No
11	C23: Voting in favour/abstaining of the MBT resolution	Yes/No
12	C24: Progress on achieving the core humanitarian objectives of the Mine Ban Treaty – Nairobi Action Plan	Article 7 MBT reporting
13	C25: No new deployments of landmines	Landmine Monitor
14	C26: Level of pressure of State actors to inhibit non-State actors from using landmines/ERW	Deeds of Commitment?
15	C31: Resource mobilization per capita	Landmine Monitor
16	C37: Management and planning capabilities of national mine action coordination centres	Landmine Monitor
17	C38: Having established adequate fund raising mechanisms	Landmine Monitor
18	C39: Level of integration of mine action in peacekeeping/building operations	UN website or Landmine Monitor
19	C42: Balanced and effective public awareness campaigns and objective framing of the landmine problem	Assessment missions

Table V.1: Criteria from Phase I which are relevant regarding the high politics and global dimension of mine action

V.2. Exploring the global dimension of mine action

V.2.1. The relevancy of global goal setting and costing

When addressing specific questions related to global goal setting and costing, it needs to be emphasized that this dissertation deliberately stayed clear of estimates such as the total number of landmines or the global sum-up of mine-infested square kilometres. It was explained that these and other similar elements can be interesting yardsticks but finally would not provide any significant insights regarding the real impact of the problem. This underscores once again the essential difference between trying *to solve* the global landmine problem, compared to trying *to control* or reduce the impact of it. Although both courses of action overlap, they nevertheless require different politics and especially different policies to support it.

It is also necessary to comprehend the politics or forces which hinder clarity on the basic questions regarding global goal setting and costing of the landmine problem. The UN has categorized some of them as follows:

“All of us want to know the scale of the landmine problem and the level of success in addressing it so far. Why have we all found it so difficult to answer the basic questions? First, *reliable figures on conflict-related issues are notoriously hard to find*. [...] Secondly, *the problem is by definition hidden!* And those who created the problem are often understandably reluctant to provide accurate data. And so, we are forced to tell people that we *do not know how many mines we are looking for or how many square miles of land are contaminated and we have only a rough idea of the number of victims*.”⁵⁹⁰

The sobering publication “*Mine Action after Diana*” rather heavily criticized the UN on its mine action policy making, strategy and global guidance... or lack of it. The cumbersome analysis revealed that UN agencies, instead of competing with NGOs and bilateral agencies at the project level, should better *concentrate on elaborating a clearer vision for the future of mine action*.⁵⁹¹ As discussed in Phase-I, the revised UN strategy for 2006-2010 has only partially met that requirement.⁵⁹²

Not only the UN is under fire for poor strategic vision and global goal setting, also those involved in mine action research and development face mounting criticism. Long-time campaigners for a total ban state that they have seen millions, if not billions, being spent on research to develop hi-tech equipment that finally cannot be used in mine-affected countries. Often, all they needed were better off-the-shelf mine detectors.⁵⁹³ Workshops like “*Is humanitarian demining technology a broken promise?*” are further indicative that the development of mine clearance technology is not widely regarded as a success story.⁵⁹⁴ Apart from some gradual improvements of the mine action “toolbox”⁵⁹⁵, no technological breakthroughs have ever been announced. This was another sobering conclusion after the research and development sector in mine action technology absorbed significant funding at a global level.

⁵⁹⁰ Statement of the by then Director of UNMAS, Mr. Martin Barber, during the Reinforced Mine Action Support Group Meeting of November 2004, New York.

⁵⁹¹ MASLEN, S. (2004). *Mine Action after Diana – Myths and Realities*, United Kingdom

⁵⁹² Refer to page

⁵⁹³ National Action Plans urged for a mine-free world, July 16, 2004, United Nations, suggestion by ICBL Intersessional Program Officer Susan Walker.

⁵⁹⁴ Internet. Available at www.eudem.vub.ac.be/files/EUEDEM2_Final_Workshop.pdf - EU EUEDEM Brussels October 2004, accessed on 22 August 2006

⁵⁹⁵ The toolbox term is generally used to indicate three methods of mine clearance: manual, mechanical and via Mine Detection Dogs or other biosensors.

Sometimes strategic questions related to the global dimension or costing of the landmine problem are wisely put off by: “*It is impossible to calculate*”.⁵⁹⁶ Indeed, it is not possible to calculate precisely most global mine action issues, but it is harder to overrule the possibility to *estimate* the global costing and update the estimations as more accurate data becomes available. It might therefore be important to partially redirect the political consultative processes in order to increase the research efforts to establish those estimates which are useful towards a better understanding of the global landmine problem. So, the recurrent question “What is it going to cost or take to solve it?” should not be ignored as it tends to put the politics and ongoing mine action efforts into an interesting perspective. However, *global costing of the landmine problem is in relevancy clearly subordinate to the bigger questions related to global goal setting* and the targets for clearance and stockpile destruction advocated by the MBT.

V.2.2. Mine action funding

A. Global resource mobilisation

As in previous years, tracking financial support for mine action remains difficult. There continues to be a great deal of variation in what donors report on, the level of detail reported, and for what time period, despite greater transparency and better reporting mechanisms. The most reliable source of resource allocation information is again the Landmine Monitor, which provides a consolidated and comprehensible picture of the global funding situation. The mine action investments database maintained by UNMAS is quite comprehensive but often poorly updated by both donor and recipient countries.⁵⁹⁷

Traditionally, the Landmine Monitor has not included funds for R&D into demining technologies and equipment in these totals, and has instead listed available R&D funding separately. Together with the European Commission, only a few countries —Belgium, Canada, France, Japan, Luxembourg, Norway, the United Kingdom and the United States—report precise R&D funding. Together they spent between 5 and 10 % of the total estimated annual funding of mine action on R&D.⁵⁹⁸

R&D funds aside, the Landmine Monitor figures likely under-state global donor mine action funding to a significant degree, for a number of reasons. Funding for victim assistance programs is included where possible, but for some major donors landmine victim assistance funding cannot be separated out from other non-landmine-specific programs. In some cases, donors do not report the value of *in-kind* as opposed to *cash* contributions. The totals also do not reflect mine action funding provided by NGOs or the private sector.⁵⁹⁹ Apart from international donor funding, some mine-affected countries themselves have made significant contributions to mine action.

As studied in the previous phases, unlikely increases in mine action funding will be needed in the future to cope fully with the global landmine problem and to enable Mine Ban Treaty States Parties to meet their *10-year deadlines for mine clearance*. Under the Nairobi Action Plan 2005-2009, States Parties indeed agreed they will ensure the sustainability of their commitments. New conflicts and shifting requirements, however, easily jeopardize the desired multiple-year funding to

⁵⁹⁶ Reply of Mr. Martin Barber, Director of the UN Mine Action Service when asked how much more is needed to reach the goals of the Mine Ban Treaty (e.g. mine-affected countries free of landmines ten years after ratification of the Treaty), July 16, 2004 – Politics: National Action Plans urged for a mine-free world, by Susanne Link

⁵⁹⁷ <http://www.mineactioninvestments.org/frameset.asp?iCurrentLanguage=0>

⁵⁹⁸ ICBL (2006), *Landmine Monitor Report 2005: Toward a Mine-Free World: International Campaign to Ban Landmines*. New York

⁵⁹⁹ ICBL (2005), *Landmine Monitor Report 2005: Toward a Mine-Free World: International Campaign to Ban Landmines*. New York

facilitate long-term planning of mine action.⁶⁰⁰ A new trend is to increasingly involve regional organizations and the World Bank and regional development banks and financial institutions to support States Parties requiring assistance in fulfilling their treaty obligations. Afghanistan has done remarkably well in this regard.⁶⁰¹ Quite unique about the mine action sector is its relentless search and efforts to identify new and non-traditional sources of support, be they technical, material or financial.⁶⁰² In sum, in absence of one comprehensive database there is quite some information available from different sources.

B. Donor countries

Based on Landmine Monitor 2006 data, table V.2 provides an overview of the mine action funding per capita in 2005 of the top-25 donor countries and the same funding as a percentage of Gross National Income.⁶⁰³ It is important to note that this data does not take into account the tens of millions US\$ of EC contributions to mine action. According to the categorization introduced in Phase-I, the majority of the donor countries could be labelled as “*first class donors*”. This includes Finland, the US and Poland not being a State Party to the MBT.

Quite some substantial differences are noticeable between a ranking based on funding per capita compared to funding as % of the Gross National Income (GNI). It puts in perspective the often repeated official US statements of being the biggest single contributor to mine action programmes, while Norway, Slovenia and Iceland pay more than 20 times their contribution in terms of funding per capita or as % of GNI.

	DONOR COUNTRIES	FUNDING PER CAPITA	DONOR COUNTRIES	FUNDING AS % OF GNI
1	Norway	\$7.90	Slovakia	0.0168%
2	Iceland	\$5.08	Norway	0.0133%
3	Luxembourg	\$2.84	Iceland	0.0110%
4	Denmark	\$2.09	Denmark	0.0044%
5	Switzerland	\$1.63	Luxembourg	0.0043%
6	Slovakia	\$1.34	Netherlands	0.0032%
7	Sweden	\$1.30	Sweden	0.0032%
8	Netherlands	\$1.18	Finland	0.0030%
9	Finland	\$1.12	Switzerland	0.0030%
10	Canada	\$0.64	Canada	0.0019%
11	Ireland	\$0.53	Australia	0.0014%
12	Australia	\$0.44	Ireland	0.0013%
13	Belgium	\$0.38	Czech Republic	0.0013%
14	United Kingdom	\$0.36	Slovenia	0.0011%
15	Japan	\$0.31	Belgium	0.0011%
16	United States	\$0.28	United Kingdom	0.0009%
17	Austria	\$0.27	New Zealand	0.0008%
18	Germany	\$0.26	Japan	0.0008%
19	New Zealand	\$0.22	Germany	0.0007%
20	Slovenia	\$0.19	Poland	0.0007%
21	Czech Republic	\$0.14	Austria	0.0007%
22	Italy	\$0.08	United States	0.0006%
23	France	\$0.06	Italy	0.0003%
24	Poland	\$0.05	France	0.0002%
25	Spain	\$0.04	Spain	0.0002%

Table V.2 Top-25 Donor Countries

⁶⁰⁰ Action #45 of the Nairobi Action Plan. Internet. Available at [icrc.org/Web/eng/siteeng0.nsf/htmlall/68LGY8/\\$File/ActionPlan.pdf](http://icrc.org/Web/eng/siteeng0.nsf/htmlall/68LGY8/$File/ActionPlan.pdf), accessed on 30 June 2006

⁶⁰¹ Based on information from the consecutive Landmine Monitors and the mine action investment database, Afghanistan has generated frequently more than 10% of its funding through the EU and the World Bank.

⁶⁰² This is reflected in Action 48 and 50 of the Nairobi Action Plan.

⁶⁰³ Internet. Available at <http://www.icbl.org/lm/2006/es/funding.html#fn128>, accessed on 22 July 2006

C. Recipient countries

Table V.3 provides the reported mine action funding data in 2005 of the main *recipient* countries or those countries which receive a minimum of one million US\$. Several criteria of table V.1 have been added from column 3 to 10 in order to reflect the profile or category of the recipient country. Column 3 provides the reported number of mine victims, column four reflects if the nation acceded to the MBT, columns 5 and 6 reflect the adherence to Protocol II and III of the CCW. The 2005 co-Sponsor record of the UN resolution “Assistance in mine action” is reflected in column 7 and the 2005 voting record of the UN resolution on the MBT in column 8. The most concerning element is reflected in column 9 and 10 regarding the new deployments of landmines by non-State actors and State actors respectively.

N°	MINE AFFECTED NATIONS	2005 FUNDING MILLION USD	2005 MINE/ERW VICTIMS	MBT	CCW P II	CCW P V	VOTING/ SPONSOR		NEW LANDMINE USE/PRODUCTION NSA SA	
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)
1	Afghanistan	66.8	848	Yes	No	No	NS	Yes	Yes	No
2	Sudan	48.4	79	Yes	No	No	NS	Yes	No	No
3	Angola	35.8	96	Yes	No	No	S		No	No
4	Iraq	27.8	358	No	No	No	NS	Yes	Yes	No
5	Cambodia	23.9	875	Yes	No	No	NS	Yes	No	No
6	Sri Lanka	19.1	56	No	Yes	No	NS	Yes	No	No
7	Bosnia	15.0	19	Yes	Yes	No	NS	Yes	No	No
8	Croatia	9.1	12	Yes	Yes	Yes	NS	Yes	No	No
9	Mozambique	7.9	57	Yes	No	No	NS	Yes	No	No
10	Laos	7.0	164	No	No	No	NS		No	No
11	Lebanon	6.5	22	No	No	No	NS		No	No
12	Vietnam	5.8	112	No	No	No	NS	A	No	Yes
13	DRC	4.9	0	Yes	No	No	NS	Yes	No	No
14	Eritrea	4.9	68	Yes	No	No	NS	Yes	No	No
15	Albania	4.8	23	Yes	Yes	Yes	S	Yes	No	No
16	Azerbaijan	4.1	59	No	No	No	NS	Yes	No	No
17	Somaliland	3.7	276	No	No	No	NS	Yes	No	No
18	Nicaragua	3.5	15	Yes	Yes	Yes	S	Yes	No	No
19	Guinea-Bissau	3.5	30	Yes	No	No	NS	Yes	Yes	No
20	[Abkhazia]	3.3	15	(No)	(No)	(No)	NS	Yes	(No)	(No)
21	Ethiopia	2.6	31	Yes	No	No	NS	Yes	No	No
22	Yemen	2.5	35	Yes	No	No	NS	Yes	No	No
23	Colombia	2.3	1110	Yes	Yes	No	NS	Yes	Yes	No
24	Burundi	2.1	11	Yes	No	No	NS	Yes	Yes	No
25	Cyprus	1.9	0	Yes	Yes	No	S	Yes	No	No
26	[Kosovo]	1.9	11	(Yes)	(Yes)	(No)	S	Yes	(No)	(No)
27	Uganda	1.7	40	Yes	Yes	No	NS	Yes	No	No
28	Serbia	1.7	2	Yes	No	No	NS	Yes	No	No
29	[Nagorno-Kb]	1.3	18	(No)	(No)	(No)	NS	Yes	(No)	(No)
30	Chad	1.2	35	Yes	No	No	NS		No	No
31	[Chechnya]	1.0	24	(No)	(Yes)	(No)	(NS)	(A)	(No)	(No)

Legend: NS= No Sponsor of the UN Resolution, A= abstaining during the voting procedures

Table V.3: Recipient countries which receive ≥ 1 million US\$ in annual funding

A first analysis does not really indicate any significant facts. Only two countries, Albania and Nicaragua have a “perfect country profile” according to the criteria used above. Five affected nations, non-members of the MBT, receive more than 5 million US\$ with Iraq and Sri Lanka almost totalizing 50 million US\$. Sometimes the MBT is used as leverage to force mine-affected nations to join the Treaty, often with limited or eroding effects.

D. Global funding versus global human cost of landmines

Hence, based on table V.3, no significant conclusions or observations could be made. Trying to categorize States according to their voting records and/or adherence to treaties and conventions provides at best a quite generic “country profile”, may be interesting but likely of limited added value. A last comparison which is somehow interesting is the absence of a strong correlation between the number of mine victims and the global funding pattern. The graph in figure V.1 shows in yellow the 2005 reported funding versus the number of 2005 reported victims in black. The five countries with the highest human cost received an annual funding varying from 66.8 million US\$ for Afghanistan to a mere 2.3 million US\$ for Columbia.

Fig. V.1: Reported mine action funding per year compared to reported mine/ERW victims per year

V.2.3. Landmine impact assessment at a global scale

A. Past efforts

A former multiple-country impact assessment is illustrated in table IV.4. It takes into account some familiar elements: the impact of mines on the population from humanitarian, health, socio-economic and development perspectives; the security situation; and local capacities for mine action; the willingness of the mine-affected state to support a mine action programme and its adherence to the Mine Ban Treaty.⁶⁰⁴ Paradoxically, the information, criteria and indicators are so vague that it facilitates cross-country comparison.

⁶⁰⁴ Landmines (1999) A review of United Nations Activities in Mine Action, United Nations. New York, p.15

Country	AZERBAIJAN	BURUNDI	ETHIOPIA	JORDAN	LEBANON	SOMALIA	SUDAN	YEMEN
Impact of Mines/UXO on:								
Repatriation of refugees	medium	medium	low	low	low	medium	high	low
Resettlement of IDPs	medium	low	medium	low	medium	medium	high	low
Delivery of humanitarian aid	low	medium	low	low	low	low	high	low
Settled Populations (casualties)	low	low	low	low	low	low	high	medium
Socio-economic Development	medium	low	low	low	medium	high	high	medium
Health	low	low	low	low	low	low	high	low
Requirement for Assistance:								
Victim assistance	low	low	low	medium	medium	medium	high	medium
Mine awareness	high	medium	medium	medium	medium	medium	high	medium
Survey and marking	high	low	high	low	high	high	high	high
Mine clearance	medium	low	medium	medium	medium	medium	medium	high
Status on Ottawa Convention:	unsigned	signed	signed	ratified	unsigned	unsigned	signed	ratified

Table IV.4: Cross-country comparison of former Level One Landmine Surveys

This collected outcome of assessments is the result of what was previously called a *Level One Survey*⁶⁰⁵, nowadays called *General Survey*. It is designed as an information gathering process not only to identify the general location of mined or suspected mined areas, but also as a first measurement of the impact of landmine contamination on the society and general requirements for assistance. The simplistic cross-country comparison through the familiar high-medium-low categorization was a precursor on the ranking of mine-affected communities as it is known today according to the LIS-scale of low, medium and high impact.

Some other global surveys looked solely into the socio-economic impact of explosive remnants of war and came to the conclusion that the effects are quite similar to the presence of landmines. The ERW survey methodology seems also to merge human cost with the socio-economic impact:

“This Survey does not contain any estimate of the global total of casualties of explosive remnants of war, as there is *not sufficient information to attempt this*. However, even if it is impossible at present to reach reliable consolidated estimates of casualties, comparisons between the general characteristics of casualty profiles in different places can provide some useful indications of the broad socio-economic effects of ERW.”⁶⁰⁶

In summary, early efforts to assess the global impact of the landmine problem gained some support but the complexities have been generally underestimated.

B. The Global Landmine Survey

a. A global success story?

During the preceding research phases, many of the strengths and weaknesses of the LIS methodology were addressed in detail, together with ample recommendations on how to optimize the exploitation of survey data. An evaluation of the *Global Landmine Survey Process* by Scanteam⁶⁰⁷ confirmed that the task of identifying the mine-affected areas and deriving an unambiguous impact assessment of these suspected contaminated areas has been a much more

⁶⁰⁵ Prior to the term “General Survey”, surveys of mine-affected countries were subdivided in four levels I, II, III and IV, the latter associated with a post-clearance survey. Level I survey has been defined as the process of identifying and mapping all suspected mined areas. A new definition has been developed by the Survey Action Centre (SAC), and national Level 1 Impact survey is now considered to be “... an information/data gathering process designed to collect information on areas contaminated, suspected to be contaminated by mines or UXO. This process is intended to provide a basis for analysis to measure the impact of the national mine/UXO problem and to identify critical planning criteria.” The SAC has developed a methodology, and has established a set of standards and guidelines which govern the conduct of national Level I Impact surveys planned and coordinated by the SAC and its partners. http://www.mineactionstandards.org/revision/ToRs_body.htm

⁶⁰⁶ BORRIE, J. (2003). *Explosive remnants of war; a global survey*, United Kingdom, p. 11

⁶⁰⁷ The Survey Action Centre, Washington DC contracted Scanteam of Norway to carry out this evaluation. Scanteam is a partner-owned Norwegian consulting firm that supports activities in developing countries and transitional economies. They provide analysis, advice and facilitation services for projects and programmes, and to the organisations that develop and implement them. Internet. Available at www.scanteam.no, accessed on 23 May 2007

daunting task than originally thought. One of the recurrent concerns is the *lack of cooperation and coordination between national mine action authorities and NGO mine action operators*, especially those run by internationals. The LIS has *not* been successful in increasing the local cooperation and coordination between national mine action authorities and NGO mine action operators. This recalls the *trust dilemma* studied in Phase-I.

“There are a number of examples where dialogue between LIS implementers and local mine actors has contained *distrust* and *conflict*. There has thus been little interest and confidence in the LIS, and furthermore a feeling that the SHA information is of such low quality that it simply does not provide operators with operationally helpful information.”⁶⁰⁸

It is therefore aspired that through enhanced LIS data exploitation more reliable information can be presented to the decision-makers and operators to better assist them in prioritizing their life-saving activities to maximum effect. Logically an increase in interest and confidence will follow.

b. Cumulated costs of Landmine Impact Surveys

In 2004, the total cost of the surveys of the nine countries was already well beyond 20 million US\$, which makes the current LIS-methodology particularly vulnerable to criticism.

“So has \$20 million been wasted? Certainly, the word *impact* has entered the vocabulary of mine action, where it is likely to remain and even increase in relevance. But as Richard Kidd from the US State Department has noted, the survey has been followed by the same level of mine action planning, or, more accurately, *lack of planning* as before.”⁶⁰⁹

As depicted in figure V.2, several surveys are ongoing and even more countries are on watch. Hence, the costs of ongoing and outstanding surveys could easily mount to another 20 million US\$; without having even one landmine cleared.

Fig V.2: The Global Landmine Survey in action

Taking into account the *time-bound value* of the results of a LIS and the need for ongoing investments and efforts to keep the survey results up to date and operationally useful, leads to the observation that it is indeed a *funding-hungry concept*. This justifies again the

⁶⁰⁸ Scanteam. Draft copy of the evaluation of the Global Landmine Survey Process, p.50

⁶⁰⁹ MASLEN, S. (2004). *Mine Action after Diana – Myths and Realities*, United Kingdom, p.33

effort of this dissertation to improve the exploitation of LIS-data without incurring any significant additional costs. Enhancing data exploitation will be critical to maintain donor interest and better connect the politics and decision-making at the different levels. This will also mitigate the earlier cited trust dilemmas. The next section will address more ambitious objectives to improve the LIS in order to live up to the concept of a “global” landmine survey.

V.2.4. Cross-country comparison

A. Enhancing the LIS: the most suitable platform for cross-country comparison?

A commending but at the same time sobering reflection on this question is summarized in the following statement:

“The Landmine Impact Survey has allowed us to identify afflicted communities and to describe the level of impact that mines have on these communities. Although *these Surveys are not strictly comparable*, they do give us a *sense of the order of magnitude of the problem.*”⁶¹⁰

The weak-metric system of the LIS lies at the basis of having only a limited cross-country capability. The outcome of all the finalised LIS is visualized in figure V.6 below based on the number and level of impacted communities in nine mine-affected countries. From the total 8869 impacted communities: 1212 are high impacted communities or 14%; 2416 are medium impacted communities or 27% and 5241 are low impacted communities or 59%.

Fig.V.6: Landmine Impact Level by Country

⁶¹⁰ Reinforced Mine Action Support Group, November 2004 meeting, New York, Minutes of the meeting, p.17

It is a significant observation that almost 60% of the communities are categorized as low impact. In case of a global prioritization of mine action, clearing activities that lower the mine impact scores of the high impacted communities would most optimally reduce the impact of landmines. Hence, in absence of global prioritization mechanism, this would theoretically be the most effective way to start clearing the mine fields causing communities to be highly impacted.

“These surveys have already revealed that over 80 per cent of landmines’ social and economic harm is caused by less than 20 per cent of the world’s minefields. With the help of the LIS Explorer, officials in the surveyed countries and foreign donors will be able to more effectively prioritize landmine clearance, refine mine risk education campaigns, and better direct health care and psycho-social assistance to landmine survivors.”⁶¹¹

Mine-affected Country	Mine-affected communities						Total	Ranking	Funding In 2003 (Mio USD)	Funding In 2005 (Mio USD)	LIS Weighted distribution of funding
	High		Med		Low						
Cambodia	564	*3 +	463	*2 +	911	*1 =	3529	1	17	23.9	35.9
Afghanistan	258	*3 +	362	*2 +	1102	*1 =	2600	2	75.2	66.8	26.5
Bosnia	154	*3 +	696	*2 +	516	*1 =	2370	3	10.4	15	24.1
Mozambique	25	*3 +	205	*2 +	759	*1 =	1244	4	15.3	7.9	12.7
Thailand	69	*3 +	233	*2 +	228	*1 =	901	5	1.2	< 1	9.2
Yemen	14	*3 +	84	*2 +	494	*1 =	704	6	3.6	2.5	7.2
Azerbaijan	11	*3 +	101	*2 +	368	*1 =	603	7	5.3	4.1	6.1
Somaliland	45	*3 +	102	*2 +	210	*1 =	549	8	2.1	3.7	5.6
Chad	49	*3 +	52	*2 +	148	*1 =	399	9	1.2	1.2	4.1
Total									131.3	126.1	

Table V.5 Cross-country comparison assuming mine affected communities would be a standard unit

Table V.5 provides a cross-country comparison of LIS data in terms of high, medium and low impacted communities. By means of illustration, a simplistic weighting system has been introduced whereby a weight factor 3 is given to highly impacted communities, 2 to medium and 1 to low impact. If the number and impact level of mine-affected communities would be standard and equal, than a very simple methodology as the one used here could give us already a reliable cross-country comparison technique and an indicative weighted distribution of funding or resource allocation. All this is however based on the strategic assumption that the classification of the high, medium and low impacted communities systematically follows the same standards and objective criteria.

Theoretically, this allows for the determination of weight coefficients, which in combination with funding or resource allocation data⁶¹² permits the calculation of a weighted distribution of funding as depicted in the table below. Projecting that funding of mine action solely depends on the number and degree of impacted communities is currently not credible but shows the potential if, based on the methodology presented in this dissertation, a more sophisticated impact ranking would be expanded for cross-country comparison and resource allocation purposes. Consequently, above table theoretically proves, what has also been stated

⁶¹¹ SAC website first-of-its kind web-based research tool, the “LIS Explorer,” funded by a \$25,000 grant from the U.S. Department of State’s Office of Weapons Removal and Abatement, that enables decision makers and the general public to easily examine the results of Landmine Impact Surveys (LIS) in selected countries to better understand the scope of the problem and make more informed decisions. The LIS Explorer contains extensive data on landmine and unexploded ordnance infestation and casualties in Bosnia and Herzegovina, Chad, north-western Somalia (“Somaliland”), Thailand and Yemen. Data on Afghanistan, Azerbaijan, Eritrea, Ethiopia, Lebanon and north-eastern Somalia will be added to it shortly. Until the advent of the LIS Explorer, the locations of suspected mined areas, their relative impact on men, women, children and other demographic information, and degree to which the mines infested vital natural resources and infrastructure, were not accessible to the general public, nor readily available to government officials. Now, anyone with access to the Internet can use the LIS Explorer at sac-na.org/lisexplorer/ to review the findings of comprehensive nationwide landmine impact surveys.

⁶¹² Landmine Monitor Report 2004: Executive Summary, p.65

by competing programme managers, that Afghanistan is getting too much funding and Cambodia too little.

In summary, the absence of a transparent and global overview of the funding of mine action further complicates at this stage global data analysis and research. Coordination and cooperation amongst donor governments and recipient countries has been in general restricted and unclear, resulting in the absence of a common coherent approach. Certain experts are convinced there is no donor fatigue and that the global mine action budget will remain well above the estimated (US) 250 million dollars per year. The European Commission⁶¹³ and the US have both published funding strategies which, for the time being, support this conviction. For the time being, the mine action Survey Centre in Washington will continue to touch upon the significant information gathering problems present in the donor community:

“We are getting more information, there are a lot of sources, but *we still can't define the problem we are trying to solve*. Donors should begin to have a coherent and broad strategy. Can the donor community agree on a consistent reporting by recipient countries? The donors could come together to define categories and requirements for consistent reporting.”⁶¹⁴

B. No charity, but facts!

While it might be argued that information-sharing is far from perfect, it works well enough for most purposes. Donors receive periodic progress reporting, the public is informed of hazards, and the turnover of cleared land and resource allocation is accomplished. Unfortunately, this approach does not mean that cross-country data comparisons or regional aggregation of data is actually being accomplished. This is because mine action information is collected by each national authority according to its local needs and standards. Even the definition of the various data elements collected can vary considerably between actors in a single programme and between the various country programmes. This makes cross-country comparison of information difficult at the best of times and dangerous at the worst.

A worthy alternative to the global approach is the establishment of smaller scale mechanisms to compare mine action requirements at a *regional* level or between two affected countries. In this regard, there is some analogy with the statistical *clustering or reductionism applied throughout the case-study*. However, for a variety of reasons, the mine action community has been reluctant to rely on cross-country comparison of mine-affected States. The question how comparatively well mine action programs have been doing has generally been tacitly avoided during important mine action conferences by complimenting each other profusely while avoiding the specific challenges that remain to be addressed. Political sensitivities are obviously at stake. The discussion about comparison between mine-affected countries should thus be reopened in a refined way, but how?

In the financial world, investment research and comparative analysis of stocks is common place, and extensively boosted by the development of computer-driven systems. Automatic ranking of companies according to their fundamental value indicators and growth potential is standard practice. The detailed calculation of this growth potential is further translated in estimated profit margins and predictions on how stock quotes might evolve in the short and medium term, albeit mostly within a broad margin. Is it technically possible to develop a similar appraisal system for the approximately eighty mine-affected countries, whilst simultaneously respecting political sensitivities? What would be the impact on the donor community if the current large variety of ways and means of reporting was to be replaced by a “two-page” document? This would portray per mine-affected country the inputs, that is to say the funding of mine action programs, in relation to the

⁶¹³ EU Mine Actions 2002-2004: Strategy and Multi-annual Indicative Programming. <http://eu-mine-actions.jrc.cec.eu.int> (accessed on May, 20, 2004)

⁶¹⁴ EATON, B. (2004). *Reinforced Mine Action Support Group Newsletter*, New York, p.5

outputs: the estimated generated socio-economic benefits and reductions in human cost? Until now, the desirability of such a pragmatic and concise document has been outweighed by the predicted obstacles and risks to apply such a methodology. Moreover, poor data, or worse, corrupted data, might endlessly complicate the application of analogue models to those used in the financial world, where companies are subject to stringent, harmonised and transparent reporting regulations.

However, it remains theoretically relevant, desirable and practical if potential donors could deduct from cross-country comparison that one million USD spent on mine action in country X would save an estimated double amount of people from mine accidents than when it would be “invested” in a mine action programme of country Y, or if the amount of refugees which can return to their cleared villages and farmland would be triple in country Y compared to country Z. This study will, therefore, substantially address issues related to cross-country comparison.

As discussed during Phase-I, support and contact groups, some of them directly related to the MBT, undertake increased efforts that result in more reliable resource mobilization data. In extension of increased global donor coordination, donor countries regard a more methodological and strategic approach of recipient countries as equally important. In light of future funding and resource mobilization for mine action, this “business” approach might offer a new momentum to the politics of mine action and mine action activities. A statement of a US representative puts it in clear terms: **“no charity but facts”**.

“In making decisions on how to allocate these [mine action] resources, we expect potential recipients to propose *sound national strategies for investment, not charity*. Strategies should include clearly articulated visions and precise, measurable objectives [...]. Progress should not be measured simply by the number of mines destroyed or area cleared, but rather in terms of social and economic benefits such as casualties reduced and food production restored.”⁶¹⁵

⁶¹⁵US statement at the meeting of the Mine Ban Treaty - Standing Committee Meeting on mine clearance, Mine Risk Education, and Mine Action Technologies, 22 June 2004, delivered by Richard G. Kidd IV

V.3. Conclusions and “Grand Strategy” recommendations

Conclusion/recommendation 1: The developed prioritization model provided a comprehensive response to the research aim and subordinate research objectives but its role should remain limited to decision *analysis* and *advise* decision makers accordingly.

The normative, game and decision theoretic approach, together with the phased research process, provided an adequate response to the research aim. The broad-based political analysis resulted in a comprehensive identification of the main political actors and dynamics in the field of mine action, together with the concrete development of innovative decision analysis approaches. Based on the available real-world data, the multiple criteria decision analysis model proved its functionality and ability to determine a best *national* mine action response to heavily affected countries such as Afghanistan. Better data and *continuous efforts to update and expand the model* with more relevant decision criteria will *increase the potential of the model even further*. Contrary to conservative mainstream thinking, the outputs of the model and its ample possibilities validates that the politics of mine action can benefit highly from a scientifically sound model based on systematic, objective and advanced multiple criteria decision analysis. In seeking a best response to complex problems, the model can serve as a useful tool in rationalising the emotion-laden field of *national* resource allocation to save human life, generate socio-economic benefits and enhance peacekeeping/building.

However, like many other research approaches available to international relations scientists, models should be used with prudence and must never be mistaken for the real world. This was acknowledged even before the modelling effort started. However, having a better understanding of the possible outputs of the models recognizes that there is a pertinent danger that the *presented mathematical or statistical elegance and formalism become research objectives in themselves*, instead of a means to gain greater insight about complex situations. Clearly, this is something this dissertation tried to avoid through seeking pragmatic methodologies versus overly complicated ones. Similarly, the model focused on decision *analysis* and therefore functions merely in an *advisory capacity* in support of decision-makers. It was not developed to replace sound judgement.

The last research phase illustrated that global or regional landmine impact surveys and information management as a concept has not yet managed to establish the flow of standardized data required to achieve multiple criteria decision analysis at a regional or global scale. If there would be a political will, then the methodologies presented at a national level illustrated that a modelling process should not necessarily be overly demanding or complicated. However, the current relevancy to develop a prioritization model at a regional or global level remains questionable, taking into account the identified political sensitivities and agendas.

Conclusion/recommendation 2: Mine action requires a comprehensive *performance and risk management* system.

With mine action related data becoming increasingly available, political decision-makers and the mine action programme management will struggle more to assimilate large amounts of information while staying focused on what is vital to achieve the strategic objectives, together with running effective and efficient mine action operations. Through statistical analyses and human cost predictions, the multiple criteria decision analysis effectively models the anticipated effects of mine action in order to optimize its performance regarding *risk management* and alignment within a post-conflict restoration environment.

Political decision-makers need assistance in *strategic performance and risk management* while the programme managers need help monitoring the *operational* performance of their mine

action assets, so they can identify prioritization problems and recognize potential opportunities at a glance.

The methodology and tools presented in this dissertation aspire to inform the different kinds of decision makers at all levels to execute confidently their strategy and drive performance of their mine action efforts by providing insight and its ability to facilitate *understanding, communication and accountability* at the envisaged strategic management level. The methodology and structure of the modelling has proven to be a flexible concept which could be tailored towards the specific requirements at the different political and managerial levels of mine action.

Conclusion/recommendation 3: Multiple criteria decision analysis needs to be *championed* by regional or global organisations active in the field of mine action.

To follow up on the previous recommendation, a standardized approach in multiple criteria analysis for the prioritization of mine action will not be done unless a *regional or global organisation champions its use*. If at all possible, the United Nations and/or the Survey Action Centre should initiate, standardise and support its initial use by providing the necessary resources for it. The technique will then find easier its advocates within the existing managerial capabilities of the mine action programmes. It is anticipated these advocates will eventually include project managers and experienced strategic and operational planners. Admittedly, it is not likely that political authorities will ask specifically for these kinds of tools, if they by all means know they exist.

Inevitably, decision-makers will be drawn to multiple criteria analysis because so many of their current mine action prioritization decisions involve competing elements, trade-offs, qualitative criteria, uncertainty and judgment. For this reason, the political analysis has emphasized throughout that compromise is the only possible lasting outcome of conflicting or diverging views, and compromise requires a thorough understanding of the criteria of all mine action stakeholders in the decision making process. The dissertation, therefore, advocates that multiple criteria analysis has great value for providing a structure for informed discussions which could at many occasions avoid senseless discussions related to poor priority-setting or ineffective allocation of resources. The different phases have illustrated that in the field of mine action it is not unusual to be confronted with various single-interest pressure groups. Moreover, it is a small community with *competing interests* and *trust dilemmas*. A solid application of multiple criteria analysis can demonstrate that the final decision is reached through a rational process fully cognizant of the views of all stakeholders.

Conclusion/recommendation 4: Multiple criteria decision analysis needs also to be *championed* by the programme management and decision-makers themselves with the goal to incorporate it in the “mine action toolbox” at the inception of a mine action programme.

In the more advanced programmes mine action takes place according to an optimal balance between manual mine clearance, mine detection through biosensors and mechanical clearance. The study illustrated that today’s politics in mine action can benefit significantly from applying a similar toolbox principle in terms of “aggressive” statistical data analysis, multiple criteria decision analysis, strategic planning and other management instruments. Not only does it provide a better understanding in which internal and external dynamics a mine action programme takes place, it also starts to provide for the longer term perspective donor countries look for and counters the “*dumping funding into a black hole*” effect.

Many positive indications have been highlighted throughout the study on what the mine action's global future and politics could and should be. The process and the combined approach of the landmine impact surveys and multiple criteria decision analysis have been a cornerstone of the proposed more methodological and systematic prioritization of mine action activities. In many, if not

all cases, it will swiftly transfer clearance resources from *high-density minefields* to *high-impacted communities*.

The combined usage of LIS, MCDA, IMSMA, GIS and Strategic Planning Software will significantly contribute to an integrated approach that shifts away from *unproductive large area clearance*, to focus instead on the *blockages* that are killing people and paralysing the local economy. If this can be established at the inception of a mine action programme, then the biggest return on investment can be achieved. In sum, the success of applying MCDA in mine action essentially depends on the *motivated choice of the decision-makers and/or programme management themselves to use this type of decision aid* before resources are allocated.

Conclusion/recommendation 5: Mine action requires standardization of short-term prioritization and integrated strategic planning procedures.

Mine action is experiencing many of the political, humanitarian and development issues one would expect to find in any nascent sector of multilateral activity. In order to have a more effective impact through the politics of mine action, there is a clear requirement for further standardization of business processes and operating procedures, as well as performance indicators and realistic benchmarks for all components of mine action.

One objective would be to improve and standardize the measurement of achievements against strategic plans and activities, for the purpose of continuous improvement. This implies the effective and uniform incorporation of the basic principles of a *strategic planning framework* presented in this dissertation. Furthermore, standardization of both mine action prioritization and strategic planning is *critical for cross-country comparison* of mine action programmes. In this regard, this dissertation has aimed to provide solid but easily accessible methodologies and techniques and addressed comprehensively the current challenges related to cross-country comparison.

Conclusion/recommendation 6: Mine action should seek more proactively its incorporation and streamlining in the strategic planning framework promoted in this dissertation.

The understanding of mine action by donor countries continues to improve but it is not sufficient to come up with new ways and slogans to justify the levels of required funding; other humanitarian and development activities do this as well and are often more effective in their fundraising efforts. The ambition levels of mine programs have to correspond to broader political objectives. The broader strategic planning framework of needs assessments, poverty reduction strategies (PRSP) and MDGs are key instruments toward a more integrated and balanced nation building and/or recovery process. Consequently, lining up mine action activities with overarching strategies and MDG goal setting can indeed result in less funding available for mine action. This may require the mine action community to abandon a “tunnel vision” approach on the issues.

Indeed, owing to its complexity and cross-cutting characteristics, mine action will have to continue to firmly make its case to improve its mainstreaming into development and reconstruction activities in mine-affected States. This should not cause concern but rather acceptance of a broader prioritization process, whereby no scarce funding should go to the "demining of mountaintops or deserts" whilst the population in the valley is suffering - or worse, dying from the consequences of extreme poverty. There is no rationale that can justify this: not a humanitarian, a development or even an Ottawa Convention one. The straightforward rationale to prevail should be the prioritization of those humanitarian and/or development projects that most significantly reduce human suffering or create the biggest socio-economic benefits. In this regard, the strategic guidance from the MDG framework is helpful and the option to extend Mine Ban Treaty deadlines useful.

Conclusion/recommendation 7: The mine action sector should continue to question its current goal setting of a world free of anti-personnel mines.

The dissertation emphasized how mine action as a dynamic enterprise requires eliminating the most pressing effects of landmines in a prioritized order. As such, the future of mine action depends highly on the consensus regarding the setting of goals, based on the usage of commonly agreed indicators.

With the MBT providing a solid advocacy platform for the noble cause of a landmine free world, mainstreaming of mine action in the broader realm of post conflict reconstruction and development activities will continue to reinforce its too simplistic ideological connotation. The progressive dialogue and adherence to the Convention of Certain Conventional Weapons is moving this regulating legal instrument gradually out of the MBT shadow. The ratified protocol on Explosive Remnants of War and the ongoing discussions on mines other than anti-personnel mines are clear examples that the CCW further matures in its complementary role to the MBT and increasingly alleviate the stagnation of the universalisation of the latter.

The comparison of both legal instruments in percentage of global military expenditure or population instead of in number of States Parties sheds furthermore a different light on how adherence to legal instruments can be perceived differently if one agrees that the recent adherence of the Island of Vanuatu is, although encouraging, quite different from the adherence of one of the permanent members of the United Nations Security Council.

Its absolutist and overly idealistic approach, overlooks the true threat presented by all landmines, assumes the availability of unlimited resources to achieve its aims, and fails to accommodate national security interests of three out of the five permanent members of the UN Security Council.

Conclusion/recommendation 8: Surveys and information management should be further enhanced to improve prioritization and ultimately facilitate cross-country comparison of mine action programmes.

With the many LIS completed or underway, the knowledge base of the problem has a global dimension. This increasingly supports the intensified usage of inferential statistics which could further aid the development and usage at a global scale of risk assessment models and victim prediction.

Modelling should precede and accompany, rather than succeed, the field work if maximum benefit is to be gained from it. This is for two reasons. Firstly, one of the main benefits is to guide data collection and this is a continuing process; it cannot happen, and there is a risk of valuable mine action data loss, if the data are gathered first. Secondly, some modelling can be done with virtually no data, and the Afghan case-study has proven a considerable amount can be done with only few data.

Although satisfactory modelling and prioritization results were achieved based on existing sources of information and survey methods, it is assessed that with little additional costs landmine surveys could be further enhanced to better define the nature, scope and impact of the landmine and ERW problem. In order to achieve optimal results, these efforts need to be harmonized with the ongoing developments of other advanced information management systems, such as the Information Management System for Mine Action (IMSMA) and the Geographic Information System (GIS).

Conclusion/recommendation 9: The “effectiveness” of the politics of mine action remains a tough measurable; nevertheless, enhancing the effectiveness will continue to require the concerted and continued effort of all involved in the competitive world of post-conflict recovery.

The first finding of Phase-I indicated how dynamic the politics of mine action are in a normative sense. This triggers the question if the politics of mine action are becoming more focused and effective by the day? Even after all the analysis it remains a difficult question to answer, since it depends on the approach taken. Mine action itself is undoubtedly an activity which is implemented with increasing effectiveness and efficiency. The many professionally run mine action programmes prove this on a daily basis. However, effective mine action programmes do not necessarily imply equally effective politics or resource allocation.

This dissertation stresses that the amount of funding will theoretically never be there to make the world completely free of landmines and explosive remnants of war. The Diner’s Dilemma explained the effects of too many mine-affected countries failing to take national ownership of their programmes, based on the false assumption that if they sign the Mine Ban Treaty, others will take care of their landmine problem. However, a variety of actors are committed to provide the resources and expertise to at least significantly reduce worldwide the human cost and socio-economic impact. If this means that the politics are effective, then they definitely are. If effective politics mean achieving a universal ban, then with several military superpowers outside a total ban, the politics did not yet achieve their objective and may never. If effective politics mean establishing an effective name and shame campaign or stigmatization process for the countries outside the Mine Ban Treaty, then again most of the systematic efforts are effective to the highest standards. If effective politics mean that the majority of mine action resources are well spent, then the answer is even more difficult due to the absence of an internationally managed resource allocation process. Equally, the gained momentum of the mine action politics is sensitive to eroding and “undermining” effects related to utopian norms or goal setting, donor fatigue, competitiveness amongst its key actors, and lack of cooperation and coordination.

However, whichever way one looks at the politics of mine action, either bottom-up in terms of efficiency and effectiveness reached at field level, or a top-down analysis of the high politics, it can be observed that stigmatizing the use of landmines has been so successful that State actors likely will only revert to its use as a last resort national security option. This remains above all an extraordinary disarmament achievement.

As a closing note, it is important to underline continuously the real human costs and human faces behind all the measurables, outranking processes, goals or strategic plans. Mine action is still much more than the UN mine action resolutions, Mine Ban Treaty clearance deadlines, and even outranking processes such as PROMETHEE, but they offer critical yardsticks. Therefore, the campaigns for a “mine-free world” or “making poverty history” should not refrain from using the confrontational element of detailing the human costs of poor prioritization and programme management, missed opportunities and clearance deadlines. Once more, the credibility of the mine action sector is at stake if it does not undertake everything to use the scarce resources to best effect.

This dissertation began with a quote from former UN Secretary-general Kofi Anan and ends with the applicable vision and *businesslike* approach to UN reform of the recently appointed Secretary-general Ban Ki-moon: “*We need to find out the comparative, competitive edge of each and every UN department and agency, it is necessary to maximize the strength and minimize the redundancy ... we need to use already limited resources in a more effective, efficient way.*”⁶¹⁶

⁶¹⁶ Reuters : I’m no pushover, says next UN chief By Paul Holmes and Evelyn Leopold Sat Oct 14 2006

V.4. Future research and other applications

In seeking a best response to very complex problems, the rather unique methodology of combining normative, game and decision theory offered in the end useful tools in rationalising the resource allocation to save human life, generate socio-economic benefits and enhance peacekeeping. Although the conducted research did clarify aspects of the politics related to peacekeeping/building and post-conflict response, it also opened new areas one can explore for further or similar research. Indeed, a better understanding of the studied methodology and theoretic fields could help actors involved in other protracted post-conflict restoration processes to set out their respective policies.

Being a UN planner for the Darfur peace operations, allowed me to recognize some, if not all, characteristics of similar complex multiple criteria problems. The deployment of a military force (UNAMID) of 20000 troops in more than 50 camp sites poses many challenges, in particular the choice of deployment locations. Applying MCDA to inform the decision-makings process on the future deployment locations presents an excellent example of a similar multiple criteria problem whereby a methodology as presented in this dissertation could be applied.

Fig. V.7.: DARFUR: Example of a complex operational environment where multiple criteria problems could benefit from multiple criteria analysis

However, like many other research approaches available to international relations scientists, methodologies from one particular research area should be used with prudence in another area. On the other hand, used with discretion, the interesting but not necessarily exhaustive combination of *normative*, *game* and *decision* theory can serve to add precision and rigour to the analyst's reasoning. In this regard, rather than being a competitor to single or mainstream approaches in the field, game theory's proper but maybe slightly controversial role in this dissertation is to be primarily a supporting discipline which occasionally enables to develop arguments which go further than may be possible with purely verbal reasoning. As Phase-I demonstrates, this regularly enriched the conclusions derived from otherwise sound analysis, possibly making it through accessible *metaphoric considerations* more clear what the assumptions and elements are under which the various conclusions hold true.

Appendix

Fifty-eighth session
Agenda item 22

Resolution adopted by the General Assembly

[Without reference to a Main Committee (A/58/L.50 and Add.1 included)]

Argentina, Armenia, Australia, Belgium, Brazil, Bulgaria, Canada, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Japan, Liechtenstein, Lithuania, Malta, Mexico, Netherlands, Nigeria, Panama, Poland, Portugal, Republic of Moldova, Romania, Serbia and Montenegro, Slovakia, Switzerland, the former Yugoslav Republic of Macedonia, Turkey, Ukraine, United States of America and Zambia: draft resolution

Addendum: Add the following countries to the list of sponsors of the draft resolution: Andorra, Austria, Bolivia, Cyprus, Estonia, Iceland, Ireland, Luxembourg, Mali, Monaco, Mozambique, New Zealand, Peru, Republic of Korea, San Marino, Senegal, Slovenia, Sweden, Thailand, Tunisia and United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland

58/127. Assistance in mine action

The General Assembly,

Recalling its resolution 57/159 of 16 December 2002 and all its previous resolutions on assistance in mine clearance and mine action, all adopted without a vote,

Recognizing that, in addition to the primary role of States, the United Nations has a significant role to play in the field of assistance in mine action, and considering mine action to be an important and integrated component of United Nations humanitarian and development activities,

Reaffirming its deep concern at the tremendous humanitarian and development problems caused by the presence of mines and other unexploded ordnance that constitute an obstacle to the return of refugees and other displaced persons, to humanitarian aid operations and to reconstruction and economic development, as well as to the restoration of normal social conditions, and that have serious and lasting social and economic consequences for the populations of mine-affected countries,

Bearing in mind the serious threat that mines and other unexploded ordnance pose to the safety, health and lives of local civilian populations, as well as of personnel participating in humanitarian, peacekeeping and rehabilitation programmes and operations,

Encouraged by the reduction in the number of new mine victims, but reiterating its dismay at the existing high number of victims of mines and other unexploded ordnance, especially among civilian populations, including women and children, and recalling in this context its resolution 57/190 of 18 December 2002 and Commission on Human Rights resolutions 2003/49 of 23 April 2003, on the human rights of persons with disabilities, and 2003/86 of 25 April 2003, on the rights of the child,⁶¹⁷

Deeply alarmed by the number of mines that continue to be laid each year, as well as the presence of a decreasing but still very large number of mines and other unexploded ordnance as a result of armed conflicts, and therefore remaining convinced of the necessity and urgency of a significant increase in mine-clearance efforts by the international community with a view to eliminating the threat of landmines to civilians as soon as possible,

Noting the inclusion in Amended Protocol II⁶¹⁸ to the Convention on Prohibitions or Restrictions on the Use of Certain Conventional Weapons Which May Be Deemed to Be Excessively Injurious or to Have Indiscriminate Effects⁶¹⁹ of a number of provisions of importance for mine-clearance operations, notably the requirement of detectability, and provision of information and technical and material assistance necessary to remove or otherwise render ineffective minefields, mines and booby traps, and noting also that Amended Protocol II to the Convention entered into force on 3 December 1998,

⁶¹⁷ See Official Records of the Economic and Social Council, 2003, Supplement No. 3 (E/2003/23), chap. II, sect. A.

⁶¹⁸ CCW/CONF.I/16 (Part I), annex B.

⁶¹⁹ See The United Nations Disarmament Yearbook, vol. 5: 1980 (United Nations publication, Sales No. E.81.IX.4), appendix VII.

Noting also the conclusions and recommendations adopted at the Fourth⁶²⁰ and Fifth⁶²¹ Annual Conferences of the States Parties to Amended Protocol II to the Convention on Prohibitions or Restrictions on the Use of Certain Conventional Weapons Which May Be Deemed to Be Excessively Injurious or to Have Indiscriminate Effects, held in Geneva on 11 December 2002 and on 26 November 2003, respectively,

Noting further the new additional Protocol to address the post-conflict impact of explosive remnants of war adopted by the Meeting of States Parties to the Convention on Prohibitions or Restrictions on the Use of Certain Conventional Weapons Which May Be Deemed to Be Excessively Injurious or to Have Indiscriminate Effects, held in Geneva on 27 and 28 November 2003,⁶²² and noting the agreement reached on mandates for further work by the same Meeting,

Noting that additional States have ratified or acceded to the Convention on the Prohibition of the Use, Stockpiling, Production and Transfer of Anti-personnel Mines and on Their Destruction,⁶²³ which entered into force on 1 March 1999, bringing the total number of States that have formally accepted the obligations therein to one hundred and forty-one,

Noting also the conclusions of the Fifth Meeting of the States Parties to the Convention on the Prohibition of the Use, Stockpiling, Production and Transfer of Anti-personnel Mines and on Their Destruction, held in Bangkok from 15 to 19 September 2003,⁶²⁴ taking note of the reaffirmed commitments that were made by the States parties in the Bangkok Declaration,⁶²⁵ among other things, to pursue efforts related to the core humanitarian objectives of the Convention, urging all States parties and relevant organizations to participate actively in the work of the intersessional programme established by States parties to the Convention, and taking note also that the First Review Conference, to which the Secretary-General will be invited, will be held in Nairobi, from 29 November to 3 December 2004,

Stressing the need to convince mine-affected States to halt new deployments of anti-personnel mines in order to ensure the effectiveness and efficiency of mine-clearance operations,

Stressing also the pressing need to urge non-State actors to halt immediately and unconditionally new deployments of mines and other associated explosive devices,

Recognizing the importance of assisting mine clearance in mine-affected countries by ensuring that the necessary maps and information and appropriate technical and material assistance are provided to help to remove existing minefields, mines, booby traps and other unexploded ordnance,

Noting that the resources allocated to mine-action activities have increased in recent years, but stressing the need to mobilize additional resources and to secure the best possible utilization of such resources, particularly for victim assistance, in order to meet increasing requirements, and encouraging all States, the United Nations and other international, regional and non-governmental and private organizations to continue their efforts in this regard,

Concerned at the limited availability of safe and cost-effective mine-detection and mine-clearance equipment, as well as the need for effective global coordination in research and development to improve relevant technologies, and conscious of the need to promote further and more rapid progress in this field and to foster international, national and local technical cooperation to that end,

Reaffirming the need to reinforce cooperation and coordination in the area of mine action at all levels and to devote the necessary resources to that end, including resources to support national and regional capacity-building initiatives, where applicable, and the work of the United Nations in this regard,

Noting with appreciation the finalization of an emergency response plan by the United Nations to respond to emergency mine-action requirements,

Welcoming the various established mine-action coordination centres, as well as the creation and existence of international trust funds for mine-action activities,

Noting with satisfaction the inclusion in the mandates of several peacekeeping operations of provisions relating to mine-action work carried out under the direction of the Department of Peacekeeping Operations of the Secretariat, in the context of such operations,

Commending the action taken by donor and recipient Governments, the United Nations system, regional organizations, the International Committee of the Red Cross and non-governmental organizations to coordinate their efforts and seek solutions to the problems related to the presence of mines and other unexploded ordnance, as well as their assistance to victims of mines,

Welcoming the role of the Secretary-General in increasing public awareness of the problem of landmines,

⁶²⁰ CCW/AP.II/CONF.4/3 (Part I), sect. IV.

⁶²¹ See CCW/AP.II.CONF.5/2.

⁶²² CCW/GGE/VI/2, annex II.

⁶²³ See CD/1478.

⁶²⁴ See APLC/MSP.5/2003/5.

⁶²⁵ *Ibid.*, part II.

1. *Welcomes* the report of the Secretary-General on assistance in mine action⁶²⁶ and the recommendations contained therein, and takes note with appreciation of the revised mine-action strategy contained in the addendum to the report;⁶²⁷
2. *Calls*, in particular, for the continuation of the efforts of States, with the assistance of the United Nations and relevant organizations involved in mine action, as appropriate, to foster the establishment and development of national mine-action capacities in countries in which mines and other unexploded ordnance constitute a serious threat to the safety, health and lives of the local population or an impediment to social and economic development efforts at the national and local levels, and urges all Member States, in particular those that have the capacity to do so, to assist mine-affected countries in the establishment and development of national capacities in mine action;
3. *Invites* Member States to develop and support national programmes, where appropriate, in cooperation with the relevant bodies of the United Nations system and relevant regional, governmental and non-governmental organizations, to reduce the risks posed by landmines and other unexploded ordnance, including among women and children;
4. *Expresses its appreciation* to Governments, regional organizations and other donors for their financial and in-kind contributions to mine action, including contributions for emergency operations, peacekeeping operations and for national and local capacity-building programmes;
5. *Encourages* efforts to conduct mine action in accordance with accepted national and international standards, including International Mine Action Standards, and also encourages all States involved in mine action, including troop-contributing countries conducting mine action in peacekeeping operations, to follow these standards, as applicable;
6. *Emphasizes* the importance of using an information management system, such as the Information Management System for Mine Action, in full coordination with the United Nations Mine Action Service and with the instrumental support of the Geneva International Centre for Humanitarian Demining;
7. *Appeals* to Governments, regional organizations and other donors to continue and, whenever possible, increase their support to mine action through reliable, predictable and timely contributions, including contributions through the Voluntary Trust Fund for Assistance in Mine Action as well as to national mine-action efforts and humanitarian mine-action programmes of non-governmental organizations, to allow for the timely delivery of mine-action assistance, and stresses that such assistance should be integrated into broader humanitarian, development and other strategies;
8. *Stresses* the importance of international support for emergency assistance to victims of mines and other unexploded ordnance and for the care, rehabilitation and social and economic reintegration of the victims, and also stresses that such assistance should be integrated into broader public health and socio-economic strategies;
9. *Encourages* all relevant multilateral and national programmes and bodies to include, in coordination with the United Nations, activities related to mine action in their humanitarian, rehabilitation, reconstruction and development assistance activities, where appropriate, bearing in mind the need to ensure national and local ownership, sustainability and capacity-building;
10. *Encourages* Member States, the United Nations system, international and regional organizations and relevant non-governmental organizations to take further action to mainstream a gender perspective and integrate gender and age-appropriate considerations in all aspects of mine-action programming, particularly including programmes to reduce the number of child victims and relieve their plight;
11. *Stresses* the importance of cooperation and coordination in mine action, while emphasizing once again the important role of the United Nations in the effective coordination of mine-action activities, based on the United Nations policy on mine action and effective coordination,⁶²⁸ and especially the role of the Mine Action Service, stresses also the important role that national authorities and regional organizations can play in this regard, as well as the important role of relevant non-governmental organizations, and underlines the need for the continuous assessment of these roles by the General Assembly;
12. *Emphasizes* the role of the Mine Action Service as the focal point for mine action within the United Nations system and its ongoing collaboration with and coordination of all mine-related activities of the United Nations agencies, funds and programmes, and in this regard expresses its appreciation of the roles played by other bodies of the United Nations system, in accordance with United Nations mine-action policy;
13. *Urges* Member States and regional, governmental and non-governmental organizations and foundations to continue to extend full assistance and cooperation to the Secretary-General and, in particular, to provide him with information and data, as well as other appropriate resources that could be useful in strengthening the coordination role of the United Nations in mine action;
14. *Takes note with appreciation* of the Mine Action Guidelines for Ceasefire and Peace Agreements,⁶²⁹ requests the Secretary-General to make them widely available to United Nations mediators, moderators, special representatives of the Secretary-General and others, as appropriate, and calls upon all parties to conflict to

⁶²⁶ A/58/260.

⁶²⁷ A/58/260/Add.1.

⁶²⁸ See A/53/496, annex II.

⁶²⁹ The Guidelines are available from E-MINE, Internet. Available at www.mineaction.org, accessed on 12 July 2006

incorporate provisions on mine action, where relevant, in ceasefire and peace agreements or other relevant arrangements;

15. *Takes note* of the potential that mine action can have as a peace and confidence-building measure in post-conflict situations among concerned parties;

16. *Encourages* the Secretary-General to continue to propose, where appropriate, provisions related to mine action in his recommendations to the Security Council for peacekeeping operations;

17. *Emphasizes* the importance of undertaking further multisectoral assessments and surveys to better define the nature, scope and impact of the landmine and other unexploded ordnance problem in affected countries and to support the establishment of clear priorities and national economic and development plans of action, underlining the need for the participation of populations of mine-affected areas in this regard;

18. *Notes with appreciation* the ongoing development by the United Nations of the International Mine Action Standards, with the assistance of the Geneva International Centre for Humanitarian Demining and other partners in mine action, to support the safe and effective conduct of mine-action activities, and emphasizes the need for an inclusive process to be followed in the development and review of such standards and the importance of developing in mine-affected countries national mine-action standards based on the International Mine Action Standards;

19. *Recognizes* the importance of building national capacities for and ownership of mine-action programmes, encourages the further establishment of national mine-action centres, including those supported by the United Nations Development Programme and the United Nations Children's Fund as well as those established under the auspices of the Mine Action Service in emergency situations, and encourages States to support the activities of those centres and the trust funds established for the coordination of assistance in mine action and the promotion of national ownership;

20. *Requests* the Mine Action Service to continue developing the electronic mine information network as a user-friendly repository of mine-related information and as a means for mine-action programmes to circulate on a regular basis to donors and other partners standard reports on the scope and impact of the mine problem, available mine-action resources and capacities and the progress achieved in the field;

21. *Emphasizes* the importance of recording the location of mines, of retaining all such records and making them available to concerned parties upon cessation of hostilities, and welcomes the strengthening of the relevant provisions in international law;

22. *Calls upon* Member States, especially those that have the capacity to do so, to provide the necessary information and technical, financial and material assistance, as appropriate, and to locate, remove, destroy or otherwise render ineffective minefields, mines, booby traps and other devices, in accordance with international law, as soon as possible;

23. *Urges* Member States and regional, intergovernmental and non-governmental organizations and foundations that have the ability to do so to provide, as appropriate, technological assistance to mine-affected countries and to promote user-oriented scientific research on and development of mine-action techniques and technology, within reasonable time frames, so that mine-action activities may be carried out more safely and cost-effectively, and also urges them to promote collaboration at all levels in this regard;

24. *Invites* States to explore the possibility of strengthening internationally negotiated and non-discriminatory legal instruments that address landmines and other unexploded ordnance, as well as their victims;

25. *Takes note with appreciation* of the ongoing efforts of the Secretary-General to increase public awareness of the impact of the problem of landmines and unexploded ordnance;

26. *Requests* the Secretary-General to submit to the General Assembly at its fifty-ninth session a report on the progress achieved on all relevant issues outlined both in his previous reports to the Assembly on assistance in mine action and in the present resolution, including the progress made by the International Committee of the Red Cross and other international and regional organizations as well as national programmes, and on the operation of the Voluntary Trust Fund for Assistance in Mine Action and other mine-action programmes, as well as a report on the first implementation of the emergency response plan and lessons learned from this experience and on the implementation of the strategy for the period 2001–2005;¹¹

27. *Decides* to include in the provisional agenda of its fifty-ninth session the item entitled "Assistance in mine action".

76th plenary meeting
19 December 2003

		MBT			CCW			Mine Affected Country	VOTING RECORD MBT RESOLUTION AND CO-SPONSORSHIP UN RESOLUTION												TOTAL CO- SPONSORING		
		sign.	appr.	acc.	ratif.	sign.	ratif.		II ratif.	'93	'94	'95	'96	'97	'98	'99	'00	'01	'02	'03		'04	'05
										Corresponding General Assembly Session													
										48	49	50	51	52	53	54	55	56	57	58		59	60
71	Guinea-Bissau	1997			2001			X		x		x											2
72	Guyana	1997			2003																		0
73	Haiti	1997																			x		1
75	Honduras	1997			1998			2003	X	x		x	x										3
76	Hungary	1997			1998	1981	1982	1998		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	12
77	Iceland	1997			1999	1981				x	x	x	x	x									10
78	India					1981	1984	1999	X	x													1
79	Indonesia	1997																					0
80	Iran								X														0
81	Iraq								X														0
82	Ireland	1997			1997	1981	1995	1997		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x			11
83	Israel					1995	2000		X	x													1
84	Italy	1997			1999	1981	1995	1999		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x			12
85	Jamaica	1997			1998																		0
86	Japan	1997			1998	1981	1982	1997		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x			11
87	Jordan	1998			1998		1995	2000	X						x		x						3
88	Kazakhstan									x			x	x									3
89	Kenya	1997			2001				X						x		x						2
90	Kiribati			2000																			0
91	Korea (Dem. People's Rep. of)								X														0
92	Korea (Republic of)						2001		X	x	x	x					x	x	x				6
93	Kuwait								X	x													1
94	Kyrgystan								X														0
95	Laos					1983			X			x											1
96	Latvia				2005	1993	2002		X	x	x	x						x					4
97	Lebanon								X														0
98	Lesotho	1997			1998		2000			x					x	x							3
99	Liberia			1999											x	x		x					3
100	Libya								X														0
101	Liechtenstein	1997			1999	1982	1989	1997		x		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x			10
102	Lithuania	1999			2003		1998	1998	X	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x			11
103	Luxembourg	1997			1999	1981	1996	1999		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x			11
104	Macedonia (FYR of)		1998				1996	2005				x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x			9
105	Madagascar	1997			1999															x			1
106	Malawi	1997			1998				X	x										x			2
107	Malaysia	1997			1999					x													1
108	Maldives	1998			2000		2000	2000															0
109	Mali	1997			1998		2001									x	x	x	x				4
110	Malta	1997			2001		1995	2004		x		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x				9
111	Marshall Islands	1997																					0
112	Mauritania	1997			2000				X														0
113	Mauritius	1997			1997		1996			x	x											x	3
114	Mexico	1997			1998	1981	1982														x	x	2
115	Micronesia										x												1
116	Moldova (Republic of)	1997			2000		2000	2001	X	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x			10
117	Monaco	1997			1998		1997	1997		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x			12
118	Mongolia					1981	1982		X	x	x	x					x						4
119	Morocco					1981		2002	X														0
120	Mozambique	1997			1998				X	x	x	x	x	x	x		x	x	x	x			9
121	Myanmar (Burma)								X														0
122	Namibia	1997			1998				X		x						x						2
123	Nauru			2000				2001													x		1
124	Nepal								X	x	x												2
125	Netherlands	1997			1999	1981	1987	1999		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x			11
126	New Zealand	1997			1999	1981	1993	1998		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x			12
127	Nicaragua	1997			1998	1981		2000	X	x	x	x	x				x	x	x				9
128	Niger	1997			1999		1992		X							x	x						2
129	Nigeria				2001	1982				x										x			2
130	Niue	1997			1998																		0
131	Norway	1997			1998	1981	1983	1998		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x					9
132	Oman								X														0
133	Pakistan					1982	1985	1999	X	x													1
134	Palau																						0
135	Panama	1997			1998		1997	1999		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x				10
136	Papua New Guinea																						0
137	Paraguay	1997			1998			2004													x		1
138	Peru	1997			1998		1997	1997	X			x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x			10
139	Philippines	1997			2000	1981	1996	1997	X						x	x	x	x	x				6
140	Poland	1997				1981	1983	2003		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x			12

United Nations

A/C.4/59/L.9

General Assembly

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Fifty-ninth session
Special Political and Decolonization Committee
(Fourth Committee)
Agenda item 22
Assistance in mine action

Netherlands: draft decision

Assistance in mine action

The General Assembly,

Recalling its resolution 58/127 of 19 December 2003 on assistance in mine action,

Decides to include in the provisional agenda of its sixtieth session the item entitled "Assistance in mine action".

Annex D. MBT versus CCW based on percentage of global population and global military expenditures

		MBT	CCW	Population	Percentage of Global Population	Military Expenditures	Percentage of Global Military Expenditures
1	Afghanistan	2002		30	0,48%	188	0,02%
2	Albania	2000	2002	3,6	0,06%	56	0,01%
3	Algeria	2001		33	0,53%	2480	0,24%
4	Andorra	1998		0,1	0,00%		0,00%
5	Angola	2002		11,8	0,19%	183	0,02%
6	Antigua and Barbuda	1999		0,1	0,00%		0,00%
7	Argentina	1999	1998	40	0,65%	4300	0,42%
8	Armenia			3	0,05%	135	0,01%
9	Australia	1999	1997	20	0,32%	16650	1,62%
10	Austria	1998	1998	8,2	0,13%	1497	0,15%
11	Azerbaijan			7,9	0,13%	121	0,01%
12	Bahamas	1998		0,3	0,00%		0,00%
13	Bahrain			0,7	0,01%	628	0,06%
14	Bangladesh	2000	2000	14	0,23%	995	0,10%
15	Barbados	1999		0,3	0,00%		0,00%
16	Belarus	2003	2004	10,3	0,17%	176	0,02%
17	Belgium	1998	1999	10,4	0,17%	3999	0,39%
18	Belize	1998		0,3	0,00%	18	0,00%
19	Benin	1998		7,6	0,12%	96	0,01%
20	Bhutan	2005		2,2	0,04%	14	0,00%
21	Bolivia	1998	2001	8,9	0,14%	132	0,01%
22	Bosnia and Herzegovina	1998	2000	4,4	0,07%	234	0,02%
23	Botswana	2000		1,6	0,03%	338	0,03%
24	Brazil	1999	1999	186	3,00%	11000	1,07%
25	Brunei Darussalam			0,4	0,01%	290	0,03%
26	Bulgaria	1998	1998	7,4	0,12%	356	0,03%
27	Burkina Faso	1998	2003	13,5	0,22%	64	0,01%
28	Burundi	2003		7,8	0,13%	39	0,00%
29	Cambodia	1999	1997	13,6	0,22%	112	0,01%
30	Cameroon	2002		17	0,27%	221	0,02%
31	Canada	1997	1998	33	0,53%	9801	0,96%
32	Cape Verde	2001	1997	0,4	0,01%	14	0,00%
33	Central African Republic	2002		4,2	0,07%	15	0,00%
34	Chad	1999		9,7	0,16%	101	0,01%
35	Chile	2001	2003	16	0,26%	3420	0,33%
36	China		1998	1306	21,07%	67490	6,58%
37	Colombia	2000	2000	43	0,69%	3300	0,32%
38	Comoros	2002		0,7	0,01%	12	0,00%
39	Congo (Brazzaville)			3,6	0,06%	126	0,01%
40	Congo (Democratic Rep.)	2002		60	0,97%	93	0,01%
41	Cook Islands			0,02	0,00%		0,00%
42	Costa Rica	1999	1998	4	0,06%	64	0,01%
43	Côte d'Ivoire	2000		17,3	0,28%	180	0,02%
44	Croatia	1998	2002	4,5	0,07%	620	0,06%
45	Cuba			11,3	0,18%	572	0,06%
46	Cyprus	2003	2003	0,8	0,01%	384	0,04%
47	Czech Republic	1998	1998	10,2	0,16%	2170	0,21%
48	Denmark	1998	1997	5,4	0,09%	3271	0,32%
49	Djibouti	1998		0,5	0,01%	29	0,00%
50	Dominica	1999		0,1	0,00%		0,00%
51	Dominican Republic	2000		9	0,15%	180	0,02%
52	Ecuador	1999	2000	13,4	0,22%	655	0,06%
53	Egypt			77	1,24%	2440	0,24%
54	El Salvador	1999	2000	6,7	0,11%	157	0,02%
55	Equatorial Guinea			0,5	0,01%	126	0,01%
56	Eritrea	2001		4,7	0,08%	151	0,01%
57	Estonia		2000	1,3	0,02%	155	0,02%
58	Ethiopia	1997		73	1,18%	337	0,03%
59	Fiji	1998		0,9	0,01%	36	0,00%
60	Finland		1998	5,2	0,08%	1800	0,18%
61	France	1998	1998	60	0,97%	45238	4,41%
62	Gabon	2000		1,4	0,02%	184	0,02%
63	Gambia	2002		1,6	0,03%	1	0,00%
64	Georgia			4,7	0,08%	23	0,00%
65	Germany	1998	1997	82	1,32%	35063	3,42%
66	Ghana	2000		22	0,36%	49	0,00%
67	Greece	2003	1999	10,7	0,17%	5890	0,57%
68	Grenada	1998		0,1	0,00%		0,00%
69	Guatemala	1999	2001	12	0,19%	201	0,02%
70	Guinea	1998		9,4	0,15%	57	0,01%
71	Guinea-Bissau	2001		1,4	0,02%	9	0,00%
72	Guyana	2003		0,8	0,01%	6	0,00%

73	Haiti			8,1	0,13%	26	0,00%
74	Holy See	1998	1997	0,001	0,00%		0,00%
75	Honduras	1998	2003	7,2	0,12%	101	0,01%
76	Hungary	1998	1998	10	0,16%	1080	0,11%
77	Iceland	1999		0,3	0,00%		0,00%
78	India		1999	1080	17,43%	16970	1,66%
79	Indonesia			241	3,89%	1300	0,13%
80	Iran			68	1,10%	4300	0,42%
81	Iraq			26	0,42%	1300	0,13%
82	Ireland	1997	1997	4	0,06%	700	0,07%
83	Israel		2000	6,3	0,10%	9110	0,89%
84	Italy	1999	1999	58	0,94%	28182	2,75%
85	Jamaica	1998		2,7	0,04%	31	0,00%
86	Japan	1998	1997	127	2,05%	45841	4,47%
87	Jordan	1998	2000	5,8	0,09%	1460	0,14%
88	Kazakhstan			15,2	0,25%	221	0,02%
89	Kenya	2001		34	0,55%	177	0,02%
90	Kiribati			0,1	0,00%		0,00%
91	Korea (Dem. People.'s Rep. of)			23	0,37%	5217	0,51%
92	Korea (Republic of)		2001	49	0,79%	16180	1,58%
93	Kuwait			2,3	0,04%	2584	0,25%
94	Kyrgystan			5,1	0,08%	19	0,00%
95	Laos			6,2	0,10%	11	0,00%
96	Latvia	2005	2002	2,3	0,04%	87	0,01%
97	Lebanon			3,8	0,06%	540	0,05%
98	Lesotho	1998		2	0,03%	33	0,00%
99	Liberia			2,9	0,05%	2	0,00%
100	Libya			5,8	0,09%	1300	0,13%
101	Liechtenstein	1999	1997	0,03	0,00%		0,00%
102	Lithuania	2003	1998	3,6	0,06%	230	0,02%
103	Luxembourg	1999	1999	0,5	0,01%	231	0,02%
104	Macedonia (FYR of)		2005	2,1	0,03%	200	0,02%
105	Madagascar	1999		18	0,29%	44	0,00%
106	Malawi	1998		12,7	0,20%	11	0,00%
107	Malaysia	1999		24	0,39%	1690	0,16%
108	Maldives	2000	2000	0,4	0,01%	41	0,00%
109	Mali	1998	2001	11,4	0,18%	22	0,00%
110	Malta	2001	2004	0,4	0,01%	31	0,00%
111	Marshall Islands			0,06	0,00%		0,00%
112	Mauritania	2000		3,1	0,05%	21	0,00%
113	Mauritius	1997		1,2	0,02%	12	0,00%
114	Mexico	1998		106	1,71%	6043	0,59%
115	Micronesia			0,1	0,00%		0,00%
116	Moldova (Republic of)	2000	2001	4,5	0,07%	9	0,00%
117	Monaco	1998	1997	0,03	0,00%		0,00%
118	Mongolia			2,8	0,05%	23	0,00%
119	Morocco		2002	33	0,53%	2305	0,22%
120	Mozambique	1998		19,4	0,31%	117	0,01%
121	Myanmar (Burma)			47	0,76%	39	0,00%
122	Namibia	1998		2	0,03%	168	0,02%
123	Nauru		2001	0,01	0,00%		0,00%
124	Nepal			28	0,45%	99	0,01%
125	Netherlands	1999	1999	16,4	0,26%	9408	0,92%
126	New Zealand	1999	1998	4	0,06%	1147	0,11%
127	Nicaragua	1998	2000	5,5	0,09%	33	0,00%
128	Niger			12,2	0,20%	33	0,00%
129	Nigeria	2001		128	2,07%	544	0,05%
130	Niue	1998		0,002	0,00%		0,00%
131	Norway	1998	1998	4,6	0,07%	4033	0,39%
132	Oman			3	0,05%	252	0,02%
133	Pakistan		1999	162	2,61%	3848	0,38%
134	Palau			0,02	0,00%		0,00%
135	Panama	1998	1999	3,1	0,05%	147	0,01%
136	Papua New Guinea			5,5	0,09%	17	0,00%
137	Paraguay	1998	2004	6,3	0,10%	53	0,01%
138	Peru	1998	1997	28	0,45%	829	0,08%
139	Philippines	2000	1997	88	1,42%	805	0,08%
140	Poland		2003	39	0,63%	3500	0,34%
141	Portugal	1999	1999	10,5	0,17%	3497	0,34%
142	Qatar	1998		0,9	0,01%	723	0,07%
143	Romania	2000	2003	22	0,36%	985	0,10%
144	Russian Federation		2005	143	2,31%	70000	6,83%
145	Rwanda	2000		8,4	0,14%	50	0,00%
146	Saint Kitts and Nevis	1998		0,04	0,00%		0,00%
147	Saint Lucia	1999		0,16	0,00%		0,00%

148	Saint Vincent & Grenadines	2001		1	0.02%		0.00%
149	Samoa	1998		0.1	0.00%		0.00%
150	San Marino	1998		0.03	0.00%	1	0.00%
151	Sao Tome e Principe			0.1	0.00%	1	0.00%
152	Saudi Arabia			26	0.42%	18000	1.85%
153	Senegal	1998	1999	11.7	0.19%	107	0.01%
154	Seychelles	2000		0.1	0.00%	12	0.00%
155	Sierra Leone	2001	2004	5.9	0.10%	13	0.00%
156	Singapore		2000	4.4	0.07%	4470	0.46%
157	Slovakia		1999	5.4	0.09%	406	0.04%
158	Slovenia	1998	2002	2	0.03%	370	0.04%
159	Solomon Islands	1999		0.5	0.01%		0.00%
160	Somalia			8.6	0.14%	19	0.00%
161	South Africa	1998	1998	44	0.71%	3172	0.33%
162	Spain	1999	1998	40	0.65%	9906	1.02%
163	Sri Lanka		2004	20	0.32%	514	0.05%
164	Sudan	2003		40	0.65%	587	0.06%
165	Suriname	2002		0.4	0.01%	7	0.00%
166	Swaziland	1998		1.1	0.02%	40	0.00%
167	Sweden	1998	1997	9	0.15%	5729	0.59%
168	Switzerland	1998	1998	7.5	0.12%	2548	0.26%
169	Syria			18.4	0.30%	858	0.09%
170	Tadjikistan		1999	7.2	0.12%	35	0.00%
171	Tanzania (United Republic)	2000		37	0.60%	21	0.00%
172	Thailand	1998		64	1.03%	1775	0.18%
173	Timor-Leste	2003		1	0.02%	4	0.00%
174	Togo	2000		5.4	0.09%	35	0.00%
175	Tonga			0.1	0.00%		0.00%
176	Trinidad and Tobago	1998		1.1	0.02%	67	0.01%
177	Tunisia	1999		10.1	0.16%	356	0.04%
178	Turkey	2003	2005	69	1.11%	12155	1.25%
179	Turkmenistan	1998	2005	5	0.08%	90	0.01%
180	Tuvalu			0.01	0.00%		0.00%
181	Uganda	1999		27	0.44%	170	0.02%
182	Ukraine	2005	1999	47	0.76%	618	0.06%
183	United Arab Emirates			2.6	0.04%	1600	0.16%
184	United Kingdom	1998	1999	60	0.97%	42836	4.40%
185	United States of America		1999	295	4.76%	437000	44.91%
186	Uruguay	2001	1998	3.4	0.05%	257	0.03%
187	Uzbekistan			27	0.44%	200	0.02%
188	Vanuatu	2005		0.2	0.00%		0.00%
189	Venezuela	1999	2005	25	0.40%	1687	0.17%
190	Vietnam			8.3	0.13%	650	0.07%
191	Yemen	1998		21	0.34%	885	0.09%
192	Serbia and Montenegro	2003		10.8	0.17%	654	0.07%
193	Zambia	2001		11.2	0.18%	107	0.01%
194	Zimbabwe	1998		12.2	0.20%	217	0.02%
	Total			6197	100%	972933	100%

x million people

x million US\$

Annex E. Non-State Actors that have signed the Deed of Commitment for Adherence to a Total Ban on Anti-personnel Mines and for Cooperation in Mine Action⁶³⁰

AFRICA - Burundi:

1. Conseil National pour la Défense de la Démocratie-Forces pour la Défense de la Démocratie (CNDD-FDD) (Hussein Radjabu), signed 15 December 2003.

AFRICA – Somalia:

2. Banidiri (Chairman Mohamed Osman Maye), signed 11 November 2002.
3. Hiran Patriotic Alliance (HPA)/ Somali Reconciliation and Restoration Council (SRRC) (Chairman Hasan Abdulle Qalad), signed 11 November 2002.
4. Jowhar Administration (Chairman Mohamed Omar Habeb “Dhere”), signed 11 November 2002.
5. Puntland State of Somalia (President Abdullahi Yusuf), signed 11 November 2002.
6. Rahanweyn Resistance Army (RRA)/SRRC (faction of Chairman Col. Hassan Mohamed Nur “Shatigudud”), signed 11 November 2002.
7. Rahanweyn Resistance Army (RRA)/SRRC (faction of Chairman Sheikh Adan Madobe), signed 11 November 2002.
8. Somali African Muki Organisation (SAMO)/SRRC/Nakuru, 11 November 2002.
9. Somali National Front/Somali Reconciliation and Restoration Council (SNF)/SRRC (Chairman Mohamed Sayid Aden), signed 11 November 2002.
10. Somali Patriotic Movement (SPM)/SRRC, signed 11 November 2002.
11. Southern Somali National Movement (SSNM)/BIREM, 11 November 2002.
12. Southern Somali National Movement (SSNM)/SNA/SRRC, 11 November 2002.
13. Transitional National Government (Prime Minister Hassan Abshir and Abdalla Derow Isak, Speaker of the Parliament), 11 November 2002.
14. United Somali Congress (USC)/Somalia Reconciliation and Restoration Council (SRRC), 11 November 2002.
15. Somali National Alliance (SNA)/ Somalia Reconciliation and Restoration Council (SRRC), 11 November 2002.
16. USC/Somali Salvation Army (SSA), 11 November 2002

AFRICA – Sudan:

17. Sudan People’s Liberation Movement and Sudan People’s Liberation Army (SPLM/A) (Nhial Deng Nhial), , signed 4 October 2001.

ASIA - Burma/Myanmar:

18. Arakan Rohingya National Organisation (ARNO) (Nurul Islam, Salim Ullah), signed 2003.
19. National United Party of Arakan (NUPA) (Khing Maung, Khaing Zaw), signed 2003.

ASIA – North East India:

20. National Socialist Council of Nagalim (NSCN) (Thuingaleng Muivah), signed 17 October 2003.

ASIA – Philippines:

21. Moro Islamic Liberation Front (MILF) (Al Haj Murad), signed 7 April 2002.
22. Implementing Guidelines for the MILF pursuant to its Deed of Commitment under Geneva Call.
23. Revolutionary Proletarian Army - Alex Boncayao Brigade (RPA-ABB), signed 10 September 2002.
24. Revolutionary Workers Party of Mindanao (RPM-M) (Harry Tubongbanwa), 11 September 2003.

MIDDLE EAST - Iraqi Kurdistan:

25. Kurdistan Regional Government - Erbil, Democratic Party of Kurdistan, signed 11 August 2002.
26. Kurdistan Regional Government – Sulaimanya, Patriotic Union of Kurdistan (Adnan Mufti), signed 10 August 2002.

⁶³⁰ Deducted from <http://www.genevacall.org/resources/testi-referencematerials/deeds-signatory-groups.htm>

Picture F.1: If all minefields would look like this, the global landmine problem would be nearly eliminated by now.

Picture F.2: During rainy seasons, most vehicles cannot operate in areas with flooding; e.g. Southern Sudan.

Picture F.3: Rough terrain as this makes prodding and mechanical mine clearance nearly impossible; e.g. Afghanistan.

Picture F.4: Landmines in jungle environments and vegetation pose tremendous challenges; e.g. Honduras

Picture F.5: Mine clearance in sandy deserts requires technologies even to consider phenomena such as landmine creep; e.g. Yemen.

Picture F.6: Many African minefields look like this; with elephant grass, excessively high temperatures and other complicating factors; e.g. malaria.

Picture F.7: Dealing with vegetation is a significant mine clearance challenge in most areas.

Picture F.8: The use of machines and mechanical assistance can also be impeded by trees.

Picture F.9: Many challenges in mechanical assistance come from common ditches and culverts.

Picture F.10: The theoretic structure of safe lanes needs often to be adapted to the landscape and terrain.

Picture F.11: The grade and slope are a major concern along mountain top minefields, which can significantly increase the risks for deminers.

Picture F.12: Residential areas can make mine clearance extremely time consuming, especially when the danger is aggravating by booby-traps.

⁶³¹ Picture Courtesy of Roger Hess and Joe Lokey, <http://www.humanitarian-demining.org/demining/threats/minefield.asp>

Annex G. Correlation Poverty-Mine/UXO problems (affected nations highlighted in yellow)

Low-income economies (61)

Afghanistan	Guinea-Bissau	Pakistan
Angola	Haiti	Papua New Guinea
Bangladesh	India	Rwanda
Benin	Kenya	Sao Tome and Principe
Bhutan	Korea, Dem Rep.	Senegal
Burkina Faso	Kyrgyz Republic	Sierra Leone
Burundi	Lao PDR	Solomon Islands
Cambodia	Lesotho	Somalia
Cameroon	Liberia	Sudan
Central African Republic	Madagascar	Tajikistan
Chad	Malawi	Tanzania
Comoros	Mali	Timor-Leste
Congo, Dem. Rep.	Mauritania	Togo
Congo, Rep.	Moldova	Uganda
Cote d'Ivoire	Mongolia	Uzbekistan
Equatorial Guinea	Mozambique	Vietnam
Eritrea	Myanmar	Yemen, Rep.
Ethiopia	Nepal	Zambia
Gambia, The	Nicaragua	Zimbabwe
Ghana	Niger	
Guinea	Nigeria	

Lower-middle-income economies (56)

Albania	Georgia	Philippines
Algeria	Guatemala	Romania
Armenia	Guyana	Russian Federation
Azerbaijan	Honduras	Samoa
Belarus	Indonesia	Serbia and Montenegro
Bolivia	Iran, Islamic Rep.	South Africa
Bosnia and Herzegovina	Iraq	Sri Lanka
Brazil	Jamaica	Suriname
Bulgaria	Jordan	Swaziland
Cape Verde	Kazakhstan	Syrian Arab Republic
China	Kiribati	Thailand
Colombia	Macedonia, FYR	Tonga
Cuba	Maldives	Tunisia
Djibouti	Marshall Islands	Turkey
Dominican Republic	Micronesia, Fed. Sts.	Turkmenistan
Ecuador	Morocco	Ukraine
Egypt, Arab Rep.	Namibia	Vanuatu
El Salvador	Paraguay	West Bank and Gaza
Fiji	Peru	

Upper-middle-income economies (37)

American Samoa	Grenada	Panama
Antigua and Barbuda	Hungary	Poland
Argentina	Latvia	Saudi Arabia
Barbados	Lebanon	Seychelles
Belize	Libya	Slovak Republic
Botswana	Lithuania	St. Kitts and Nevis
Chile	Malaysia	St. Lucia
Costa Rica	Mauritius	St. Vincent and the Grenadines
Croatia	Mayotte	Trinidad and Tobago
Czech Republic	Mexico	Uruguay
Dominica	Northern Mariana Islands	Venezuela, RB
Estonia	Oman	
Gabon	Palau	

High-income economies (54)

Andorra	Germany	Netherlands
Aruba	Greece	Netherlands Antilles
Australia	Greenland	New Caledonia
Austria	Guam	New Zealand
Bahamas, The	Hong Kong, China	Norway
Bahrain	Iceland	Portugal
Belgium	Ireland	Puerto Rico
Bermuda	Isle of Man	Qatar
Brunei	Israel	San Marino
Canada	Italy	Singapore
Cayman Islands	Japan	Slovenia
Channel Islands	Korea, Rep.	Spain
Cyprus	Kuwait	Sweden
Denmark	Liechtenstein	Switzerland
Faeroe Islands	Luxembourg	United Arab Emirates
Finland	Macao, China	United Kingdom
France	Malta	United States
French Polynesia	Monaco	Virgin Islands (U.S.)

Annex H. Kabul data used for statistical analysis; based on the Afghan Landmine Impact Survey

		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	Independent Variable
District	Community	Total years of mine laying	Years since last mine laying	Years since last conflict	Mil Act Quantified	Distance RefPt to MA-edge(meters)	Old Victims Killed/Injured	Affected Population	Mined Areas	Total blockages	Total AP/AT/UXO contamination	Total Recent Victims
1	Community 1	12	9	9	3	300	98	6000	1	1	2	0
	Community 2	4	9	9	3	440	3	1200	1	1	2	2
	Community 3	13	8	8	3	200	16	510	4	2	1	0
	Community 4	4	9	9	3	660	13	8400	1	1	2	2
	Community 5	4	9	9	3	800	10	420	1	1	2	0
	Community 6	1	9	9	3	680	0	120	1	1	2	2
M1		6.33	8.83	8.83	3.00	513.33	23.33	2775.00	1.50	1.17	1.83	1.00
2	Community 7	9	10	8	3	11	0	42	4	4	2	3
	Community 8	11	12	3	3	15	19	900	2	1	1	2
	Community 9	10	12	12	3	390	7	720	2	1	1	2
	Community 10	5	17	8	3	33	5	210	1	2	2	0
	Community 11	11	12	3	3	120	12	180	4	2	1	0
	Community 12	9	13	8	2	112	24	2400	4	3	1	4
	Community 13	11	8	8	2	300	0	150	2	1	1	4
	Community 14	16	8	8	3	60	18	210	1	2	2	0
	Community 15	2	15	12	1	930	22	600	2	2	2	0
	Community 16	2	15	12	2	250	7	240	1	2	1	0
Community 17	12	8	3	3	20	2	18	1	1	1	0	
Community 18	12	10	9	2	225	0	90	1	2	1	2	
M2		9.17	11.67	7.83	2.50	205.50	9.67	480.00	2.08	1.92	1.33	1.42
3	Community 19	20	3	3	3	25	5	900	2	2	1	0
	Community 20	9	9	9	2	297	7	600	4	4	1	1
	Community 21	13	11	11	3	3	12	3120	2	4	1	0
	Community 22	18	3	3	3	195	4	720	4	5	3	8
	Community 23	19	4	3	2	300	30	4800	2	2	2	0
	Community 24	9	3	3	3	130	0	4200	1	1	1	2
	Community 25	7	12	12	2	210	17	1200	2	2	1	0
	Community 26	13	12	12	3	5	4	300	1	4	2	0
	Community 27	21	3	3	3	30	6	210	1	3	1	0
	Community 28	10	11	11	3	30	11	1230	2	2	2	4
	Community 29	10	12	12	3	100	8	720	1	2	1	0
	Community 30	19	3	3	3	60	12	3000	5	3	2	6
	Community 31	11	12	12	1	780	16	4200	1	1	1	0
	Community 32	9	12	12	2	250	24	2700	2	2	2	0
	Community 33	7	14	12	2	250	5	900	3	2	3	0
	Community 34	4	8	8	2	2	3	1320	1	2	1	0
	Community 35	7	12	12	2	100	35	2400	6	2	1	0
	Community 36	13	11	11	3	90	5	420	1	1	2	5
Community 37	9	15	8	3	20	2	720	4	1	1	0	
Community 38	0	15	25	3	30	2	360	4	2	1	0	
M3		11.4	9.25	9.25	2.55	145.35	10.4	1701	2.45	2.35	1.5	1.3
4	Community 39	13	6	3	3	300	10	600	1	1	1	0
	Community 40	16	4	4	2	50	3	480	1	1	1	0
	Community 41	1	5	3	3	170	1	420	1	1	1	1
	Community 42	14	8	3	2	30	12	720	2	1	2	0
	Community 43	13	6	3	3	150	15	1800	1	1	1	0
	Community 44	2	17	3	3	200	10	1800	2	1	1	4
	Community 45	1	5	3	3	200	2	1200	1	1	1	3
Community 46	1	23	3	2	275	9	720	2	1	1	0	
M4		7.63	9.25	3.13	2.63	171.88	7.75	967.50	1.38	1.00	1.13	1.00
5	Community 47	2	2	2	3	20	10	360	1	1	1	0
	Community 48	2	2	2	3	500	5	420	2	1	1	0
	Community 49	2	2	2	3	10	20	6000	1	1	2	0
Community 50	19	19	17	3	1200	15	720	1	1	1	0	
M5		6.25	6.25	5.75	3.00	432.50	12.50	1875.00	1.25	1.00	1.25	0.00
6	Community 51	17	3	3	2	50	1	3000	2	1	1	1
	Community 52	8	3	3	3	370	11	1200	1	2	1	0
	Community 53	9	3	3	3	200	1	2100	1	1	1	0
	Community 54	2	12	3	2	80	7	2100	2	2	1	1
	Community 55	25	3	3	3	20	15	2100	1	1	2	0
	Community 56	3	9	9	3	10	75	1500	1	1	1	0
	Community 57	16	3	3	3	1000	15	2500	1	1	1	0
	Community 58	7	3	10	2	100	30	2760	2	1	1	1
	Community 59	7	3	3	3	50	0	2000	2	4	2	0
	Community 60	7	3	3	3	100	1	2200	1	2	2	0
	Community 61	0	11	3	3	140	8	3180	1	3	1	1
	Community 62	9	3	3	3	700	82	12000	1	1	2	0
	Community 63	13	3	3	3	120	20	3600	1	1	1	0
	Community 64	9	3	3	3	200	0	10800	2	1	2	1
	Community 65	0	11	3	3	140	9	2700	2	3	2	2
	Community 66	5	3	3	3	100	0	1500	1	1	1	0
	Community 67	9	3	3	3	12	60	3600	1	0	1	2
Community 68	2	8	8	3	2	1	1200	1	0	1	0	
Community 69	5	3	3	3	50	0	1500	1	1	2	0	
Community 70	8	3	3	3	1000	0	1800	1	1	1	0	
Community 71	15	3	3	3	500	10	3000	1	1	1	0	
Community 72	4	4	4	2	150	9	1740	1	2	1	0	
Community 73	15	3	3	2	1000	14	300	1	1	1	0	
Community 74	17	3	3	3	20	6	5160	2	2	1	0	
M6		8.83	4.54	3.79	2.71	254.75	15.63	3064.17	1.29	1.42	1.29	0.38
7	Community 75	19	3	3	3	8	1	720	6	1	2	3
	Community 76	21	3	3	3	50	35	1800	5	3	2	5
	Community 77	23	3	3	3	5	2	300	2	1	1	0
	Community 78	12	12	12	3	6	4	318	4	2	2	1
	Community 79	20	3	3	3	0	7	420	2	2	1	0
	Community 80	20	3	3	3	0	13	600	1	2	2	1
	Community 81	15	3	3	3	2	3	600	2	1	1	2
	Community 82	22	3	3	3	2	0	600	1	1	1	0
	Community 83	18	5	3	3	160	3	180	5	4	2	2
	Community 84	18	3	3	3	10	4	1200	2	2	2	0
	Community 85	21	3	3	3	5	6	300	1	1	1	0
M7		20.9	4.4	4.2	3.3	24.8	7.8	703.8	3.1	2	1.7	1.4

		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	Independent Variable
District	Community	Total years of mine laying	Years since last mine laying	Years since last conflict	Mil Act Quantified	Distance RefPt to MA-edge(meters)	Old Victims Killed/Injured	Affected Population	Mined Areas	Total blockages	Total AP/AT/UXO contamination	Total Recent Victims
8	Community 86	2	8	8	3	20	0	180	1	4	1	0
	Community 87	10	8	8	3	30	4	210	3	3	2	4
	Community 88	16	8	8	3	80	2	960	2	2	3	0
	Community 89	14	8	12	3	500	6	120	2	3	2	3
	Community 90	16	8	8	3	300	2	72	1	3	2	0
	Community 91	12	8	8	3	345	17	300	2	2	1	1
	Community 92	2	8	8	3	103	20	220	4	7	2	11
	Community 93	14	8	8	3	10	10	300	2	2	1	0
	Community 94	16	8	8	3	400	2	180	2	1	1	0
	Community 95	16	8	8	3	360	17	1800	1	3	1	7
	Community 96	11	8	8	3	100	25	240	1	3	2	0
	Community 97	12	8	8	3	375	4	48	2	3	1	0
Community 98	12	8	8	3	23	37	420	3	7	2	0	
Community 99	10	8	8	3	69	4	60	3	3	1	0	
Community 100	12	8	8	3	14	42	4800	10	8	2	7	
Community 101	14	8	8	3	600	3	120	1	1	1	0	
Community 102	14	8	8	3	200	6	1800	3	2	1	0	
Community 103	9	8	8	3	120	0	600	3	2	2	3	
Community 104	13	8	8	3	50	2	96	1	2	1	2	
Community 105	10	8	8	3	100	25	120	4	1	1	4	
Community 106	6	12	12	3	60	30	1080	2	4	2	0	
Community 107	11	8	8	3	800	1	3000	1	1	1	0	
Community 108	11	8	8	3	100	0	180	1	6	1	4	
Community 109	10	8	8	3	184	16	240	3	3	1	1	
Community 110	12	8	8	3	440	7	120	3	2	1	0	
Community 111	16	8	8	3	100	4	72	1	4	1	0	
Community 112	10	8	8	3	3	4	78	3	4	2	0	
M8		11.96	8.46	8.62	3.12	211.00	11.23	671.77	2.50	3.31	1.50	1.81
9	Community 113	18	4	3	3	50	3	300	2	3	1	0
	Community 114	21	3	3	3	14	5	480	1	1	2	0
	Community 115	14	3	3	3	5	8	480	4	2	1	0
	Community 116	17	5	3	3	400	22	1620	2	3	2	7
	Community 117	20	3	3	3	10	6	600	4	1	1	0
	Community 118	19	3	3	3	20	2	600	1	1	1	0
	Community 119	20	3	3	3	10	12	600	8	2	1	0
	Community 120	3	3	3	3	20	3	240	1	2	1	0
	Community 121	5	3	3	3	15	0	360	4	3	2	2
	Community 122	19	3	3	3	20	7	300	4	5	2	2
	Community 123	19	3	3	3	10	9	300	4	1	2	0
	Community 124	6	8	3	3	10	8	150	1	1	2	0
Community 125	9	3	3	3	15	20	360	3	2	1	0	
Community 126	19	3	3	3	40	9	900	1	1	1	2	
Community 127	21	3	3	3	10	11	1500	6	2	1	0	
Community 128	19	3	3	3	100	4	900	2	1	1	0	
Community 129	15	3	3	3	10	6	600	2	2	1	0	
Community 130	17	3	3	3	5	5	900	2	2	1	0	
Community 131	15	8	3	3	15	9	420	3	4	3	0	
Community 132	19	3	3	3	25	5	360	3	3	2	2	
Community 133	19	3	3	3	50	42	7800	1	2	1	3	
M9		16.7	3.8	3.15	3.15	42.7	10.2	988.5	2.95	2.2	1.5	0.9
10	Community 134	12	10	9	3	350	8	300	1	2	2	2
	Community 135	6	12	8	3	450	20	1200	1	2	1	2
	Community 136	10	8	8	3	150	5	180	2	3	1	0
	Community 137	8	11	11	3	1600	0	480	1	1	1	0
	Community 138	8	12	12	2	812	7	90	1	2	1	0
	Community 139	11	8	8	3	30	10	120	1	2	2	0
	Community 140	10	8	8	2	493	5	84	2	2	1	0
	Community 141	13	8	8	3	30	6	900	1	1	1	0
	Community 142	8	12	12	3	1204	2	90	1	1	1	1
	Community 143	1	8	8	3	260	0	300	1	2	1	0
	Community 144	10	12	12	3	330	9	300	2	4	1	0
	Community 145	14	3	3	2	740	5	480	1	3	1	0
M10		10.09	10.18	9.73	3.00	586.27	7.00	411.27	1.36	2.27	1.36	0.45
11	Community 146	0	18	12	3	250	9	420	1	4	2	0
	Community 147	18	3	3	3	10	3	72	2	1	2	0
	Community 148	7	17	12	3	50	10	216	1	5	2	0
	Community 149	20	3	3	3	350	110	30000	3	1	1	1
	Community 150	5	11	3	3	110	9	60	2	4	2	0
	Community 151	11	8	8	3	2000	1	120	3	1	1	0
	Community 152	17	3	3	3	20	5	180	2	1	1	0
	Community 153	20	3	3	3	100	8	330	1	1	2	0
	Community 154	13	3	3	3	310	20	270	1	2	2	0
	Community 155	19	3	3	3	100	40	1500	2	1	1	0
	Community 156	6	18	12	3	250	4	960	1	2	2	0
	Community 157	0	3	23	3	50	3	720	2	1	1	0
Community 158	19	3	3	3	200	5	240	3	3	1	1	
Community 159	17	3	3	3	500	12	312	1	1	1	0	
Community 160	7	15	12	3	350	18	1500	2	4	2	3	
Community 161	6	10	3	3	200	21	720	1	4	2	0	
Community 162	19	3	3	3	200	13	720	2	2	1	0	
Community 163	14	8	8	3	10	33	3000	3	2	1	0	
Community 164	17	3	3	3	20	35	2400	4	3	2	0	
Community 165	12	11	3	3	15	12	78	1	2	2	1	
Community 166	18	3	3	3	200	2	180	3	1	1	0	
Community 167	8	12	12	3	50	8	60	4	4	1	0	
Community 168	20	3	3	3	100	9	600	2	1	1	0	
Community 169	17	3	3	3	500	7	72	2	2	1	1	
Community 170	17	3	3	3	100	17	840	2	1	1	1	
Community 171	10	8	6	3	2500	18	54	1	2	2	0	
Community 172	11	12	12	3	200	22	3000	3	3	1	9	
Community 173	18	3	3	3	100	10	720	1	2	1	0	
Community 174	16	3	3	3	100	2	132	2	1	1	0	
Community 175	19	3	3	3	50	39	900	3	2	2	4	
Community 176	18	3	3	3	100	7	180	1	1	2	0	
Community 177	7	15	12	3	220	6	2100	1	1	2	0	
Community 178	18	3	3	3	10	17	900	3	1	3	0	
Community 179	12	8	8	3	380	6	360	1	2	1	2	
Community 180	19	3	3	3	200	30	3600	4	1	1	8	
Community 181	8	11	9	3	200	3	120	1	2	1	0	
Community 182	7	16	12	3	200	20	540	4	8	2	1	
Community 183	6	16	3	3	200	13	12000	2	2	2	5	
Community 184	7	15	3	3	300	9	360	3	2	2	1	
Community 185	0	16	12	3	200	19	540	2	5	2	1	
Community 186	6	16	12	3	250	39	2100	4	4	3	1	
Community 187	4	12	12	3	50	6	360	1	1	2	0	
Community 188	19	3	3	3	50	17	480	4	1	1	0	
Community 189	0	16	3	3	30	1	132	1	1	1	0	
Community 190	16	3	11	3	200	35	3600	2	1	1	4	
Community 191	16	3	3	3	10	3	120	2	3	1	0	
Community 192	9	15	12	3	200	8	360	1	4	2	1	
Community 193	9	9	9	3	300	7	600	1	4	1	12	
Community 194	8	16	3	3	280	26	360	2	1	2	4	
Community 195	17	3	3	3	400	20	300	1	1	1	8	
Community 196	0	16	12	3	200	5	1800	1	5	2	0	
Community 197	4	18	3	3	200	8	210	2	5	3	0	
Community 198	19	3	3	3	100	9	420	3	1	1	0	
Community 199	9	9	9	3	32	11	720	5	3	2	5	
Community 200	17	3	3	3	100	11	72	3	1	2	0	
Community 201	17	3	3	3	50	4	300	1	2	1	0	
Community 202	19	3	3	3	400	22	1680	1	1	1	1	
Community 203	17	3	3	3	2500	5	150	2	1	1	0	
Community 204	19	3	3	3	100	9	180	1	1	1	0	
Community 205	17	3	3	3	500	8	42	1	1	1	0	
M11		12.63	7.90	6.12	3.05	287.41	14.71	1441.73	2.03	2.22	1.56	1.34

		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	Independent Variable
District	Community	Total years of mine laying	Years since last mine laying	Years since last conflict	Mil Act Quantified	Distance RefPt to MA-edge(meters)	Old Victims Killed/Injured	Affected Population	Mined Areas	Total blockages	Total AP/AT/UJO contamination	Total Recent Victims
12	Community 206	15	4	4	3	100	2	900	1	1	1	0
	Community 207	20	3	3	3	10	58	1800	2	2	1	0
	Community 208	19	3	3	3	25	5	240	2	2	1	0
	Community 209	21	3	3	3	12	24	1800	1	1	1	0
	Community 210	16	3	3	3	20	18	480	2	2	1	0
	Community 211	19	3	3	3	8	5	1800	1	0	2	0
	Community 212	17	3	3	3	300	25	1020	1	2	2	9
	Community 213	3	5	4	3	180	34	1800	1	2	2	8
	Community 214	1	3	3	3	6	25	1800	6	1	2	1
	Community 215	21	3	3	3	85	14	60	1	1	1	0
Community 216	2	4	3	3	10	15	240	1	1	1	0	
Community 217	17	3	3	3	465	16	330	2	1	2	2	
Community 218	18	4	3	3	44	16	300	2	6	2	5	
Community 219	3	5	4	3	5	14	300	2	2	1	0	
M12		14.77	3.77	3.46	3.23	97.69	20.85	990.00	1.92	1.85	1.54	1.92
13	Community 220	15	3	3	3	200	15	2400	1	1	1	0
	Community 221	3	4	4	3	100	13	270	1	2	1	3
	Community 222	15	3	3	3	100	3	180	1	1	1	0
	Community 223	15	3	3	3	200	2	180	1	1	1	0
	Community 224	13	5	3	3	150	13	360	2	2	2	0
	Community 225	20	3	3	3	300	11	240	2	4	1	0
	Community 226	16	3	3	3	60	12	180	2	1	1	0
	Community 227	16	3	3	3	10	16	1200	3	3	1	0
	Community 228	0	15	3	3	15	19	102	2	3	2	2
	Community 229	2	5	4	3	100	4	600	2	1	1	0
	Community 230	16	3	3	3	100	9	600	1	1	1	0
	Community 231	0	22	3	3	20	11	90	2	7	3	0
	Community 232	16	4	4	3	8	10	600	4	3	1	33
	Community 233	20	3	3	3	5	16	1800	4	2	1	1
	Community 234	11	7	3	3	255	7	210	1	2	1	3
	Community 235	0	23	3	3	300	11	300	1	6	2	0
	Community 236	17	3	3	3	300	4	1500	2	1	1	0
	Community 237	17	3	3	3	25	63	10800	1	1	1	5
	Community 238	17	4	4	2	50	22	1200	2	1	1	2
	Community 239	0	22	3	3	10	28	3000	4	6	1	0
	Community 240	0	15	3	3	130	18	540	1	2	1	1
	Community 241	14	3	3	3	100	23	150	2	1	1	0
	Community 242	16	3	3	2	150	26	240	1	1	1	0
	Community 243	9	7	3	3	210	10	180	1	2	2	3
	Community 244	0	6	3	3	320	6	90	1	2	1	0
	Community 245	17	3	3	3	100	55	3000	2	1	1	0
	Community 246	16	3	3	3	100	31	270	2	1	1	5
	Community 247	16	3	3	3	100	23	3000	2	2	1	1
	Community 248	0	16	3	3	280	2	600	1	2	1	0
	Community 249	21	3	3	3	100	3	1200	3	1	1	0
	Community 250	19	3	3	3	250	19	1800	1	1	1	0
	Community 251	17	3	3	2	60	8	120	1	1	1	0
	Community 252	0	20	3	3	5	14	4200	2	2	1	0
	Community 253	16	7	3	3	60	18	36	1	3	1	1
	Community 254	17	3	3	3	10	10	360	3	2	1	0
	Community 255	0	17	3	3	150	18	108	1	1	1	3
Community 256	0	18	3	3	200	21	270	1	1	1	0	
Community 257	16	4	4	3	15	3	180	2	2	1	0	
Community 258	15	3	3	3	400	10	900	1	1	1	0	
Community 259	14	4	3	3	200	11	240	3	1	1	0	
Community 260	17	3	3	3	180	5	180	1	1	1	0	
Community 261	16	3	3	3	200	12	480	1	1	1	0	
Community 262	0	16	3	3	190	5	174	1	1	1	0	
Community 263	17	3	3	3	1	27	600	3	5	2	5	
Community 264	19	4	4	3	300	14	360	1	1	1	0	
Community 265	17	3	3	3	15	2	1800	1	1	1	0	
Community 266	15	3	3	3	200	13	3000	1	2	1	1	
Community 267	3	13	3	3	280	13	720	1	2	1	2	
Community 268	0	22	3	3	100	21	60	2	6	1	0	
Community 269	15	7	3	3	140	6	150	2	2	1	0	
Community 270	15	3	3	3	400	5	1680	1	1	1	3	
Community 271	0	18	3	3	100	11	60	1	1	2	0	
Community 272	4	17	3	3	100	14	300	2	5	2	0	
Community 273	21	3	3	3	20	0	900	1	1	1	0	
Community 274	17	3	3	2	20	37	2160	2	4	1	0	
Community 275	16	4	4	2	100	8	360	1	1	1	0	
Community 276	16	3	3	2	200	30	3600	1	2	1	4	
Community 277	0	16	3	2	225	13	360	1	2	2	1	
Community 278	12	6	3	3	200	7	150	1	3	2	2	
Community 279	15	3	3	1	60	15	240	1	1	1	0	
Community 280	17	3	3	2	15	14	1200	1	1	1	0	
Community 281	0	17	3	3	5	10	210	2	1	2	0	
Community 282	2	5	3	3	10	45	1500	3	2	1	13	
Community 283	17	3	3	3	30	20	540	2	1	2	0	
Community 284	21	3	3	3	50	22	1800	3	2	1	1	
Community 285	5	3	3	3	20	5	1200	1	1	1	0	
M13		11.52	7.26	3.15	2.89	129.37	15.26	1032.00	1.68	2.00	1.22	1.46
14	Community 286	16	8	6	3	80	12	420	2	2	2	0
	Community 287	2	17	7	2	200	14	24	1	1	1	0
	Community 288	2	22	7	3	20	30	1620	5	1	1	9
	Community 289	1	23	10	3	40	44	336	6	2	1	4
	Community 290	2	17	7	3	150	9	72	2	1	1	0
	Community 291	2	22	7	3	20	47	660	2	1	1	0
	Community 292	18	6	6	3	25	5	138	2	2	1	0
	Community 293	8	16	3	3	40	7	60	4	1	1	2
	Community 294	19	5	3	3	100	4	48	3	1	2	0
	Community 295	1	23	7	2	270	24	558	2	1	1	4
	Community 296	3	17	7	3	130	7	60	4	1	1	0
	Community 297	10	14	9	2	60	5	60	4	4	1	0
	Community 298	3	17	7	3	150	86	180	1	1	1	4
	Community 299	17	7	7	3	60	1	120	3	1	1	0
	Community 300	18	6	6	3	60	4	600	2	3	1	0
	Community 301	1	11	7	2	200	4	90	1	2	1	0
	Community 302	18	4	3	3	10	5	72	1	1	1	0
	Community 303	4	16	7	3	100	261	7200	5	3	2	22
	Community 304	4	17	7	3	100	5	240	2	1	1	0
	Community 305	3	17	7	3	100	5	120	5	1	1	0
Community 306	3	17	8	3	150	11	90	1	1	1	0	
Community 307	1	23	7	2	30	14	180	2	1	1	0	
Community 308	2	22	7	3	10	17	180	8	1	1	8	
Community 309	11	8	7	3	50	15	36	5	2	1	1	
Community 310	2	22	7	3	360	51	120	1	1	1	7	
Community 311	1	23	7	3	50	27	420	6	1	1	6	
Community 312	17	3	7	3	0	0	200	1	0	1	0	
Community 313	2	22	12	3	150	11	240	2	1	1	3	
M14		7.07	15.74	7.11	2.93	100.56	26.85	523.85	3.07	1.44	1.15	2.59

Annex I. Simple Linear Regression analysis of the recency factor in Kabul

1. Simple Regression - SEM1 vs. SEM3

Dependent variable: SEM1

Independent variable: SEM3

Coefficients

	Least Squares	Standard	T	
Parameter	Estimate	Error	Statistic	P-Value
Intercept	0.382909	1.8279	0.20948	0.8383
Slope	0.679129	0.19807	3.42873	0.0065

Analysis of Variance

Source	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F-Ratio	P-Value
Model	187.1	1	187.1	11.76	0.0065
Residual	159.15	10	15.915		
Total	346.25	11			

Correlation Coefficient = 0.735093

R-squared = 54.0361 percent

Standard Error of Est. = 3.98936

Mean absolute error = 2.70063

$$SEM1 = 0.382909 + 0.679129 * SEM3$$

Since the P-value in the ANOVA table is less than 0.05, there is a statistically significant relationship between SEM1 and SEM3 at the 95.0% confidence level.

The R-Squared statistic indicates that the model as fitted explains 54.0361% of the variability in SEM1. The correlation coefficient equals 0.735093, indicating a moderately strong relationship between the variables. The standard error of the estimate shows the standard deviation of the residuals to be 3.98936.

2. Simple Regression - SEM1 vs. SEM4

Dependent variable: SEM1

Independent variable: SEM4

Coefficients

	Least Squares	Standard	T	
Parameter	Estimate	Error	Statistic	P-Value
Intercept	2.0231	1.50717	1.34232	0.2092
Slope	0.387228	0.115032	3.36627	0.0072

Analysis of Variance

Source	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F-Ratio	P-Value
Model	183.933	1	183.933	11.33	0.0072
Residual	162.317	10	16.2317		
Total (Corr.)	346.25	11			

Correlation Coefficient = 0.728845

R-squared = 53.1216 percent

Standard Error of Est. = 4.02885

Mean absolute error = 2.7577

$$SEM1 = 2.0231 + 0.387228 * SEM4$$

Since the P-value in the ANOVA table is less than 0.05, there is a statistically significant relationship between SEM1 and SEM4 at the 95.0% confidence level.

The R-Squared statistic indicates that the model as fitted explains 53.1216% of the variability in SEM1. The correlation coefficient equals 0.728845, indicating a moderately strong relationship between the variables. The standard error of the estimate shows the standard deviation of the residuals to be 4.02885.

3. Simple Regression - Kabul SEM2 vs. Kabul SEM3

Dependent variable: Kabul SEM2 (SEM2)

Independent variable: Kabul SEM3 (SEM3)

Coefficients

	<i>Least Squares</i>	<i>Standard</i>	<i>T</i>	
<i>Parameter</i>	<i>Estimate</i>	<i>Error</i>	<i>Statistic</i>	<i>P-Value</i>
Intercept	2.87716	2.97172	0.968181	0.3558
Slope	1.41249	0.322012	4.38645	0.0014

Analysis of Variance

<i>Source</i>	<i>Sum of Squares</i>	<i>Df</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>F-Ratio</i>	<i>P-Value</i>
Model	809.357	1	809.357	19.24	0.0014
Residual	420.643	10	42.0643		
Total (Corr.)	1230.0	11			

Correlation Coefficient = 0.81118

R-squared = 65.8014 percent

Standard Error of Est. = 6.4857

Mean absolute error = 3.73405

$$\text{Kabul SEM2} = 2.87716 + 1.41249 * \text{Kabul SEM3}$$

Since the P-value in the ANOVA table is less than 0.05, there is a statistically significant relationship between Kabul SEM2 and Kabul SEM3 at the 95.0% confidence level.

The R-Squared statistic indicates that the model as fitted explains 65.8014% of the variability in Kabul SEM2. The correlation coefficient equals 0.81118, indicating a moderately strong relationship between the variables. The standard error of the estimate shows the standard deviation of the residuals to be 6.4857.

4. Simple Regression - Kabul SEM2 vs. Kabul SEM4

Dependent variable: Kabul SEM2 (SEM2)

Independent variable: Kabul SEM4 (SEM4)

Coefficients

	<i>Least Squares</i>	<i>Standard</i>	<i>T</i>	
<i>Parameter</i>	<i>Estimate</i>	<i>Error</i>	<i>Statistic</i>	<i>P-Value</i>
Intercept	7.49049	3.11603	2.40386	0.0371
Slope	0.661141	0.237825	2.77994	0.0195

Analysis of Variance

<i>Source</i>	<i>Sum of Squares</i>	<i>Df</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>F-Ratio</i>	<i>P-Value</i>
Model	536.186	1	536.186	7.73	0.0195
Residual	693.814	10	69.3814		
Total (Corr.)	1230.0	11			

Correlation Coefficient = 0.660245

R-squared = 43.5923 percent

Standard Error of Est. = 8.32955

Mean absolute error = 5.29384

$$\text{Kabul SEM2} = 7.49049 + 0.661141 * \text{Kabul SEM4}$$

Since the P-value in the ANOVA table is less than 0.05, there is a statistically significant relationship between Kabul SEM2 and Kabul SEM4 at the 95.0% confidence level.

The R-Squared statistic indicates that the model as fitted explains 43.5923% of the variability in Kabul SEM2. The correlation coefficient equals 0.660245, indicating a moderately strong relationship between the variables. The standard error of the estimate shows the standard deviation of the residuals to be 8.32955.

5. Simple Regression - Kabul SEM3 vs. Kabul SEM4

Dependent variable: Kabul SEM3 (SEM3)
 Independent variable: Kabul SEM4 (SEM4)
 Linear model: $Y = a + b \cdot X$

Coefficients

	<i>Least Squares</i>	<i>Standard</i>	<i>T</i>	
<i>Parameter</i>	<i>Estimate</i>	<i>Error</i>	<i>Statistic</i>	<i>P-Value</i>
Intercept	3.12908	1.28345	2.43802	0.0350
Slope	0.484511	0.097957	4.94616	0.0006

Analysis of Variance

<i>Source</i>	<i>Sum of Squares</i>	<i>Df</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>F-Ratio</i>	<i>P-Value</i>
Model	287.961	1	287.961	24.46	0.0006
Residual	117.706	10	11.7706		
Total (Corr.)	405.667	11			

P-Value = 0.0006
 Correlation Coefficient = 0.842524
 R-squared = 70.9846 percent
 Standard Error of Est. = 3.43083
 Mean absolute error = 1.96042

$Kabul\ SEM3 = 3.12908 + 0.484511 \cdot Kabul\ SEM4$

Since the P-value in the ANOVA table is less than 0.05, there is a statistically significant relationship between Kabul SEM3 and Kabul SEM4 at the 95.0% confidence level.

The R-Squared statistic indicates that the model as fitted explains 70.9846% of the variability in Kabul SEM3. The correlation coefficient equals 0.842524, indicating a moderately strong relationship between the variables. The standard error of the estimate shows the standard deviation of the residuals to be 3.43083.

Annex J. Simple Linear Regression analysis of the recency factor in the Northern Cluster

1.Simple Regression - SEM1 vs. SEM2

Dependent variable: SEM1
Independent variable: SEM2

Coefficients

	<i>Least Squares</i>	<i>Standard</i>	<i>T</i>	
<i>Parameter</i>	<i>Estimate</i>	<i>Error</i>	<i>Statistic</i>	<i>P-Value</i>
Intercept	-0.0844758	0.4442	-0.190175	0.8502
Slope	0.609096	0.0433985	14.035	0.0000

Analysis of Variance

<i>Source</i>	<i>Sum of Squares</i>	<i>Df</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>F-Ratio</i>	<i>P-Value</i>
Model	1090.31	1	1090.31	196.98	0.0000
Residual	199.265	36	5.53515		
Total	1289.58	37			

P-Value = 0.0000
Correlation Coefficient = 0.9195
R-squared = 84.548 percent
Standard Error of Est. = 2.35269
SEM1 = -0.0844758 + 0.609096*SEM2

2. Simple Regression - SEM1 vs. SEM3

Dependent variable: SEM1
Independent variable: SEM3

Coefficients

	<i>Least Squares</i>	<i>Standard</i>	<i>T</i>	
<i>Parameter</i>	<i>Estimate</i>	<i>Error</i>	<i>Statistic</i>	<i>P-Value</i>
Intercept	0.153353	0.794142	0.193105	0.8480
Slope	0.606338	0.0923007	6.56916	0.0000

Analysis of Variance

<i>Source</i>	<i>Sum of Squares</i>	<i>Df</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>F-Ratio</i>	<i>P-Value</i>
Model	703.065	1	703.065	43.15	0.0000
Residual	586.514	36	16.292		
Total (Corr.)	1289.58	37			

P-Value = 0.0000
Correlation Coefficient = 0.73837
R-squared = 54.519 percent
Standard Error of Est. = 4.03634
Mean absolute error = 2.25877
SEM1 = 0.153353 + 0.606338*SEM3

3. Simple Regression - SEM1 vs. SEM4

Dependent variable: SEM1
Independent variable: SEM4

Coefficients

	Least Squares	Standard	T	
Parameter	Estimate	Error	Statistic	P-Value
Intercept	1.76403	1.10337	1.59877	0.1186
Slope	0.191605	0.0884594	2.16602	0.0370

Analysis of Variance

Source	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F-Ratio	P-Value
Model	148.685	1	148.685	4.69	0.0370
Residual	1140.89	36	31.6915		
Total (Corr.)	1289.58	37			

Correlation Coefficient = 0.339555
R-squared = 11.5298 percent
Standard Error of Est. = 5.62952
Mean absolute error = 3.451

$$SEM1 = 1.76403 + 0.191605 * SEM4$$

4. Simple Regression - SEM2 vs. SEM3

Dependent variable: SEM2
Independent variable: SEM3

Coefficients

	Least Squares	Standard	T	
Parameter	Estimate	Error	Statistic	P-Value
Intercept	0.722688	1.1799	0.612498	0.5441
Slope	0.927232	0.137137	6.76138	0.0000

Analysis of Variance

Source	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F-Ratio	P-Value
Model	1644.15	1	1644.15	45.72	0.0000
Residual	1294.72	36	35.9643		
Total (Corr.)	2938.87	37			

Correlation Coefficient = 0.747965
R-squared = 55.9451 percent
Standard Error of Est. = 5.99703
Mean absolute error = 3.291

$$SEM2 = 0.722688 + 0.927232 * SEM3$$

5. Simple Regression - SEM2 vs. SEM4

Dependent variable: SEM2
Independent variable: SEM4

Coefficients

	Least Squares	Standard	T	
Parameter	Estimate	Error	Statistic	P-Value
Intercept	2.57511	1.58465	1.62503	0.1129
Slope	0.380247	0.127045	2.993	0.0050

Analysis of Variance

Source	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F-Ratio	P-Value
Model	585.58	1	585.58	8.96	0.0050
Residual	2353.29	36	65.3691		
Total (Corr.)	2938.87	37			

Correlation Coefficient = 0.446378

R-squared = 19.9254 percent

Standard Error of Est. = 8.08512

Mean absolute error = 5.3345

$$\text{SEM2} = 2.57511 + 0.380247 * \text{SEM4}$$

6. Simple Regression - SEM3 vs. SEM4

Dependent variable: SEM3

Independent variable: SEM4

Coefficients

	Least Squares	Standard	T	
Parameter	Estimate	Error	Statistic	P-Value
Intercept	1.60521	1.04949	1.52951	0.1349
Slope	0.466173	0.0841404	5.54041	0.0000

Analysis of Variance

Source	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F-Ratio	P-Value
Model	880.134	1	880.134	30.70	0.0000
Residual	1032.21	36	28.6724		
Total (Corr.)	1912.34	37			

Correlation Coefficient = 0.678409

R-squared = 46.0239 percent

Standard Error of Est. = 5.35467

Mean absolute error = 3.73287

$$\text{SEM3} = 1.60521 + 0.466173 * \text{SEM4}$$

Annex K. Calculation and averaging of mine action clearance rates for strategic planning

1. Demining Agency For Afghanistan (DAFA)

DAFA conducts mine clearance mainly in the southern and western regions of the country, with its head office located in Kandahar. It employs about 658 people with a 2001 budget of \$3.9 million. In 2001, DAFA operated with 11 manual clearance teams, four battle area clearance teams, and three mechanical mine clearance teams, clearing about 1.148 million square meters of mine-contaminated area and 3.3 million square meters of former battlefield area. During these clearance operations, 267 antipersonnel mines, 94 anti-vehicle mines, and 11,069 UXO were destroyed. DAFA States that it suffered damage/loss of equipment worth \$5-6 million dollars during the recent military operations in Afghanistan.

With 11 manual clearance teams and 3 mechanical mine clearance teams, the landmine monitor States that DAFA cleared 1,15 million square meters in 2001. The MAPA monthly progress reports mentions a slightly higher number of square meters for 2001: 1,35 million. For 2000, it has been equally reported that DAFA cleared 2,88 million square meters, for 1999, a total of 2,95 million square meters, for 1998 a total of 2,4 million Square meters.⁶³²

The lower annual output in 2001 compared to the previous two years can be partly subscribed to the disruption of the programme as from October 2001 on, due to the successive military interventions by the coalition forces together with the reported significant destruction of DAFA de-mining equipment. Assuming that the period 1998 – 2001 is more representative, one can assume that an average output over this period for the 11 DAFA teams is approximately 2,395 million square meters.

The mentioned mechanical clearance teams are considered able to perform only mechanical ground preparation, in other words not directly contributing to the cleared land output. Consequently the annual output per manual DAFA team per year is $2,395/11 = 218000 \text{ m}^2/\text{team}$; average output per day (216 working days/year): $1008 \text{ m}^2/\text{day}/\text{team}$.

Due to insufficient post clearance data, further disaggregated data regarding which type of land has been cleared by DAFA is not available. Still being significantly higher than the ATC and HALO manual clearance rates, one can assume that faster clearance in certain southern areas of Afghanistan is aided by less contaminated ground, proportionally less high priority residential area clearance (= very complex and slow) and possible proportionally more area reduction of the area to be cleared of mines, leading in this case to a mixture of mine clearance rates with area reduction rates.

Important to mention is the fact that HALO teams have 22 de-miners/team (only one de-miner/lane), whilst others (except AREA) have 24 de-miners/team (two de-miners/lane), which logically should be proportionally accountable for 10% less clearance output/team of HALO. In a similar way, a mathematical analysis of the data available for OMAR can provide more realistic data regarding their clearance output.

2. Organization for Mine Clearance and Afghan Rehabilitation (OMAR)

OMAR conducts mine and UXO clearance and mine awareness in various parts of the country, with its head office recently relocated from Peshawar to Kabul and offices in Jalalabad, Kandahar, and Herat. OMAR has 645 employees, with 550 involved in mine clearance and 95 in mine awareness education. It also runs primary education, health care, and rehabilitation projects with a separate staff and budget. In 2001, OMAR operated with ten manual clearance teams, four battle area clearance teams, and three mechanical mine clearance teams, clearing more than 1.9 million square meters of mine contaminated area. During these clearance operations, 1,526 antipersonnel mines, one anti-vehicle mine, and 1,727 UXO were destroyed.⁶³³

With ten manual clearance teams, the OMAR annual output over the years 1998, '99, '00 and '01 was respectively 2,75 - 3,5 - 1,87 - 1,9 → leading to an average of $2,5 \text{ km}^2/10 = 250500 \text{ m}^2/\text{team}$; average output

⁶³² Internet. Available at <http://www.afghan-network.net/Landmines/fn4269>

⁶³³ Internet. Available at <http://www.afghan-network.net/Landmines/fn4269> - MAPA progress report, December 2001.

per day (260 working days/year): 963 m²/day/team, being very close to the DAFA daily output per team and probably for similar reasons higher than the output of ATC and HALO Trust.

The information of the landmine monitor reports in combination with the MCPA monthly progress reports gives another output: with two manual teams (at the end of 2001 three manual teams), 136294 m² was cleared. This allows for following calculation: $136294/2/220 = 310 \text{ m}^2/\text{team}/\text{day}$.

In order to facilitate the usage of the Cranfield support software, HIGHWAY®, it is preferable to have one acceptable and defensible average clearance rate in order to allow for a transparent methodology regarding the key parameter for long-term strategic planning. Since above calculations already provide one average clearance rate for DAFA and OMAR, it requires additional calculations for the other de-mining organizations. In this regard, these disaggregated clearance rates should be weighed with the currently ranked high priority area to be cleared (189 km² agricultural, 20 km² residential, 5 km² irrigation channels, 39 km² roads and 163 km² grazing land):

- ATC this average output/team/day:
 $[(500*189) + (250*5) + (750*163) + (200*20) + (N/A*39)] / (410 - 39) = 598 \text{ m}^2/\text{team}/\text{day}$
- HALO Trust average output/team/day:
 $[(330*189) + (220*5) + (440*163) + (154*20) + (110*39)] / 410 = 348 \text{ m}^2/\text{team}/\text{day}$

Cross-checking this with their performance of 2001 => 2 503 422 m² with 31 teams⁶³⁴:
 $2\,503\,422 / 31 / 232 \text{ working days}$, gives equally 348 m²/team/day

- AREA average output/team/day:
 $[(900*189) + (N/A*5) + (600*163) + (N/A*20) + (N/A*39)] / (410-5-20-39) = 774 \text{ m}^2/\text{team}/\text{day}$

For an over-arching MAPA clearance rate, further weighing - in respect with the number of manual teams of each de-mining organization - can be applied as follows:

- HALO Trust: 35 % of MAPA manual de-mining human resources/employees
- ATC: 25 %
- DAFA: 16 %
- OMAR: 14 %
- DDG: 5 %
- AREA: 5%

Average MAPA manual team clearance rate:

$$(35\% * 348) + (25\% * 598) + (16\% * 1008) + (14\% * 963) + (5\% * 310) + (5\% * 774) = \mathbf{621 \text{ m}^2/\text{team}/\text{day}}$$

FIELD VISITS AND RESEARCH

I. Visits of Mine Action Programmes or related Mine Action activities:

1. **ERITREA** (2002): In the capacity of Secretary of the Mine Action Support Group
2. **ETHIOPIA** (2002): In the capacity of Secretary of the Mine Action Support Group
3. **BELGIUM** (2002): In the capacity of Secretary of the Mine Action Support Group to the Belgian DOVO/SEDEE (Dienst voor Opruiming en Vernietiging van Ontploffingstuigen / Service d'Enlèvement et de Destruction d'Engins Explosifs), the bomb disposal unit of the Belgian army.
4. **SOUTH AFRICA** (2002): In the capacity of Military Adviser to the Belgian Ministry of Foreign Affairs
5. **DEMOCRATIC REPUBLIC OF CONGO** (2002): In the capacity of Military Adviser to the Belgian Ministry of Foreign Affairs
6. **ANGOLA** (2002): In the capacity of Military Adviser to the Belgian Ministry of Foreign Affairs
7. **AFGHANISTAN** (2002, 2003 and 2004): First in the capacity of Secretary of the Mine Action Support Group, afterwards as UN Consultant for strategic mine action planning in Afghanistan
8. **WESTERN SAHARA** (2005): In the capacity of UN Planning Officer for the Department of Peacekeeping Operations, United Nations Headquarters, New York
9. **BURUNDI** (2005): In the capacity of UN Planning Officer for the Department of Peacekeeping Operations, United Nations Headquarters, New York
10. **SUDAN** (2006): In the capacity of UN Planning Officer for the Department of Peacekeeping Operations, United Nations Headquarters, New York

II. Related Missions abroad:

1. **UNITED KINGDOM** (Sep 2002): In the capacity of UN Consultant for the United Nations Mine Action Service, United Nations Headquarters, New York
2. **FLORIDA – TAMPA** (Apr-Sep 2004): In the capacity of Senior National Representative for Belgium to the United States Central Command
3. **KINGSTON – CANADA** (Nov 2005): In the capacity of UN Planning Officer for the Department of Peacekeeping Operations, United Nations Headquarters, New York

CONFERENCES / INTERNATIONAL MEETINGS

I. NEW YORK:

1. 2000: Monthly and Reinforced Mine Action Support Group Meetings; in the capacity of Military Adviser to the Belgian Ministry of Foreign Affairs
2. 2001: Monthly and Reinforced Mine Action Support Group Meetings; in the capacity of Military Adviser to the Belgian Ministry of Foreign Affairs
3. 2002: Monthly and Reinforced Mine Action Support Group Meetings; in the capacity of Secretary of the Mine Action Support Group
4. 2003: Monthly and Reinforced Mine Action Support Group Meetings; in the capacity of Military Adviser to the Belgian Ministry of Foreign Affairs

II. GENEVA:

1. Intersessional Programme to the Mine Ban Treaty (January 2002); in the capacity of Secretary of the Mine Action Support Group
2. 5th Meeting of UN Mine Action Programme Directors (February 2002); in the capacity of Secretary of the Mine Action Support Group
3. 4th Meeting of States Parties to the Mine Ban Treaty (September 2002); in the capacity of Secretary of the Mine Action Support Group
4. Intersessional Programme to the Mine Ban Treaty (May 2003); in the capacity of Military Adviser to the Belgian Ministry of Foreign Affairs and Defence

III. VIENNA:

Feb 2004: Conference at the Organization for Security and Cooperation in Europe; in the capacity of Military Staff Officer of the Belgian Ministry of Defence

IV. AFGHANISTAN:

Anti-Personnel Mine Ban Conference: Building a Peaceful Future for Afghanistan (July 2002); in the capacity of Secretary of the Mine Action Support Group

V. FLORIDA:

July 2004: Coalition Humanitarian Working Group; in the capacity of Senior National Representative for Belgium to the United States Central Command

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